

**Integrated Natural Resources
Management Plan**
for
**Naval Base Ventura County
Port Hueneme
Port Hueneme, California**

March 2012

**INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN**

**NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY
PORT HUENEME
PORT HUENEME, CALIFORNIA**

March 2012

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Prepared for:

Navy Region Southwest
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*INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PLAN
NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY
PORT HUENEME, CALIFORNIA*

APPROVAL

This document fulfills the requirements for the Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP) in accordance with the Sikes Act (16 USC 670a et seq.) as amended and U.S. Department of Defense Instruction (DoDINST) 4715.03 and Naval Operations Instruction (OPNAVINST) 5090.1C.

For Plan Period: 2011 – 2030

Approving Official—Commanding Officer, U.S. Navy, Naval Base Ventura County

Lawrence Vasquez
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Port Hueneme, California

Date

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For Plan Period: 2011 – 2030

Concurring Agency—U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

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For Plan Period: 2011 – 2030

Concurring Agency—U.S. National Marine Fisheries Service

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Date

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PORT HUENEME, CALIFORNIA*

APPROVAL

Through a Tripartite Agreement (herein referred to as a Memorandum of Understanding [MOU]) signed January 2006, the Department of Defense (DoD), U.S. Department of Interior (USDOI), USFWS, and CDFG, have a statutory obligation to coordinate preparing, reviewing and implementing INRMPs. The California Department of Fish and Game, as the designated state wildlife agency has participated in the review of this Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP), in accordance with the Sikes Act (16 USC 670a et seq.) as amended and DoDINST 4715.03 and OPNAVINST 5090.1C.

For Plan Period: 2011 – 2030

Concurring Agency—California Department of Fish and Game

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) is to provide Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC) Port Hueneme a framework and criteria for the sustainable management of natural resources that integrates with and supports the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) mission. The Sikes Act Improvement Act (SAIA) of 1997 required the DoD to prepare and implement an INRMP for each installation that contains significant natural resources. A successfully implemented INRMP will: (1) ensure the sustainability of all ecosystems in the installation, and (2) ensure no net loss of the capability of installation lands to support the DoD mission. This INRMP will be used to manage DoD terrestrial and aquatic natural resources at NBVC Port Hueneme. This document is the first formal revision of the original 1999 Integrated Resource Management Plan (IRMP).

To fulfill the requirements of the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) of 1969 (42 United States Code 4321 et seq.), and in accordance with Chief of Naval Operation (CNO) guidance (DoD 2010), an Environmental Assessment has been prepared to analyze potential effects of implementing this INRMP, ([Appendix B](#)).

NBVC Port Hueneme encompasses 1,650 acres of mostly developed coastal land, in Ventura County, California, approximately 60 miles northwest of Los Angeles. Approximately 199 acres are managed under the NBVC natural resources program. NBVC Port Hueneme is bordered by the City of Port Hueneme to the north and west, the City of Oxnard to the east, and Channel Islands Harbor to the west. Silver Strand Beach borders the southwest, and Port Hueneme Beach is southeast of the Port Hueneme Harbor entrance channel. NBVC Port Hueneme owns and operates a major portion of Hueneme Harbor that provides maritime support for the Navy.

The primary mission of NBVC Port Hueneme is to provide a home port and to furnish training, administrative, and logistical support for the Naval Construction Battalions (or Seabees) serving in many parts of the world (U.S. Department of the Navy [[Navy](#)] 1998). As part of the Navy's streamlined shore structure management under the direction of Commander Navy Installation Command, NBVC Port Hueneme, and Commander Navy Region Southwest in San Diego, provide site operation support services to the military defense complex in Ventura County that encompasses all military activities at NBVC Port Hueneme, NBVC Point Mugu, and NBVC San Nicolas Island.

The goals of this INRMP are to:

- Achieve sustainable military readiness while maintaining ecosystem resilience to mission impacts.
- Maintain and enhance, through adaptive management principles, functioning ecological communities and sensitive species recovery.

- Achieve collaborative internal and external partnerships to maximize mutual benefits, such as identifying additional funding sources, improving cost-effectiveness, and sharing compatible data.
- Improve DoD personnel, contractor, and public awareness of the natural resources and how impacts to these resources can affect the military mission.

Key issues or concerns identified in this INRMP are:

- The harbor and port are mission critical resources used by fish and wildlife protected under federal regulations.
- Many of the habitat types on base have been greatly reduced on a regional scale and are sensitive to human impacts. On the base, these natural areas are fragmented, lack buffers, and are sensitive to impacts such as soil erosion, pollution, changes in hydrology, invasive species, and human disturbances.

This INRMP is structured to meet these goals and objectives. For each INRMP topic, key issues and concerns are identified, current management is described and its effectiveness assessed. Out of the identified concerns and management assessment, objectives and specific management strategies are presented. From the management strategies, natural resource management projects are identified, and appended to this document as a list of projects ([Appendix E](#)). Strategies are presented as a framework, and not to the level of detail of a work plan or proposal.

The outline of this INRMP is:

[Section 1.0](#), Introduction—discusses the purpose, scope and authority of this INRMP, the installation location, military mission, military land use, and INRMP stakeholders and ecosystem approach;

[Section 2.0](#), Military Use and Natural Resource Management—describes installation activities, operations and planning;

[Section 3.0](#), Current Condition and Management of Natural Resources—identifies the current condition of natural resources, and key issues or concerns for each topic;

[Section 4.0](#), Sustainability of the Military Mission and Compatible Use—presents sustainable land use decision making processes, regulatory compliance, and environmental awareness;

[Section 5.0](#), Implementation Strategy—presents staffing, funding, budget considerations, and adaptive management.

Appendices to this document are:

[Appendix A](#)—List of Acronyms and Abbreviations,

[Appendix B](#)—Environmental Assessment,

[Appendix C](#)—List of Natural Resources Management Drivers and Integrating Other Plans,

[Appendix D](#)—Land Use and Cover Types and Acreages,

[Appendix E](#)—NBVC Port Hueneme INRMP Project List,

[Appendix F](#)—Memorandum of Understanding,

[Appendix G](#)—Biological Surveys,

[Appendix H](#)—Species Lists,

[Appendix I](#)—Migratory Bird Management,

[Appendix J](#)—Benefits for Threatened and Endangered Species,

[Appendix K](#)— NBVC Approved Landscaping Plant List,

[Appendix L](#)—NBVC Bard Estate Plant List,

[Appendix M](#)—Annual Metrics Reports, and

[Appendix N](#)—Natural Resources Manager Appointment Letter.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	ES-1
1.0 INTRODUCTION	1-1
1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE	1-1
1.2 AUTHORITY	1-3
1.3 LOCATION AND PLANNING FOOTPRINT	1-3
1.4 REAL ESTATE SUMMARY	1-5
1.5 MILITARY MISSION	1-5
1.6 MILITARY LAND USE AND CATEGORIES OF OPERATIONS	1-6
1.6.1 Regional U.S. Navy Military Land Use	1-7
1.7 ACHIEVING SUCCESS AND NO NET LOSS TO THE MILITARY MISSION	1-10
1.7.1 Mission Sustainability and the INRMP “No Net Loss” Requirement ...	1-10
1.8 INRMP VISION, GOALS AND OBJECTIVES	1-11
1.9 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES FOR THE INRMP	1-14
1.9.1 INRMP Working Group	1-14
1.9.2 Installation Stakeholders	1-15
1.9.3 External Stakeholders	1-17
1.10 ECOSYSTEM APPROACH	1-17
1.11 REVISION AND ANNUAL REVIEW	1-19
1.12 COMPLIANCE AND STEWARDSHIP CRITERIA FOR IMPLEMENTING PROJECTS	1-21
1.13 INTEGRATING OTHER PLANS	1-21
2.0 MILITARY USE AND NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT	2-1
2.1 HISTORICAL OVERVIEW OF NATURAL RESOURCE USE	2-1
2.1.1 Pre-Navy Land Use	2-1
2.1.2 Historical Navy Land Use	2-1
2.2 OPERATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE	2-2
2.2.1 Mission Critical	2-2
2.2.2 Mission Support	2-7
2.2.3 Quality of Life	2-11
2.3 LEASES AND REAL ESTATE OUTGRANTS	2-11
2.4 FUTURE USE PATTERNS AND PLANS: THE NBVC PORT HUENEME ACTIVITY OVERVIEW PLAN AND SUSTAINABLE PLANNING AND DESIGN	2-12
2.5 OVERVIEW OF GOVERNMENT REGULATORY CONTEXT OF NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT	2-13
2.6 OPPORTUNITIES	2-14
2.6.1 Internal Opportunities	2-14

- 2.6.2 External Opportunities 2-14
- 2.7 CONSTRAINTS 2-16
 - 2.7.1 Internal Encroachment 2-16
 - 2.7.2 External Encroachment 2-17
- 3.0 CURRENT CONDITION AND MANAGEMENT OF NATURAL RESOURCES 3-1
- 3.1 ECOREGIONAL SETTING 3-1
 - 3.1.1 Topography 3-1
 - 3.1.2 Geology 3-2
 - 3.1.3 Climate and Climate Change 3-3
- 3.2 PHYSICAL CONDITIONS AND MANAGING THE PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL ENVIRONMENT 3-8
 - 3.2.1 Air Quality 3-8
 - 3.2.2 Soils and Soil Conservation 3-9
 - 3.2.2.1 Shoreline Sediment 3-12
 - 3.2.3 Water Resources and Water Management 3-15
 - 3.2.3.1 Groundwater 3-15
 - 3.2.3.2 Surface and Stormwater Management 3-17
 - 3.2.3.3 Jurisdictional Waters-Wetlands Management 3-19
- 3.3 ECOSYSTEMS 3-22
 - 3.3.1 Coastal and Marine Communities 3-23
 - 3.3.1.1 Marine Subtidal 3-23
 - 3.3.1.2 Sandy Beach 3-26
 - 3.3.2 Terrestrial Communities 3-28
 - 3.3.2.1 Dune Mat 3-28
 - 3.3.2.2 Coyote Brush Scrub 3-30
 - 3.3.2.3 Non-Native Annual Grassland 3-32
 - 3.3.2.4 Arroyo Willow Thickets and Drainage Channels 3-34
- 3.4 FISH AND WILDLIFE MANAGEMENT 3-38
 - 3.4.1 Terrestrial Invertebrates 3-38
 - 3.4.2 Pollinators 3-40
 - 3.4.3 Reptiles and Amphibians 3-41
 - 3.4.4 Birds 3-42
 - 3.4.5 Mammals 3-49
 - 3.4.6 Aquatic Invertebrates 3-50
 - 3.4.7 Fish 3-52
 - 3.4.8 Marine Mammals 3-54
- 3.5 SPECIAL STATUS SPECIES AND THEIR PROTECTION 3-56
 - 3.5.1 Federally Listed Species and Critical Habitat 3-56

- 3.5.1.1 Western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*). 3-56
- 3.5.1.2 California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*) 3-57
- 3.5.1.3 Southern sea otter (*Enhydra lutris nereis*) 3-58
- 3.5.2 Other Special Status Species Having Potential to Occur at NBVC Port Hueneme 3-59
 - 3.5.2.1 Least Bell’s Vireo (*Vireo bellii pusillus*) 3-59
 - 3.5.2.2 Burrowing owl (*Athene cunicularia*) 3-59
 - 3.5.2.3 Silvery legless lizard (*Aniella pulchra*) 3-60
 - 3.5.2.4 Western pond turtle (*Emys marmorata*) 3-60
 - 3.5.2.5 Globose dune beetle (*Coelus globosus*) 3-60
 - 3.5.2.6 Sandy Beach tiger beetle (*Cicindela hirticollis gravida*) 3-60
 - 3.5.2.7 Monarch butterfly (*Danaus plexippus*) 3-60
- 3.5.3 Special Status Species Protection 3-61
 - 3.5.3.1 Federally Listed Species Protection 3-61
 - 3.5.3.2 Other Special Status Species Management 3-64
- 3.6 INVASIVE SPECIES MANAGEMENT 3-65
 - 3.6.1 Terrestrial Invasives 3-66
 - 3.6.2 Aquatic Invasives 3-70
 - 3.6.3 Pests and Disease Vectors 3-75
- 3.7 NATURAL RESOURCES LAW ENFORCEMENT 3-77
- 3.8 DATA INTEGRATION, ACCESS, AND REPORTING 3-77
- 4.0 SUSTAINABILITY OF THE MILITARY MISSION AND COMPATIBLE USE 4-1
 - 4.1 INTEGRATED MILITARY MISSION AND SUSTAINABLE LAND USE DECISIONS/OPERATIONS PLANNING AND REVIEW 4-1
 - 4.2 SUSTAINABILITY IN THE BUILT ENVIRONMENT 4-5
 - 4.3 ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS 4-9
 - 4.4 BENEFICIAL PARTNERSHIPS AND COLLABORATIVE RESOURCES PLANNING 4-10
 - 4.5 REGULATORY COMPLIANCE 4-12
 - 4.6 CONSISTENCY WITH OTHER PLANS 4-22
 - 4.6.1 Consistency with Integrated Cultural Resource Management Plan 4-23
 - 4.7 REMEDIATION OF CONTAMINATED MEDIA 4-24
 - 4.8 OIL SPILL RESPONSE AND HAZARDOUS SUBSTANCE PREVENTION AND CLEANUP 4-28
 - 4.9 HARBOR OPERATIONS 4-30
 - 4.10 CONSTRUCTION, FACILITY AND UTILITIES MAINTENANCE 4-31
 - 4.11 LANDSCAPING AND GROUNDS MAINTENANCE 4-33
 - 4.12 LEASES AND REAL ESTATE OUTGRANTS 4-37
 - 4.13 RECREATION AND PUBLIC ACCESS 4-38

4.14	PUBLIC OUTREACH	4-40
5.0	IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY	5-1
5.1	GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS	5-1
5.1.1	Responsibility	5-2
5.1.2	Federal Anti-Deficiency Act.....	5-3
5.1.3	Staffing.....	5-4
5.1.3.1	Contractor Support.....	5-4
5.1.3.2	Professional Development and Natural Resources Training .	5-4
5.2	ADAPTIVE MANAGEMENT: ANNUAL UPDATE, REVIEW AND METRICS	5-5
5.3	BUDGET CONSIDERATIONS	5-8
5.3.1	Natural Resources Management Priorities and Funding Classifications .	5-8
5.3.2	External Assistance.....	5-12
5.4	FUNDING SOURCES	5-13
5.4.1	Department of Defense Funding Sources	5-13
5.4.2	Use of Cooperative Agreements and Partnerships.....	5-15
5.4.3	Research Funding Requirements	5-15
5.4.4	Non-DOD Funding Sources.....	5-16
5.5	INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY AND SCHEDULE	5-16
6.0	LITERATURE CITED	6-1

APPENDICES

A	LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS
B	ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT (2001)
C	LIST OF NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT DRIVERS AND INTEGRATING OTHER PLANS
D	LAND USE AND COVER TYPES AND ACREAGES
E	NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP PROJECT LIST
F	MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
G	BIOLOGICAL SURVEYS
H	SPECIES LISTS
I	MIGRATORY BIRD MANAGEMENT
J	BENEFITS FOR THREATENED AND ENDANGERED SPECIES
K	NBVC APPROVED LANDSCAPING PLANT LIST
L	NBVC BARD ESTATE PLANT LIST
M	ANNUAL METRICS REPORTS
N	NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGER APPOINTMENT LETTER

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 3-1: MONTHLY TEMPERATURE REGIME PORT HUENEME, 1960-2010 (DATA FOR POINT MUGU, CA; WESTERN REGIONAL CLIMATE CENTER [WRCC] 2011; NOAA 2011)..... 3-4

FIGURE 3-2: MEAN MONTHLY RAINFALL AT PORT HUENEME, 1923-2003 (DATA FOR OXNARD, CA; WRCC 2011) 3-4

FIGURE 3-3: AVERAGE ANNUAL RAINFALL TOTAL FOR PORT HUENEME, 1925-2003 (DATA FOR OXNARD, CA; WRCC 2011) 3-5

LIST OF MAPS

MAP 1-1 GENERAL LOCATION 1-4

MAP 1-2 FACILITIES..... 1-8

MAP 1-3 LAND USE 1-9

MAP 2-1 OPPORTUNITIES AND CONSTRAINTS..... 2-18

MAP 3-1 STORM DRAINAGE..... 3-6

MAP 3-2 TERRESTRIAL AND MARINE COMMUNITIES 3-14

MAP 3-3 JURISDICTIONAL WATERS 3-21

MAP 4-1: ACTIVE CERCLA SITES 4-25

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE A: TABLE OF CONTENTS CROSSWALK TO DoD TEMPLATE VI

TABLE 1-1: VARIOUS PLANNING DOCUMENTS INCORPORATED INTO THIS INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN 1-22

TABLE 2-1: NBVC PORT HUENEME TENANT COMMANDS DISCUSSED IN THIS INRMP... 2-3

TABLE 2-2: FEDERAL REGULATIONS TO BE CONSIDERED IN PORT HUENEME NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT 2-15

TABLE 4-1: PARTIAL CHECKLIST (PORTION RELATING TO NATURAL RESOURCES) AND SCORING SYSTEM FOR NAVY LEED PROJECTS 4-7

TABLE 4-2: FEDERAL AND STATE STATUTES AFFECTING MANAGEMENT OF CONTAMINATED MEDIA..... 4-26

TABLE A: TABLE OF CONTENTS CROSSWALK TO DoD TEMPLATE

PH INRMP Table of Contents		DoD Template (DoDINST 4715.03 [DoD 2010])
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY		DoD 3—Executive Summary
1.0	Introduction	DoD 5—Overview
1.1	Purpose and Scope	DoD 5.a.1—Purpose DoD 5.b—Scope
1.2	Authority	DoD 5.a.2—Authority and Background
1.3	Location and Planning Footprint	DoD 6.a—General Description DoD 6.b—Regional Land Use
1.4	Real Estate Summary	DoD 6.a—General Description DoD 6.e—Operations and Infrastructure
1.5	Military Mission	DoD 6.d—Military Mission
1.6	Military Land Use and Categories of Operations	DoD 6.d—Military Mission DoD 6.e.3—Military Operations and Activities
	1.6.1 Regional U.S. Navy Military Land Use	DoD 6.d—Military Mission DoD 6.e.3—Military Operations and Activities
1.7	Achieving Success and No Net Loss to the Military Mission	DoD 7.b.2—Achieving No Net Loss
	1.7.1 Mission Sustainability and the INRMP “No Net Loss” Requirement	DoD 7.a.4—Sustainability Challenges DoD 7.b.2—Achieving No Net Loss
1.8	INRMP Vision, Goals and Objectives	DoD 5.d—Goals and Objectives
1.9	Roles and Responsibilities for the INRMP	DoD 5.c—Responsibilities
	1.9.1 INRMP Working Group	DoD 5.c—Responsibilities
	1.9.2 Installation Stakeholders	DoD 5.c.1—Internal INRMP Stakeholders
	1.9.3 External Stakeholder	DoD 5.c.2—External INRMP Stakeholders
1.10	Ecosystem Approach	DoD 5.e—Management Strategy
1.11	Revision and Annual Review	DoD 5.g—Review and Revision Process
1.12	Compliance and Stewardship Criteria for Implementing Projects	DoD 5.f—Stewardship and Compliance Discussion
1.13	Integrating Other Plans	DoD 5.h—Other Plan Integration and Preparing Prescriptions for Projects
2.0	Military Use and Natural Resources Management	DoD 6—Current Installation Conditions and Use
2.1	Historical Overview of Natural Resource Use	DoD 6.c—Historic Land Use
	2.1.1 Pre-Navy Land Use	DoD 6.c—Historic Land Use
	2.1.2 Historical Navy Land Use	DoD 6.c—Historic Land Use
2.2	Operations and Infrastructure	DoD 6.d—Military Mission DoD 6.e—Operations and Infrastructure
	2.2.1 Mission Critical	DoD 6.d—Military Mission DoD 6.e—Operations and Infrastructure
	2.2.2 Mission Support	DoD 6.d—Military Mission DoD 6.e—Operations and Infrastructure
	2.2.3 Quality of Life	DoD 6.e—Operations and Infrastructure
2.3	Leases and Real Estate Outgrants	DoD 8.q.—Other Leases
2.4	Future Use Patterns and Plans: The NBVC Port Hueneme Activity Overview Plan and Sustainable Planning and Design	DoD 7.a.4—Sustainability Challenges DoD 7.a.1—Operations Planning and Review
2.5	Overview of Government Regulatory Context of Natural Resources Management	DoD 7.d.—Consultation Requirements
2.6	Opportunities	DoD 6.g—Opportunities
	2.6.1 Internal Opportunities	DoD 6.g.1—Internal Opportunities
	2.6.2 External Opportunities	DoD 6.g.2—External Opportunities
2.7	Constraints	DoD 6.f—Constraints
	2.7.1 Internal Encroachment	DoD 6.f.1—Internal Encroachment
	2.7.2 External Encroachment	DoD 6.f.2—External Encroachment

PH INRMP Table of Contents (continued)		DoD Template (DoDINST 4715.03 [DoD 2010])
3.0	Current Condition and Management of Natural Resources	DoD 7—Natural Resources Management and Military Mission Sustainability
3.1	Ecoregional Setting	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 6.h.2—Ecoregions
	3.1.1 Topography	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment
	3.1.2 Geology	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment
	3.1.3 Climate and Climate Change	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 6.h.9—Climate Change Vulnerability Assessment
3.2	Physical Conditions And Managing the Physical and Chemical Environment	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 8—Natural Resources Management Program Actions
	3.2.1 Air Quality	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 8—Natural Resources Management Program Actions
	3.2.2 Soils and Soil Conservation	DoD 8.d—Soil and Water Management
	3.2.2.1 Shoreline Sediment	DoD 8.d—Soil and Water Management
	3.2.3 Water Resources and Water Management	DoD 8.d—Soil and Water Management
	3.2.3.1 Groundwater	DoD 8.d—Soil and Water Management
	3.2.3.2 Surface and Stormwater Management	DoD 8.d—Soil and Water Management
	3.2.3.3 Jurisdictional Waters—Wetlands Management	DoD 6.h.4—Aquatic Habitats DoD 8.c.—Wetlands Management
3.3	Ecosystems	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 6.h.5—Flora and Vegetative Communities
	3.3.1 Coastal and Marine Communities	DoD 6.h.4—Aquatic Habitats DoD 8.c.—Wetlands Management DoD 8.e—Coastal/Marine Management
	3.3.1.1 Marine Subtidal	DoD 6.h.4—Aquatic Habitats DoD 8.c.—Wetlands Management DoD 8.e—Coastal/Marine Management
	3.3.1.2 Sandy Beach	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 8.e—Coastal/Marine Management
	3.3.2 Terrestrial Communities	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 6.h.5—Flora and Vegetative Communities
	3.3.2.1 Dune Mat	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 6.h.5—Flora and Vegetative Communities DoD 8.b—Vegetation Management
	3.3.2.2 Coyote Brush Scrub	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 6.h.5—Flora and Vegetative Communities DoD 8.b—Vegetation Management
	3.3.2.3 Non-Native Annual Grassland	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 6.h.5—Flora and Vegetative Communities DoD 8.b—Vegetation Management
	3.3.2.4 Arroyo Willow Thickets and Drainage Channels	DoD 6.h—Natural Environment DoD 6.h.5—Flora and Vegetative Communities DoD 8.b—Vegetation Management
3.4	Fish and Wildlife Management	DoD 8.h—Fish and Wildlife Management
	3.4.1 Terrestrial Invertebrates	DoD 6.h.6—Fauna DoD 8.h—Fish and Wildlife Management
	3.4.2 Pollinators	DoD 6.h.6—Fauna DoD 8.h—Fish and Wildlife Management
	3.4.3 Reptiles and Amphibians	DoD 6.h.6—Fauna DoD 8.h—Fish and Wildlife Management
	3.4.4 Birds	DoD 6.h.6—Fauna DoD 8.h—Fish and Wildlife Management
	3.4.5 Mammals	DoD 6.h.6—Fauna DoD 8.h—Fish and Wildlife Management
	3.4.6 Aquatic Invertebrates	DoD 6.h.6—Fauna DoD 8.h—Fish and Wildlife Management

PH INRMP Table of Contents (continued)	DoD Template (DoDINST 4715.03 [DoD 2010])
3.4.7 Fish	DoD 6.h.6—Fauna DoD 8.h—Fish and Wildlife Management
3.4.8 Marine Mammals	DoD 6.h.6—Fauna DoD 8.h—Fish and Wildlife Management
3.5 Special Status Species and Their Protection	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.1 Federally Listed Species and Critical Habitat	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.1.1 Western snowy plover (<i>Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus</i>)	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.1.2 California least tern (<i>Sterna antillarum browni</i>)	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.1.3 Southern sea otter (<i>Enhydra lutris nereis</i>)	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.2 Other Special Status Species Having Potential to Occur at NBVC Port Hueneme	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.2.1 Least Bell’s Vireo (<i>Vireo bellii pusillus</i>)	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.2.2 Burrowing owl (<i>Athene cunicularia</i>)	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.2.3 Silvery legless lizard (<i>Aniella pulchra</i>)	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.2.4 Western pond turtle (<i>Emys marmorata</i>)	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.2.5 Globose dune beetle (<i>Coelus globosus</i>)	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.2.6 Sandy Beach tiger beetle (<i>Cicindela hirticollis gravida</i>)	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.2.7 Monarch butterfly (<i>Danaus plexippus</i>):	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.3 Special Status Species Protection	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.3.1 Federally Listed Species Protection	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.5.3.2 Other Special Status Species Management	DoD 6.h.7—Resources of Special Interest DoD 8.i—Threatened and Endangered Species Management
3.6 Invasive Species Management	DoD 8.g—Invasive Species Management
3.6.1 Terrestrial Invasives	DoD 8.g—Invasive Species Management
3.6.2 Aquatic Invasives	DoD 8.g—Invasive Species Management
3.6.3 Pests and Disease Vectors	DoD 8.k—Pest Management
3.7 Natural Resources Law Enforcement	DoD 8.m—Natural Resources Conservation Law Enforcement
3.8 Data Integration, Access, and Reporting	DoD 8.o—Geographic Information System Management
4.0 Sustainability of the Military Mission and Compatible Use	DoD 7—Natural Resources Management and Military Mission Sustainability DoD 7.a—Integrating Natural Resources Management and Military Mission
4.1 Integrated Military Mission and Sustainable Land Use Decisions/Operations Planning and Review	DoD 7.a—Integrating Natural Resources Management and Military Mission DoD 6.f.4—Constraints Map DoD 6.g.3—Opportunities Map DoD 7.b.2—Achieving No Net Loss
4.2 Sustainability in the Built Environment	DoD 7.a.4—Sustainability Challenges
4.3 Environmental Awareness	DoD 7.a.3—Environmental Awareness
4.4 Beneficial Partnerships and Collaborative Resources Planning	DoD 9.c—Cooperative Agreements and Partnerships DoD 7.b.1—Encroachment Partnering
4.5 Regulatory Compliance	DoD 7.c—NEPA DoD 7.d—Consultation Requirements

PH INRMP Table of Contents (continued)	DoD Template (DoDINST 4715.03 [DoD 2010])
4.6 Consistency with Other Plans	DoD 5.h—Other Plan Integration and Preparing Prescriptions for Projects
4.6.1 Consistency with Integrated Cultural Resource Management Plan	DoD 5.h—Other Plan Integration and Preparing Prescriptions for Projects
4.7 Remediation of Contaminated Media	DoD 6.e—Operations and Infrastructure
4.8 Oil Spill Response and Hazardous Substance Prevention and Cleanup	DoD 6.e—Operations and Infrastructure
4.9 Harbor Operations	DoD 6.e—Operations and Infrastructure
4.10 Construction, Facility and Utilities Maintenance	DoD 6.e—Operations and Infrastructure
4.11 Landscaping and Grounds Maintenance	DoD 6.e—Operations and Infrastructure
4.12 Leases and Real Estate Outgrants	DoD 8.q.—Other Leases
4.13 Recreation and Public Access	DoD 7.f.1—Public Access and Outdoor Recreation DoD 8.j—Outdoor Recreation
4.14 Public Outreach	DoD 7.f.2—Public Outreach
5.0 Implementation Strategy	DoD 9—Implementation
5.1 General Considerations	Not Applicable
5.1.1 Responsibility	DoD 5.c—Responsibilities
5.1.2 Federal Anti-Deficiency Act	DoD 5.c—Responsibilities
5.1.3 Staffing	DoD 9.b—Staffing
5.1.3.1 Contractor Support	Not Applicable
5.1.3.2 Professional Development and Natural Resources Training	DoD 9.b.3—Professional Development and Natural Resources Training
5.2 Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review and Metrics	DoD 5.e—Management Strategy DoD 5.g—Review and Revision Process DoD 9.d—Metrics
5.3 Budget Considerations	DoD 9.a—Funding
5.3.1 Natural Resources Management Priorities and Funding Classifications	DoD 9.a—Funding
5.3.2 External Assistance	DoD 9. c—Cooperative Agreements and Partnerships
5.4 Funding Sources	DoD 9.a—Funding
5.4.1 Department of Defense Funding Sources	DoD 9.c—Cooperative Agreements and Partnerships
5.4.2 Use of Cooperative Agreements and Partnerships	DoD 9.c—Cooperative Agreements and Partnerships
5.4.3 Research Funding Requirements	DoD 9.a—Funding
5.4.4 Non-DoD Funding Sources	DoD 9.a—Funding
5.5 INRMP Implementation Summary and Schedule	DoD 5.h—Other Plan Integration and Preparing Prescriptions for Projects
6.0 REFERENCES	DoD 11—References/Literature Cited
APPENDICES	
A. List of Acronyms	Appendix 1—List of Acronyms
B. Environmental Assessment	Not Applicable
C. List of Natural Resources Management Drivers and Integrating Other Plans	Appendix 2—List of Natural Resources Management Drivers
D. Land Use and Cover Types and Acreages	Appendix 7—Training Area Acreages Appendix 8—Landcover Types & Acreages
E. List of Projects and Detailed Natural Resource Management Prescriptions	Appendix 17—Detailed Natural Resources Management Prescriptions Appendix 18—List of Projects
F. Memorandum of Understanding	Appendix 3—Tri-Partite Agreement
G. Biological Surveys	Appendix 9—Results of Planning Level Surveys—Flora Appendix 10—Results of Planning Level Surveys—Fauna
H. Species Lists	Appendix 9—Results of Planning Level Surveys—Flora Appendix 10—Results of Planning Level Surveys—Fauna Appendix 12—List of Special Status Species Appendix 13—List of Species Greatest Conservation Need

PH INRMP Table of Contents (continued)	DoD Template (DoDINST 4715.03 [DoD 2010])
I. Migratory Bird Management	Appendix 14—INRMP Benefits for Migratory Birds
J. Benefits to Threatened and Endangered Species	Appendix 15—INRMP Benefits for Endangered Species
K. NBVC Approved Landscaping Plant List	Not Applicable
L. NBVC Bard Estate Plant List	Not Applicable
M. Annual Metrics Reports	Appendix 5—Results of Annual Review
N. Natural Resources Manager Appointment Letter	Not Applicable

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

The purpose of an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) generally is to help installation commanders manage natural resources more effectively to ensure that installation lands and waters remain available and in good condition to support the military mission. Designed to facilitate both stewardship and compliance with natural resource laws in the context of military mission requirements, this INRMP is to provide a viable and implementable framework for the management of natural resources at Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC) Port Hueneme, California. This INRMP integrates natural resource components of existing Port Hueneme plans, environmental documents, and the requirements of all applicable U.S. Department of Defense (DoD), U.S. Department of the Navy (Navy), and installation regulations and guidelines.

An INRMP is a long-term planning document designed to guide an installation in the management of its natural resources to support the installation mission while protecting and enhancing installation resources for multiple use, sustainable yield, and biological integrity (Navy 2006). An INRMP is to provide an implementable framework for sustainable, multipurpose use, and conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources. Required by the Sikes Act Improvement Act (SAIA) of 1997 (as amended), an INRMP is the primary means by which natural resources compliance and stewardship priorities are set, and funding requirements are determined. A commitment to implement priority projects, as funding availability permits, comes with the signatures at the front of this INRMP.

The SAIA stipulates that this INRMP provide for:

- Public access that is necessary and appropriate for the use described above, subject to requirements necessary to ensure safety and military security;
- Specific natural resources management goals and objectives, and time frames for acting on them;
- Fish and wildlife management, land management, forest management, and fish and wildlife-oriented recreation;
- Fish and wildlife habitat enhancement or modifications;
- Wetlands protection, enhancement, and restoration where necessary, for support of fish, wildlife, or plants;
- Integration of and consistency among the various activities conducted under the INRMP;

- Sustainable use of natural resources by the public, to the extent that use is consistent with needs of the fish and wildlife resources;
- Enforcement of natural resource laws and regulations;
- No net loss in the capability of the military installation lands to support the military mission of the installation; and,
- Such other activities as the Secretary of the Navy (SECNAV) determines appropriate.

By direction of the Office of the Undersecretary of Defense (OUSD) memo of 08 August 1994, *Implementation of Ecosystem Management in the Department of Defense*, INRMPs are required to ensure that ecosystem management is the basis for all future management of DoD lands and waters. Based on an ecosystem approach, this INRMP takes a large geographic view to ensure the overriding purpose of protecting the properties and functions of natural ecosystems (DoD Instruction [DoDINST] 4715.03 *Natural Resources Conservation Program*). Because ecosystem boundaries are rarely synonymous with property ownership, installations such as Port Hueneme are encouraged to form cooperative partnerships with resource management agencies, as appropriate, and take part in public awareness initiatives to manage ecosystems more successfully. The OUSD memorandum provides principles and guidelines for implementing ecosystem management on DoD lands. This includes participation in regional ecosystem initiatives.

INRMPs as formalized under SAIA, are developed jointly by the Navy, the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS), state fish and wildlife agencies such as the California Department of Fish and Game (CDFG), and National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS). Mutual agreement from these agencies is sought for the fish and wildlife component of natural resource management identified in the INRMP, and an annual review with the agencies to discuss Navy installation-wide natural resources is mandatory. Agency agreement is formalized on the signatory pages at the front of this INRMP.

This document is the first formal revision of the original 1999 Integrated Resource Management Plan (IRMP). This revision was undertaken to update the resource goals and objectives of NBVC Port Hueneme. The previous IRMP dealt with cultural and natural resource management. Cultural resources are now addressed in a separate management document ([ASM Affiliates, Inc. 2010](#)). Some legal requirements have been instituted since the IRMP, such as guidelines for complying with the Magnuson-Stevenson Fisheries Conservation and Management Act and associated habitat conservation provisions for Essential Fish Habitat (EFH), and the Final Rule removing the brown pelican (*Pelecanus occidentalis*) from the Federal List of Endangered and Threatened Wildlife (74 Federal Register [FR] 59443). Since the original 1999 IRMP, changes have also occurred in DoD guidance on INRMP content ([DoD 2010](#); [DoD 2011](#)).

The Navy and Port Hueneme will implement recommendations in this INRMP within the framework of regulatory compliance, national Navy mission obligations, anti-terrorism and force protection limitations, and funding constraints. All actions contemplated in this INRMP are

subject to the availability of funds properly authorized and appropriated under federal law. Nothing in this INRMP is intended to be nor may be construed to be a violation of the Anti-Deficiency Act (31 U.S. Code [USC] 1341 et seq.).

1.2 AUTHORITY

The Sikes Act directs the DoD to take the appropriate management actions necessary to protect and enhance the land and water resources on all installations under its control. DoDINST 4715.03, *Natural Resources Conservation Program*, has been implemented to establish fundamental land management policies and procedures for all military lands to preserve the military mission while simultaneously protecting the natural resources. Naval Facilities Engineering Command (NAVFAC) MO-100.1 (Maintenance Operating Manual, *Natural Resources Land Management*) provides basic technical guidance for land management practices of all DoD land and water resources. Office of the Chief of Naval Operations Instruction (OPNAVINST) 5090.1C, *Environmental Readiness Program Manual, Chapter 24 Natural Resources Management* (Navy 2011a), further establishes program responsibilities and standards for complying with resource protection laws, regulations and Executive Orders (EOs) to conserve and manage natural resources on Navy installations in the U.S. and its territories and possessions. The U.S. Navy Chief of Naval Operations (CNO) INRMP Guidance for Navy Installations, *How to Prepare, Implement, and Revise INRMPs, April 2006*, supplies guidelines on the process and procedure for developing an INRMP.

The effects of implementing this INRMP are addressed under the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) by the Environmental Assessment (EA) (Appendix B). NEPA documentation was prepared in accordance with CNO guidance on conducting NEPA analysis of alternatives and methodologies for accomplishing the management objectives of the INRMP (DoD 2010). Other federal legal requirements that are the primary drivers for natural resources management are listed in Appendix C (USC, Public Laws [PL], EOs, and Code of Federal Regulations [CFR]).

The development of this INRMP is in accordance with the 2011 DoD guidance (DoDINST 4715.03) (DoD 2011) and is also consistent with Navy guidance (both the CNO Guidance of April 2006, and OPNAVINST 5090.1C), to ensure compliance with all guidelines (Navy 2006, 2011a; DoD 2010, 2011). The organization and outline of this INRMP is consistent with the 2010 DoD Template for INRMPs (DoD 2010), as detailed in Table A Table of Contents Crosswalk to DoD Template.

1.3 LOCATION AND PLANNING FOOTPRINT

NBVC includes the Point Mugu and San Nicloas Island installations; however, this INRMP applies only to Port Hueneme. NBVC Port Hueneme (referred to herein as both “installation” and “base”), encompasses 1,650 acres of mostly developed coastal land in Ventura County, California, approximately 60 miles northwest of the City of Los Angeles (Map 1-1). The installation is bordered by the City of Port Hueneme to the west and north, the City of Oxnard to the east, and Channel Islands Harbor to the west. Silver Strand Beach borders the southwest, and Port Hueneme Beach is southeast of the Port Hueneme Harbor entrance channel.

LEGEND

 NBVC PORT HUENEME BOUNDARY

Naval Base Ventura County Port Hueneme
Port Hueneme, California

**MAP 1-1
GENERAL LOCATION**

INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN

The base is in and shares important regional relationships with Ventura County, and the independent incorporated cities of Port Hueneme, Oxnard, and Camarillo. Current and future community land use proposals and development in Ventura County potentially affect operations at Navy installations and the operations of the installations can impact local community plans. All planning agency general plans, regional coastal plans, the Ventura County Coastal Area Plans and City Local Coastal Plans should be monitored and potential impacts to operations at NBVC considered. Therefore, it is important to monitor and interact with the land use planning agencies of the County of Ventura and incorporated cities to foster information exchange and cooperation ([Onyx Group 2006](#)).

1.4 REAL ESTATE SUMMARY

The Port Hueneme installation is mostly developed or paved and has a mix of residential, industrial, and commercial land uses. Approximately 199 acres are managed under the NBVC natural resources program, which includes 90 acres of upland and 108 acres of harbor area. There are no agricultural outlease areas on base. It hosts a variety of tenant activities and lessees such as the Civil Engineer Corps Officers School (CECOS) and Global Auto Processing Services (GAPS). At the time of writing, approximately 103 acres of land and port area at Port Hueneme are under lease agreement. All proposed actions on leased lands are subject to the Navy's project planning and review process, as described in Section 4.5 Regulatory Compliance. NBVC Port Hueneme also owns and operates a major portion of Hueneme Harbor that provides maritime support for the Navy.

The approximately 108-acre Port of Hueneme Harbor was created by dredging in 1934, and is used for commercial and naval activities ([Stearns, Conrad, and Schmidt \[SCS\] and Landau Associates 1985](#)). Port Hueneme is the only deep-water commercial port facility between Los Angeles and San Francisco, and the Navy's only deep-water port between San Diego County and Washington State. The installation shares Port Hueneme Harbor with Oxnard Harbor District (OHD).

The Navy-owned portion of the port comprises about 200 acres on the southern end of the installation. The Navy owns seven wharves (Wharves 4, 5, 6, A, B, C and D), and has a joint use agreement with OHD for use of Wharf 3 in times of need ([Onyx Group 2006](#)) ([Map 1-2](#)). OHD owns and operates approximately 69 acres of land in the harbor area and eastern channel (Channel A), including wharves 1 and 2, with five berths used for deep-draft mooring and cargo transfer. NBVC Port Operations has complete control of all military vessels entering and exiting the harbor, and all internal movements. Commercial traffic in the eastern channel is controlled and organized by OHD in collaboration with NBVC Port Operations. Numerous commercial fishing boats enter and exit OHD as well ([Tetra Tech 2011a](#)).

1.5 MILITARY MISSION

The NBVC mission is to provide integrated shore services to support the diverse needs of the fleet, fighter and family in Ventura County. The mission of the base is the same as when it was established in 1942: to provide a home port and to furnish training, administrative, and logistical

support for the Naval Construction Battallions (or Seabees) serving in many parts of the world. As part of the Navy's streamlined shore structure management under the direction of Commander Navy Installation Command and Commander Navy Region Southwest in San Diego, the installation provides site operation support services to the military defense complex in Ventura County that encompasses all military activities at NBVC Port Hueneme, NBVC Point Mugu, and NBVC San Nicolas Island.

Through this effort, the installation supports more than 40 tenant commands with diverse DoD missions ranging from Seabee support, mobilization and military training, to test and evaluation of air and shipboard weapons systems for the strategic defense of the United States. Mission-related functions at the base include Port Operations, Research Development Testing and Evaluation (RDT&E), Training, Ordnance, and Seabee Operations and Mobilization. Many of the installation's departments, such as the Supply Department, Comptroller, Civil Engineers Support Office, and Facilities System Office provide direct support to other Navy commands. Other branches of the military are supported through various tenant missions, including the U.S. Coast Guard, U.S. Marines, U.S. Army and U.S. Air Force, as detailed in [Section 2.2](#), Operations and Infrastructure ([Onyx Group 2006](#)). The primary tenants discussed in this INRMP are shown on [Map 1-2](#), Facilities, and discussed further in [Section 2.2](#), Operations and Infrastructure.

1.6 MILITARY LAND USE AND CATEGORIES OF OPERATIONS

The installation is currently designated for the homeported and deployed military functions of:

- Storing and shipping construction materials, equipment, and provisions;
- Berthing surface craft and surface targets;
- Training personnel in various types of construction projects; and,
- Engineering and technical services.

The base property comprises 9 major land uses: logistics, operations, training, housing, community support, administration, natural resource management areas, ordnance, and public works ([Map 1-3](#)). [Map 1-3](#) shows the most recent land use classifications provided by NBVC GIS and Planning departments for this INRMP. [Appendix D](#) details acreages for each land use designation and land cover type. Nearly half of the land use acreage is devoted to logistics land uses. The operations category includes (RDT&E) and port operations land uses, which were formerly segregated in the Naval Base Ventura County Activity Overview Plan (AOP) of 2006 ([Onyx Group 2006](#)). Operations and ordnance land uses are along the harbor. The main training area for construction activities is at the northwest corner of the base, and a smaller training site is in the central eastern portion. The housing area is along the central eastern boundary of the site. Integrated into the housing areas are a variety of community and recreational support facilities. Natural resources management area land uses are along the drainage canals that run parallel and also intersect Pennsylvania Road, and at sandy beach and dune habitat near the harbor entrance. Natural resources management area land uses include one Installation Restoration Program (IRP)

site (IRP 14) that was a 33-acre landfill that is now capped and covered with annual grassland vegetation. Further information on IRP sites is in [Section 4.7](#), Remediation of Contaminated Media. Public works facilities are clustered throughout the base.

Land uses have been categorized and assessed according to their mission criticality, most recently in the NBVC AOP ([Onyx Group 2006](#)). According to the AOP, land uses are considered Mission Critical, Mission Support, or Quality of Life.

Mission Critical: Mission critical lands and facilities are those that directly support the mission of the installation and tenants. Mission critical functions include Port Operations, RDT&E, Training, Ordnance, and Seabee Operations/Mobilization.

Mission Support: Mission support lands and facilities are those that indirectly support the mission of the installation and tenants. Mission support functions include Supply/Logistics, Facilities/Sustainment Restoration Modernization (SRM), Utilities, Base services, IT/Communications, Federal Fire, Force Protection, Environmental, and Religious Services.

Quality of Life: Quality of life lands and facilities are those that support the well-being of the war-fighter. Quality of life lands and facilities include Bachelor Housing, Family Housing, Recreation/Community Support, Food Services, Social Services, and Health Services.

Activities and tenants associated with each land use category are described further in [Section 2.0](#), Military Use and Natural Resources Management.

1.6.1 Regional U.S. Navy Military Land Use

Southern California is home to the nation's largest concentration of Naval forces. One-third of the U.S. Pacific Fleet makes its homeport in San Diego. The Southern California (SOCAL) Range Complex is an adjacent ocean training range south of the Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division (NAWCWD) Point Mugu Sea Range (PMSR) and services a unique national military training capability in the southwestern U.S., centered around the Naval Auxiliary Landing Field (NALF) San Clemente Island (SCI). Considering the large expanse of the NAWCWD PMSR, other military bases benefit from electronic monitoring capabilities and availability of controlled air and sea space including Vandenberg Air Force Base, California and NBVC Port Hueneme, California.

LEGEND

	PORT HUENEME BOUNDARY
	RAILROAD
	ROAD
	BUILDING
	PAVED AREA (NOT ROAD)
	SURFACE WATER DITCH AND OR WATER
	OXNARD HARBOR DISTRICT
	WHARF

TENANT COMMANDS

	Civil Engineers Corps Officers School
	Naval Construction Regiment
	Naval Construction Training Center
	Naval Facilities Engineering Command Engineering Service Center
	Naval Research Lab
	Port Hueneme Division, Naval Surface Warfare Center
	Naval Facilities Engineering Logistics Command/31st Seabee Readiness Support Group

Naval Base Ventura County Port Hueneme
Port Hueneme, California

**MAP 1-2
FACILITIES**

INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN

GIS Map by ERM - TTEMI Data Source: Navy2011b
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MAP1-2_PH_INRMP_FACILITIES_MAP_031312.mxd

LEGEND

- NBVC PORT HUENEME BOUNDARY
- RAILROAD
- ROAD
- BUILDING
- PAVED AREA (NOT ROAD)
- SURFACE WATER DITCH AND OR WATER

LAND USE

- NATURAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AREA
- COMMUNITY/SUPPORT
- OPERATIONS
- ADMINISTRATION
- HOUSING
- LOGISTICS
- PUBLIC WORKS
- TRAINING
- ORDNANCE

Naval Base Ventura County Port Hueneme
Port Hueneme, California

**MAP 1-3
LAND USE**

INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN

GIS Map by ERM Data Source: Navy 2011b and TetraTech Databases
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MAP1-3_PH_INRMP_LAND_USE_MAP_031312.mxd

1.7 ACHIEVING SUCCESS AND NO NET LOSS TO THE MILITARY MISSION

The military mission, derived from Title 10 of the USC, requires the Navy to “maintain, train and equip combat-ready naval forces capable of winning wars, deterring aggression and maintaining freedom of the seas.” In keeping with the principal use of military installations to ensure the preparedness of the U.S. Armed forces, SAIA mandates that the INRMP shall provide for no net loss of the capability of the installation’s lands to support the military mission. The important points regarding the military mission and natural resources at NBVC Port Hueneme are:

- Port Hueneme consists largely of developed or paved land, with Navy use largely confined to existing developed areas.
- Land-based military training activities occur in designated training zones, consisting of disturbed open space areas ([Map 1-3](#)).
- Activities that occur in the Harbor are federally regulated and require coordination with regulatory agencies.
- Natural resource areas on base are fragmented, contain little to no buffer zones, and are vulnerable to human disturbances.
- Most activity in the natural areas is conducted by NBVC Environmental Division (NBVC ED) and focused on resource management.

1.7.1 Mission Sustainability and the INRMP “No Net Loss” Requirement

The common principal between national security and public land stewardship is the concept of sustainability. Sustainability is a relative condition of the ecosystem and the military mission that can be measured; however, measures of sustainability are scale-dependent. The most widely used definition of sustainability was developed by the World Commission on Environment and Development (also known as the [Brundtland Commission \[1987\]](#)): “Sustainable resource management is...the capacity to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”

Sustainability may be considered as having at least several measurable components in the context of this INRMP: military use facilitation, soil and water resource protection, ecological integrity, cultural resource protection, and base safety for current and future use. For this INRMP, an impact to mission accomplishment has occurred when any of the above are constrained or when one of these conditions occurs:

- Quality of military training is impacted by natural resource restrictions.
- Environmental issues hamper scheduled operations: training qualification objectives to deploy are not accomplished without significant delay or conflict.

- Conflict resolution impacts training intensity or tempo and the target resource condition is impacted.
- Soil and water resources are impaired such that compliance has become a problem and irretrievable damage has occurred. Managing for sustainability means preventing damage that will eliminate the use of an area for the foreseeable future, or for which restoration or mitigation is excessively costly.
- Ecological integrity is irretrievably harmed. Compliance under the SAIA for mission sustainability (“no net loss”) is also defined in this INRMP to include the ecological integrity of training lands, since this integrity will carry these lands into the long-term with all the elements that allow self-recovery to remain intact. Keeping all the pieces (habitats and species) that allow the ecosystem to function at various scales and at the highest level possible, given the mandate for land and water use, is one component of protecting sustainability.
- Cultural resources compliance is impaired. Long-term strategies include cultural resources surveys of areas that are not targeted for immediate use. Some of these areas may be opened to training in the future. Under Section 110 of the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA), federal land managers are directed to inventory cultural resources on lands under their control even when no activity or undertaking is planned. Such investigations aid in long-term planning and contribute to the archaeological context developed to evaluate resources.
- Base safety for current and future use is impaired. The ability to keep the base free from hazardous material aids in assuring the safety of the base for current training purposes and any potential alternate future uses.

Under the SAIA, NBVC Port Hueneme must ensure mission sustainability and see that there is no net loss to the military mission due to implementation of this INRMP. To do this, the link between the installation’s military mission and land use must be maintained by identifying and partitioning the requirement of resource protection and the military missions of the landowner and its tenant users. Management of natural resources can support the military mission by avoiding unnecessary conflicts between mission requirements and legal mandates regarding natural resources, promoting positive public relations, and enhancing the quality of life for site personnel.

1.8 INRMP VISION, GOALS AND OBJECTIVES

The vision for this INRMP is to institutionalize a Navy conservation ethic and fully comply with regulatory requirements. This will occur by maintaining the continued ability of the Navy at Port Hueneme to support mission requirements while improving the conditions for long-term certainty and permanence through applying the principles of ecosystem management, adaptive management, and cooperative management in an integrated approach.

INRMPs have goals that are shaped by DoD guidelines and directives, pertinent laws and regulations, public needs, public values, ecological theory and practice, and management experience. For the purposes of this INRMP, a “goal” is a broad statement of intent, direction and purpose. A goal is an enduring, visionary description of an end outcome, but is not necessarily completely attainable. It describes a desired outcome related to the mission, rather than an activity or process.

The goals of the NBVC Port Hueneme INRMP are to:

- Achieve sustainable military readiness while maintaining ecosystem resilience to mission impacts.
- Maintain and enhance through adaptive management principles functioning ecological communities and sensitive species recovery.
- Achieve collaborative internal and external partnerships to maximize mutual benefits, such as identifying additional funding sources, improving cost-effectiveness, and sharing compatible data.
- Improve DoD personnel, contractor, and public awareness of the natural resources and how impacts to these resources can affect the military mission.

The planning terms used in this document such as “goal,” “objective,” and “strategy” cover a gradient of specificity and durability, ranging from a very broad, enduring goal to specific implementation or management strategies. Below are explanations of the planning terms used in Sections 3 through 5. Management strategies are developed and presented using a step-down approach. The objectives and their associated management strategies addressed in [Sections 3.0](#) through [5.0](#) were developed through expert interviews conducted with installation managers. This collaborative and interactive process allowed specific concerns to be identified, current management practices to be documented, and the sufficiency of those practices to address those specific concerns to be assessed. Objectives and management strategies were then collaboratively developed and reviewed by stakeholders (Section 1.9.2 Internal Stakeholders and Section 1.9.3 External Stakeholders) to guide future practices to reconcile those deficiencies to ensure that specific concerns are addressed. The purpose for including specific concerns, current management, assessment of current management, objectives and management strategies is further discussed below.

Specific Concerns: The discussion of specific concerns identifies management concerns or issues specific to NBVC Port Hueneme. These specific concerns may describe any aspect of the status and trend of the resource that may be a concern to its health, abundance, or stability, or address what controlling factors may be involved. The harbor and port are mission critical resources that are used by fish and wildlife protected under federal regulations. Many of the habitat types on base have been greatly reduced on a regional scale and are sensitive to human impacts. On the base, these natural areas are fragmented, lack buffers and are sensitive to impacts such as soil erosion, pollution, changes in hydrology, invasive species, and human

disturbances. Specific concerns are identified and addressed for each resource detailed in Section 3 Current Condition and Management of Natural Resources.

Other questions that specific concerns address include:

- Are there known threats to the health of the resource?
- Does the resource have any particular vulnerabilities (e.g., small breeding area in few locations)?
- Does the expansion of the resource create a problem for other resources or the military mission?
- Is there uncertainty about the status or trend of the resource such that environmental documentation (NEPA, etc.), adaptive management, or ecosystem management is impaired (i.e., is there sufficient inventory and monitoring)?

Current Management: The discussion of current management states how the resource is currently managed under the directives of natural resource laws and regulations, Records of Decision (RODs), permits, zoning, policies, NEPA site approval process, and inventory or survey reports. Details specific to the installation should include the type of management approach used to carry out the natural resources program, such as ecosystem, adaptive, and/or cooperative management (DoD 2010).

The purpose of the current management discussion is to describe the tools and plans used for natural resource management at NBVC Port Hueneme, specific to each INRMP topic.

Assessment of Current Management: The discussion of the assessment of current management at NBVC Port Hueneme relates the specific concerns to management adequacy for each INRMP topic. This discussion states the installation's findings with respect to data gaps, any military mission conflicts, the ability to support avoidance and minimization of impacts, or the sustainability of natural resource uses. This discussion considers the relationship between risks, vulnerabilities, uncertainties, costs, and benefits to develop objectives and management strategies that support adaptive management.

Objective: The previous discussions lead to the identification of an objective and management strategy for each INRMP topic. For this INRMP, an objective describes the desired outcome in terms of the structure and function of what is being protected. An objective should be a specific statement that describes a desired future end-state or successful outcome that supports an INRMP goal or Navy policy. The objective can be quantitative and should be followed by a "standard" that is an observable indicator by which successful attainment of a condition stated in the objective is measured. The definition of an objective from Navy guidance and from the INRMP scopes of work is:

“...the contractor shall work with the installation and other stakeholders to develop objectives for resource management that translates the vision into a strategy. Objectives should be specific, measurable, achievable, and realistic in time frame and budget. They should also have a fixed end point. Objectives and strategies should be based on the principles of adaptive management, whereby management actions are treated as scientific hypotheses to be tested.”

Each INRMP topic is addressed, at a minimum, with an objective and a management strategy.

Management Strategy: A management strategy is an explicit description of the ways and means by which the objective will be achieved. Management strategies detailed in Sections 3 through 5 are the basis for developing projects identified in [Section 5.5](#), Implementation Summary and Schedule; and [Appendix E](#), NBVC Port Hueneme INRMP Project List. All management strategies developed in this INRMP support projects pertaining to each respective INRMP topic. A management project may be supported by a single management strategy or may be supported by multiple strategies categorized in various INRMP topics. For example, a project related to terrestrial invasive exotic species control may be supported by management strategies discussed in terrestrial vegetation communities and in the terrestrial invasive exotic species section. Thus, all the projects included in this INRMP will support an ecosystem based management approach if fully implemented, funded, and enforced.

1.9 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES FOR THE INRMP

The following sections address roles and responsibilities of the INRMP Working Group (WG) and details internal and external stakeholders.

1.9.1 INRMP Working Group

A WG consisting of internal Navy and external stakeholders was formed to develop this INRMP. They met with this mission:

The Port Hueneme INRMP WG will develop an implementable plan to maintain long-term ecosystem health and minimize adverse impacts to existing habitats consistent with the operational requirements of DoD’s training and testing mission.

The WG met to assess NBVC Port Hueneme’s ecological needs, develop objectives, and review the conservation strategies proposed. Based on Navy guidance, the expectations of the WG are to:

- Assess ecological needs.

- Develop a mission statement. A mission statement defining the philosophy, core values, mandates, and natural resources management goals on NBVC Port Hueneme will be developed by the WG. The statement will be included in the INRMP and will provide a clear concept of where the installation is going and help define the INRMP objectives.
- Develop conservation priorities. The WG and other stakeholders will set conservation priorities by focusing on sensitive species, their habitats, and threats to their existence. Once these are identified, a vision of the desired future of the resources within the context of the military mission will be developed.
- The WG and other stakeholders will use the desired visionary outcome as mentioned above to discuss objectives and resulting strategies for resources management. The objectives will be achievable and realistic for the time frame and available budget. They should be based on the principles of adaptive management, whereby management actions are treated as scientific hypotheses to be tested.
- Develop a project implementation table with prioritized ranking of projects and a timeline.

1.9.2 Internal Stakeholders

The following is a list of internal stakeholders and their role in supporting the installation and the development, revision, and implementation of this INRMP. Policy leadership and liaison with non-Navy partners is provided by the Commander, Navy Region Southwest (CNRSW) N40, NAVFAC SW, and NBVC. Further detail on roles and responsibilities is in Section 5.1.1 Responsibility.

CNO—The Chief of Naval Operations (CNO) serves as the principal leader and overall Navy program manager for the development, revision, and implementation of this INRMP. The CNO provides policy, guidance and resources for the development, revision, and implementation of the INRMP and associated NEPA documentation. The CNO approves all INRMP projects prior to submittal to regulatory agencies for signature ([Navy 2006](#)).

CNIC—The Commander of Navy Installations Command (CNIC) reviews the entire INRMP. Their role is to ensure that installations comply with DoD, Navy, and CNO policy on INRMPs and their associated NEPA documentation. They also ensure the programming of resources necessary to maintain and implement INRMPs, participate in the development and revision of INRMPs, and provide overall program management oversight for all natural resources program elements. CNIC reviews and endorses projects recommended for INRMP implementation prior to submittal for signature, and evaluates and validates EPR-web project proposals ([Navy 2006](#)).

Navy Region Southwest— Regional Commanders ensure that installations comply with DoD, Navy, and CNO policy on INRMPs and their associated NEPA documentation. They ensure that installations under their control undergo annual reviews and formal five-year evaluations. They

ensure the programming of resources necessary to maintain and implement INRMPs, which involves the evaluation and validation of EPR-web based project proposals and the funding of installation natural resources management staff. Navy Region Southwest maintains close liaison with the INRMP signatory partners (USFWS, NOAA and CDFG) and other INRMP stakeholders. They provide endorsement of the INRMP through the Regional Commander signature ([Navy 2006](#)).

Installation Commanding Officers— Installation Commanding Officers ensure the preparation, completion, and implementation of INRMPs and associated NEPA documentation. Their role is to: act as stewards of natural resources under their jurisdiction and integrate natural resources requirements into the day-to-day decision-making process; ensure natural resources management and INRMPs comply with all natural resources related federal regulations, directives, instructions, and policies; involve appropriate tenant, operational, training, or R&D commands in the INRMP review process to ensure no net loss of military mission; designate a Natural Resources Manager/Coordinator responsible for the management efforts related to the preparation, revision, implementation, and funding for INRMPs, as well as coordination with subordinate commands and installations; involve appropriate Navy Judge Advocate General or Office of the General Counsel legal counsel to provide advice and counsel with respect to legal matters related to natural resources management and INRMPs; and endorse INRMPs via Commanding Officer signature.

Public Affairs Office—The Public Affairs Office is involved in aspects of the environmental program at NBVC. This includes being informed of the public notice process required in various NEPA analysis processes.

Office of Counsel—The Office of the General Counsel, Commander Navy Region Southwest, provides legal services to NBVC on a variety of environmental matters. Particularly pertinent to natural resources management, is their review of NEPA documentation and legal interpretations involving compliance with natural resources laws as they pertain to base operations.

Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest

Public Works Department—The NBVC Facilities Planning Office, Public Works Department (PWD), is responsible for the comprehensive oversight and planning of all land use issues relating to NBVC. Their role for this INRMP is to provide document review to confirm that this INRMP describes compatible land uses.

Environmental Division—The NBVC Environmental Division (ED), as delegated by command directive, is responsible for the preparation and implementation of this INRMP. Acting through the Natural Resources Manager, NBVC ED is responsible for the management of natural resources as part of the overall NBVC environmental program ([Appendix N](#)). NBVC natural resources staff provides technical support. This INRMP is the direct “vehicle” for

accomplishment of many of the responsibilities of the Commanding Officer (CO) as detailed below.

Business Line Team Leader (N45) — Natural resources business line team specialists (N45) provide technical support and contractual oversight in the development, revision and implementation of this INRMP. In addition, NAVFAC SW is responsible for providing support for natural resources management at NBVC when requested. NAVFAC SW personnel such as the NEPA and INRMP coordinators, have natural resources programming and/or technical support roles in developing this INRMP.

1.9.3 External Stakeholders

As required in the Sikes Act as amended (Section 2904[a][2]), INRMPs are to be developed in cooperation with the USFWS, NOAA, and CDFG. Through a Tripartite Agreement (herein referred to as a Memorandum of Understanding [MOU]) signed January 2006, the DoD, U.S. Department of Interior (USDO), USFWS, and CDFG, have a statutory obligation to coordinate preparing, reviewing and implementing INRMPs. The MOU is in [Appendix F](#). Mutual agreement among the agencies is formalized on the signatory pages at the front of this INRMP. The CDFG is responsible for management of most fish and wildlife in the state. Nothing in this INRMP affects any provision of a federal law governing the conservation or protection of fish and wildlife species, or enlarges or diminishes California's responsibility and authority for the protection and management of fish and resident wildlife. The CDFG and other state fish and wildlife agencies were represented by the International Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies (IAFWA). The desire is for "synchronization of INRMPs with existing USFWS and state natural resource management plans" and "mutually agreed-upon fish and wildlife service conservation objectives to satisfy the goals of the Sikes Act."

The external stakeholders participating in this INRMP are:

- USFWS—Ecological Services
- NOAA- NMFS Habitat Conservation
- CDFG—Habitat Conservation, Marine and Terrestrial

1.10 ECOSYSTEM APPROACH

The DoD and the Navy have adopted a policy of ecosystem-based management for INRMPs. The DoD (DoDINST 4715.03, *Natural Resources Conservation Program*) describes ecosystem-based management as, "a goal-driven approach to managing natural and cultural resources that supports present and future mission requirements; preserves ecosystem integrity; is at a scale compatible with natural processes; is cognizant of nature's timeframes; recognizes social and economic viability within functioning ecosystems; is adaptable to complex and changing requirements; and is realized through effective partnerships among private, local, State, tribal, and Federal interests. Ecosystem-based management is a process that considers the environment as a complex system functioning as a whole, not a collection of parts, and recognizes that people

and their social and economic needs are a part of the whole.” The DoD goal with regard to ecosystem-based management is, “To ensure that military lands support present and future training and testing requirements while preserving, improving, and enhancing ecosystem integrity. Over the long term, that approach shall maintain and improve the sustainability and biological diversity of terrestrial and aquatic (including marine) ecosystems while supporting sustainable economies, human use, and the environment required for realistic military training operations.” The regulatory context and strategies for reaching this goal are detailed in the DoD’s Ecosystem Services Policy (DoD 2011).

DoD and Navy Instructions mandate an ecosystem framework and approach for the INRMP (DoDINST 4715.03 and OPNAVINST 5090.1C, *Environmental Readiness Program Manual*). Ecosystem management in DoD draws on a long-term vision of integrating ecological, economic and social factors. This approach shall take a long-term view of human activities, including military uses, and biological resources as part of the same environment. The goal is to conserve and enhance ecosystem integrity, and to sustain both biological diversity and continued availability of those resources for military readiness and sustainability and other human uses (as defined in OPNAVINST 5090.1C). Managing for sustainability and ecosystem management are approaches that attempt to integrate long-term goals with short-term project lists.

The ecosystem mandate is accomplished by applying principles of sustainable use at several scales—emphases on partnerships, public outreach, long-term monitoring, and adaptive management. Consistent with Navy policy (OPNAVINST 5090.1C and DoDINST 4715.03), ecosystem-based management shall include:

- A shift from single species to multiple species conservation.
- Formation of partnerships necessary to consider and manage ecosystems that cross boundaries.
- Use of the best available scientific information and adaptive management techniques.

An adaptive management approach is a requirement for INRMPs under DoDINST 4715.03, and is defined as: “The process of implementing policy decisions as scientifically driven management experiments that test predictions and assumptions in management plans and using the resulting information to improve the plans” (DoD 2011). Adaptive management occurs through the INRMP annual review and revision process, as described below in Section 1.11. Installation natural resource managers also practice adaptive management on a continual, day-to-day basis, in response to a range of environmental or programmatic variables, which may require a change in management strategy. Adaptive management is partly implemented through the Navy’s Environmental Management System (EMS) to integrate environmental considerations into day-to-day activities across all levels and functions of Navy enterprise. EO 13423, “Strengthening Federal Environmental, Energy, and Transportation Management” (24 January 2007), required each DoD component to adopt an EMS. An EMS is a formal management framework that provides a systematic way to review and improve operations, create awareness, and improve environmental performance. Systematic environmental management as an integral

part of day-to-day decision making and long-term planning processes is an important step in supporting mission readiness and effective use of resources. The most significant resource for every organization is their senior leadership's commitment and visibility in EMS implementation and sustainability. A robust EMS is essential to sustaining compliance, reducing pollution and minimizing risk to mission. The Navy's EMS has a concerted focus on preventing pollution, consistent regulatory compliance, and reducing environmental impacts, including environmental practice for energy and transportation functions, using a "plan-do-check-act" management model (OPNAVINST 5090.1C [Navy 2011a]). It conforms to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 14001:2004 EMS standard.

The Navy commitment to environmental sustainability, regulatory compliance, and mission readiness is implemented on a project by project basis through the NEPA Site Approval and Project Review Board Process (SA/PRB), codified in NBVCINST 11010.1A. All projects at NBVC Port Hueneme must go through the SA/PRB. Projects are reviewed for regulatory compliance by an interdisciplinary team, including members of NBVC Environmental Division (ED). Projects must receive site approval from local and regional Navy planning. The project screening process is a streamlined means for project sponsors to comply with NEPA, and applicable state and federal laws, regulations and guidelines described in [Appendix C](#). This process is further described in [Section 4.5](#), Regulatory Compliance.

1.11 REVISION AND ANNUAL REVIEW

DoD policy (DoDINST 4715.03) requires installations to review INRMPs annually in cooperation with the two primary parties to the INRMP, USFWS and the CDFG. Annual reviews provide an opportunity for the parties to review the goals and objectives of the INRMP, and establish a realistic schedule for undertaking proposed actions. To facilitate an annual review, this INRMP has been developed so that historical data is in the text of the substantive chapters of this document while appendices for special status species allow for insertion of annual monitoring data.

Section 101(b)(2) of the Sikes Act [16 USC 670a(b)(2)] specifically directs that the INRMPs be reviewed "as to operation and effect" by the primary parties "on a regular basis, but not less often than every 5 years," emphasizing that the review is intended to determine whether existing INRMPs are being implemented to meet the requirements of the SAIA and contribute to the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations. The OUSD Memorandum for Implementation of Sikes Act Improvement Amendments (17 May 2005) guidance states that joint review should be reflected in a memorandum or letters. Review documentation and signatures are also required by DoD policy (DoDINST 4715.03).

Recent guidance on INRMP implementation interpreted that the 5-year review would not necessarily constitute a “revision,” that this would occur only if deemed necessary. The Annual Review process is broadly guided by the DoD Natural Resources Conservation Program Instruction (DoDINST 4715.03 [DoD 2011]) and by OPNAVINST 5090.1C, Environmental Readiness Program Manual (Navy 2011a).

The following policy memoranda clarified procedures for INRMP reviews and revisions:

- Deputy Undersecretary of Defense for Installations and the Environment (DUSD [I&E]) Policy Memo 10 October 2002 that replaced a 1998 policy memorandum.
- Assistant Deputy Undersecretary of Defense (ADUSD) for Environment, Safety and Occupational Health (ESOH) Policy (01 November 2004 memo).

The DUSD (I&E) memorandum (10 October 2002 memo) improved coordination external to DoD (USFWS, state agencies, and the public) and internal to DoD (military operators and trainers, cultural resources managers, pest managers). It added new tracking procedures, called metrics, to ensure proper INRMP coordination occurred and that projects were implemented.

The Supplemental DoD INRMP Guidance (01 November 2004 memo) further defined the scope of the annual and 5-year review, public comment on INRMP reviews, and ESA consultation. A formal review must be performed by “the parties” at least every 5 years. Informal annual reviews are mandatory to facilitate adaptive management, during which INRMP goals, objectives, and “must fund” projects are reviewed, and a realistic schedule established to undertake proposed actions. The outcome of this joint review should be documented in a memorandum or letter summarizing the rationale for the conclusions the parties have reached. This written documentation should be jointly executed or in some other way reflect the parties’ mutual agreement. The signature pages should be updated upon the completion of the 5-year review, to validate the management objectives and strategies of the INRMP as current.

According to Public Comment On *INRMP Reviews Legislative Language Section 2905 of the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997* [16 USC 670a note] the Secretary of each Military Department is required to provide the public an opportunity for the submission of comments on the initial INRMPs prepared pursuant to new Section 101(a)(2) of the Sikes Act [16 USC 670a(a)(2)]. The installation shall provide the public with a meaningful opportunity to review and comment on the initial draft INRMP and initial draft INRMP revision (other than minor technical amendments). There is no legal obligation to invite the public either to review or to comment on the parties’ mutually agreed upon decision to continue implementation of an existing INRMP without revision (DUSD [I&E] memorandum, 10 October 2002). If the parties determine that revisions to the INRMP are necessary, but are not expected to result in biophysical consequences materially different from those anticipated in the existing INRMP and analyzed in an existing NEPA document, then neither additional NEPA analysis nor an opportunity for public comment should be necessary. If substantial revisions (“substantial” meaning those which result in biophysical consequences materially different from those

anticipated in the existing INRMP and associated NEPA document) are necessary, public comment shall be invited in conjunction with any required NEPA analysis.

1.12 COMPLIANCE AND STEWARDSHIP CRITERIA FOR IMPLEMENTING PROJECTS

For this INRMP, the terms compliance and stewardship have specific meanings as criteria for implementing project lists. Project rankings are assigned based on whether an activity fulfills a mandatory obligation for compliance with a legal requirement such as the ESA, Clean Water Act (CWA), or MBTA. Alternatively, a project may be considered good land stewardship but is not considered an obligation for Port Hueneme to be found in compliance with environmental laws. Projects with a regulatory driver are prioritized higher than stewardship projects during funding cycles. The budget programming hierarchy for this INRMP is based on both DoD and Navy funding level classifications. The DoD programming and budgeting priorities for conservation programs are detailed in the DoDINST 4715.03 Natural Resources Conservation Program. The Instruction divides programming and budget requirements into two categories: Recurring and Non-recurring. Compliance activities are in the Recurring category and the Non-recurring Current and Maintenance Compliance categories. Stewardship activities are in the Enhancement Actions Beyond Compliance category.

The Navy programming hierarchy is based on DoD funding level classifications. The projects recommended in this INRMP have been prioritized based on the Navy programming hierarchy of Environmental Readiness Levels (ERLs) (Navy 2006, 2011a). ERL 3 & 4 projects are compliance driven (DoD Class 0, I, II) and ERL 1 & 2 projects are under the stewardship category. Section 5.3, Budget Considerations, describes ERL levels in more detail. Funding is routinely programmed three years in advance of project implementation.

1.13 INTEGRATING OTHER PLANS

The INRMP provides guidance and direction for natural resources management activities and provides a framework for plan implementation. The INRMP is consistent with, and integrates other planning documents from a variety of sources listed in Table 1-1. Descriptions of plans are in Appendix C.

The need for the INRMP to be consistent with different planning processes, such as any applicable USFWS recovery plans and state wildlife action plan, is not mandatory (Navy 2006). However, the INRMP must state whether it is considered with these plans. If the development of this INRMP is used to preclude the designation of Critical Habitat for federally threatened and endangered species from the USFWS, an explanation is required as to how NBVC Port Hueneme is participating in the recovery of the species.

Certain related or neighboring planning processes may affect this INRMP, and the WG will assess this Plan's consistency with the plans described below.

TABLE 1-1: VARIOUS PLANNING DOCUMENTS INCORPORATED INTO THIS INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN

Authoring Agency	Title	Date
U.S. Department of the Navy	Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division Point Mugu Sea Range Environmental Impact Statement/ Overseas Environmental Impact Statement	2002
U.S. Department of the Navy	Naval Base Ventura County Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan	2010
U.S. Department of the Navy	Naval Base Ventura County Comprehensive Land Use Management Plan	2005a
U.S. Department of the Navy	Naval Base Ventura County Activity Overview Plan	2006
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	North American Waterfowl Management Plan	2004
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	North American Waterbird Management Plan	2002
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	United States Shorebird Conservation Plan	2001
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	Regional Seabird Conservation Plan Pacific Region	2005
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	Partners-in-Flight Landbird Conservation Plans	
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	Recovery Plan for the Pacific Coast Population of the Western Snowy Plover	2007
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	Draft Post-Delisting Monitoring Plan for the Brown Pelican	2009
California Department of Fish and Game	Marine Life Management Act Nearshore Fishery Management Plan	2002
California Department of Fish and Game	Marine Life Protection Act Master Plan for Marine Protected Areas	2008a
California Department of Fish and Game	California Aquatic Invasive Species Management Plan	2008b
California Department of Fish and Game	Wildlife Action Plan	2007
California Department of Fish and Game and California Environmental Protection Agency	Ocean Action Plan	2004
Regional Water Quality Control Board	Los Angeles Region Basin Plan	1994
State Water Resources Control Board	Marine State Water Quality Protection Areas, Areas of Special Biological Significance	2003

2.0 MILITARY USE AND NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

2.1 HISTORICAL OVERVIEW OF NATURAL RESOURCE USE

The following sections summarize the use of Port Hueneme natural resources pre- and post-Navy ownership.

2.1.1 Pre-Navy Land Use

NBVC Port Hueneme has a rich cultural history, likely dating back at least 7,000 years. Diverse terrain and abundant natural resources provided sustenance to early populations. The Chumash people were among the first encountered by European explorers in the late 1700s. The Ventureno, Barbareno, and Ynezeno, related linguistically and culturally, made up the Eastern Coastal Chumash. By the early 1800s the Chumash population had declined significantly following their recruitment into the Franciscan Missions and lack of natural resistance to European diseases ([ASM Affiliates, Inc. 2010](#)).

NBVC Port Hueneme lands were once part of a land grant awarded to eight Anglo-European soldiers in 1837, the Rancho Rio de Santa Clara o La Colonia. The land was sold to Thomas A. Scott in the 1860s and resold to Thomas R. Bard in 1869. Following the establishment of the town of Hueneme in 1871, Bard constructed a wharf that eventually became the largest shipping facility south of San Francisco. The fertile Oxnard Plain and availability of the port contributed to the area becoming important in the regional agricultural economy ([ASM Affiliates, Inc. 2010](#)).

Additional information on the prehistory, ethno-history and history of the Port Hueneme area can be found in NBVC Port Hueneme's (Cultural and Natural) IRMP for the Construction Battalion Center (CBC) ([Tetra Tech 1999](#)), the *Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan for Point Mugu and Port Hueneme, Naval Base Ventura County, California* ([ASM Affiliates, Inc. 2010](#)), and the *Cultural Resources Overview, Naval Construction Battalion Port Hueneme* ([Wills, C.D. and W. Self 1995](#)).

2.1.2 Historical Navy Land Use

Following the attack on Pearl Harbor and declaration of war in 1941, the Navy was charged with gathering materials and personnel to build advance bases on the West coast for mobilization and deployment of military forces throughout the Pacific. In response to this command, the Naval Construction Battalion (or "Seabees") was formed. In 1942, Port Hueneme was established by the Navy as a large storage facility, as well as a training and staging center needed by the Seabees. Port Hueneme was selected primarily because it had a small commercial harbor that could be used immediately. In 1942, the Navy purchased the harbor from the Oxnard Harbor District and built the Advance Base Depot, Port Hueneme, later re-designated as a CBC. The Advance Base Depot of Port Hueneme was established in 1942 to train, stage, and supply Naval Construction Battalions and to amass and ship construction materials needed to support the war effort in the Pacific. The majority of the physical infrastructure, including 65 miles of paved

roads, was constructed during World War II. Historical fluctuations in the growth of the base occurred in response to increased mobilization activities necessitated by World War II, the Korean War, and the Vietnam War. Most existing facilities were constructed to support these periods of increased military activity (Onyx Group 2006).

Following World War II, action at the base declined during peacetime with resurgence in activity in the 1950's during the Korean War, the 1960's and '70s during the Vietnam War and starting again in 1990 with the conflicts in the Middle East. Additional information on historical Navy land use can be found in the *(Cultural and Natural) IRMP for the CBC, Port Hueneme, California* (Tetra Tech 1999), and the *Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan for Point Mugu and Port Hueneme, Naval Base Ventura County, California* (ASM Affiliates, Inc. 2010).

2.2 OPERATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE

NBVC Port Hueneme encompasses approximately 1,650 acres of flat, mostly developed or paved lands with residential, industrial, and commercial land uses. The 408 buildings on base cover approximately 110 acres (4,627,000 square feet [ft²]), not including family housing. Family housing is described in Section 2.2.3 Quality of Life. All development at NBVC Port Hueneme is associated with the military, and land uses and facilities have most recently been categorized and assessed in the NBVC AOP of September 2006 (Onyx Group 2006). Land uses and facilities are categorized by their mission criticality as Mission Critical, Mission Support, or Quality of Life.

Of the 40 tenant commands supported by NBVC Port Hueneme lands and facilities, Table 2-1 details those tenant commands that conduct activities on the ground or in the Harbor, and have the potential to affect or be affected by natural resources and their associated environmental regulations. The individual missions of these commands guide the activities of the tenants. For information on the other tenant commands at NBVC Port Hueneme, please refer to the AOP (Onyx Group 2006).

2.2.1 Mission Critical

Mission critical lands and facilities are those that directly support the mission of the installation and tenants. Mission critical functions at Port Hueneme are Port Operations, RDT&E, Training, Ordnance and Seabee Operations/Mobilization.

Port Operations: The 108-acre Port Hueneme Harbor is at the southern end of NBVC Port Hueneme. Commercial and military vessels use the port. The Navy controls the northern and western portions of the harbor, and the Oxnard Harbor District (OHD) is responsible for the eastern channel (Map 1-2). NBVC Port Operations control all military traffic, and commercial traffic is controlled in collaboration with OHD (Onyx Group 2006).

TABLE 2-1: NBVC PORT HUENEME TENANT COMMANDS DISCUSSED IN THIS INRMP

Tenant Name	Mission Criticality	Land Use*	Command Summary
Naval Facilities Engineering Service Center (NAVFAC-ESC) Installation Management Claimant (IMC): NAVFAC	Mission Critical	Research, Development, Testing and Evaluation (RDT&E), Port	NAVFAC-ESC's mission is to leverage new and emerging technologies to optimize the Navy's performance of its wide range of operations. They are the Navy's center for specialized facilities engineering and technology. They specialize in products and services related to shore, ocean, and waterfront facilities, environment, amphibious and expeditionary operations, and energy and utilities.
Port Hueneme Division, Naval Surface Warfare Center (PHD-NSWC) IMC: Naval Sea Systems Command (NAVSEA)	Mission Critical	RDT&E, Ordnance, Port	The NAVSEA Port Hueneme Surface Warfare Center Division provides in-service engineering, test and evaluation, and integrated logistics support for combat and weapon systems installed in the US Navy surface fleet, US Coast Guard fleet, and many foreign navy fleets. NAVSEA Port Hueneme Surface Warfare Center Division's mission is to ensure that warfare systems operate safely for the fleet sailors and are effective in hitting their mark.
Naval Research Lab (NRL) IMC: Office of the Chief of Naval Research (OCNR)	Mission Critical	RDT&E)	The NRL is dedicated to research and education in vibrations, acoustics, structural dynamics, nonlinear dynamics, and wave propagation.
Naval Facilities Engineering Logistics Command (NFELC)/31 st Seabee Readiness Support Group (SRG) IMC: NAVFAC	Mission Critical	Port, Seabee Operations/Mobilization, and Training	NFELC provides management and maintenance of the Seabee Table of Allowance. They provide communication and information technology development in support of the Naval Construction Force (NCF) and Naval Beach Group (NBG), and a variety of sealift support development and products. NFELC develops training curriculums for the NCF and NBG and manages and maintains the Prepositioned War Reserve Material Stock for the NCF. NFELC also provides information technology support to the Naval Facilities Engineering Command (NAVFAC).

TABLE 2-1: NBVC PORT HUENEME TENANT COMMANDS DISCUSSED IN THIS INRMP (CONT.)

Tenant Name	Mission Criticality	Land Use*	Command Summary
30th Naval Construction Regiment (NCR) IMC: 3 rd Naval Construction Battalion	Mission Critical	Training	Commander, 30 th Naval Construction Regiment exercises administrative and operational control over four Pacific Fleet Naval Mobile Construction Battalions, a Construction Battalion Maintenance Unit, and an Underwater Construction Team.
Naval Construction Training Center (NCTC) IMC: Commander Naval Training and Education	Mission Critical	Training	NCTC is a preeminent multi-service training school providing world-class professionals. They deliver to the military engineering forces technically and militarily proficient Seabees, Airmen, Soldiers, and Marines who are ready and capable to operate in any environment.
Civil Engineer Corps Officer School (CECOS) IMC: Commander Naval Training and Education	Mission Critical	Training	CECOS is the pinnacle of professional military education for Civil Engineer Corps officers and civilians. On graduation, each student is ready to assume the challenging duties of a Naval Officer and engineer in support of the Navy's military construction force and shore installations.

Source: NBVC AOP, [Onyx Group 2006](#)

Notes: * Land Use is described according to the 2006 AOP classifications. The most recent revision of land use classifications, provided by NBVC Planning and GIS departments in 2011, are shown on [Map 1-3](#). RDT&E and Port Operations land uses are combined into the Operations land use on Map 1-3.

The entrance channel is 2,300 feet (701 meters [m]) long with the narrowest width of the channel entrance at 330 feet (101 m). The average depth of the harbor is 34.5 feet (10.5 m) at Mean Lower Low Water (MLLW). Port operations comprise approximately 200 acres at the southern end of NBVC Port Hueneme. Total berthing capacity at NBVC Port Hueneme is 4,278 feet (1.3 kilometers [km]) of berthing. NBVC Port Hueneme owns and operates seven wharves, a surface craft berth, a tug mooring dolphin, a launch slip, a Landing Ship Tank ramp, a booster ramp, the San Nicolas Island (SNI) barge and a small craft marina, and Wharf Delta, called “Wharf D” ([Map 1-2](#)). There are no inland ship maintenance facilities at NBVC Port Hueneme. Common operations around all of the Navy-owned wharves include maintenance of ship exteriors, removal of bilge water and loading and unloading of materials.

The port is a crucial part of NBVC and plays a vital role in the mobilization capability of the Pacific NCF units. It is the only Seabee mobilization site on the West Coast.

The wharves at NBVC Port Hueneme are homeport to several RDT&E ships due to the proximity to the NBVC PMSR, and many small craft. The NAVFAC-ESC Ocean Division also uses the west side of the port, Wharf 4, for structural design and testing of underwater constructs

([Tetra Tech 2011b](#)). The NAVSEA PHD-NSWC conducts a periodic program of grooming ships and conducting minor maintenance, and thus requires access to the wharves. Heavy duty repairs are done elsewhere, off-base, as NBVC Port Hueneme does not have a ship yard.

For natural resource management issues, objectives, and strategies regarding port operations, see [Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management; [Section 3.3.1.1](#), Marine Subtidal; [Section 4.8](#), Oil Spill Response and Hazardous Substance Prevention and Cleanup; and [Section 4.9](#), Harbor Operations.

RDT&E: There are three tenant activities at NBVC Port Hueneme that conduct various RDT&E functions—NAVFAC-ESC, PHD-NSWC, and Naval Research Lab (NRL) ([Map 1-2](#)).

NAVFAC-ESC headquarters are at NBVC Port Hueneme, and contain unique testing laboratories and equipment to support their ocean and shore facility programs. NAVFAC-ESC's Ocean Division designs and builds structures to be erected in the ocean, such as piers and underwater tables. The port facilities at NBVC Port Hueneme are critical to support the operation of NAVFAC-ESC's ship Merchant Vessel "Independence" for diving exercises and ocean operations. NAVFAC-ESC uses a seawater desalinization test facility near the harbor entrance for long-term test and evaluation of water purification technologies for government and private industry ([Onyx Group 2006](#)).

At the northwest corner of the base, NAVFAC-ESC operates the National Environmental Test Site with a biodiesel production test facility run under cooperative agreement with a private research entity. The biodiesel facility includes a 10,000 gallon storage tank housed in secondary containment. The entire site is sloped toward a retention area, with discharge controlled by an isolation valve. The material stored is combustible, but not flammable ([Tetra Tech 2011b](#)). Natural resource management issues regarding this facility are addressed under the Stormwater Pollution and Prevention Program (SWPPP); detailed in [Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management.

PHD-NSWC is a major tenant of NBVC, occupying approximately 79 acres in the southwest corner of NBVC Port Hueneme and dependent upon NBVC for the port, utilities and other facilities. They rely on NBVC's PWD to maintain the roads and utilities. Some specific natural resource management concerns, objectives, and strategies regarding RDT&E activities on land and in the Harbor are addressed under [Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management; [Section 3.3.1.1](#), Marine Subtidal; and [Section 4.9](#), Harbor Operations.

Training: There are several tenant commands at NBVC with training missions, as shown in [Table 2-1](#). The majority of NBVC training facilities are located at NBVC Port Hueneme ([Onyx Group 2006](#)). Training land use at NBVC Port Hueneme is segmented into two major areas (shown on [Map 1-2](#), NCTC tenant command). The Seabee Earthmoving Training Area is concentrated at the northwest corner of the base and other training areas are on paved surfaces concentrated near the eastern border of the base in industrialized areas. Training areas are designated for NCTC, 31st SRG, and various Naval Reserve activities. Due to the tactical

training opportunities, enhanced Battle Group interoperability, and use of over-water ranges, NBVC is able to provide superior training to several tenant commands and visitors.

In the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area, Seabees are instructed in earthmoving activities with bulldozers, graders, backhoes, etc. As a result, terrain in this area consists of earthen berms, large open spaces, numerous piles of loose soils and low areas with built-up embankments.

Natural resource management concerns as related to activities that occur in the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area are addressed in [Section 3.2.2](#), Soils and Soil Conservation; [Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management; and [Section 3.3.2.2](#) Coyote Brush.

Ordnance: At NBVC Port Hueneme, the NBVC Weapons program provides support to pier and wharf operations in transporting and loading ammunition and explosives for PHD-NSWC and other transient surface ammunition ships and operations. Natural resource management issues as related to ordnance transport and loading are addressed under the SWPPP (also see [Section 3.2.3.2](#) Surface and Stormwater Management).

Seabee Operations/Mobilization: With assets such as the deepwater port, railroad system, and laydown area, NBVC Port Hueneme has the resources and capabilities to be one of the most effective and efficient mobilization areas on the west coast. NBVC Port Hueneme is critical to the Seabees' ability to mobilize and meet required Office of the Chief of Naval Operations (OPNAV) Time Phased Force Deployment Data timelines. NBVC Port Hueneme also serves to support mobilizations of the Marines and Army. During Operation Desert Storm heavy equipment was transported to NBVC Port Hueneme for servicing, painting, and deployment. The port and extensive laydown areas were used.

The rail system and deepwater port at NBVC Port Hueneme play a critical role in mobilization capability. There is capability for over 1,600 NCF containers and 2,300 pieces of NCF rolling stock to be staged, mobilized, and shipped out of port in a very short time. Approximately 20 percent of mobilization material is received by rail. The rail system and spurs, flanked by large industrial warehouses and laydown areas, run the length of the base to the harbor. This configuration allows efficient mobilization of equipment and material. The NBVC Port Hueneme Supply Department ([Section 2.2.2](#), Mission Support) supports mobilization packing for the Seabees, the Army, Air Force, and Marine Corps units. Mobilization on even a modest scale is likely to include several military service branches, members of NCF, and significant amounts of material.

Navy Facilities Expeditionary Logistics Center (NFELC) and the 31st SRG require laydown to support their activities during peacetime, training exercises, and during mobilization. "Peace time" laydown areas are routinely used as open storage areas, marshalling yards, and vehicle circulation and parking associated with 31st SRG and NBVC Port Hueneme facilities. The largest NBVC laydown area is 256,260 square yards associated with Civil Engineer Support Equipment (CESE) maintenance facilities.

Natural resource management concerns, objectives, and strategies regarding laydown and mobilization areas are addressed under the SWPPP (also see [Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management).

2.2.2 Mission Support

Mission support lands and facilities are those that indirectly support the mission of the installation and tenants. Mission support functions at Port Hueneme include Supply/Logistics, Facilities/SRM, Utilities, Base Services, IT/Communications, Federal Fire, Force Protection, Resource Management, Defense Reuse and Marketing Office (DRMO), and Religious Services.

Supply/Logistics: NBVC's Supply Department provides support to NBVC Point Mugu, NBVC Port Hueneme, and NBVC SNI, and for most tenant commands. They also support the Army, Air Force, and Marine Corps units that may move through NBVC during mobilizations. The majority of warehouses in NBVC are at NBVC Port Hueneme, in the central industrialized area. The supply function provides logistic support for DoD units using the port during routine deployment and during mobilization. To meet the military's needs for rapid mobilization and deployment, most equipment and gear is packed and shipped in large standardized shipping containers by ship or aircraft. Logistic support is provided for the NCF and their home-ported ship which results in large long-term storage requirements for Pre-Positioned War Reserve Material Stock and containerized deployment kits. Items stored include trucks, cranes, graders, excavators, and a wide array of other CESE.

NBVC Supply manages fuel facilities at NBVC Port Hueneme, Point Mugu, and SNI. Since 1997, the NBVC Supply Department has been implementing a program of facility improvement projects to reconstruct and update fuel facilities at all three locations. The only fuel project currently expected at NBVC Port Hueneme involves converting an existing biodiesel tank to regular diesel.

Natural resource management concerns, objectives, and strategies regarding supply/logistics are addressed under other NBVC planning documents such as the SWPPP and the San Nicolas Island Biosecurity Plan, and discussed herein under the following sections: [Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management; [Section 3.6](#), Invasive Species Management; [Section 4.3](#), Environmental Awareness; and [Section 4.9](#) Harbor Operations.

Facilities/SRM: Public Works facilities include facilities for maintenance, automobile maintenance and Public Works maintenance. Public works facilities are generally grouped in small clusters at various locations around NBVC. The PWD specializes in engineering, planning, facility maintenance and management, transportation operations, and utility energy management. NBVC Public Works, led by the Public Works Officer, is responsible for the SRM of facilities that includes maintenance, repair, replacement, and upgrades to NBVC Port Hueneme facilities. Concerns, objectives, and strategies related to natural resources management in the context of facilities upgrades and maintenance are addressed in [Section 4.10](#), Construction, Facility and Utilities Maintenance.

Transportation operations at NBVC Port Hueneme consist of maintaining 65 miles of paved roads and 16 miles of railroad, 14 of which are active. All paved roads on base were constructed during World War II. Access to the base is by four entrance gates located on the east, southwest, and west perimeters. Vehicular circulation is on two-lane roads that run primarily north-south and east-west ([Map 1-2](#)) ([Navy 1997](#) and [Onyx Group 2006](#)).

As part of utility energy management, NBVC was established as a Navy Energy Showcase in April 1995. The goals of the showcase are to demonstrate the innovation and leadership of the Navy in the field of energy efficiency and conservation. The showcase strives to reduce energy use below the 30 percent reduction goal established by EO 12902. The purpose of the showcase is to produce energy cost savings in a manner that can be adapted and implemented by other Navy facilities ([Onyx Group 2006](#)).

The centerpiece of the showcase is the Navy's Energy Demonstration Facility that uses environmentally sustainable building technologies and products, including photovoltaics and solar hot water. The showcase facility was designed to capture 100 percent of the natural daylight and have zero net energy use from the electric utility power grid.

Over time, this program can greatly help the Navy reduce costs. Energy efficient programs help make personnel aware of their energy use habits and lay the groundwork for cost reduction through energy reduction (see [Section 4.2](#), Sustainability in the Built Environment).

Utilities: The following sections summarize utilities infrastructure at NBVC Port Hueneme. Concerns, objectives, and strategies related to natural resources management in the context of utilities upgrades and maintenance, are addressed in [Section 4.10](#), Construction, Facility and Utilities Maintenance.

Electrical Distribution

Electrical infrastructure at NBVC Port Hueneme consists of overhead and underground electrical distribution systems. Electricity for NBVC is purchased from the Southern California Edison Company and Strategic Energy. The overhead distribution system consists of 773 primary poles and copper conductor lines that were recorded to be in adequate condition during a 2006 inspection, according to the AOP ([Onyx Group 2006](#)).

Water Supply and Distribution

NBVC Port Hueneme purchases all of its potable water from the Port Hueneme Water Agency (PHWA), the wholesale provider for the City of Port Hueneme, the Channel Islands Beach Community Services District, and NBVC Port Hueneme and Point Mugu. The PHWA obtains water from the United Water Conservation District (UWCD) and Calleguas Municipal Water District (CMWD). The PHWA serves a population of approximately 50,000, and has relatively fixed water requirements. Its potable water is made by treating UWCD water at the PHWA Brackish Water Reclamation Demonstration Facility that uses three different desalination techniques. CMWD water is used to meet demand, and is obtained from the Sierra Nevada Mountains, delivered through State Water Project reservoirs, aqueducts, and pump stations ([City of Port Hueneme 2011](#)). Currently, NBVC Port Hueneme uses approximately 730 to 900 acre-

feet of water each year. The water pressure at NBVC Port Hueneme is approximately 55 pounds per square inch (psi).

Irrigation water for landscaping is from an on-base well and the UWCD. There is one non-potable water supply well on base, well 22 (State Well No. T1N/R21W-17C03) that pumps groundwater used for irrigation purposes only. There is a pipeline delivering untreated UWCD water for irrigation to avoid using the more costly treated water.

Within approximately 0.5 mile of NBVC Port Hueneme there are 11 active groundwater supply wells tapping into the upper and lower aquifers beneath the Oxnard Plain. Three are screened in the Oxnard aquifer, two in the Hueneme aquifer, two in the Fox Canyon aquifer, and four in the lower aquifer system (Earth Technology Corporation [ERTEC] 1989). Before 1983, 16 additional wells were screened in the Oxnard aquifer near NBVC Port Hueneme. These wells were abandoned after seawater intrusion progressively rendered them unusable for potable water.

There are currently no known drinking-water supply wells developed in the semi-perched aquifer near NBVC Port Hueneme. Few water wells have been completed in this zone because of limited yield and poor water quality (PRC Environmental Management Inc. [PRC] 1995a). The Water Quality Control Plan for Los Angeles Region designates the semi-perched aquifer for existing beneficial use for municipal and domestic supply (California Regional Water Quality Control Board [RWQCB] 1994).

Sanitary Sewer System

All sanitary waste generated at NBVC Port Hueneme is pumped through the City of Port Hueneme's sewer system to the City of Oxnard sewer system. From there it is conveyed to the Oxnard Regional Wastewater Treatment Plant for secondary treatment and discharge.

Base Services: The base services at NBVC are provided by the CO, Chief Staff Officer (CSO), Administration, and Human Resources. Administrative facilities supporting base services and command staffs are dispersed throughout NBVC Port Hueneme. In general, the majority of stakeholders have administrative space in their main buildings. Other larger stakeholders have buildings solely dedicated to administrative support.

IT/Communications: The IT Department currently has space in seven facilities at NBVC Port Hueneme. NBVC IT personnel provide installation and implementation of comprehensive document management systems and the creation of Web-based applications.

Federal Fire: The Federal Fire Department (FFD) Ventura County provides NBVC with fire prevention, engineering and education programs, urban search and rescue, hazardous response, and emergency medical service. They respond to and mitigate emergencies involving aircraft, ships, and structures 24 hours a day. The NBVC Fire Department has an agreement with the City of Oxnard and Ventura County for assistance with fire services. The Fire Department is composed of three stations at NBVC; one station, Station 3, is located at NBVC Port Hueneme (Map 1-2).

Force Protection: NBVC security personnel provide security to protect activities and their facilities, materials, equipment, personnel, and documents against espionage, unlawful entry, and other acts that affect the ability of the command and its supported activities to perform their missions efficiently and effectively. Security personnel operate a 9-1-1 emergency telephone system. Other tasks include providing support to NBVC ED by enforcing sensitive area closures and communicating information on marine mammal strandings or injured wildlife (see [Section 3.7](#)). Other duties of force protection include providing information on all traffic and parking regulations, requirements for obtaining vehicle decals, passes and badges, bicycle registration, weapons registration, and temporary vehicle storage for deploying personnel. The Naval Criminal Investigative Service is co-located with Force Protection. NBVC has an Emergency Operations Center (EOC) to manage disaster response and recovery. According to the AOP, NBVC is working toward a cohesive multi-tenant approach to enhance EOC capability ([Onyx Group 2006](#)).

Resource Management: The NBVC ED manages the Navy's natural and cultural resources through its environmental programs, which include the following: Natural Resources, Cultural Resources, Pollution Prevention, Air and Water Quality, Hazardous Materials, Solid Waste, Hazardous Waste, Site Cleanup, Field Operations, Emergency Planning, Pest Management, and Environmental Quality. Environmental personnel at NBVC Port Hueneme occupy buildings 1428PH and 1430PH and include the following programs: Hazardous Waste Storage Facility, Compliance, Water Quality and Conservation, Planning, and Energy Conservation. The Natural Resource management program for NBVC Port Hueneme is administered from the Environmental Division office at NBVC Point Mugu, Building B632.

The NBVC Recycling Program is administered from Port Hueneme, Building 1378PH. Port Hueneme has recycling offices and fully functional recycling centers. The NBVC Recycling Office assists individuals and activities in developing or expanding recycling programs by offering recycling information, equipment, and recyclable material pickup services.

Defense Reutilization and Marketing Office (DRMO): DRMO provides reuse and recycling services to NBVC Point Mugu, Port Hueneme and other DoD clients in the area from Long Beach to Paso Robles. DRMO is currently involved in a joint venture with a private contractor to reuse or dispose of excess material. Computerized material trading replaced on-site auctions as part of the new Most Efficient Operation (MEO) procedures. The goal of the MEO is to reduce or eliminate DRMO facility requirements by converting to a "virtual warehouse," where items will be shipped directly from the source to a new user. Recyclable electronics, rehabilitated equipment, and scrap metal are shipped directly to new users. This process has reduced storage, facility, and handling costs ([Onyx Group 2006](#)).

Religious Services: The Religious Services Ministry and chapel at NBVC Port Hueneme provides multi-faith religious services and support programs to assigned fleet personnel, civilians, and their dependents.

2.2.3 Quality of Life

Quality of life lands and facilities are those that support the well-being of the warfighter. Quality of life lands and facilities at Port Hueneme include Housing, Recreation/Community Support, Food Services, Social Services, and Health Services.

Housing: Bachelor housing is provided for those who are single or stay at NBVC without their families. NBVC Port Hueneme provides 1,091 beds for bachelor housing. Military family housing is mostly concentrated on the eastern end of the site. Approximately 1,546 civilian and military personnel and their dependents, live on-site in 798 family housing units. Camarillo housing has 315 units and 16 mobile home spaces, on 51.35 acres owned by the Navy ([Onyx Group 2006](#)). [Map 1-2](#) shows the location of housing facilities.

Recreation/Community Support: Morale Welfare and Recreation (MWR) personnel provide a full range of recreation and hospitality services to meet the physical, social, leisure, and mental well being needs of military personnel, their family members, DoD civilians, and other authorized personnel. NBVC Port Hueneme is primarily surrounded by urban development that offers off-base recreation/community support opportunities. Other community support includes educational programs offered through the Navy College Office, Navy College Learning Center and other on-base degree programs, such as the University of LaVerne, Embry Riddle Aeronautical University, and the University of Phoenix.

Refer to [Section 4.13](#), Recreation and Public Access, for additional detail on recreational opportunities.

Food Services: The NBVC Supply program handles food service facilities at the galley. The galley can serve 3,000 to 3,500 personnel per day. During mobilization, the galley must be able to handle a rapid influx of personnel, so it is set up for large areas with expansion capability.

Social Services: Social services at NBVC Port Hueneme include Red Cross, the Fleet and Family Support Center, and youth programs. Services include clinical and financial counseling, transition support, child development and childcare, and CPR and First Aid.

Health Services: The Naval Ambulatory Care Center at NBVC Port Hueneme provides medical services to NBVC personnel, including urgent care, routine outpatient services, pharmacy, physical therapy, psychology, and non-therapeutic activities. The dental clinic offers routine general dental services to NBVC personnel including examinations, X-rays, treatment planning, preventive dentistry, and fillings.

2.3 LEASES AND REAL ESTATE OUTGRANTS

Many portions of NBVC Port Hueneme are used for a real estate outlease program. NBVC began leasing parcels in the mid-1970s under authority of *Title 10 USC 2667*. At the time of writing, eight lease agreements are in place at NBVC Port Hueneme, and comprise

approximately 103 acres of land and port area. NBVC ED manages leased lands similarly to unleased lands: all proposed projects go through the SA/PRB process, which includes review by the NBVC ED Natural Resources Manager and other NBVC ED staff (Section 4.5, Regulatory Compliance). GAPS is the largest lessee and has an agreement that all cars will be removed from laydown areas within 24 hours if a mobilization emergency occurs or if required by the base. Funds collected on leases are used for facility improvements throughout NBVC Point Mugu and Port Hueneme Bases. Lessees assist the base by conducting improvement projects within and in conjunction with their parcels, including traffic studies, pavement resurfacing, lighting, and landscaping. As of 2006, completed lease-related improvement projects were valued in excess of \$24 million. NBVC Port Hueneme is working on providing additional lease parcels while continuing to have full control over the uses of the lay-down areas (Onyx Group 2006).

The Oxnard Harbor District holds a license that allows for up to 25 acres of land to be used. The actual acreage used varies from day to day, depending upon operations of the harbor. The outleased land is used for storage of goods that come through the portion of the harbor owned by the Oxnard Harbor District (Tetra Tech 1999). Oxnard Harbor District has a joint use agreement with the Navy, for use of wharf 3 in times of need.

OPNAVINST 5090.1C requires the Navy to identify areas that may be suitable and available for agricultural out leasing or commercial forestry. More specifically, the Military Construction Authorization Act provides for the use of DoD lands under a lease to an agency, organization, or person for agricultural out leasing or the production of and sale of forest products with commercial value. At NBVC Port Hueneme, there are no lands suitable for agricultural or forest timber production due to its urban setting, developed lands, and limited amount of open space.

2.4 FUTURE USE PATTERNS AND PLANS: THE NBVC PORT HUENEME ACTIVITY OVERVIEW PLAN AND SUSTAINABLE PLANNING AND DESIGN

Due to the largely developed, industrial land use pattern of NBVC Port Hueneme, expansion outside the current footprint is limited by neighboring land use and ownership. Future use patterns focus on maximizing efficiency of existing spaces by upgrading current facilities and infrastructure. Efficient use of existing facilities is identified in the NBVC AOP as crucial to maintaining mission readiness (Onyx 2006). The AOP proposes a land use plan that depicts a long-range framework for development, renovation and consolidation within the existing land use pattern. While the proposed land use plan does not recommend the addition of a large number of newly constructed facilities, it does recommend alterations to present land use designations, renovations, demolitions, and consolidation projects that will help the base maintain mission activities. The demolition of facilities, in particular, creates an opportunity to rebuild in the developed footprint, reducing the need to break new ground (Onyx Group 2006).

The AOP identified a preferred vision to construct facilities supporting new and expanded mission requirements, create more community support to meet facility requirements, eliminate duplication, and reduce infrastructure costs. The preferred vision presents an implementation

strategy for meeting short-term, mid-term, and long-term planning actions for land and facility use ([Onyx Group 2006](#)).

Short-term planning actions are those that will occur within 5 years. These actions consist of high priority construction to meet immediate deficiencies, reuse of facilities with minor to no modification, conversion of Navy owned land into training ranges, leased facilities, and minor construction with few development constraints.

Mid-term planning actions are those that will occur between 5 to 10 years, and consist of projects that typically require a series of actions. Those actions include projects that must be processed through the Installation Integrated Priority List (IPL) and actions predicated on prior planning actions such as facility demolitions or user relocation.

Long-term planning actions occur beyond 10 years, but as they relate to the AOP, are to be implemented by 2030. Long-term planned projects are those that are lower on an installation's IPL than other similar projects, are predicated on facilities exceeding their life expectancy prior to 2030, have significant costs precluding mid-term implementation, or are dependent on the implementation of mid-term actions ([Onyx Group 2006](#)).

Projects recommended for implementation are detailed in the NBVC AOP. They consist largely of infrastructure improvements in existing footprints. The recommended projects are based on the principles of sustainable planning and design, with the goal of implementing strategies for buildings and landscapes that conserve the environment, reduce life cycle costs, increase energy efficiency, and improve the quality of living conditions ([Onyx Group 2006](#)). Operating costs can be lowered by reducing the energy use through high performance building systems, employing renewable energy sources, optimizing solar orientation, and reducing the amount of materials and man hours required for maintenance. Providing good ventilation, natural task lighting and avoiding items that emit chemicals, can optimize living conditions ([Onyx 2006](#)). See [Section 4.2, Sustainability in the Built Environment](#), for detail on sustainable strategies employed by the Navy.

2.5 OVERVIEW OF GOVERNMENT REGULATORY CONTEXT OF NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

This INRMP supports NBVC Port Hueneme's compliance with federal and state laws, such as those related to environmental documentation, wetlands, endangered species, and land and wildlife management. [Table 2-2](#) has an overview of federal government laws and concomitant regulations that must be considered when managing NBVC Port Hueneme's natural resources. This table identifies the federal agencies and applicable laws involved in oversight of natural resource management. Laws may be identified more than once in [Table 2-2](#) if they guide the management actions of more than one federal agency.

Detailed descriptions of the most relevant federal, state, and local laws and regulations that can pertain to projects that occur at NBVC Port Hueneme are in [Appendix C](#). Natural resources

consultation requirements, including any current or planned consultations, consistency with ESA Recovery Plans, RWQCB Basin Plans, and with EFH permit and consultation processes are all discussed in [Appendix C](#).

A Strategic Action Plan (03 February 2005) was developed by the DoD, USFWS and CDFG, for improving the quality and consistency of INRMPs, and ensuring compliance with two amendments to DoD responsibilities under the Migratory Bird Treaty Act (MBTA) and the Endangered Species Act (ESA). The MBTA, as amended by the National Defense Authorization Act (NDAA; 2003 Authorization) for Fiscal Year (FY) 2003, allowed the DoD to take migratory birds incidental to authorized military readiness activities until the Secretary of Interior prescribed regulations addressing military readiness activities. The Secretary of the Interior promulgated such regulations in 50 Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) Part 21. These regulations are discussed in Section 3.4.4 and Appendix I. The DoD will give appropriate consideration to the protection of migratory birds when planning and executing military readiness activities and migratory bird conservation will be incorporated into INRMPs, where applicable, to protect migratory birds. The NDAA for FY 2004 changed the ESA regarding INRMPs that were justified on the basis of the need to promote military readiness while protecting listed species. Under new Section 4(a)(3)(B)(i) of the ESA, the Secretary of the Interior or the Secretary of Commerce, as appropriate, is precluded from designating critical habitat on any areas owned, controlled, or designated for use by DoD where an INRMP has been developed that, as determined by the Interior or Commerce Secretary, provides a benefit to the species for which the critical habitat designation is proposed.

2.6 OPPORTUNITIES

Opportunities, in the context of this INRMP, are defined as areas of NBVC Port Hueneme where there are little to no restrictions on training. The following sections detail internal and external opportunities at NBVC Port Hueneme. Opportunities are displayed on [Map 2-1](#).

2.6.1 Internal Opportunities

The AOP identified existing opportunities for infill development of needed facilities near the railroad tracks in the central portion of NBVC Port Hueneme. Infill development in this area would be compatible with surrounding land uses ([Onyx Group 2006](#)).

2.6.2 External Opportunities

Due to neighboring land ownership and development surrounding NBVC Port Hueneme, few opportunities exist for base growth adjacent to existing boundaries. Opportunities for additional base support functions may exist outside installation boundaries in neighboring communities, such as that afforded by the Camarillo housing development that provides additional family housing.

**TABLE 2-2: FEDERAL REGULATIONS TO BE CONSIDERED IN PORT HUENEME
NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT**

Federal Agencies and Applicable Laws	Authority and Activities
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE)	
Clean Water Act, Section 404	Responsible for issuing Section 404 permits for placement of dredge and fill material into waters of the U.S. (up to higher high water line in tidal waters) and into wetlands in compliance with EPA regulations.
Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899, Sect. 10	Regulates construction, excavation, and deposition in navigable waters (up to mean high water in tidal waters).
National Environmental Policy Act	Commenting or lead agency authority for environmental review of proposed projects.
U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)	
Clean Water Act, as amended	Develops Section 404 regulations and may veto USACE Section 404 permits. Regulates waste disposal in coastal waters. Administers National Estuary Program.
National Environmental Policy Act	Commenting authority on proposed projects.
U.S. Department of the Interior, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS)	
Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act	Reviews/comments on federal actions that affect many habitat-related issues, including wetlands and waters considered under Clean Water Act Section 404 and Rivers and Harbors Act Section 10 permit applications.
Federal Endangered Species Act	Regulates, monitors, and implements programs for protecting the ecosystem on which freshwater and estuarine fishes, wildlife, and habitat of listed species depend. Enforces international treaties and conventions related to species facing extinction.
Migratory Bird Treaty Act	Enforces prohibition against the taking of migratory birds, their eggs, or their nests.
National Environmental Policy Act	Commenting authority on proposed projects.
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS)	
Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act	Reviews and comments on federal actions that affect marine fishery resources and many habitat related issues, including Clean Water Act Section 404 and Rivers and Harbors Act Section 10 permit applications.
Federal Endangered Species Act	Jurisdiction over most threatened or endangered marine species.
Magnuson-Stevens Fisheries Conservation and Management Act	Responsible for maintaining and conserving fisheries and rebuilding overfished stocks. Responsible for determining whether projects or activities adversely impact Essential Fish Habitat zones (those waters and substrate necessary to fish for spawning, breeding, feeding, or growth to maturity).
Marine Mammal Protection Act	Enforces protection provisions for marine mammals.
National Environmental Policy Act	Commenting authority on proposed projects.

2.7 CONSTRAINTS

The Navy defines constraints or encroachment primarily as any action planned or executed that inhibits, curtails, or has the potential to impede the performance of Navy activities. Encroachment challenges can include urban development; environmental constraints such as water quality or endangered species; population growth; competition for air, land, and sea space; competition for resources such as potable and irrigation water; and safety arcs and footprints (Onyx Group 2006). The following sections identify potential internal and external encroachments at NBVC Port Hueneme.

2.7.1 Internal Encroachment

Environmental constraints at NBVC Port Hueneme can dictate where and when certain types of activities can occur to ensure regulatory compliance and the long-term sustainability of natural resources on the installation. Constraints can include the presence of listed species, marine mammals, Essential Fish Habitat (EFH), USACE delineated wetlands, and constraints to some activities in the Coastal Zone (Appendix C). There are currently no environmental constraints to military activities, as training occurs in areas limited in natural resources, such as disturbed open space land (Map 1-2). If the needs of the military mission and associated resource requirements change, the potential for conflicts with natural resources could occur in the areas discussed below. Natural resources at NBVC Port Hueneme with the ability to limit activity include USACE jurisdictional wetlands, special status species, marine mammals, migratory birds, and EFH. Areas where activity should be limited are shown on Map 2-1, and the related constraints are discussed below:

- Activities in and around wetlands, and shorelines are limited due to CWA regulations that prohibit fill in wetlands. Activities that could result in a CWA violation include filling, modifying, draining, or construction in USACE delineated wetlands. Any new projects or types of training in or around wetlands, and shorelines, must be coordinated with NBVC ED staff to ensure they comply with all applicable laws.
- Activities that would result in construction in the Coastal Zone and associated Environmentally Sensitive Habitat Area.
- Constraints due to new arrivals of special status species may impact operations.
- Constraints due to migratory birds would relate to any operation that may result in the abandonment of nests from the Brandt's cormorant colony at Wharf D.
- Constraints due to marine mammals (California sea lions) would stem from any Harbor activities near their regular haul-out that could negatively affect them if exclusion from Wharf Delta is unsuccessful. If marine mammals that could be impacted from active sonar are present there would need to be consultation with federal regulatory agencies. In accordance with NEPA requirements, sonar or detonation activities in the harbor would likely necessitate analysis and documentation of potential impacts through production of an EA.
- Constraints due to activities that may impact EFH.

2.7.2 External Encroachment

NBVC assists the DoD in ensuring the conservation and management of coastal and estuarine environments and works cooperatively with local communities to minimize encroachment and ensure compatible land use on surrounding lands. At NBVC Port Hueneme, external encroachment pressures consist of urban expansion, conflicting land uses and competition for port facilities from Oxnard Harbor District (OHD) ([Onyx Group 2006](#)), as described below.

- Constraints due to urban expansion include pressure northeast of the base for construction of a proposed elementary school.
- Constraints due to conflicting land uses from housing communities adjacent to the base, such as the beach community immediately south of Port Hueneme. Constraints have occurred in the past in the form of limits on ammunition handling and public relations and perception conflicts regarding military activities or constructs in the adjacent community's visual corridor.
- Constraints due to competition for port facilities by OHD. According to the most recent AOP for NBVC Port Hueneme, encroachment from the OHD has become an increasingly pressing issue. OHD increased its need for more areas throughout NBVC Port Hueneme and has gone as far as preparing a strategic plan to relieve the base of about 60% of its land for transfer to OHD.

LEGEND		AREAS WITH CONSTRAINTS	
	NBVC PORT HUENEME BOUNDARY		USACE JURISDICTIONAL WATERS OF THE U.S. AND NOAA/NMFS ESSENTIAL FISH HABITAT
	RAILROAD		COASTAL ZONE BOUNDARY
	ROAD		
	USACE JURISDICTIONAL WETLANDS		
	NO POTENTIAL CONSTRAINTS FROM NATURAL RESOURCE ISSUES		
	NATURAL RESOURCE AREAS		

Naval Base Ventura County Port Hueneme
Port Hueneme, California

MAP 2-1
OPPORTUNITIES AND CONSTRAINTS

INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN

GIS Map by ERM - TTEMI Data Source: California Coastal Commission 2011, USACE 2007
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 MAP2-1_PH_INRMP OPPORTUNITIES2_031312.mxd

3.0 CURRENT CONDITION AND MANAGEMENT OF NATURAL RESOURCES

3.1 ECOREGIONAL SETTING

NBVC Port Hueneme is in the Oxnard Plain-Santa Paula Valley, Southern California Coast eco-region (U.S. Department of Agriculture [USDA] 1997). The base lies at the southwest margin of the Oxnard Plain, in the western portion of the Ventura Basin. The Ventura Basin is a relatively broad and nearly level floodplain and river delta formed by the Santa Clara River. The Ventura Basin is bounded on the north and northwest by the Santa Ynez Mountains, to the south and east by the Santa Monica Mountains, and to the southwest by the Pacific Ocean and the Channel Islands (Mukae and Turner 1975). Elevations in this eco-region range from sea-level to approximately 800 feet (244 m). Climate is typically hot and subhumid, greatly modified by marine air (USDA 1997).

The predominant natural plant communities in the Oxnard Plain-Santa Paula Valley have been classified and described according to the vegetation classification system of *A Manual of California Vegetation* (Sawyer, Keeler-Wolf and Evens 2009), and include California sagebrush scrub, Purple sage scrub, and small areas of Pickleweed mat. These vegetative community descriptions are based on “alliances” that are floristic units defined by the dominant or characteristic species in the community. Other alliances in the Oxnard Plain-Santa Paula Valley include:

- Herbaceous Alliances and Stands – California cordgrass marsh (*Spartina foliosa*), Ditch-grass mat (*Ruppia maritima*), Pickleweed mat (*Sarcocornia pacifica*), and various semi-natural herbaceous stands of grassland that include Annual brome (*Bromus daindrus*, *B. hordeaceus*) grassland and Wild oats grassland (*Avena barbata*, *A. fatua*) (formerly grouped as “California annual grassland” in *A Manual of California Vegetation, First Edition* [Sawyer and Keeler-Wolf 1995]);
- Shrubland Alliances – Black sage scrub (*Salvia mellifera*), California buckwheat scrub (*Eriogonum fasciculatum*), California sagebrush scrub (*Artemisia californica*), California sagebrush-Black sage scrub (*Artemisia californica*- *Salvia mellifera*), California sagebrush-California buckwheat scrub (*Artemisia californica*-, *Eriogonum fasciculatum*), Coyote brush scrub (*Baccharis pilularis*), Purple sage scrub (*Salvia leucophylla*);
- Woodland Alliances– California sycamore woodland (*Platanus racemosa*), Coast live oak woodland (*Quercus agrifolia*).

3.1.1 Topography

The ground at NBVC Port Hueneme is relatively flat and slopes gently from the northeast corner of the installation toward the western and southern portions of the installation. The elevation at the northeast corner of the installation is approximately 27 feet (8.2 m) above mean sea level

(msl), and the western and southern portions lie at approximately 5 (1.5 m) and 10 feet (3 m) above msl. The land along the shoreline consists primarily of sand dunes and beach sands forming the southern and southwestern boundaries of the installation.

The coastal area surrounding NBVC Port Hueneme has undergone several constructed modifications in addition to the creation of the Port of Hueneme Harbor and the deposition of its dredge material. Based on historical records, sand dunes have been present in the Port Hueneme area since the Holocene transgression approximately 15,000 years ago. The ancient dune system provided several salt- and freshwater lakes and ponds to support small wildlife, waterfowl, fish, and associated plant species (Horne 1980). The lakes and ponds in the region were drained by 1933 with the exception of McGrath Lake, approximately 2 miles northwest of Port Hueneme. Dredge material produced from the construction of the Channel Islands Harbor in the late 1950s was deposited along the western side of the base. The dredge material raised land levels, filled swampy areas, and separated the Port Hueneme Harbor from the Oxnard power plant canal. As a result, surface soils in the southwestern half of NBVC Port Hueneme are largely composed of fill material from historical dredging. Excavated material from construction of the Channel Islands Harbor and a small off-site trash disposal area, were placed at various locations along the western perimeter of the installation.

3.1.2 Geology

NBVC Port Hueneme is at the southwest margin of the Oxnard Plain, in the western portion of the Ventura Basin, in the western Transverse Ranges geomorphic province (PRC 1997). The western Transverse Ranges is a west-trending geomorphic province in southern California bounded on the north by the Santa Ynez fault, on the east by the San Gabriel Mountains, on the south by the Transverse Ranges Frontal Fault Zone, and on the west by the Pacific Ocean. Several geologic faults are located near NBVC Port Hueneme, including the McGrath fault and the Bailey fault. Major seismic activity has not occurred along either of these faults in recent history.

The Ventura basin, including its offshore continuation in the Santa Barbara Channel, is filled with a sequence of Cenozoic sedimentary rocks estimated to be more than 20,000 feet (6 km) thick. Major east-trending folds and reverse faults reflect regional north-south compression and are characteristic of the basin (Norris and Webb 1990). Unconsolidated alluvial deposits occur in the uppermost 2,000 feet (0.61 km) of sediment underlying the Oxnard Plain (ERTC 1991).

NBVC Port Hueneme contains coastline in the Santa Barbara littoral cell, a 94-mile length of California coastline that extends from the mouth of the Santa Maria River, passes around Point Conception, and terminates at Point Mugu, where sediment drops off into the Mugu Submarine Canyon. Coastline along this stretch is largely composed of bluff-backed beaches perched on bedrock shore platforms. There are a few dune-backed beaches that formed near ephemeral creeks and sloughs, typically controlled by the complex faulting in the Western Transverse Ranges (Barnard and others 2008). Soil maps from 1917 document the predevelopment geomorphology of the area surrounding NBVC Port Hueneme as coastal dune and back-dune lagoon habitats. The Hueneme lagoon was immediately inland of the offshore Hueneme

Canyon. This lagoon was part of five smaller lagoons or wetlands between Hueneme and Point Mugu. Most of the former Hueneme lagoon was excavated to construct the Port of Hueneme, or filled with development ([RJR Engineering Group 2007](#)).

3.1.3 Climate and Climate Change

The NBVC Port Hueneme climate is typically described as “Mediterranean,” due to the influence of its coastal setting, and moist, mild winters and warm, dry summers ([WESTEC and Stollar 1988](#)). Regional climate is primarily controlled by the semi-permanent Pacific High pressure system over the ocean to the west, thermal contrasts between the land and adjacent ocean, and geographic factors. Geographic factors include the change in coastline orientation at Point Conception, gradual curvature of the coastline between Santa Barbara and Point Mugu, and the orientation of the coastal mountains.

The annual daily temperature range is about 16 degrees Fahrenheit (°F), with slightly greater ranges in winter than summer. Mean monthly temperatures range from 54.5 °F in January to 66 °F in August. The warmest temperatures usually occur in late summer and early fall; daily maximum temperatures can be in the upper 80s and low 90s. The extreme maximum temperature of 104 °F occurred in October 1971; the extreme minimum temperature of 27 °F occurred in February 1971 and December 1972 (Western Regional Climate Center [[WRCC 2011](#)]). Monthly mean temperatures are summarized in [Figure 3-1](#).

The average annual rainfall at NBVC Port Hueneme is approximately 15 inches. Monthly mean precipitation annual totals are in [Figure 3-2](#), and average annual rainfall totals for 1925 through 2003 are in [Figure 3-3](#). About 85 percent of this falls between November and March ([WRCC 2011](#)). Summer precipitation is usually in the form of early morning drizzle and typically leaves only trace amounts. Thunderstorms are uncommon at NBVC Port Hueneme.

Surface visibility is often restricted by fog and haze in the early morning hours; however, in the afternoon, smoke or haze transported to the coast from the Los Angeles basin on southeasterly winds frequently restricts visibility regardless of the season.

Low level inversions that limit the height of the surface atmospheric mixing layer occur frequently over the Oxnard Plain. Subsiding air associated with the Pacific High helps to maintain a semi-permanent inversion over most of southern California. Nocturnal cooling and the intrusion of drainage and marine air masses over the Oxnard Plain frequently cause inversions to form within 985 feet (300 m) of the surface.

Prevailing daytime surface winds near the installation are from the west at 8 to 12 knots, and become northerly in the evening hours at about 5 knots. Seasonally, in the late summer and early fall, prevailing conditions are occasionally interrupted for a two to three day period of strong, gusty, and dry northeasterly winds known as the “Santa Anas.” During periods of Santa Anas, relative humidity drops to less than 20 percent and fire danger in nearby brush-covered hillsides rises to extreme levels.

The most potentially damaging winds in the NBVC Port Hueneme area are prefrontal southeasters. These winds typically occur for 15 to 20 days between October and April. Wind speeds are usually less than 35 miles per hour (15 meters per second [m/sec]); however, on an average of once every two years, winds of 55 miles per hour (25 m/sec) may be expected in coastal areas. The duration of southeasters is typically 6 to 9 hours; under certain conditions, when a low pressure center lies to the west, or a quasistationary front is present, a southeaster may persist for up to 3 days.

FIGURE 3-1: MONTHLY TEMPERATURE REGIME PORT HUENEME, 1960-2010 (DATA FOR POINT MUGU, CA; WESTERN REGIONAL CLIMATE CENTER [WRCC] 2011; NOAA 2011A)

FIGURE 3-2: MEAN MONTHLY RAINFALL AT PORT HUENEME, 1923-2003 (DATA FOR OXNARD, CA; WRCC 2011)

FIGURE 3-3: AVERAGE ANNUAL RAINFALL TOTAL FOR PORT HUENEME, 1925-2003 (DATA FOR OXNARD, CA; WRCC 2011)

Climate change and sea level rise have potential to impact NBVC Port Hueneme facilities, infrastructure and natural resources. The Navy has not conducted a formal climate change vulnerability assessment for NBVC Port Hueneme, but numerous scientific models have been created that focus on the effects of climate change and sea level rise in different scenarios. Based on historical trends, there is general agreement that temperatures and climatic variability will increase, but there is less agreement on projections of precipitation trends (Lawson et. al. 2010). Under medium- to medium-high greenhouse gas emissions models, msl is expected to rise 1.0 to 1.4 m by the year 2100 (Heberger and others 2009).

Based on modeling conducted by the Pacific Institute's California Climate Change Center, at a 1.0 and 1.4 m sea level rise, the western half of NBVC Port Hueneme would be at risk for flooding (http://www.pacinst.org/reports/sea_level_rise/gmap.html). Flood delineations under those scenarios are similar to the Federal Emergency Management Agency 100-year flood zone (Map 3-1). Existing drainage channels are designed to handle flood flows from surrounding overland runoff. The tide gate at the intersection of the Pennsylvania Road Channel and Pleasant Valley Road Channel prevents tidal water from backing up into the drainage channels. At current sea levels, when extreme high tides coincide with a major storm, flooding can occur in the drainage channels at the western portion of the base (Section 3.2.3.2, Surface and Stormwater Management). If climate change results in increased storm intensity coupled with predicted sea rise, NBVC Port Hueneme infrastructure and resource areas may be threatened by flooding and erosion.

LEGEND

- NBVC PORT HUENEME BOUNDARY
- RAILROAD
- ROAD
- SURFACE DRAINAGE DIRECTION
- DRAINAGE AREA
- BUILDING
- SURFACE WATER DITCH AND OR WATER

- TSUNAMI INUNDATION LINE FROM ESTIMATED 10M WAVE
- FEMA 100 YEAR FLOOD ZONE

Naval Base Ventura County Port Hueneme
Port Hueneme, California

**MAP 3-1
STORM DRAINAGE**

INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN

GIS Map by ERM - TTEMI Data Source: Navy 2011b and TetraTech Databases
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MAP3-1_PH_INRMP_IRP_STORM_DRAINAGE_031312.mxd

Based on various projections of greenhouse gas emissions, and different scenarios of rainfall and temperature, research has shown that the NBVC Port Hueneme region will likely experience a decrease in plant diversity, with regional reductions in endemic species' geographic ranges (Loarie et.al. 2008). Mediterranean ecosystems are among the highest in species richness and endemism globally, and also among the most sensitive to climate and land-use change. The natural areas at NBVC Port Hueneme are currently challenged by loss and fragmentation, with little room for species adaptation and dispersal. The effects of climate change may further challenge these areas, reducing their habitat value for other species, or effects may result in habitat conversion. If climate change translates to drier conditions, then wetland habitats could shrink in size, or convert to saltmarsh, depending on whether tidal inputs extend to the 23rd Avenue wetland area.

Specific Concerns

- A climate change vulnerability assessment has not been conducted for NBVC Port Hueneme.
- Infrastructure and resources could be at risk of flooding, based on predictions of sea-level rise.
- Shifts in plant species distributions will likely occur, based on current models. The developed nature of NBVC Port Hueneme and small size of remaining habitats would limit the ability for species to adapt and disperse on a local scale. On a larger geographic scale, shifts that occur at NBVC Port Hueneme would result in minimal impacts on the survivorship of regional populations.
- NBVC Port Hueneme lacks the open spaces necessary to accommodate for species and habitat shifts.

Current Management

This issue is currently not managed.

Assessment of Current Management

An analysis of facilities vulnerable to a rise in sea level should be conducted for NBVC Port Hueneme. Based on outcomes of models, adaptation strategies and implementation budgets should be developed and planned for, as facilities will likely require protection and/or alteration.

Climate change strategies detailed in Population Vulnerability Assessments or Landscape Conservation Cooperatives will likely have little influence on the management of natural resources at NBVC Port Hueneme, due to the limited amount of natural habitat and resources at the installation. Sea level rise models and evaluation should consider the potential impacts to IRP sites and water quality. Areas within base boundaries where storm and ocean waters could be absorbed need evaluation. Adaptation strategies developed in response to sea level rise,

should take into account the value and function of wetlands in mitigating flood waters and improving water quality. A primary function of wetlands is their ability to absorb and store flood waters, for groundwater recharge or evaporation. Open spaces, natural areas, existing drainage channels, and unused hardscape should be examined for potential creation of suitable areas for surface water storage and percolation, or drainage. Existing drainage channels and site hydrology should be examined for areas where improvements could be made to accommodate greater drainage.

Management Strategy

Objective: Manage NBVC Port Hueneme natural areas to minimize impacts of climate change and sea level rise.

- I. Collaborate with regulatory agencies, Oxnard Harbor District, NBVC Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation, and Liability Act (CERCLA) program, NBVC Water Quality Division, Planning, Public Works, and other relevant regional planning entities, to develop strategies to protect and adaptively manage base resources in a manner consistent with regional coastal plans.
 - A. Adaptation strategies should align with the natural resources management goals described in this INRMP, and satisfy state and federal regulatory requirements.

3.2 PHYSICAL CONDITIONS AND MANAGING THE PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL ENVIRONMENT

The management of air, soil and water resources is discussed in the following sections.

3.2.1 Air Quality

Specific Concerns

Currently, there are no specific concerns about air quality and the effects of air quality on natural resources management.

Current Management

The federal Clean Air Act (CAA), as amended, requires each state to develop, adopt, and implement a State Implementation Plan (SIP) to achieve, maintain, and enforce federal air quality standards throughout the state. The SIP documents are developed on a pollutant-by-pollutant basis whenever one or more air quality standards are being violated. Areas that violate a federal air quality standard are designated as nonattainment; areas that comply with federal air quality standards are designated as attainment areas; areas that have been reclassified from nonattainment to attainment are designated as attainment/maintenance areas. Areas that lack monitoring data to demonstrate attainment or nonattainment status are designated as unclassified areas and are treated as attainment areas for various regulatory purposes.

Section 176(c) of the CAA, USC § 7506(c), requires federal agencies to ensure that actions undertaken in nonattainment or maintenance areas are consistent with the CAA and with federally enforceable air quality management plans. The EPA has promulgated separate rules that establish conformity analysis procedures for transportation-related actions and for other (general) federal agency actions. The EPA general conformity rule applies to federal actions occurring in nonattainment or maintenance areas when the total direct and indirect emissions of nonattainment pollutants (or their precursors) exceed specified thresholds.

The CAA conformity guidelines apply to the NBVC Port Hueneme because it is in a nonattainment part of Ventura County. The EPA and the State of California have designated Ventura County to be a serious nonattainment area for ozone. This means any federal action that results in emissions greater than 50 tons per year for ozone pre-cursors (oxides of nitrogen and reactive organic compounds) will be subject to a Conformity Determination per EPA guidelines. Any project emissions less than the 50 tons per year threshold are considered de minimis and a Record of Non Applicability of Federal Conformity requirements must be prepared.

The federal CAA authorizes the EPA to establish national ambient air quality standards (NAAQS) to protect public health and welfare. NAAQSs have been adopted for the criteria pollutants: nitrogen oxides, ozone, carbon monoxide, sulfur oxides, particulate matter (less than 10 microns in diameter and less than 2.5 microns in diameter), and lead.

The NBVC Air Quality program is managed by the NBVC Environmental Division for all of NBVC including Point Mugu, Port Hueneme, and SNI. NBVC has been issued three Title V federal operating permits by the Ventura County Air Pollution Control District, one each for Point Mugu, Port Hueneme, and San Nicolas Island. Each permit includes various equipment or operations listed that result in emissions of criteria pollutants. NBVC is required to provide Annual Compliance Certification for each of the three Title V permits. For permitting new equipment, emission offsets must be provided due to Ventura County's nonattainment status for ozone. In lieu of emission offsets, emission reduction credits may be purchased from the market and provided as emission offsets to permit a new piece of equipment.

Assessment of Current Management

The NBVC Air Quality program effectively addresses emissions monitoring and regulatory compliance.

Management Strategy

No strategies are needed due to the lack of NBVC ED management responsibilities.

3.2.2 Soils and Soil Conservation

The soils at NBVC Port Hueneme are represented, in part, by the soils of the Camarillo, Hueneme, and Pacheco series. The soils consist of relatively level, deep, poorly drained, loamy sands to silty clay loams ([SCS and Landau Associates 1985](#)). Camarillo Series soils are typified

by poorly drained sandy loams approximately 5 feet (1.5 m) thick or thicker. Hueneme Series soils are generally located in shoreline areas with slopes of 0 to 5 percent. Pacheco Series soils consist of poorly drained, silty clay loam, and are similar in thickness and topographic settings to that of Camarillo and Hueneme series soils ([SCS and Landau Associates 1985](#)).

Two additional surface soil types appear near NBVC Port Hueneme. Coastal Soils occur in narrow sand beaches and dunes adjacent to NBVC Port Hueneme. Drainage from these soils ranges from very poor to good, and permeability is generally high. Fill material characterizes the surficial soils in the southwestern half of the installation. In some portions of this area, the fill material was mechanically compacted. Some of the imported material consists of dredge material, but may also contain boulders, concrete, asphalt, demolition debris, and soil from local borrow sources. Although permeability and infiltration rates may vary, drainage of fill material is generally poor ([The Earth Resources Corporation 1987](#)).

Specific Concerns

- Erosion from land use practices at the training area could threaten the integrity of adjacent natural wetland habitat.
- Maintenance activities in drainage channels for flood control may cause unnecessary soil loss.
- Erosion control measures may be eliminated from projects as a cost-cutting measure.

Current Management

Federal agencies must manage lands to control and prevent soil erosion and conserve natural resources by conducting surveys and implementing soil conservation measures. The SAIA, the CWA, DoDINST 4715.03, and OPNAVINST 5090.1C require best management practices (BMP) for soil and water resources on federal lands. The CAA also restricts particulate matter emissions that result from soil disturbance.

Any project that may disturb the soil must go through a screening process with the SA/PRB, to receive a site approval from local and regional Navy. This includes any soil disturbing activities such as digging, grading, stockpiling, dumping, staging, or establishing a laydown area. As necessary, BMPs are required to protect the soil from erosion by wind and water. This project screening process is a streamlined means for project sponsors to comply with NEPA, and the laws, regulations and guidelines described above.

BMPs are implemented in the drainage channels and are described in the NBVC Port Hueneme SWPPP ([Jonas 2010](#)). In drainage channels where heavy rain storms produce erosion of soil into the channel, erosion control blankets are installed to reduce sediment entering the channels and to improve slope stability. Hydroseeding is used to stabilize severely eroded channel banks. The

drainage channels and culverts are frequently inspected to ensure that all BMPs in the facility SWPPP are implemented.

The drainage channels are part of the CERCLA program and listed as IRP Site 19A. As a CERCLA site, no disturbance or reconstruction of the ditches is allowed until the CERCLA process is completed. Details regarding Site 19A are discussed in [Section 4.7](#), Remediation of Contaminated Media.

Assessment of Current Management at NBVC Port Hueneme

Soil conservation is needed to provide the ecological structure necessary for terrestrial habitats and communities to function and perform the ecosystem services that support the Navy's current use of NBVC Port Hueneme. The threshold beyond which an area loses its capability to sustain its original training load is loosely termed the carrying capacity. Protection of soil and water resources will protect the capacity of the ecosystem to recover from disturbance, and sustain its natural carrying capacity to support plants and animals and provide a realistic training environment. Soil surface stabilization is needed to minimize erosion, and maximize opportunities for soils to self-stabilize after disturbance. Water supply, natural hydrologic processes, and water quality are essential to most ecological functions including recoverability from disturbance.

Implementation of NBVCINST 11010.1 has been necessary and sufficient to avoid and minimize impacts to soil resources from activities related to the military mission at NBVC Port Hueneme. The site-specific erosion control provisions and guidelines for site re-vegetation requirements provide the means to control and manage site-specific erosion at NBVC Port Hueneme. Military construction projects and construction training activities that include soil movement (grading, digging, etc.) necessitate BMPs to control soil loss, and better oversight and review to ensure that adequate soil conservation measures are included in the project.

The implementation of restoration recommendations made in the Wildlife Survey Habitat report (The Environmental Company [TEC] 2003), for drainage channels in NBVC Port Hueneme, will ensure the protection and maintenance of soil resources along drainageways.

Management Strategy

Objective: Implement best management practices to prevent and control soil erosion.

- I. Ensure enforcement of the SA/PRB requirements to prevent erosion and repair any damage from construction or maintenance activities.
- II. Use the specific guidance for selecting BMPs as presented in the *California Stormwater Best Management Practices Handbook*, including project planning and design guides, SWPPPs, Water Pollution Control Programs preparation manuals, Construction Site

BMPs Manual ([Caltrans 2000](#)), other specifications in use on island projects, and other proven techniques, with the following strategy:

- A. Minimize site disturbance;
 - B. Stabilize site disturbance;
 - C. Protect slopes and channels;
 - D. Control site perimeter;
 - E. Control internal erosion;
 - F. Add source-control BMPs and treatment control BMPs after construction; and,
 - G. Require reviews of BMPs that involve re-vegetation of slopes, by appropriate staff at NBVC ED, to ensure no non-native species are used. The NBVC Landscape Plant Selection Guide-Approved Plant List is the initial guideline for identifying the appropriate landscaping to be used at NBVC Port Hueneme.
- III. Minimize disturbance by continuing to locate staging areas and construction training activities in disturbed areas only.
- IV. Work collaboratively with NBVC Public Works to develop maintenance practices and BMPs that reduce soil loss and improve habitat in drainage channels, without reducing or impeding channel flow.

3.2.2.1 Shoreline Sediment

There is a small sand beach at the mouth of the Port Hueneme Harbor, south of PHD-NSWC Surface Warfare Engineering Facility (SWEF) (referred to as “SWEF beach”) ([Map 3-2](#)). The length of tidal shoreline in this area is approximately 800 feet (244 m). The beach is backed by concrete beams, riprap, and a pipeline for moving sand past the harbor from dredging activities at Channel Islands Harbor to the west.

SWEF beach may be classified as a low energy beach with a steep face and slope of approximately 1:10. The beach has a southeasterly aspect and is protected from the dominant southwesterly swells by the jetty to the west. As a result, wave heights at the beach are much lower than beaches on either side of the east or west jetties.

Sandy beaches of Ventura County are fed by littoral transport of sediments originating from river mouths in the Santa Barbara littoral cell, and locally, largely from the Santa Clara River. The Santa Clara River is the largest source of sediment in the area, and in terms of discharge of suspended sediment load, ranks the highest in Southern California ([RJR Engineering Group 2007](#)). Calculations on sediment loads of dammed rivers in the Santa Barbara littoral cell show a 40 percent reduction of sediment delivery compared with historical sediment loads, pre-dam construction. Net littoral drift along this section of California coastline is essentially

unidirectional, with sand movement travelling southeast and down-coast ([Patsch and Griggs 2007](#)).

The construction of Ventura Harbor, Channel Islands Harbor, and Port Hueneme Harbor, and private development on the beaches, has had a large influence on the evolution of shoreline in this area. The harbors and their associated jetties act as interceptors to the lateral movement and deposition of sediment along the shoreline, acting as huge sand sinks and depriving surrounding beaches of sand ([Patsch and Griggs 2007](#)). To compensate for losses of sand along beaches east of Port Hueneme Harbor, the USACE implemented the Channel Islands Harbor Sand Bypassing Program in 1960. This program involves the biennial activity of transferring dredged sand from Channel Islands Harbor to the beaches southeast of Port Hueneme Harbor through a dredge pipe that lies underneath Port Hueneme Harbor ([USACE 1997](#)). The USACE conducts soundings of Port Hueneme Harbor every 2 years, before and after dredging in Channel Islands Harbor, to ensure that the pipe that delivers Channel Islands dredge material does not leak into Port Hueneme Harbor ([Tetra Tech 2011a](#)).

Dredging of sediment occurs in the Port Hueneme Harbor. To maintain proper depths for marine vessels and commercial boats to dock in Port Hueneme Harbor, the USACE conducts periodic dredging in the approach channel and harbor about every 6 years. Dredging of the harbor was most recently completed in 2009. Depths are maintained at approximately 35 feet (10.7 m) MLLW along the wharves, and 40 feet (12 m) MLLW in the entrance channel and turn basin. The wharf pilings at Port Hueneme Harbor are designed for water approximately 34.5 feet (10.6 m) deep. In 2009, dredge spoils that were tested and approved for beach replenishment were hydraulically pumped to nearby Port Hueneme Beach on the east side of the channel. Contaminated sediments that exceeded regulatory action levels were excavated and placed in an in situ underwater repository in Port Hueneme Harbor and capped. The remediation project is addressed under Site 19 of the IRP program. Dredging activities are addressed in [Section 4.7, Remediation of Contaminated Media](#).

Shoreline erosion at SWEF beach and the security road east of SWEF was identified in the AOP and previous INRMP as an issue of concern needing address ([Tetra Tech 1999](#); [Onyx Group 2006](#)). Shoreline erosion could threaten infrastructure and facilities with increased risk of flooding and damage. Currently, no shoreline erosion management plan is in place at NBVC Port Hueneme.

Specific Concerns

- Shoreline sediment transport and potential erosion may reduce roosting habitat for shorebirds. Infrastructure installation that could occur in response to shoreline erosion could impact the beach habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme.
- Dredging activities have potential to impact marine mammals and nesting migratory bird species, such as the Brandt's cormorant colony at Wharf D.

LEGEND		HABITAT TYPE	
	NBVC PORT HUENEME BOUNDARY		ANNUAL GRASSLAND
	RAILROAD		ARROYO WILLOW THICKETS
	ROAD		COYOTE BRUSH SCRUB
	PACIFIC OCEAN		ENHANCEMENT AREA
	DRAINAGE CHANNEL		DUNE MAT
	BUILDINGS		SANDY BEACH
			SAND DOLLAR AREA
			KELP BEDS - MAY 2008

Naval Base Ventura County Port Hueneme
Port Hueneme, California

MAP 3-2
TERRESTRIAL AND MARINE COMMUNITIES
INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN

GIS Map by ERM - TTEMI Data Source: Navy 2011b and Merkel 2008
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MAP3-2_PH_INRMP_TERRESTRIAL_COMMUNITIES_031312.mxd

Current Management

Shoreline sediment and erosion are not currently managed by NBVC ED. Infrastructure installation projects that have potential to impact natural resources are reviewed through the SA/PRB process.

The USACE conducts sand bypass activities every other year. The USACE conducts maintenance dredging of Port Hueneme Harbor on an as needed basis. Coordination occurs with NBVC ED to ensure impacts to nesting or roosting Brandt's cormorants are avoided.

Assessment of Current Management

The SA/PRB process is effective at addressing natural resources management in the context of activities associated with shoreline sediment and erosion.

Currently no erosion management plan is in place to address shoreline erosion at NBVC Port Hueneme. The AOP ([Onyx Group 2006](#)) identified shoreline erosion at SWEF beach as a problem that threatens facilities and infrastructure. On a regional level, management of shoreline erosion at and near NBVC Port Hueneme remains a critical issue for the base and must be conducted from a regional perspective. Coordination with the USACE is critical in managing shoreline resources at NBVC Port Hueneme. Key considerations for future management of shoreline erosion at NBVC Port Hueneme should include analysis of the impacts that could occur to sensitive habitat and the limited coastal habitats on base.

Coordination should continue to occur with the USACE and NBVC ED to avoid or minimize impacts to the Brandt's cormorant colony at Wharf D.

Management Strategy

Objective: Manage shoreline erosion to protect sensitive species and habitats.

- I. Work collaboratively with NBVC Public Works, NBVC Planning, NBVC Port Operations, regulatory agencies, Beach Erosion Authority for Clean Oceans and Nourishment, and the Oxnard Harbor District, to address shoreline erosion concerns on a local and regional level.

3.2.3 WATER RESOURCES AND WATER MANAGEMENT

3.2.3.1 Groundwater

NBVC Port Hueneme is in the Oxnard Plain, a subbasin of the Santa Clara River Valley Basin. Underlying the Oxnard Plain is a substantial aquifer system that is the primary source of water for the region's population, used for urban and agricultural purposes. Groundwater in the

Oxnard Plain is primarily managed by the UWCD. UWCD oversees groundwater pumping, facilitates recharge efforts, and provides drinking water to cities and urban areas in the Oxnard Plain (UWCD 2008).

The major freshwater resources of NBVC Port Hueneme and its surroundings include the Oxnard Plain subbasin aquifers, an unnamed stream, an overflow pond, and artificial drainages. The groundwater aquifers beneath the Oxnard Plain are contained in late Pleistocene to Holocene age sand and gravel deposits associated with the development of the Santa Clara River, its floodplain, delta, and estuary. The aquifers have maximum depths of 3,000 feet (0.91 km) or more and include five major units. In order of increasing depth, these aquifers are the Semi-Perched, Oxnard, Mugu, Hueneme, and Fox Canyon aquifers. A sixth aquifer, the Grimes Canyon, is beneath the Fox Canyon in the southern and eastern portions of the Oxnard Plain. It is not beneath NBVC Port Hueneme, due to a change in lithology (rock type) (PRC 1997). The Oxnard and the Fox Canyon aquifers are considered the two primary freshwater-bearing units (CA Water Resources 2003).

The aquifers underlying NBVC Port Hueneme can be divided into three systems. The uppermost system consists of the semi-perched aquifer. The Oxnard and Mugu aquifers are referred to as the upper aquifer system. The Hueneme and Fox Canyon aquifers are referred to as the lower aquifer system. The aquifers are separated from one another by aquitards (barriers to water flow) of continuous layers of silt or clay (City of Port Hueneme 1977). Water in the semi-perched aquifer is unconfined and poor quality (CA Water Resources Division 2003). The upper and lower aquifer systems are classified as confined to semi-confined. The water table of the semi-perched aquifer is approximately 5 to 10 feet (1.5 to 3 m) below ground surface (PRC 1995a). Current data indicate that the semi-perched aquifer discharges to the harbors, Pacific Ocean, and potentially the surface water drainage ditches near NBVC Port Hueneme (PRC 1997). At NBVC Port Hueneme, the dominant groundwater flow direction in the semi-perched aquifer is toward the southwest, with a gradient of approximately 0.0005 to 0.004 foot per foot (PRC 1995a). Site specific groundwater flow patterns are locally influenced by tidal effects or proximity to surface water ditches. Monitoring well pairs installed in the semi-perched aquifer indicate a slight downward vertical gradient in the aquifer (PRC 1995b).

Freshwater recharge to the aquifers beneath the Oxnard Plain and NBVC Port Hueneme occurs naturally from precipitation during above-average rainfall periods, infiltration through the Santa Clara Riverbed, and artificial seepage areas in Saticoy and El Rio operated by UWCD northwest of the installation (Ventura County Public Works Agency 1981). The point of recharge is called the Oxnard forebay, an area of the Oxnard subbasin where the aquifer units intersect and confining clays are absent, allowing for direct recharge to the permeable gravel deposits (CA Water Resources Division 2003, UWCD 2008). A more thorough discussion on the upper and lower aquifers is in the previous INRMP (Tetra Tech 1999). For detail on the use of aquifers for local and regional water supply, refer to Section 2.2.2, Mission Support.

3.2.3.2 Surface and Stormwater Management

The primary surface water features at NBVC Port Hueneme include four drainage channels, a tidal channel, wetlands at the northwestern corner of the base, and Port Hueneme Harbor. There are no natural streams on the base.

Impermeable building and pavement surfaces cover most of the base, resulting in a high amount of surface runoff during storms. Surface water flow at the installation is in response to intermittent seasonal precipitation. With the exception of the northernmost portion of the base, stormwater runoff ultimately discharges into the Port of Hueneme Harbor, conveyed through a network of drainage channels that parallel roadways and intercept overland flows. Stormwater in the northern portion of the base drains off-site into Channel Islands Harbor through the Channel Island Boulevard Canal immediately north of the base. NBVC Port Hueneme drainage channels carry surface water through the base from surrounding urban and agricultural land use discharges. The surface waters draining into NBVC Port Hueneme are highly mineralized.

Flood Control

In NBVC Port Hueneme, there may be flooding from overflow of natural watercourses and man-made drainage systems due to excessive storm run-off or high tides. The tide gate at the intersection of the Pennsylvania Road Channel and Pleasant Valley Road Channel prevents tidal water from backing up into the drainage channels. However, when extreme high tides coincide with a major storm, some flooding may occur in the drainage channels. Primary flood areas are in the western portion of the base. FEMA has identified a localized area that is subject to flooding during the 100-year flood ([Map 3-1](#)). The 100-year flood is based on historical records that suggest that a flood this size would be expected to occur on the average of once every 100 years. The 100-year flood area in NBVC Port Hueneme includes the harbor, flood control channels, and beach ([Cotton Beland Associates, Inc. 1993](#)).

Specific Concerns

- Harbor waters are vulnerable to potential degradation or contamination from activities that occur throughout the base, when stormwater runoff is conveyed through the drainage ditches and storm drainage system.
- Stormwater runoff and influx of sediment from erosion has the potential to degrade nearshore water quality. Stormwater management practices that maintain water quality are most important in the interface between terrestrial and aquatic resources.

Current Management

NBVC Port Hueneme is required to comply with federal and state stormwater regulations under the CWA, as amended in 1987 (Section 402 [p]), and the Coastal Zone Act Reauthorization

Amendments (CZARA) of 1990 (Section 6217). These regulations address nonpoint source pollution from urban and stormwater runoff.

Stormwater discharge to navigable waters is prohibited unless a National Pollution Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) permit is obtained from the Los Angeles Regional Water Quality Control Board (LARWQCB). The Navy has coverage under two general stormwater permits: the statewide General Industrial Activities Stormwater Permit No. CAS000001, and California General Permit No. CAS000002 for Stormwater Discharges Associated with Construction and Land Disturbance Activities. It is anticipated that NBVC Port Hueneme will be subject to the Small Municipal Separate Storm Sewer Systems (MS4s) General Permit.

The three main objectives of the NPDES permit program are (1) to identify and correct the sources of pollution that affect the quality of stormwater discharges, (2) to identify and monitor the sources of potential pollution that may affect the quality of stormwater discharges, and (3) to identify and implement BMPs to reduce potential pollution of stormwater discharges associated with industrial activity.

The General Permit for Industrial Activities requires development and implementation of a SWPPP. The SWPPP is intended to identify and evaluate potential sources of stormwater pollutants and to specify BMPs to control these sources and prevent or reduce pollutants in stormwater discharges and authorized non-stormwater discharges (Jonas 2010).

Assessment of Current Management

Under the stormwater NPDES General Permits for industrial sites and construction sites, the Navy adequately maintains the drainage channels for stormwater conveyance and to meet water quality requirements stated in the General Permits. The Navy has a SWPPP as required for the General Permit for industrial sites that is updated yearly. As part of the Monitoring and Reporting Program Plan (MRPP), stormwater samples are collected and analyzed to ensure contaminants are not entering harbors and the ocean. Dry and wet season observations are conducted, as mandated by the SWPPP, to verify that non-stormwater discharges are eliminated and to ensure BMPs are being implemented.

Proposed construction sites are required to be reviewed by the NBVC PRB to assess if the construction site meets the requirements of the General Construction Permit and Phase II Rule and to ensure that construction is not occurring on an IRP site.

Management Strategy

Objective: Coordinate with NBVC Water Quality program to ensure projects remain in compliance to reduce impacts to natural resources.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB process to ensure compliance with federal and state water regulations, to ensure water quality is not impacted from project activities.

- A. Ensure the implementation of BMPs and water quality improvement goals developed under the NBVC Port Hueneme SWPPP and CERCLA program (see [Section 4.7](#), Remediation of Contaminated Media).

3.2.3.3 Jurisdictional Waters-Wetlands Management

Jurisdictional wetlands, as defined under Section 404 of the CWA, were formally delineated at NBVC Port Hueneme by the USACE in 2007, according to protocol set forth in the 1987 U.S. Army Corps Wetlands Delineation Manual, Arid West Supplement, and recent Rapanos Guidance ([USACE 2007](#)). The base has 12.45 acres of wetlands shown on [Map 3-3](#). Jurisdictional wetland types at NBVC Port Hueneme largely consist of drainage channels that empty into traditional navigable waters, and the Arroyo willow thicket habitat north of the 23rd Avenue Channel.

Specific Concerns

- Sedimentation from land use practices could threaten the integrity of remaining wetland habitat on base, altering hydrology and vegetation composition.
- Wetland habitats on base do not all have natural buffers.
- The freshwater marsh North of 23rd Avenue is fragmented by an unused dirt road that presents a source of sedimentation to the two marsh areas, and limits the hydrologic functioning of these wetlands.
- Hydrology of the wetlands north of 23rd Avenue is poorly understood.
- Contaminants associated with IRP Site 19 threaten the ecological integrity of wetlands on base.
- Non-native species pose a threat to wetlands on base, out-competing native species and in some cases, altering hydrology.

Current Management

Under EO 11990 (Protection of Wetlands) and Navy policy (OPNAVINST 5090.1C), there shall be “no net loss” of Waters of the U.S. at NBVC Port Hueneme. Waters of the U.S. include navigable waters and vegetated wetlands.

Wetlands at NBVC Port Hueneme are managed by NBVC ED under the authorities of the USACE and EPA under Section 404 of the CWA (33 USC Part 1344), and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act (33 USC Part 403). Ancillary authorities include the USFWS, NOAA-NMFS, LARWQCB and the Category Coastal Commission (CCC) ([Appendix C](#)). The USFWS and NMFS, pursuant to the Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act, may review federal and federally permitted projects and require project conditions or mitigations to minimize impacts to

fish and wildlife. The RWQCB, under Section 401 of the CWA, has the authority to review permits that may authorize dredge or fill to waters under state jurisdiction. Under authority of the California Coastal Act (CCA) and the federal Coastal Zone Management Act (CZMA) (16 USC Section 1451), the CCC has jurisdiction over permits for development in the coastal zone in wetlands, tidelands, submerged lands (below mean low tide), beaches, estuaries, riparian habitat, streams and public trust lands (see [Section 4.5](#) and [Appendix C](#)).

In the Port of Hueneme Harbor, Section 404 jurisdiction extends to the high tide line and Section 10 jurisdiction extends to the mean high water mark. Any action that could affect wetlands on base requires environmental review. Placement of fill, discharge of material of any kind, or movement of earth, is prohibited unless under permit from the USACE. If it is demonstrated that impacts to wetlands are unavoidable, then mitigation is required. Loss of wetland function is to be mitigated through wetlands enhancement, restoration, or creation.

Maintenance activities in the drainage channels are conducted by NBVC PWD to improve flood control and involve regular herbicide application to wetland vegetation, and mechanical clearing of sediment as needed.

Projects that could result in conveyance of sediment to wetlands are managed through the SA/PRB.

Assessment of Current Management

Wetlands on base were delineated in 2007 by the USACE ([Map 3-3](#)). A formal delineation should be done every 5 years to monitor gain or loss in jurisdictional acreage, and to maintain valid delineation records with the USACE and EPA. Wetlands management involves reviewing projects to determine potential impacts to wetlands, conducting formal delineations, preparing permits, conducting routine inspections, and invasive plant control.

There are opportunities for enhancement and restoration that would improve wetland function and habitat values in current wetlands. These opportunities were identified and recommended actions are detailed in the *Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat Restoration Plan (TEC 2003)*, in [Appendix G](#). Recommendations include removal of non-native species and increasing the size and native diversity of vegetative buffers. Currently, there are only small buffers of non-native vegetation around jurisdictional wetlands. Enhancing and increasing the size of the buffers would further protect the wetland integrity from surface runoff and human disturbance, benefiting water and habitat quality. There are additional opportunities for restoring connectivity to two freshwater marsh areas north of 23rd Avenue, that are currently divided by an unused dirt road.

<p>LEGEND</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 	<p>Naval Base Ventura County Port Hueneme Port Hueneme, California</p> <p>MAP 3-3 JURISDICTIONAL WATERS</p> <p>INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN</p>	
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GIS Map by Scott Holle - TTEMI Data Source: USACE 2007
 This map is government property, not to be reproduced or distributed without concurrence from the Naval Base Ventura County Environmental Division.
 MAP3-3_PH_INRMP_WATERS_111811.mxd

Flood control maintenance activities in the drainage channels results in clearing of wetland vegetation, that is a major component of proper wetland function. The *Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat Restoration Plan (TEC 2003)* details restoration practices that could be implemented in drainage channels that improve habitat quality without impeding flood control. No formalized project conditions are in place for activities that result in clearing of wetland vegetation. Wetland enhancement projects could be identified and prioritized for conditional placement on activities that result in clearing of wetland vegetation.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect the natural and beneficial functions of NBVC Port Hueneme wetlands by ensuring no net loss of area, function, or value as required by federal regulation.

- I. Update the USACE delineation boundaries at a minimum of every five years and the GIS database as needed (OPNAVINST 5090.1C; DoDINST 4715.03).
- II. Continue to use the SA/PRB process to avoid and minimize potential impacts.
- III. Prohibit dumping, filling or other contamination of wetlands and Waters of the U.S. Filling requires a permit from USACE.
 - A. Ensure project plans and budgets include BMPs for activities that have potential to transport sediment and contaminants to wetlands.
 - B. Monitor Seabee Earthmoving Training Area and other project sites for implementation of BMPs to reduce and contain soil erosion.
- IV. Enhance and increase vegetative buffers around wetlands, as recommended in restoration report of 2003 (TEC 2003).
- V. Identify and prioritize potential restoration and enhancement projects using survey data available in restoration report of 2003 (TEC 2003), and data from any current surveys.

3.3 ECOSYSTEMS

Much of the habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme is highly disturbed and fragmented into small patches. These natural areas offer valuable habitat to a variety of plant and wildlife. The following sections present a description of natural habitats and species found in coastal, marine, and terrestrial communities. Terrestrial communities are described and classified according to the dominant vegetation community present. Vegetation classification is based on *A Manual of California Vegetation (Sawyer, Keeler-Wolf and Evens 2009)*. The vegetation classification system used in this INRMP meets the standards of national vegetation classification systems, as required by the Federal Geographic Data Committee. This vegetation classification system differs from the habitat classification system detailed on the Navy Conservation Website. The Navy Conservation Website has not yet incorporated many of the California alliances and associations that are detailed in *A Manual of California Vegetation (Sawyer, Keeler-Wolf and*

[Evens 2009](#)). Summary descriptions of flora and fauna associated with the habitats are provided. Full flora and fauna species lists produced from biological inventories are in [Appendix H](#). Special status species documented or having the potential to occur at NBVC Port Hueneme are also listed in [Appendix H](#). Sources for this information include CDFG's California Statewide Wildlife Habitat Relationships System ([Mayer and Laudenslayer 1988](#) [Zeiner et al. 1988](#), [1990a](#), [1990b](#)), *A Natural History of California* ([Schoenherr 1992](#)), various field guides ([Eschmeyer and Herald 1991](#), [Hickman 1996](#), [Page and Burr 1991](#), [Robbins et al. 1983](#), [Stebbins 1985](#), [Whitaker 1997](#)), results from a survey conducted by a private consultant in October 2003 (*Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat and Restoration Plan, Naval Base Ventura County, Port Hueneme Site, California, October 2003*), and a marine biological resources survey conducted in 2008 (*Marine Biological Resources Assessment for the Port Hueneme Sediment Dredging and Confined Aquatic Disposal Project* [[Merkel and Associates 2008](#)]), and ongoing biological surveys conducted by NBVC ED. The survey reports are in [Appendix G](#).

3.3.1 Coastal and Marine Communities

Marine resources in Port Hueneme are described below. Prior to 2008, NBVC ED did qualitative surveys along the shoreline. In 2008, an assessment of in-water habitats using side-scan sonar and imagery provided from a remotely operated vehicle was conducted by a private contractor as a requirement of harbor dredge operations. The 2008 survey report, *Marine Biological Resources Assessment for the Port Hueneme Sediment Dredging and Confined Aquatic Disposal Project* ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#)) is provided in [Appendix G](#).

3.3.1.1 Marine Subtidal

Port Hueneme Harbor is bounded by pile-supported shipping piers and sheet pile walls, with some areas of riprap shoreline that include jetties along the entrance to the Port. The depth of water in the harbor ranges from -36 feet to -46 feet (-11 to -14 m) MLLW, with shallower areas at the corners of the entrance jetties that range from 0 to -16.4 feet (0 to -5 m) MLLW. The substrate is predominantly mud, with occasional rock debris at the base of the inlet jetties and sand along the beaches formed inside of the east and west jetties. Two small intertidal areas are present: one at the far north, and another at the far eastern end of the area bounded by Berths 3 and 5. The intertidal areas are included in the marine subtidal discussion. Harbor operations are discussed in [Section 4.9](#), Harbor Operations. Marine subtidal habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme consists of communities associated with sand, mud, and rock substrates. Shoreline features in the harbor, such as riprap, revetment, and wharf pilings, also provide habitat and contribute to species diversity by providing attachment locales and structure for a variety of organisms.

In the marine subtidal habitat type, kelp beds are among the most diverse communities, providing food and cover for many species of fish and invertebrates. There are 150 species of fishes along the California coast, and nearly all of them can be found at one time or another in kelp beds.

Shallow subtidal reefs inside the breakwater at NBVC Port Hueneme support an abundance of kelp forest habitat, shown on [Map 3-2](#). Kelp beds have been recorded along both the west and east jetties and at the west side of the mouth of the harbor. Kelp bed presence was most recently surveyed in 2008 ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#)). The survey and species recorded are in [Appendix H](#). The survey provided preliminary information on kelp habitat in NBVC Port Hueneme, but was not designed to provide a comprehensive description of kelp habitat. Kelp recorded in the harbor consists primarily of giant kelp (*Macrocystis pyrifera*), with occasional patches of feather boa kelp (*Egregia menziesii*) in areas of shallower intertidal riprap. Drift algae occurs along the soft bottom and consists of species of *Ulva*, *Gracilaria*, *Mastocaropus papillatus* and *Macrocystis*, mixed with ocean coastal species that presumably drift in from outside the port. Invasive non-native Japanese kelp (*Undaria pinnatifida*) has been recorded on docks and hulls of docked vessels at the port. To date, the invasive “killer seaweed” *Caleurpa taxifolia* has not been recorded in the port ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#), [Tetra Tech 2011a](#)).

Pickleweed (*Salicornia* spp.) occurs in the intertidal mudflat areas, but is not extensive, due to the small area of intertidal habitat ([Tetra Tech 2010a](#)).

Fish species recorded during recent surveys in the harbor include topsmelt (*Atherinops affinis*), spotted kelpfish (*Gibbonsia elegans*), Pacific staghorn sculpin (*Leptcottus armatus*), queenfish (*Sepiphus politus*), bay pipefish (*Syngnathus griseolineatus*), and pile perch (*Rhacochilus vacca*) ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#)).

In the harbor, surveys of the soft-bottom habitats in the navigation channels and basins showed signs of burrowing invertebrate activity, but low species diversity. Invertebrate species recorded during the surveys include bat star (*Asterina miniata*), Dungeness crab (*Cancer magister*), acorn barnacle (*Balanus* sp.), black spotted shrimp (*Crangon nigromaculata*), Giant Pacific octopus (*Enteroctopus dofleini*), and green sea urchin (*Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*). The species noted were captured during otter trawl surveys, where they were likely attached to other smaller “substrate islands” in the channels, such as debris, drift algae, or small rocks. A large sand dollar (*Dendraster excentricus*) bed occurs parallel to SWEF beach, in a band extending from -1.5 to -2.5 m MLLW. Several hundred per square meter were recorded during a recent survey of the seafloor ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#)).

Bird species recorded in the harbor and tidal mudflats of the slough northwest of the harbor, include species such as killdeer (*Charadrius vociferous*), lesser yellow legs (*Tringa flavipes*), California brown pelicans (*Pelicanus occidentalis californicus*), and federally listed endangered California least terns (*Sterna natillarum browni*). California least terns have on occasion, been recorded foraging in the harbor. Brandt’s cormorants (*Phalacrocorax penicillatus*) nest along a bulkhead wall of the entrance channel. A variety of waterfowl may be found in the harbor and slough at various times of the year.

Numerous marine mammals occupy or migrate through the waters off the coast of NBVC Port Hueneme, including dolphins, porpoises, whales, and pinnipeds. California sea lions (*Zalophus californianus*) and their pups visit the harbor, along with occasional visits from Pacific harbor seals (*Phoca vitulina*) and elephant seals (*Mirounga angustirostris*). A southern sea otter

(*Enhydra lutris*) was recorded using kelp beds at Port Hueneme on three dates during the fall of 2006 and again twice in February of 2007.

[Section 4.9](#), Harbor Operations, details Navy and commercial activities within the harbor.

Specific Concerns

- Threats to the integrity and biodiversity of the marine subtidal community include dredging operations in the harbor, harbor traffic, rip-rap construction along the harbor mouth and jetties, pollution, invasive species, and potential contaminant impacts. This may affect the distribution, abundance and diversity of marine flora and fauna.
- The integrity of the marine subtidal community is exposed to risks from mission critical in-harbor military research and testing activities. To date, impacts from research and testing activities to the subtidal community have been negligible ([Tetra Tech 2010b](#)).

Current Management

Projects that occur in, or have the potential to affect, marine subtidal habitat are managed through use of the SA/PRB. This process ensures that project impacts to this habitat are minimized or avoided. The Harbor is under regulatory authority of the following federal and state agencies: USACE, NOAA-NMFS, EPA, USFWS, LARWQCB and CCC. The USACE is the primary permitting authority, implementing requirements of Section 404 of the CWA and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act. Any project that has potential impacts to EFH requires consultation with NMFS. The Navy must incorporate into project plans NMFS recommendations for conservation practices that minimize, offset, or avoid impacts to EFH ([Appendix C](#)).

Assessment of Current Management

Though the SA/PRB process is effective at managing natural resources in the context of activities in Port Hueneme Harbor, there may be activities that could occur without SA/PRB review ([Tetra Tech 2010b](#)). Identification of those type of activities and analyses of their potential impacts is necessary to ensure the integrity of the marine subtidal habitat is not threatened.

Shoreline features in the harbor such as riprap, revetment, and wharf pilings, provide attachment locales and structure for a variety of organisms. However, the disposal or placement of this artificial substrate can disrupt or smother benthic faunal communities, and may provide habitat for species brought into the harbor by boats, facilitating the spread of aquatic invasive species. Harbor waters are currently not regularly monitored for aquatic invasive species. Aquatic invasives can be detrimental to the marine subtidal ecosystem. Harbor waters and artificial substrate such as wharf pilings and revetments should be regularly monitored for aquatic

invasives. For additional information on management objectives and strategies for aquatic invasives, see [Section 3.6](#), Invasive Species Management.

It is unknown whether there are potential areas in the harbor that would support restoration efforts for eelgrass or oyster bed creation. Historical occurrence of these species in the harbor is also unknown.

Management Strategy

Objective: Manage for ecological integrity of marine subtidal habitat on base.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to avoid and minimize potential impacts to marine subtidal habitat.
 - A. Ensure project plans include the use of BMPs in accordance with the SWPPP.
- II. Implement protection measures for kelp beds at NBVC Port Hueneme.
- III. Maintain current GIS surveys of the spatial extent of kelp beds within base boundaries.
- IV. Investigate opportunities to restore or create eelgrass and oyster beds.

3.3.1.2 Sandy Beach

There are approximately 1.25 acres of sandy beach at NBVC Port Hueneme, at SWEF beach ([Map 3-2](#)), as described in [Section 3.2.2.1](#), Shoreline Sediment. This area is exposed to regular tidal action and has no foredune habitat. Low-energy beaches such as SWEF are typically species-poor. In addition, the presence of coarse sands and gravel below the mid-tide level may reduce the quality of habitat for those invertebrate species typically found in the lower intertidal zones of beaches. One of the most common animals of sandy beaches is the mole crab. Qualitative sampling of SWEF beach has occurred in the past by NBVC ED. Sampling results showed infaunal organisms such as the mole crab (*Emerita talpoida*) occupy a narrow band at the mid-tide level. Cirolanid isopods were present throughout the mid- to upper-intertidal zone. No benthic infauna were found below the mid-tide level. Kelp flies (*Fucellia* spp., *Coelopa* spp., etc.) were abundant in decaying piles of seaweed.

Sandy beach habitat provides resting and foraging areas for a number of shorebirds. Among the birds that occur on the sandy beach at NBVC Port Hueneme are the California gull (*Larus californicus*), Heerman's gull (*Larus heermanni*), ring-billed gull (*Larus delawarensis*), Western gull (*Larus occidentalis*), willet (*Catoptrophorus semipalmatus*), Western sandpiper (*Calidris mauri*), double-breasted cormorant (*Phalacrocorax auritus*), and California brown pelican (*Pelecanus occidentalis*). The beach provides a small amount of foraging habitat for western snowy plovers (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*), but no nesting activity occurs at NBVC Port Hueneme. California least terns do not nest at NBVC Port Hueneme. Nesting colonies of

California least terns occur in neighboring areas of coastline, at Hollywood beach to the north and Ormond and Mugu beaches to the south.

The sandy beach is used as an occasional haulout area for pinnipeds, including Pacific harbor seals (*Phoca vitulina*), juvenile elephant seals (*Mirounga angustirostris*), and California sea lions (*Zalophus californianus*).

Specific Concerns

- Sandy beach habitat at SWEF provides roosting and forage habitat for shorebirds, gulls, and seabirds, including sensitive species, and is on rare occasions a haulout area for pinnipeds. This habitat and the species inhabiting it are sensitive to actions that may result in disturbance, including human and vehicle traffic, construction activities, debris, pollution and erosion.

Current Management

The SWEF sandy beach is a relatively small area that is monitored by base biologists for human disturbance; no active management occurs in this habitat. Access to the beach is restricted and monitored by NBVC Force Protection. In the past, this area has been subject to illegal disposal of dredge spoils, construction debris and litter. Impacts to this habitat from potential construction activities near the sandy beach are generally avoided and minimized through the SA/PRB codified in NBVCINST 11010.1.

Assessment of Current Management

Reducing access to the beach promotes its use by migratory birds and marine mammals, and reduces potential impacts from disturbance and anthropogenic materials. In addition to use restrictions for this habitat, sustained efforts to remove accumulated debris, and continued monitoring efforts will contribute to this habitat's conservation.

Management Strategy

Objective: Maintain and enhance sandy beach habitat.

- I. Protect sandy beach habitat from potential human-induced disturbances by restricting vehicle and foot traffic.*
- II. Continue to use SA/PRB to avoid and minimize potential impacts.*
- III. Work collaboratively with NBVC, base facility tenants, and regional authorities if shoreline stabilization measures are required in this area, to ensure impacts to sandy beach habitat are minimized.*

- IV. Prevent disposal of debris (e.g., construction fill, dredge spoils) on the sandy beach by installing signs prohibiting this activity and informing of the presence of sensitive habitat.
- V. Protect beach from erosion by sand replenishment, beach stabilization, or other means as necessary.

3.3.2 Terrestrial Communities

Terrestrial communities of NBVC Port Hueneme are described and classified according to the dominant vegetation community present. Vegetation classification is based on *A Manual of California Vegetation, Second Edition* (Sawyer, Keeler-Wolf and Evens 2009). The major vegetation types that occur are discussed below and include: Coyote brush scrub (*Baccharis pilularis* shrubland alliance); non-native annual grassland (a shared community type of wild oats grassland [*Avena barbata*, *fatua*, semi-natural herbaceous stand] and annual brome grasslands [*Bromus diandrus*, hordeaceus-*Brachypodium distachyon*] [Sawyer, Keeler-Wolf and Evens 2009]; formerly classified as “California annual grassland”, and herein referred to as “non-native annual grassland”); Arroyo willow thickets (*Salix lasiolepis* shrubland alliance); and dune mat (*Abronia latifolia*-*Ambrosia chamissonis* herbaceous alliance). The discussion provides a preliminary list of species found in each habitat type. Appendix H has a species list of flora and fauna recorded at NBVC Port Hueneme. For additional information on the habitat types, planning level surveys are in Appendix G.

The dominant vegetation types at NBVC Port Hueneme are non-native annual grassland and coyote brush scrub. Coyote brush scrub, a plant community dominated by soft woody shrubs, occurs at the intersection of Track Road and 23rd Avenue near the golf course. Ruderal plant communities are on the northwest portion of the base and are dominated by introduced annual grasses. The dune mat habitat is along the coast approximately 1,000 feet (305 m) west of the harbor along the southwestern boundary. Arroyo willow thickets habitat is in the drainage channels and a ponded area north of 23rd Avenue. Map 3-2 shows the locations of terrestrial plant communities that are in the western portion of the base. The eastern half is highly urbanized and landscaped. Sensitive flora and fauna are discussed in Section 3.5 Special Status Species and Their Protection, and listed in Appendix H.

3.3.2.1 Dune Mat

Dune mat (formerly classified as sand-verbena-beach bursage [Sawyer and Keeler-Wolf 1995]) habitat occurs in coastal foredunes and is regionally reduced from urban and other development. This habitat is characterized by vegetation highly tolerant of wind, sand movement, and an arid climate. At NBVC Port Hueneme, this habitat occurs along the southwest boundary of the base and is fragmented into two areas, divided by the SWEF overflow parking lot. The southern area is southwest of SWEF beach atop the west jetty and the north portion is west of the main SWEF parking lot (Map 3-2). The combined area of foredune habitat at the base is approximately 3.15 acres. Native species recorded in this habitat include sand verbena (*Abronia maritima*), a

California Native Plant Society list 4.2 (limited distribution [[Calflora 2010](#)]) species, dune saltbush (*Atriplex leucophylla*), beach-bur (*Ambrosia chamissonis*), beach morning glory (*Calystegia soldanella*), and beach evening primrose (*Camissonia cheranthifolia*). Non-native species include sea rocket (*Cakile maritima*) and iceplant (*Carpobrotus* spp.). West of the SWEF facility, this habitat type is dominated by non-native ornamental vegetation, invasives, with some occurrence of native back-dune species. [Appendix H](#) has a preliminary list of species recorded in this habitat type.

Sand dunes are relatively low in nutrients and generally do not support multiple trophic levels; insects are typically the most common species in this habitat. Surveys conducted September 14, 2011 in dune mat habitat, confirmed presence of globose dune beetles (*Coelus globosus*), a state-ranked “critically imperiled” species ([CDFG 2011](#); [Navy 2011b](#)). The silvery legless lizard (*Anniella pulchra* ssp. *pulchra*), a CDFG species of special concern, has potential to occur on site, as it prefers areas of beach bur growth. The coyote (*Canis latrans*), red-tailed hawk (*Buteo jamaicensis*), and American kestrel (*Falco sparverius*) are among the vertebrate species that may forage in dune habitat and have been recorded at other habitats in NBVC Port Hueneme.

Dune mat is further described (as formerly classified sand-verbena-beach bursage habitat [[Sawyer and Keeler-Wolf 1995](#)]) in the *Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat and Restoration Plan, Naval Base Ventura County, Port Hueneme Site, California, October 2003* ([Appendix G](#)). The area atop the west jetty was restored in 2008. Disturbance by foot traffic and off-road vehicles occurs in this area. Restoration included removal of iceplant by solarization, enhancement of dune morphology, and re-vegetation with native dune species. Prior to restoration the site was dominated by iceplant, but contained scattered populations of beach morning glory, alkali heath, sand verbena, silver beachbur, and telegraph weed (*Heterotheca grandiflora*). Baseline conditions and restoration are detailed in *Beach Restoration Assessment and Design, Naval Base Ventura County, Port Hueneme, California, August 2008* ([Tetra Tech 2008](#)).

Specific Concerns

- Past dune management practices used non-native species to stabilize drifting dunes.
- Special status terrestrial invertebrate and reptile species occur regionally in dune mat communities. The presence of special status species in this habitat type at NBVC Port Hueneme is unknown and is a data gap for natural resource management decision making processes.

Current Management

Impacts are generally avoided and minimized through the SA/PRB.

The restoration area is managed by restricting vehicle access to the site using k-rail that separates the restoration site from the adjacent road. Invasive plant control and maintenance is budgeted for each year. Surveys for special status silvery legless lizards occurred in September 2011, with

none recorded to date (Navy 2011c). Base biologists continue to conduct periodic surveys for silvery legless lizards, globose dune beetles and sandy beach tiger beetle (*Cicindela hirticollis gravida*).

At the northern portion of this habitat type, the dynamic nature of dunes likely prompted the planting of non-native iceplant to stabilize their movement. The resultant dune morphology is an unnaturally steep, elevated accumulation of sand at the west of SWEF. This serves as a visual shield between the base and adjacent housing community. If drifting dunes start to cross the road, Public Works staff moves the sand back to the dune, or transports it south to the area adjacent to the SWEF overflow parking lot (Tetra Tech 2011c).

Assessment of Current Management

The area restored in 2008 will continue to require monitoring and prevention of the establishment of non-native species, and protection from encroachment by human activities.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conserve and enhance the ecological integrity of dune mat habitat.

- I. Encourage growth of the dune mat plant community and development of natural dune morphology by protecting native vegetation in this habitat type. Native vegetation helps to trap and hold sand on dunes.
 - A. Continue to restrict vehicle and foot traffic in the dune mat habitat by keeping k-rail intact and periodic patrol of the area by NBVC Force Protection.
 - B. Prevent invasion and spread of new exotic plant species, and control existing invasives.
 - C. Continue to use the SA/PRB and ensure that this habitat type is not used for project staging activities.

3.3.2.2 Coyote Brush Scrub

Approximately 4 acres of coyote brush scrub habitat remains on base (Map 3-2). Coyote brush scrub habitat is a diverse vegetation type dominated by coyote brush (*Baccharis pilularis*). This habitat type typically occurs in upland settings, including stabilized dunes, coastal bluffs, open slopes, or terraces. At NBVC Port Hueneme, this habitat type is highly disturbed and isolated. The most extensive coyote brush scrub habitat on base occurs at the intersection of Track 14 Road and 23rd Avenue adjacent to the golf course; the dominant species is coyote brush.

Other species recorded include mulefat (*Baccharis salicifolia*), saw-toothed goldenbush (*Hazardia squarrosa*), laurel sumac (*Malosma laurina*), and telegraph weed. Invasives include iceplant (*Carpobrotus edulis*), myoporum (*Myoporum laetum*), white sweetclover (*Melilotus*

alba), Russian thistle (*Salsola tragus*), pampas grass (*Cortaderia* spp.) and annual grasses such as bromes (*Bromus* spp.), wild oats (*Avena barbata*) and Bermuda grass (*Cynodon dactylon*). A complete list of flora recorded in this habitat type at NBVC Port Hueneme is in [Appendix H](#).

Coyote brush scrub habitats have the potential to support numerous migratory and resident bird species. Bird species recorded in this habitat type at NBVC Port Hueneme include warbling vireo (*Vireo gilvus*), killdeer, mourning dove (*Zenaida macroura*), Anna's hummingbird (*Calypte anna*), Costa's hummingbird (*Calypte costae*), blue-grey gnatcatcher (*Polioptila caerulea*), song sparrow (*Melospiza melodia*), and white-crowned sparrow (*Zonotrichia leucophrys*). A complete list of bird species recorded at NBVC Port Hueneme is in [Appendix H](#).

Survey data from 2002 through 2004 show no observation records for mammals and reptiles within coyote brush scrub habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme. However, the surveys were general presence or absence and not focused surveys ([TEC 2004](#)). The feral cats (*Felis catus*) regularly observed at the golf course pose a threat to avian populations in the coyote brush habitat. Mammals typically common to this habitat type include coyote, desert cottontail (*Sylvilagus audubonii*) and deer mouse (*Peromyscus maniculatus*). Western fence lizard (*Sceloporus occidentalis*) and side-blotched lizard (*Uta stansburiana*) were recorded during surveys conducted in 2011 ([Navy 2011c](#)). Gopher snakes (*Pituophis melanoleucus*) are expected to occur as they are typical reptile species found in coyote brush scrub habitat.

Specific Concerns

- The integrity of coyote brush scrub habitat is threatened with non-native plant species.
- Updated mammal and reptile surveys would benefit natural resource management of this habitat type.
- Avifauna populations in this habitat type could be impacted by feral cats.

Current Management

This habitat is managed through the SA/PRB. A focused, invasive plant control effort occurred in this habitat type in 2011, with focus on the enhancement of buffers around the habitat. Maintenance-level invasive plant control is scheduled to occur regularly. Base biologists do regular monthly bird surveys in this habitat type.

Assessment of Current Management

This area was identified in the *Wildlife Survey and Habitat Restoration Plan* ([Appendix G](#)) as having the third highest potential for restoration on base, based on acreage, abundance of avifauna, and potential habitat value for other wildlife species ([TEC 2003](#)). This area will benefit from currently planned restoration activities that include exotic plant control and re-vegetation with natives. Other native species that typically occur in this vegetation type and

could be included in the plant palette when conducting restoration include: California blackberry (*Rubus ursinus*), California buckwheat (*Eriogonum fasciculatum*), California coffeeberry (*Rhamnus californica*), wax myrtle (*Myrica californica*), white sage (*Salvia apiana*) and/or yellow bush lupine (*Lupinus arboreus*) (Sawyer and Keeler-Wolf 1995).

Small mammal surveys should continue and reptile surveys could be conducted, adding to the current dataset for this habitat type to aid natural resource managers in prioritizing natural resource projects, and identifying appropriate BMPs for projects that have potential for impacts.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conserve and enhance the ecological integrity and native diversity of coyote brush scrub habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to native species.
 - A. Use species-level information gathered from surveys to guide development of project-specific BMPs for this habitat type.
- II. Implement restoration recommendations made in the *Wildlife Survey and Habitat Restoration Plan* (TEC 2003).
 - A. Control non-native plants.
 - B. Re-vegetate with plant species native to coyote brush scrub habitat.
 - C. Restore continuity by permanently closing the dirt road that runs through the habitat and re-vegetating with natives.
- III. Enhance and increase vegetative buffer adjacent to the golf course, to minimize potential human-induced disturbances to wildlife using the coyote brush scrub habitat.

3.3.2.3 Non-Native Annual Grassland

Non-native annual grasslands are composed of introduced annual grasses and forbs. Native perennial species are sparse in this habitat type. Non-native annual grassland is at the northwest portion of the base in an approximately 32-acre area dominated by introduced annual grasses (Map 3-2). This habitat type occurs in IRP Site 14, which was graded and re-seeded with fast-growing annuals to combat erosion after CERCLA restoration activities. Non-natives at these sites include bromes, wild oats, ryegrasses (*Lolium* spp.), mustards (*Brassica* spp.), filarees (*Erodium* spp.), and star thistles (*Centaurea* spp.). These areas may have historically been occupied by coyote brush scrub habitat. Appendix H has a list of plant species recorded in this habitat.

Bird species recorded in the annual grassland habitat include killdeer, mourning dove, rock dove (*Columba livia*), American crow (*Corvus brachyrhynchus*), red-tailed hawk, and house finch (*Carpodacus mexicanus*).

California ground squirrels (*Spermophilus beecheyi*) have been recorded in this habitat, but the TEC surveys of 2002 through 2004 recorded none (TEC 2004). They may have abandoned the area due to ground disturbance activities, or been eradicated as part of the base pest control program. Feral cats (*Felis catus*) are prevalent in this area (TEC 2003). Mammals common to this habitat include opossum (*Didelphis virginiana*), black-tailed jackrabbit, desert cottontail, deer mouse, California pocket mouse, and western harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys megalotis*). Reptile species that typically occur in grasslands are western fence lizard and gopher snake.

Specific Concerns

- The large presence of non-native plant species in this habitat type poses a threat of seed dispersal to other nearby natural areas.
- The selection of annual grass species for erosion control is a practice that needs to be addressed for all sites that may require re-vegetation to satisfy BMPs.
- Updated surveys of small mammal and reptile occurrence in this habitat type would aid natural resources management decisions.
- Avifauna populations in this habitat type could be impacted by feral cats.

Current Management

Other than fringe areas throughout the base, this habitat type mainly occurs in IRP Site 14 and is managed under the recommendations made in the *Postclosure Maintenance Plan for Site 14 Landfill Cover* (Tetra Tech 2004), and *Final Landfill Optimization Work Plan, Operation and Maintenance of IR Site 14 Landfill Cover* (Terry Nee and Associates [TN&A] 2009). After CERCLA remediation activities were conducted at the landfill, the primary goal for final restoration of the site was rapid establishment of vegetative cover. Approximately 2 feet (0.7 m) below the surface is landfill cap material made of a geosynthetic clay liner. To maintain the integrity of the liner, roots and wildlife activity are managed to prevent penetration of the liner. Maintenance includes removal of deep-rooted non-natives such as fennel, myoporum, tree tobacco (*Nicotiana glauca*) and tamarisk (*Tamarix sp.*). Invasive species such as fountain grass and fennel were treated with herbicide in 2011. Burrowing rodents are controlled with application of Fumitoxin. The site will be monitored for wildlife activity and maintained for vegetative growth, until at least 2031.

Assessment of Current Management

The plant palette used for final restoration of IRP Site 14 included fast growing species to prevent erosion. Four of the seven species seeded are not native to California, with two of the non-natives listed on the California Invasive Plant Council (Cal-IPC) list as species with moderate potential for disrupting native ecosystems. Replacement seeding or planting should occur to improve the native diversity of the site, provided there are no identified conflicts with mission and CERCLA program goals. It is stated in the Post Closure Maintenance Plan that a goal for maintenance of the site is to maintain conditions that prevent creation of wildlife habitat. Despite control measures, there continues to be a gopher population. The work plan for the site recommends exploring alternative options of rodent control, including the enhancement of natural ecosystem rodent control mechanisms (TN&A 2009). Options should be investigated, including the installation of perimeter perches that would attract raptors. For increasing native plant diversity, herbaceous species could be installed that would not pose a threat to the integrity of the liner.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conserve and enhance the ecological integrity and native diversity of California grassland habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to this habitat type.
- II. Reduce non-native species so they are no longer a significant component of the vegetative community structure.
 - A. Develop and implement restoration goals for California grassland habitat that meet the goals of the CERCLA program requirements for vegetative cover.

3.3.2.4 Arroyo Willow Thickets and Drainage Channels

Arroyo willow thickets habitat occurs under freshwater conditions north of 23rd Avenue, adjacent to the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area (Map 3-2). Drainage channels contain a range of salinity from freshwater to brackish conditions, depending on proximity to the harbor. Drainage channel acreage is approximately 8 acres, and the ponded freshwater marsh areas are approximately 2.2 acres. The drainage channels and freshwater marsh areas were delineated and described under one vegetative community, bulrush-cattail habitat, in the *Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat Restoration Plan* (TEC 2003) (Appendix G). For consistency with the 2003 report and its restoration recommendations, Arroyo willow thickets and the drainage channels identified on Map 3-2 are discussed under the same habitat heading, despite the absence of Arroyo willow, bulrush, and cattail species in some stretches of drainage channels.

The narrow ponded Arroyo willow thicket habitat east of the training area is separated into two freshwater marshes by a dirt road, and contains dilapidated infrastructure that includes two wooden viewing decks and a wooden bridge spanning the marsh. The area is fenced off for

safety reasons. Sparsely vegetated California annual grassland abuts the marsh, leaving little buffer against sedimentation from adjacent land use practices. Plant species include a dominance of Arroyo willow (*Salix lasiolepis*) and narrowleaf willow (*S. exigua*), with California bulrush (*Scirpus californicus*) and broad-leaved cattail (*Typha latifolia*). Non-natives occur at the marsh edges and include fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*) and myoporum (*Myoporum laetum*). A patch of common reed (*Phragmites australis*) occurs north of 23rd Avenue. [Appendix H](#) has a list of plant species recorded in this habitat.

The drainage channels are generally more saline the closer they are to the harbor. Vegetation community composition changes in response to disturbance in the drainage channels from channel clearing done under the NBVC Water Quality Program. Vegetation at the bottom and banks of the channels is routinely manually removed and herbicide is applied ([Woodward-Clyde 1998](#)). Native plant species in the drainage channels under unmaintained conditions include broad-leaved cattail, tule (*Scirpus acutus*), California bulrush, and American bulrush (*Scirpus americanus*). Native species under maintained conditions include species typically found in saline soils such as saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata* var. *spicata*), pickleweed (*Salicornia virginica*) and heliotrope (*Heliotropium curassavicum*). Non-native species that provide the dominant cover under maintained conditions include crownbeard (*Verbesina encelioides*) and sourclover (*Melilotus indica*). Vegetation on the slopes of drainage channels consists largely of non-natives, including iceplant, myoporum and pampas grass.

The Arroyo willow thicket habitat type supports an abundant bird population and provides excellent habitat for other wildlife species. Several bird species use the Arroyo willow thicket habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme primarily for forage and rest, including the great blue heron (*Ardea herodias*), great egret (*Casmerodius albus*), snowy egret (*Egretta thula*), greater yellowlegs (*Tringa melanoleuca*), California towhee (*Pipilo crissalis*), black-necked stilt (*Himantopus mexicanus*), belted kingfisher (*Ceryle alcyon*), red-winged blackbird (*Agelaius phoeniceus*), American coot (*Fulica americana*), and mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*). Black-crowned night herons (*Nycticorax nycticorax*) roost in the thickest and northernmost portions of this habitat type.

The Pacific treefrog (*Hyla regilla*) is ubiquitous in the region and uses freshwater habitat on base. A variety of immature and adult aquatic invertebrates occur in Arroyo willow thicket habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme including amphipods (*Gammarus* sp., *Hyaella azteca*), isopods (Cirolanidae), midges (Chironomidae), damselflies (*Enallagma* sp.), mayflies (*Callibaetis* sp.), skimmers (*Libellula* sp.), and backswimmers (*Notonecta* sp.). Mussels (*Mytilus* ssp.) also occur in this habitat. Copepods may be present in the zooplankton in this habitat and non-native crayfish (*Pacifasticus* sp.) have also been recorded in the drainage channels.

California killifish (*Fundulus parvipinnis*) is a common native species that has been recorded in the drainage channels at NBVC Port Hueneme. Non-native fish have been recorded in this habitat and include the sailfin molly (*Poecilia latipinna*) and mosquitofish (*Gambusia affinis*).

Large- to medium-sized mammals found in the freshwater habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme include the coyote and raccoon. Small mammals that are typically found in this habitat type, but have not been recorded, include the deer mouse and western harvest mouse.

Specific Concerns

- Activities in the training area north of 23rd Avenue pose a threat of sedimentation and conveyance of pollutants to the Arroyo willow thicket habitat. These impacts could degrade water quality and alter the hydrology and vegetative composition of this habitat type.
- The Arroyo willow thicket habitat has small native vegetative buffers, and is at increased threat of impacts from invasive species, erosion, and human-induced disturbances.
- The integrity of Arroyo willow thicket is threatened with non-native plant species.
- North of 23rd Avenue, this habitat type is fragmented by an unused dirt road that could be a source of sedimentation to the two marsh areas, and limits the hydrologic functioning of these wetlands.
- Litter and unused infrastructure degrade Arroyo willow thicket habitat.
- Minimal small mammal, reptile and amphibian baseline data is a data gap that could lead to misinformed decision-making when managing this habitat type.

Current Management

Arroyo willow thicket habitat and the drainage channels shown on [Map 3-2](#) are in USACE jurisdictional wetlands. Impacts are avoided and managed through coordination with NBVC ED and the USACE (see [Section 3.2.3.3](#), Jurisdictional Waters-Wetlands Management).

Projects in areas surrounding Arroyo willow thicket and drainage channels are managed through the SA/PRB process (NBVCINST 11010.0) to minimize potential impacts. Roadway improvements or other projects that could result in conveyance of sediment to these habitats are managed with implementation of BMPs, in accordance with the NBVC Port Hueneme SWPPP.

There has been little invasive plant control in the Arroyo willow thicket habitat, but intensive control began in 2011. Vegetation is regularly cleared in the drainage channels as part of the NBVC Water Quality program. No formal project conditions are placed on this activity.

Hydrology in the drainage channels is controlled by a tide gate (located near the intersection of the Pennsylvania Road Channel and the Pleasant Valley Road Channel) that impedes tidal influx into the channels to prevent flooding of the base ([Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management).

The drainage channels are designated part of IRP Site 19A due to past contamination from spills and leaks into storm sewers on base and current contamination by nonpoint source pollution. A scoping-level ecological risk assessment was conducted during the preparation of a draft risk evaluation for IRP Site 19A that indicated the potential for negative impacts to ecological receptors due to exposure to contaminants in the drainage channels (PRC 1995b). See Section 4.7, Remediation of Contaminated Media, for details on the CERCLA program at NBVC Port Hueneme.

Assessment of Current Management

This habitat type was cited in the *Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat Restoration Plan* (TEC 2003), in Appendix G, as having the highest potential for successful restoration. Currently, only small buffers of California annual grassland and small shrubs and trees exist around the Arroyo willow thicket habitat north of 23rd Avenue, and slopes of drainage channels consist of iceplant, myoporum, and pampas grass. Restoration recommendations include invasive plant removal at the buffers and restoring with natives to increase cover and native diversity of buffers. Wildlife species inhabiting the Arroyo willow thicket habitat north of 23rd Avenue would benefit from planting additional tree and shrub species at its buffer. Hydrology in this area could be improved by removing the old dirt road and re-connecting the split marsh.

NBVC PWD does periodic flood control maintenance in the drainage channels, using manual and chemical methods to clear willow, bulrush and cattail vegetation. The *Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat Restoration Plan* (TEC 2003) details restoration practices that could be implemented in drainage channels to improve habitat quality without impeding flood control. No formalized project conditions are currently in place for this activity. Projects that result in enhancement of existing wetlands could be identified and prioritized for conditional placement with activities that result in clearing of wetland vegetation.

Water quality in Arroyo willow thicket and the drainage channels is currently managed under the NBVC Port Hueneme SWPPP (see Section 3.2.3.2, Surface and Stormwater Management), and CERCLA program (see Section 4.7, Remediation of Contaminated Media).

Management Strategy

Objective: Conserve and enhance the ecological integrity, native diversity and wetland functions of Arroyo willow thicket and drainage channel habitats at NBVC Port Hueneme.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to the Arroyo willow thicket and drainage channel habitats.
 - A. Use species-level information gathered from surveys to guide development of project-specific BMPs for these habitats.

- B. Continue to comply with water regulations as outlined in the NBVC Port Hueneme SWPPP, to ensure wetlands are not at risk of pollution.
 - C. Monitor project activities near or in drainage channels and training sites, to ensure implementation of BMPs that prevent soil erosion into Arroyo willow thicket and drainage channel habitats.
- II. Conduct restoration or enhancement activities as recommended in the restoration report of 2003 (TEC 2003).
- A. Identify and prioritize potential projects using survey data available in the restoration report of 2003 (TEC 2003), and data from any current surveys.
 - B. Enhance and increase vegetative buffers by continuing to remove invasive species and replant with natives such as willows at edges of freshwater marsh areas, and native saline tolerant species such as saltgrass, pickleweed and frankenia (*Frankenia salina*) along drainage channel slopes. Taller native woody species should be planted at edges of buffers (TEC 2003).
 - C. Restore connectivity and enhance hydrology of Arroyo willow thicket habitat north of 23rd Avenue, by removing road that bisects the area if there is no operational need.
 - D. Remove wooden decks and bridge if there is no operational need.
 - E. Remove litter from the banks of the marsh and drainage channels on a regular basis, annually, or after major storms.

3.4 FISH AND WILDLIFE MANAGEMENT

The following sections address fish and wildlife management at NBVC Port Hueneme. Faunal surveys may occur concurrently with other NBVC installations.

3.4.1 Terrestrial Invertebrates

Little is known about the terrestrial invertebrate community at NBVC Port Hueneme, other than observation records of monarch butterflies (*Danaus plexippus*) roosting in eucalyptus trees, and a recent survey record of globose dune beetles in sandy-beach-bursage habitat (Section 3.3.2.1 and Appendix H) (Navy 2011b). Other taxa of special significance include the sandy beach tiger beetle (*Cicindela hirticollis gravida*), a state-ranked critically imperiled species (CDFG 2011), that has potential to occur in sandy beach and sandy-beach-bursage habitat.

Specific Concerns

- No baseline inventory of terrestrial invertebrates has been conducted at NBVC Port Hueneme.
- The presence of special status and non-native species is unknown and is a data gap for natural resource management decision making processes.

Current Management

Terrestrial invertebrates are not actively managed on base. Impacts to the habitats where they may occur are managed and minimized through the SA/PRB. Presence or absence surveys are periodically informally conducted by base biologists.

Assessment of Current Management

An inventory of terrestrial invertebrates should occur in all habitat types. Survey results would confirm the suitability of NBVC Port Hueneme habitats to support these populations and identify the presence of non-native species and special status species. Information on species presence would aid natural resource managers and likely affect how habitats are managed and what kinds of BMPs are developed for activities in their associated habitats. Monitoring populations through time can provide valuable information on habitat function and its ability to sustain a diversity of species.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conduct monitoring of terrestrial invertebrates throughout the base to obtain baseline information to facilitate and guide natural resource management decisions.

- I. Develop community and species-level terrestrial invertebrate baseline information.
- II. Integrate resultant survey data into GIS database.

Objective: Integrate resultant species knowledge into decision-making processes.

- III. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to native species and habitats.
- IV. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.

- V. If non-natives are present, determine their potential for ecosystem damage and prioritize for their removal.
 - A. Include identified problem non-native species in the Integrated Pest Management Plan.

3.4.2 Pollinators

Specific Concerns

The issues that could negatively impact pollinator populations and their habitats at NBVC Port Hueneme are:

- Improper use of pesticides
- Anthropogenic disturbances
- Invasive flora and fauna
- Erosion and sedimentation
- Climate change

Current Management

Pollinators are not specifically managed on base. Their habitats are managed through SA/PRB, habitat enhancement, and invasive plant control.

Assessment of Current Management

Because NBVC Port Hueneme is not currently managing for pollinator species an assessment of current management cannot be made. Assessment of habitat management is described in [Section 3.3.2, Terrestrial Communities](#).

Management Strategy

Objective: Maintain and enhance pollinator populations and their habitats when not in conflict with the military mission.

- I. Inventory and monitor populations of pollinators.
- II. Develop BMPs to ensure that pollinator species are not adversely impacted by base activities.

- III. Identify and develop pollinator friendly landscapes.
- IV. Develop and distribute outreach and education materials on pollinators.
- V. Revegetate with native species on the NBVC Port Hueneme Approved Plant List.
- VI. Control the spread of invasive species.
- VII. Review existing literature on pollinators.
- VIII. Develop and implement a management program that supports bee and wasp relocation as opposed to eradication.

3.4.3 Reptiles and Amphibians

Reptile and amphibian species common to NBVC Port Hueneme include the Pacific treefrog (*Hyla regilla*), gopher snake (*Pituophis melanoleucus*), western fence lizard, common side-blotched lizard, and southern alligator lizard (*Elgaria multicarinata*). Species having potential to occur at NBVC Port Hueneme include silvery legless lizard, a CDFG species of special concern that prefers vegetated sand dunes. Their presence at NBVC Port Hueneme has not been confirmed; they occur regionally and are secretive in nature, typically observed only during targeted surveys. Western pond turtles (*Emys marmorata*) have not been recorded at NBVC Port Hueneme, and are unlikely to occur due to the isolated nature of the wetlands on base.

Specific Concerns

- The presence of special status and non-native species is unknown and is a data gap for natural resource management decision making processes.
- Drainage channel maintenance has potential to impact reptile and amphibian populations.

Current Management

Reptiles and amphibians are not actively managed on base. Potential impacts to their habitats are managed and minimized through the SA/PRB. Minimal baseline data exists; however, a survey for reptiles and amphibians was done in 2011 ([Navy 2011c](#)).

Assessment of Current Management

An inventory of reptiles and amphibians in all habitat types at NBVC Port Hueneme should be kept current. Survey results would confirm the suitability of NBVC Port Hueneme habitats to support these populations and identify the presence of non-native species and special status species. Information on species presence would aid natural resource managers and likely affect how habitats are managed and what kinds of BMPs are developed for activities in their

associated habitats. Monitoring populations through time can provide valuable information on habitat function and its ability to sustain a diversity of species.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conduct surveys of reptiles and amphibians throughout the base to obtain current information to facilitate and guide natural resource management decisions.

- I. Develop community and species-level reptile and amphibian baseline information.
 - A. Integrate resultant survey data into GIS database.
- II. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to native species and habitats.
- III. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.
- IV. If non-natives are present, determine their potential for ecosystem damage and prioritize for their removal.

3.4.4 Birds

This section addresses the presence and management of migratory birds that, under the federal directive of the MBTA (16 USC § 703 *et seq.*) and EO 13186 ([Appendix C](#)), includes federally listed and non-listed species. Specific measures for management of federally listed species are detailed in [Section 3.5](#), Special Status Species and Their Protection.

Migratory birds use the natural and man-made areas of NBVC Port Hueneme for forage and nesting. Birds found in natural areas are detailed in [Sections 3.3.1](#), Coastal and Marine Communities and [Section 3.3.2](#), Terrestrial Communities. Developed areas provide roosting and nesting habitat in structures and landscaping. Cliff swallows (*Petrochelidon pyrrhonota*), mourning doves, house finches, and other common species have been recorded nesting on various buildings and structures. Great blue herons and snowy egrets are regularly documented nesting in eucalyptus trees along the western fence line of the base. Few great horned owls (*Bubo virginianus*) likely nest on base, with one nest recorded in 2010 at the Bard Mansion grounds. Red-tailed hawks may nest on base, but none have been confirmed. Waterfowl, particularly mallard ducks, use the ponded areas at the golf course and Arroyo willow thicket habitat, and have occasionally been recorded nesting or with ducklings. Mist-netting of riparian areas has shown the presence of riparian-dependent passerines such as the yellow warbler (*Dendroica petechia*), many of whom may nest on base. Waterfowl potentially use the riparian area for nesting. In 2003 and 2005, a thorough breeding bird survey with point counts focusing on natural habitats was conducted at NBVC Port Hueneme ([TEC 2003, 2005](#)). Species recorded are in [Appendix H](#), Species Lists.

Starting in 2007, a colony of Brandt's cormorants (*Phalacrocorax penicillatus*) began nesting on Wharf D, along a cement wall that parallels the harbor. NBVC ED staff has monitored the colony in each subsequent year. The colony has grown and increased in productivity each nesting season. Due to the colony's success, it is expected to continue to grow.

Specific Concerns

- Conflicts may arise between birds and facility tenants, particularly through maintenance or demolition activities that could result in potential take under the MBTA.
- The Brandt's cormorant (*Phalacrocorax penicillatus*) colony in the working harbor area is vulnerable to human induced impacts and competition from the marine mammals that haul out at Wharf D.
- Improved monitoring methods, incorporating systematic surveys, are needed to provide a better understanding and to reduce gaps in knowledge of the use of NBVC Port Hueneme by birds, especially sensitive species. This information will help inform natural resource managers and ensure their protection during the project review process.
- Difficulty in educating building tenants on protocols for responding to the discovery of nesting or trapped birds, particularly raptors, in their facilities.

Current Management

All bird species at NBVC Port Hueneme, with the exception of rock doves, European starlings, and house sparrows, are protected by federal law under the MBTA (16 USC § 703 *et seq.*) and EO 13186 ([Appendix C](#)). [Appendix I](#), Migratory Bird Management, further details NBVC Port Hueneme's efforts and strategies for bird conservation to maintain compliance with the MBTA. The MBTA, enforced by the USFWS, makes it unlawful "by any means or manner, to pursue, hunt, take, capture [or] kill" any migratory bird except as permitted by regulation. The number of bird species covered by the MBTA is extensive, includes listed and non-listed species, and is listed at 50 CFR § 10.13. The regulatory definition of "migratory bird" is broad and includes any mutation or hybrid of a listed species and includes any part, egg, or nest of such bird (50 CFR §10.12.).

To provide guidance for conflicts arising between military readiness activities and the MBTA, the USFWS issued the final rule on, "Migratory Bird Permits: Take of Migratory Birds by the Armed Forces" (50 CFR Part 21 in FR 28 February 2007, pages 8931-8950), hereinafter referred to as the Migratory Bird Rule. The Migratory Bird Rule authorizes the military to "take" migratory birds during military readiness activities under the MBTA without a permit. However, if the military determines that the activity will have a "significant adverse effect" on a population of migratory birds, they must work with the USFWS to develop and implement conservation

measures to minimize and/or mitigate the effects. Currently there are no anticipated takes of migratory birds at NBVC Port Hueneme that would require use of this exemption.

Conservation measures under the Migratory Bird Rule require monitoring and record-keeping for 5 years from the date the Armed Forces commence their conservation action. During INRMP reviews, the Armed Forces must report to the USFWS migratory bird conservation measures implemented and the effectiveness of the conservation measures in avoiding, minimizing, or mitigating take of migratory birds (50 CFR Part 21 in FR 28 February 2007, pages 8931-8950).

Current management generally strives to meet these goals:

- Integrate migratory bird conservation principles, measures and practices into installation activities and avoiding or minimizing, to the extent practicable, adverse impacts on migratory birds and migratory bird habitats.
- Identify unintentional actions that are, or are likely to have, a measurable negative effect on migratory bird populations.
- Develop and implement standards and practices designed to lessen the amount of unintentional takings to the extent practicable and consistent with mission requirements.

Implementation of federal regulations requires an understanding of bird populations and their seasonal and yearly fluctuations, to assess potential impacts to population viability. At NBVC Port Hueneme, a monthly survey route was recently implemented to determine species presence, abundance and seasonal patterns. These surveys target natural habitat, areas of high bird use, and the harbor, but do not inventory all bird species present. Particular species of interest include California least terns, western snowy plovers, and breeding cormorants, herons, and egrets. The survey route includes the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area where there was one record of a burrowing owl (*Athene cunicularia*) observation. These surveys, along with anecdotal observations, are used to continually update the species list in [Appendix H](#).

Current management of the Brandt's cormorant colony involves protecting their nesting area from human disturbance, with signs, installed during the nesting season, to prohibit pedestrian access to the Wharf D wall. However, activity associated with the working harbor occurs 15 feet (4.5 m) below the colony, at the base of the wall.

Conflicts arise occasionally between facility tenants and birds or raptors, from demolition or maintenance of buildings and landscaping activities. These are currently minimized by the general practice of scheduling these activities outside of the nesting season. For activities that must occur during nesting season, surveys for bird nests are conducted prior to the demolition of any structure, or removal of trees or brush. If nests are found, NBVC ED and associated MBTA regulations direct that the nests are not to be disturbed and potentially disruptive activities must be halted until the young have fledged.

Open bay doors of the large warehouses and hangars frequently attract owls and raptors to their interiors. Once inside, they often cannot exit on their own and may be injured or perish. Currently, facility tenants report the presence of injured or trapped birds to the NBVC ED. Staff members attempt to capture these individuals for release or transport to local wildlife rehabilitators.

Assessment of Current Management

The absence of a comprehensive database of historical and previous avifauna surveys, limits the installation's ability to determine seasonal patterns and trends.

Monthly surveys have recently been established to document the status and trend of easily observed avian populations. It is important to continue to investigate and assess military use impacts on resident and migratory bird populations, particularly those that are nesting, to document any significant adverse effects and maintain compliance with the MBTA.

The current checklist of birds may be used as a source of baseline data to develop a comprehensive database. Data from subsequent surveys, such as the newly implemented monthly survey route, can be used to update the database. New survey data may be added to appendices of this INRMP as part of the INRMP metrics annual update process. The intent of this INRMP is to provide an assessment of historical baseline data in the document and an opportunity to update survey data.

NBVC ED distributes a basewide email prior to each nesting season, on appropriate actions to take when encountering nesting birds. Indoctrination materials should continue to include information on nesting and trapped birds. Dissemination of information could be improved in instances of changes in staff or building tenants.

The Brandt's cormorant colony remains vulnerable to human disturbance despite signs closing pedestrian access to the Wharf D wall. The colony is located atop the wall, approximately 15 feet (4.5 m) above activities regularly conducted in association with the working harbor. To ensure impacts to the colony are avoided or minimized, base biologists should continue regular monitoring. The SA/PRB process effectively manages for potential impacts to nesting and migratory birds, but additional coordination with NBVC ED staff should occur regarding the timing and location of project activities near the Brandt's cormorant colony.

Management Strategy

Objective: Ensure protection of bird species throughout the base and conserve, restore, and enhance migratory bird habitat, as practicable.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to avoid and minimize potential impacts and "takes" of migratory, resident, and special status bird species, and their habitats.

- A. Implement bird conservation principles, measures, and practices through avoidance and minimization measures to protect migratory bird populations.
 1. Use species-level information gathered from surveys to guide development of project-specific BMPs for migratory birds.
 2. BMPs shall include protective measures such as siting projects to avoid important nesting areas or to avoid collisions of birds with structures, or timing projects to avoid peak breeding activity.
 3. There are no resident special status species, however, if special status species are regularly recorded, identify areas of unintentional take of species of concern and minimize such take. EO 13186 states that agencies will identify where unintentional take reasonably attributable to agency actions is having, or is likely to have, a measurable negative effect on migratory bird populations, focusing first on species of concern, priority habitats, and key risk factors. With respect to those actions, the agency (NBVC) shall develop and use principles, standards, and practices that will lessen the amount of unintentional take, developing any such conservation efforts in cooperation with the USFWS. These principles, standards, and practices shall be regularly evaluated and revised to ensure that they are effective in lessening the detrimental effect of agency actions on migratory bird populations.
 - a. Restrict access into and disturbance of nesting and breeding grounds during critical periods. Incorporate this restriction as mitigation for proposed projects.
 - b. Prevent or abate effects on migratory bird populations caused by pollution.
 - c. Reduce pesticide use (see [Section 4.11](#), Landscaping and Grounds Maintenance).
 - d. Limit the use of rodenticides. Remove any dead or dying rodents from a treated area to reduce the possibility of secondary poisoning through raptor consumption of poisoned rodents.
 4. Protect natural habitats, especially primary roosting, foraging, and nesting areas, from human induced disturbance and invasive species.
 - a. Provide training and information to facility managers regarding protection of migratory birds in compliance with laws to avoid and minimize take, and conserve and restore habitat (EO 13186).
 - b. Limit disturbance during the breeding season. When disturbances are absolutely necessary, ensure that NBVC ED has provided

- approval and disturbance is timed to minimize its impacts on nesting birds and avoid take.
- c.* Ensure tree trimming occurs outside the nesting season, except for instances where health and safety are a concern; in this instance, coordination with NBVC ED must occur prior to tree trimming activities.
 - d.* Ensure surveys are conducted prior to building maintenance, restructuring, or demolition activities.
 - e.* Ensure tenants are aware of protocols for responding to birds injured or trapped inside buildings and warehouses.
 - f.* Protect wetland habitat as directed by EO 11990 and Navy policy (OPNAVINST 5090.1C).
 - g.* Avoid detrimental habitat alteration caused by establishment of invasive plants. Eliminate and prevent the spread of invasive species that crowd out other species necessary to migratory bird survival (2003 Defense Reauthorization Act [DRA] Proposed Rule).
 - a.* Conduct regular program of weed removal from areas identified as primary roosting, foraging, and nesting areas.
 - h.* Identify opportunities and funding for restoration or enhancement of degraded bird habitats.
 - i.* Support cleanup efforts to reduce contaminants and toxic buildup in the ecosystem, including monitoring and reducing nonpoint sources.
 - j.* Maintain closure signs and gates around Brandt's cormorants nesting colonies.
 - k.* Work with facilities to resolve conflicts associated with excessive cormorant bird feces by modifying the wall or potentially excluding nesting and roosting habitat and potentially providing cormorants with an alternative nesting site, if available.

Objective: Conduct a regular program of bird monitoring throughout the base to improve the current inventory and inform on listed species' usage of the harbor, to facilitate and guide natural resource management decisions.

- II. Monitor populations and maintain, restore, and enhance habitats that provide for the health of migratory and resident populations of birds depending on habitats at NBVC Port Hueneme to complete their life cycles, emphasizing Birds of Conservation Concern and other special status species.
 - A. Inventory and monitor habitat and populations of migratory birds that use NBVC Port Hueneme to evaluate conservation effectiveness
 - B. Identify migratory bird species of concern that will be the focus of monitoring.
 1. To identify bird species of concern, use periodic reports of Birds of Conservation Concern published by the USFWS Division of Migratory Bird Management; priority migratory bird species documented in the comprehensive bird conservation plans (U.S. Shorebird Conservation Plan, Colonial Seabird Conservation Plan, North American Waterbird Conservation Plan); species or populations of waterfowl identified as high, or moderately high, continental priority in the North American Waterfowl Management Plan; focus species identified in the California Partners-In-Flight (PIF) plans; listed threatened and endangered bird species in 50 CFR 17.11; and MBTA-listed game birds below desired population size 2.
 - C. Maximize the effectiveness of ongoing monitoring and management efforts by continuing to implement standardized, scientifically sound survey protocols to collect and analyze distribution of birds across habitat types and seasonally
 1. Consolidate existing migratory bird monitoring information.
 2. Maximize cost effectiveness by collecting standardized data on multiple species in addition to any specialized protocols aimed at one species.
 3. Inventory birds using methods that can be integrated with the work of regional partners.
 - a. Investigate the compatibility of the USDA Forest Service (USFS) published guidelines for standardized monitoring techniques for monitoring birds (Ralph *et al.* 1993).
 - b. Determine how current established monitoring programs might contribute to regional databases and monitoring protocols.
 - D. Collect and assess information on environmental contaminants and other physical or biological stressors having potential relevance to migratory bird conservation. Where such information is collected in the course of agency actions or supported

through federal financial assistance, reasonable efforts shall be made to share such information with the USFWS, U.S. Geological Survey-Biological Resources Division, and other appropriate repositories of such data.

- E. To comply with the DRA, use the best scientific data available to assess through the NEPA process, or other environmental requirements, the expected impact of proposed or ongoing military readiness activities on migratory bird species likely to occur in action areas.
- F. Regularly monitor infrastructure that may pose a hazard to migratory birds in order to document any significant adverse impact to populations.
- G. NBVC Port Hueneme has no resident listed species; however, in the event that they are regularly recorded on base, the following applies: Through the SA/PRB process, address project impacts on species of concern thoroughly and specifically, focusing on the effects of the proposed action on the sustainability of these populations. Special consideration should be given to priority habitats, such as important nesting areas, migration stop-over areas, and wintering habitats.
- H. Include the results of monitoring in the annual review of this INRMP.
- I. Promote research and information exchange, including coordinated inventory and monitoring (EO 13186).
 1. Increase communication and coordination between land managers and specialists hired to implement specific projects or conduct monitoring.
 2. Use cooperative assistance from wildlife agencies, organizations, and volunteers to help collect needed data. Integrate with regional databases.

III. Monitor populations of resident land birds, shorebird, and seabirds to protect sustainability of populations, breeding colonies, and their habitat.

3.4.5 Mammals

Mammals recorded during surveys at NBVC Port Hueneme are listed in [Appendix H](#). Most records are from scat and tracks recorded while conducting planning level surveys, and include species such as coyote, fox, Botta's pocket gopher (*Thomomys bottae*) and opossum (*Didelphis virginiana*).

Specific Concerns

- A minimal inventory of mammals has been conducted at NBVC Port Hueneme.
- The minimal data on mammals present on base is a data gap for natural resource management decision making processes.

Current Management

Mammals are not actively managed on base, other than gopher control activities at IRP Site 14 and pest management in buildings (refer to [Section 3.6](#), Invasive Species Management). Potential impacts to their habitats are managed and minimized through the SA/PRB.

Assessment of Current Management

There should be an updated inventory of mammals in all habitat types. Survey results would establish the suitability of NBVC Port Hueneme habitats to support these populations and identify non-native species presence. Information on species presence would aid natural resource managers and likely affect how habitats are managed and what kinds of BMPs are developed for activities in their associated habitats. Monitoring populations through time can provide valuable information on habitat function and its ability to sustain a diversity of species.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conduct surveys of mammals throughout the base to obtain baseline information and to facilitate and guide natural resource management decisions.

- I. Develop community and species-level mammal baseline information.
 - A. Integrate resultant survey data into GIS database.
- II. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to native species.
 - A. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.
- III. If non-natives are present, determine their potential for ecosystem damage and prioritize for their removal.

3.4.6 Aquatic Invertebrates

Marine invertebrates were surveyed in 2008 ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#)). Results of this survey are in [Appendix H](#). The Harbor substrate is mud bottom, and surveys showed signs of burrowing invertebrate activity on the surface. A large sand dollar (*Dendraster excentricus*) bed occurs southeast of SWEF beach, inside the west jetty. Most marine invertebrate species represented in [Appendix H](#) were likely captured on algae, debris, or other sources of structure along the Harbor floor ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#)). Surveys for aquatic nuisance species are conducted periodically by CDFG under the California Aquatic Invasive Species Management Plan ([CDFG 2008a](#)). Aquatic species sampled from Port Hueneme Harbor by CDFG are listed in [Appendix H \(CDFG 2008b\)](#).

Specific Concerns

- Marine invertebrates at NBVC Port Hueneme have the potential to be affected by project activities of various tenants that affect sandy beach and marine subtidal habitats.
- Pollution, sedimentation and aquatic invasive species are threats that could devastate marine invertebrate populations.
- Potential may exist in the harbor for oyster bed restoration.
- The sand dollar bed should be avoided during Harbor dredging activities.

Current Management

Aquatic invertebrates are not actively managed on base, other than minimizing and avoiding impacts to their habitats through the SA/PRB, and consultation with NMFS under EFH directives ([Appendix C](#)).

Water quality for aquatic invertebrates in harbor waters is managed under the NBVC Port Hueneme SWPPP (see [Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management), and CERCLA program (see [Section 4.7](#), Remediation of Contaminated Media).

Assessment of Current Management

Most of what is known of marine invertebrate populations at NBVC Port Hueneme is through the CERCLA program ([Section 4.7](#), Remediation of Contaminated Media). Aquatic invertebrates and benthic macro-invertebrates are useful indicators of water and sediment quality. Species differ in their tolerances to the amount and types of pollution. Numerous studies on benthic fauna have been conducted and are planned for in the harbor and drainage channels in relation to IRP Site 19 and 19A. Coordination for sharing of benthic community data collected in association with CERCLA activities would inform natural resource managers on the condition of the marine ecosystem and invertebrate community trends. The availability of population data collected on a regular basis could aid natural resource managers when evaluating vulnerability and changes in populations, in response to natural or anthropogenic effects.

It is unknown whether potential areas exist in the harbor that would support restoration efforts for oyster bed creation.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conserve and enhance the integrity of aquatic invertebrate populations and their habitats in NBVC Port Hueneme waters.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to native species and their habitats.
 - A. Continue to coordinate with NMFS to determine appropriate BMPs to reduce impacts to EFH.
 - B. Enforce and comply with all applicable state regulations regarding the take and management of marine invertebrates, should any such activity occur.
- II. Protect and improve water quality throughout the base.
 - A. Ensure the implementation of BMPs and water quality improvement goals developed under the NBVC Port Hueneme SWPPP and CERCLA program (see [Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management and [Section 4.7](#), Remediation of Contaminated Media).
- III. Conduct surveys of aquatic habitats throughout the base to facilitate and guide natural resource management decisions.
 - A. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.
 - B. If non-natives are present, determine their potential for ecosystem damage and prioritize for their removal.
 - C. Conduct surveys that identify suitable locations for oyster bed and eelgrass restoration.
- IV. Based on results of oyster bed surveys, develop and implement an oyster bed creation plan.

3.4.7 Fish

Fish species in sub-tidal areas of the harbor were surveyed in 2008 ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#)). That survey represents a baseline for fish in the sub-tidal areas of the Harbor, as no other surveys had been conducted previously. Fish species recorded include topsmelt (*Atherinops affinis*), spotted kelpfish (*Gibbonsia elegans*), Pacific staghorn sculpin (*Leptcottus armatus*), queenfish (*Sepiphus politus*), bay pipefish (*Syngnathus griseolineatus*) and pile perch (*Rhacochilus vacca*) ([Appendix H](#)). No fish surveys have been conducted in shallow water habitats at NBVC Port Hueneme.

Specific Concerns

- No baseline inventory of fish in shallow water habitats has been conducted at NBVC Port Hueneme.
- The lack of data on fish in shallow water areas on base is a data gap for natural resource management decision making processes.
- Pollution, sedimentation and aquatic invasive species are threats that could devastate fish populations.
- The 2008 survey of Port Hueneme Harbor ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#)) did not record large fish species that are typically expected to occur in Harbor waters.

Current Management

Fish are not actively managed on base. Potential impacts to their habitats are managed and minimized through the SA/PRB. Port Hueneme Harbor waters are designated EFH for groundfish, coastal pelagic species, and some highly migratory species (the likelihood of highly migratory species occurring within the harbor is small, due to water depth). EFH that is considered to be particularly important to the long-term productivity of populations of one or more managed species, or to be particularly vulnerable to degradation, may also be identified by NMFS as Habitat Areas of Particular Concern. Port Hueneme Harbor is also designated a Habitat Area of Particular Concern for estuaries ([Map 2-1](#)) ([NOAA 2011b](#)).

Activities that could impact EFH require coordination with NMFS and are avoided, offset, or mitigated. Federal action agencies that fund, permit or carry out activities that may adversely affect EFH are required to consult with NMFS regarding the potential effects of their actions on EFH and respond in writing to NMFS conservation recommendations. Under the EFH regulations, an adverse effect is any impact that reduces the quality or quantity of EFH. Direct impacts include (but are not limited to) physical destruction or degradation of the habitat by construction or contamination. Indirect effects take many forms, including loss of prey, interference with reproductive success, or disruption of resting or social behavior ([NMFS 2011](#)). At the time of this INRMP, no EFH consultations are in place.

Water quality for fish in drainage channels and harbor waters is managed under the NBVC Port Hueneme SWPPP (see [Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management), and CERCLA program ([Section 4.7](#), Remediation of Contaminated Media).

Assessment of Current Management

An inventory of fish should occur in drainage channels and intertidal areas of the harbor. Survey results would establish the suitability of NBVC Port Hueneme aquatic habitats to support these populations and identify the presence of special status and non-native species. Information on species presence would aid natural resource managers and likely affect how habitats are

managed and what kinds of BMPs are developed for activities that occur in their associated habitats. Additionally, monitoring populations through time can provide valuable information on habitat function and its ability to sustain a diversity of species.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conduct fish surveys to obtain baseline information in shallow water habitats, and update the inventory of sub-tidal habitat, to facilitate and guide natural resource management decisions.

- I. Develop community and species-level fish baseline information.
 - A. Integrate resultant survey data into GIS database.
 - B. If non-natives are present, determine their potential for ecosystem damage and prioritize for their removal.
- II. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to fish and aquatic habitats.
 - A. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.
 - B. Continue to coordinate with NMFS for project activities that may result in impacts to EFH.
 - C. Enforce and comply with all applicable state regulations regarding the take and management of marine fishes, should any such activity occur.

3.4.8 Marine Mammals

Marine mammals occur in the harbor and on the shoreline of NBVC Port Hueneme. One federally threatened sea otter has been recorded using the kelp beds off of SWEF beach, over the course of a few months in the fall of 2006. Pacific harbor seals, elephant seals and California sea lions use the harbor and have been recorded hauling out on rare occasions on SWEF beach. The marine survey of 2008 recorded sea lion pups along the riprap of the channel ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#)).

Specific Concerns

- Marine mammals and the sandy beach and marine sub-tidal habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme have potential to be impacted by project activities of various tenants.
- The haul-out of marine mammals on Wharf D infrastructure poses a conflict between natural resources and mission activities. If there is an unexpected spill or release of contaminants, water pollution may threaten the health and viability of marine mammals.

Current Management

All marine mammals are protected by the Marine Mammal Protection Act (MMPA) of 1972, as amended. The MMPA prohibits the take (hunting, killing, capture or harassment) of marine mammals in U.S. waters and by U.S. citizens on the high seas, and the importation of marine mammals and marine mammal products into the U.S. The USFWS is responsible for the following marine mammals: sea and marine otters, walrus, polar bear, three species of manatees, and dugong. The USFWS may authorize and permit take (with limitations and mitigation measures) of marine mammals under their purview. Those mammals that are truly marine inhabitants, cetaceans and pinnipeds, other than walrus, are the responsibility of NMFS.

Potential impacts to marine mammals and their associated habitats are managed and minimized through the SA/PRB. Activities that occur in the Harbor, that have potential to impact marine mammals are discussed in [Section 3.3.1.1](#), Marine Subtidal; [Section 4.9](#), Harbor Operations; and [Section 4.8](#), Oil Spill Response and Hazardous Substance Prevention and Cleanup. The sandy beach and kelp beds at SWEF beach are surveyed monthly for presence of sea otters. Cetaceans are not regularly observed within the harbor. Sea lions regularly haul out at Wharf D, an active floating dock. This presents a conflict between natural resources and mission activities. Excrement on the dock cannot be easily removed under the regulations of the stormwater program, and as a result, the dock is not regularly used. NBVC ED and the NBVC Port Operations Harbor Master have made unsuccessful attempts at excluding marine mammals from hauling out at Wharf D. Future attempts at pinniped exclusion will be conducted in coordination with NMFS.

Assessment of Current Management:

Current management of marine mammals provides necessary information to guide the decision-making process of the natural resource managers. Continued monitoring of marine mammals and their habitats should occur to ensure their protection in accordance with MMPA regulations. Information on species presence and distribution throughout the Harbor aids natural resource managers and affects how their habitats are managed and what kinds of BMPs are developed for their conservation. Monitoring populations through time can provide valuable information on habitat function and its ability to sustain a diversity of species.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect marine mammals and their habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to marine mammals and their habitats.
 - A. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.

II. Maintain compliance with MMPA mandates.

- A. Continue to monitor marine mammal populations and evaluate interactions related to base activities.
 - 1. Monitor and protect NBVC Port Hueneme haul out sites, where not in conflict with mission critical needs.
- B. Implement educational instruction on marine mammal issues and individual responsibility for NBVC Port Hueneme personnel, for presentation during indoctrination.
- C. Ensure facility tenants know who to call in the case of marine mammal strandings.

3.5 SPECIAL STATUS SPECIES AND THEIR PROTECTION

Federally listed and other special status species are discussed in the following sections. Management objectives and strategies for all special status species are addressed in [Section 3.5.3](#), Special Status Species Protection.

3.5.1 Federally Listed Species and Critical Habitat

Animals found at NBVC Port Hueneme that are listed under the federal ESA as threatened or endangered are described here. No designated critical habitat exists in NBVC Port Hueneme, and no BO is in place for base activities, as no listed species are common or expected. NBVC Port Hueneme contains an area of proposed critical habitat for the western snowy plover; a portion of Hueneme Beach lies within NBVC Port Hueneme boundaries ([Map 3-2](#)). The base will likely be removed from critical habitat designation due to the lack of primary constituent elements within base boundaries. This section of Hueneme Beach is underwater for the majority of the year and fluctuates in response to the discharge of dredge material from dredging that occurs at Channel Islands Harbor.

3.5.1.1 *Western snowy plover (Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus)*

The western snowy plover is listed by the USFWS as threatened and by the CDFG as a species of special concern. The western snowy plover is a subspecies of snowy plover that breeds and winters on coastal beaches along the Pacific coastline from southern Washington State south to Magdalena Bay, Baja Sur, Mexico. Populations consist of migrants and year-round residents depending on locality. Snowy plovers breeding in Oregon have been recorded wintering in California as far south as Monterey, while snowy plovers breeding in central California have been recorded south as far as Guerrero Negro, Baja Mexico ([Warriner et al. 1986](#)).

The western snowy plover nests on undisturbed, flat areas with loose substrate, such as sandy beaches and dried mudflats along the California coast. Sand spits, dune backed beaches, sparsely to unvegetated beach strands, open areas around estuaries, and beaches at river mouths are the preferred coastal nesting areas (Page and Stenzel 1981; Powell *et al.* 1997; Wilson 1980). Nesting generally occurs between March 1 and September 15 of each year, though egg laying in southern California has been documented as early as mid-February, and continues through late July.

Snowy plovers forage primarily on the wet sand at the beach-surf interface, where they feed on small crustaceans, marine worms, insects, and amphipods. Adults and young forage on these invertebrates along intertidal areas, beaches in wet sand and surf cast kelp, in foredune areas of dry sand above the high tide, on salt pannes, and along the edges of salt marshes and salt ponds.

Nesting populations occur near NBVC Port Hueneme at an inlet to the Channel Islands Harbor on Hollywood Beach, Ormond Beach (north of the Southern California Edison Company plant and 0.62 mile (1 kilometer [km]) southeast of the Port Hueneme sewage disposal plant), and McGrath State Beach, at the mouth of the Santa Clara River. The decline in western snowy plover populations has been attributed to lower reproduction due to human disturbance, predation, and habitat loss through invasion by nonnative plants. The key threats to the local population are human use and domestic or feral animals such as dogs or cats. This species was recorded in December of 2006 on two occasions, at NBVC Port Hueneme, with limited roosting and foraging areas existing on the sandy beach habitat. Few individuals may use the beach to forage on few occasions throughout the year.

3.5.1.2 California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*)

The California least tern is listed by the USFWS and the CDFG as endangered. This migratory bird species breeds mostly in coastal foredunes and in other sparsely vegetated sites with sandy or gravelly soils. One brood of 1-3 chicks is raised yearly. Least terns arrive at colonial nesting locations in late April and nest from mid-May through August. After breeding, family groups regularly occur at lacustrine waters near the coast of southern California. Because this species tends to abandon nesting areas readily if disturbed, it requires nests in areas relatively free of human or predatory disturbance (Zeiner *et al.* 1990a). The decline in California least tern populations has been attributed to lower reproduction due to human disturbance, predation, and habitat loss. Another key threat includes predation by other wildlife species (such as burrowing owls and American kestrels) or domestic or feral animals (such as cats) (USAF 1997a).

California least terns may forage occasionally in Port Hueneme Harbor and were recorded on one occasion roosting at the northwest end of the harbor, but no nesting activity occurs on the base. Terns at NBVC Port Hueneme are monitored during monthly surveys, but it is unknown how often and what areas of the Harbor they prefer to use. Nesting colonies of California least terns occur in neighboring areas of coastline, at Hollywood Beach and McGrath State Beach to the north of NBVC Port Hueneme, and further south at Ormond and Mugu Beaches.

3.5.1.3 Southern sea otter (*Enhydra lutris nereis*)

Southern sea otters are listed by the USFWS as threatened, and fully protected by CDFG (CDFG 2011). The population of southern sea otters historically ranged from northern California or southern Oregon to approximately Punta Abreojos, Baja California (Wilson *et al.* 1991). Currently the southern sea otter's primary range is restricted to the coastal area of central California, from San Mateo County to Santa Barbara County, plus a small translocated population (currently about 46 animals) around SNI (USGS unpublished data).

Sea otters prefer rocky shorelines with kelp beds and waters about 66 feet (20 m) deep (USFWS 2003). Few sea otters venture beyond 5,200 feet (1,600 m) from shore, and most remain within 1,600 feet (500 m) (Estes and Jameson 1988). They require a high intake of energy to satisfy their metabolic requirements. Sea otters feed on or near the bottom in shallow waters, often in kelp beds feeding on primarily benthic invertebrates such as abalones, sea urchins, and rock crabs. Sea otters eat other types of shellfish, cephalopods, and sluggish near-bottom fish, although the consumption of fish is extremely rare in southern sea otters. The diet varies with the physical and biological characteristics of the habitats in which they live (Estes and Bodkin 2002). Most sea otters in California tend to be active at night and rest in the middle of the day (Ralls and Siniff 1990), but there is extensive variation in the activity of individuals both among and within age and sex classes (Ralls *et al.* 1995). Sea otters breed throughout their range and have two peaks in pupping, January to March and October (USFWS 2003).

Sea otters are approximately 4 feet (1.2 m) long, and can range from 45-65 pounds. They have flattened tail flipper-like hind feet for propulsion, with extremely thick fur (about 600,000 per square inch). Otters feed on about 40 different marine invertebrates diving as deep as 180 feet (55 m) foraging for food. Otters must eat the equivalent of 20 to 25 percent of their body weight each day to maintain a high level of internal heat production. They do not have blubber for warmth like other marine mammals, so they compensate by generating a high metabolism fueled by eating large amounts of food and depending on their dense fur for warmth. They spend a large portion of each day grooming.

Harvest of sea otters for their pelts during the 1700s and 1800s reduced the species throughout its range. In 1974, the total California population was estimated to be about 50 animals. The small size and limited range of the sea otter population, along with the otter's vulnerability to mortality from oil spills, were the main factors that resulted in listing it as federally threatened in 1977. Between 1987 and 1990, the USFWS translocated 140 sea otters to SNI (Hatfield 2005). Currently the sea otter population is estimated to be 2,711 from the 2010 survey (Hatfield 2010). Acanthocephalan parasites (worms) in the intestines, *Toxoplasma gondii encephalitis* (single cell parasite), and shark attacks are the important causes of mortality in sea otters (Kreuder *et al.* 2003; Johnson *et al.* 2009) and are likely responsible for the slow growth and periods of decline in the sea otter population (Estes *et al.* 2003; USFWS 2009).

A sea otter was first sighted at NBVC Port Hueneme in fall of 2006, in the kelp beds on the west side of the harbor entrance. The single otter was seen on two consecutive days in the fall and a second sighting occurred approximately two months later. It is believed that this was the same otter. Male otters are known to wander during the non-breeding season.

3.5.2 Other Special Status Species Having Potential to Occur at NBVC Port Hueneme

The species described below have potential to occur at NBVC Port Hueneme and are either listed under the federal ESA as threatened or endangered, or recognized by CDFG as Species of Special Concern or species at risk, and tracked through the California Natural Diversity Database (CDFG 2011).

3.5.2.1 Least Bell's Vireo (*Vireo bellii pusillus*)

The least Bell's vireo was listed endangered by USFWS in 1986 and CDFG in 1980. This small, gray, migratory songbird breeds almost exclusively in riparian habitats of Southern California and northern Baja California. It is a disjunct subspecies of Bell's vireo which breeds throughout the southwest and into the Midwestern U.S. Least Bells' vireos prefer riparian areas with dense understory for nest placement, and a structurally diverse mature canopy for foraging. They are typically associated with willow scrub, cottonwood, and sycamore, but vegetative structure rather than individual species is most important in territory selection. They occur regionally in Ventura County and could occur in the Arroyo willow thicket habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme. Their decline is attributed to habitat loss and fragmentation, and loss of riparian vegetation associated with water development and flood control projects that alter natural flow regimes. No records exist to date of occurrence of least Bell's vireo at NBVC Port Hueneme. No critical habitat for this species is within NBVC Port Hueneme boundaries.

3.5.2.2 Burrowing owl (*Athene cunicularia*)

The burrowing owl is a CDFG Species of Special Concern. This owl species has been declining in numbers across much of its range in western North America, and is found primarily in open grassland and coastal scrub habitats, and in agricultural and rangelands. The burrowing owl is a winter visitor in the region. It is one of the few diurnal owls, and depends on ground squirrels and other small mammals for creating burrows that it uses for refuge and roosting. They may also dig their own burrows or use artificial burrows (Zeiner *et al.* 1990a).

The owls tend to be opportunistic feeders that mostly prey on small mammals and insects. They are known to prey on the federally endangered California least tern. Predators include prairie falcons (*Falco mexicanus*), red-tailed hawks, Swainson's hawks (*Buteo swainsoni*), ferruginous hawks (*Buteo regalis*), northern harriers (*Circus cyaneus*), golden eagles (*Aquila chrysaetos*), foxes, coyotes, and domestic dogs and cats (Zeiner *et al.* 1990a). Burrowing owls tend to avoid areas near trees, perhaps where other raptors may roost and prey on them. The main threats to this species are habitat loss, poisoning of ground squirrels, and predation by feral cats and dogs (Rosenberg *et al.* 1998; USAF 1998; Zeiner *et al.* 1990a). The burrowing owl was recorded at

NBVC Port Hueneme in 1998 and 2003 ([Appendix H](#)) at the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area. Potential exists for burrowing owls to occupy other dirt mounds and in non-native annual grassland habitat on base, however recent surveys have not recorded any observations. If present, they are likely wintering birds, as there is no recent documentation of nesting burrowing owls in Ventura County ([Tetra Tech 2011d](#)).

3.5.2.3 *Silvery legless lizard (Aniella pulchra)*

The silvery legless lizard is a CDFG Species of Special Concern known to occur regionally, but not recorded during surveys at NBVC Port Hueneme. Silvery legless lizards typically live in loose sand and vegetation found under dune plants. Habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme where the lizards may live is limited to the southeast portion of the base in the sand-verbena-beach bursage habitat. Additional surveys for this species are planned for.

3.5.2.4 *Western pond turtle (Emys marmorata)*

The western pond turtle is a CDFG Species of Special Concern, known to occur regionally, but not recorded during surveys at NBVC Port Hueneme. Western pond turtles are found in slack or slow moving waters and favor areas with emergent logs or boulders for basking. They require suitable upland habitat such as sandy or grassy banks to lay their eggs. It is unlikely they occur at NBVC Port Hueneme due to the fragmented nature of the wetlands on site, and their distance from natural freshwater systems. However, there is potential that they may occur, and are thus included here.

3.5.2.5 *Globose dune beetle (Coelus globosus)*

The globose dune beetle was documented at NBVC Port Hueneme during surveys conducted in September 2011 ([Navy 2011b](#); [Appendix G](#)). The beetle usually burrows in the sand under dune vegetation. The beetle was documented at NBVC Port Hueneme in sand-verbena-beach-bursage habitat. Future surveys will be conducted to document the extent of the population at NBVC Port Hueneme.

3.5.2.6 *Sandy Beach tiger beetle (Cicindela hirticollis gravida)*

The sandy beach tiger beetle is not known to occur at NBVC Port Hueneme, but is found regionally. The sandy beach tiger beetle typically lives near bodies of water with sandy substrates. The beetle could occur in the sandy beach or Arroyo willow thicket habitats at NBVC Port Hueneme. This species was not documented during the recent survey ([Navy 2011b](#)).

3.5.2.7 *Monarch butterfly (Danaus plexippus)*

Winter roost sites for the Monarch butterfly range along the coast from northern Mendocino to Baja California, and the species has been recorded at NBVC Port Hueneme. Trees provide important resting sites for overwintering ([Scott 1986](#)). Adults hibernate by roosting in tree

groves, especially eucalyptus, Monterey pine, and cypress. They require nectar and water sources nearby. Eggs are laid singly under host leaves, stems, and flowers; the larvae eat the leaves and flowers as they hatch. Although roosting has not been recorded on base, eucalyptus and cypress trees at NBVC Port Hueneme provide potential roost sites for this species. Recent surveys have not identified butterfly roosts at NBVC Port Hueneme.

3.5.3 Special Status Species Protection

Specific Concerns

- Threats to special status species at NBVC Port Hueneme include disturbance from human activities such as training, habitat destruction by development, and potential contaminant impacts.
- The spread and sometimes the abatement of disease vectors and pest populations on base threatens native fish and wildlife populations at NBVC Port Hueneme.
- Minimal or no surveys have been conducted to determine the presence or absence of some potentially occurring special status species.
- Survey data is needed to understand the timing and preferred areas for tern foraging in the harbor.
- The current data gap on special status species having potential to occur at NBVC Port Hueneme may result in land use management decisions that could negatively affect these species.

3.5.3.1 Federally Listed Species Protection

The ESA was revised by the NDAA of 2004 (PL 108-136) to recognize INRMP conservation measures and species benefits that could obviate the need for critical habitat designation on Navy lands. All Navy installations with federally listed threatened or endangered species, proposed federally listed threatened or endangered species, candidate species, or unoccupied habitat for a listed species where critical habitat may be designated, must structure the INRMP to avoid the designation of critical habitat. The INRMP may obviate the need for critical habitat if it specifically addresses the benefit provided to the listed species and the provisions made for the long-term conservation of the species. The species benefit must be clearly identifiable in the document and should be referenced as a specific topic in the INRMP table of contents.

Currently, there is no critical habitat designated at NBVC Port Hueneme. There is proposed critical habitat for the snowy plover. The following describes the USFWS three-point criteria test used to determine if an INRMP provides a benefit to the species. An installation is strongly encouraged to use these USFWS criteria when structuring its INRMP to avoid the need for critical habitat designation. These criteria and specific conservation measures that provide for

long-term conservation of listed species that may occur at NBVC Port Hueneme are further detailed in [Appendix J](#), Benefits for Threatened and Endangered Species.

- 1) The plan provides a conservation benefit to the species. The cumulative benefits of the management activities identified in a management plan, for the length of the plan, must maintain or provide for an increase in a species population, or the enhancement or restoration of its habitat in the area covered by the plan (i.e., those areas deemed essential to the conservation of the species). A conservation benefit may result from reducing habitat fragmentation, maintaining or increasing populations, ensuring against catastrophic events, enhancing and restoring habitats, buffering protected areas, or testing and implementing new conservation strategies.
- 2) The plan provides certainty that the management plan will be implemented. Persons charged with plan implementation are capable of accomplishing the objectives of the management plan and have adequate funding for the management plan. They have the authority to implement the plan and have obtained all the necessary authorizations or approvals. An implementation schedule, including completion dates, for the conservation effort is provided in the plan.
- 3) The plan provides certainty that the conservation effort will be effective. The following criteria will be considered when determining the effectiveness of the conservation effort: the plan includes (1) biological goals (broad guiding principles for the program) and objectives (measurable targets for achieving the goals); (2) quantifiable, scientifically valid parameters that will demonstrate achievement of objectives and standards for these parameters by which progress will be measured are identified; (3) provisions for monitoring and, where appropriate, adaptive management; (4) provisions for reporting progress on implementation (based on compliance with the implementation schedule) and effectiveness (based on evaluation of quantifiable parameters) of the conservation effort are provided; and (5) a duration sufficient to implement the plan and achieve the benefits of its goals and objectives.

Current Management

NBVC ED regularly conducts avian surveys to determine how often or whether listed species use habitats at Port Hueneme. If new listed species are recorded in NBVC Port Hueneme, this INRMP addresses management of those species at the individual and community levels through avoidance, minimization, and monitoring measures developed to achieve conservation benefits. If nesting of a listed species occurs at NBVC Port Hueneme, the NBVC ED biologist will contact USFWS and CDFG, as appropriate, to determine management strategies. Annual INRMP metric updates provide a formal means to use adaptive management and review progress made for protecting and conserving potentially occurring federally threatened and endangered species at NBVC Port Hueneme.

Assessment of Current Management

To identify the potential impacts of base activities on listed species and other sensitive species at NBVC Port Hueneme, regular basewide surveys for sensitive species are recommended. Some species are currently being surveyed by NBVC ED personnel, while other species surveys require specialist support. Intensive species-specific surveys should be conducted in suitable habitat on base using USFWS or CDFG protocols, to confirm whether these species occur at NBVC Port Hueneme. Survey reports should expand on information in this INRMP by discussing the habitat requirements of each species and providing recommendations for their enhancement.

Management Strategies

Objective: Continue to conduct surveys for presence of federally endangered or threatened species, species proposed for listing as endangered or threatened, and federal candidate species for listing. If listed species are recorded using habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme, then support surveys in accordance with the federal ESA of 1973, as amended. Support surveys for state-listed, proposed listed species, and state candidate species for listing.

- I. Conduct surveys (using established methodology) of listed species to determine presence or absence of species during breeding and nonbreeding season.
 1. Develop a standard format and a database to collect and maintain records of observations.
 2. If new listed species are found, contact USFWS to discuss recommendations on how to modify the INRMP to manage this species.
- B. Promote research and information exchange, including coordinated inventory and monitoring (EO 13186).
 1. Increase communication and coordination between land managers and specialists hired to implement specific projects or conduct monitoring.
 2. Partner with, and use cooperative assistance from, wildlife agencies, organizations, and volunteers to help collect needed data. Integrate with regional databases.

Objective: Protect and enhance federally endangered or threatened species, species proposed for listing as endangered or threatened, and federal candidate species for listing that occur at NBVC Port Hueneme in accordance with the federal ESA of 1973, as amended. Protect and enhance state-listed, proposed listed species, and state candidate species for listing.

- II. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to special status species and their habitats.

- A. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.

III. Enhance and restore habitats used by special status species.

- A. Conduct habitat restoration as outlined in habitat-specific goals and strategies in this INMRP.
- B. Limit human disturbance by protecting areas used by special status species.
 - 1. Restrict access to protected areas.
 - 2. Install signs to inform on sensitive species and habitats.
 - 3. Educate personnel on protected species regulations and responsibilities.

3.5.3.2 Other Special Status Species Management

Current Management

Although NBVC is not required to manage for sensitive species warranting stewardship, the Navy recognizes the value of maintaining diverse ecosystems. The Navy recognizes that it is prudent to protect rare species as a proactive strategy to prevent future federal listings. Through the SA/PRB, the Navy complies with the laws pertaining to regulated species by avoiding and minimizing impacts to habitats where those species may occur. To the extent that resources are available to support the management of such species, NBVC intends to implement the following objectives and strategies.

Assessment of Current Management

The habitat based and species specific management measures proposed in this INRMP in conjunction with the SA/PRB provide a sufficient level of natural resource management to protect and conserve species warranting Navy stewardship at NBVC Port Hueneme.

Objective: Conduct species level surveys that target the presence of special status species in the habitats where they may occur.

- IV. Fund and conduct surveys for special status species, using qualified biologists certified to conduct special status species surveys.
- V. Incorporate data into natural resource management databases.

Objective: Provide for the recovery, enhancement, and protection of species warranting Navy stewardship, as a proactive strategy to prevent federal listings.

VI. Based on results of surveys, species warranting Navy consideration and the habitats that support them should be protected to the extent practicable by giving them consideration during the land use planning processes.

- A. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to special status species and their habitats.
 - I. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.
- B. Maintain contact with regional specialists and regulatory agencies regarding the listing status of unique species known or thought to occur at NBVC Port Hueneme.
- C. Continue to participate in the USFWS/NMFS review and listing process for species known or thought to occur at NBVC Port Hueneme that are being considered for listing under the ESA.
- D. Stay updated on agency decisions, published material, and meetings that change the listing status of species.

VII. Continue to resolve baseline biological data gaps.

- A. Support ongoing and new research on distribution and ecology of species warranting Navy stewardship. Encourage academic institutions to facilitate resource data collection.
- B. Continue to inventory and map existing species warranting Navy stewardship.

3.6 INVASIVE SPECIES MANAGEMENT

Non-native invasive plants and animals pose a serious threat to native ecosystems. Without the natural enemies of their original habitats, non-native invasive species can spread rapidly and out-compete California native species. Invasive plants can alter ecosystem processes, transport disease, or cause cascading impacts to native populations, potentially impacting multiple trophic levels. Whether introduced unknowingly by early settlers hundreds of years ago, or more recently by global commerce and travel, the spread of non-native invasive species throughout California is the second greatest threat to biodiversity next to direct habitat destruction. On a local level, the Navy has the potential to contribute to the spread of invasive species across NBVC installations, through everyday activities such as transport of cargo and equipment by

land, air and ocean. In installations, construction and military readiness activities have the potential to spread invasives from developed areas into natural areas.

Descriptions of invasive terrestrial and aquatic species documented at NBVC Port Hueneme, and management objectives and strategies are provided below. A complete list of invasives recorded at NBVC Port Hueneme is in [Appendix H](#).

EO 13112 (Invasive Species) (03 February 1999) requires federal agencies to prevent the introduction of invasive species and restore native species and habitats that have been invaded. EO 13112 defines an invasive species as “an alien whose introduction does or is likely to cause economic or environmental harm or harm to human health.” This EO requires federal agencies to:

- Prevent the introduction of invasive species;
- Detect and respond rapidly to and control populations of such species in a cost-effective and environmentally sound manner;
- Monitor invasive species populations accurately and reliably;
- Provide for restoration of native species and habitat conditions in ecosystems that have been invaded;
- Conduct research on invasive species and develop technologies to prevent introduction and provide for environmentally sound control of invasive species; and
- Promote public education on invasive species and the means to address them.

This EO does not authorize, fund or support actions that are likely to cause or promote the introduction or spread of invasive species in the United States or elsewhere unless federal agencies determine and have made public that the benefits of such actions outweigh the potential harm caused by invasive species ([National Archives and Records Administration 1999](#)).

3.6.1 Terrestrial Invasives

Terrestrial invasive exotic species that occur at NBVC Port Hueneme include invasive terrestrial plants, mammals, birds, and invertebrates.

The introduction and spread of non-native plants into the remaining few natural communities that exist at NBVC Port Hueneme, further threatens the viability and quality of these already fragmented habitats. All natural habitats described in [Section 3.3](#), Ecosystems, have some level of non-native plant occurrence. The most problematic and widespread species currently identified at NBVC Port Hueneme are fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*), ngaio tree (*Myoporum laetum*), iceplant (*Carpobrotus edulis*), fountain grass (*Pennisetum* sp.), and pampas grass (*Cortaderia* spp.). Other invasive species include annual grasses, narrow-leaved iceplant

(*Conicosia pugioniformis*), and crystalline iceplant (*Mesembryanthemum crystallinum*). Invasive species surveyed in each habitat are described in the *Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat Restoration Plan* (TEC 2003). Invasive plant control and habitat-specific restoration recommendations are detailed in that report. Invasive species sold as ornamentals but prohibited from landscape use in NBVC are documented in [Appendix K](#), NBVC Approved Landscaping Plant List.

Known invasive terrestrial fauna recorded at NBVC Port Hueneme include feral cats and rodents. Feral cats can be among the most detrimental of invasive species, causing population decline and extirpation of a variety of species, including insects, birds, reptiles and small mammals (Lowe et al 2000; Nogales et al 2004). Birds constitute approximately 20 to 30 percent of the diet of a feral cat. Feral cats are also thought to depend upon food from people, garbage, and carrion; as these sources of food increase, so do the feral cat populations (National Audubon Society 1998). The urban setting of NBVC Port Hueneme and housing communities within and adjacent to the base ensures a steady supply of predatory domestic and feral cats to the base, making control of their populations a difficult task. No program is currently in place to control feral cat populations on the base.

Rodents comprise a major invasive species group. The black rat (*Rattus rattus*), the Norway rat (*Rattus norvegicus*), and the house mouse (*Mus musculus*) all have a record of severely impairing ecosystems. Rodents can survive on a variety of food sources, are able to adapt quickly to new habitat, and are prolific breeders. In developed areas, rodents are controlled through the Pest Management Program ([Section 3.6.3](#) Pests and Disease Vectors).

Invasive exotic birds at NBVC Port Hueneme include but are not limited to European starlings, house sparrows, and rock doves.

No invertebrate studies have been conducted at NBVC Port Hueneme, but Argentine ants (*Linepithema humile*) likely occur. They are regionally abundant and problematic. Studies have found that Argentine ants recruit rapidly and will numerically dominate and aggressively displace native ant species. This directly reduces biodiversity and alters the food web from the bottom up. Once established, Argentine ants are detrimental to other arthropods and, alter the plant community and availability of food for vertebrates (Tetra Tech 2009). They pose a threat to nesting birds and their offspring, reducing survivorship of fledglings. Argentine ants that occur in developed areas may be managed under the Pest Management Program.

Specific Concerns

- Invasive plant species are present throughout the natural habitats of NBVC Port Hueneme and threaten the integrity of these communities.
- Invasive terrestrial mammals such as feral cats and rodents pose a serious risk to the integrity of various avian, reptile, and mammal species.

- Argentine ants are an invasive terrestrial invertebrate species that poses a potential threat to the integrity of NBVC Port Hueneme's terrestrial ecosystems and populations of nesting migratory birds.
- Habitats or communities are not monitored regularly to identify new occurrences of invasive species.
- Management strategies are not guided by an Invasive Species Management Plan.
- Invasive species have the potential of being transported from NBVC Port Hueneme to other locations like NBVC San Nicolas Island (SNI) through cargo stored on base.

Current Management

Implementation of EO 13112 is covered by National Invasive Species Council's (NISC) 2008-2012 National Invasive Species Management Plan (NISMP) (NISC 2008). Management objectives and strategies in this INRMP build upon the framework provided by the NISMP. In addition to EO 13112, the Federal Noxious Weed Act (7 USC Sec. 2801 et seq.) explicitly provides for the control and eradication of noxious plants on land under the control of the federal government.

Pesticide use in natural resources management programs must comply with applicable requirements of Chapter 17 of OPNAVINST 5090.1C (Navy 2011a) as identified in the NBVC Integrated Pest Management Plan (IPMP) (Navy 2011d). The control and eradication of invasive species is of primary importance to natural resources management at NBVC Port Hueneme, and is a fundamental step toward recovery and conservation of natural ecosystems.

Currently there is no Invasive Species Management Plan (ISMP) for NBVC Port Hueneme. Control and eradication of invasive plant species at NBVC Port Hueneme is currently conducted by NBVC Pest Control and limited to roadsides and developed areas. Weed management has occurred in natural areas, including restoration activities conducted in dune mat habitat southwest of SWEF beach in 2008 (Tetra Tech 2008). There was a large weed eradication effort in all natural areas of NBVC Port Hueneme in 2011. Species targeted for removal included myoporum, fennel, iceplant, pampas grass and fennel. These areas will require additional treatment in the future.

The DoD Pest Management Program of 2008 (DoDINST 4150.07) includes weeds, rodents, ants, and other organisms that could negatively affect ecosystems. The focus of pest management at NBVC Port Hueneme is primarily on control of species bothersome to humans, in developed areas, and not necessarily invasive species having potential for ecosystem damage.

A Biosecurity Plan for NBVC SNI has been developed that addresses strategies for prevention of the transport of invasive and pest species to SNI (Tetra Tech 2011e). Strategies include management of invasive species associated with port and cargo operations at NBVC Port

Hueneme. In this way, the strategies outlined in the Biosecurity Plan for shipments of materials and ballast water will work to protect the natural resources of NBVC.

Assessment of Current Management

An ISMP for NBVC Port Hueneme should be developed based on the IPMP that includes guidelines for the systematic method of identifying, prioritizing, and eradicating invasive species. The ISMP would detail specific management strategies for various plant species that occur on the installation. Prevention, early detection and rapid response are necessary for the effective management of invasive introduction and spread, to avoid costly eradication of large populations. Strategic planning consistent with other government agencies' strategic plans is also necessary to address complex invasive species issues on a local and regional scale.

The Invasive Species Management Plan should include strategic goals that focus on prevention, early detection and rapid response, control and management, restoration, and organizational collaboration. Strategies should include the catalog, map and documentation of weed control efforts, to better track success of weed management activities. The plan should be revised regularly to update priority lists based on regional invasive species lists updates, and to detail current research on species, and the most up to date control practices.

Management Strategy

Objective: Minimize introduction of invasive non-native terrestrial species to NBVC Port Hueneme through prevention.

- I. Implement the SNI Biosecurity Plan to prevent non-natives from entering NBVC Port Hueneme and spreading to SNI.
- II. Develop and implement an Invasive Species Management Plan that includes prevention measures.
- III. Support development of BMPs for projects in or adjacent to natural areas. For example (but not limited to):
 - A. Certify as “weed free,” to the extent possible, gravel and fill materials.
 - B. Require that native plant species provided in [Appendix K](#) of this INRMP are used for landscaping, unless a species is specifically approved by NBVC ED.
 - C. Revegetate disturbed areas with native NBVC approved plants.
- IV. Include in indoctrination information for NBVC Port Hueneme military staff to prevent the introduction of non-native species.

Objective: Develop early detection and rapid response protocols and capabilities.

- V. Establish monitoring locations to detect invasive species introduction and spread.
- VI. Develop a communication network as a rapid response tool to quarantine specific invaders and identify the pathway.
- VII. Support rapid response by determining funding sources, contract vehicles, cooperative mechanisms that can be accessed quickly.

Objective: Evaluate control and management capabilities for established invasive non-native species populations and identify strategic gaps.

- VIII. Develop and implement an Invasive Species Management Plan based on current needs, information, and priorities.
- IX. Map and prioritize terrestrial invasive non-native species populations.
- X. Support studies that determine if there are impacts from invasive non-native species already present.
- XI. Investigate and implement methods to control invasive non-native invertebrate species found at NBVC Port Hueneme.
 - A. Ensure funding is secured for non-native removal during all phases (including post-project), if applicable.
 - B. Monitor projects to ensure personnel are following BMPs, conservation measures, and other guidelines and requirements.

Objective: Promote cooperative interagency efforts to collect and analyze comprehensive monitoring data, including shared funding and staffing.

- XII. Support regional invasive species management initiatives and task forces, as opportunities arise.

Objective: Promote awareness of the threats and pathways of invasive species among military personnel, civilian employees, contractors, and other visitors to NBVC Port Hueneme.

- XIII. Prepare educational materials that include measures to prevent the introduction of invasive non-native species.

3.6.2 Aquatic Invasives

Aquatic invasives have the potential for rapid spread and colonization, smothering and outcompeting native reef, aquatic plants, and wildlife populations, decreasing native biodiversity. Their decay can rob waters of dissolved oxygen, and their presence can be a nuisance to beachgoers, an operational hazard for ships, and damaging to infrastructure such as levees,

docks, and water delivery systems. Removal of aquatic invasives has proven extremely costly, with the most successful eradication efforts conducted in a rapid response manner, at the onset of identification. Eradication and control requires regional coordination on multiple levels, quick access to funding, public outreach, and efficient regulatory permitting (NISC 2008). Prevention of species introductions through vector management is considered the most desirable way to address aquatic nuisance species.

Specific Concerns

- Port Hueneme Harbor receives much ship traffic, including commercial vessels, with various types of cargo that could be vectors for invasive species introductions from other parts of the world.
- Shipments from Asia come in regularly, on the commercial side of Port Hueneme Harbor. These boats could carry and introduce invasives to Port Hueneme Harbor.
- Dredging activities or other activities that disturb the sea floor in Port Hueneme Harbor could result in spread of existing invasives, to waters outside Port Hueneme Harbor.
- Vertical structures in the harbor, such as debris along the sea floor, riprap, and pilings, provide suitable habitat for invasive species attachment and spread.

The following describes aquatic invasives recorded or potentially occurring at NBVC Port Hueneme, due to regional presence:

Caulerpa (*Caulerpa taxifolia*) is a green alga native to tropical waters that has now invaded many coastal areas, including southern California. In areas where the species has become well established, it has caused ecological and economic devastation by overgrowing and eliminating native seaweeds, seagrasses, reefs, and other communities. This alga poses a substantial threat to marine ecosystems, particularly to the extensive eelgrass meadows and other benthic environments that make coastal waters such a rich and productive environment for fish and birds. Caulerpa surveys of Port Hueneme were done on May 8 and May 9, 2006, and on May 28 and 29, 2008, with no recorded occurrence of caulerpa in the harbor (Merkel and Associates, Inc. 2008). Protocol surveys for this species are typically requested by NMFS and USACE prior to initiation of dredging or other sea floor disturbance activities. Caulerpa surveys should continue, to ensure Port Hueneme Harbor remains free of caulerpa, to allow for early detection, and to avoid the spread of any newly established population.

Wakame (*Undaria pinnatifida*), a kelp native to Japan, is a threat to NBVC Port Hueneme's marine waters. Due to its fast growth rate and biomass, this seaweed quickly starves the natural understory algae of light. As the native algae die, fish and invertebrates must move elsewhere to find food, thus creating extra feeding pressure on adjacent areas. This alga has drastically affected the ecosystems it has invaded. It is a nuisance species on boats, fishing nets, ropes,

moorings, and other structures and its presence poses increased labor and maintenance costs for removal. This species was recorded on docks and hulls of docked vessels in Port Hueneme Harbor in May 2008 ([Merkel and Associates 2008](#)).

Mosquitofish (*Gambusia affinis*) are native to the Atlantic and Gulf Coast drainages and tend to outcompete native fish where they are introduced if not managed appropriately. Mosquitofish are often reared by mosquito abatement districts and released to control mosquitos. Mosquitofish have been found in the drainage channels at NBVC Port Hueneme ([Woodward-Clyde 1998](#)). They were placed in the drainage channels sometime prior to 1993 for mosquito control and are currently not monitored by the base.

Pests Associated with Ballast Water and Hull Fouling. To maintain stability during transit along coasts and on the open ocean, ships fill their ballast tanks with water from coastal ports from which they originate. Associated sediments also are taken up into the ballast along with a load of living organisms. Species that end up in ballast water range in size from tiny microorganisms to larger species, including schools of fish. After arriving at their destination, ships typically release their ballast water and the associated organisms into the new port. Certain invading species (also known as aquatic nuisance species [ANS]) such as zebra mussel (*Dreissena polymorpha*), can cause complex changes in the structure and function of their new ecosystem, including restructuring established food webs, importing new diseases to the region, and outcompeting indigenous species. Ballast water is not released in Port Hueneme Harbor. Ships docking at Oxnard Harbor District pump and containerize ballast for disposal off-site. In accordance with OPNAVINST 5090.1C, ballast from DoD ships is released at least 12 nautical miles from shore ([Tetra Tech 2011a, 2011f](#)).

Exotic marine species are also introduced by attaching themselves onto ship hulls, propellers, rudders, anchors and anchor chains. Hull fouling by organisms such as mussels, barnacles, seaweed, and anemones creates an environment for smaller more mobile species such shrimps, worms, and sea snails that can hide amongst the larger fouling species. Organisms associated with hull fouling are susceptible to environmental factors such as fluctuations in salinity and water temperature; survival and introduction rates are lower for fouling species compared with those in ballast water ([Sylvester and MacIsaac 2010](#)). However, hull fouling remains a risk for introduction of nuisance species to Port Hueneme Harbor. Due to regular ship maintenance at NBVC, such as hull cleaning and painting, this risk is lowered. See [Section 4.9](#), Harbor Operations, for detail on activities that occur in the harbor.

Current Management

The DoD supports implementation of federal aquatic invasive species laws including but not limited to EO 13112, the National Invasive Species Act (NISA) of 1996, and the Nonindigenous Aquatic Nuisance Prevention and Control Act of 1990.

NBVC supports CDFG as the lead agency for managing aquatic invasive species found in the nearshore waters of NBVC Port Hueneme and would collaborate with the CDFG Habitat Conservation Branch and the state invasive species coordinator. The CDFG conducts a number

of programs related to aquatic invasive species, including serving as the lead agency in developing the statewide aquatic invasive species management plan, and a rapid response plan for invasions. The CDFG is responsible for enforcement of regulations concerning the aquaculture industry; recreational fishing; commercial fishing; the importation and transport of live wild animals, aquatic plants, and fish into the state; and the placement of any such animals or plants in state waters. Recent programs have focused on the aquarium plant *Caulerpa taxifolia*, the voracious northern pike (*Esox lucius*), and the New Zealand mudsnail (*Potamopyrgus antipodarum*). All species of *Caulerpa* are regulated in the state of California under CDFG Division 3, Chapter 3.5, Section 2300. Other state agencies with regulatory authority over aquatic invasive species include the California Department of Food and Agriculture through the California Food and Agriculture Code, California Department of Water Resources through the California Water Code, and the State Lands Commission through the Ballast Water Management Act of 1999, and the Marine Invasive Species Act of 2003.

In OPNAVINST 5090.1C, Navy installations are directed to prevent the introduction of invasive non-native species and provide for their control:

“The Navy will identify actions that affect the introduction of invasive species, prevent their introduction, respond rapidly to their control, monitor populations, restore affected native species and their habitat, conduct research and develop technologies to prevent further introductions, and promote public education of the issue. The Navy will not authorize, fund, or implement actions that are likely to cause or promote the introduction or spread of invasive species in the U.S. or abroad. Proper ecosystem management requires the control of noxious weeds, ANS, and other invasive species. Use of native plants in landscaping, grounds maintenance, and land restoration projects is required. Installation natural resources managers shall ensure that invasive species prevention recommendations are incorporated into new construction programs and operations. Land or ecosystem restoration projects shall require the use of native species only. Natural resources managers shall monitor invasive species populations and identify areas where research and new technology may be needed to better control invasive species in the military environment.”

OPNAVINST 5090.1C requires that ships dispose of ballast water before entering within 12 nautical miles (nm) (22 km) of the next operating area, thereby preventing introduction directly to harbor waters:

“If it is necessary for a surface ship to load ballast water in an area that is either potentially polluted or within 3 nm from the shore, the ship shall pump the ballast water out when outside 12 nm from shore and twice fill the tank(s) with clean sea water and pump prior to the next entry within 12 nm from shore. Surface ships will effect a ballast exchange twice in clean water, even if ballast water was pumped out before exiting the polluted waters or 3 nm limit, since residual water remaining in a tank after emptying it may still contain unwanted organisms, which could be transferred during the next ballasting evolution. Ballast water exchange is not required during local operations or when reentering within 12 nm in the same locale as the ballast water was initially loaded.”

On the OHD commercial side of Port Hueneme Harbor, qualifying vessels (those over 300 gross register tons in size) must comply with state regulations. Under California's Marine Invasive Species Act (AB433), passed in 2003, qualifying vessels entering Port Hueneme Harbor from ports within the Pacific Coast region must conduct near-coast exchange of ballast in waters at least 50 nm offshore, and 200 meters deep, or retain ballast and associated sediments on board. All vessels must complete and submit a ballast water report form upon departure from each port of call in California. They must comply with good housekeeping practices including rinsing anchors and removing fouling organisms from the hull. A ballast water management plan must be prepared specifically for each vessel, and a ballast water log must be maintained for each ballast water tank on board. Under the act, the vessel master and crew must attend training on ballast water management and treatment procedures. Under this act, and California's Aquatic Invasive Species Management Plan (CDFG 2008a), CDFG conducts periodic monitoring of the harbor for new aquatic nuisance species. Aquatic species sampled from Port Hueneme Harbor by CDFG are detailed in [Appendix H \(CDFG 2008b\)](#).

Prior to conducting dredging of the harbor, aquatic invasives are monitored for presence or absence. NBVC Port Hueneme does not regularly monitor for aquatic invasives in the harbor or the drainage channels.

Assessment of Current Management The prevention of aquatic invasive species into Port Hueneme Harbor could be enhanced through the SA/PRB process that guides BMPs for in-water construction or other marine activities. Prevention measures should be incorporated into contract language, operational and transportation policies, and pest management plans. Early detection of aquatic invasives is key to avoiding costly control of spread, therefore, regular monitoring for aquatic invasives should be conducted in marine and wetland habitats at NBVC Port Hueneme. Project specific surveys such as those conducted prior to dredging, should continue. The Navy should support other entities that want to survey the harbor's flora and fauna.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect the ecological integrity of marine and inland waters and associated native biota, of NBVC Port Hueneme.

- I. Prevent the introduction of aquatic invasive species into NBVC Port Hueneme waters.
 - A. Continue to use the SA/PRB to proactively prevent ANS incursions, by incorporating BMPs and prevention measures into contract language.
 - B. Promote ballast water management for all vessels entering NBVC Port Hueneme.
 - C. Support the continuation of the Navy's ballast water exchange policy for open ocean exchange.

- II. Develop and implement a standardized monitoring system to facilitate early detection and rapid response for high priority aquatic invasive species.
- III. Promote cooperative interagency efforts to collect and analyze comprehensive monitoring data.
- IV. Support the response of CDFG and California Department of Food and Agriculture in the event of an ANS incursion.

Objective: Promote awareness of the threats and pathways of aquatic invasive species among military personnel, civilian employees, contractors, and other visitors to NBVC Port Hueneme.

- V. Prepare educational materials that include measures to prevent the introduction of invasive aquatic species.

3.6.3 Pests and Disease Vectors

The DoD Pest Management Program of 1996 (DoDINST 4150.07) defines pests as arthropods, birds, rodents, nematodes, fungi, bacteria, viruses, algae, snails, marine borers, snakes, weeds, and other organisms (except disease-causing organisms) that adversely affect readiness, military operations, or the well-being of personnel and animals; or attack or damage real property, supplies, equipment, or vegetation.

The DoD Pest Management Program of 1996 (DoDINST 4150.07) defines disease vectors as organisms capable of transmitting the causative agent of a human disease; serving as an intermediate or reservoir host of a pathogenic organism; or producing human discomfort or injury.

Disease vectors and pest wildlife populations that are known or expected to occur at NBVC Port Hueneme are described below.

Mosquitoes. Two mosquito species are currently known at NBVC Port Hueneme: *Aedes taeniorhynchus* and *Culex tarsalis* (Tetra Tech 1999). Mosquitoes recorded in Ventura County also include *Anopheles franciscanus* and *Anopheles occidentalis*. These species can be carriers of diseases such as yellow or dengue fever (*Aedes* sp.), malaria, viral encephalitis, West Nile virus (*Anopheles* sp.), meningitis, and filaria diseases (*Culex* sp.) (Tetra Tech 2009). Hosts for these species include birds, mammals, and humans.

Rodents. The deer mouse (*Peromyscus maniculatus*), a native species, can be a host of hantavirus, a virus often fatal to human beings. This species is primarily responsible for an outbreak of the virus in 1993 in the southwestern United States. Deer mouse populations are widespread in the United States and NBVC Port Hueneme is likely to have an abundant population on base. There is currently no management program for these animals.

California ground squirrels (*Spermophilus beecheyi*) occur at NBVC Port Hueneme and are considered pests that have potential for carrying the plague virus, and require control. The California ground squirrel may disturb landscaped areas by digging up vegetation. Studies have shown that ground squirrel populations decline in fields where vegetative cover is allowed to increase; decreasing field cover allows ground squirrels to detect predators more easily. Ground squirrel populations are currently not managed at NBVC Port Hueneme. Possible actions for control include rodenticides, live trappings, construction of raptor perches, and increasing grass heights. Ground squirrels provide habitat for burrowing owls, by providing burrows for this sensitive species.

Botta's pocket gopher (*Thomomys bottae*) occurs at NBVC Port Hueneme in California annual grassland habitat. The species is controlled as part of Site 14 CERCLA restoration and maintenance activities. Management actions currently include weekly application of Fumitoxin, but a more effective remedy could include construction of raptor perches. Grass heights cannot exceed 18 inches, per the CERCLA site maintenance goals ([Tetra Tech 2004](#)).

Current Management

Priorities and management strategies for invasive species control at NBVC Port Hueneme are outlined in the NBVC IPMP. NBVC recently revised their IPMP in 2011 ([Navy 2011d](#)). Revisions recur every five years.

The position of Integrated Pest Management Coordinator is housed in the NBVC ED. This position entails coordination of all pest control activities on the installation to ensure compliance with INMRP and other mandates. Pest control activities are managed and conducted by NBVC PWD and their contractors.

Assessment of Current Management

For general pest species, remove all non-native predators from NBVC Port Hueneme and prevent new introductions. Native pest species should continue to be controlled in developed facilities.

Management Strategy

Objective: Detect introductions of new pests and manage current populations of existing pests.

- I. Coordinate with IPMP to establish monitoring programs and reporting of changes in populations or new detections.

3.7 NATURAL RESOURCES LAW ENFORCEMENT

Specific Concerns

- Unauthorized access or activities in natural areas, or areas used by nesting birds or marine mammals, may disrupt and limit the viability of native populations or habitats.
- Gaps in communication between NBVC ED and NBVC Force Protection, related to enforcement of closure areas or other areas requiring special protection, could result in mismanagement of natural resources, or non-compliance with federal environmental regulations.

Current Management

Protection of natural resources at NBVC Port Hueneme is currently provided through NBVC Force Protection. No Wildlife Law Enforcement Program is currently in place at NBVC Port Hueneme.

Assessment of Current Management

Natural resources are sufficiently protected under the current program. Improvements may be made in communication of protocols related to marine mammal strandings and injured or trapped wildlife. Natural resource management activities (restoration, area closures, etc.) should be continually communicated to NBVC Force Protection, to ensure successful management and protection of resources.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect sensitive habitat areas and species from the impacts of unauthorized access, activities, or other disturbances.

- I. Ensure NBVC Force Protection is informed of special closures due to listed or sensitive species presence, nesting, or habitat restoration activities.
- II. Maintain regular communication between NBVC Force Protection and NBVC ED, to inform on areas that require regular patrol, and protocols for reporting trapped or injured wildlife and marine mammal strandings.

3.8 DATA INTEGRATION, ACCESS, AND REPORTING

Compiling planning and natural resources data into a single, accessible system provides a critical natural resources management tool, enabling managers to identify resources, conflicts, opportunities, and facilitating natural resources decision-making management.

Specific Concerns

- GIS maps and shapefiles may not have appropriate metadata that identifies who, when, and for what purposes the data were collected.
- Natural resource management decisions could be misguided if there are information gaps in the natural resources database, or if the database is not kept current.

Current Management

NBVC Port Hueneme has used an EMS program to track natural resources including coastal resources and waste products. NBVC's EMS is a conformance requirement for the Navy's environmental program and contributes to standardized methods for data integration, access, and reporting.

The GIS database for NBVC Port Hueneme was developed using ArcView GIS Version 3.0a software developed by the Environmental Systems Research Institute. The North American Datum 83 State Plane Coordinate System is used for X and Y coordinates, and the North American Vertical Datum 88 State Plane Coordinate System is used for Z coordinates. Global positioning system (GPS) data collected in the field is integrated into the GIS database on a continual basis.

GIS and data management for INRMP updates and revisions are supported on the regional level (Navy Region Southwest, San Diego) by maintenance of a central database for all GIS files and associated plans and reports, for each installation.

Assessment of Current Management

The intent of the EMS data management program at NBVC Port Hueneme is to provide a central clearinghouse of resource-related data that is continually systematically updated and organized. Proper use and management of the EMS will ensure resource managers, base planners, other base personnel, appropriate base contractors, and outside agencies have access to the latest information on natural resources at NBVC Port Hueneme so these resources are properly protected according to the INRMP.

Data collected for future additions to the GIS database for NBVC Port Hueneme should be compatible with the GIS software and coordinate systems, and compatible for use on Windows based computers.

Metadata for the GIS overlays at NBVC Port Hueneme currently do not exist. Annotation of all GIS overlays with Federal Geographic Data Committee metadata using a predefined metadata template is recommended. The National Biological Information Infrastructure (NBII) biological metadata standard should be used for describing biological data (NBII MetaMaker Version 2.20).

Development of a Metadata Dictionary for all of the data developed for the GIS database at NBVC Port Hueneme is also recommended.

Management Strategy

Objective: Ensure the technically sound, practical and appropriate use of library and computer technology to organize, analyze, and communicate natural resource information in support of management decisions.

- I. Set up a central clearinghouse for data, reports, and publications pertaining to NBVC's EMS that addresses natural resources and that is accessible to staff.
- II. Seek standardization of the approach to communicate research and monitoring results.
- III. Continue to develop and maintain NBVC Port Hueneme's data management capabilities.

4.0 SUSTAINABILITY OF THE MILITARY MISSION AND COMPATIBLE USE

Sustainability takes a long-term view of natural resources stewardship, Navy mission accomplishment, social responsibility, and economic prosperity into the future. For this INRMP, the topic of sustainability encompasses:

- Sustainability of the Navy mission at Port Hueneme with respect to how natural resources support this mission.
- Resource-specific best practices, consistent with the Navy's EMS for the use of renewable and non-renewable resources and how pollution and wastes are prevented and processed. The practices may address energy, water, water quality, air quality, greenhouse gas management, reducing natural and human threats, and securing habitat for special status and indicator species. This topic is more fully developed in specific INRMP sections including, but not limited to: Water Resources, and Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review and Metrics.
- Preparing for climate change and regional growth.
- Using resources in the built environment.

4.1 INTEGRATED MILITARY MISSION AND SUSTAINABLE LAND USE DECISIONS/OPERATIONS PLANNING AND REVIEW

A successfully implemented INRMP will meet two basic purposes:

1. It will ensure the sustainability of all natural resources at an installation, and,
2. It will ensure no net loss of the capability of installation lands to support the DoD mission.

These two purposes are closely related and not mutually exclusive. Healthy ecosystems support realistic military training and testing needs by providing large open space, buffers, stable soils, clear air, clean water, and a range of natural conditions available for the indefinite future.

Disturbances that characterize NBVC Port Hueneme include:

- Facilities
- Roads
- Construction training grounds
- Harbor uses

To facilitate sustainable land use decisions during operations planning and review, opportunities and constraints in NBVC Port Hueneme have been identified and mapped, as required in the INRMP Template (DoD 2010). [Map 2-1](#), “Opportunities and Constraints,” is intended to show all the areas where there are little to no restrictions on training, and also illustrate potential encroachment partnering areas. The map shows NBVC Port Hueneme environs to consider potential buffer areas and corridors. [Map 2-1](#) also shows locations resources that may require regulatory permits or coordination (“Constraints”), as required in the INRMP Template (DoD 2010). Constraints shown on the map are all areas on the installation where limitations on training or mission may occur due to natural resources related issues such as wetlands or listed species.

Specific Concerns

- Management units could be defined that would allow for analyzing sustainability at a finer scale than all of the base and its surrounding waters at once.
- Sustainability in siting and resource use is only beginning to be considered a metric of successful project design.

Current Management

Most of NBVC Port Hueneme’s natural resources are extremely small, fragmented and surrounded by developed or disturbed land uses. Few open spaces are available for development or expansion of infrastructure. Sustainable land use and the protection and enhancement of the remaining habitats on base, are mutually compatible.

To date, sustainability has been applied in military installations somewhat narrowly to the built environment and focused mostly on energy and recycling. It is beginning to be applied to stormwater management such as with low impact development (LID) approaches, and to ecological sustainability of habitats, species, and ecological functions.

Future land use planning at NBVC Port Hueneme incorporates sustainability concepts with its emphasis on confining facility renovations in existing footprints. This practice also has an economic benefit, as using existing facility sites enables the re-use of existing instrumentation and infrastructure and avoids economic and environmental costs associated with establishing new areas. There is always the possibility of a change in mission which could lead to a degradation or development of natural resource areas.

In support of sustainability, the SA/PRB is used to manage environmental compatibility with the military mission. Sometimes the natural resources staff provides on-site monitoring of a military operation to ensure environmental compliance. NEPA and the SA/PRB process are further addressed in [Section 4.5](#), Regulatory Compliance.

Each year the CO of NBVC must answer, as part of the INRMP metrics review, the following questions:

- Does the natural resources team coordinate with operators when making changes to the INRMP to keep it current? Coordination examples include: maps, signs, pamphlets, other communications, orientations, meetings, training, etc.
- To what level do natural resources compliance requirements support the installation's ability to sustain the operational mission?
- Has there been a net loss of training lands?
- Does the INRMP process effectively consider current mission requirements?

Assessment of Current Management

The SAIA guidance indicates the need to focus on improving the ties between natural resource management and military readiness. While the “no net loss” policy of the Sikes Act and DoD guidance is broadly accomplished by the Range Complex Management Plan and Environmental Impact Statement (EIS), there remain unfulfilled opportunities to facilitate the connection between natural resources and the mission. More locally specific planning criteria could be used for site selection criteria such as using landform, soil recoverability, plant community condition and sensitivity, and considering the timing and intensity of use. Management units help develop priorities and reconcile conflicts. Natural areas, as described in [Section 3.3.2](#), Terrestrial Communities, and as described in the *Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat Restoration Plan (TEC 2003)* as Special Interest Natural Areas, could be the basis for delineating management units.

Management Strategy

Objective: Achieve no net loss of military mission by aligning current and future land and water use (location, extent, timing, and intensity) with environmental value protection.

- I. Maintain and enhance existing land uses to support core RDT&E, training, and mission-support capabilities through coordinating of all facilities siting, relocation, expansion, or change in use by continued use of the SA/PRB process.*
- II. The placement of continuing and evolving military land uses, to the extent practicable, should be in previously disturbed areas to fully use existing operational areas and minimize potential effects to sensitive resources.*
- III. Ensure compliance with statutes and regulations to protect sensitive natural resources, to maintain environmental quality and to exercise responsible stewardship of public lands.*

- IV. Maintain and enhance coordination and cooperation with neighboring communities, agencies, and organizations to ensure compatibility of base natural resource uses with the Navy's mission.
- V. Provide reasonable accommodation of compatible nonmilitary land use to the extent practicable.
- VI. Maintain healthy and intact habitats that self-recover from disturbance, using principles of ecosystem management and sustainability to balance short-term projects with long-term goals.
 - A. Ensure water quality improvement and protection measures are fully implemented, which will contribute to overall ecosystem health.
 - B. Manage land use compatibility by adopting management units that consider operational control.
 - C. Use management units to provide a finer spatial scale for analyzing military mission needs and conserving high-value, scarce habitats and species.
 - D. Align infrastructure to contribute to the military mission, concentrating it in operations areas, and integrating it with the environment with proper siting and sustainability practices.
 - E. Use criteria in each natural habitat area to define the resilience of the area to various types of use or disturbance patterns to set restoration priorities.
- VIII. Address long-term threats to the stability of the natural environment including but not limited to soil erosion, invasive exotic species, climate change, sea level rise, and habitat fragmentation.
 - A. Assess the hydrology of the base and existing condition of natural areas, for opportunities to create or enhance natural area buffers, to allow for shifts in habitats and percolation, storage, or drainage of flood waters.
 - B. Avoid the addition of hardscape. Continue to develop in existing footprints and use LID concepts in all facility renovations.
 - C. Avoid and minimize road or traffic characteristics that promote plant invasions, or result in significant habitat fragmentation for animals.
- IX. Continue to use NEPA documentation, including cumulative effects analysis, to guide specific projects and document choices.
- X. Ensure the CO's preparedness to answer as part of the INRMP metrics review, the questions identified above, in Current Management.

4.2 SUSTAINABILITY IN THE BUILT ENVIRONMENT

Sustainable development practices produce highly efficient and cost effective buildings that reduce the use of natural resources such as water and oil, decrease pollution, and provide a healthier indoor environment. This type of development takes into account the full life cycle cost of a project, including broader concerns such as its effect on the environment and the community, not just the financial cost.

In support of promoting sustainability in the built environment, the National Institute of Building Sciences, in collaboration with federal agencies, private sector companies, non-profit organizations and educational institutions, developed a set of sustainability principles and design guidelines set forth in the Whole Building Design Guide (WBDG 2011). To evaluate objectively, whether a building project meets the definition of “sustainable,” in 1994 the U.S. Green Building Council (USGBC) developed the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) Green Building Rating System. The LEED program is one of several ratings systems for energy performance. It includes a checklist of various “green” options for building design and construction, developed through a consensus by a consortium of industry groups. It evaluates environmental performance from a “whole building” perspective over a building's life-cycle, providing a definitive standard for what constitutes a “green building.” The LEED rating system's six credit areas for new construction are:

- Sustainable Sites (includes site selection, site resource protection, landscaping, and stormwater management);
- Water Efficiency (water efficient landscaping, water conservation, and innovative technologies);
- Energy and Atmosphere;
- Materials and Resources;
- Indoor Environmental Quality; and
- Innovation and Design Process (includes exceptional performance beyond the LEED requirements).

For sustainable water management, the EPA developed several documents that include a literature review, concepts, case studies, and guidance in LID, that are becoming requirements in some stormwater permits. On 20 January 2005, the State Water Resources Control Board adopted sustainability as a core value for all California Water Boards' activities and programs, and directed California Water Boards' staff to consider sustainability in all future policies, guidelines, and regulatory actions. Additional information on EPA guidance for LID can be found at www.epa.gov/owow/nps/lid/.

While standards exist for sustainable structures—“green buildings” and “water management”—there are no comprehensive guidelines and performance benchmarks for those who want to create and measure sustainable landscapes in the built environment (SSI 2010). The Sustainable Sites Initiative (SSI) is an interdisciplinary effort by the American Society of Landscape Architects, the Lady Bird Johnson Wildflower Center at the University of Texas at Austin, and the U.S. Botanic Garden to create voluntary national guidelines and performance benchmarks for sustainable land design, construction, and maintenance practices (SSI 2010). For more information refer to www.sustainablesites.org

Specific Concerns

- The true long-term cost of choices is not as visible to leadership as it could be because natural resources assets are not assigned a value, and thresholds or tipping-points of change in their value are not known.
- There is a need, for those involved in executing development projects, for education about costs and technologies to understand the difference in environmental approaches and choices. This uncertainty hampers the adoption of more projects that meet sustainability criteria.

Current Management

EO 13123 “Greening the Government Through Efficient Energy Management” (superseding EO 12902) directs that the federal government significantly improve its energy management. It promotes energy efficiency through building design, construction, and operation; water conservation; use of renewable technologies; and fostering markets for emerging technologies.

In the Navy, the first requirement of facilities is mission support; however, as stated in NAVFACINST 11010.45, “Sustainable development is required by law and policy, and is a requirement for the Navy” up to and including completion of project documentation (DD Form 1391). The Navy’s goal is to exceed the LEED “certified” level where justified by life cycle costs (NAVFACINST 11010.45). The Navy uses LEED as a tool in applying sustainable development principles and as a metric to measure the sustainability achieved.

The Navy was the first federal agency to participate in the LEED program. In 2005, apart from the Government Services Administration, the Navy had the highest number of LEED certified structures of any federal agency at 17. The Navy continues to pursue sustainable development in its facilities requiring all applicable projects to meet the LEED Certified level, unless there are justifiable conditions that limit accomplishment of the LEED credits necessary. With the USGBC, the Navy supports development of the LEED for Homes Committee. Submission to the USGBC for certification is recommended for high visibility and to showcase projects.

Much sustainability planning in the Navy occurs in the Regional Shore Infrastructure Plan (RSIP) process, because this is the tool where facility needs are evaluated, and siting options are examined. One of the stated Navy goals of the RSIP process is (as stated in NAVFACINST

11010.45): “Recognizing the environmental association of all planning recommendations and providing ecologically sustainable solutions that support and enhance the regional shore establishment.” Properly following the RSIP process means that a planner is already taking a longer-term approach (NAVFACINST 11010.45).

NAVFACINST 11010.45 adds the LEED and National Governors Association (NGA) New Community Design checklist requirement to the RSIP process. The Navy’s LEED checklist has the scoring shown in [Table 4-1](#) (only elements related to natural resources are shown).

TABLE 4-1: PARTIAL CHECKLIST (PORTION RELATING TO NATURAL RESOURCES) AND SCORING SYSTEM FOR NAVY LEED PROJECTS

Erosion and Stormwater Control
Construction site sediment and erosion control plan that conforms to best management practices.
No net increase in the rate or quantity of stormwater runoff from existing to developed conditions, OR, if existing imperviousness is greater than 50 percent, new development will result in a 25 percent decrease in the rate and quantity of stormwater runoff.
Stormwater treatment systems designed to remove 80 percent of the average annual post development total suspended solids, and 40 percent total phosphorous.
Site Selection
If the site is FREE from the following unfavorable conditions.
Land elevation is lower than 5 feet (1.5 m) above the elevation of the 100-year flood as defined by Federal Emergency Management Agency. Within 100 feet (30.5 m) of any federal, state, or local wetland.
Land that provides habitat for any species on the federal or state threatened or endangered list.
If the site has any of these problems, strongly consider using another area.
Urban Redevelopment
Develop on a site classified as a brown field and provide remediation.
Conserve water use through xeriscaping with native plants.
Reduced Site Disturbance/Reduced Heat Islands
Post development landscaping uses native plants that improve habitat for native species.
Light Pollution Reduction
Do not exceed Illuminating Engineering Society of North America foot candle level requirements, and design interior and exterior lighting such that zero direct-beam illumination leaves the building site.
Water Use Reduction
Use only captured rain, graywater, or trenched wastewater to water landscape.
Install non-potable water system for toilets, cooling towers, boilers, landscaping, vehicle washing, and other non-potable water needs.
Employ strategies that in aggregate use 20 percent less water than the water use baseline after meeting Energy Policy Act of 1992 fixture performance requirements.
Exceed the potable water use reduction by an additional 10 percent.
Comply with the Department of Energy Performance Measured Protocol.

The NGA Checklist for better “smart growth” land use approaches is the second set of standards used by the Navy. Their sustainability evaluation includes one criterion that addresses protection of open space, natural beauty, and critical environmental areas:

1. Does the project avoid fragmenting existing green space, especially natural habitats and forests?
2. Does the project design protect the local watershed? Water runoff and other factors should be examined to determine whether the development is harming the watershed.
3. Does the project location avoid increasing the risk or negative impacts of natural disasters? Consideration should be given to what kinds of periodic natural hazards exist for the site and whether a specific location is vulnerable, for example, to flooding, wildfires, mudslides, beach erosion, or high winds.

Assessment of Current Management

Across nearly all sectors of environmental concern, there is unfulfilled potential to conduct operations in a more sustainable manner. In addition, there are few projects that meet criteria as sustainable. Information sharing among agency practitioners with the work of professional societies in a range of resource areas is only beginning. LEED is well integrated into agency work due to the application of EO 13423—Strengthening Federal Environmental, Energy, and Transportation Management (January 2007).

Many opportunities exist for the construction of infrastructure in a way that promotes the achievement of the Navy’s mission in an environmentally integrated way. For example, the use of LID approved permeable surfaces and bioswales reduces storm-water runoff and reduces contaminants of concern in stormwater runoff. Bioengineering techniques can promote favored wildlife while excluding undesirable species, such as rats. It is less expensive to design to prevent such impacts rather than to fix them after the fact.

Sustainability indicators for specific resources, such as water, energy, wildlife, etc., are undergoing research and scrutiny for criteria and selection of the best indicators of sustainability. Resource indicators are developed through the expert opinions of scientists, management agency personnel, non-governmental organization representatives, practitioners, and other stakeholders. A suite of variables, when complemented with other sustainability indicators, produce a viable system to monitor at the national level the biophysical, social, and economic characteristics indicating trends of sustainability. There is a need to develop local indicators that tier off these.

The following objective and strategies are designed to improve sustainability of both development projects and natural habitats. Many are adapted from EO 13423.

Management Strategy

Objective: Sustain natural resources and the Navy institutional mission by enabling innovation in planning, design, project management, and implementation for development projects affecting the built environment.

- I. Ensure Navy leadership has visibility with respect to the total cost of mission sustainment, day-to-day operations, infrastructure and building development, and redevelopment. This should incorporate climate change scenarios and the projected value of the loss of habitat associated with action decisions.
- II. Apply sustainability principles to the management of habitats, species, and ecological functions on NBVC Port Hueneme by identifying resource-specific BMPs similar to what has been done for energy and water in the built environment using LEED, LID, and SSI approaches.
 - A. Continue to comply with EO 13123 that tasks federal agencies with defining principles for implementing sustainable development in construction.
 - B. Use construction siting, materials, and methods that promote biotic communities to the fullest extent possible.

4.3 ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS

Specific Concerns

- Communication about the natural resources of Port Hueneme, environmental regulations, and protocols for situations where wildlife is trapped or injured, or birds are nesting or roosting in unwanted areas, may not be effectively conveyed due to staff turnover.

Current Management

The SAIA requires each military service to support environmental education for personnel and for the public where and when it is compatible with military safety and security needs.

Conservation awareness on NBVC Port Hueneme is implemented by multiple basewide environmental programs. The conservation effort on site will continue to expand as this INRMP and subsequent natural resource management programs are undertaken to ensure efficient and thorough management of the natural resources on base. Conservation efforts at NBVC Port Hueneme address energy, water resources, recycling, pollution prevention, and public outreach and education. Conservation programs currently in place on NBVC Port Hueneme include:

- Recycling program for materials used in basewide operations, including metals, oil, oil filters, cardboard, white paper, glass, and aluminum.
- Indoctrination program for newly stationed military personnel, presenting an overview of the Environmental Program, from hazardous waste to wetlands and endangered species.
- Environmental coordinator (EC) program which designates department lead and unit environmental coordinators to promote installation ownership of environmental programs. NBVC ED provides guidance and training for this program, which outlines appointment directives and specifies the responsibilities of an EC for each NBVC organization including tenant and geographically separated units. This program has been established to fully deploy the NBVC EMS and pollution prevention program and provides additional oversight of environmental compliance, recycling, and remediation activities; provide strategic direction for environmental management and compliance; and ensure conformance with the NBVC EMS on a continuing basis ([Tetra Tech 2011g](#)).

Assessment of Current Management

The indoctrination program should continue to instruct personnel on NBVC Port Hueneme natural resources, and protocols for responding to issues such as trapped or injured wildlife, and nesting birds on facilities. Applicable goals and directives of this INRMP should be communicated to new staff in indoctrination materials, and through personnel training programs.

General conservation awareness and education could be enhanced through projects such as a demonstration water conservation garden of regionally native or low water usage plants.

Management Strategy

Objective: Increase natural resources outreach to military and civilian staff and contractors.

- I. Continue to support and develop the indoctrination program for new staff.
- II. Identify opportunities on base for enhanced natural resource education and awareness of military and civilian staff and contractors.

4.4 BENEFICIAL PARTNERSHIPS AND COLLABORATIVE RESOURCES PLANNING

Ecosystems and the species that populate them (especially migratory species) usually transcend administrative boundaries, and their conservation can best be accomplished through cooperative ventures. “Preserving all the parts” with an emphasis on habitats is central to the ecosystem management approach mandated by DoD. The ecosystem approach involves going beyond addressing short-term approaches one species at a time. Regional planning processes are a

means to address natural resource management using an ecosystem approach. Partnerships among private, local, state, tribal, and federal interests are vital to help realize ecosystem management, the basis for management of Navy lands and waters.

Cooperative management of terrestrial and marine NBVC Port Hueneme flora and fauna is required under the federal SAIA and the Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act. Like NEPA, the Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act is essentially procedural as no specific outcome is mandated. The USFWS and CDFG have a statutory obligation to review and coordinate on INRMPs. Recognizing this core, three-way partnership in preparing, reviewing, and implementing INRMPs among the DoD, USDOJ, USFWS, and state fish and wildlife agencies, a MOU was signed in January 2006. The CDFG and other state fish and wildlife agencies were represented by the IAFWA. The desire is for “synchronization of INRMPs with existing fish and wildlife service and state natural resource management plans” and “mutually agreed-upon fish and wildlife service conservation objectives to satisfy the goals of the Sikes Act.”

Specific Concerns

- Currently, no beneficial partnerships exist at NBVC Port Hueneme, except for those mandated by the SAIA.

Current Management

The Navy policy calls for its installations to expand involvement in regional ecosystem planning, management, and restoration initiatives. INRMP coordination and metric reviews are the only beneficial partnerships in place for collaborative resource planning at NBVC Port Hueneme. If the opportunity arises, NBVC would participate in any Landscape Conservation Cooperatives and Population Vulnerability Assessment (Section 4.6 Consistency with Other Plans). Information on Landscape Conservation Cooperatives can be found at: <http://www.fws.gov/science/shc/>.

The Navy also sees partnerships as a means to manage encroachment pressure on the Navy mission. The instruction also defines encroachment to be any lack of action by the Navy to coordinate with local jurisdictions, monitor the development plans of adjacent communities, or adequately manage facilities and real property. At NBVC Port Hueneme, urban development surrounds the installation, offering little to no opportunities for encroachment partnering.

Assessment of Current Management

Establishing cooperative planning efforts with surrounding land agencies and individuals will benefit NBVC Port Hueneme natural resources and those of the entire region. Cooperative planning can also reduce the costs of actions that require management across boundaries such as biological monitoring.

Management Strategy

Objective: Be proactive in cooperative resources planning partnerships to create regional conservation, ecosystem-based solutions of mutual benefit while also protecting the military mission.

- I. Continue to participate in conservation and encroachment planning.
- II. Participate in regional conservation and ecosystem planning, by relating its priorities to local and regional initiatives, in collaboration with other government agencies ([Section 4.6 Consistency with Other Plans](#)).
- III. Seek planning partnerships for invasive species and feral animal removal with adjacent landowners if compatible with mission activities.
- IV. Meet annually with USFWS, NOAA, and CDFG to fulfill SAIA provisions and related inter-agency cooperative agreements.
- V. Foster relationships with university research programs to increase knowledge base of NBVC Port Hueneme natural resources.

4.5 REGULATORY COMPLIANCE

At NBVC Port Hueneme proposed projects, operations, or other actions are scrutinized for potential environmental impacts through a formal review process. The INRMP is used as a tool to identify at an early stage, the potential impacts of planned Navy action on natural resources and provide a basis for altering the action to prevent or minimize those impacts.

Mitigation is the process of minimizing impacts to protected habitats or species. As defined by the Council on Environmental Quality in 1978, it includes measures to avoid, minimize, rectify, reduce, eliminate, or compensate for the impact. In most cases, mitigation is undertaken in that order or “sequence” of preference, that is, from avoidance as a first priority to compensation as a last resort. Most mitigation policies and measures are agreed to as a result of protection under the NEPA, ESA, or the CWA.

NEPA

NEPA (Public Law 91-190, 42 U.S.C. 4321-4347 as amended) was enacted to prevent environmental damage by ensuring that federal agency decision makers give environmental factors appropriate weight before taking any discretionary actions. NEPA requires the preparation of a report that studies the effects of a proposed federal agency action and evaluates whether the action “significantly affects the quality of the human environment” (42 USC 4332). Elements of the report include an analysis of project alternatives and analysis of cumulative effects on each resource topic. The analysis is used as a decision making tool on whether to proceed with the proposed action. The SA/PRB process (NBVCINST 11010.1, 04 June 2003) guides NEPA implementation and permitting procedures, as described below.

Each year, approximately 100 to 300 Categorical Exemptions (CATEX) are prepared under NEPA for activities at NBVC installations; approximately 40 percent of those cover all or a portion of activities at NBVC Port Hueneme. For fiscal year 2011, 115 CATEXs were prepared for activities at NBVC Port Hueneme. At the time of this INRMP, an EA is being developed for “Homeporting of the Littoral Combat Ship on the West Coast of the United States” that involves the preparation and storage of mission support packages at Port Hueneme ().

ENDANGERED SPECIES ACT

Under the ESA, federal agencies may not jeopardize the continued existence of any federally listed threatened and endangered species (TES) or cause the destruction or adverse modification of critical habitat. Currently the USFWS has not issued any BOs nor has any critical habitat been designated at NBVC Port Hueneme. Section 7 of the ESA requires all federal agencies to enter into consultation with the USFWS or the NMFS whenever proposed actions might affect listed TES plants and animals. Section 7 consultations will be initiated if warranted; otherwise, written documentation that there are no effects on TES will be generated by NBVC ED and kept in project files.

The USFWS policy does not use the term “mitigation” because it is not mentioned in the ESA. In the context of consultation under the ESA, restoration and other conservation measures are voluntary actions proposed by the project proponent to minimize impacts to listed species and provide alternative or protected habitat that promotes conservation. The USFWS ranks four habitat categories according to their scarcity value, with “unique and irreplaceable” habitat receiving top priority for conservation measures. A mitigation planning goal must be established that may range from “no loss of existing habitat value” to “minimize loss of habitat value.”

CLEAN WATER ACT

Regulatory authority for Section 404 of the CWA has been delegated by the EPA to the USACE. Section 404 regulates the discharge of dredge or fill material into the Waters of the U.S. (WOUS) and adjacent wetlands. The USACE has set up the Nationwide Permit Program (NWP) to streamline the permit process for activities similar in nature and with minimal impacts. The NWP Program is re-evaluated every 5 years; NEPA is performed and each NWP is re-evaluated. If the thresholds determined for the NWP will be exceeded or conditions cannot be met, the NWP does not apply and the proposed action will require application for an Individual Permit (IP). An IP requires a public notice, an alternatives analysis (the 404(b)(1) analysis), and a NEPA document specific to the proposed project. USACE is currently implementing a National policy for “no net loss of values and functions” for wetlands and WOUS.

The USACE regulation provides that “all mitigation will be directly related to the impacts of the proposal, approximate to the scope and degree of those impacts, and reasonably enforceable.” It also states “Consideration of mitigation will occur throughout the permit application review process and includes avoiding, minimizing, rectifying, reducing or compensating for resource losses. Losses will be avoided to the extent practicable. Compensation may occur on-site or at an off-site location” (33 CFR S 320.4[r]).

USACE has a three-step sequencing procedure for evaluating impacts to wetlands (Memorandum of Agreement between USACE and EPA dated February 7, 1990): (1) avoid, (2) minimize, and (3) compensate. First, the project proponent must first demonstrate avoidance and minimization of impacts to WOUS to the maximum extent possible. Avoidance includes demonstrating that there is no practicable alternative which would have less adverse impact. Minimization requires that consideration be given to redesigning or staging a project to reduce impacts. Compensatory mitigation is only authorized for unavoidable impacts and must replace the loss of values and functions of the WOUS proposed for impact. Compensatory mitigation includes creation, restoration, enhancement or preservation. All impacts must be avoided or minimized before compensating mitigation will be considered. In some cases, mitigation banking is the appropriate approach to compensating mitigation (33 CFR S 320.4[r]).

As of the date of this INRMP, NBVC ED secured one Section 404 USACE permit in 2011, for repairs to the Landing Ship Tank Ramp ([Tetra Tech 2011i](#)).

COASTAL ZONE MANAGEMENT ACT

The Coastal Zone Management Act (CZMA) of 1972 (16 USC Section 1451-1464) encourages coastal states to be proactive in managing coastal zone uses and resources. CZMA established a voluntary coastal planning program; participating states submit a Coastal Management Plan (CMP) to the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration for approval. Under the CZMA, federal agency actions within or outside the coastal zone that affect any land or water use or natural resource of the coastal zone shall be carried out in a manner that is consistent to the maximum extent practicable with the enforceable policies of the approved state management programs. Each state defines its coastal zone in accordance with the CZMA. Excluded from any coastal zone are lands the use of which by law is subject solely to the discretion of the federal government or which is held in trust by the Federal government (16 USC 1453). Accordingly, although NBVC Port Hueneme land is federal government property and therefore excluded from the coastal zone, the Navy conducts an effects test as part of its determination of an action's effects for purposes of federal consistency review under the CZMA, to factually determine whether that action (even if conducted entirely within a federal enclave) would affect any coastal use or resource. As this INRMP Revision is a programmatic document, no consultation with the California Coastal Commission is required at this time. There are, however, specific actions or projects discussed in this INRMP Revision for possible future implementation that may require additional environmental effects analysis, as required through the National Environmental Policy Act, prior to being implemented. If and when such projects are to be carried forward, the Navy would engage in consultation with the California Coastal Commission to the extent necessary and appropriate under the CZMA.

ESSENTIAL FISH HABITAT

The Magnuson-Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act (Public Law 94-265; 16 USC 1801-1884) as amended (P.L. 109-479), provides for the conservation and management of fishery resources. The Magnuson-Stevens Act defines Essential Fish Habitat (EFH) as those waters and substrate necessary to fish for spawning, breeding, feeding, or growth to maturity.

These waters include aquatic areas and their associated physical, chemical, and biological properties used by fishes and may include areas historically used by fishes. The NMFS is given responsibility for identifying EFH for all federally managed marine and anadromous fish species. Many marine fish that are federally managed by the Pacific Fishery Management Council and NOAA/NMFS rely on shallow coastal habitats during part of their lives. The Pacific Fishery Management Council and NMFS are responsible for designating EFH for each life stage of federally managed marine fish species.

Any project with potential impacts to EFH requires consultation with NMFS. The Navy must incorporate into project plans, NMFS recommendations for conservation practices that minimize, offset, or avoid impacts to EFH. At the time of this INRMP, no EFH consultations are in place.

Current Management

All proposed projects for NBVC must be planned in accordance with the SA/PRB (NBVCINST 11010.1, 04 June 2003). The SA/PRB guides NEPA implementation and permitting procedures; the primary responsibility for NEPA implementation is NBVC ED. The steps for the SA/PRB process are:

1. The project proponent must first submit all project plans, and a SA/PRB Request Form, to PWD who enters the project into e-Projects (a web-based tracking tool) and sends an announcement to the PRB Manager and Asset Management (AM) Branch.
2. The AM Branch decides whether the plan is consistent with the Regional Master Plan and if the proposed project needs a Safety Site Approval (Explosive Safety, Electromagnetic Radiation, or Airfield Safety Waiver).
3. The PRB Manager makes the proposed project available to an interdisciplinary team for review. Either the proponent organization environmental coordinator or an NBVC ED representative performs an initial review. The interdisciplinary team includes environmental specialists, security officers, safety officers, fire department and industrial hygiene. The PRB reviews the proposed project for compliance with NEPA, assesses potential project impacts to natural resources, and determines whether the proposed project is Categorical Excluded (CATEX), requires an EA or an EIS.
4. If a planned project is determined to have the potential to adversely impact the environment, the proponent will generate a request for formal environmental analysis by the NBVC ED.
5. The team will review the proposed project and fill out the PRB Checklist with applicable conditions related to their specific media or program area (i.e. air quality, water quality, cultural resources, etc.).
6. The PRB Manager will include all project conditions in the CATEX memorandum and forward the memorandum to the NBVC CO for review and signature. The final signed CATEX will be returned to the requestor along with a "Statement of Understanding

Form" which increases the project proponents' accountability for reviewing and complying with all conditions of the CATEX. The Statement of Understanding Form is signed and returned to the PRB Manager within two weeks of receipt. After the project has been completed, changed or cancelled, the requestor must fill-out and submit to the PRB Manager a Project Closure Form, which closes the start-to-finish loop for projects on NBVC.

NBVC ED's responsibilities for NEPA implementation include:

- Ensuring each action proposal is reviewed in a timely manner;
- Completing and forwarding documentation for CATEX and continuing action determinations to the action proponent;
- Coordinating consultation and document preparation with the proponent for actions requiring an EA or EIS;
- Assisting action proponents in development of an EA or EIS;
- Serving as a member of the PRB (NBVCINST 11010.1);
- Forwarding EA and EIS documents to OPNAV via the chain of command; and
- Serving as a single point of contact with regulatory agencies while engaged in the NEPA process.

Assessment of Current Management

NBVC ED effectively uses NEPA to ensure its activities (as described in this INRMP) are properly planned, coordinated, and documented. It also uses NEPA to identify issues associated with other organizations' projects, which affect Port Hueneme's natural resources, when it has the opportunity to review such projects. Project and mitigation planning at NBVC Port Hueneme will continue to avoid, minimize, rectify, reduce, eliminate, or compensate for any identified environmental impact. In most cases at NBVC Port Hueneme mitigation will continue to be undertaken in that order or "sequence" of preference, that is, from avoidance as a first priority to compensation as a last resort.

An important offshoot of proper NEPA implementation is that projects are often enhanced by the effort. When natural resources managers understand mission and project requirements in terms of land features and requirements, they often not only offer more potential site options to mission or project planners but also offer alternatives to avoid future environmental conflicts.

Project and mitigation planning at NBVC Port Hueneme will continue to avoid, minimize, rectify, reduce, eliminate, or compensate for any identified environmental impact. In most cases at NBVC Port Hueneme mitigation will continue to be undertaken in that order or “sequence” of preference, that is, from avoidance as a first priority to compensation as a last resort.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conduct planning of mission activities having potential environmental effects by applying NEPA's requirements and policies to enhance the mission-related use and protection of natural resources.

- I. Define and identify measures for “no net loss” of military value, and seek agreement among resource and regulatory agencies on these measures during INRMP planning updates, NEPA review, and ESA consultations.
 - A. Seek opportunities for streamlining EA procedures. As much as possible, NEPA, BOs, and other environmental documentation should be as programmatic as possible so that documents tiered below these can be facilitated in a timely manner and with an ecosystem management approach.
- II. Continue to implement the SA/PRB (NBVCINST 11010).
 - A. Integrate the site approval planning process early into the regular planning functions of each office.
 1. Technical assistance should be provided by staff to support other offices, when needed, before and after a proposed action is submitted to the project review board, giving guidance on: determining the necessary regulatory permits, documentation, and consultations, project design, site selection, and scope of work; development of reasonable alternatives, including alternative sites; and selection of appropriate conservations measures so the proposal integrates avoidance and minimization measures from the beginning.
 2. Determine the necessary regulatory requirements for the project (level of NEPA documentation, Section 404 permits, ESA consultations), including coordination with regulatory agencies in the early stages of the planning process.
 - B. Update the Site Approval Checklist periodically to ensure consideration of all issues.
 1. Provide a list of pre-approved conservation measures or mitigation for project proponents.
 2. Reference appropriate environmental protection and mitigation policies from this INRMP.

3. Make available to project planners updated GIS maps of sensitive resources on the property to assist in evaluating potential impacts of proposed projects and in recommending appropriate mitigation opportunities.
- C. Communicate directly with all affected parties during the regulatory process to avoid misunderstandings and delays.
- III. Follow up on conservation measures proposed in NEPA, consultation, and permit documents to maintain a consistent relationship of trust with regulatory agencies and the public.*
- A. If required, have the project proponent hire a qualified biological monitor in coordination with the NBVC ED biologists, for all proposed actions that require active avoidance or that may affect threatened or endangered species, wetlands (including vernal pools), or require active revegetation, or require habitat compensation. The qualified biological monitor would educate workers, oversee and implement impact avoidance and minimization measures, document impacts, and guide revegetation efforts.
 - B. Ensure compliance with the MBTA.

Objective: Plan conservation measures to avoid or minimize effects on natural resources first, then compensate for unavoidable effects.

- I. Improve the success of mitigation and enhancement projects based on regulatory, functional, and ecosystem criteria.
 - A. Use this INRMP as an initial screen for review of projects proposed on the installation from both Navy and outside interests. All proposals should provide the following information regarding natural resources:
 1. The acres of habitat currently present on the site based on the most current vegetation map for the installation.
 2. The natural resources on or adjacent to the site which can be obtained from the NBVC ED GIS specialist.
 3. A natural resource review should still only be one part of a project-by-project review conducted for each proposal.
 - B. Require performance work statements that detail project activity work plans, quality control standards, and funding.
 - C. Use standardized scopes of work for recurring work.

- II. Ensure that all necessary permits are obtained for restoration projects or ensure they are part of the restoration banking package, such as USACE Section 404 permit (federal), CCC, 1603 section permit CDFG, and possibly NPDES permits for discharges into WOUS ([RWQCB 2004](#)).
 - A. Provide clear direction on how to exercise a USACE Nationwide Permit to facilitate project work.
 - 1. When possible, combine multiple projects under one permit with one public contact period.
 - 2. Prescribe project BMPs.
 - 3. Describe project activities including BMPs in a letter to the USACE to notify them of the project. This may negate the need for public notification and would streamline consultation.
- III. Ensure NBVC Port Hueneme operations, activities, projects, and programs are consistent to the maximum extent practicable, with Coastal Zone Plans, as authorized by the CZMA (OPNAVINST 5090.1C).
 - A. Cooperate with state regulatory agencies in resolving concerns identified during the consistency review process.
- IV. Implement seasonal avoidance measures as project conditions to avoid disturbance that may cause harm, harassment, or severe damage to native species and habitats.
- V. Implement standard conservation measures for all proposed actions unless a determination can be made in consultation with the NBVC ED, that they are not appropriate.
 - A. Require that proposed actions include measures for impact avoidance and minimization. Most regulatory authorizations require demonstration of maximum impact avoidance and minimization before authorization may be given.
 - 1. Avoidance of impacts should be the priority.
 - 2. Minimize remaining impacts.
 - 3. Consider off-site compensation for damaged resources as a last resort.
 - 4. Require for all standard operating procedures, work requests, and contracts during planning, an environmental protection plan that outlines mitigation and avoidance measures, and can include:

- a.* Worker environmental protection briefings;
 - b.* Signs, markers, protective fencing;
 - c.* Biological monitoring;
 - d.* Erosion and sedimentation prevention;
 - e.* Noise baffling; and,
 - f.* Temporary impact restoration.
- B.* Consider indirect and less tangible direct effects of all proposed actions, in and outside of project boundaries, and mitigate accordingly.
 - 1.* Outdoor lighting may require shielding;
 - 2.* Noise associated with construction may affect nesting birds or other species and require that project activities occur outside nesting season;
 - 3.* Increased access by vehicles or off-road vehicles may require defined routes, parking areas and landscape mitigation;
 - 4.* Increased use by humans or pets of natural areas adjacent new or renovated facilities may require protective signs or barriers;
 - 5.* Invasive plant introductions may occur as a result of construction activities and may be mitigated with additional BMPs;
 - 6.* Herbicides or fertilizer overspray or runoff may threaten viability of native species and may require scheduling to avoid windy days, or limit usage to areas far from natural habitats;
 - 7.* Irrigation runoff may introduce pollutants into WOUS, increase erosion, or promote weeds and require installation or alteration of flow meters and timers;
 - 8.* Pesticides, oil, grease and gasoline runoff may introduce pollutants into WOUS and require BMPs as detailed in the NBVC Port Hueneme SWPPP;

9. Shading from new facilities or landscaping may negatively affect native plant species;
 10. Erosion and sedimentation from project activities may increase and require additional BMPs as detailed in the SWPPP;
 11. Operation and maintenance of new facilities may result in harassment to native wildlife; and,
 12. Wetland hydrology may be impacted by additional hardscape in the vicinity, or alterations of surface flow, and may require mitigative actions to restore pre-project flows.
- C. Where applicable, conduct surveys for presence or absence of potential federally threatened or endangered species using survey guidelines developed by or acceptable to the USFWS.
- D. Require that all actions that require active habitat restoration, enhancement, and/or compensation must have an appropriate restoration plan developed and approved by the NBVC ED, prior to implementation.
1. All such plans must discuss the site conditions, methods to be implemented, monitoring and maintenance (usually 3-5 years), success criteria, remedial actions if expected success is not being achieved, and reporting requirements.
 2. The plans must ensure that all applicable requirements of regulatory approvals are incorporated. Often, regulatory agencies require that they have an opportunity to review and approve plans where their authorization for resource impacts is provided. Review and approval of plans must be accomplished through the site approval process.
- E. Develop and maintain a reference catalog of past avoidance, mitigation, and compensatory measures that have been used, and a system for ongoing evaluation of their effectiveness, to effectively track success of measures employed.
- F. Catalog and track mitigation sites by maintaining records of all mitigation sites and the status and phases of each.

4.6 CONSISTENCY WITH OTHER PLANS

Consistency with California Wildlife Action Plan

Congress asked each state to develop a Wildlife Action Plan (WAP) to examine the health of wildlife and prescribe actions to conserve wildlife and vital habitat before they become rarer and more costly to protect. In response, the CDFG developed the California WAP. The WAP provides for the conservation of species and their habitats and recommends conservation actions that address stressors to habitats. It calls for federal-state partnerships and partnerships with Non-Governmental Organizations and a multitude of institutions in California with a stake in wildlife, land, and aquatic management. The WAP provides guidance to these partnering institutions by identifying wildlife and habitat conservation goals and information needs at a strategic level.

The INRMP management strategies are consistent with a number of Statewide and South Coast region-specific conservation actions:

- NBVC works with a number of local, state, and federal agencies and non-profits on a number of statewide and regional conservation management efforts.
- NBVC has an active Integrated Pest Management Program and coordinates with other agencies to improve effectiveness through information sharing and landscape planning efforts.
- NBVC seeks encroachment buffer opportunities and works with state, federal, and conservation organizations.
- NBVC considers natural resources conservation education a high priority in managing natural resources.
- NBVC has started to consider the most current projections of the effects of global warming in their conservation planning and ecosystem restoration work.
- NBVC seeks to adequately fund projects and staff to sufficiently manage sensitive species and important wildlife habitats on its installations.

Other Regional Planning Efforts [Table 1-1](#) lists other planning documents from a variety of sources also detailed in [Section 1.13](#), Integrating Other Plans. NBVC would also participate in any Landscape Conservation Cooperatives or Population Vulnerability Assessments, as applicable.

Management Strategy

Objective: Collaborate where appropriate on regional plans that may have an impact on the natural resources of NBVC Port Hueneme.

- I. Develop and maintain collaborative resource planning relationships, as detailed in [Section 4.4](#), Beneficial Partnerships and Collaborative Resources Planning.

4.6.1 Consistency with Integrated Cultural Resource Management Plan

Specific Concerns

- The management of natural resources has the potential to negatively impact cultural resources; conversely, the management of cultural resources has the potential to negatively impact natural resources.

Current Management

The SA/PRB provides the primary planning mechanism for projects conducted by the Natural Resource program to be reviewed by other programs such as Cultural Resources. An Integrated Cultural Resource Management Plan (ICRMP) for NBVC is currently being developed. This ICRMP includes NBVC Port Hueneme in its planning footprint and is intended to provide strategic guidance to NBVC to support a conservation and stewardship program for historic and archaeological resources present on property owned or controlled by the Navy. The cultural resource conservation and stewardship program enables NBVC to comply with DoD cultural resource instructions such as DoDINST 4715.16 Cultural Resources Management, EOs such as EO 11593 Protection and Enhancement of the Cultural Environment, and cultural resource laws including but not limited to the American Antiquities Act, Archaeological Resources Protection Act, Archaeological and Historic Preservation Act, NHPA, and the Historic Sites Act. Cultural resource management activities encompassed in the ICRMP include access restrictions to archaeological sites and surveys of historic and archaeological resources.

Assessment of Current ManagementThe SA/PRB process reviews all projects that may affect sensitive natural or cultural resources at NBVC Port Hueneme and sufficiently protects cultural and historical resources. There is potential that maintenance landscape activities may not be submitted for review or assessed through the SA/PRB. The Cultural Resource program should review landscaping or exotic removal projects that occur in or near the Bard Estate grounds. GIS files and maps of Bard Estate cultural resources should be provided during the project planning phase, to avoid impacts to the historic landscape.

Management Strategy

Objective: Coordinate management activities between the cultural and natural resource management programs when a natural resource management activity impacts, or has the potential to impact, a cultural resource.

- II. Continue to participate in the SA/PRB to ensure communication and coordination between the natural and cultural resource management programs when natural resource management program activities have the potential to impact cultural resources.

4.7 REMEDIATION OF CONTAMINATED MEDIA

Per OPNAVINST 5090.1C, Navy policy relative to IRP sites requires every effort must be made to ensure that Navy projects are not constructed on contaminated sites. If contamination is discovered during the planning stages of a project or during construction, careful project controls must be in place to ensure proper investigation and clean-up procedures are followed.

The IRP site types at NBVC Port Hueneme consist of industrial waste treatment waste, landfill or disposal areas, improper storage or maintenance areas, contaminated soil or sediment, underground storage tanks (UST), above ground storage, and Petroleum, Oil, Lubricants (POL) lines. The major IRP sites at NBVC Port Hueneme consist of a 33-acre site on the western edge of the base, fuel farm, burning pit, sewage pits, paint storage yard, railroad oil spills, USTs, above ground storage, POL lines, and the harbor and canals ([Onyx Group 2006](#)).

At NBVC Port Hueneme 31 sites are in various phases of the CERCLA process; active CERCLA sites are identified on [Map 4-1](#).

The drainage channels at NBVC Port Hueneme have been designated as IRP Site 19A due to present contamination by nonpoint source pollution and past contamination from spills and leaks into storm sewers on base. A scoping-level ecological risk assessment was conducted for the ditches during the preparation of a draft risk evaluation for IRP Site 19 that indicated the potential for negative impacts to ecological receptors due to exposure to contaminants in the drainage channels ([PRC 1995b](#)). Since then, a remedial investigation of Site 19A has been completed ([ChaduxTt 2010](#)) and a feasibility study has been initiated. A remedial investigation at IRP Site 19 is in progress. Once feasibility studies for both sites are completed, one proposed plan and ROD will be prepared for Sites 19A and Site 19.

In 1994, four bioremediation systems were installed to test the effectiveness of groundwater circulation wells designed to prevent MTBE-contaminated groundwater from reaching the harbor or contaminating other aquifers. One large system was placed at a source of contamination for source removal. Three smaller units were installed perpendicular to the flow, downgrade from the source, to remediate and contain the contaminated water ([Tetra Tech 1999](#)).

MAP 4-1: ACTIVE CERCLA SITES

Specific Concerns

- Contaminated media found in soils, groundwater, and surface water can lead to impairment of human health and the environment.
- If coordination does not occur with NBVC ED Resources Manager during the IRP site remediation process, use and introduction of non-native landscaping and invasive vegetation could occur at IRP sites.

Current Management

- Cleanup or remediation of CERCLA and Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA) sites is regulated by several state and federal statutes. The primary laws that apply, or may apply in some instances, are listed in [Appendix C](#). The most important of these is the Porter-Cologne Water Quality Control Act, which is the basis of the California Water Code.
- Similarly, several different federal, state, and local governmental or regulatory agencies have official responsibility for issues involving contaminated media, as shown in Table 4-2. The lead agencies are the RWQCB, EPA, and USACE. The Navy has a major role in the CERCLA process, as the lead agency in conjunction with federal and state agencies to ensure contaminated media are remediated.

TABLE 4-2: FEDERAL AND STATE STATUTES AFFECTING MANAGEMENT OF CONTAMINATED MEDIA

Clean Water Act	California Water Code, Division 7
Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899	California Health and Safety Code
Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuaries Act	California Fish and Game Code
National Environmental Policy Act	California Environmental Quality Act
Fish and Wildlife Act	California Food and Agricultural Code
National Historic Preservation Act	California Harbor and Navigation Code
Endangered Species Act	California Coastal Zone Management Act

The Navy's policy on cleanup of identified CERCLA and RCRA sites where contamination has been identified is that the source must be controlled before cleanup, the cleanup must be risk-based and have site specific cleanup goals, and the monitoring criteria for any monitoring plan must be established before the first sample is collected.

NBVC Port Hueneme recognizes that adverse impacts to natural resources described in this INRMP may result from the release of hazardous substances, pollutants, and contaminants into the environment. The Navy IRP is responsible for identifying CERCLA releases, RCRA

releases, and releases under related provisions; considering risks and assessing impacts to human health and the environment, including impacts to endangered species, migratory birds, and biotic communities; and developing and selecting response actions when a release may result in an unacceptable risk to human health and the environment.

NBVC Port Hueneme follows management strategy pursuant to the Navy's INRMP Guidance (Navy 2006). When appropriate, the regional or installation's natural resources management staff will help the IRP Remedial Project Manager (RPM) identify potential impacts to natural resources caused by the release of these contaminants.

Regional or installation natural resources staff will also participate, as appropriate, in the IRP decision-making process by communicating natural resource issues on the installation to the RPM, attending Restoration Advisory Board meetings, reviewing and commenting on IRP documents (e.g., Remedial Investigation, Ecological Risk Assessment), and ensuring that response actions, to the maximum extent practical, are undertaken in a manner that minimizes impacts to natural resources on the installation.

When appropriate, the regional or installation natural resources staff will make recommendations to the IRP RPM regarding clean up strategies and site restoration. During initial monitoring protocols, the natural resources manager may suggest sampling and testing be accomplished so as to not impact sensitive or critical areas. Also during site restoration, the natural resources manager has the opportunity to recommend site restoration practices that are outlined in the INRMP. Examples include, landfill caps restored to grasslands, excavation areas restored to wetland/pond areas, and treated water located to enhance a pond area.

Assessment of Current Management

The CERCLA and RCRA programs are effective at remediation of contaminated media. Management of IRP sites should continue to coordinate with NBVC ED natural resource managers. During planning for site restoration, coordination with NBVC ED should occur when restoration plans involve revegetation, to ensure NBVC-approved native landscaping is used.

Management Strategy

Objective: Prevent or minimize impacts from contaminated media to ecological receptors.

- I. Continue to coordinate with the CERCLA program to ensure that remedial site designs do not conflict with policies stated in this INRMP.
 - A. NBVC ED should coordinate on site remediation restoration plans that include revegetation, to ensure invasive non-natives are not used.
 - B. Continue to update GIS database of natural resources to support remediation planning.
 - C. Continue to integrate baseline ecological surveys into preparedness planning.

4.8 OIL SPILL RESPONSE AND HAZARDOUS SUBSTANCE PREVENTION AND CLEANUP

Oil spill prevention and response are regulated under the federal Water Pollution Control Act of 1972 (33 USC 1251, *et seq.*), as amended by the CWA of 1977, and the Oil Pollution Prevention Act (OPPA) of 1990. Under the CWA, Natural Resource Trustees are authorized to recover damages for injury to, destruction of or loss of natural resources resulting from a discharge or the substantial threat of discharge, of oil into navigable waters. Hazardous substances other than oil are addressed by CERCLA (42 USC 9601, *et seq.*), which authorizes Natural Resource Trustees to recover damages for injury to, destruction of or loss of natural resources resulting from the release of a hazardous substance. At the state level, the Office of Spill Prevention and Response (OSPR) was formed in 1990 with the passage of Senate Bill 2040. OSPR is responsible for protecting California's natural resources by preventing, preparing for, and responding to spills of oil and other deleterious materials, and through restoring and enhancing affected resources. Federal and state regulations and laws are detailed in [Appendix C](#).

The U.S. Coast Guard (USCG) is the lead agency for oil spill prevention and response, and is authorized to direct state and local agencies in controlling pollution in bays and coastal waters. The CDFG normally leads wildlife response during a spill in California.

NOAA is assigned responsibility for Natural Resource Damage Assessment (NRDA) from spills, and the Navy has adopted NOAA procedures for damage assessment (15 CFR 990). Similarly, the USDOJ is in charge of damage assessment for hazardous substance spills under EO 12580. The baseline condition of the natural resources and services that would have existed had the oil or hazardous substance release not occurred is estimated using historical data, reference data, control data or data on incremental changes, alone or in combination, as appropriate. Navy guidance (OPNAVINST 5090.1C) suggests that this information may be obtained from INRMPs, NEPA Documents, or special studies. NAVFAC Southwest has developed an Ephemeral Data Collection Plan in support of NRDA ([Robilliard et al. 1997](#)). Immediately during and after a spill, data will be collected to evaluate the injury. Examples include macro invertebrate surveys, water and sediment samples, and vegetation surveys. Following federal guidelines, this is often done cooperatively with the responsible party, and with fellow trustee agencies. The NAVFAC plan identifies specific locations, methodologies, and responsibilities for data collection.

Specific Concerns

- Cumulative effects of small, medium, and large oil spills from boats, personal watercraft, and ships can contaminate Port Hueneme Harbor and affect natural resources.
- Coordinated planning for oil spill cleanup activities should be integrated with conservation priorities of this INRMP.

- There is a need to incorporate planning for NRDA under both federal and state oil spill prevention regulation, and to establish a quantitative baseline to support natural resources management decisions, habitat mitigation and enhancement planning, and sustainability planning.
- Oil spills most notably affects marine birds and marine mammals, but also exerts damaging effects on plankton and other organisms either directly or indirectly through habitat damage. The size of an oil spill doesn't necessarily correlate with the amount of damage it can do. Even small spills can have big consequences for birds if the oil contaminates an area where large numbers of seabirds are rafting or foraging (Bunn *et al.* 2008).

Current Management

NBVC Port Hueneme's storage and transfer operations have the potential for a discharge of oil onto land or into navigable waters that could cause substantial harm to the environment, including injury to fish and wildlife and sensitive areas. Operational efficiency and safety of personnel and equipment, and Federal, State, and Navy regulations require that a plan exist to effectively respond to oil and hazardous substance spills.

Oil and hazardous substance spill prevention and response planning requirements include the National Contingency Plan, Area Contingency Plan (ACP), Spill Prevention Control and Countermeasure Plan, Federal Facility Response Plans, State of California Oil Spill Contingency Plan, Navy Instructions, Additional Emergency Response Planning, and an Integrated Contingency Plan (ICP). NBVC Port Hueneme operates within the guidelines of the USCG, EPA, and the State of California under the *Los Angeles/Long Beach ACP* published in January 2006. Agency notification and coordination protocols are outlined in this plan.

Facilities that handle or store hazardous substances, the release of which could endanger health and human safety and adversely impact the environment, must comply with additional federal regulations that govern emergency planning, notification, and response. These requirements are part of the RCRA, CERCLA, and the Emergency Planning and Community Right-to-Know Act regulations contained in 40 CFR Part 264, 40 CFR Part 302, and 40 CFR Part 355, respectively. The Occupational Safety and Health Administration has regulations governing emergency response and planning. Applicable requirements contained in 29 CFR Part 1910 are addressed in the NBVC ICP (SAIC 2007).

At NBVC Port Hueneme, as a preventative measure, all ships that enter NBVC wharves, with the exception of ships that dock for only a few hours, are surrounded by oil booms until they leave the port. Spill response drills are conducted annually, to ensure NBVC staff are trained and prepared in spill response and protocol.

Assessment of Current Management

Oil spill response and hazardous substance prevention and cleanup are effectively managed by the implementation of federal and state plans listed above. The collection and maintenance of ecological information required by OPNAVINST 5090.1C (Chapter 24) are essential to pre-incident planning on behalf of the Navy's Regional Environmental Coordinator. NBVC ED should continue to support planning and response readiness by maintaining the natural resource survey and GIS databases. If there is a spill, coordination with NOAA/NMFS should occur prior to using dispersants, to determine management actions that are species and habitat-specific.

Management Strategy

Objective: Support the effectiveness of prevention and response planning.

- I. Continue to integrate the protection priorities of this INRMP into contingency spill response and NRDA planning.
 - A. Continue to update GIS layers of natural resources to support preparedness planning.
 - B. Continue to integrate baseline ecological surveys into preparedness planning.
 - C. Integrate invasive exotic species response planning with oil spill contingency plans.
 - D. Continue to have NBVC and ED staff participate in the annual spill training exercise.

4.9 HARBOR OPERATIONS

The Port of Hueneme is owned in part by the Oxnard Harbor District; the Navy owns the remaining dock space, Wharf 1 and 2. The Oxnard Harbor District owns and operates approximately 69 acres of land in the harbor area and adjacent fishing channel. Wharf 3 is under a joint use agreement between the Navy and Oxnard Harbor District. The Port of Hueneme is the only deep-water commercial harbor port between Los Angeles and San Francisco. Importing primarily occurs through the commercial portion of the harbor. In 1986, 627,700 revenue metric tons came through the port. By 2008, up to 1,497,853 revenue metric tons came through the port, with a decrease in recent years due to the effects of the recession ([Tetra Tech 2011f](#)).

Commercial traffic through the Port of Hueneme is controlled and organized by Oxnard Harbor District in collaboration with NBVC Port Operations. Commodities shipped through the port include bananas, automobiles, oil products, lumber, fish, livestock, wood pulp, liquid fertilizer, and other agricultural products. The Port of Hueneme is the import center for GAPS automobiles in Southern California. Vehicles from Europe, Asia and Australia are brought through the port. Bananas and other fruits and wood pulp are large-scale commodities that go through the harbor. The Port of Hueneme serves as the principle staging area for supplies, equipment, and crews for the oil platforms located in the Santa Barbara Channel. The newest commodity to be imported through the port is liquid fertilizer, which comes in bulk tankers. Numerous commercial fishing boats also enter and exit Oxnard Harbor District.

Specific Concerns

- Activities that occur in the Port of Hueneme Harbor, whether conducted by Oxnard Harbor District and commercial boat operators, or the Navy, have the potential to affect the water quality and ecological integrity of marine waters.
- Unauthorized release of water from ship ballasts and bilges could be a potential source of pollutants and invasive species.
- Harbor dredging operations could disturb nesting migratory birds or kelp bed habitat.
- Harbor infrastructure maintenance could result in the discharge of pollutants, negatively affecting water quality and the sea floor.

Current Management

NBVC Port Operations manages incoming and outgoing harbor traffic. Projects in the harbor go thru the SA/PRB process. The Harbor is under regulatory authority of the following federal and state agencies: USACE, NOAA-NMFS, EPA, USFWS, LARWQCB and CCC. The USACE is the primary permitting authority, implementing requirements of Section 404 of the CWA and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act. Any project with potential impacts to EFH requires consultation with NMFS. The Navy must incorporate into project plans, NMFS recommendations for conservation practices that minimize, offset, or avoid impacts to EFH. See [Section 3.6.2 Aquatic Invasives](#) for discussion of aquatic invasives management.

Assessment of Current Management

NBVC Port Operations, the SA/PRB process, and federal and state regulations ensure effective management of harbor waters and the natural resources that occupy them.

Management Strategy

None needed, as the harbor is not managed by NBVC ED.

4.10 CONSTRUCTION, FACILITY AND UTILITIES MAINTENANCE

Specific Concerns

- Construction and facility maintenance projects may result in the incidental take of avifauna, such as bird nests, and direct mortality of less mobile species such as small mammals and herpetiles.
- Construction and facility maintenance projects may result in the introduction or spread of terrestrial invasive exotic plant species that may be transported in materials or on equipment.

- Erosion control measures may be eliminated from a project as a cost-cutting measure.

Current Management

By EO, the President has directed that federal agencies shall design, use, or promote construction practices that minimize adverse effects on the natural habitat where cost-effective and to the extent practicable (EO 13112). Several other laws are pertinent: CWA, CAA, ESA, NEPA, and Soil Conservation Act. Routine maintenance activities that may affect drainages fall under the USACE authority from Section 404 of the CWA.

Future use patterns focus on maximizing efficiency of existing spaces by upgrading current facilities and infrastructure. The NBVC Proposed Land Use Plan depicts a long-range framework for development, renovation and consolidation within the existing land use pattern, rebuilding in existing developed footprints and thus reducing the need to break new ground (Onyx Group 2006).

NBVC ED is consulted from project inception, through the SA/PRB, to avoid delays in project schedule and minimize adverse environmental effects.

Assessment of Current Management

The goals of renovation and consolidation stated in the NBVC Proposed Land Use Plan, and SA/PRB, are adequate to avoid and minimize potential impacts to natural resources from construction and facility maintenance and upgrades. Potential exists however, for activities to disrupt nesting birds, or contribute to soil erosion. BMPs and processes by which to avoid bird disturbance and soil erosion are further addressed in [Section 3.4.4](#), Birds; [Section 3.2.3.2](#), Surface and Stormwater Management; and [Section 3.2.2](#), Soils and Soil Conservation.

Management Strategy

Objective: Conduct construction and facility maintenance in a way that allows for protection of sensitive environmental resources while ensuring accomplishment of the military mission.

- I. Ensure continued use of the SA/PRB to avoid and minimize potential impacts to native habitats and species.
 - a. Ensure that new construction or reconstruction of facilities on or near coastal areas meet the requirements detailed in the federal CZMA and CCA for construction in the coastal zone ([Map 2-1](#) and [Appendix C](#)).
- II. Ensure impacts to migratory birds are avoided during project implementation.
 - a. The MBTA requires that federal agencies coordinate with USFWS if a construction or site activity would result in the take of a migratory bird. If construction or clearing activities are scheduled during nesting season (March 15 through September 15), NBVC ED should be consulted to conduct surveys to

identify potential active nests. If construction activities would result in the take of a migratory bird, then coordination with USFWS and the NBVC ED should occur, and applicable permits obtained prior to construction or clearing activities.

- b. If possible, schedule all building demolition to occur during the non-nesting season to avoid possible delays or accidental take of migratory birds.

III. Ensure water resources are protected.

- a. Implement BMPs at construction sites for controlling soil erosion from wind and water transport, as outlined in the *California Stormwater Best Management Practices Handbook* (Caltrans 2000), and SWPPP for NBVC Port Hueneme.
- b. Monitor and enforce compliance with stated BMPs.
- c. Obtain necessary regulatory permits, as related to CWA regulations.

4.11 LANDSCAPING AND GROUNDS MAINTENANCE

The main urbanized area of NBVC Port Hueneme consists of residential, industrial, community service, administrative, and recreation uses. This area contains various turf and landscaping improvements. The most significantly landscaped area on base is the Bard Estate, which includes a unique collection of exotic ornamental species planted by Thomas R. Bard from 1871 to 1915. Plants from many parts of the world including India, New Caledonia, Japan, China, Brazil, and Australia cover the 15 to 20-acre estate area. Some native California species are also present. A list of plant species documented at the Bard Estate is in [Appendix L](#). Other landscaped areas on base are “improved” areas that include family housing lawns, golf course fairways and greens, and other small areas. Many introduced and native species have been used for landscaping in the improved areas, and include varieties of coniferous and broadleaf trees, lawn grasses, shrubs, vines, and colorful flowers used to decorate building surroundings. Landscaped areas at NBVC Port Hueneme, especially the Bard Estate grounds, shelterbelts and windrows, and the Seabee Golf Course, provide important habitat for native bird species and other wildlife species because these areas serve as ecological islands in an urban environment ([Siena College–Audubon International Institute 1997](#)).

Specific Concerns

- The Grounds Maintenance Contract needs to be evaluated for consistency with recent EOs or Navy policy.
- The Base Exterior Architecture Plan should be evaluated for consistency with respect to landscaping recommendations herein.
- Landscaping practices have the potential to disrupt nesting birds or monarch butterflies.

- Potential exists along the west and southwestern border of the base, to enhance the aesthetic and ecological value of the area with the installation of native plants in bare areas, and replacement of ornamentals with native species in others. This would increase the visual barrier and provide additional nesting, roosting and forage for avifauna, and promoting positive community relations and the goals of force protection and privacy.
- Opportunities exist at the urban-natural area interface, to create or enhance buffers with native plant species.
- Grounds maintenance activities have the potential to negatively impact natural resources on base, through the use of fertilizers and pesticides.
- The golf course presents an opportunity to create additional wildlife, using native plants and xeriscaping.

Current Management

Maintenance of semi-developed and developed grounds is accomplished at NBVC Port Hueneme with technical assistance from staff in NBVC ED. Landscaping and grounds keeping work occurs primarily in the Community Support, Housing, and Administrative land use areas at NBVC Port Hueneme ([Map 1-2](#)) ([Tetra Tech 2011j](#)). The historic landscape at Bard Estate is protected under the National Historic Act of 1966, as amended. It is anticipated that future native plant landscaping will be developed to accompany facility renovations and improvements at NBVC Port Hueneme.

Future landscaping at NBVC Port Hueneme will follow the guidance set forth in the NBVC Smart Landscape Master Plan and Approved Plant List ([Navy 2008](#)). The purpose of the list is to provide a clear set of approved landscaping plants that are known to not be invasive in the NBVC Port Hueneme region. The NBVC Approved Landscaping Plant List is in [Appendix K](#) and also includes plants that are prohibited from use under any circumstances. This plan requires that a minimum of 80% native plants are used for landscaping projects. However, all landscape designs and plant lists shall be reviewed and approved by NBVC ED and the NAVFAC Landscape Architect in the planning stages of project design.

NBVC supports the goals of EO 13148 (21 April 2000) *Greening the Government Through Leadership in Environmental Management* and promotes the President's 26 April 1994 *Memorandum on Environmentally Beneficial Landscaping*. It is Navy policy to:

1. Use regionally native plants for landscaping.
2. Design, use and promote construction practices that minimize adverse effects on natural habitat.
3. Prevent pollution by reducing fertilizer and pesticide use, integrated pest management practices, recycling green waste (composting) and minimizing runoff.

4. Implement water-efficient practices, use efficient irrigation systems and recycled water, and use landscaping to conserve energy.
5. Create additional demonstration projects to promote awareness of environmental and economic benefits of these practices.

The NBVC Smart Landscape Master Plan focuses on resource conservation through creative and appropriate landscape design and management. The plan is designed to reduce the consumption of all resources including irrigation water, labor, materials (fuel, pesticides and fertilizers) and the transportation and disposal of green waste (clippings and prunings). The fundamentals of smart landscaping can be summarized in seven steps—planning and design, low water use plants, limited turf areas, efficient irrigation, soil improvement, mulches, and sound maintenance (Navy 2008).

Assessment of Current Management

Use of the NBVC Smart Landscape Master Plan and its Approved Plant List satisfies compliance with EOs and Navy policy. The guidelines provided in the NBVC Smart Landscape Master Plan should be updated as needed when changes occur to the goals and strategies of the water conservation efforts under the Energy Showcase Program, the Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan, or the Integrated Pest Management Plan.

The vegetative structure of landscaped areas is particularly important to wildlife and must be considered when maintaining these landscaped areas or when developing new landscaping for the base. Native plants require less irrigation and maintenance than ornamental species, and are the preferred food resource for native pollinators and birds. Exotic ornamentals have the potential to escape and spread into natural areas, which then require costs for removal.

Coordination must occur with NBVC ED and the NAVFAC Landscape Architect in the early phases of planning to determine site specific needs and constraints. Other species may be used for landscaping but must be approved by NBVC ED and the NAVFAC Landscape Architect prior to producing site plans or scopes of work. These species must be screened through regional invasive plant lists. The plant list may be updated periodically, due to additions or changes to regional invasive species lists. Prior to initiating a project, please obtain the most recent list from NBVC ED.

Management Strategy

Objective: Sustainably improve the visual and aesthetic environment of NBVC Port Hueneme, while maintaining the integrity and character of natural and cultural resources.

- I. Comply with cultural and environmental laws, EOs, and Navy policies.
 - a. Ensure mowing, use of rodenticides, and other grounds keeping practices are consistent with the IPMP, the SWPPP, EPA regulations on herbicides near

wetlands, terms of USACE permits, mitigation obligations, BOs, EISs and any other legal agreements or natural resource management plans.

- i. Ensure that these requirements are communicated to grounds keeping staff.
 - ii. All NBVC Port Hueneme contracts related to grounds maintenance should include language that promotes implementation of the INRMP.
 - b. Coordinate with NBVC Cultural Resources Program Manager before starting any landscaping project at Bard Estate, or other cultural sites, to make sure no cultural resources will be negatively affected.
 - c. Continue to update the NBVC Port Hueneme Approved Plant List to reflect changes in regional invasive species lists.
 - d. Coordinate with NBVC ED for questions, comments, or concerns regarding landscaping before a project is submitted.
- II. Implement sustainable landscape guidelines set forth in the NBVC Smart Landscape Master Plan.
 - a. Use urban planning designs such as LID landscape design concepts to benefit the human working environment by moderating environmental influences (e.g. solar heat gain, glare, dust, and wind), conserving energy, protecting water quality, preventing soil erosion, reducing glare, buffering noise, improving visual aesthetics, providing wildlife habitat, and unifying exterior spaces.
 - b. New lawns are discouraged except where functionally essential such as formal areas used for ceremonies, family housing, recreation fields, and children's playgrounds. Replacing turf with native and drought tolerant plants in combination with rocks or gravel over bare areas will promote the goals of the water conservation program and meet the needs of dust control.
 - c. Contribute to NBVC Port Hueneme water conservation efforts.
 - i. Reduce water usage by implementing xeriscaping concepts, using mulch, performing regular maintenance and upgrades to irrigation systems.
 - ii. Give priority to landscape improvement projects that will reduce water usage and help meet water conservation goals.

- d. Minimize the use of pesticides and herbicides in landscape management.
 - i. Be consistent with existing NAVFACINSTs on Integrated Pest Management guidance (OPNAVINST 6250.4B 1998) and continue to follow the Integrated Pest Management Plan to effectively deal with pest problems at NBVC Port Hueneme.
- III. Consider the connectivity of landscaped areas to stormwater runoff conveyances and wetlands when planning for new or replacement plantings, to ensure compatibility with natural resource objectives.
- IV. Avoid groundskeeping practices that may negatively affect migratory and resident birds or sensitive invertebrate species.
 - a. Conduct tree trimming outside nesting season, between September 15 and March 15, to comply with the MBTA.
 - i. Trimming or removal that must occur during the nesting season, due to a safety hazard or mission critical needs, will require a pre-activity survey by NBVC ED to determine that active nests will not be affected.
- V. Augment goals of force protection by incorporating landscaping into physical barriers surrounding buildings, and visual protection barriers between NBVC Port Hueneme and adjacent property boundaries, or between high security areas.
 - a. Use landscape planters to create a physical barrier between vehicles and structures at the specified distance as required under new security restrictions following the September 11, 2001, terrorist attack.
 - b. Use native trees and shrubs to block all undesirable views, noise, and lights, and provide privacy.

4.12 LEASES AND REAL ESTATE OUTGRANTS

Specific Concerns

- Stormwater runoff from paved surfaces in leased areas could be negatively impacted if appropriate SWPPP BMPs are not in place.
- Erosion control measures may be eliminated from projects as a cost-cutting measure.
- Activities of lessees have potential to affect natural resources.

Current Management

NBVC ED is involved in the management of leased lands, similarly to how they manage all other lands on the installation: all proposed projects on leased land must go through the SA/PRB screening process and receive a site approval from local and regional Navy. As necessary, BMPs are required of the project to protect soil integrity and water quality. This project screening process is a streamlined means for project sponsors to comply with NEPA, and the laws, regulations and guidelines described above. [Section 4.5](#) Regulatory Compliance further describes the SA/PRB process.

Assessment of Current Management

The SA/PRB project review process adequately ensures that base improvement projects and activities conducted by lessees satisfy all environmental regulations. Potential exists however, for lessees to be unaware of the various land use protocols outlined in this INRMP.

Management Strategy

Objective: Ensure that all activities of lessees are in accordance with federal environmental regulations, EOs, and guidance outlined in this INRMP.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to avoid and minimize potential impacts, and project timing is scheduled to avoid conflicts with sensitive natural resources.
 - a. Ensure project plans are in accordance with the principles and guidance stated in this INRMP.
 - b. Support enforcement of implementation of BMPs as required by permits, regulatory authorities, and the SA/PRB.
- II. Ensure that protocols for responding to trapped or injured wildlife are communicated to lessees, as outlined in [Section 4.3](#), Environmental Awareness.
- III. Ensure landscaping activities of lessees is in line with the objectives and strategies stated in [Section 4.11](#), Landscaping and Grounds Maintenance.

4.13 RECREATION AND PUBLIC ACCESS

There is no current recreation plan in place for NBVC Port Hueneme. However, the MWR Department manages recreational use on base for NBVC personnel. Additionally, opportunities for civilian recreation exist at NBVC Port Hueneme. Recreational areas at NBVC Port Hueneme include the golf course and driving range, a playing field, a park, track and field facilities, softball fields, limited bicycle trails, and a recreational vehicle park. There are no allowable recreational uses of the shoreline or harbor. There are currently no areas set aside for wildlife viewing.

NBVC Port Hueneme Golf Course is located on the eastern side of the base, adjacent to Channel Islands Boulevard. Encompassing 118.51 acres, the golfing green is separated into two parts by Patterson Avenue. The golf course is an 18-hole course with a driving range (approximately 8 acres, which is not included in the acreage given above), chipping green, putting green, five lakes, and night lighting (Tetra Tech 1999).

The golf course is open to base personnel and the public. About 30 to 40 percent of the users are civilians. Usually there are about 45,000-50,000 rounds per year played. Several tournaments are held each year at NBVC Port Hueneme Golf Course. Military clubs that hold regular events at the golf course include the Men's Golf Association and the Women's Golf Association. About two civilian tournaments are held per month; the groups that hold these must have a military sponsor (Tetra Tech 1999).

Major recreational areas surrounding NBVC Port Hueneme include city, county, and state beaches; McGrath and Mugu State Parks; and bicycle/hiking trails.

Specific Concerns

- Activities associated with the golf course may disturb wildlife populations inhabiting the coyote brush natural area.
- The golf course presents an opportunity to create additional wildlife habitat by using native plants and xeriscaping.

Current Management

DoD installations are to provide for sustained public access and use of natural resources for educational or recreational purposes when such access is compatible with mission activities, and with other considerations such as security, safety, or resources sensitivity (DoD 1996). Recreational access at NBVC Port Hueneme should be compliant with the requirements associated with the provisions of the Americans with Disabilities Act of 1990 as amended, and the Disabled Sportsman Access Act of 1998, as amended. Recreation-related projects that result in ground disturbance are managed through the SA/PRB (NBVCINST 11010.0) to avoid and minimize potential impacts.

Assessment of Current Management

NBVC should continue to ensure that public access is allowed only for temporary uses that are compatible with the Port Hueneme mission, natural resources responsibility, safety, and security.

The golf course presents an opportunity to improve the visual aesthetics of the recreational experience and at the same time, increase the ecological value of this open space area. The golf course landscape design could be modified to include native vegetative buffers at its perimeter and islands of native vegetation throughout its open spaces. Disruptions to wildlife in the

adjacent natural area would be minimized by the increase in vegetative buffer, and the creation of islands would provide additional forage for birds and native pollinators. Landscape modification should occur where appropriate and not in conflict with the recreational goals and values of the golf course. The design should be developed in coordination with the NBVC ED and in accordance with the NBVC Smart Landscaping Plan guidelines. Groundskeeping practices should follow strategies outlined in [Section 4.11](#), Landscaping and Grounds Maintenance.

Management Strategy

Objective: Protect and enhance the ecological value of the golf course area.

- I. Coordinate MWR and NBVC ED staff to identify areas along the golf course perimeter and throughout its core, for planting of native vegetation. See [Section 4.11](#), Landscaping and Grounds Maintenance, for landscaping guidelines.
- II. Increase passive recreation opportunities by installing interpretive signs at vegetated islands and along buffer to natural area, educating on native plant and pollinator species and sustainable landscape design.

4.14 PUBLIC OUTREACH

Specific Concerns

There are no concerns in regards to public outreach efforts as related to natural resources management at Port Hueneme.

Current Management

Public outreach occurs during special events hosted at NBVC Point Mugu, such as Earth Day, where the natural resources of Port Hueneme are discussed.

Assessment of Current Management

The public outreach efforts that occur at special events are adequate at informing the public of the kinds of natural resources present at Port Hueneme, and how they are managed.

Management Strategy

Objective: Support public outreach efforts as they relate to natural resources at Port Hueneme.

- I.* Continue to incorporate discussion of the natural resources that exist at Port Hueneme, and how they are managed, into the topics addressed at the various special events held at NBVC Point Mugu.
- II.* Where appropriate, develop interpretive signs at natural resource areas.

5.0 IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY

5.1 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

A successfully implemented INRMP will:

- Ensure the sustainability of all habitats in NBVC Port Hueneme.
- Ensure no net loss of the capability of NBVC Port Hueneme lands to support the DoD mission.

Formal adoption of an INRMP by a Regional Commander or Installation Commanding Officer constitutes a commitment to seek funding and execute, subject to the availability of funding, all Level 4 projects and activities in accordance with specific timeframes identified in the INRMP. The INRMP is considered implemented if the installation:

1. Actively requests, receives, and uses funds for all Level 4 projects and activities;
2. Ensures that sufficient numbers of professionally trained natural resources management staff are available to perform the tasks required by the INRMP.
3. Coordinates annually with all cooperating offices; and,
4. Documents specific INRMP action accomplishments undertaken each year.

For a description of “Level 4” projects and activities and budget programming hierarchy for this INRMP (both DoD and Navy), see [2](#), Compliance and Stewardship Criteria for Implementing Projects.

Successful implementation of this INRMP will depend upon not only the guidelines set up and projects described, but how well these are translated into performance work statements (who will do what and with what money), project lists and scopes of work, and a workload plan. It must fit into the formal EMS established at NBVC for integrating environmental considerations into day-to-day activities across all levels and functions of Navy enterprise (see [Section 1.10](#), Ecosystem Approach). To accomplish this, NBVC Port Hueneme will need to take advantage of funding opportunities outside normal program boundaries, consistent with authority to receive and use any such funds.

5.1.1 Responsibility

The responsibility for development, revision, and implementation of INRMPs is shared at every level among many different command elements, as described below.

The Chief of Naval Operations (CNO) serves as the principal leader and overall Navy program manager for the development, revision, and implementation of this INRMP. The CNO provides policy, guidance and resources for the development, revision, and implementation of the INRMP and associated NEPA documentation. The CNO approves all INRMP projects prior to submittal to regulatory agencies for signature (Navy 2006).

The Commander of Navy Installations Command (CNIC) reviews the entire INRMP and ensures that installations comply with DoD, Navy, and CNO policy on INRMPs and their associated NEPA documentation. They also ensure the programming of resources necessary to maintain and implement INRMPs, participate in the development and revision of INRMPs, and provide overall program management oversight for all natural resources program elements. CNIC reviews and endorses projects recommended for INRMP implementation prior to submittal for signature, and evaluates and validates EPR-web project proposals (Navy 2006).

Regional Commanders ensure that installations comply with DoD, Navy, and CNO policy on INRMPs and their associated NEPA documentation. They ensure that installations under their control undergo annual reviews and formal five-year evaluations. They ensure the programming of resources necessary to maintain and implement INRMPs, which involves the evaluation and validation of EPR-web based project proposals and the funding of installation natural resources management staff. Navy Region Southwest maintains close liaison with the INRMP signatory partners (USFWS, NOAA and CDFG) and other INRMP stakeholders. They provide endorsement of the INRMP through the Regional Commander signature (Navy 2006).

NAVFAC SW is responsible for providing technical assistance for both compliance and stewardship obligations, and to evaluate and validate requests for funds for natural resource projects. This engineering activity administers the Navy forestry and agricultural outlease budgets, fish and wildlife/hunting and fishing fee and permit projects, contracts, and cooperative agreements. Upon request from CNO/CNIC, NAVFAC SW coordinates natural resources requirements with other federal, state, or local agencies, including the acquisition of INRMP “mutual agreement” between the Navy, USFWS, and state fish and wildlife agencies. NAVFAC SW also maintains natural resources program information needed to satisfy reporting requirements, legislative information requests and to support project requests. This information is collected in the Navy Conservation Website and applicable GIS programs.

Installation COs or Officers-in-Charge (OICs) endorse via signature their INRMPs. Their responsibility is to act as stewards of natural resources under their jurisdiction and integrate natural resources requirements into the day-to-day decision-making process. To accomplish this, they involve appropriate tenant, operational, training, or research and development commands in the INRMP review process to ensure no net loss of military mission. At their discretion they may bring in Navy Judge Advocate General or Office of the General Counsel Legal Counsel to

provide advice and counsel with respect to legal matters related to natural resources management and INRMPs (OPNAVINST 5090.1C).

Formal adoption of an INRMP by a CO or OIC constitutes a commitment to seek funding and execute, subject to the availability of funding, all "must fund" projects and activities in accordance with specific time frames identified in the INRMP. Under the SAIA, any natural resources management activity that is specifically addressed in the INRMP must be implemented (subject to availability of funds). Failure to implement the INRMP is a violation of SAIA and may be source of litigation. Since the SAIA requires implementation of the INRMP, there is a clear fiscal connection between INRMP preparation, revision, implementation and funding. Funding to implement natural resources management will largely come from program sources (through NRSW). Accordingly, it is vital that budget personnel understand and participate in the INRMP process.

A SECNAV memorandum (12 August 1998), stated:

“All projects essential to fulfill the selected alternative (mix of management objectives) must be implemented within a timeframe indicated in the INRMP. Any deviation or change from achieving the selected alternative may require supplementation to the EA or EIS and an opportunity for public comment.”

Adequate training of natural resource personnel is important to the success of military sustainability and land management. OPNAVINST 5090.1C requires that Navy commands develop, implement and enforce the management plan through personnel with professional training in natural resources. “Natural resources programs shall support military readiness and sustainability and commands shall assign specific responsibility, provide centralized supervision and assign professionally trained personnel to the program. Natural resources personnel shall be provided an opportunity to participate in natural resource management job-training activities and professional meetings.” The SAIA (Section 670g) and DoDINST 4715.03 (18 March 2011) also addresses this need.

5.1.2 Federal Anti-Deficiency Act

NBVC Port Hueneme intends to implement recommendations in this INRMP within the framework of regulatory compliance, national Navy mission obligations, anti-terrorism and force protection limitations, and funding constraints. All actions contemplated in this INRMP are subject to the availability of funds properly authorized and appropriated under federal law. Nothing in this INRMP is intended to be nor must be construed to be a violation of the Anti-Deficiency Act (31 USC 1341 *et seq.*).

5.1.3 Staffing

The SAIA specifically requires that there be “sufficient numbers of professionally trained natural resources management and natural resources enforcement personnel to be available and assigned responsibility” to implement an INRMP. The NBVC ED is responsible for identifying personnel requirements to accomplish INRMP goals and objectives. The NBVC ED is also responsible for providing input into this process by allocating existing budgetary and personnel resources and then identifying staffing needs based on any additional current and future projects. Personnel assigned to natural resources management are the core staff responsible for implementing the INRMP. These personnel ensure that a consistent conservation program is carried out by using strategies outlined in this plan to support the Navy mission and achieve INRMP goals and objectives. Staff coordination includes both planning teams for initiating projects and staffing teams to manage and run projects. Some of the projects described in this plan will depend on coordination with the Public Works Department and other installation personnel.

The following staffing is required to implement this INRMP at NBVC Port Hueneme:

- Ecologist
- Wildlife biologist
- Environmental Protection Specialist (NEPA)

5.1.3.1 Contractor Support

Most projects can be carried out with Navy staff. Some projects, such as targeted surveys, may require contractor services or other federal agency services, either because of a need for expertise or for personnel. In accordance with Circular No. A-76, the federal government is mandated to use commercial sources to supply the products and services the Government needs. Contractors are able to provide a wide variety of specialties to aid NBVC ED with implementation of this INRMP. Specialties range from NEPA documentation, vegetation surveys, vertebrate and invertebrate surveys, water quality surveys, production of management plans, and similar activities. These projects will require preparation of a request for proposal to acquire services, which should be considered to ensure appropriate funding can be obtained.

5.1.3.2 Professional Development and Natural Resources Training

Properly trained personnel are required to achieve objectives and guidelines of this INRMP. Environmental staff members entrusted with this work must have a thorough knowledge and understanding of biology and natural resources, and administrative duties such as project management, reporting, and contracting. Periodically, additional training is needed to keep personnel updated on the current practices and advances in knowledge of these topics. This training may be obtained from a variety of sources, including universities, regulatory agencies, professional societies, and other Navy or military organizations. These training opportunities may be offered in the forms of structured courses or conferences, workshops, and symposia.

NBVC Port Hueneme will evaluate the following annual workshops or professional conferences for attendance depending on funding available for travel and training:

- National Military Fish and Wildlife Association annual workshop;
- North American Natural Resources Conference;
- Wildlife Society – Western Section; and
- Partners-In-Flight national, regional, and state meetings (generally in conjunction with other listed meetings).

Other conferences and workshops will be evaluated for their usefulness, and decisions will be made based on appropriateness to ongoing projects and funding availability. Projects, which are especially useful, are GPS, GIS, and endangered species training. The Wildlife Society, Society for Ecological Restoration, and National Military Fish and Wildlife Association are among the professional societies applicable to meeting the needs of NBVC Port Hueneme’s natural resources managers. Membership in these societies is encouraged. The Wildlife Society has some of the best scientific publications in the profession, and literature review is a necessary commitment to maintain standards. Attending meetings of these societies provides excellent opportunities to communicate with fellow professionals and maintain professional standards.

Objective: Continue to improve the success of natural resources management activities through professional development and information exchange.

- I. Maintain staff knowledge of management strategies through training and participation in or hosting workshops, research presentations, and other activities of regional, interstate, and international professional natural resources research and conservation programs.
- II. Share information with natural resources experts to ensure maximum benefits of adaptive management and research efforts.

5.2 ADAPTIVE MANAGEMENT: ANNUAL UPDATE, REVIEW AND METRICS

DoD policy requires installations to review INRMPs annually in cooperation with the two primary partnering parties to the INRMP: USFWS and the state fish and wildlife agency. Annual reviews facilitate “adaptive management” by providing an opportunity to review the goals and objectives of the plan, and establish a realistic schedule for undertaking proposed actions. In addition to tracking the implementation of the INRMP, an annual report is to be provided that briefly summarizes the project and activities that have been implemented during the fiscal year and how these fulfill the objective identified in the INRMP. Annual reports are in [Appendix M](#), Annual Metrics Reports.

Section 101(b)(2) of the SAIA [16 USC 670a(b)(2)] specifically directs that the INRMPs be reviewed “as to operation and effect” by the primary parties “on a regular basis, but not less often than every 5 years,” emphasizing that the review is intended to determine whether existing INRMPs are being implemented to meet the requirements of the SAIA and contribute to the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations. The OUSD guidance (17 May 2005) states that joint review should be reflected in a memo or letters.

Recent guidance on INRMP implementation interpreted that the 5-year review would not necessarily constitute a “revision,” that this would occur only if deemed necessary. The Annual Review process is broadly guided by the Natural Resources Conservation Program (DoDINST 4715.03 [DoD 2011]) and by OPNAVINST 5090.1C, Environmental Readiness Program Manual, (Navy 2011a). Policy memoranda in 2002, and supplemented in 2004, clarified procedures for INRMP reviews and revisions:

- *DUSD[I&E] Policy Memo 10 October 2002, which replaced a 1998 policy memorandum.*
- *ADUSD ESOH Policy Memo (01 November 2004).*

The INRMP Implementation Guidance (10 October 2002 Memo) improved coordination external to DoD (USFWS, state agencies, and the public) and internal to DoD (military operators and trainers, cultural resources managers, pest managers). It also added new tracking procedures, called metrics, to ensure proper INRMP coordination occurred and that projects were implemented.

The Navy Conservation Website details a set of natural resources metrics, as defined by CNIC, for Navy Natural Resource managers to measure conservation impacts on installation missions and the success of partnerships with the USFWS and state fish and game agencies, as required by the SAIA. The Navy Conservation Website contains seven natural resources metrics focus areas which include: (1) INRMP Project Implementation, (2) Listed Species and Critical Habitat, (3) Partnership Effectiveness, (4) Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use, (5) Team Adequacy, (6) Ecosystem Integrity, and (7) INRMP Impact on the Installation Mission. Each focus area has three to seven criteria that are used to determine the status of a given functional area within Natural Resources.

The 2002 guidance also required that each installation provide a notice of intent (NOI) to prepare or revise the INRMP. Each military installation now must request that USFWS and the state fish and wildlife agency participate in both the development and review of the INRMPs. Current coordination guidelines are that the USFWS field office is the appropriate entry point for military installations, and the USFWS Regional Sikes Act Coordinator is the liaison to facilitate INRMP review.

The Supplemental DoD INRMP Guidance (01 November 2004 Memo) further defined the scope of the annual and 5-year review, public comment on INRMP reviews, and ESA consultation. A formal review must be performed by “the parties” at least every 5 years. Informal annual reviews are mandatory to facilitate adaptive management, during which INRMP goals, objectives, and “must fund” projects are reviewed, and a realistic schedule established to undertake proposed actions.

There is no legal obligation to invite the public either to review or to comment upon the parties’ mutually agreed upon decision to continue implementation of an existing INRMP without revision. If the parties determine that substantial revisions to an INRMP are necessary, public comment shall be invited in conjunction with any **required** NEPA analysis.

In most cases INRMPs will incorporate by reference the results of an installation’s previous species-by-species ESA consultations, including any reasonable and prudent measures identified in an incidental take statement. Neither a separate biological assessment nor a separate formal consultation should be necessary. Because the INRMP may include management strategies designed to balance the potentially competing needs of multiple species, it may be prudent to engage in informal consultation.

Objective: Improve and refine natural resources management, by adaptively adjusting success criteria and priorities based on past accomplishments, new risks and threats, new biological information, and changes in policy (DoDINST 4715.03).

- I. Notify the USFWS Field Office and CDFG if an INRMP revision is found necessary. Ensure that the USFWS Regional Sikes Act Coordinator is notified.
- II. Comply with recent DoD guidance (DoD 2010, 2011) on INRMPs, and compliance with SAIA:
 - a. All INRMPs shall be reviewed annually by the DoD installation with the cooperation of the USFWS and the state fish and wildlife agency, and others with a stake in the outcome of the INRMP at the discretion of the Conservation Program Manager. Annual reviews shall verify that:
 1. Current information on all conservation metrics is available.
 2. All “must fund” projects and activities have been budgeted for and implementation is on Schedule.
 3. All required trained natural resources positions are filled or are in the process of being filled.
 4. Projects and activities for the upcoming year have been identified and included in the INRMP. An updated project list does not necessitate revising the INRMP.

5. All required coordinations have occurred.
 6. All significant changes in the installation's mission requirements or its natural resources have been identified.
- b. Establish a mutually agreed-upon, realistic schedule to undertake proposed actions.
 - c. The outcome of this joint review should be documented in a memorandum or letter summarizing the rationale for the conclusions the parties have reached. This written documentation should reflect the parties' mutual agreement.
- III.* Fulfill the reporting requirements of new measures to promote better understanding of the health of Navy conservation programs, using the Navy Conservation Website's natural resources metrics focus areas, as defined by CNIC.
- IV.* Track implementation to guide and learn from past experience.
- A. Derive the most benefit possible from learning and experience by documenting it and disseminating the information to others.
 - B. To track the progress of each of the INRMP's strategies, a spreadsheet program (e.g. Paradox, Access) and GIS geodatabase should be constructed and maintained. Fields can be included to help (a) build queries; (b) track progress by location, type, sponsor, year, etc.; and (c) provide different types of reports.

5.3 BUDGET CONSIDERATIONS

The following sections address budget considerations for funding INRMP implementation.

5.3.1 Natural Resources Management Priorities and Funding Classifications

The budget programming hierarchy for this INRMP is based on both DoD and Navy funding level classifications (see [Section 1.12](#) Compliance and Stewardship Criteria for Implementing Projects). The DoD programming and budgeting priorities for conservation programs are detailed in the DoDINST 4715.03 Natural Resources Conservation Program. The four programming classes detailed in the Instruction implement policy, assign responsibilities, and prescribe procedures for the integrated management of natural and cultural resources on property under DoD control. Budget priorities are also described in OPNAVINST 5090.1C, Environmental Readiness Program Manual (Navy 2011a).

The four DoDINST programming and budgeting priority classes are divided into Recurring and Non-Recurring activities. The first three classes are compliance activities in the Recurring category and the Non-Recurring Current and Maintenance Compliance categories. The fourth class is stewardship activities that fall into the Non-Recurring Enhancement Actions Beyond Compliance category. The four classes are: DoD Class 0, Recurring Natural and Cultural Resources Conservation Management Requirements; DoD Class I, Current Compliance; DoD Class II, Maintenance Requirements; and DoD Class III, Enhancement Actions Beyond Compliance.

The Navy funding programming hierarchy of recurring and non-recurring projects consists of four ERLs that are based on DoD funding level classifications. Navy policy requires funding of all DoD Class 0 and Class I projects. ERLs enable capability-based programming and budgeting of environmental funding, and facilitate capability versus cost trade-off decisions. Projects recommended in this INRMP have been prioritized based on ERLs (Navy 2006, 2011a). ERL 3 & 4 projects are compliance driven (DoD Class 0, I, II). ERL 4 is considered the absolute minimum level of environmental readiness capability required to maintain compliance with applicable legal requirements. ERL 1 & 2 projects are under the stewardship category DoD Class III). Funding is routinely programmed three years in advance of project implementation. ERL levels, as defined in the 2006 INRMP Guidance (Navy 2006, 2011a) are:

Environmental Readiness Level 4:

- Supports all actions specifically required by law, regulation or EO (DoD Class 0, I, and II requirements).
- Supports all DoD Class 0 requirements as they relate to a specific statute such as hazardous waste disposal, permits, fees, monitoring, sampling and analysis, reporting and record keeping.
- Supports recurring administrative, personnel and other costs associated with managing environmental programs that are necessary to meet applicable compliance requirements (DoD Class 0).
- Supports DoD policy requirement to comply with overseas Final Governing Standards and Overseas Environmental Baseline Guidance Document.
- Supports minimum feasible Navy executive agent responsibilities, participation in Office of Secretary of Defense (OSD) sponsored inter-department and inter-agency efforts, and OSD mandated regional coordination efforts.

Environmental Readiness Level 3:

- Supports all capabilities provided by ERL 4.
- Supports existing level of Navy executive agent responsibilities, participation in OSD sponsored inter-department and inter-agency efforts, and OSD mandated regional coordination efforts.
- Supports proactive involvement in the legislative and regulatory process to identify and mitigate requirements that will impose excessive costs or restrictions on operations and training.
- Supports proactive initiatives critical to the protection of Navy operational readiness.

Environmental Readiness Level 2:

- Supports all capabilities provided under ERL 3.
- Supports enhanced proactive initiatives critical to the protection of Navy operational readiness.
- Supports all Navy and DoD policy requirements.
- Supports investments in pollution reduction, compliance enhancement, energy conservation and cost reduction.

Environmental Readiness Level 1:

- Supports all capabilities provided under ERL 2.
- Supports proactive actions required to ensure compliance with pending or strong anticipated laws and regulations in a timely manner or to prevent adverse impact to Navy mission.
- Supports investments that demonstrate Navy environmental leadership and pro-active environmental stewardship.

It is the Navy's policy to fully fund compliance with all applicable federal, state and local laws; EOs; and associated implementing rules, regulations, DoDINSTs and DoDDIRs, and applicable international and overseas requirements (OPNAVINST 5090.1C). Budget priorities for threatened and endangered species management, especially compliance with BOs, receive the *highest possible* budgeting priority, and support NBVC Port Hueneme's need to avoid critical habitat designations under Section 4(b)(2) of the ESA (based on the three compliance level DoD classes described in Section 1.12, Compliance and Stewardship Criteria for Implementing Projects), or Section 4(a)3 of the ESA (exemption from critical habitat designations for national security reasons).

Environmental Readiness Program Assessment Database

Environmental Program Requirements (EPR) cover multiple subject matter or "business lines" aside from natural and cultural resources. EPRWeb is an optimized online database used to define all programming for the Navy's environmental requirements, and is the tool for providing the four ERL capabilities used in fiscal planning. All natural resources requirements are entered into EPRWeb and are available for review/approval by the chain of command by the dates specified in the Guidance letter provided annually by CNO (N45). EPRWeb records data on project expenditures, and provides immediate, web-based access to requirements entered by the multiple Navy environmental programs, including Environmental Compliance, Pollution Prevention, Conservation, Radiological Controls, and Range Sustainment as related to environmental costs on military ranges.

Implementation Schedule

This INRMP will become effective upon the acceptance and signatory release described in [Section 5.1.1](#) Responsibility. Current projects, activities, and plans have been incorporated into the INRMP, as the plan serves as a formal structuring and integration of the existing natural resources management program.

Future work identified herein will be implemented as funding becomes available. Priorities identified in this INRMP will generally determine the order of implementation. The NBVC ED will determine what projects and activities are appropriate to initiate, given funding, at any particular time. The INRMP is meant to be flexible, dynamic, and adaptable to the immediate concerns and needs of natural resources management and the Navy mission.

Program Monitoring

The NBVC ED will be responsible for oversight and monitoring of the overall program identified in this INRMP. Cooperative projects among different Navy organizations will be monitored by the originating or controlling office as specified prior to project implementation.

5.3.2 External Assistance

Opportunities for external assistance with natural resource programs at NBVC Port Hueneme are identified below.

Other Agencies

NBVC recognizes the importance of cooperating with federal and state agencies in addition to private organizations. [Section 1.0](#), Introduction and [Section 4.4](#), Beneficial Partnerships and Collaborative Resources Planning, identify other agencies and organizations with which NBVC Port Hueneme has cooperatively worked in recent years. These organizations, particularly INRMP signatory partners (USFWS, NOAA and CDFG) will continue to assist with implementation of various aspects of this INRMP.

Volunteers

Volunteers could be a potential valuable source of personnel assistance at NBVC Port Hueneme but are currently not sought for assistance.

University Assistance

Universities are an excellent source of assistance for research and provide resource specific expertise, as well as assistance with implementation of restoration activities. Collaborative investigations performed in conjunction with installation biologist provide the most likely and cost effective sources of assistance with implementation of this INRMP. Local and regional universities, such as UC Los Angeles, UC Santa Barbara and California State University Channel Islands should be contacted for potential sources of graduate and undergraduate assistance with implementation of this INRMP.

Contractors

Most projects can be carried out with Navy staff. Some projects, such as targeted surveys, may require contractor services or other federal agency services, because of a need for expertise or for necessary personnel. In accordance with Circular No. A-76, the federal government is mandated to use commercial sources to supply the products and services the Government needs. Contractors are able to provide a wide variety of specialties to aid NBVC ED with implementation of this INRMP. Specialties range from NEPA documentation, vegetation surveys, vertebrate and invertebrate surveys, vegetation surveys, water quality surveys, production of management plans, and similar activities. Contractor supported projects require preparation of a request for proposal to acquire services, which should be considered during project planning, to ensure appropriate funding can be obtained.

5.4 FUNDING SOURCES

To implement the various research, surveys, and programs necessary to fulfill the mission of the NBVC ED, funding must be identified and acquired. The NBVC ED, under the direction of the CO, NBVC, is responsible for coordinating efforts and funding for natural resource and environmental programs. NBVC ED receives funding, program, and policy support and guidance from the Navy Region Southwest (NRSW), San Diego. The Region is the CNIC local agent for ensuring environmental programs are effectively managed. The Region is supported by NAVFAC SW who provides assistance to many local installations.

There are several avenues of funding available to the NBVC ED, beyond the typical Naval operational budget, that allow the inclusion of additional projects to assist the NBVC ED in their mission-related and stewardship endeavors. The NBVC ED must continually assess the priority and level of budgetary needs to fulfill Navy and regulatory requirements and to sustain overall program goals. These funding sources are discussed below in general terms, as this process is dynamic and is dependent on the INRMPs continuously developing program.

These programs will be implemented using Navy personnel and program resources as much as possible; however, it is likely that contractors will accomplish many projects. NBVC ED will identify projects that would be accomplished using contract vehicles, with existing contracts being used where possible and appropriate.

For large projects that involve different Navy organizations, representatives of these organizations would coordinate budgeting and scheduling to ensure that the project can be accomplished in the planned timeframe. Large-budget projects may not be completely funded in a fiscal year, requiring incremental funding over the term of the project.

In some cases, smaller, lower-priority projects may be conducted using unspent funds from other tasks or year-end fallout funding. Some projects may be accomplished with little or no funding required, such as those requiring only a change of policy or coordination and effort from volunteer labor. These tasks can be implemented virtually as soon as planning is performed.

5.4.1 Department of Defense Funding Sources

The costs of executing INRMP actions may be funded from a variety of DoD sources. Funding sources should be reviewed carefully to identify qualifying projects. Execution of this plan by the federal government is contingent on the availability of funds properly allocated to the plan in accordance with applicable law. The primary funding sources to Navy natural resources programs include:

1. **Operations and Maintenance Funds.** Funding sources for the natural resources program are derived from General and Administrative, Operations and Maintenance Navy (O&MN), Major Range Test Facility Base, and input into the Navy EPR system for funding. This primary budgetary source is the basis for maintaining the personnel

- and core programs inherent to the natural resources program. It is the responsibility of ED to manage the natural resources program budget and funding. Once O&MN funds are appropriated for core personnel and the program, funding can be justified for other project requirements.
2. **Agricultural Outlease Funds.** Funds accumulated through the outleasing of agricultural lands on many installations are directed back into the natural resource program and reallocated throughout the Navy by NAVFAC Headquarters. These are the broadest use funds available exclusively to natural resource managers. These funds are available to all installations to offset the costs of preparing and implementing INRMPs.
 3. **Recycling Funds.** Installations with a Qualified Recycling Program may use proceeds for some types of natural resource projects.
 4. **Navy Working Capital Fund.** Many natural resource projects may be funded with the Navy Working Capital Fund (NWCF). All projects submitted for NWCF funding must be included in the INRMP, or a clear justification for their omission must be provided. NWCF funds are generally not available for Navy Level 2-5 projects. The NWCF is a revolving fund that is generated by fees for services and used to pay expenses.

Other DoD funding sources are described below:

Sikes Act Funds

Sikes Act funds are collected via sales of licenses to hunt or fish ([Navy 2005a](#)). They are authorized by the Sikes Act and may be used only for fish and wildlife management on the installation where they are collected. NBVC Port Hueneme generates no Sikes Act funds, and none are anticipated unless security and safety conditions change to allow hunting on the installation, which is not anticipated.

Legacy Funds

The Legacy Resource Management Program (LRMP) was enacted in 1990 to provide financial assistance to military natural and cultural resources management. The program assists with protection and enhancement of natural resources while supporting military readiness. Legacy projects may involve regional ecosystem management initiatives, habitat preservation efforts, archaeological investigations, invasive species control, and/or monitoring, and predicting migratory patterns of birds and other animals.

5.4.2 Use of Cooperative Agreements and Partnerships

Cooperative agreements are legal relationships between the Navy and states, local governments, institutions of higher education, hospitals, non-profit organizations or individuals. The principal purpose of the relationship is to transfer a thing of value to the state, local government, or other recipient to carry out a public purpose of support or stimulation authorized by a law of the U.S. instead of acquiring (by purchase, lease, or barter) property or services for the direct benefit or use of the U.S. Government. Cooperative agreements may be entered into for inventories, monitoring, research, minor construction and maintenance, and public awareness, to provide for the maintenance and improvement of natural resources or conservation research on DoD installations (DoDINST 4715.03). To use a cooperative agreement, substantial involvement is expected between the Navy and the state, local government, or other recipient when carrying out the activity contemplated in the agreement. Cooperative agreements provide a mutually beneficial means of acquiring, analyzing, and interpreting natural resources data, which can then be used to inform natural resources management decisions. Cooperative agreements are funded by the Navy and produce information that can be used to help resource managers achieve project-specific compliance with environmental laws. Authorization for cooperative agreements is arranged through NAVFAC.

NBVC Port Hueneme recognizes the importance of cooperating with federal and state agencies, in addition to private organizations. No cooperative agreements are in place other than this INRMP's signatory partners (USFWS, NOAA and CDFG) and NAVFAC SW, who will continue to assist with implementation of various aspects of this INRMP. Cooperative agreements may provide future funding opportunities for the Resources Management Program at NBVC Port Hueneme and should be pursued.

Cooperative Ecosystem Studies Units

The Cooperative Ecosystem Studies Units (CESU) program is a working collaboration among federal agencies, universities, state agencies, non-governmental organizations, and other nonfederal institutional partners. The CESU National Network provides multidisciplinary research, technical assistance, and education to resource and environmental managers. Although the overall program is overseen by USDI, one of the participating agencies is DoD. For more information regarding the CESU program, refer to the following website: <http://www.cesu.psu.edu>.

5.4.3 Research Funding Requirements

Environmental program funding in the Navy is primarily based upon federally mandated requirements. Program managers are encouraged to seek outside funding for projects consistent with the INRMP, such as research, that will benefit natural resources on installations, but that are not directly related to federal mandates.

New funding sources should be sought from federal, state, local, and nonprofit organizations with an interest in achieving the goals and objectives of this INRMP in partnership with NBVC Port Hueneme. Any such funding would need to be consistent with authorization to receive and use such funds. These will often require cost-sharing. This funding opportunity should be sought for projects that are not Navy Class 0 or 1 “must fund” items, tied directly to immediate regulatory compliance. Examples are watershed management, habitat enhancement, or wetland restoration.

5.4.4 Non-DOD Funding Sources

There are a number of grant programs available for natural resource management projects such as watershed management and restoration, habitat restoration, and wetland and riparian area restoration. When federally funded, these programs typically require non-federal matching funds. However, installations may be able to partner with other groups to propose eligible projects. One example grant program is listed below, but many more are available.

The National Association of Counties, National Association of Service and Conservation Corps, National Fish and Wildlife Foundation, and Wildlife Habitat Council sponsor the Five Star Restoration Challenge Grants program, in cooperation with EPA, NMFS and other sponsors. This program provides modest financial assistance (\$5,000 to \$20,000) on a competitive basis to support community-based wetland and riparian restoration projects that build diverse partnerships and foster local natural resource stewardship. Installations would need to partner with other groups to be eligible for this type of program. Applications are due in March. Information is available on the web at <http://www.epa.gov/owow/wetlands/restore/5star/>.

5.5 INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY AND SCHEDULE

The objectives and strategies that support INRMP implementation are identified in this section. Detailed natural resource management prescriptions and a list of projects are in [Appendix E](#). The SAIA requires implementation of this INRMP; however, INRMP implementation is also subject to the provisions of the Federal Antideficiency Act. Some INRMP projects are accomplished with installation staff; others involve contracting work to specialists. The implementation schedule identified in [Appendix E](#), Table E-4 is suggested for long-term planning purposes; however, the schedule may be modified based on need, resources, and seasonal requirements.

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APPENDIX A
LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

TABLE A-1: ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS IN THIS INRMP

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
°F	Degrees Fahrenheit
ACP	Area Contingency Plan
ADUSD	Assistant Deputy Undersecretary of Defense
ANS	Aquatic Nuisance Species
AOP	Activity Overview Plan
ASBS	Areas of Special Biological Significance
BA	Biological Assessment
BMP	Best Management Practice
BO	Biological Opinion
CAA	Clean Air Act
CATEX	Categorical Exclusion
Cal-IPC	California Invasive Plant Council
CBC	Construction Battalion Center
CCA	California Coastal Act
CCC	Category Coastal Commission
CDFG	California Department of Fish and Game
CECOS	Civil Engineers Corps Officers School
CEQ	Council on Environmental Quality
CERCLA	Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation and Liability Act
CESA	California Endangered Species Act
CESE	Civil Engineer Support Equipment
CESU	Cooperative Ecosystem Studies Units
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations
CMWD	Calleguas Municipal Water District
CNDDDB	California Natural Diversity Database
CNIC	Commander of Navy Installations Command
CNO	Chief of Naval Operation
CNRSW	Commander Navy Region Southwest
CO	Commanding Officer
COMNAVREGSWINST	Commander Navy Region Southwest Instruction
COTP	Captain of the Port
CSFE	Center for Seabees and Facilities Engineering
CSO	Chief Staff Officer
CWA	Clean Water Act
CZARA	Coastal Zone Act Reauthorization Amendments
CZMA	Coastal Zone Management Act
CZMP	Coastal Zone Management Program
DASN	Deputy Assistant Secretary of the Navy
DAU	Defense Acquisition University
DoD	U.S. Department of Defense
DoDDIR	U.S. Department of Defense Directive
DoDINST	U.S. Department of Defense Instruction
DRA	Defense Reauthorization Act
DRMO	Defense Reutilization and Marketing Office
DUSD(I&E)	Deputy Under Secretary of Defense for Installations and the Environment

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
EA	Environmental Assessment
EC	Environmental Coordinator
EDOS	Engineering Duty Officer School
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EFH	Essential Fish Habitat
EIS	Environmental Impact Statement
EMS	Environmental Management System
EO	Executive Order
EOC	Emergency Operations Center
EPA	U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
EPCRA	Emergency Planning and Community Right-to-Know Act
EPR	Environmental Program Requirements
ERL	Environmental Readiness Level
ERTEC	Earth Technology Corporation
ESA	Endangered Species Act
ESOH	Environment, Safety and Occupational Health
ft ²	Square feet
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FEPCA	Federal Environmental Pesticide Control Act
FFD	Federal Fire Department
FGDC	Federal Geographic Data Committee
FIFRA	Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act
FONSI	Finding of No Significant Impact
FOSC	Federal On-Scene Coordinator
FQPA	Food Quality Protection Act
FR	Federal Register
FRP	Facility Response Plan
FY	Fiscal Year
GAPS	Global Auto Processing Services
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global positioning system
HABS	Historic American Building Survey
HAER	Historic American Engineering Record
HEA	Habitat Equivalency Analysis
HSWA	Hazardous and Solid Waste Amendments
IAFWA	International Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies
ICP	Integrated Contingency Plan
ICRMP	Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan
IMC	Installation Management Claimant
INRMP	Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
IPL	Integrated Priority List
IPMP	Integrated Pest Management Plan
IRMP	Integrated Resources Management Plan
IRP	Installation Restoration Program
ISMP	Invasive Species Management Plan
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
km	Kilometer
LARWQCB	Los Angeles Regional Water Quality Control Board
LEED	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design
LID	Low Impact Development
LOA	Letter of Authorization
LRMP	Legacy Resource Management Program
m	meter
m/sec	meters per second
MBTA	Migratory Bird Treaty Act
MBTRA	Migratory Bird Treaty Reform Act
MEO	Most efficient operation
MLLW	Mean lower low water
MLMA	Marine Life Management Act
MLPA	Marine Life Protection Act
MMPA	Marine Mammal Protection Act
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
MRPP	Monitoring and Reporting Program Plan
msl	mean sea level
MWR	Morale, Welfare, and Recreation
NAAQS	National Ambient Air Quality Standards
NABCI	North American Bird Conservation Initiative
NALF	Naval Auxiliary Landing Field
NANCPA	Non-indigenous Aquatic Nuisance Prevention and Control Act
NAVFAC	Naval Facilities Engineering Command
NAVFAC-ESC	Naval Facilities Engineering Command Engineering Service Center
NAVFACINST	Naval Facilities Engineering Command Instruction
NAVFAC SW	Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest
NAVSEA	Naval Sea Systems Command
Navy	U.S. Department of the Navy
NAWCWD	Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division
NBII	National Biological Information Infrastructure
NBVC	Naval Base Ventura County
NBVC ED	Naval Base Ventura County Environmental Division
NBVCINST	Naval Base Ventura County Instruction
NCF	Naval Construction Force
NCP	National Contingency Plan
NCR	Naval Construction Regiment
NCTC	Naval Construction Training Center
NDAA	National Defense Authorization Act
NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act
NFELC	Naval Facilities Engineering Logistics Command
NFI	Naval Facilities Institute
NGA	National Governors Association
NHPA	National Historic Preservation Act
NISA	National Invasive Species Act
NISC	National Invasive Species Council
NISMP	National Invasive Species Monitoring Plan

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
NMFS	National Marine Fisheries Service
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Association
NOI	Notice of Intent
NPDES	National Pollution Discharge Elimination System
NPL	National Priorities List
NPS	National Park Service
NRC	Naval Reserve Center
NRCS	Natural Resources Conservation Service
NRDA	Natural Resources Damage Assessment
NRHP	National Register of Historic Places
NRL	Naval Research Lab
NRT	National Response Team
O&MN	Operations and Maintenance Navy
OCNR	Office of the Chief of Naval Research
OEIS	Overseas Environmental Impact Statement
OHD	Oxnard Harbor District
OIC	Officer-in-Charge
OPNAV	Office of the Chief of Naval Operations
OPNAVINST	Naval Operations Instruction
OPPA	Oil Pollution Prevention Act
OSD	Office of the Secretary of Defense
OSHA	Occupational Safety and Health Administration
OSPR	Office of Oil Spill Prevention and Response
OUSD	Office of the Undersecretary of Defense
PFMC	Pacific Fishery Management Council
PHD-NSWC	Port Hueneme Division, Naval Surface Warfare Center
PIF	Partners-In-Flight
PL	Public Law
PMSR	Point Mugu Sea Range
PRC	PRC Environmental Management Inc.
Psi	Pounds per square inch
PWD	Public Works Department
RCRA	Resource Conservation and Recovery Act
RDT&E	Research Development Testing and Evaluation
REA	Resource Equivalency Analysis
ROD	Record of Decision
RSIP	Regional Shore Infrastructure Plan
RWQCB	Regional Water Quality Control Board
SAIA	Sikes Act Improvement Act
SA/PRB	Site Approval Project Review Board
SARA	Superfund Amendments and Reauthorization Act
SCA	Soil Conservation Act
SCI	San Clemente Island
SCS	Stearns, Conrad, and Schmidt
SECNAV	Secretary of the Navy
SECNAVINST	Secretary of the Navy Instruction
SIP	State Implementation Plan

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
SNI	San Nicolas Island
SOCAL	Southern California
SPCC	Spill Prevention Control and Countermeasure
SRG	Seabee Readiness Support Group
SRM	Sustainment Restoration Modernization
SSI	Sustainable Sites Initiative
SWEF	Surface Warfare Engineering Facility
SWPPP	Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan
SWRCB	State Water Resources Control Board
TBD	To be determined
TEC	The Environmental Company
TN&A	Terry Nee and Associates
TRS	Training Squadron
USACE	U.S. Army Corp of Engineers
USAF	U.S. Air Force
USC	U.S. Code
USCG	U.S. Coast Guard
USDA	U.S. Department of Agriculture
USDOC	U.S. Department of Commerce
USDOJ	U.S. Department of the Interior
USFWS	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
USGBC	U.S. Green Building Council
USGS	U.S. Geological Survey
UST	Underground storage tank
UWCD	United Water Conservation District
WAP	Wildlife Action Plan
WG	Working Group
WOUS	Waters of the U.S.
WRCC	Western Regional Climate Center

Notes: Acronyms listed include those found in appendices.

APPENDIX B
ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT

January 30, 2012

**Naval Base Ventura County, Port Hueneme
Revised Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) Compliance**

To: Administrative Record

Determination: It has been determined that the Environmental Assessment (EA) and Finding of no Significant Impact (FONSI) completed for the Port Hueneme 2002 Integrated Natural Resources Plan (INRMP) sufficiently meets the NEPA requirements for the 2012 Port Hueneme Revised INRMP. The likely and occurring effects of the Revised INRMP would not be significantly different or qualitatively more severe than what was documented in the 2002 INRMP EA and FONSI. Therefore, no additional NEPA documentation is required for the 2012 Port Hueneme Revised INRMP.

History: Naval Base Ventura County, Port Hueneme's current INRMP was completed in 2002. That same year, an EA was prepared and a FONSI was signed by the Vice Commander of Navy Installations Command Southwest. Since that time, a revision to the INRMP has been initiated and the existing EA for the original 2002 INRMP has been reviewed for adequacy.

Changes in the 2012 Revised INRMP from the Original 2002 INRMP: The need to revise the 2002 INRMP was largely driven by the 2006 Navy Guidance on preparing INRMPs and the preference to have these documents consistent throughout the Navy Facilities Engineering Command. In this Port Hueneme INRMP revision process, only minor revisions and updates have been made to the INRMP including: reformatting the document; addressing species status and current conditions; and plan revisions. No new activities have been added nor have the potential environmental impacts increased from the original INRMP to the Revised INRMP.

Habitat Protection and Restoration Plans: No new natural resources projects have been identified in the Revised INRMP. However, additional guidance on management strategies and methodology has been included. These clarifications do not change the overall intent of the action, nor do they increase project impacts. Instead, they allow for more consistency in scientific data collection to support the INRMP.

Base Operations and Natural Resources: The Revised INRMP clarifies how the overall base operators and the natural resources program are integrated. This provides a broader framework for identifying mutual mission and natural resources opportunities.

Current Conditions Updates: The Revised INRMP includes updates to the existing baseline data collection for Port Hueneme. Ongoing activities such as species specific annual surveys, population and density calculations, invasive species management, and adaptive species management are included in the Revised INRMP.

Conclusion: The existing EA and FONSI for the INRMP (2002) sufficiently meets the NEPA requirements for the 2012 Revised INRMP, including:

- The likely and occurring effects of the Revised INRMP would not be significantly different or qualitatively more severe than what was documented in the 2002 INRMP EA and FONSI.

- In light of the relatively minor changes associated with potential implementation of the Revised INRMP, the Navy has concluded that there is no potential for significant impacts beyond the scope of what was addressed in the 2002 EA and FONSI.
- The Revised INRMP uses the same ecosystem approach to management as the original INRMP and EA. However, individual management strategies have been more clearly defined. The updated information will further enhance the sustainability of the resources on Port Hueneme.

Therefore, no additional NEPA documentation is required for the 2012 Port Hueneme Revised INRMP.

The INRMP will continue to be revised in the future, as needed, to accurately reflect the mission and management of the natural resources on Port Hueneme. As the INRMP is revised, the existing NEPA documents would also be reviewed to ensure adequacy.

Signed,

Rebecca Loomis
Coastal IPT NEPA Planner

**Environmental Assessment
for
Implementation of the Integrated
Natural Resources Management Plan
Naval Base Ventura County
Port Hueneme Site, California**

December 2001

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ADT	average daily traffic	km	kilometer
APE	area of potential effect	LCP	Local Coastal Plan
BEAP	Base Exterior Architecture Plan	L _{dn}	day-night average sound level
bgs	below ground surface	L _{eq}	equivalent noise level
BMP	Best Management Practice	LOS	level of service
CAA	Clean Air Act	m	meter
Cal EPA	California Environmental Protection Agency	mg/l	milligrams per liter
CalEPPC	California Exotic Pest Plant Council	MSL	mean sea level
CARB	California Air Resources Board	MTBE	methyl tertiary butyl ether
CCA	California Coastal Act	MWR	Morale, Welfare, and Recreation
CCAA	California Clean Air Act	NAS	Naval Air Station
CCC	California Coastal Commission	NAVFACENCOM	Naval Facilities Engineering Command
CCD	Coastal Consistency Determination	NBVC	Naval Base Ventura County
CCMP	California Coastal Management Program	NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act
CDFG	California Department of Fish and Game	NEX	Naval Exchange
CEQ	Council on Environmental Quality	NMFS	National Marine Fisheries Service
CERCLA	Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation and Liability Act	NO ₂	nitrogen dioxide
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations	NR	Natural Resources
CINCPACFLT	Commander in Chief, Pacific Fleet	NSWC	Naval Surface Warfare Center
cm	centimeter	O ₃	ozone
CNDDB	California Natural Diversity Data Base	OPNAVINST	Chief of Naval Operations Instruction
CNEL	community noise equivalent level	PA	Programmatic Agreement
CNPS	California Native Plant Society	PA/SI	preliminary assessment/site inspection
CO	carbon monoxide	PCB	polychlorinated biphenyl
CWA	Clean Water Act	PHD	Port Hueneme District
CZMA	Coastal Zone Management Act	PHS	PHS
dB	decibel	P.L.	Public Law
dBA	A-weighted decibel	PM ₁₀	particulate matter < 10 microns in diameter
DCE	dichloroethylene	ppm	parts per million
DDT	dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane	RCRA	Resource Conservation and Recovery Act
DoD	Department of Defense	RI	remedial investigation
DoDDIR	Department of Defense Directive	ROI	region of influence
DoDI	Department of Defense Instruction	RONA	Record of Non-Applicability
DTSC	Department of Toxic Substances Control	RV	recreational vehicle
EA	environmental assessment	RWQCB	Regional Water Quality Control Board
ESA	Endangered Species Act	SAIA	Sikes Act Improvement Act
EO	Executive Order	SO ₂	sulfur dioxide
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Act	SWPPP	Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan
FICON	Federal Interagency Committee on Noise	TDS	total dissolved solids
FS	final site	µg/m ³	micrograms per cubic meter
GIS	geographic information system	USACE	U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
ICU	intersection capacity utilization	USC	U.S. Code
IPM	integrated pest management	USEPA	U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
INRMP	Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan	USFWS	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
IRP	Installation Restoration Program	USNCBC	U.S. Navy Construction Battalion Center
kg	kilogram	UST	underground storage tank

ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT

**IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN,
NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY, PORT HUENEME SITE, CALIFORNIA**

**Prepared by:
Department of the Navy**

ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT

Lead Agency for the EA: Department of the Navy
Title of Proposed Action: Implementation of the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan, Naval Base Ventura County (NVBC), Port Hueneme Site (PHS), California
Affected Jurisdictions: Ventura County
Designation: Final Environmental Assessment

In accordance with the Sikes Act Improvement Act, the Secretary of Defense is required to carry out a program to prepare and implement Integrated Natural Resources Management Plans (INRMPs) for each military installation in the United States. The purpose of the INRMP is to provide for the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations. Prior to implementation, Navy guidance prescribes a National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) review of the INRMP.

A comprehensive Integrated Resources Management Plan (U.S. Navy 1999a) has been prepared for the PHS. The title of this document is the "Integrated Resources Management Plan for the Construction Battalion Center (CBC) Port Hueneme, California." The document contains both a natural and cultural resources component; however, it officially serves as the INRMP for the NBVC, PHS. Therefore, all future references in this EA will be made to the INRMP, PHS; per Navy policy, the EA only addresses natural resources. The "CBC" refers to the former name of the installation prior to regionalization. Currently, both the Port Hueneme and Point Mugu sites are combined as one command referred to as "Naval Base Ventura County," followed by a reference to the specific site. Hence the name, Naval Base Ventura County, Port Hueneme Site.

Several management strategies and proposed projects were recommended in the INRMP for the PHS, only some of which have the potential for impacts under NEPA. This EA assesses potential environmental and human resource impacts associated with the implementation of these specific management strategies and projects on a programmatic level. Two alternatives are analyzed in this EA: the proposed action (INRMP implementation) and the no-action alternative (continuation of current management activities). Implementation of the proposed action was reviewed for potential conflicts with future planned projects at the PHS. No other alternatives were identified that could fulfill the purpose and need for the proposed action. This EA has been prepared in accordance with the NEPA of 1969, as amended (42 United States Code [USC] §§ 4321 et seq.), the Council on Environmental Quality (CEQ) implementing regulations (40 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] §§ 1500-1508), and Department of the Navy Procedures for Implementing NEPA (32 CFR 775), as described in Chief of Naval Operations Instruction (OPNAVINST) 5090.1B.

Potential environmental and human resource impacts have been analyzed for biological resources, hydrology and surface water and groundwater quality; land use and visual resources; transportation and circulation; air quality; noise; and hazardous materials and wastes. Negligible impacts were assessed under the no-action alternative as well as the proposed action. However, the no-action alternative would have adverse but insignificant impacts to biological resources, surface water quality, and hazardous materials and wastes.

Prepared by: Department of the Navy
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DECEMBER 2001

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This environmental assessment (EA) has been prepared to analyze potential environmental and human resource impacts associated with implementation of the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for the Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC), Port Hueneme Site (PHS), California. This EA has been prepared in accordance with the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) of 1969, as amended (42 U.S. Code [USC] §§ 4321 et. seq.), the Council on Environmental Quality (CEQ) implementing regulations (40 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] §§ 1500-1508), and Department of the Navy Procedures for Implementing NEPA (32 CFR 775), as described in Chief of Naval Operations Instruction (OPNAVINST) 5090.1B. The Navy is the lead agency for the decision regarding the proposed action.

One of the purposes of the INRMP is to set the agenda for managing the PHS's natural resources. The INRMP also documents baseline conditions for natural resources, reviews current management practices related to natural resources at the PHS, and provides guidance on prioritizing appropriate methods for natural resource preservation and enhancement. A comprehensive Integrated Resources Management Plan (U.S. Navy 1999a) has been prepared for the PHS. The title of this document is the "Integrated Resources Management Plan for the Construction Battalion Center (CBC) Port Hueneme, California." The document contains both a natural and cultural resources component; however, it officially serves as the INRMP for the NBVC, PHS. Therefore, all future references in this EA will be made to the INRMP, PHS; per Navy policy, the EA only addresses natural resources. The "CBC" refers to the former name of the installation prior to regionalization. Currently, both the Port Hueneme and Point Mugu sites are combined as one command referred to as "Naval Base Ventura County," followed by a reference to the specific site. Hence the name, Naval Base Ventura County, Port Hueneme Site.

The INRMP contains a wide range of management actions designed to meet the goals of the Sikes Act Improvement Act (see Table ES-1 and refer to pages 2-2 and 2-5 for additional details). Details for implementation of these management actions are provided in Appendix A of this EA. The management actions identified for potential implementation can be grouped into several major categories:

- Plan/Program Updates and Improvements
- Inventories and Assessments
- Recreational Improvements
- Education/Restoration/Protection/Monitoring
- Other

The need for the proposed action is to meet statutory requirements under the Sikes Act Improvement Act (Public Law 105-85, Division B, Title XXIX, November 18, 1997, 111 Stat 2017-2019, 2020-2022). In November 1997, the Sikes Act (16 USC § 670A et seq.) was amended to require the Secretary of Defense to carry out a program to provide for the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations.

Implementation of any of the INRMP projects will be dependent on the availability of appropriate funding sources. Any requirement for the obligation of funds for projects evaluated in this EA shall be subject to the availability of funds appropriated by Congress, and none of the proposed projects shall be interpreted to require obligation or payment of funds in violation of any applicable federal law, including the Anti-Deficiency Act (31 USC § 1341 et seq.). The proposed projects have been prioritized according

to DoD Instruction 4715.3, 3 May 1996 (refer to Section 2.1.3). Project “Natural Resources” (NR)-1 will be the only INRMP project that is programmed for funding, since it has been designated as a “Class I” program priority. The estimated implementation time frame has also been included for proposed projects in the INRMP. However, certain projects/programs may be implemented at a later date due to funding or other considerations. These management actions will be subject to future review and may be revised per the Sikes Act Improvement Act.

Alternatives to the proposed action must be considered in accordance with NEPA, CEQ regulations for implementing NEPA, and Navy procedures for implementing NEPA. Two alternatives are analyzed on a programmatic level in this EA: the proposed action (INRMP implementation) and the no-action alternative (continuation of current management activities). Implementation of the proposed action was reviewed for potential conflicts with future planned projects or the military mission at the PHS. No other alternatives were identified that could fulfill the purpose and need for the proposed action.

Negligible impacts were determined under both the no-action alternative and the proposed action. A programmatic level of analysis was performed for each of the proposed projects that may trigger NEPA, since specific details regarding implementation of the proposed projects have not yet been developed. The details for implementation of INRMP projects will be determined in conjunction with the PHS staff at a future date, if funding becomes available. If it is determined at that time that additional NEPA would be required to address project impacts, an appropriate level of documentation would be prepared according to project needs.

Table ES-2 provides a comparison of environmental consequences of alternatives. The proposed action (INRMP implementation alternative) would not result in significant impacts to any issue areas analyzed under NEPA. Minor grading and site preparation activities for several general site improvement projects would result in temporary and insignificant impacts in the areas of air quality, traffic, and noise. The majority of proposed projects would have beneficial impacts on the environment at the PHS, such as recommended enhancement and restoration plans for “Special Interest Natural Areas.”

The no-action alternative would have adverse, but insignificant impacts for biological resources, surface water quality, and hazardous materials and wastes (see Table ES-2 below). In addition, there is one potential conflict that may arise with the no-action alternative related to biological resources. Specifically, an area used periodically for training exercises contains burrowing owls. Therefore, if the INRMP is not implemented and this area is not protected, a potential impact to the burrowing owls may occur if training activities are allowed to continue there. However, ample space is available adjacent to this location for training activities; therefore, no adverse impacts would be expected to occur (refer to Section 4.1 for additional information).

Table ES-1. Recommended Natural Resources Projects

Implementation Order	Project Title	Projected Implementation (years)	Program Priority***
NR-1	Pest Management Plan *	1	Class I
NR-2	Base-wide Wetland Delineation	2-5	Class II
NR-3	Sensitive Species Surveys and Floristic Inventory	2-5	Class II
NR-4	Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area A (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)	2-5	Class II
NR-5	Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area B (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)	2-5	Class II
NR-6	Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area D (Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage and Sandy Beach Habitats)	2-5	Class II
NR-7	Revision of the Base Exterior Architecture Plan (BEAP)	2-5	Class II
NR-8	Footpath/Greenbelt Loop**	6-10	Class III
NR-9	Landscape and Recreation Improvements	2-5	Class III
NR-10	Protection Measures for Potential Monarch Butterfly Roosting Sites	6-10	Class II
NR-11	Protection Measures for Kelp Beds	6-10	Class II
NR-12	Protection Measures for the California Brown Pelican and California Least Tern	6-10	Class II
NR-13	Protection Measures for Marine Mammals	6-10	Class II
NR-14	Protection Measures for Native Bird Species	6-10	Class II
NR-15	Development of a Natural Resources Monitoring Program and Database	2-5	Class III
NR-16	Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan Special Interest Natural Area C (Coyote Brush Habitat)	2-5	Class II
NR-17	Adaptive Management Plan for Burrowing Owls	2-5	Class II
NR-18	Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at Installation Restoration Program (IRP) Site 14	2-5	Class III
NR-19	Improvements to the Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan (SWPPP)	2-5	Class III
NR-20	Improvements to the Recycling Program	2-5	Class III
NR-21	Drip Irrigation System Installation	2-5	Class III
NR-22	Outdoor Recreation Assessment	6-10	Class III

Bolded items denote projects with the potential to trigger impacts under NEPA.

*The Pest Management Plan has been completed; however, it is missing specific components that are identified as management actions in the INRMP (refer to Appendices A and E for details). Therefore, it remains a high priority for management action and is a Class I priority; it is the only INRMP project that is programmed to receive funding.

**Project will be completed incrementally during projected time frame.

***Refer to Section 2.1.3 for additional information on program priority classification methods.

NR = Natural Resource

Table ES-2. Comparison of Environmental Consequences of Alternatives

<i>Section Number and Resource Area</i>	<i>INRMP Implementation Alternative</i>	<i>No-Action Alternative</i>
4.1 Biological Resources	○	●
4.2 Hydrology, Surface Water, and Groundwater Quality	○	●
4.3 Land Use and Visual Resources	○	○
4.4 Transportation and Circulation	○	○
4.5 Air Quality	○	○
4.6 Noise	○	○
4.7 Hazardous Materials and Wastes	○	●

Notes: ○ = *Less than significant impact*
 ● = *Adverse but insignificant, impact*
 ● = *Significant impact*

ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT
INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN
PORT HUENEME SITE

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONSINSIDE COVER
EXECUTIVE SUMMARYES-1
CHAPTER 1 PURPOSE AND NEED FOR THE PROPOSED ACTION..... 1-1
1.1 INTRODUCTION1-1
1.2 PURPOSE AND NEED FOR THE PROPOSED ACTION1-3
1.3 SCOPE OF ENVIRONMENTAL REVIEW1-4
1.3.1 Scope of EA1-4
1.3.2 Organization of EA1-5
CHAPTER 2 PROPOSED ACTION AND ALTERNATIVES..... 2-1
2.1 INRMP OVERVIEW/PROPOSED ACTION.....2-1
2.1.1 Project Location2-1
2.1.2 INRMP Overview.....2-1
2.1.3 Criteria for Establishing Program Priorities2-1
2.2 MILITARY USES AND INRMP CONFLICTS2-5
2.2.1 Military and Other Uses of the PHS2-7
2.3 ALTERNATIVES2-7
2.3.1 Proposed Action (Preferred Alternative).....2-7
2.3.2 No-Action Alternative2-8
CHAPTER 3 AFFECTED ENVIRONMENT 3-1
3.1 BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES3-1
3.1.1 Definition of Resource3-1
3.1.2 Existing Conditions3-2
3.2 HYDROLOGY, SURFACE WATER, AND GROUNDWATER QUALITY3-14
3.2.1 Definition of Resource3-14
3.2.2 Existing Conditions3-14
3.3 LAND USE AND VISUAL RESOURCES.....3-19
3.3.1 Definition of Resource3-19
3.3.2 Existing Conditions3-20
3.4 TRANSPORTATION AND CIRCULATION3-22
3.4.1 Definition of Resource3-22
3.4.2 Existing Conditions3-22
3.5 AIR QUALITY3-24
3.5.1 Definition of Resource3-24
3.5.2 Existing Conditions3-26
3.6 NOISE.....3-28

3.6.1	Definition of Resource.....	3-28
3.6.2	Existing Conditions	3-29
3.7	HAZARDOUS MATERIALS AND WASTES	3-30
3.7.1	Definition of Resource.....	3-30
3.7.2	Existing Conditions	3-30
CHAPTER 4 ENVIRONMENTAL CONSEQUENCES		4-1
4.1	BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES	4-2
4.1.1	Proposed Action	4-2
4.1.2	No-Action Alternative	4-5
4.2	HYDROLOGY, SURFACE WATER, AND GROUNDWATER QUALITY	4-6
4.2.1	Proposed Action	4-6
4.2.2	No-Action Alternative	4-7
4.3	LAND USE AND VISUAL RESOURCES.....	4-9
4.3.1	Proposed Action	4-9
4.3.2	No-Action Alternative	4-10
4.4	TRANSPORTATION AND CIRCULATION	4-12
4.4.1	Proposed Action	4-12
4.4.2	No-Action Alternative	4-13
4.5	AIR QUALITY.....	4-14
4.5.1	Proposed Action	4-14
4.5.2	No-Action Alternative	4-15
4.6	NOISE.....	4-16
4.6.1	Proposed Action	4-16
4.6.2	No-Action Alternative	4-16
4.7	HAZARDOUS MATERIALS AND WASTES	4-17
4.7.1	Proposed Action	4-17
4.7.2	No-Action Alternative	4-18
CHAPTER 5 OTHER CONSIDERATIONS REQUIRED BY NEPA.....		5-1
5.1	CUMULATIVE IMPACTS.....	5-1
5.1.1	Cumulative Projects	5-1
5.1.2	Cumulative Impacts.....	5-1
5.2	RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SHORT-TERM ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS AND LONG-TERM PRODUCTIVITY.....	5-2
CHAPTER 6 PERSONNEL/AGENCY CONSULTATION AND COORDINATION		6-1
CHAPTER 7 REFERENCES		7-1
CHAPTER 8 PREPARERS.....		8-1
APPENDIX A PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS.....		A-1
APPENDIX B USACE JURISDICTIONAL DETERMINATION FOR THE DRAINAGE CHANNELS AT THE PHS.....		B-1

APPENDIX C ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIVITIES STATUS MAP, IR SITE LOCATIONS AT THE PHSC-1

APPENDIX D INRMP COMMENTS AND RESPONSESD-1

APPENDIX E PEST MANAGEMENT PLAN IMPLEMENTATION RECOMMENDATIONS..E-1

APPENDIX F AIR QUALITY CALCULATIONS AND RONA F-1

APPENDIX G NAVY CHAIN OF COMMAND AND RESPONSIBILITIES..... G-1

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1-1 Location Map.....	1-2
2-1 Special Interest Natural Areas on the PHS	2-3
2-2 Areas Designated for Land Use Improvements and Enhancements	2-4
2-3 Future Planning Projects on the PHS.....	2-6
3-1a Habitats and Sensitive Species Locations on the PHS.....	3-3
3-1b Habitats and Sensitive Species Locations on the PHS.....	3-4
3-2 Surface Water Features at the PHS.....	3-16
3-3 California and National Ambient Air Quality Standards.....	3-25

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
ES-1 Recommended Natural Resources Projects	ES-3
ES-2 Comparison of Environmental Consequences of Alternatives	ES-4
2-1 Recommended Natural Resources Projects	2-2
2-2 Future Planning Projects at the PHS*	2-8
3-1 Sensitive Plant Species Potentially Occurring at the PHS.....	3-5
3-2 Sensitive Fish and Wildlife Species Potentially Occurring at the PHS.....	3-9
3-3 Level of Service (LOS) Summary During A.M. and P.M. Peak Hours.....	3-22
3-4 ICU Summary	3-23
3-5 Glossary of Air Quality Terms	3-26
3-6 Air Quality Monitoring Data from the El Rio Monitoring Station 7 Miles (11 km) North of the PHS (1997-1999).....	3-27
4-1 INRMP Projects with the Potential to Trigger the NEPA and Related Issue Area Impacts	4-2
4-2 Construction Assumptions for PHS Improvements*	4-15
4-3 Estimated Annual Construction Emissions for PHS Improvements	4-15
A-1 INRMP Project Management Actions and Implementation Strategies (All Projects).....	A-2
A-2 Required Contents of a Pest Management Plan.....	A-3
A-3 Special-Status Species Surveys Recommended for the Naval Base Ventura County PHS.....	A-8

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CHAPTER 1

PURPOSE AND NEED FOR THE PROPOSED ACTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The Department of the Navy has prepared this environmental assessment (EA) to address the potential environmental impacts associated with proposed implementation of the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for the Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC), Port Hueneme Site (PHS) (U.S. Navy 1999a). The PHS is located on the coast of Ventura County, California, adjacent to the cities of Port Hueneme and Oxnard (Figure 1-1). The INRMP provides a long-term natural resources management strategy for the 1,650-acre (670-hectare) site. The proposed action is the implementation of all goals and actions contained in the INRMP. The alternative to the proposed action is the no-action alternative (refer to Section 2.3, Alternatives). This EA has been prepared in compliance with:

- The National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) of 1969 (42 United States Code [USC] 4321, et seq.);
- Council on Environmental Quality (CEQ) implementing (40 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] §§ 1500-1508, July 1, 1986); and
- Department of the Navy Procedures for Implementing NEPA (32 CFR 775), as described in Chief of Naval Operations Instruction (OPNAVINST) 5090.1B.

For major federal actions, NEPA requires consideration of environmental impacts in the decision-making process. CEQ regulations implement the procedural provisions of NEPA to ensure that federal programs comply with the letter and spirit of NEPA. For U.S. Department of the Navy (U.S. Navy) projects, NEPA guidance is provided in 32 CFR 775.

One of the purposes of the INRMP is to set the agenda for managing the PHS's natural resources. The INRMP also documents baseline conditions for natural resources, reviews current management practices related to natural resources at the PHS, and provides guidance on prioritizing appropriate methods for natural resource preservation and enhancement. A comprehensive Integrated Resources Management Plan (U.S. Navy 1999a) has been prepared for the PHS. The title of this document is the "Integrated Resources Management Plan for the Construction Battalion Center (CBC) Port Hueneme, California." The document contains both a natural and cultural resources component; however, it officially serves as the INRMP for the NBVC, PHS. Therefore, all future references in this EA will be made to the INRMP, PHS; per Navy policy, the EA only addresses natural resources. The "CBC" refers to the former name of the installation prior to regionalization. Currently, both the Port Hueneme and Point Mugu sites are combined as one command referred to as "Naval Base Ventura County," followed by a reference to the specific site. Hence the name, Naval Base Ventura County, Port Hueneme Site.

The goal of the INRMP is to implement an ecosystem-based program for the PHS. An ecosystem management approach has been embraced and supported by the Executive Office of the President, White House Office on Environmental Policy, DoD 4715 (Environmental Conservation Program), and at least 18 federal resource agencies. The INRMP reflects an ecosystem-based approach and the recognition of

LEGEND

Streets	
Railroads	
Streams	

**LOCATION MAP
PORT HUENEME SITE**

PTHUENEME	DATE	DRAWN BY	LINKS	FILENAME	FIGURE NO.
10103-08	7/22/99	RANDALL	none	1.1-1.ai	1-1

the interconnections among species and habitats, ecosystems, and human beings. These interconnections transcend political, economic, and administrative boundaries. The INRMP also reflects the recognition that these ecological relationships and connections can change over time.

1.2 PURPOSE AND NEED FOR THE PROPOSED ACTION

The purpose of the proposed action at the PHS is to provide for:

- conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources;
- sustainable, multipurpose use of the resources (to include recreational improvements); and
- public access to the installation to facilitate such uses, subject to safety requirements and military security.

The need for the proposed action is to meet statutory requirements under the Sikes Act Improvement Act, (Public Law [P.L.] 105-85, Division B. Title XXIX, November 18, 1997, 111 State 2017-2019, 2020-2022). In November 1997, the Sikes Act (16 USC § 670A et seq.) was amended to require the Secretary of Defense to carry out a program to provide for the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations. To facilitate this program, the amendments require the Secretaries of the military departments to prepare and implement INRMPs for each military installation in the U.S. unless the absence of significant natural resources on a particular installation makes preparation of a plan installation inappropriate (P.L. 105-85, Section 670a1B). The INRMP must provide for management activities only to the extent that such activities are consistent with the use of the installation for military preparedness.

Integrated natural resource management has specific goals that are shaped by the military mission, Department of Defense (DoD) guidelines and directives, pertinent laws and regulations, public needs, public values, ecological theory and practice, and management experience. Among the most important goals are the restoration, maintenance, and protection of biological diversity, biological integrity, and ecological health, while allowing for the military mission and appropriate human uses. The INRMP is intended to be a living document integrating all aspects of natural resource management with the PHS's mission.

As required by the Sikes Act Improvement Act, the INRMP must, to the extent appropriate and applicable, provide for:

- fish and wildlife management, land management, and fish and wildlife-oriented recreation;
- fish and wildlife habitat enhancement or modification;
- wetland protection, enhancement, and restoration where necessary for support of fish, wildlife, or plants;
- integration of, and consistency among, the various activities conducted under the plan;
- establishment of specific natural resource management goals and objectives and time frames for the proposed action;
- sustainable use by the public of natural resources to the extent that the use is not inconsistent with the needs of fish and wildlife resources;
- public access to the military installation that is necessary or appropriate for the sustainable uses of natural resources, subject to requirements necessary to ensure safety and military security;

- enforcement of applicable natural resource laws (including regulations);
- no net loss in the capability of the installation's lands to support the military mission of the installation; and
- such other activities as the Navy has determined are appropriate.

In preparing the INRMP, the Navy worked in cooperation with the United States Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS). The USFWS provided a letter of concurrence for the Plan in November 2001. Although concurrence from the National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) is not an official requirement, NMFS also provided comments that were responded to in the final INRMP [Appendix D]. Therefore, the plan reflects the review of these parties concerning conservation, protection, and management of fish and wildlife resources on the installation. In August 1999, the California Department of Fish and Game (CDFG) was requested to provide comments on the INRMP. A follow-up letter was sent in May 2001 and again in October 2001 to request concurrence from this agency on the Final INRMP; however, no response has been received to date. A 30 day public review period for the INRMP was published in September 1999, and the document was available for review in the Oxnard Public Library. However, no comments from the public were received.

1.3 SCOPE OF ENVIRONMENTAL REVIEW

1.3.1 Scope of EA

This EA includes an analysis of potential environmental impacts associated with the proposed action. Resources analyzed in this EA include:

- biological resources
- hydrology, surface water, and groundwater quality
- land use and visual resources
- transportation and circulation
- air quality
- noise
- hazardous materials and wastes

CEQ regulations, NEPA, and Navy procedures for implementing NEPA specify that an EA should address only those resource areas potentially subject to impacts. In addition, the level of analysis should be commensurate with the anticipated level of environmental impact. Consequently, several resource areas have not been carried forward for detailed analysis in this EA since potential impacts were considered negligible, both for the no-action alternative as well as the proposed action. Resources not included in this EA are:

- *Socioeconomics*. Implementation of the proposed action would not affect socioeconomic resources and would comply with Executive Order (EO) 12898, *Federal Actions to Address Environmental Justice in Minority and Low-income Populations* and EO 13045, *Protection of Children from Environmental Health Risks and Safety Risks*. The proposed action would occur within the boundaries of the PHS; no change in personnel levels would occur; no impacts to schools, children, or minority populations would occur; and the small scale of the proposed action would not result in noticeable direct or indirect effects to the economy. No permanent population centers, low-income communities, or minority communities exist at the

proposed project location. Therefore, no communities would be disproportionately susceptible to adverse socioeconomic or environmental impacts. Consequently, population centers dominated by children would not be newly or disproportionately exposed to increased health or safety risks.

- *Utilities and Services.* The proposed action would not adversely affect existing utilities and services. However, since a component of the proposed action includes the minor installation of new water connections and drip irrigation systems (for recreational and landscape improvements), a discussion of potential impacts resulting from the installation of these systems is included in the hydrology and land use/visual resources sections.
- *Geology and Soils.* Implementation of the proposed action would have no adverse impacts to geology and soils. Only minor soil disturbances would occur for a small number of INRMP projects, and the entire PHS is within the 0-5 percent slope range.
- *Cultural Resources.* The proposed action would not create any impacts related to cultural resources since only minor soil disturbances would occur, and the entire PHS has been previously disturbed due to grading and construction activities in the areas proposed for improvements or enhancement.

1.3.2 Organization of EA

The organization of this EA is described below.

Chapter 1, Purpose and Need for the Proposed Action, provides an overview of the reasons why the Navy has proposed to implement an INRMP at the PHS, as well as a description of the scope of environmental review.

Chapter 2, Proposed Action and Alternatives, describes components of the proposed action, alternatives to the proposed action (no-action alternative), military uses, and potential INRMP conflicts.

Chapter 3, Affected Environment, describes existing conditions for resources listed previously in Section 1.3.1.

Chapter 4, Environmental Consequences, evaluates potential environmental impacts of the proposed action and no-action alternative on the affected environment.

Chapter 5, Cumulative Impacts, identifies impacts that may result from the incremental impacts of the proposed action (or alternative) when added to other past, present, and reasonably foreseeable future actions.

Chapter 6, Personnel/Agency Consultation and Coordination, provides background information on consultations with interested and responsible personnel and agencies.

Chapter 7, References, contains a bibliography of documents and other information sources used in preparation of the EA.

Chapter 8, List of Preparers, lists those individuals who assisted in preparing the EA.

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CHAPTER 2

PROPOSED ACTION AND ALTERNATIVES

This chapter presents a detailed discussion of the INRMP and the range of alternatives to be analyzed in the EA. Section 2.1 provides an overview of the management actions contained in the INRMP and the criteria for establishing program priorities for project funding. Section 2.2 outlines the two alternatives addressed in this EA: the preferred alternative (full implementation of the INRMP) and the no-action alternative (continuation of current management activities).

2.1 INRMP OVERVIEW/PROPOSED ACTION

2.1.1 Project Location

The PHS is located on the coast of Ventura County, California, adjacent to the cities of Port Hueneme and Oxnard (refer to Figure 1-1). Port Hueneme is surrounded by the City of Oxnard to the east and north and by Channel Islands Harbor bordering the west. It is situated within the Venturan structural basin of the Western Transverse Ranges Geomorphic Province of California (Norris & Webb 1990). Groundwater aquifers in the region are part of the Oxnard Plain groundwater basin (Turner 1975). Silver Strand Beach and the Pacific Ocean border the southern portion of the base.

2.1.2 INRMP Overview

The INRMP establishes a programmatic framework for managing the PHS's natural resources. The INRMP also documents baseline conditions for natural resources, reviews current management practices related to natural resources at the PHS, and provides guidance on prioritizing appropriate methods for natural resource preservation and enhancement.

The INRMP contains a wide range of management actions that are designed to meet the goals of the Sikes Act Improvement Act (Table 2-1). Details for implementation of these management actions are provided in Appendix A of this EA. Figures 2-1 and 2-2 show the locations of special natural areas and areas designated for land use improvements and enhancement. The management actions identified for potential implementation can be grouped into several major categories:

- Plan/Program Updates and Improvements
- Inventories and Assessments
- Recreational Improvements
- Education/Restoration/Protection/Monitoring
- Other

As is evident from the project list, the management actions proposed for the PHS represent a variety of different project types.

2.1.3 Criteria for Establishing Program Priorities

The priorities for implementation of specific actions of the resources management program at the PHS as recommended in the November 1999 INRMP have been set using criteria used by the DoD to prioritize

Table 2-1. Recommended Natural Resources Projects

Implementation Order	Project Title	Projected Implementation (years)	Program Priority***
NR-1	Pest Management Plan *	1	Class I
NR-2	Base-wide Wetland Delineation	2-5	Class II
NR-3	Sensitive Species Surveys and Floristic Inventory	2-5	Class II
NR-4	Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area A (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)	2-5	Class II
NR-5	Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area B (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)	2-5	Class II
NR-6	Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area D (Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage and Sandy Beach Habitats)	2-5	Class II
NR-7	Revision of the Base Exterior Architecture Plan (BEAP)	2-5	Class II
NR-8	Footpath/Greenbelt Loop**	6-10	Class III
NR-9	Landscape and Recreation Improvements	2-5	Class III
NR-10	Protection Measures for Potential Monarch Butterfly Roosting Sites	6-10	Class II
NR-11	Protection Measures for Kelp Beds	6-10	Class II
NR-12	Protection Measures for the California Brown Pelican and California Least Tern	6-10	Class II
NR-13	Protection Measures for Marine Mammals	6-10	Class II
NR-14	Protection Measures for Native Bird Species	6-10	Class II
NR-15	Development of a Natural Resources Monitoring Program and Database	2-5	Class III
NR-16	Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan Special Interest Natural Area C (Coyote Brush Habitat)	2-5	Class II
NR-17	Adaptive Management Plan for Burrowing Owls	2-5	Class II
NR-18	Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at Installation Restoration Program (IRP) Site 14	2-5	Class III
NR-19	Improvements to the Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan (SWPPP)	2-5	Class III
NR-20	Improvements to the Recycling Program	2-5	Class III
NR-21	Drip Irrigation System Installation	2-5	Class III
NR-22	Outdoor Recreation Assessment	6-10	Class III

Bolded items denote projects with the potential to trigger impacts under NEPA.

*The Pest Management Plan has been completed; however, it is missing specific components that are identified as management actions in the INRMP (refer to Appendices A and E for details). Therefore, it remains a high priority for management action and is a Class I priority; it is the only INRMP project that is programmed for funding.

**Project will be completed incrementally during projected timeframe.

***See Section 2.1.3 for additional information on program priority classification methods.

NR = Natural Resource

funding for resource management program projects. DoD gives priority to resource management program projects according to the following criteria: Class O receives the highest funding priority and Class III receives the lowest funding priority (Department of Defense Instruction [DoDI] 4715.3).

Implementation of any of the INRMP projects will be dependent on the availability of appropriate funding sources. Any requirement for the obligation of funds for projects evaluated in this EA shall be subject to the availability of funds appropriated by Congress, and none of the proposed projects shall be

- LEGEND**
- BUILDINGS
 - ROADS
 - MEAN SEA LEVEL (MSL)
 - SPECIAL INTEREST NATURAL AREA A (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)
 - SPECIAL INTEREST NATURAL AREA B (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)

- SPECIAL INTEREST NATURAL AREA C (Coyote Brush Habitat)
- SPECIAL INTEREST NATURAL AREA D (Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage and Sandy Beach Habitat)
- SPECIAL INTEREST NATURAL AREA E (Marine Subtidal Habitat)

- AREA F (Bard Estate grounds)
- AREA G (Shelterbelts/Windrows)
- AREA H (Seabee Golf Course)

SPECIAL INTEREST NATURAL AREAS AT THE PORT HUENEME SITE

DATE	DRAWN BY	MADE FROM	GIS FILE #	FIGURE
11/2/99	RANDALL	NCBC	4.4-1	2-1

LEGEND

- BUILDINGS
- ROADS
- CHANNELS
- RECREATION
- FOOTPATH/ GREEN BELT LOOP
- LANDSCAPE IMPROVEMENTS ALONG AND NEAR SILVER STRAND ROAD
- LANDSCAPE IMPROVEMENTS ALONG WEST ROAD
- LANDSCAPE IMPROVEMENTS AT BUILDINGS 1166 AND 1167
- LANDSCAPE IMPROVEMENTS AT BUILDINGS 69, 72, 73, AND 5058
- LANDSCAPE IMPROVEMENTS ALONG AND NEAR SILVER STRAND ROAD
- LANDSCAPE IMPROVEMENTS ALONG WEST ROAD
- LANDSCAPE & RECREATION IMPROVEMENTS AT THE PROPOSED RV PARK

AREAS DESIGNATED FOR LAND USE IMPROVEMENTS AND ENHANCEMENTS AT THE PORT HUENEME SITE

DATE	DRAWN BY	MADE FROM	GIS FILE #	FIGURE
7/22/99	RANDALL	NCBC	4.4-2	2-2

interpreted to require obligation or payment of funds in violation of any applicable federal law, including the Anti-Deficiency Act (31 USC § 1341 et seq.). The proposed projects have been prioritized according to DoDI 4715.3, 3 May 1996 (refer to Section 2.1.3). Project NR-1 will be the only INRMP project that is programmed to receive funding, since it has been designated as a “Class I” program priority. The projected implementation time frame has also been included for proposed projects in the INRMP, however, certain projects/programs may be implemented at a later date due to funding or other considerations.

Class O: Recurring Natural Resources Conservation Management Requirements. Includes activities needed to cover the recurring administrative, personnel, and other costs associated with managing DoD’s conservation program that are necessary to meet applicable compliance requirements (federal and state laws, regulations, EOs, and DoD policies) or that are in direct support of the military mission.

Class I: Current Compliance. Includes projects and activities needed because an installation is currently out of compliance (has received an enforcement action from a duly authorized Federal or State agency, or local authority); has a signed compliance agreement or has received a consent order; has not met requirements based on applicable federal or state laws, regulations, standards, EOs, or DoD policies; has needs that are immediate and essential to maintain operational integrity or sustain readiness of the military mission; and/or includes projects and activities needed that are not currently out of compliance.

Class II: Maintenance Requirements. Includes those projects and activities needed that are not currently out of compliance but will become out of compliance if projects or activities are not implemented in time to meet an established deadline beyond the current program year.

Class III: Enhancement Actions (e.g., beyond compliance). Includes those projects and activities that enhance conservation resources or the integrity of the installation mission, or are needed to address overall environmental goals and objectives, but are not specifically required under regulation or EO and are not of an immediate nature.

2.2 MILITARY USES AND INRMP CONFLICTS

The following text briefly describes the military uses of the PHS, along with a brief synopsis of potential conflicts that implementation of the INRMP would have on the military use of the site. Since the geographic area of the management goals spans throughout the entire PHS, Figure 2-1 depicts the “Special Interest Natural Areas” that would likely be affected by the proposed action. In addition, Figure 2-2 shows the areas designated for land use improvements and enhancement. Figure 2-3 contains planned future project areas for the PHS other than INRMP projects.

(NOT TO SCALE)

LEGEND

- | | |
|---|--|
| SANDY BEACH |
| COYOTE BRUSH |
| BUILDINGS |
| ROADS |

FUTURE PLANNING PROJECTS
AND SPECIAL INTEREST
AREAS AT THE
PORT HUENEME SITE

DATE
10/18/00

FIGURE 2-3

2.2.1 Military and Other Uses of the PHS

2.2.1.1 Overview

NBVC is a National Defense Resource offering a unique combination of mission capabilities to CINCPACFLT (See Appendix G). It is an aviation major shore command and a major Naval Construction Force mobilization base operating airport and seaport facilities and providing a full range of base operating support functions for operating forces and shore activities. NBVC provides aviation, logistics, and all base operating support services in support of the Naval Construction Force, and provides aircraft intermediate maintenance services to all military and transient aircraft within the Ventura County area.

2.2.1.2 Potential Conflicts with the Military Mission and Future Planning Projects

No conflicts from INRMP implementation were identified that would directly affect the military mission, due to the generally disturbed nature of most of the land and minimal extent of natural areas, as well as the relatively small size of the PHS (approximately 1,650 acres [670 hectares]). A review of future planned projects for the PHS (other than those proposed in the INRMP) showed 11 potential projects (see Figure 2-3); however, none of these planned projects would be expected to conflict with those designated in the INRMP. These projects are briefly described in Table 2-2. These projects were forecasted by PHS planners and Public Works during interviews in fall of 2000.

Other Conflicts

If the no-action alternative (continuation of current management practices) is chosen, potential conflicts may arise with known biological resources at the PHS. Specifically, an area used periodically for training exercises contains burrowing owls. Therefore, if the INRMP is not implemented and this area is not protected, a potential impact to the burrowing owls may occur if training activities are allowed to continue in this location. However, ample space is available adjacent to this location for training activities; therefore, no adverse impacts would be expected to occur (refer to Section 4.1 for additional information).

2.3 ALTERNATIVES

Alternatives to the proposed action must be considered in accordance with NEPA, CEQ regulations for implementing NEPA, and Navy procedures for implementing NEPA. Two alternatives are analyzed in this EA: the proposed action (INRMP implementation) and the no-action alternative (continuation of current management activities). Negligible impacts were assessed for the no-action alternative as well as for the proposed action. No other alternatives were identified for evaluation and compliance with the Sikes Act Improvement Act requirements.

2.3.1 Proposed Action (Preferred Alternative)

The proposed action is to implement the goals and actions described in the INRMP (refer to Table 2-1 and Appendix A) prepared for the PHS in November 1999. This plan is consistent with the military use of the property and the goals and objectives established in the Sikes Act Improvement Act (as amended). The goal of the INRMP is to implement an ecosystem-based conservation program that provides for conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources in a manner that is: consistent with the military

Table 2-2. Future Planning Projects at the PHS*

Project Number	Project Title	Project Description
Project 1	Port upgrades and improvements	Different numbered wharves located at the harbor will be improved, including pile removal and pile upgrades. Rip-rap will be placed at the harbor edge.
Project 2	Salsa Street repairs	Parking spaces will be installed to serve the nearby recreational vehicle (RV) park, as well as paving, curbs, and gutters.
Project 3	Showcase Building 850 landscaping	The area surrounding Building 850 will be landscaped with native plants.
Project 4	Various demolition projects	Buildings 1192, 816, 1265 will be demolished (corner of 32 nd and West Street).
Project 5 (a) and (b)	Demolition and facility relocation	(a) Building 1146 will be demolished, and (b) the facility operations currently in that building will be relocated to the training area northeast of 23 rd Street and Pacific Avenue.
Project 6	New Construction Equipment Department	The proposed structure will be located in the vicinity of the old construction equipment buildings (see Project 7).
Project 7	Demolition of old construction equipment buildings	Several buildings will be demolished to prepare for the New Construction Equipment Department (see Project 6).
Project 8	Demolition project	Building 1162 will be demolished.
Project 9	New building-P278 (related to Morale, Welfare, and Recreation [MWR]).	The MWR building will be moved near the west end of the golf course to make room for RV storage and expansion.
Project 10	Berm installation	A berm will be installed, to be located on the northeast side of West Road. Construction laydown areas will be needed, and Seabee training areas will be adjusted accordingly.
Project 11	Demolition/construction project	(a) Demolition of Building 283 and (b) construction of building in the "Campus" area.

*This table corresponds to project numbers shown on Figure 2-3. These projects are not part of the INRMP and reflect predictions of future planned projects at the PHS made by planners and the public works departments.

mission; integrates and coordinates all natural resources management activities; provides for sustainable multipurpose uses of natural resources; and provides for public access to natural resources, subject to safety and military security considerations. The management objectives are to integrate fish and wildlife management, land management, and management for outdoor recreational opportunities as practical and consistent with the military mission (U.S. Navy 1998a). The proposed action consists of several categories of projects that have been analyzed in Chapter 4 according to the following headings: pest management, restoration and enhancement, and general site improvements.

2.3.2 No-Action Alternative

The no-action alternative would entail continued implementation of existing natural resources management practices at the PHS. Existing natural resources management practices include the following:

- *Sensitive Species/Habitat Areas*: No comprehensive species surveys have been conducted to determine the potential for species to exist within Special Interest Natural Areas at the PHS. No monitoring baseline of grounds maintenance or other activities with the potential to

disrupt sensitive species has been established. In addition, no comprehensive formal wetlands delineation has been completed, or active management of invasive plant or animal species with the potential to threaten these areas undertaken.

- *Landscaping/Grounds Maintenance:* The Base Exterior Architecture Plan (BEAP) does not include guidelines for the use of native plants in landscaping efforts at the PHS. No official program for revegetation or erosion control exists.
- *Pest Management:* A Pest Management Plan was completed during preparation of this EA; however, key components for effectively managing and monitoring pests were not addressed in the current plan. Pest animals not actively managed at the PHS include mosquitofish, ground squirrels and other rodents, and feral cats. Mosquitoes in the drainage channels at the PHS are currently treated with pesticides and other methods, resulting in the potential to harm sensitive species.
- *Recreation:* No recreation plan or inventory has been conducted at the PHS.
- *Education:* No proactive educational materials have been produced or distributed on sensitive natural resource areas at the PHS.
- *Recycling:* A recycling center is currently operated by the MWR at the PHS.

If the no-action alternative is implemented, ongoing informal practices used for management of natural resources at the PHS would continue. The no-action alternative would not meet the Sikes Act Improvement Act requirements for an INRMP because no formal natural resources management program was in place prior to the INRMP being completed, and current practices are not adequately protecting natural resources at the PHS.

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CHAPTER 3

AFFECTED ENVIRONMENT

This chapter includes a description of existing environmental conditions at the PHS. Information presented in this chapter serves as baseline data to identify and evaluate any potential impacts that could result from the proposed action or no-action alternative. The region of influence (ROI) for each resource is the entire PHS, with the exception of transportation resources, which extend slightly outside the access gates of the PHS.

NEPA and CEQ regulations and Navy procedures for implementing NEPA specify that an EA should focus on those resource areas potentially subject to impacts. In addition, the level of analysis should be commensurate with the anticipated level of environmental impact. Consequently, the affected environment is described for the following resources: biological resources, hydrology and surface water quality, land use and visual resources, transportation and circulation, air quality, noise, and hazardous materials and wastes.

Because the INRMP specifically addresses management of biological resources, this resource is described in greater detail. The biological resources discussion also addresses disease vectors and pest animal populations.

3.1 BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES

3.1.1 Definition of Resource

Biological resources include native or naturalized plant and animal species (i.e., exotic species that have become established) and the habitats within which they occur. Plant associations are referred to as habitat types, and animal species are referred to as wildlife. Habitat can be defined as the resources and conditions present in an area that produces occupancy of a plant or animal (Hall et al. 1997). The existence and preservation of biological resources are intrinsically valuable, and these resources also provide aesthetic, recreational, and socioeconomic values to society. This analysis focuses on species or habitat types that are important to the function of the ecosystem, of special public importance, or are protected under federal or state law or statute. For purposes of this EA, these resources are divided into three major categories: habitat types, wildlife, and special status plant and animal species.

Habitat types include all existing terrestrial plant communities (including wetlands) with the exception of special status plant species.

Wetlands are considered sensitive habitats and are subject to federal regulatory authority under Section 404 of the Clean Water Act (CWA). Jurisdictional wetlands are defined by the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) as those areas that are inundated or saturated by surface or groundwater at a frequency and duration sufficient to support (under normal circumstances) a prevalence of vegetation typically adapted for life in saturated soil conditions (USACE 1987). Areas meeting the federal wetlands definition are under the jurisdiction of the USACE.

In January 2001, the U.S. Supreme Court overturned the “migratory bird rule,” under which the USACE has historically regulated non-navigable, isolated, and intrastate waters that provide habitat for migratory

birds. It was the Court's holding that non-navigable, isolated, and intrastate waters (intrastate lakes, rivers, streams [including intermittent streams], mudflats, sandflats, sloughs, prairie potholes, wet meadows, playa lakes, or natural ponds, the use, degradation, or destruction of which could affect interstate commerce) are no longer considered "waters of the U.S." based solely by virtue of their use as habitat as migratory birds. However, the Court did clearly recognize the USACE's assertion of jurisdiction over traditional navigable waters (defined as waters of the U.S.) and their tributaries and wetlands adjacent to them. Wetlands are considered important to the public interest because they perform significant biological functions, such as providing nesting, breeding, foraging, and spawning habitat for a wide variety of resident and migratory animal species. In addition, wetlands help improve water quality and provide flood protection and erosion control. Wetlands are discussed in Section 3.2.2.4 of this EA, under the Hydrology, Surface Water, and Groundwater Quality discussion. Species associated with wetlands are discussed in the following section.

Wildlife includes all vertebrate animals with the exception of those identified as special status species. Wildlife includes fish, amphibians, reptiles, birds, and mammals. Wildlife also includes those bird species protected under the federal Migratory Bird Treaty Act (MBTA). Assessment of a project's effects on migratory birds places an emphasis on "Species of Concern" as defined by EO 13186, *Responsibilities of Federal Agencies to Protect Migratory Birds*. Additional assessment of potential impacts to migratory birds that are regionally rare occurs under the Special Status Species category.

Special status species are defined as those plant and animal species listed as threatened, endangered, or proposed as such by the USFWS or the California Department of Fish and Game (CDFG), or as species that are regionally rare or of limited distribution and listed by the California Native Plant Society (CNPS). The federal and California Endangered Species Acts protect federally and state-listed threatened and endangered plant and animal species. Federal species of concern are not protected by law; however, these species could become listed and, therefore, protected at any time. Their consideration early in the planning process may avoid future conflicts that could otherwise occur. Navy policy encourages cooperation to protect state-listed animal and plant species; however, there is no statutory mandate for protection by federal entities.

3.1.2 Existing Conditions

3.1.2.1 Habitat Types

The following presents a description of each habitat type found at the PHS in order to provide an overview of habitat concerns. Existing habitat types are coyote brush, California annual grassland, bulrush-cattail, sand verbena-beach bursage, sandy beach, and marine subtidal. For purposes of this EA, habitat types are based on *A Manual of California Vegetation* (Sawyer and Keeler-Wolf 1995). Figures 3-1a and 3-1b present the habitat types identified on the western half of the PHS. Since the eastern half is highly urbanized and landscaped, this portion of the PHS is not included. Sensitive plant species are discussed in Section 3.1.2.3 and presented in Table 3-1.

Coyote Brush

Coyote brush habitat is a diverse habitat type dominated by coyote brush (*Baccharis pilularis*). This habitat is highly disturbed and isolated on the PHS; it occurs primarily at the intersection of Track Road and 23rd Avenue adjacent to the golf course (see Figure 3-1a). Other plant species observed include mulefat (*Baccharis salicifolia*), iceplant, myoporum (*Myoporum laetum*), laurel sumac (*Malosma*

LEGEND

- BUILDINGS
- ROADS
- COYOTE BRUSH
- BULRUSH-CATTAIL
- BURROWING OWL BURROWS

HABITATS AND SENSITIVE SPECIES LOCATIONS AT THE PORT HUENEME SITE

DATE	DRAWN BY	MADE FROM	GIS FILE #	FIGURE
11/5/99	RANDALL	NCBC	3.3-2B	3-1a

LEGEND

- BUILDINGS
- SANDY BEACH
- ROADS
- MARINE SUBTIDAL
- SAND VERBENA-BEACH BURSAGE
- BULRUSH-CATTAIL
- MEAN SEA LEVEL (MSL)

HABITATS AND SENSITIVE SPECIES LOCATIONS AT THE PORT HUENEME SITE

DATE	DRAWN BY	MADE FROM	GIS FILE #	FIGURE
11/5/99	RANDALL	NCBC	3.3-2A	3-1b

Table 3-1. Sensitive Plant Species Potentially Occurring at the PHS

Scientific Name	Common Name	Status				Habitat	Comments	Blooming Period
		Fed	State	CNPS	Navy			
<i>Lasthenia glabrata</i> ssp. <i>coulteri</i>	Coulter's goldfields			1B	ISC	Coastal salt marsh, playas, grassland	Collected at Hueneme in 1901, presumed extant.	Feb-Jun

Notes: ISC = Installation Species of Concern, 1B = Rare, threatened, or endangered in California and elsewhere.
 Sources: U.S. Navy 1999a, Keeney 1999, 2000.

laurina), white sweetclover (*Melilotus alba*), and English plantain (*Plantago lanceolata*) (U.S. Navy 1999a).

California Annual Grassland

California annual grasslands are typically composed of bromes (*Bromus* spp.), California poppy (*Eschscholzia californica*), filarees (*Erodium* spp.), goldfields (*Lasthenia* spp.), lupines (*Lupinus* spp.), mustards (*Brassica* spp.), wild oats (*Avena* spp.), owl's-covers (*Castilleja* spp.), ryegrasses (*Lolium* spp.), and star-thistles (*Centaurea* spp.). Some widespread and invasive exotics include wild oats, mustards, bromes, sweet-clovers (*Melilotus* spp.), and plantains (*Plantago* spp.). These exotic species occur at the PHS throughout highly disturbed grassland and in graded areas that may have been historically occupied by coyote brush. The largest area of California annual grassland is located on the northwest portion of the base and is dominated by introduced annual grasses (U.S. Navy 1999a). However, due to the scattered locations of grassland throughout the PHS, mainly found in isolated pockets surrounding developed administrative and residential areas (with the exception of the golf course), grasslands are not depicted on Figures 3-1a and b.

Bulrush-Cattail

The bulrush-cattail habitat type varies considerably in relation to salinities ranging from fresh to hypersaline. This type typically includes rushes (*Juncus* spp.), bulrushes (*Scirpus* spp.), saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata* var. *spicata*), and broad-leaf cattail (*Typha latifolia*). A more alkaline bulrush-cattail habitat type is found within the drainage channel at the PHS (Figures 3-1a and 3-1b). For purposes of this EA, these drainages will be referred to as Special Interest Natural Area B (refer to Figure 2-1). Vegetation in this area is routinely maintained through the application of an herbicide. Native plant species occurring within this area under unmaintained conditions include common thule (*Scirpus acutus*), American bulrush (*Scirpus americanus*), plantain (*Plantago subnuda*), saltgrass, and common reed (*Phragmites australis*). Nonnative plant species that provide the dominant cover under maintained conditions include crownbeard (*Verbesina enceliodes*) and sourclover (*Melilotus indica*). A freshwater bulrush-cattail type occurs at the PHS in a ponded area north of 23rd Avenue. For purposes of this EA, this freshwater pond will be referred to as Special Interest Natural Area A (refer to Figure 2-1). Dominant species include California bulrush (*Scirpus californicus*) and American bulrush (U.S. Navy 1999a).

Sandy Beaches and Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage

Sand verbena-beach bursage habitat type occurs along the coast at localized stretches of beach and isolated by headlands and rocky tidepools. It is typically characterized by sand verbenas (*Abronia* spp.), beach-bur (*Ambrosia chamissonis*), dune buckwheat (*Eriogonum latifolium*), and sea rocket (*Cakile*

maritima). This habitat type is found along the coast approximately 1,000 feet (300 meters [m]) west of the Port Hueneme Harbor along the southwest boundary of the base (see Figure 3-1b). Native plant species occurring within this area include telegraph weed (*Heterotheca grandiflora*), beach morning glory (*Calystegia soldanella*), and sand verbena (*Abronia maritima*). The dominant plant species, however, is a nonnative plant, Hottentot-fig or iceplant (*Carpobrotus edulis*), and most of the area is disturbed by off-road vehicle use (U.S. Navy 1999a).

Marine Subtidal

Marine subtidal environments consist of surface water, the water column, and sediments for areas from the low tide zone of 2.2 feet (0.7 m) to areas greater than 20 feet (6 m) mean lower low water in depth. Marine subtidal habitat consists of communities associated with sand, mud, and rock substrates; kelp beds are among the most diverse communities in this habitat. Marine subtidal environments are found at the southern border of PHS (see Figure 3-1b).

3.1.2.2 Wildlife Associated with Habitat Types

Although much of the habitat at the PHS is highly disturbed and distributed in small patches, these small patches offer valuable habitat to many wildlife species, including sensitive species. Major landscaped areas at the PHS include shelterbelts/windrows, the Bard Mansion grounds, and the Seabee Golf Course. Artificial habitat for wildlife may also exist at the PHS, including buildings, bridges, debris piles, and dirt mounds (U.S. Navy 1999a).

Following are descriptions of the wildlife species that are typically associated with each of the habitat types, landscaped areas, and artificial habitat found at the PHS. These descriptions are based on the INRMP for the PHS (U.S. Navy 1999a).

Coyote Brush

Mourning dove (*Zenaida macroura*), Anna's hummingbird (*Calypte anna*), Costa's hummingbird (*Calypte costae*), blue-grey gnatcatcher (*Poliophtila caerulea*), song sparrow (*Melospiza melodia*), and white-crowned sparrow (*Zonotrichia leucophrys*) are among the bird species observed in coyote brush habitat at the PHS. Desert cottontail (*Sylvilagus audubonii*), coyote, and deer mouse are typically common in this habitat. Western fence lizard (*Sceloporus occidentalis*), side-blotched lizard (*Uta stansburiana*), and gopher snake (*Pituophis melanoleucus*) are the typical reptile species that occur in coyote brush habitat.

California Annual Grassland

Bird species that have been observed in California annual grassland habitat at the PHS include killdeer (*Charadrius vociferus*), mourning dove, rock dove or pigeon (*Columba livia*), American crow (*Corvus brachyrhynchus*), red-tailed hawk, and house finch (*Carpodacus mexicanus*). Mammal species that are typical of this habitat include opossum (*Didelphis virginiana*), black-tailed jackrabbit (*Lepus californicus*), desert cottontail, California ground squirrel (*Spermophilus beecheyi*), deer mouse, California pocket mouse (*Chaetodipus californicus*), and western harvest mouse. Reptile species that typically occur in grasslands are western fence lizard and gopher snake.

Bulrush-Cattail

The California killifish (*Fundulus parvipinnis*) is a common fish species in bulrush-cattail habitat and has been observed at the PHS. The nonnative sailfin molly (*Poecilia latipinna*) and mosquitofish (*Gambusia affinis*) are fish species that also occur in bulrush-cattail habitat at the PHS. Several bird species utilize bulrush-cattail habitat at the PHS primarily for feeding, including the great blue heron (*Ardea herodias*), great egret (*Casmerodius albus*), snowy egret (*Egretta thula*), black-crowned night heron (*Nycticorax nycticorax*), greater yellowlegs (*Tringa melanoleuca*), black-necked stilt (*Himantopus mexicanus*), and belted kingfisher (*Ceryle alcyon*). Red-winged blackbird (*Agelaius phoeniceus*), American coot (*Fulica americana*), and mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*) have been observed in the freshwater bulrush-cattail habitat. Large- to medium-sized mammals that occur in bulrush-cattail marsh habitat at the PHS include the coyote and raccoon (*Procyon lotor*). Small mammals that are typically found in bulrush-cattail habitat include the deer mouse (*Peromyscus maniculatus*) and western harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys megalotis*). The Pacific treefrog (*Hyla regilla*) is ubiquitous in the region and utilizes freshwater bulrush-cattail habitat on base.

Sandy Beach and Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage

Although not a habitat type, sandy beaches are closely associated with sand verbena-beach bursage habitat and are important areas for wildlife. Among the vertebrates that occur on the sandy beach at the PHS are various birds, including California gull (*Larus californicus*), Heerman's gull (*Larus heermanni*), ring-billed gull (*Larus delawarensis*), Western gull (*Larus occidentalis*), willet (*Catoptrophorus semipalmatus*), spotted sandpiper (*Actitis macularia*), and Western sandpiper (*Calidris mauri*).

Marine Subtidal

The kelp beds located within the harbor at the PHS may provide habitat for many species of fish and invertebrates. There are 150 species of fish along the California coast, and nearly all of them can be found at one time or another in kelp beds. Topsmelt (*Atherinops affinis*), kelp bass (*Paralabrax clathratus*), garibaldi (*Hypsypops rubicundus*), and California sheepshead (*Semicossyphus pulcher*) are among the most common fish species that occur in kelp beds. California spiny lobster (*Panulirus interruptus*), sheep crab (*Loxorhynchus grandis*), and the common sea cucumber (*Parastichopus californicus*) are among the invertebrate species that occur in kelp beds. Bottom-feeding fish that occur in the subtidal zone include the California scorpionfish (*Scorpaena guttata*) and cabezon (*Scorpaenichthys marmoratus*). Although haul-out areas have not been observed at the PHS, California sea lions (*Zalophus californianus*) and harbor seals (*Phoca vitulina*) regularly visit the harbor.

Landscaped Areas and Artificial Habitat

Trees used for landscaping, especially those near water, may provide potential nesting sites for birds. Wood and debris piles at the PHS provide potential habitat for many species of reptiles. Eaves of buildings and bridges provide potential roosting and nesting habitat for several bat species, many of which are considered sensitive species. Dirt mounds at the PHS have been observed to provide preferred habitat for the burrowing owl (*Athene cunicularia*).

3.1.2.3 Special Status Species

Plants

A plant species is considered sensitive if it is listed as endangered, threatened, or proposed for listing as such pursuant to the federal Endangered Species Act (ESA) of 1973, as amended. Installation plant species of concern and species considered sensitive by the California Native Plant Society (CNPS) are also considered sensitive for the purposes of this EA. Installation species of concern are species whose conservation status may be of concern to the PHS. Plant species are listed as sensitive by the CNPS according to five categories: 1) List 1A – species are presumed extinct in California; 2) List 1B – species are rare or endangered in California and elsewhere; 3) List 2 – species are rare or endangered in California but are more common elsewhere; 4) List 3 – species for which more information is needed; and 5) List 4 – species with limited distribution (Skinner and Pavlik 1994). Navy policy encourages cooperation to protect state-listed animal and plant species; however, there is no statutory mandate for protection by federal entities.

The INRMP listed three sensitive plant species (salt marsh bird's beak [*Cordylanthus maritimus* ssp. *maritimus*], Ventura marsh milk-vetch [*Astragalus pycnostachyus* var. *lanosissimus*], and Coulter's goldfields [*Lasthenia glabrata* ssp. *coulteri*]) as potentially occurring at the PHS. However, after further discussions with USFWS and Navy biologists (Keeney 1999, 2000; USFWS 1999b), it was determined that only one species has the potential to occur at the PHS: Coulter's goldfields (see Table 3-1).

Coulter's Goldfields

This species, in the family Asteraceae, is an annual herb that stands up to 24 inches (60 centimeters [cm]) with yellow disks and rays. Coulter's goldfields are known to occur in coastal salt marsh, playas, valley and foothill grassland, and vernal pools. Key threats to this species include urbanization and agricultural development. This plant is an installation species of concern and is included on the CNPS List 1B. This plant was reported in Port Hueneme in 1901 and is presumed extant (CDFG 1998c). Coulter's goldfields has also been identified at the Ventura River mouth and at Mugu Lagoon. Species specific surveys are needed to confirm its presence or absence from the base (U.S. Navy 1999a).

Wildlife

A fish or wildlife species is considered sensitive if it is listed as endangered or threatened, or proposed as such pursuant to the federal ESA, as amended. In addition, marine mammals are considered sensitive since they are protected under the Marine Mammal Protection Act. Installation species of concern are also considered sensitive species and represent species whose conservation status is of concern to the PHS but do not have official status.

Table 3-2 and Figures 3-1a and 3-1b show all sensitive species either observed or potentially occurring at the PHS. Although the California red-legged frog and western snowy plover were originally listed in the Final INRMP as potentially occurring on the PHS, after further discussions with USFWS and Navy biologists, suitable habitat does not occur on base, and neither of these species is expected to occur at the PHS (Keeney 1999, 2000; USFWS 1999b). Species accounts are provided below for sensitive species that have been observed at the PHS, as well as any additional federally listed, proposed listed, or candidate species that potentially occur on base.

Invertebrates

Monarch butterfly (*Danaus plexippus*). Winter roost sites for the Monarch butterfly range along the coast from northern Mendocino to Baja California. Adults overwinter by roosting in tree groves, especially eucalyptus, Monterey pine, and cypress. Although overwintering/roosting populations of monarchs have not been observed at the PHS, monarchs have been observed on base, and the groves of eucalyptus and cypress trees provide potential roost sites for this species.

Table 3-2. Sensitive Fish and Wildlife Species Potentially Occurring at the PHS

Common Name	Scientific Name	Status ¹			Present ²
		Federal	State	Navy	
Invertebrates					
Monarch butterfly	<i>Danaus plexippus</i>			ISC	O
Reptiles					
California horned lizard	<i>Phrynosoma coronatum frontale</i>			ISC	E
Coast patch-nosed snake	<i>Salvadora hexalepis virgultea</i>			ISC	E
Coastal western whiptail	<i>Cnemidophorus tigris multiscutatus</i>			ISC	E
San Bernardino ringneck snake	<i>Diadiphis punctatus modestus</i>			ISC	E
San Diego horned lizard	<i>Phrynosoma coronatum blainvillei</i>			ISC	E
Silvery legless lizard	<i>Anniella pulchra pulchra</i>			ISC	E
South Coast garter snake	<i>Thamnophis sirtalis</i> ssp.			ISC	E
Southwestern pond turtle	<i>Clemmys marmorata pallida</i>			ISC	E
Two-striped garter snake	<i>Thamnophis hammondi</i>			ISC	E
Birds					
Burrowing owl	<i>Athene cunicularia</i>			ISC	O
California brown pelican	<i>Pelecanus occidentalis californicus</i>	FE	SE		O
California least tern	<i>Sterna antillarum browni</i>	FE	SE		E
Elegant tern	<i>Sterna elegans</i>			ISC	E
Mammals					
Long-eared myotis	<i>Myotis evotis</i>			ISC	E
Small-footed myotis	<i>Myotis ciliolabrum</i>			ISC	E
Townsend's western big-eared bat	<i>Corynorhinus townsendii townsendii</i>			ISC	E
Western mastiff bat	<i>Eumops perotis</i>			ISC	E
Yuma myotis	<i>Myotis yumanensis</i>			ISC	E

Notes: ¹E = Endangered; T = Threatened; ISC = Installation species of concern

²O = Observed; E = Expected

Source: U.S. Navy 1999a, Keeney 1999.

Birds

California brown pelican (*Pelecanus occidentalis californicus*). The California brown pelican is federally and state-listed as endangered. The key threat to this species is disturbance to rocky cliffs and roosting areas. Historical threats were DDT (dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane) and other contaminants of their food supply, causing eggshell thinning and altered parental behavior. The brown pelican roosts on rocky cliffs and coastal bluffs; offshore kelp beds provide excellent feeding areas. Pelican numbers peak in southern California from June through January as they migrate north from Mexico. They have been

sighted at numerous locations along the coast of the PHS and often roost on the sandy beach at the PHS. Their nearest known nesting site is on Anacapa Island in the Santa Barbara Channel (U.S. Navy 1999a).

California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*). The California least tern is a federally and state-listed endangered species. This migrating bird species breeds mostly in coastal foredunes and in other sparsely vegetated sites with sandy or gravelly soils. After breeding, family groups regularly occur at lacustrine waters near the coast of southern California. Because this species tends to abandon nesting areas readily if disturbed, it requires nests in areas relatively free of human or predatory disturbance. Reasons for its decline include habitat loss due to human disturbance and alteration, predation by other wildlife species (such as burrowing owls and American kestrels) or domestic or feral animals (such as cats). The nearest known nesting location is near an inlet to the Channel Islands Harbor on Oxnard Beach. This species also nests at McGrath and Ormond Beaches north of the Southern California Edison Company plant and about 0.6 mile (1 km) southeast of the Port Hueneme sewage disposal plant. Least terns have been observed foraging in the harbor at the PHS (U.S. Navy 1999a).

Burrowing owl (*Athene cunicularia*). The burrowing owl is an installation species of concern. This owl species has been declining in numbers across much of its range in western North America and is found primarily in open grassland and coastal scrub habitats as well as in agricultural areas and rangelands. The main threats to this species are habitat loss, poisoning of ground squirrels, and predation by feral cats and dogs. Burrowing owls prey mostly on small mammals and insects. The burrowing owl is a winter visitor in the region. It is one of the few diurnal owls, and it depends on ground squirrels and other small mammals for creating burrows that it uses for refuge and roosting (U.S. Navy 1999a). The burrowing owl has been observed in a dirt mound near Buildings 1421 and 1423 in the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area. Potential wintering habitat exists for this species in California annual grassland habitat throughout the base (especially where ground squirrel burrows occur) (U.S. Navy 1999a).

3.1.2.4 Pest Animal Populations, Exotic Plants, and Disease Vectors

The DoD Pest Management Program of 1996 (DoDI 4150.7) defines pests as arthropods, birds, rodents, nematodes, fungi, bacteria, viruses, algae, snails, marine borers, snakes, weeds, and other organisms (except disease-causing organisms) that adversely affect readiness, military operations, or the well-being of personnel and animals; or attack or damage real property, supplies, equipment, or vegetation. Disease vectors are animals capable of transmitting the causative agent of a human disease; serving as an intermediate or reservoir host of a pathogenic organism; or producing human discomfort or injury. Pest animal populations and disease vectors that are known or expected to occur at the PHS are described below. Pest plant populations, or noxious weeds, known or expected at the PHS have been discussed previously.

Pest Animals

Mosquitofish

Mosquitofish (*Gambusia affinis*) are native to the Atlantic and Gulf Coast drainages and tend to outcompete native fish where they are introduced if not managed appropriately. Mosquitofish are often reared by mosquito abatement districts and released to control mosquitos. Mosquitofish have been found in the drainage channels at the PHS. They were placed in the drainage channels sometime prior to 1993 for mosquito control and are presently not monitored by the base (U.S. Navy 1999a).

Pests Associated with Ballast Water

To maintain stability during transit along coasts and on the open ocean, ships fill their ballast tanks with water from coastal ports from which they originate. Associated sediments also are taken up into the ballast along with a load of living organisms. Species that end up in ballast water range in size from tiny microorganisms to larger species, including schools of fish. After arriving at their destination, ships typically release their ballast water and the associated organisms into the new port. Certain invading species (also known as invasive aquatic species) can cause complex changes within the structure and function of their new ecosystem, including restructuring established food webs, importing new diseases to the region, and outcompeting indigenous species. Ballast water is not currently treated within harbor boundaries by the PHS before being released. However, the Navy is required to flush out their ballast water tanks at least twice while on the open ocean by cycling water through the tanks (Pringle 2001). Testing for invasive aquatic species within the harbor has not yet been conducted to determine whether or not any introductions of these species has inadvertently occurred (U.S. Navy 1999a). Recommendations for testing ballast water are included in the INRMP (refer to Section 4.3.1.1) and are also detailed in Appendix E of this EA.

Ground Squirrels

California ground squirrels occur at the PHS and are considered pests that require control. They may cause habitat degradation by digging up vegetation in landscaped areas. Studies have shown that ground squirrel populations decline in fields where vegetative cover is allowed to increase; decreasing field cover allows ground squirrels to detect predators more easily. Ground squirrel populations are currently not actively managed at the PHS. However, the Pest Management Plan for the PHS provides an active management strategy to address this issue (refer to Appendices A and E). Possible actions for control include rodenticides, live trappings, construction of raptor perches, and increasing grass heights. However, ground squirrels also provide habitat for burrowing owls by providing burrows for this sensitive species.

Feral Cats

A feral cat population has been observed at the PHS. Feral cats are problematic because they are detrimental to native bird populations on base, including sensitive species such as the burrowing owl. Feral cats are also thought to depend upon food from people, garbage, and carrion. There is currently no management program on the PHS for these animals. A management program may consist of a capture and spay/neuter program, or if the problem is severe enough, an extermination program (U.S. Navy 1999a).

Exotic Plant Species

Exotic plant species or noxious weeds are problematic throughout the nation. In response to commercial, agricultural, and public health concerns, the Federal Noxious Weed Act of 1975 (Title 7, Chapter 61) was implemented to provide regulatory control for exotic species. The term “noxious weed” is defined as “any living stage (including but not limited to, seeds and reproductive parts) of parasitic or other plant of a kind, or subdivision of a kind, which is of foreign origin, is new to or not widely prevalent in the United States, and can directly or indirectly injure crops, other useful plants, livestock, or poultry or other interests of agriculture including irrigation, or navigation or the fish and wildlife resources of the United States or the public health” (USFWS 1998a). The U.S. Department of Agriculture’s Animal and Plant

Health Inspection Service is the federal legal authority for the Noxious Weed Act. In California, the Exotic Pest Plant Council (CalEPPC) provides regional and widespread lists for exotic pest plants of greatest ecological concern including those designated as Federal Noxious Weeds. Plants on CalEPPC's List A-1 are considered highly invasive and are widespread in California (CalEPPC 1996).

Exotic plant species are major threats to the continued survival of California's native flora and fauna. The most problematic and widespread species currently identified at the PHS are Hottentot-fig, pampas grass (*Cortaderia* spp.), and Tasmanian blue gum (*Eucalyptus globulus*), all of which are on CalEPPC's List A-1 (CalEPPC 1996). Hottentot-fig, or iceplant, is the dominant species occupying the sand verbena-beach bursage habitat and is also used in landscaped areas throughout the base (U.S. Navy 1999a). Pampas grass is scattered throughout the base with the largest population at the former solid waste disposal area located on Lehman Road (U.S. Navy 1999a). Tasmanian blue gum and other eucalyptus species on the PHS are used for landscaping and windbreaks between Track and West Roads, Channel Islands Boulevard, and Ventura Road (U.S. Navy 1999a).

Other exotic species that are of concern include narrow-leaved iceplant (*Conicosia pugioniformis*) and crystalline iceplant (*Mesembryanthemum crystallinum*). The habitat most threatened by these species is sand verbena-beach bursage habitat that occurs in the southwest portion of the PHS (see Figure 3-1a). Bulrush-cattail habitat is also vulnerable to invasion by German ivy (*Senecio mikanioides*), tamarisk (*Tamarix chinensis*), and giant reed (*Arundo donax*). Giant reed, reported on CalEPPC's List A-1, occurs near the bulrush-cattail habitat north of 23rd Avenue (see Figure 3-1b) (U.S. Navy 1999a).

Disease Vectors

Mosquitoes

Two mosquito species are presently known at the PHS: *Aedes taeniorhynchus* and *Culex tarsalis*. In Southern California, *Aedes taeniorhynchus* larvae are found in salt marshes that are occasionally flooded by high tides. Hosts for this mosquito include large mammals and humans. *Culex tarsalis* larvae occur in all freshwater areas (i.e., pools, riparian habitat, freshwater marshes) and salt marshes with up to 1 percent salinity (Alameda County 1999). Hosts for this species include birds and mammals. Mosquito species such as *Aedes* spp., *Culex* spp., and *Anopheles* spp., are carriers of diseases such as yellow or dengue fever, malaria, virus encephalitis, filariasis, meningitis, and filaria (threadworm) diseases; however, the carriers of these diseases have not been reported for Ventura County.

Rodents

The deer mouse is a host of hantavirus, a virus that is often fatal to human beings. Rodents that are chronically infected with hantavirus can shed the virus in their saliva, urine, and feces for long periods of time. Human infection may occur by inhalation of tiny airborne droplets of fresh or dried rodent excretions, through direct contact with the rodents, or ingestion of contaminated food or water. There is no evidence that hantavirus is transmitted from insects, livestock, or pets. Hantavirus is not normally associated with urban areas. Rather, it is normally associated with rural and semi-rural activities such as cleaning barns and sheds, occupying previously vacant cabins, planting or harvesting field crops, and camping and hiking. Deer mouse populations are widespread in the U.S., and the PHS is likely to have an abundant population on base. There is currently no management program on the PHS for this species. No surveys have been done to confirm the presence or absence of hantavirus on the PHS. However, the

Pest Management Plan for the PHS should provide an active management strategy to address this issue (refer to Appendices A and E).

3.2 HYDROLOGY, SURFACE WATER, AND GROUNDWATER QUALITY

3.2.1 Definition of Resource

This chapter describes the hydrology, surface water, and groundwater quality of the proposed project location(s), including the occurrence, beneficial uses, quality, and flood hazards associated with water resources. Hydrology addresses the quantity, circulation, and distribution of water. Water quality describes the chemical and physical composition of water as affected by natural conditions and human activities. Known wetlands at the PHS are summarized at the end of this section.

3.2.2 Existing Conditions

Surface water hydrologic information is based on Penfield & Smith (1997), the Naval Facilities Engineering Command (NAVFACENGCOM) Master Plan (1987), and Daniel Engineering (1994).

3.2.2.1 Flood Control

Flooding on the PHS may occur several times each year, causing road closures, siltation of roads and parking lots, damage to buildings, and public safety hazards (U.S. Navy 2000b). The PHS is located within areas designated by the Federal Emergency Management (FEMA) as flood hazard Zones A and B. Zone A designates areas subject to 100-year flooding and includes the area in the vicinity of the harbor and along the shoreline, generally south of Surfside Drive. Zone B generally designates areas between the limits of the 100-year and 500-year flood; most of the PHS is located in Zone B (U.S. Navy 2000b).

The Oxnard Plain is bounded by the Ventura River floodplain on the northwest and the Calleguas Creek floodplain on the southeast. The major flood-generating influence on the plain is the Santa Clara River. However, flooding sources are some distance from Port Hueneme (U.S. Navy 2000b). Flooding typically occurs on the PHS due to inadequate drainage during storm events and unusually high tides, as described in the following text (U.S. Navy 2000b). The southern portion of the PHS is particularly vulnerable to flooding.

3.2.2.2 Surface Water Drainage

The PHS is located on the southwest margin of the Oxnard Plain on a broad, level floodplain and river delta formed by the Santa Clara River. The drainage system at the PHS consists of interconnected storm drain pipes, box culverts, open ditches, and open drainage channels. These drainage channels collect runoff from the PHS and convey it to the Port Hueneme Harbor. Drainage at the PHS is generally inadequate. During times of unusually high tides, the western-most storm drains back up and water must be pumped to a higher discharge point (U.S. Navy 2000b).

The topography of the base is relatively flat, sloping from an elevation of about 27 feet (8 m) above mean sea level (MSL) in the northeastern corner of the base to between 5 and 10 feet (1.5 and 3 m) MSL in the western and southern portions of the base, respectively. Surface water hydrology at the PHS is characterized primarily by low-gradient overland flow and by surface water channels that drain south into Hueneme Harbor. Overland flow is intercepted by surface water channels located adjacent to widely spaced roadways. Water flow in the surface water channels is intermittent and seasonal, depending on rain events. However, due to shallow groundwater and tidal influence, surface water is usually present in

the main surface channels such as 23rd Avenue Channel, Pleasant Valley Road Channel, and Pennsylvania Road Channel (U.S. Navy 2000b).

The following three paragraphs summarize the surface water drainage discussion prepared for the P-513 EA (U.S. Navy 2000b). The areas north and south of 23rd Avenue drain to the 23rd Avenue Channel via underground storm drains, as well as the areas north of 28th Avenue. The eastern portion of the PHS drains to the eastern terminus of the 23rd Avenue Channel by buried storm drains.

The residential, community facilities, and administration areas east of Pacific Road drain to the west into a conduit that empties at the eastern Pleasant Valley Road Channel. This channel extends to the west, collecting runoff from the supply receiving area, fire station, and warehouse areas. It eventually joins the Pennsylvania Road Channel at the tide gates.

All flows in the Pennsylvania Road Channel exit the base through the tide gates and a pump station at the upper end of the harbor (Figure 3-2). These tide gates are closed during medium to high tides to prevent water from flowing up the drainage channels. When there is runoff from a storm and the tide is over 1-2 feet (0.3-0.6 m) MSL, the storm water is pumped from a small forebay north of the tide gates to the harbor canal.

3.2.2.3 Groundwater

Groundwater is defined as that part of the subsurface water that is in the zone of saturation: essentially, all subsurface water is distinct from surface water. Groundwater as a resource pertains to the identification and description of aquifers, depth to groundwater, groundwater quality, groundwater flow direction, recharge and infiltration, and communication between aquifers (U.S. Navy 2000b).

Groundwater beneath the Oxnard Plain occurs in at least five aquifers contained in Recent to Pleistocene Age deposits. The groundwater aquifers beneath the Oxnard Plain are contained in sedimentary deposits associated with the Santa Clara River, its floodplain, delta, and estuary. The aquifers are present to maximum depths of 3,000 feet (910 m) or more and include five major units. In order of increasing depth, these aquifers are the Semi-Perched aquifer, Oxnard aquifer, Mugu aquifer, Hueneme aquifer, and Fox Canyon aquifer. A sixth aquifer, the Grimes Canyon aquifer, is present beneath the Fox Canyon aquifer in the southern and eastern portions of Oxnard Plain. It is absent beneath the PHS due to a change in rock type (PRC Environmental Management Inc. [PRC] 1997).

The Semi-Perched Aquifer occurs from the base of surficial soils to an average depth of about 75 feet (23 m) beneath most of the Oxnard Plain (Mukae and Turner 1975) with the water table occurring at about 5 to 10 feet (1.5 to 3 m) below the ground surface (bgs). Underlying the Semi-Perched Aquifer are the Oxnard and Mugu aquifers. The Oxnard Aquifer is generally 150 feet (46 m) thick, occurring from the base of the Semi-Perched Aquifer to approximately 300 feet (91 m) bgs. The Mugu Aquifer occurs within Pleistocene deposits located about 300 to 500 feet (91 to 152 m) bgs and flows from northeast to southwest. An erosional unconformity and a discontinuous aquitard of silt and clay up to about 200 feet (61 m) thick separates the Mugu Aquifer from the underlying aquifer. The lowest aquifers, the Hueneme Aquifer and Fox Canyon aquifers, occur between 500 and 1,500 feet (152 and 457 m) bgs and are found within the San Pedro and Santa Barbara Formations of Pleistocene and Pliocene age deposits (U.S. Navy 2000b).

- LEGEND**
- BUILDINGS
 - ROADS
 - SURFACE WATER

400 0 400 800 FEET

**SURFACE WATER
FEATURES AT THE
PORT HUENEME SITE**

DATE	DRAWN BY	MADE FROM	GIS FILE #	FIGURE
7/22/99	RANDALL	NCBC	3.3-1	3-2

Groundwater flow within the Semi-Perched Aquifer is generally horizontal, and recharge of the aquifer is through rainfall infiltration and surface water runoff. The dominant groundwater flow direction in the Semi-Perched Aquifer at the PHS is toward the southwest. The Semi-Perched Aquifer discharges to the Pacific Ocean. Some Semi-Perched Aquifer groundwater also discharges to drainage ditches located along or east of the main drainage channel. The ditches then drain to the Pacific Ocean via the Port Hueneme Harbor. However, in the eastern and central portions of the base, the Semi-Perched Aquifer groundwater is diverted from this general pattern because a compromised sanitary system allows groundwater infiltration.

The City of Port Hueneme has partially repaired the sanitary sewer system with the intent of eliminating groundwater infiltration. In the area between the Channel Islands Harbor and the groundwater sink, the Semi-Perched Aquifer groundwater flows to drainage ditches, the groundwater sink, and the coast.

Tidal effects or proximity to drainage channels locally influences site-specific flow patterns where groundwater is often exposed. The hydraulic parameters of the Semi-Perched Aquifer are highly variable. Transmissivity ranges from 19,000 to 45,000 gallons per day per foot (236,000 to 559,000 liters per day per meter), and hydraulic conductivity ranges from 60 to 3,000 gallons per day per square foot (2,400 to 122,000 liters per day per square meter) (PRC 1995a). The Semi-Perched Aquifer is separated from the underlying Oxnard and Mugu Aquifers by an aquitard consisting of silt and clay with interbedded sand lenses. The aquitard is believed to be continuous across the base (U.S. Navy 2000b).

Freshwater recharge to the aquifers beneath the Oxnard Plain and NBVC Port Hueneme occurs naturally from above-average rainfall events, infiltration through the Santa Clara riverbed, and artificial seepage areas near Saticoy and El Rio northwest of the base (Ventura County Public Works Agency 1981).

There are no existing potable water supply wells in the Semi-Perched Aquifer on the base or in the county. Historically, wells in this zone were rarely developed due to poor water quality and production. However, the aquifer has a beneficial use for municipal and domestic water supply designated in the 1994 Los Angeles Regional Water Quality Control Board Basin Plan (U.S. Navy 2000b).

Groundwater in the Semi-Perched Aquifer is non-potable due to naturally occurring elevated total dissolved solids (TDS), sulfates, and chloride concentrations caused by seawater intrusion. TDS levels range from 310 to 60,000 milligrams per liter (mg/l), sulfate levels range from 110 to 25,000 mg/l, and chloride levels range from 50 to 20,000 mg/l (PRC 1995a). TDS concentrations are greater than the Regional Water Quality Control Board (RWQCB) beneficial use criteria of 3,000 mg/l in the southwestern half of the base (U.S. Navy 2000b).

The groundwater Remedial Investigation (RI) report (U.S. Navy 2000b) for the PHS indicates that the Oxnard and Mugu Aquifer groundwater as well as surface water have not been significantly impacted by metals, volatile organic compounds, or semi-volatile organic compounds. Groundwater at monitoring well GWIMW22 contains elevated concentrations of benzene, cis-1, 2-DCE (dichloroethylene), and vinyl chloride. Groundwater at monitoring well 543MW01 contains elevated concentrations of 1,2-DCE. In four areas (Sites 9, 14, 20, and 22), organic contaminants of potential concern are found at higher levels (more than an order of magnitude greater than the state of California maximum contaminant levels that identify chemicals of potential human health concern). These areas warrant further evaluation if the Semi-Perched Aquifer groundwater would ever be utilized as a drinking water source. Total petroleum hydrocarbons were also detected in Semi-Perched Aquifer groundwater; total petroleum hydrocarbon was

evaluated based on the presence of its toxic constituents (benzene, ethylbenzene, toluene, and xylene). Free-phase petroleum was consistently identified at and near Site 22 (U.S. Navy 2000b).

3.2.2.4 Wetlands and Jurisdictional Waters of the U.S.

A wetland determination was conducted in 1997 (Woodward-Clyde 1998) and updated in 2000 at the drainage channels to determine the extent of wetlands based on the USACE three-parameter definition. The drainage canals include the 23rd Avenue Channel, Pennsylvania Road Channel to the harbor, Lehman Road Channel, and the Pleasant Valley Road and Eastern Pleasant Valley Road Channels.

The field investigations followed the routine determination procedures in the USACE (1987) wetland delineation manual, except that soil samples were not examined due to the contaminated nature of the sediments. Dominant plant species were recorded for each habitat type. Visual evidence of wetland hydrology was recorded in the drainages (U.S. Navy 2000b).

Hydrophytic plants dominate the two small patches of vegetation that occur in the channel bottoms in unmaintained conditions. The bottoms of the channels at the PHS are mostly covered with water throughout the year due to a combination of winter runoff, tidal influence, and shallow groundwater. Therefore, wetland hydrology is present. Hydric soils are presumed to be present due to the continual inundation of the channel bottoms. In total, the vegetation in this area encompasses 130 square feet (12 m²), or 0.003 acres (0.001 hectares). Under normal circumstances, these wetland patches would be under the jurisdiction of the USACE. In Section 404 of the Clean Water Act, the USACE regulates dredged material and fill discharged into “waters of the United States.” Waters of the U.S. are generally defined in 33 CFR 328.3(a) to include navigable waters (e.g., rivers, streams, lakes) and vegetated wetlands. The USACE issued jurisdictional determination for the drainage channels at the PHS in March 1994.

However, the USACE does not consider the channels above the mean high water point to be “navigable waters” or “waters of the United States” because they were excavated on dry land. Both of the wetland patches are above the mean high water point and are located in excavated channels on previously dry land (U.S. Navy 2000b). Hence, the USACE has waived permitting requirements for these wetlands (refer to Appendix B).

Wetlands at other locations on the PHS may be present but have not been formally delineated. A formal delineation is currently being performed by the Army Corps of Engineers.

The Port Hueneme harbor area and beach lie immediately adjacent to the Pacific Ocean. Under definitions of Section 404, the ocean is considered to be a jurisdictional resource shoreward to the high tide line. The Port Hueneme Harbor also qualifies as a bay with regulatory jurisdiction extending to the entire surface and bed of all water bodies subject to the tidal action.

3.3 LAND USE AND VISUAL RESOURCES

3.3.1 Definition of Resource

Land use encompasses both undeveloped and developed land. Undeveloped land is commonly classified as open space, while developed land uses range from residential and commercial to recreational and agricultural. Land use is regulated by plans and policies that identify the type and extent of uses allowed in specific areas.

Visual resources are defined as the natural and man-made features that constitute aesthetic qualities and values of an area. These features contribute to the overall impression that an observer receives when viewing an area. Landforms, water surfaces, vegetation, and structures are considered distinctive elements of an area's visual character.

3.3.1.1 California Coastal Management Program

Coastal states are provided the authority to evaluate projects conducted, funded, or permitted by the federal government through the Coastal Zone Management Act (CZMA) of 1972, as amended. Under the CZMA, any federal project or activity affecting the coastal zone must be consistent to the maximum extent practicable with the provisions of federally approved state coastal plans.

The California Coastal Act (CCA) established the California Coastal Commission (CCC), the state agency responsible for implementing the CZMA. The CCC developed the California Coastal Management Program (CCMP) pursuant to the requirements of the CZMA. The CCC is responsible for reviewing proposed federal and federally authorized activities affecting the state's coastal resources to assess their consistency with the federally approved CCMP. If the action may affect coastal resources, the federal entity proposing the action must submit a Coastal Consistency Determination to the CCC documenting how the action complies with the policies of the CCA.

The CCC regulates activities within the California coastal zone pursuant to the California Coastal Zone Management Program. The CCC has the power to govern public access, recreation, marine and land resources (including wetlands and coastal waters), and development within the coastal zone or activities that may affect coastal resources. The geographic limit of the CCC's seaward jurisdiction is generally limited to 3 nautical miles offshore.

3.3.1.2 City of Port Hueneme General Plan, Local Coastal Plan, and Port Hueneme Master Plan

As a federal facility, the PHS is not subject to the land use jurisdiction of the Port of Hueneme. The General Plan and Local Coastal Plan (LCP) are local documents prepared by the City of Port Hueneme. Therefore, the policies in the General Plan and Local Coastal Plan (developed as a component of the General Plan) do not apply to activities on the PHS. Although designations and policies do not currently apply to the PHS, the General Plan map contains land use designations for the PHS. It is designated as a "Naval Construction Battalion Center."

The PHS is designated Area I in the City's LCP, which states that facilities on the base are exempt from the LCP. However, CZMA requires that all federal agencies ensure that their activities are consistent, to the maximum extent practicable, with the state's coastal management program established pursuant to the

CZMA. Therefore, applicable coastal zone policies for the proposed action are contained in the state Coastal Act (U.S. Navy 2000b).

The portion of Port Hueneme Harbor outside the PHS is under the jurisdiction of the Oxnard Harbor District, which has a certified Port Master Plan prepared by the Oxnard Harbor District and approved by the California Coastal Commission (U.S. Navy 2000b).

3.3.2 Existing Conditions

3.3.2.1 Land Use

The PHS is located within the City of Port Hueneme's limits. The base is bounded on the southwest by the residential communities of Silver Strand and Hollywood-by-the-Sea, on the northwest by commercial development associated primarily with Channel Islands Marina, on the north by commercial development, on the east by residential uses, and on the southeast by port development associated with the Port of Hueneme. The latter is the U.S. Port of Entry for California's Central Coast region and serves international businesses and ocean carriers from both the Pacific Rim and Europe. It is also the primary support facility for offshore industry in the Central Coast area. Hueneme Beach lies directly south of the easternmost portion of the base, and Ormond Beach lies farther to the southeast. Silver Strand Beach adjoins the southernmost portion of the base.

The PHS provides training, administrative, and logistic support for "Seabees" (i.e., Construction Battalion) throughout the world. Although the Port Hueneme Division (PHD) Naval Surface Warfare Center (NSWC) and the PHS are physically located together, operationally they remain separate. The facilities within the PHD NSWC complex are used for providing test and evaluation, in-service engineering, and integrated logistics support for surface warfare combat systems, subsystems, and related expendable ordnance of the U.S. Navy Surface Fleet. Most of the facilities within the PHS boundaries are of an industrial or office nature, but the eastern portion of the property contains residential uses and ancillary facilities, recreational facilities, and a Seabee Museum. Refer to Section 2.2 for additional discussion of military uses of the PHS.

Developed Grounds

The PHS encompasses approximately 1,650 acres (670 hectares) of flat, mostly developed or paved lands with residential, industrial, and commercial land uses. There are 36 miles (58 km) of road and 16 miles (26 km) of railroad at the PHS (U.S. Navy 1997). There are 408 buildings on 110 acres (45 hectares), not including family housing.

Housing

Military family housing at the PHS is mostly concentrated on the southern end of the PHS. Civilian and military personnel, along with their dependents, live on the PHS in 817 family housing units.

Operations/Industrial

Out Leasing

The Oxnard Harbor District holds a license that allows for up to 25 acres (10 hectares) of land to be used. This acreage varies from day to day, depending upon operations of the harbor. The out-leased land is

used for storage of goods that come through the portion of the harbor that is owned by the Oxnard Harbor District (Thompson 1999). Several additional leases are held at the PHS by private corporations.

The Port of Hueneme

The Port of Hueneme is the only deep-water harbor port between Los Angeles and San Francisco. The Port of Hueneme is owned in part by the Oxnard Harbor District; the U.S. Navy owns the remaining dock space. The Oxnard Harbor District also owns and operates approximately 69 acres (28 hectares) of land in the harbor area and adjacent channel (Ortiz 1999). Importing primarily occurs through the commercial portion of the harbor.

The Port of Hueneme serves as the principal staging area for supplies, equipment, and crews for the oil platforms located in the Santa Barbara Channel. The port also handles a small amount of fuel oil for Southern California Edison Company, near the PHS (Southern California Association of Governments 1988). The newest commodity to be imported through the port is liquid fertilizer, which comes in bulk tankers (Ortiz 1999).

The Port of Hueneme is also vitally important to operations at the PHS. A port facility with a total of 10 berths exists in the harbor. Imports and exports through the Navy include bulk items and wheeled cargo, which serve military operations for bases throughout the Pacific range (Ortiz 1999).

Administration Area

Building 1000 serves as the main administration area for the PHS. In addition to this main building, other administrative structures are found throughout the PHS.

3.3.2.2 Visual Resources

Visual resources on the PHS primarily include developed lands, with administrative buildings or housing throughout the base. There are also isolated patches of Special Interest Natural Areas (i.e., small areas of open space considered a visual resource due to their aesthetic and natural value). This includes a 33-acre (13-hectare) grassland that was formerly an IRP site on the west side of the PHS (refer to Figure 2-1). The PHS is visible from the surrounding communities, and views from public recreational areas (such as beaches and parks) are considered to be sensitive.

3.4 TRANSPORTATION AND CIRCULATION

3.4.1 Definition of Resource

Transportation and circulation refers to the movement of vehicles on roadway networks. Primary roads, such as major interstates, are designed to move traffic and do not necessarily provide access to all adjacent areas. Secondary roads (or surface streets) are used to gain access to residential and commercial areas, hospitals, and schools. Operating conditions and the adequacy of roadway systems and intersections are described in terms of their average daily traffic (ADT) volumes and level of service (LOS). The LOS measure is an indicator of a roadway’s ability to accommodate vehicular movement. LOS describes operational conditions as influenced by speed, travel time, freedom to maneuver, safety, driving comfort, and convenience. LOS measures range from good (LOS A) to gridlock (LOS F). The ROI for transportation and circulation includes the PHS and the intersections at its primary access gates.

3.4.2 Existing Conditions

A comprehensive network of local roadways serves the PHS. Existing conditions at key intersections near the PHS are summarized in Table 3-3. As shown in the table, the intersection with the heaviest congestion during peak-hour conditions is the Bard Road exit to Ventura Road.

Table 3-3. Level of Service (LOS) Summary During A.M. and P.M. Peak Hours

Intersection	Peak Hour	Existing LOS
Channel Islands Blvd. at Victoria Ave	A.M.	A
	P.M.	C
Channel Islands Blvd at Patterson Road/U.S. Navy Construction Battalion Center (USNCBC)	A.M.	A
	P.M.	A
Channel Islands Blvd. at Ventura Road	A.M.	A
	P.M.	C
Sunkist Ave./USNCBC at Ventura Road	A.M.	A
	P.M.	A
Bard Road/USNCBC at Ventura Road	A.M.	A
	P.M.	D
Pleasant Valley Road at Ventura Road	A.M.	A
	P.M.	A
Port Hueneme Road at Ventura Road	A.M.	A
	P.M.	A

Source: U.S. Navy 2000b.

The *Port Hueneme Traffic Study and Evaluation of Main Gate Relocation* contains details on the local transportation conditions for the PHS (Austin-Foust Associates 1998). Existing daily traffic conditions as well as morning and evening peak hour volumes are summarized from this study in the following text.

The highest traffic volume on the PHS occurs on 23rd Avenue at the PHS Gate, where approximately 15,000 vehicles were counted in a 24-hour period. Once on the PHS, however, the volumes drop dramatically and range from ADT volumes of 5,700 vehicles down to less than 100 vehicles. A total of approximately 28,000 vehicles enter and exit the base daily. In the morning, most vehicles are entering the PHS (peak of 1,750 vehicles per hour); in the afternoon, most vehicles exit. At midday, the volumes entering and exiting are relatively equal and make up the highest two-way total for a typical day (Austin-Foust Associates 1999).

With respect to hourly traffic volumes, the peak hours display normal weekday trends (i.e., heavy entering in the A.M. and exiting in the P.M.). The peak hour for total two-way traffic movement is noontime for both weekdays and weekends. The existing conditions, according to the intersection capacity utilization (ICU) method were used in order to determine the LOS at each intersection on the PHS. Table 3-4 summarizes the ICU for each intersection (Austin-Foust Associates 1999).

Table 3-4. ICU Summary

Intersection*	A.M.	P.M.
Patterson and 23 rd	0.20	0.21
Pacific and 23 rd	0.32	0.43
Harris and 23 rd	0.30	0.52
Patterson and 32 nd	0.13	0.15
Pacific and 32 nd	0.41	0.45
Patterson and Lehman	0.09	0.09
Patterson and Tower	0.08	0.06
Pacific and Pleasant Valley	0.16	0.18

Source: Austin-Foust Associates 1999.

*Assumes signalized intersections. Level of Service ranges: A = 0-0.60; B = 0.61-0.70; C = 0.71-0.80; D = 0.81-0.90; E = 0.91-1.00; F = > 1.00.

3.5 AIR QUALITY

This section addresses air quality conditions for the PHS and includes a description of air quality terminology, air quality conditions, and regulatory requirements applicable to the proposed action.

3.5.1 Definition of Resource

Air quality is defined as the ambient air concentrations of specific criteria pollutants determined by the USEPA to be of concern to the health and welfare of the general public. These criteria pollutants include ozone (O₃), carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), particulate matter less than 10 microns in diameter (PM₁₀), and lead (Pb). Both the federal government and California have established ambient air quality standards (National Ambient Air Quality Standards and California Ambient Air Quality Standards, respectively) for these criteria pollutants (Figure 3-3). These standards identify the maximum allowable concentrations of criteria pollutants that are considered safe, with an additional adequate margin of safety to protect human health and welfare. Depending on the type of pollutant, these maximum concentrations may not be exceeded at any time, or may not be exceeded more than once per year (USEPA 1999). As shown in Figure 3-3, the state standards are somewhat more stringent than the comparable federal standards.

Both the State of California and the federal government have established ambient air quality standards for several different pollutants, which are often referred to as “criteria pollutants” (Figure 3-3). Responsibility for air quality management programs in California is divided between the California Air Resources Board (CARB) (the primary state air quality management agency) and air pollution control districts (the primary local air quality management agencies). Definitions of technical air quality terms used in this section are defined in Table 3-5.

3.5.1.1 Permit Programs

Section 176(c) of the CAA, as amended, requires federal agencies to ensure that actions undertaken in nonattainment or maintenance areas are consistent with the CAA and with federally enforceable air quality management plans. The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) General Conformity Rule applies to federal actions occurring in nonattainment or maintenance areas when the total direct and indirect emissions of nonattainment pollutants (or their precursors) exceed specified thresholds. The *de minimis* levels for O₃ and particulate matter less than 10 microns in diameter (PM₁₀) are 25 tons (50,000 pounds or 22,680 kilograms [kg]) and 100 tons (200,000 pounds or 90,720 kg) per year, respectively. Compliance is presumed if the net increase in direct and indirect emissions from a federal action would be less than the relevant *de minimis* level. However, if the increase in emissions for a nonattainment pollutant exceeds the relevant *de minimis* level, a formal conformity determination process must be followed.

The California Clean Air Act (CCAA) of 1988 requires air pollution control districts and air quality management districts to develop air quality management plans for meeting state ambient air quality standards for O₃, CO, SO₂, and NO₂. CARB is responsible for developing a plan for meeting state PM₁₀ standards. California Ambient Air Quality Standards generally are somewhat more stringent than the comparable federal standards (see Figure 3-3).

POLLUTANT	AVERAGING TIME	CALIFORNIA STANDARDS (1)	NATIONAL STANDARDS (2)	
			Primary	Secondary
Ozone (O ₃) (3)	8 Hour	•	0.08 ppm (157 µg/m ³)	Same as Primary Standards
	1 Hour	0.09 ppm (180 µg/m ³)	0.12 ppm (235 µg/m ³)	
Carbon Monoxide (CO)	8 Hour	9.0 ppm (10 mg/m ³)	9.0 ppm (10 mg/m ³)	•
	1 Hour	20 ppm (23 mg/m ³)	35 ppm (40 mg/m ³)	
Nitrogen Dioxide (NO ₂)	Annual Average	•	0.053 ppm (100 µg/m ³)	Same as Primary Standard
	1 Hour	0.25 ppm (470 µg/m ³)	•	
Sulfur Dioxide (SO ₂)	Annual Average	•	0.030 ppm (80 µg/m ³)	•
	24 Hour	0.04 ppm (105 µg/m ³)	0.14 ppm (365 µg/m ³)	•
	3 Hour	•	•	0.50 ppm (1300 µg/m ³)
	1 Hour	0.25 ppm (655 µg/m ³)	•	•
Respirable Particulate Matter (PM ₁₀)	Annual Arithmetic Mean	30 µg/m ³	50 µg/m ³	Same as Primary Standards
	24 Hour	50 µg/m ³	150 µg/m ³	
Respirable Particulate Matter (PM _{2.5})	Annual Arithmetic Mean	no separate standard	15 µg/m ³	Same as Primary Standards
	24 Hour		65 µg/m ³	
Sulfates	24 Hour	25 µg/m ³	•	•
Lead (Pb)	30 Day Average	1.5 µg/m ³	•	•
	Calendar Quarter	•	1.5 µg/m ³	Same as Primary Standard
Hydrogen Sulfide (HS)	1 Hour	0.03 ppm (42 µg/m ³)	•	•
Vinyl Chloride (chloroethene)	24 Hour	0.010 ppm (26 µg/m ³)	•	•
Visibility Reducing Particles	8 Hour (10:00 a.m. to 6:00 p.m. PST)	In sufficient amount to produce an extinction coefficient of 0.23 per kilometer due to particles when the relative humidity is less than 70 percent. Measurement in accordance with CARB Method V.	•	•

ppm – parts per million
µg/m³ – micrograms per cubic meter
mg/m³ – milligrams per cubic meter
• – no standard established

Sources: CARB 2000a; USEPA 1999.

- (1) CO, SO₂ (1- and 24-hour), NO₂, O₃, PM₁₀, and visibility reducing particles standards are not to be exceeded. All other California Standards are not to be equaled or exceeded.
- (2) Not to be exceeded more than once a year except for annual standards.
- (3) USEPA promulgated new federal 8-hour O₃ and fine particulate matter standards in 1997. The federal 1-hour O₃ standard continues to apply in areas that violated the standard. Attainment status for the 8-hour standard will be determined in 2000.

Figure 3-3
California and National Ambient Air Quality Standards

Table 3-5. Glossary of Air Quality Terms

Term	Definition
<i>General Terminology</i>	
Ambient Air Quality	Atmospheric concentration of a specific compound (amount of pollutants in a specified volume of air) actually experienced at a particular location (this may be some distance from the source of the pollutant emissions).
Criteria Pollutants	Pollutants for which state and federal standards have been established.
Federal Standards	National Ambient Air Quality Standards established by the Clean Air Act (CAA).
Primary Pollutants	Pollutants emitted directly into the atmosphere such as carbon monoxide (CO), sulfur dioxide (SO ₂), lead particulates, and hydrogen sulfide.
Pollutant Emissions	Amount (usually stated as a weight) of one or more specific compounds introduced into the atmosphere by a source or group of sources.
Secondary Pollutants	Pollutants formed through chemical reactions in the atmosphere such as ozone (O ₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO ₂), and sulfate particles.
State Standards	Standards established by the California Clean Air Act (CCAA).
<i>Conformity Terminology</i>	
Attainment Areas	Areas that comply with federal standards.
Attainment/Maintenance Areas	Areas that have been reclassified from nonattainment to attainment.
Conformity Determination	Process required if the increase in emissions for a nonattainment pollutant exceeds the relevant <i>de minimis</i> level.
<i>de minimis</i>	Emission thresholds that trigger requirements for a conformity analysis.
Nonattainment Areas	Areas that violate federal standards.
Unclassified Areas	Areas that lack monitoring data to demonstrate attainment or nonattainment status.

3.5.2 Existing Conditions

Ventura County is in nonattainment for the federal and state O₃ standards and for the state PM₁₀ standard (CARB 2000). Table 3-6 summarizes air quality monitoring data in the vicinity of the PHS. The closest air quality monitoring station is in the community of El Rio, approximately 7 miles (11 km) north of the PHS. It is generally representative of air quality conditions in the coastal portion of Ventura County. Federal O₃ standards are exceeded only occasionally at this location, while the more stringent state O₃ standards are exceeded several times each year (U.S. Navy 1998c). Over the past three years, the federal PM₁₀ standard has been exceeded once and the state PM₁₀ standard has been exceeded five times.

Table 3-6. Air Quality Monitoring Data from the El Rio Monitoring Station 7 Miles (11 km) North of the PHS (1997-1999)

Air Quality Indicator	1997	1998	1999
Ozone*			
Peak 1-hour value (ppm)	0.10	0.10	0.10
Days above federal standard (0.12 ppm)	0	0	0
Days above state standard (0.09 ppm)	2	1	1
Particulate Matter less than 10 microns in diameter**			
Peak 24-hour value ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	252.5	70.3	50.8
Days above federal standard ($150 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	1	0	0
Days above state standard ($50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	3	1	1
Carbon Monoxide			
Peak 8-hour value (ppm)	1.9	2.0	1.2
Days above federal standard (9.0 ppm)	0	0	0
Days above state standard (9.0 ppm)	0	0	0
Sulfur Dioxide			
Peak 24-hour value (ppm)	0.01	0.01	0.006
Days above federal standard (0.14 ppm)	0	0	0
Days above state standard (0.04 ppm)	0	0	0
Nitrogen Dioxide			
Peak 1-hour value (ppm)	0.07	0.09	0.1
Days above state standard (0.25 ppm)	0	0	0
<i>Notes:</i> * Ventura County is in nonattainment for the federal and state O ₃ standards. ** Ventura County is in nonattainment for the state PM ₁₀ standard. ppm = parts per million by volume $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ = micrograms per cubic meter <i>Source:</i> CARB 2000.			

3.6 NOISE

3.6.1 Definition of Resource

Noise is defined as any sound that is undesirable because it interferes with communication, is intense enough to damage hearing, or is otherwise annoying (Federal Interagency Committee on Noise [FICON] 1992). Human response to noise can vary according to the type and characteristic of the noise source, the distance between the noise source and the receptor, the sensitivity of the receptor, and the time of day.

Sound travels through the air as waves of small pressure fluctuations caused by some type of vibration. In general, sound waves travel away from the noise source as an expanding spherical surface. The energy contained in a sound wave is consequently spread over an increasing area as it travels away from the source. This results in a decrease in loudness at greater distances from the noise source.

Sound level meters measure the actual air pressure fluctuations caused by sound waves, with separate measurements made for different vibrational frequency ranges. These measurements are reported using a decibel (dB) scale. Decibel scales are a logarithmic index based on a ratio of the actual pressure fluctuations generated by sound waves compared to a standard reference pressure value.

3.6.1.1 Noise Terminology

Most sounds consist of a broad range of sound frequencies. Because the human ear is not equally sensitive to all frequencies, a large number of frequency weighting schemes have been used to develop composite decibel scales that approximate the way the human ear responds to noise levels. The “A-weighted” decibel scale (dBA) is the most widely used for this purpose. The A-weighted scale significantly reduces the measured pressure level for low-frequency sounds while slightly increasing the measured pressure level for some high frequency sounds.

Varying noise levels are often described in terms of the equivalent constant decibel level. Equivalent noise levels (L_{eq}) are used to develop single-value descriptions of average noise exposure over various periods of time. Such average noise exposure ratings often include additional weighting factors for potential annoyance due to time of day or other considerations. The L_{eq} data used for these average noise exposure descriptions are generally based on A-weighted sound level measurements.

Average noise exposure over a 24-hour period is often presented as a day-night average sound level (L_{dn}) or as a community noise equivalent level (CNEL). L_{dn} values are calculated from hourly L_{eq} values, with the L_{eq} values for the nighttime period (10 P.M. – 7 A.M.) increased by 10 dB to reflect the greater potential for disturbance from nighttime noise. CNEL values are very similar to L_{dn} values, but include a 5-dB annoyance adjustment for evening (7 P.M. – 10 P.M.) L_{eq} values in addition to the 10-dB adjustment for nighttime L_{eq} values. Unless specifically noted otherwise, L_{dn} and CNEL values are based on dBA measurements. Because CNEL and L_{dn} values for the same noise condition seldom differ by more than 1 dB, they are often used interchangeably when interpreting noise level criteria and standards.

3.6.1.2 Noise Level Criteria and Standards

Federal Agency Guidelines

The Noise Control Act of 1972 established a requirement that all federal agencies must comply with applicable federal, state, interstate, and local noise control regulations. Local and state agencies have no applicable authority over military aircraft operations. Federal agencies also are directed to administer their programs in a manner that promotes an environment free from noise that jeopardizes public health or welfare. The Navy has established suggested land use compatibility criteria for different noise zones (OPNAVINST 11010.36A). Residential areas are considered compatible where the L_{dn} is up to 65 dBA. Professional services buildings are considered compatible where the L_{dn} is up to 70 dBA.

Local Noise Guidelines

Local Noise Guidelines are presented in the following text to provide the regional noise setting for analysis in this EA. However, no activities were identified in this EA that would generate noise issues at the PHS or the surrounding community (refer to Section 4.6). Airports and highway traffic are major contributors to noise conditions in Ventura County. Aircraft flight operations from Oxnard Airport, Camarillo Airport, and NBVC Point Mugu affect noise conditions in the Oxnard, Port Hueneme, and Point Mugu areas. Channel Islands Boulevard, Victoria Boulevard, Ventura Boulevard, and local arterial roadways are major traffic noise sources in the PHS area.

The noise element of the Ventura County General Plan sets a CNEL level of 65 dB as the normally acceptable limit for residential and other noise-sensitive land uses. Proposals for new noise-sensitive development are generally reviewed to ensure that designs provide an acceptable interior noise environment when outdoor noise exposure is expected to exceed a CNEL of 60 dB.

3.6.2 Existing Conditions

The most common source of noise in the project area is from transportation-related sources, primarily motor vehicles. Other noise sources include equipment used to load and unload ships in the harbor, the railroad, heavy vehicle repairs, staging of aircraft exercises, and foghorns. Noise levels along primary roadways, such as Hueneme Road and Ventura Road, are about CNEL 65 immediately adjacent to the roadways and drop to CNEL 60 dB within approximately 500 feet (150 m) of the road's edge (U.S. Navy 2000b). Average noise levels in the Silver Strand area range from 43 to 62 dBA. The average noise at Port Hueneme beach is about 63 dBA; near the entrance to the Port of Hueneme, noise averages about 57 dBA (U.S. Navy 1996).

3.7 HAZARDOUS MATERIALS AND WASTES

This section includes a description of hazardous materials and wastes that potentially affect personnel at the PHS. These items are identified to provide a context for potential safety-related issues in conjunction with implementation of the proposed projects listed in the INRMP, such as the agricultural outlease area (NR-18), which would be located on a former Installation Restoration Program (IRP) site. Safety issues addressed in this section include hazardous materials, hazardous wastes, and the potential effects of these issues with regard to personnel safety.

3.7.1 Definition of Resource

A hazardous material is a substance, pollutant, or contaminant that, due to its quantity, concentration, or physical and chemical characteristics, poses a potential hazard to human health and safety or to the environment if released into the workplace or the environment. This definition is consistent with the Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation and Liability Act (CERCLA) of 1980, as amended by Superfund Amendments and Reauthorization Act of 1986. The Navy's Environmental and Natural Resources Program Manual states that hazardous materials include but are not limited to hazardous substances, hazardous waste, and any material that a handler or administering agent has a reasonable basis for believing would be injurious to the health and safety of persons or harmful to the environment if released into the workplace or the environment.

The Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA) of 1976, as amended by the Hazardous and Solid Waste Amendments of 1984, defines hazardous wastes. A hazardous waste is a solid waste or combination of wastes which, due to its quantity, concentration, or physical, chemical or infectious characteristics, may cause or significantly contribute to an increase in mortality or an increase in either serious irreversible, or incapacitating reversible illness, or may pose a substantial present or potential hazard to human health or the environment when improperly treated, stored, disposed of, or otherwise managed. A solid waste is a hazardous waste if it either exhibits any ignitable, corrosive, reactive or toxic characteristic or if it is listed in Subpart D of RCRA.

The purpose of the IRP is to identify, investigate, and clean up or control releases of hazardous substances from past waste disposal operations and hazardous material spills at Navy facilities.

3.7.2 Existing Conditions

3.7.2.1 IRP Sites

A total of 21 sites are currently being investigated at the PHS under the IRP. None of these sites currently impact any off-base areas. Please refer to Appendix C for a map of these sites. The sites have been grouped into seven status categories as follows:

- 1) Sites Closed – All Actions completed
- 2) Sites Proposed for No Further Action/Site Closure
- 3) Sites Requiring an RI or Feasibility Study
- 4) Sites Undergoing the Removal Action Process
- 5) Sites Requiring Long-term Monitoring
- 6) Sites Requiring Additional Data
- 7) Other Sites

Site inspections were performed at Sites 13, 16, 18, and 22. These sites were found either to contain no contamination levels or to contain levels of contamination low enough to warrant a “no further action” or “site closed” designation. An RI was conducted at Site 17; a “hot spot removal” of pesticides occurred, and the site was administratively transferred from the IRP to the RCRA program for closure. Site 7, another “site closed” area, is a paved area composed of crushed rock covered with asphalt. The rock contains very small quantities of low-level radioactive material and is licensed by the Nuclear Regulatory Commission and monitored by the Navy.

Two sites (Sites 10 and 11) contain solvents, fuels, and paints in the soil. These sites contain levels of contamination below cleanup levels and warranted “no further action” designations.

Four sites (Sites 4, 5, 6, and 8) have “final site” (FS) inspections prepared by the Navy. These site inspections detected very low levels of contamination. A feasibility study will be conducted for these sites. An RI was conducted at Site 21; an FS will be conducted.

Three sites (Sites 9, 12B, and 23) are undergoing the removal action process. A final Engineering Evaluation/Cost Analysis has been prepared, and an action memorandum is in progress for the three sites. In addition, confirmation sampling is underway in other areas at Site 9 to evaluate whether environmental conditions are fully characterized and if additional action is required (U.S. Navy 2000b).

Long-term monitoring of base-wide actions at the PHS include groundwater and surface water studies. These studies evaluate the dynamics of groundwater beneath the PHS and provide information on how contaminants are distributed and transported in groundwater and impacts to surface water. The final base-wide groundwater and surface water study report for the PHS is scheduled for completion in 2001.

Long-term monitoring is also being conducted to address concerns specific to individual sites at the PHS. Specifically, Site 7 is under Nuclear Regulatory Commission jurisdiction and is undergoing long-term groundwater monitoring. Since monitoring began 23 years ago at the site, monitoring tests have shown no concentrations greater than those normally found in native soil. In addition, Site 14 is being capped and closed according to USEPA “presumptive remedy” standards that include groundwater monitoring and soil cap maintenance.

Two sites require additional data (Sites 12A and 15). These sites were studied for polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) as part of the preliminary assessment/site inspection (PA/SI). Low levels of PCBs were found at both sites, and confirmation sampling is in progress. Site 19 was studied under a PA/SI, and a risk evaluation was completed indicating the need for further evaluation of potential impacts to ecological receptors, including plant and animal life. Two underground storage tanks (USTs) were removed from Site 20 after low levels of contaminants were detected during an initial SI. Preliminary investigations at Site 20 indicated that a removal action study may be necessary, and a focused SI is in progress. The results of additional data collection at these sites will determine if future environmental action is needed.

3.7.2.2 Methyl Tertiary Butyl Ether (MTBE)

MTBE, a clear colorless liquid that is a byproduct of crude oil refining, was detected in the groundwater beneath the PHS in December 1992. From late 1984 to early 1985, approximately 10,800 gallons (40,900 liters) of gasoline leaked from two storage tanks and piping under the Naval Exchange (NEX) gas station at the PHS. Sampling and testing were conducted to determine how much gasoline has mixed with the groundwater under the PHS and exactly where the water and gasoline mixture is located.

The contamination at the PHS begins 6 to 10 feet (1.8 to 3 m) bgs and is confined to a shallow aquifer not used for drinking water. In 1997, during the process to permanently close the NEX gas station site, the Los Angeles RWQCB asked for further evaluation of the MTBE-contaminated groundwater, commonly referred to as the MTBE plume. Since then, three investigations have been undertaken to determine the extent of the plume.

Results indicate that the MTBE plume is located in areas underlying primarily the commercial and industrial activities of the base. The plume begins at the NEX gas station and extends about 4,800 feet (1,460 m) with a maximum width of about 500 feet (150 m). It is confined to a semi-perched aquifer from 6 to 25 feet (1.8 to 7.6 m) bgs. A clay layer, which ranges from approximately 20 to 50 feet (6 to 15 m) in thickness in the vicinity of the site, isolates the contaminated water from underlying aquifers. The MTBE plume is totally confined within the limits of the PHS boundaries, and there are no wells on base or near the plume that are currently being used to pump drinking water. Since 1996, the Navy has closely monitored the MTBE plume, which has moved in a southwesterly direction at speeds up to 1 foot (0.3 m) per day in some areas.

The MTBE plume was selected in 1994 as one of four National Environmental Technology Test Sites. Results of the MTBE cleanup technology demonstrations at the PHS will be made available to government and private industry for use as a resource in planning MTBE cleanup projects.

3.7.2.3 Personnel Safety

Relevant health and safety requirements fall into two areas: industrial hygiene and ground safety. Responsibilities of the PHS include monitoring and minimizing exposure to workplace chemicals and physical hazards, hearing and respiratory protection, medical monitoring of workers subject to chemical exposures, and oversight of all hazardous or potentially hazardous operations.

Ground safety includes protection from hazardous situations and hazardous materials. All activities related to construction and/or facility operations at the PHS are subject to the requirements of the Occupational Health and Safety Act. Personnel safety is an important consideration with implementation of INRMP projects, since the potential exists for exposure of natural resources or other personnel to hazardous chemicals at the PHS.

3.7.2.4 Hazardous Materials and Wastes

Hazardous materials are used for various operations throughout the PHS and are managed under Instruction 4110.1, Hazardous Materials Control and Management. Hazardous materials include batteries, lubricants, paints, adhesives, pesticides, herbicides, and sealing compounds. Most of the hazardous materials are used for facility operations. These materials are stored at various locations throughout the PHS. Hazardous materials are also used and stored for cleaning and other maintenance operations throughout the PHS. Hazardous wastes generated from use of hazardous materials are managed according to RCRA Subtitle C (40 CFR Parts 260-280) regulations administered by the USEPA, unless otherwise exempted by CERCLA actions.

Hazardous wastes are regulated by the California Environmental Protection Agency (Cal EPA) Department of Toxic Substances Control (DTSC) under the California Health and Safety Code, Sections 25100 through 67188. These regulations require that wastes be handled, stored, transported, disposed of, or recycled according to defined procedures.

CHAPTER 4

ENVIRONMENTAL CONSEQUENCES

This chapter describes potential environmental consequences associated with the proposed action (implementation of the natural resources portion of the INRMP at the PHS), as well as the no-action alternative (continuation of current management practices). CEQ regulations implementing NEPA state that the environmental consequences discussion shall include direct and indirect effects as well as their significance. This discussion addresses all resource areas described in Chapter 3. Specifically, potential impacts are analyzed for both the proposed action and the no-action alternative. No impacts requiring mitigation were identified for any proposed INRMP projects. However, the no-action alternative would have adverse but insignificant impacts to biological resources, hydrology and surface water quality, and hazardous materials and wastes (refer to Table ES-2).

A programmatic level of analysis was performed for each of the proposed projects that may trigger NEPA, since specific details regarding implementation of the proposed projects (such as the Agricultural Outlease Area and the Footpath/Greenbelt Loop) have not yet been developed. The details for implementation of several INRMP projects will be determined in conjunction with the PHS staff at a future date, if funding becomes available. If it is determined at that time that additional NEPA would be required to address project impacts, an appropriate level of documentation would be prepared according to project needs.

Table 4-1 depicts INRMP projects analyzed for environmental impacts under NEPA. It also summarizes the associated issue areas discussed in the environmental consequences section of this EA for each project. Depending on the level of impact, projects are either grouped together under a general heading or discussed individually within each issue area. The majority of INRMP projects do not have the potential to trigger any environmental impacts (refer to Chapter 2 and Appendix A).

Table 4-1. INRMP Projects with the Potential to Trigger the NEPA and Related Issue Area Impacts

<i>Project</i>	<i>Biological Resources</i>	<i>Hydrology/Surface Groundwater Quality</i>	<i>Land Use and Visual Resources</i>	<i>Transportation and Circulation</i>	<i>Air Quality</i>	<i>Noise</i>	<i>Safety</i>
Integrated Pest Management	X	X					X
Restoration and Enhancement Projects							
Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area A (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)	X	X	X				
Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area B (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)	X	X	X				
Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan Special Interest Natural Area C (Coyote Brush Habitat)	X		X				
Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area D (Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage and Sandy Beach Habitats)	X	X	X				
Adaptive Management Plan for Burrowing Owls	X		X				
General PHS Improvements							
Footpath/Greenbelt Loop	X		X	X	X	X	X
Landscape and Recreation Improvements	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Drip Irrigation System Installation		X	X				

4.1 BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES

This section analyzes the potential for impacts to biological resources from implementation of the proposed action or no-action alternative. The primary factors used in determining significance of an impact on biological resources are the potential for species or habitats of concern to be adversely affected over relatively large areas and the potential for disturbances to cause reductions in population size or distribution of a species of concern. This analysis focuses specifically on the implementation of various INRMP projects and how they may affect biological resources.

4.1.1 Proposed Action

The following text summarizes impacts resulting from those projects in the INRMP with the potential to trigger impacts to biological resources (see Table 4-1).

4.1.1.1 Integrated Pest Management

Pest Management Plan

The Pest Management Plan would be updated with recommendations contained in the INRMP (also refer to Appendices A and E). These measures would reduce the amount of pesticides used for purposes of pest management and would also require monitoring of application procedures for pesticides. The recommended treatment procedures for dealing with pests would be chosen and timed to provide natural

controls (whenever possible) of problem pests. If this method proves unsuccessful, the least environmentally harmful pesticides would be used.

The INRMP requires the Pest Management Plan to include a description of pest management operations with “special environmental considerations.” These considerations include the use of restricted or experimental-use pesticides, pesticide use with the potential to contaminate ground or surface water, any aerial applications of pesticides, and the application of pesticides over 640 or more contiguous acres (260 hectares) in one operation. These types of pesticide use would be closely monitored (U.S. Navy 1999a).

An active monitoring program (refer to Appendices A and E) would help to reduce the unnecessary application of pesticides in areas with nearby sensitive species or habitat types (e.g., least terns or wetlands). This would therefore create beneficial impacts to biological resources by reducing the amount and type of harmful pesticides used at the PHS. No significant impacts from the recommended Pest Management Plan revisions contained in the INRMP are expected.

Ballast Water

As described in Section 3.1, ballast water is not currently treated within the harbor before being released. Testing for invasive aquatic species has not yet been conducted to determine whether any introductions of these species has inadvertently occurred (U.S. Navy 1999a). Recommendations for testing ballast water are included in the INRMP (refer to page 4-13) and are also detailed below and in Appendix E of this EA.

One method of preventing exotic species invasions is to exchange ballast water on the high seas. The introduction of peracetic acid into ballast water and treatment of ballast water in dockside facilities are treatment methods that are currently being explored. The Integrated Pest Management Plan should evaluate potential options for the treatment of ballast water in Navy ships, including the feasibility of treating the ballast water using the existing Bilge and Oily Wastewater Treatment System.

4.1.1.2 Restoration and Enhancement Projects

Habitat Protection and Restoration Plans for Special Interest Natural Areas A, B, C, and D

Development of a habitat and protection plan for Special Interest Natural Areas A through D would protect and enhance the native habitats at the PHS (refer to Appendix A). In addition, signs would be installed near these areas indicating the presence of sensitive habitat and seasonal prohibitions on access. The Planning Branch would be consulted before implementation of the recommended actions for this area. Implementation of the recommendations would result in beneficial impacts to biological resources by protecting and restoring those portions of native habitat still remaining at the PHS.

Adaptive Management Plan for Burrowing Owls

The burrowing owl, a species of concern at the PHS, has been observed in a dirt mound near Buildings 1421 and 1423 in the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area. Potential wintering habitat exists for this species in the dirt mound and in California annual grassland habitat throughout the base (especially where ground squirrel burrows occur) (U.S. Navy 1999a). Protection of burrowing owls at the PHS is important since few colonies of this species remain in Ventura County.

The main threats to the burrowing owl at the PHS include harassment by human activities, habitat loss, ground squirrel control, predation by feral cats, disturbance by dogs, and potential contaminant impacts. Training activities within the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area are likely to disturb the burrowing owls that reside in this area and may destroy active burrows. Additional burrowing owls are likely to occur at the PHS where other construction or training activities occur, as well as in open storage areas and possibly at IRP sites that contain open ground or California annual grassland habitat.

The preparation of an adaptive management plan for burrowing owls would assist in the protection of the species on the PHS by: 1) developing a Pest Management Plan that addresses the control of California ground squirrels while avoiding potential impacts to burrowing owls, an inhabitant of ground squirrel burrows; 2) providing guidance on developing additional burrowing owl nesting opportunities in protected, unused portions of the PHS; 3) developing interim protection measures for the known burrowing owl locations at the PHS; and 4) providing guidance on the balanced protection of both the burrowing owl and the federally protected California least tern (a known prey of burrowing owls). Implementation of the adaptive management plan would have a beneficial effect on biological resources at the PHS, particularly the burrowing owl.

4.1.1.3 General PHS Improvements

Footpath/Greenbelt Loop

The construction of a new Footpath/Greenbelt Loop would improve recreational opportunities at the PHS and provide potential wildlife habitat. The footpath would wind through previously developed areas (i.e., housing, administration, and recreational areas) predominantly in the northern portion of the PHS. It would be constructed of an aggregate gravel base and would be used for jogging, walking, and bicycling. Native trees would be planted along the footpath to provide shade and would provide potential wildlife habitat. Although the construction and use of the footpath is not expected to result in impacts to biological resources, the planting of native trees would be expected to result in a beneficial effects.

Landscape and Recreation Improvements

The proposed landscape and recreation improvement projects would use native plant species. The addition of native tree, shrub, and ground-cover species would provide wildlife habitat and would beneficially impact biological resources.

Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14

After IRP Site 14 was covered, a detention basin was constructed along the southern edge of the site. According to recommendations in the INRMP, the detention basin should be planted with native wetland plant species to provide potential wildlife habitat – particularly for invertebrates, amphibians, birds, and mammals. As part of the post-closure monitoring plan, storm water monitoring procedures would be implemented for the detention basin and for the created wetlands to ensure adequate protection of plant and wildlife species in the vicinity. Construction of an aggregate gravel base over the site would prevent colonization by ground squirrels and the subsequent potential colonization by burrowing owls, a Species of Concern on the PHS. Implementation of the management recommendations in the INRMP (refer to Appendix A) regarding the covering of IRP Site 14 would protect biological resources. Therefore, construction of the agricultural out-lease area (consisting of a containerized nursery operation) at IRP Site 14 would not impact biological resources except in a beneficial manner (i.e., creation of wetland habitat).

4.1.2 No-Action Alternative

4.1.2.1 Integrated Pest Management

Under this alternative, the Pest Management Plan would not be implemented according to the recommendations specified in the INRMP. The current pest management program would continue. As described in Section 2.4.2, current pest management procedures would have the potential to create adverse but insignificant impacts to sensitive habitats and species.

The INRMP's recommendations for addressing ballast water treatment are described above and in Appendix E of this EA. No information is available on the presence or absence of invasive aquatic species within the PHS harbor, since they are not currently tested. However, if these recommendations are not implemented, the potential exists for invasive aquatic species to enter the PHS harbor, thereby causing adverse but insignificant impacts to marine water quality or biological resources.

4.1.2.2 Restoration and Enhancement Projects

Under this alternative, the threat of harassment to sensitive species and habitats from human activities at the PHS would continue. In addition, comprehensive surveys of Special Interest Natural Areas A, B, C, D would not occur; therefore, these areas would not be adequately protected or monitored.

Potential conflicts with training activities in the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area may arise with the no-action alternative since the area currently used periodically for training exercises contains burrowing owls. Therefore, if the INRMP is not implemented and this area is not protected, a potential impact to the burrowing owls may occur if training activities are allowed to continue. However, ample space is available adjacent to this location for training activities; therefore, no adverse impacts would be expected to occur (see Section 4.1.1.2 above for additional information).

Therefore, the no-action alternative would have the potential to create adverse but insignificant impacts to biological resources.

4.1.2.3 General PHS Improvements

No impacts to biological resources would occur if the proposed general improvement projects detailed in the INRMP were not implemented. However, no additional habitat for wildlife use would be developed.

4.2 HYDROLOGY, SURFACE WATER, AND GROUNDWATER QUALITY

Water quality impacts are evaluated based on the potential for long-term effects to aquatic resources. Factors for evaluating hydrology, surface water, and ground water quality include flooding on and off site; runoff that would exceed existing storm water drainage capacity; and/or degradation of surface or groundwater quality.

4.2.1 Proposed Action

The following text summarizes impacts resulting from those projects in the INRMP with the potential to trigger impacts to hydrology and surface water quality (see Table 4-1 and Appendix A).

4.2.1.1 Integrated Pest Management

The Pest Management Plan would be updated with recommendations contained in the INRMP. These measures would reduce the amount of pesticides used for purposes of pest management and would also require monitoring of application procedures for pesticides. The recommended treatment procedures for dealing with pests would be chosen and timed to provide natural controls (whenever possible) of problem pests. If this method proves unsuccessful, the least environmentally harmful pesticides would be used.

The INRMP requires the Pest Management Plan to include a description of pest management operations with “special environmental considerations.” These include the use of restricted or experimental-use pesticide, pesticide use with the potential to contaminate ground or surface water, any aerial applications of pesticides, and the application of pesticides over 640 or more contiguous acres (260 hectares) in one operation. These types of pesticide use would be closely monitored (U.S. Navy 1999a).

An active monitoring program would help to reduce the unnecessary application of pesticides in areas with nearby surface water or shallow groundwater. This would create beneficial impacts to water quality by reducing the amount and type of harmful pesticides entering surface water bodies at the PHS. No adverse impacts from the recommended Pest Management Plan revisions contained in the INRMP would occur. Additional suggested measures for updating the Pest Management Plan are included in Appendix E.

4.2.1.2 Restoration and Enhancement Projects

Bulrush-Cattail Habitat (Special Interest Natural Area A)

The habitat enhancement and restoration plan guidelines for this area include the development of a vegetative buffer (such as willow trees) designed to provide additional protection from surface water runoff into the area. This would be expected to act as a natural debris filter of surface water that may enter the area during a storm event. In addition, other measures, such as the active removal of litter and debris, would help to improve the general water quality in the project area. Debris removal would not be substantial enough to affect drainage patterns. Therefore, no impacts other than beneficial water quality improvements would occur.

Bulrush-Cattail Habitat (Special Interest Natural Area B)

The habitat enhancement and restoration plan guidelines for this area include a recommendation to complete a predictive ecological risk assessment for the drainage channels and, if necessary, to determine

cleanup goal requirements pursuant to the Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation and Liability Act (CERCLA). It also recommends continued implementation of the Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan (SWPPP) (along with INRMP-recommended updates to the SWPPP described in Appendix A) to prevent future contamination of the channels. In addition, an active litter removal program would be implemented. These measures would be expected to improve the quality of surface and groundwater within the area. Debris removal would not be substantial enough to affect drainage patterns. Therefore, no impacts other than beneficial water quality improvements would occur.

Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage Habitat (Special Interest Natural Area D)

The habitat enhancement and restoration guidelines outlined in the INRMP for this area include the prevention of debris disposal (e.g., construction fill, dredge spoils) on the sandy beach or sand verbena beach bursage habitat. It would also require litter removal from these areas on a regular basis, and the placement of trash receptacles outside the PHS boundaries to help prevent the public from littering in the area. These measures would be expected to create beneficial impacts to water quality in the adjacent harbor by preventing the flushing of litter and debris into the ocean during a storm or wind event. Debris removal would not be substantial enough to affect drainage patterns. No impacts other than beneficial improvements to water quality would occur.

4.2.1.3 General PHS Improvements

Planned recreational and landscape improvements for the PHS with the potential to impact surface water quality include the following projects: 1) Landscape/Recreational Improvements, 2) Construction of the Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14, and 3) Drip Irrigation System Installation.

Each of these improvements would require very minor grading for site preparation activities. Best Management Practices (BMPs) (e.g., silt fences, soil stockpiling) would be incorporated during construction to minimize potential erosion, runoff, and sedimentation impacts. None of the proposed projects would increase runoff beyond the existing stormwater drainage capacity at the PHS. Therefore, no impacts to surface water or groundwater quality would be expected. None of the improvement projects are located in areas prone to flooding. The agricultural out-lease area (consisting of a containerized nursery operation) would include stormwater monitoring procedures as part of the post-closure maintenance plan for IRP Site 14. Implementation of the guidelines outlined in the INRMP for pesticide use after the construction of an agricultural out-lease area at IRP Site 14 would also ensure that no environmentally harmful pesticides would be used by future lessors of the site. Therefore, no impacts other than beneficial improvements to water quality would occur.

4.2.2 No-Action Alternative

4.2.2.1 Integrated Pest Management

If the Pest Management Plan is not updated according to the recommendations specified in the INRMP, the current management program would continue; therefore, impacts from the use of pesticides would have the potential to degrade water quality at the PHS. Without implementation of the INRMP, no active monitoring program for pesticide use in Special Interest Natural Areas or other sensitive areas would occur. Impacts would be considered adverse but insignificant with the implementation of the no-action alternative.

4.2.2.2 Restoration and Enhancement Projects

If the habitat and restoration guidelines defined in the INRMP are not implemented, no active water quality improvement measures such as litter removal programs or vegetative buffers would be implemented for Special Interest Natural Areas A through D. Therefore, water quality conditions would not be expected to improve, and impacts would be considered adverse but insignificant.

4.2.2.3 General PHS Improvements

If the general site improvements proposed in the INRMP are not implemented, no beneficial water resources impacts would occur. If the Footpath/Greenbelt loop is not constructed, it would have no impact on water resources. If the agricultural out-lease area is not constructed, IRP Site 14 would still be capped according to CERCLA requirements, and a stormwater monitoring plan would still be required. Without the installation of a drip irrigation system, excess water would continue to be used for landscaping purposes. Nonetheless, no significant impacts to water resources would occur for general PHS improvement projects associated with the no-action alternative.

4.3 LAND USE AND VISUAL RESOURCES

This section evaluates potential effects on land use and visual resources associated with the proposed action and the no-action alternative. Factors considered when evaluating potential impacts to land use and visual resources include the extent or degree to which the various projects under the proposed action would change existing land use or the existing viewshed.

4.3.1 Proposed Action

The following text summarizes impacts resulting from those projects in the INRMP with the potential to trigger impacts to land use and visual resources (see Table 4-1 and Appendix A).

4.3.1.1 Restoration and Enhancement Projects

Bulrush-Cattail Habitat, Coyote Brush Habitat, Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage Habitat (Special Interest Natural Areas A, B, C, D)

Land Use

The habitat enhancement and restoration plan guidelines for these areas include the development of vegetative buffers, the creation of a wildlife viewing area, footpaths, a litter removal program, and the installation of signs indicating the presence of sensitive habitats. These proposed changes would not alter the land use of the area, except for minor restrictions for vehicle and foot traffic in sensitive habitat areas. Mission-critical activities would be exempted from the restriction; hence, no mission-related impacts associated with minor changes in land use activities in and around the restoration and enhancement projects would occur. Therefore, no land use impacts, other than beneficial land use improvements, would be expected.

Visual Resources

The proposed land use improvements described above would improve the visual quality of the Special Interest Natural Areas by removing unsightly litter and debris and constructing interpretive signage to educate viewers on the importance of each of the areas. In addition, the removal of exotic plant species would improve the visual quality of the area by enhancing the opportunity for native plant life to flourish. No effects to visual resources would occur other than beneficial improvements to the areas proposed for enhancement.

Adaptive Management Plan for Burrowing Owls

The proposed adaptive management plan for burrowing owls would potentially restrict training activities in the immediate vicinity of known owl burrows. However, the specifics of limitations on training areas have yet to be determined, and there is adequate space in the area to keep such activities away from the owl locations without disrupting the mission.

4.3.1.2 General PHS Improvements

Land Use

Planned recreational and landscape improvements for the PHS with the potential to impact land use activities include the following projects: 1) Footpath/Greenbelt Loop, 2) Landscape/Recreational Improvements, 3) Construction of the Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14, and 4) Drip Irrigation System Installation.

Each of the general improvement projects would enhance land use opportunities at the PHS. General landscape and recreational improvements would not actually change the land use of the PHS; rather, they would increase beneficial uses of the areas proposed for enhancement. The footpath/greenbelt would allow for safer recreational areas for personnel stationed at the PHS. Proposed landscape and recreational improvements would include construction of a recreational vehicle (RV) Park and other minor improvements at the PHS. The construction of the agricultural out-lease area would change the land use from an IRP site to a more beneficial use. The proposed drip irrigation system installation would not be expected to change land use at the PHS. Although a limited number of new utility connections would be necessary, the existing infrastructure at the PHS would be adequate to service the proposed projects.

Any minor equipment needed to complete construction of the proposed improvements would be temporarily present in the proposed project location and would not be expected to generate significant land use impacts. Equipment staging areas would be carefully chosen to avoid impacts any nearby personnel or sensitive natural areas.

For these reasons, the general site improvement projects proposed in the INRMP would not be expected to impact land use, except in a beneficial manner.

Visual Resources

The proposed general site improvement projects for the PHS would enhance the visual character of the area via the addition of landscape and recreational improvements. No visual impacts would be expected other than beneficial additions to existing vistas.

4.3.2 No-Action Alternative

4.3.2.1 Restoration and Enhancement Projects

If the Habitat and Restoration guidelines defined in the INRMP are not implemented, no improvements would occur to Special Interest Natural Areas A, B, C, D. Therefore, no impacts to existing or planned land uses would be expected. No removal of litter or visual improvements would occur in the Special Interest Natural Areas. This would not be considered a significant visual impact. However, if these areas are not enhanced, the potential for continued human presence and degradation to these areas would continue, and further destruction of sensitive areas at the PHS would occur.

4.3.2.2 General PHS Improvements

If the proposed improvements at the PHS are not implemented, no impacts to land use would be expected to occur since existing land uses currently serve the military mission. Increased recreational opportunities would be diminished, and no site improvements would be constructed. Visual resources in the project

areas would not be enhanced with new recreational opportunities or increased landscaping. However, this would not be considered a significant recreational or visual impact.

4.4 TRANSPORTATION AND CIRCULATION

This section evaluates the nature and extent of potential changes to existing transportation and circulation associated with the proposed action and alternatives. Examples of transportation and circulation impacts include potential traffic increases and their effects on roadway and intersection capacities.

4.4.1 Proposed Action

The following text summarizes impacts resulting from those projects in the INRMP with the potential to trigger impacts to transportation and circulation (see Table 4-1 and Appendix A). Three of the proposed projects would have this potential: 1) Footpath/Greenbelt Loop, 2) Landscape and Recreational Improvements, and 3) Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14.

4.4.1.1 General PHS Improvements

Footpath/Greenbelt Loop

The footpath/greenbelt loop would be developed to provide recreational areas for personnel stationed at the PHS to walk, jog, or use a bicycle. This “loop” is intended for recreation and would not be expected to alter any traffic or circulation patterns on the PHS. As is discussed in the hazardous materials and wastes section of this EA (refer to Section 4.7), safety risks associated with use of roads for recreation (e.g., bicycling and jogging) would likely be reduced. Any associated circulation pattern issues would be avoided since persons doing recreation-oriented activities would likely use the loop instead of the existing roadway system. Therefore, the majority of circulation conflicts with road use for recreational purposes would be avoided with construction of the footpath/greenbelt loop. No significant impacts other than beneficial impacts to traffic circulation patterns at PHS would occur.

Landscape and Recreation Improvements and Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14

The proposed landscape and recreation improvements recommended in the INRMP would occur in several different areas on the PHS. These improvements would include the demolition of several structures, the construction of an RV Park, and the creation of agricultural, greenspace and landscaped areas.

Traffic resulting from construction of the proposed improvements would constitute only a small portion of the total existing traffic volume in the region and would be considered insignificant. Even if the construction traffic trips occurred during the peak periods of traffic, the increase could be adequately accommodated since the area is currently operating at acceptable levels of service. In addition, the majority of vehicles used for construction activities would be driven to the proposed project locations and stored on site for the duration of construction; therefore, the number of trips required during construction activities would be minimal. Upon completion of construction, no long-term impacts to on- or off-base traffic and circulation would occur, and no additional traffic trips would be generated other than for the use of the proposed RV site. Therefore, impacts to traffic and circulation would not be significant.

4.4.2 No-Action Alternative

Under this alternative, elements of the INRMP would not be implemented. The existing traffic and circulation patterns at the PHS would continue. No significant impacts to transportation and circulation would occur.

4.5 AIR QUALITY

Emission thresholds associated with federal CAA conformity requirements are the primary means of assessing air quality impacts. A formal conformity determination is required for federal actions occurring in nonattainment or maintenance areas when the total direct and indirect stationary and mobile source emissions of nonattainment pollutants or their precursors exceed *de minimis* thresholds. Factors for evaluating air quality impacts include: emissions that would be the primary cause or significantly contribute to a violation of state or federal ambient air quality standards; land uses that would expose people to localized (as opposed to regional) air pollutant concentrations that violate state or federal ambient air quality standards; pollutant or pollutant precursor emissions that exceed relevant emission significance thresholds (such as CAA conformity *de minimis* levels or the numerical values of major source thresholds for nonattainment pollutants); adopted air quality management plan policies or programs; and/or emission levels assumed by the applicable air quality management plan.

4.5.1 Proposed Action

The following text summarizes impacts resulting from those projects in the INRMP with the potential to trigger impacts to air quality (see Tables 4-1 and 4-3 and Appendix A). Three of the proposed projects would have this potential: 1) Footpath/Greenbelt Loop, 2) Landscape and Recreational Improvements, and 3) Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14.

4.5.1.1 General PHS Improvements

Each of the projects listed above would include either minor demolition and/or earth-moving activities. The footpath/greenbelt loop would be constructed using an aggregate gravel base. The proposed landscape and recreation improvements would involve demolition activities and subsequent landscaping. The RV Park would include the construction of a small convenience store, maintenance building, clubhouse, laundry facilities, and a game room.

Air quality emissions from earth-moving activities, landscaping, minor demolition, and construction would be associated with the operation of fuel-powered construction equipment. For the purposes of this EA, it is assumed that a diesel-powered wheeled loader, bulldozer, excavator, motor grader, off-highway truck, fork-lift, and water truck would be required.

Emissions have been estimated using data and procedures described by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA 1985, 1995). Assumptions for these estimates are shown in Table 4-2 (refer to Appendix F for detailed emissions assumptions and calculations). It is conservatively estimated that construction activities for these three PHS improvements identified in the INRMP would collectively last nine months, or three months for each proposed project. The PHS improvements would be implemented in phases and would not occur simultaneously; however, for the purposes of providing a conservative analysis for this EA, air quality emissions for the PHS improvements are analyzed collectively.

Table 4-2. Construction Assumptions for PHS Improvements*

Vehicle Type	Number of Vehicles	Hours per Day	Emission Factors (grams/hour)				
			VOC	NO _x	CO	SO _x	PM ₁₀
Wheeled loader	1	3	110.4	858.1	259.5	82.5	77.9
Planer/bulldozer	1	3	84.7	1,889.1	816.8	158.0	75.0
Motor grader	1	3	17.6	324.4	68.4	39.0	27.7
Excavator/crawler	1	5	67.7	767.3	306.4	64.7	63.2
Off-highway truck	1	5	84.7	1,889.1	816.8	206.0	116.0
Fork-lift	1	2	67.7	767.3	306.4	64.7	63.2
Water truck	1	5	84.7	1,889.1	816.8	206.0	116.0

Sources: USEPA 1985, 1995.

* PHS Projects include: 1) Footpath/Greenbelt Loop, 2) Landscape and Recreational Improvements, and 3) Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14.

Ventura County is in nonattainment for the federal and state O₃ standards, and for the state PM₁₀ standard (refer to Section 3.5). However, proposed construction activities and associated construction emissions would be minor, and proposed construction projects would be staggered over several years (refer to Table 2-1). As shown in Table 4-3 and Appendix F (Air Quality Calculations and RONA), emissions associated with the PHS improvements would be below Clean Air Act conformity *de minimis* levels; consequently, a conformity analysis would not be necessary. In addition, proposed construction activities would be short-term in nature; no long-term increases in emissions would occur. Therefore, implementation of the general PHS improvements would not result in significant air quality impacts.

Table 4-3. Estimated Annual Construction Emissions for PHS Improvements

Component	Emissions (tons/year)				
	VOC	NO _x	CO	SO _x	PM ₁₀
Construction emissions (tons)	0.60	10.03	4.12	1.00	20.10 ^a
<i>de minimis</i> threshold (tons per year)	25	25	NA	NA	NA
Exceeds <i>de minimis</i> threshold?	No	No	No	No	No

Notes: NA = not applicable.

^aFugitive dust emission rate for proposed projects = 1.2 tons/acre/month x % PM₁₀ in soil; = 1.2 x 6 x 9 x 0.3 + 0.64 = 20.10 tons per year.

Sources: USEPA 1985, 1995.

Impacts to air quality associated with increased fugitive dust levels generated during construction activities at the project sites would be short-term and minor; no long-term increases in fugitive dust emissions would occur. The impacts of temporary fugitive dust generation would be further minimized by incorporating dust control measures, such as frequent application of water on the soil and excavated materials. Since fugitive dust control measures would be implemented, PM₁₀ emissions would not have significant impacts to air quality.

4.5.2 No-Action Alternative

Under this alternative, elements of the INRMP would not be implemented. Therefore, no additional stationary or mobile emissions would be generated beyond those existing at the PHS. No significant impacts to air quality would occur.

4.6 NOISE

The primary factor considered in determining the significance of noise effects includes the extent or degree to which implementation of the proposed action would affect baseline noise environments. The primary issue of concern with regard to noise is the potential for impacts to humans and terrestrial wildlife. Factors for evaluating noise impacts include ambient CNEL levels at noise-sensitive land uses beyond the “normally acceptable” land use compatibility criteria (typically 60 or 65 dB CNEL for residential, education, and health care land uses; as noted in Section 3.6, Ventura County uses the 65-dB CNEL contour to define “airport noise impact zones” for schools and other noise-sensitive land uses and/or noise-sensitive land use (residential, educational, and health care uses) in areas exposed to ambient noise levels that are higher than the applicable land use compatibility criteria (typically 60 or 65 dB CNEL).

Less stringent guidelines are applied to temporary noise sources that are restricted to daytime hours (such as most construction and demolition activities) unless they affect noise-sensitive land uses and result in CNELs more than 10 dB above the respective land use compatibility criteria.

4.6.1 Proposed Action

The following text summarizes impacts resulting from those projects in the INRMP with the potential to trigger noise impacts (see Table 4-1 and Appendix A). Three of the proposed projects would have this potential: 1) Footpath/Greenbelt Loop, 2) Landscape and Recreational Improvements, and 3) Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14.

4.6.1.1 General PHS Improvements

As described in the air quality section (refer to Section 4.5), each of the proposed projects would include either minor demolition and/or earth-moving activities. Proposed construction activities would be small in scale and short-term in nature, and the timing of construction would be staggered over several years. In addition, none of the proposed projects would be located near noise-sensitive land uses, and construction activities would be limited to normal daytime hours (i.e., 7 A.M. to 5 P.M.). At a distance of 1,000 feet (300 m), construction noise levels would range between 55 and 59 dB CNEL. This would be consistent with the existing noise environment at PHS, which ranges from 57-63 dBA (refer to Section 3.6). In the long term, the only additional traffic trips generated from any of the proposed projects would be occasional recreational vehicles entering the proposed RV Park. Therefore, the proposed action would not have short- or long-term noise impacts.

4.6.2 No-Action Alternative

Under this alternative, elements of the INRMP would not be implemented. The existing noise setting described in Section 3.6 would remain. Therefore, no significant noise impacts would occur.

4.7 HAZARDOUS MATERIALS AND WASTES

This section evaluates potential impacts of hazardous materials and wastes associated with the proposed action and no-action alternative. Safety impacts would occur if implementation of the proposed action would substantially increase risks to the public or the environment. Impacts associated with hazardous materials and wastes are considered significant if the storage, use, transportation, or disposal of these substances increases human health risks or environmental exposure.

4.7.1 Proposed Action

The following text summarizes impacts resulting from those projects in the INRMP with the potential to trigger impacts to hazardous materials and wastes (see Table 4-1 and Appendix A).

4.7.1.1 Integrated Pest Management

The Pest Management Plan would be updated with recommendations contained in the INRMP as described in Appendices A and E. These measures would reduce potential hazardous materials and wastes-related impacts resulting from the application of pesticides and other methods of pest management. The main objective of the Pest Management Plan, as required by DoDI 4150.7, *DoD Pest Management Program* and OPNAVINST 6250.4B, *Pest Management Programs*, is to establish and maintain a safe, effective, and environmentally sound integrated pest management program. Active implementation of the Pest Management Plan would help to prevent and control disease vectors and pests that may adversely affect readiness or military operations, the natural environment, or humans at the PHS. In general, Pest Management Plan implementation requires physical, mechanical, cultural, biological, genetic, regulatory, chemical, and educational methods to keep disease vector and pest populations low. The specific recommendations for the Pest Management Plan contained in the INRMP would help to assure that unnecessary safety risks would not be incurred from pest management activities or storage of pesticides. It specifically recommends that a description of all health and safety measures taken to protect pest management personnel and the general public from pesticide exposure and risk be included in the Pest Management Plan. In addition, as described earlier, a monitoring program would be implemented for sensitive pesticide application areas and uses (see Section 4.2.1.1).

No adverse safety or hazardous materials impacts related to pesticide use or storage from the recommended Pest Management Plan revisions contained in the INRMP would be expected (refer to Appendices A and E). Beneficial effects to hazardous materials and wastes management at the PHS would be expected.

4.7.1.2 General PHS Improvements

Footpath/Greenbelt Loop

The footpath/greenbelt loop would be developed to provide areas for personnel located at the PHS to walk, jog, and use a bicycle. This “loop” would provide a needed recreational area and would help to reduce general safety risks associated with people using developed roadways for recreational purposes (e.g., bicycling and jogging). Therefore, beneficial impacts related to human safety on the PHS would be expected.

Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14

An agricultural area, consisting of a containerized nursery operation at IRP Site 14, would be constructed after contaminants are capped at the Site. IRP Site 14 (a former municipal solid waste landfill) is 33 acres (13 hectares) in size and is located in the northwest quadrant of the PHS. The cleanup and capping of Site 14 is warranted due to unacceptable human health risks associated with soils contaminated with certain polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, toxaphene (a pesticide), Aroclor-1260, and antimony (Tetra Tech EMI 1998). The construction of an agricultural out-lease area would reduce the potential for active human use of the area, therefore reducing potential safety impacts. Any future pesticide use for the agricultural operation would be strictly monitored to reduce safety hazards from use of the site as an agricultural out-lease area. With implementation of the procedures outlined in the INRMP, impacts related to human safety would not be expected.

4.7.2 No-Action Alternative

4.7.2.1 Pest Management Plan

If the Pest Management Plan is not updated according to the recommendations specified in the INRMP, the current management program would continue; therefore, safety impacts associated with pesticide use and other pest controls would not be closely monitored at the PHS (refer to Section 2.4.2). This would be considered an adverse but insignificant impact.

4.7.2.2 General PHS Improvements

If general improvements recommended in the INRMP are not implemented, no significant impacts would occur. However, safety risks related to the use of roadways for recreational purposes would continue. This would be considered an adverse but insignificant impact. No other hazardous materials and wastes-related issues would occur, and no significant impacts would be expected.

CHAPTER 5

OTHER CONSIDERATIONS REQUIRED BY NEPA

This chapter addresses topics required by NEPA in an EA, including cumulative impacts, and short-term versus long-term productivity.

5.1 CUMULATIVE IMPACTS

CEQ regulations implementing the procedural provisions of NEPA define cumulative effects as:

“The impact on the environment which results from the incremental impact of the action when added to other past, present, and reasonably foreseeable future actions regardless of what agency (federal or non-federal) or person undertakes such other actions” (40 CFR § 1508.7).

In order to analyze cumulative effects, a cumulative effects region must be identified for which effects of the proposed action and other past, proposed, and reasonably foreseeable actions would be cumulatively recorded or experienced. The region where cumulative effects may occur includes the PHS and the immediate area surrounding the PHS. Past, present, and reasonably foreseeable actions in the cumulative effects region are briefly described below.

5.1.1 Cumulative Projects

Planners at the PHS were interviewed during preparation of this EA to determine which projects are scheduled to occur within a one to five-year period. These projects are detailed in Chapter 2 of this EA (refer to Table 2-2). In addition, a representative of the Harbor District (Kreiger 2001) was interviewed to determine if any natural resource-related projects planned for the harbor would be relevant to the proposed project. No projects are planned in the harbor that would add to the cumulative impacts of the proposed project. No other known reasonably foreseeable projects surrounding the PHS are scheduled (Pringle 2001). Past and present actions at the PHS have led to the existing conditions described in Chapter 3. The following impact analysis reflects consideration of existing conditions with implementation of the proposed project taken together with future planned projects in and around the PHS.

5.1.2 Cumulative Impacts

The proposed projects recommended in the INRMP would be expected to generate beneficial impacts to natural resources on the PHS, as well as contribute to regional efforts for restoration and preservation of remaining natural habitats in the region. While certain aspects of the implementation of the proposed projects would generate short-term and insignificant impacts, no significant short-term or long-term impacts that would require mitigation have been identified for the proposed action in this EA. Based on the nature of the impacts associated with the INRMP project recommendations, no impacts would be significant when considered cumulatively with potential future actions. For example, temporary and short-term truck traffic trips during construction of general improvement projects and other “future planned projects” for the PHS would not be expected to push the traffic impacts of any future projects over the significance threshold.

The future planned projects at the PHS were compared to the proposed projects for the INRMP, and no conflicts were identified, nor were any cumulative impacts. The future projects would occur over a long-term implementation period, and would not trigger any thresholds of significance due to the minor nature of the projects, even when combined with impacts generated by the proposed action.

Proposed minor construction activities that would be necessary for several general improvement projects at the PHS would result in a minor cumulative increase in regional ozone precursors and carbon monoxide levels at the PHS.

Upon consideration of the types of impacts (beneficial) associated with implementation of the INRMP and the reasonably foreseeable future actions at and around the PHS, the proposed action would not generate any cumulatively significant impacts. Only beneficial effects would be expected. For example, the proposed "Special Interest Natural Area" improvements would help to create improved habitat conditions for plants and animals native to the PHS region.

5.2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SHORT-TERM ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS AND LONG-TERM PRODUCTIVITY

NEPA requires an analysis of the relationship between a project's short-term impacts on the environment and the effects that these impacts may have on the maintenance and enhancement of the long-term productivity of the affected environment. Impacts that narrow the range of beneficial uses of the environment are of particular concern. This refers to the possibility that choosing one development option reduces future flexibility in pursuing other options, or that giving over a parcel of land or other resource to a certain use often eliminates the possibility of other uses being performed at that site.

The proposed action would result in both short-term environmental effects and long-term productivity. Short-term effects would be primarily related to construction activities involving the additional use of vehicles and equipment that are currently used for other purposes. However, the long-term effects of the proposed action would be beneficial in nature, since the majority of INRMP recommended projects would enhance the productivity of the natural and recreational resources found at the PHS.

Short-term effects to traffic, air and noise at the PHS location would be offset by the long-term, beneficial impacts expected from implementation of the INRMP. The proposed action would not result in any impacts that would reduce environmental productivity, permanently narrow the range of beneficial uses of the environment, or pose long-term risks to health, safety or the general welfare of the public.

CHAPTER 6

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CHAPTER 8

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

The following text provides an overview of management actions required to implement INRMP projects. The first ten projects have the potential to trigger impacts under NEPA, while the remaining projects would not. However, the details of the remaining projects have been provided in this appendix for informational purposes and ease of reference. Table A-1 provides a general overview of Management Goals outlined in the INRMP for different resources.

1. Pest Management Plan

Management Action

Preparation of a Pest Management Plan for the PHS is recommended and required by DoDI 4150.7, *DoD Pest Management Program* and OPNAVINST 6250.4B, *Pest Management Programs*, to establish and maintain a safe, effective, and environmentally sound integrated pest management program on base. The main objective of the Pest Management Plan at the PHS should be to prevent and control disease vectors and pests that may adversely affect readiness or military operations and that may adversely impact the natural environment on base.

Integrated pest management (IPM) is the preferred method for disease vector and pest management at DoD installations (DoDI 4150.7). Integrated pest management uses regular or scheduled monitoring to determine if and when treatments are needed to control disease vectors or pests, and employs physical, mechanical, cultural, biological, genetic, regulatory, chemical, and educational tactics to keep disease vector and pest populations low enough to prevent unacceptable damage or impacts. Treatments are chosen and timed to provide natural controls of pests with minimal disruption to the surrounding environment. If required, the least environmentally harmful pesticides are used as a last resort. Malathion (ULV) should not be used in areas or during conditions when the chemical may enter waterways or natural habitat areas. It is recommended that the IPM Plan include designations of areas unsuitable for spraying and for weather conditions when the ULV spray is least likely to enter natural areas (e.g., onshore wind days) (USFWS 1999b).

Table A-1. INRMP Project Management Actions and Implementation Strategies (All Projects)

Key Resource	Management Goal
Natural Resources	
All Resources	Implement the Resource Management Program according to Volume II of the <i>Navy Operations and Natural Resources Management Procedural Manual</i> pursuant to DoDDIR 4700.4, DoDDIR 4710.1, and DoDI 4715.3.
	Review the INRMP every year and revise the INRMP at 5-year increments, at a minimum.
	Perform required environmental impact analyses and special studies or mitigation for all current and proposed projects subject to NEPA. Coordinate NEPA compliance activities with NBVC Point Mugu when proposed projects affect both bases.
Sensitive Species	Protect and enhance populations of federally endangered or threatened species, species proposed for listing as endangered or threatened, and federal candidates for listing that occur at the PHS in accordance with the federal ESA of 1973, as amended.
	Prevent the taking of any native wild bird species, including their nests, eggs, and young, except by special permit, pursuant to the Migratory Bird Treaty Act of 1918, as amended. "Take" means to kill, pursue, harass, wound, trap/capture, or attempt any such conduct.
	Protect and enhance state-listed and proposed listed species, state candidate species for listing, and Installation species of concern.
Plant/Wildlife Habitats	Protect and enhance wetlands at the PHS in compliance with the Wetlands Protection Act (Executive Order 11990) and Section 404 of the Clean Water Act.
	Restore areas on base with potential for enhancement.
Water, Soil, and Air Quality	Maintain the Installation Restoration Program (IRP) at the PHS pursuant to CERCLA. Continue cleanup efforts at IRP sites as required by the Department of Toxic Substances Control.
	Maintain the Surface Water and Storm Water Program element of the Compliance Program at the PHS in compliance with the Clean Water Act. Maintain, improve, and implement the SWPPP as required under the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System General Permit for Storm Water Discharges Associated with Industrial Activities.
	Maintain the UST Program at the PHS pursuant to California's UST regulations (Title 23, Division 3, Chapter 16, Articles 1-10 of the California Code of Regulations). Continue cleanup efforts as required by the Department of Toxic Substances Control and the Los Angeles Regional Water Quality Control Board.
	Maintain and improve the Pollution Prevention Program at the PHS, including the Recycling Program and Energy Showcase Program.
	Protect navigable waters of the United States pursuant to Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act.
Key Resource	Management Goal
Aesthetic and Recreational Resources	Optimize current and future recreational opportunities at the PHS.
	Improve landscaping and recreational opportunities in close proximity to housing and main administration.
	Address aesthetic concerns of the public with the base.
Disease Vectors and Pests	Prevent and control disease vectors and pest populations associated with the facilities and ships at the PHS in compliance with the DoD Pest Management Program (DoDI 4150.7 and OPNAVINST 6250.4B).

Table A-2 presents the required contents of a Pest Management Plan for the PHS, according to DoDI 4150.7.

Table A-2. Required Contents of a Pest Management Plan

Description of the disease vector and pest management requirements and minimum disease vector and pest management staffing requirements at the PHS.
Description of all integrated pest management (IPM) procedures required to monitor and control pests at the PHS.
Identification of all resources (e.g., work years, facilities, equipment) required to support the Pest Management Program.
Identification of all pesticides, including EPA registration numbers, approved for use in the Pest Management Program (e.g., pesticides used for the golf course).
Description of all health and safety measures that will be taken to protect pest management personnel and the general public from pesticide exposure and risk.
Identification of any planned measures to comply with DoD Memoranda of Agreement with State pesticide regulatory offices relating to the use or application of pesticides.
Description of any pest management operation with special environmental considerations, such as (1) the use of a restricted-use or experimental-use pesticide; (2) use of a pesticide application that may contaminate groundwater or surface water; (3) application of a pesticide over 640 or more contiguous acres (260 hectares) in one operation; (4) an operation that may adversely affect sensitive species; (5) aerial application of pesticides; and (6) management or control of designated noxious weeds.
Identification of animal control efforts required for feral cats or wildlife.
Identification of active or potential vector-borne diseases at the PHS and a description of any collaboration with local and state agencies for vector surveillance and control.
Identification of golf course pest management operations.

2. Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area A (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)

Management Action

Development of a habitat protection and restoration plan for Special Interest Natural Area A is recommended to protect and enhance the bulrush-cattail habitat at the PHS and to improve passive recreational use of the area.

The recommended objectives of the habitat protection and restoration plan are:

- Restore the continuity of the bulrush-cattail habitat by permanently restricting vehicle and foot traffic along the dirt road that currently bisects the habitat.
- Create a wildlife viewing area near the marsh by constructing interpretive signs and benches on both wooden decks, constructing footpaths between the decks and the wooden bridge, and by making the wooden bridge safe for foot traffic.
- Develop a vegetative buffer (e.g., willow trees) around the marsh that provides more protection from runoff.
- Prevent the invasion of exotic plant species into this habitat, especially pampas grass and giant reed (*Arundo donax*), by eradicating nearby stands of these species and any exotic plant species that already exist within the marsh to the extent practicable.
- Remove litter from the banks of the marsh on a regular basis.
- Install signs near the area indicating the presence of sensitive habitat. Signs should be constructed at a low height and should be fitted with materials to discourage perching,

especially by predatory birds. Materials such as Nixalite™ and CatClaw™ are appropriate, non-lethal means of preventing potential predators from gaining additional advantage over other birds. Signs should also indicate seasonal prohibitions on access to the area where vulnerable species nest or roost (USFWS 1999b).

- Evaluate the possibility of obtaining mitigation credit for restoration of the area.

The Planning Branch should be consulted before implementation of the recommended actions for this area.

3. Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area B (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)

Management Action

Development of a habitat protection and restoration plan for Special Interest Natural Area B is recommended to protect and enhance the bulrush-cattail habitat at the PHS.

The recommended objectives of the habitat protection and restoration plan are as follows:

- Complete a predictive ecological risk assessment for the drainage channels to determine the need for remediation and, if necessary, determine cleanup goals pursuant to CERCLA.
- Continue to prevent future contamination of the drainage channels to the extent practicable through implementation of the SWPPP for the base.
- Implement mitigation measures for the proposed Drainage Channel Improvement Project pursuant to NEPA to reduce potential impacts to biological resources to less than significant levels.
- Determine the feasibility of planting pickleweed (*Salicornia* spp.), alkali heath (*Frankenia salina*), or salt grass (*Distichlis spicata*) within the drainage channels and/or within the forebay south of the tide gate to develop potential habitat for the Belding's savannah sparrow and light-footed clapper rail. If feasible, this should be done after all construction and remediation within the channels is complete.
- Prevent the invasion of exotic plant species, especially pampas grass, iceplant (*Carpobrotus edulis*) and giant reed (*Arundo donax*), by eradicating nearby stands of exotic plant species and any exotic plant species that exist within the bulrush-cattail to the extent practicable.
- Remove litter from the drainage channels at the PHS, especially from the trash rack, on a regular basis (e.g., annually or after major storms).
- Install signs near the drainage channels indicating the presence of sensitive habitat. Signs should be constructed at a low height and should be fitted with materials to discourage perching, especially by predatory birds. Materials such as Nixalite™ and CatClaw™ are appropriate, non-lethal means of preventing potential predators from gaining additional advantage over other birds. Signs should also indicate seasonal prohibitions on access to the area where vulnerable species nest or roost (USFWS 1999b).

The Planning Branch should be consulted before implementation of the recommended actions for this area.

4. Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Coyote Brush Habitat (Special Interest Natural Area C)

Management Action

Development of a habitat protection and restoration plan for Special Interest Natural Area C is recommended to protect and enhance the coyote brush habitat at the PHS. Species-specific surveys are recommended for this project.

The recommended objectives of the habitat protection and restoration plan are:

- Restore the continuity of the coyote brush habitat by permanently restricting vehicle and foot traffic along the dirt road that currently runs through the habitat.
- Prevent the invasion of exotic plant species by eradicating nearby stands of exotic plant species and any exotic plant species that already exist within the coyote brush habitat to the extent practicable.
- Remove litter from the area on a regular basis.
- Install signs near the area indicating the presence of sensitive habitat. Signs should be constructed at a low height and should be fitted with materials to discourage perching, especially by predatory birds. Materials such as Nixalite™ and CatClaw™ are appropriate, non-lethal means of preventing potential predators from gaining additional advantage over other birds. Signs should also indicate seasonal prohibitions on access to the area where vulnerable species nest or roost (USFWS 1999b).

The Planning Branch should be consulted before implementing the recommended actions for this area.

5. Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan for Special Interest Natural Area D (Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage and Sandy Beach Habitats)

Management Action

Development of a habitat protection and restoration plan for Special Interest Natural Area D is recommended to protect and enhance the sandy beach and sand verbena-beach bursage habitat at the PHS.

The recommended objectives of the habitat protection and restoration plan are:

- Permanently restrict vehicle traffic on the beach and restrict foot traffic on the beach except for mission-critical activities.
- Restrict vehicle and foot traffic in the sand verbena-beach bursage habitat.
- Prevent disposal of debris (e.g., construction fill, dredge spoils) on the sandy beach or sand verbena-beach bursage habitat.
- Encourage growth and repair of the sand verbena-beach bursage habitat by protecting the native vegetation in these areas. Native vegetation helps to trap and hold sand on dunes.
- Prevent the invasion of exotic plant species into the sand verbena-beach bursage habitat, especially pampas grass and iceplant, by eradicating nearby stands of exotic plant species and any exotic plant species that already exist within this area to the extent practicable.
- Remove litter from these areas on a regular basis.

- Prevent the public from littering in the sand verbena-beach bursage habitat on the PHS property by installing trash cans outside of the base boundary at Silver Strand Beach and installing signs indicating the presence of sensitive habitat.
- Install signs within the base boundary near the sand verbena-beach bursage habitat and sandy beach indicating the presence of sensitive habitat. Signs should be constructed at a low height and should be fitted with materials to discourage perching, especially by predatory birds. Materials such as Nixalite™ and CatClaw™ are appropriate, non-lethal means of preventing potential predators from gaining additional advantage over other birds. Signs should also indicate seasonal prohibitions on access to the area where vulnerable species nest or roost (USFWS 1999b).

The Planning Branch should be consulted before implementation of the recommended actions for these areas.

6. Footpath/Greenbelt Loop

Management Action

A new footpath/greenbelt would be developed using an aggregate gravel base; the footpath would begin at the soccer field at the corner of Pleasant Valley Road and Pacific Road, extend down Pacific Road, wind through the administration areas, and eventually loop around the Seabee Golf Course. The footpath would be designated for walking, jogging, and bicycle use. Native trees would be planted along the footpath for shade and to provide wildlife habitat. Landscaping procedures should follow guidelines established in the BEAP for the PHS. Vegetation should be selected from a native plant species list for the PHS.

The Planning Branch should be consulted before implementation of these recommended improvements.

7. Landscape and Recreation Improvements

Management Action

The following management actions are recommended:

- Install lawns and native shade trees to the west and south of the proposed RV Park.
- Construct a swimming pool, a small convenience store, a maintenance building, and an office/clubhouse containing showers, laundry facilities, and a game room at the proposed RV Park site.
- Install a lawn and native shade trees near Buildings 1166 and 1167, especially where Building 77 is proposed for demolition.
- Install native vegetation near Buildings 69, 72, 73, and 5058.
- Install multiple canopy levels along Silver Strand Road and other areas along the southwest boundary of the base.
- Landscape along West Road using native shrub species, where possible.
- Landscaping procedures should follow guidelines established in the BEAP for the PHS (see Section 4.3.1.7).
- Vegetation should be selected from a native plant species list for the PHS.

8. Adaptive Management Plan for Burrowing Owls at the PHS

Management Action

- Preparation of an adaptive management plan for burrowing owls at the PHS is recommended to develop land use practices that are conducive to protection of the species on base. The USFWS (1999b) recommends that areas where burrowing owls are found should be managed as preserves for the species. Because the burrowing owl is a known predator of a listed species (California least tern), preparation of a plan is recommended to balance the protection of both species. A similar plan has been prepared for Naval Air Station (NAS) Lemoore. A survey of burrowing owls at the PHS to complete a census of the population on base and to map the population would be required as the first task to complete this project.
- Limit control of California ground squirrels on base because this species creates new habitat for the burrowing owl and control measures used (e.g., rodenticides) may harm burrowing owls (USFWS 1999b).
- Develop new opportunities for burrowing owls to nest in protected, unused portions of the PHS through the construction of berms with burrows and nesting dens (USFWS 1999b).
- Develop interim protection measures for the known burrowing owl location at the PHS (e.g., avoid training in the burrow location to the extent practicable).
- Develop educational materials for base personnel (especially personnel that train in or around areas with known burrows) to minimize disturbance to this species.

9. Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at IRP Site 14 (consisting of a containerized nursery operation)

Management Action

Implementation of the following management actions is recommended to protect natural resources at IRP Site 14:

- Construct an aggregate gravel base over IRP Site 14 immediately after construction of the final landfill cover to prevent colonization by burrowing owls and invasion of nonnative grasses.
- In the post-closure maintenance plan for IRP Site 14, develop storm water monitoring procedures for the detention basin that protect plant and wildlife species within the basin (as planned) and corresponding success criteria.
- Ensure that no environmentally harmful pesticides will be used by the future lessors of the site (e.g., for maintenance of the potted plant nursery).

10. Drip Irrigation System Installation

Management Action

Installation of drip irrigation systems in landscaped areas with exotic, ornamental species at the PHS is recommended, to the extent practicable. Installation of these systems should follow guidelines established in the BEAP for the PHS.

A drip irrigation system is much more efficient than other irrigation methods (Whitney 1999). For example, an average drip emitter (used for drip irrigation) uses about 1 gallon (3.8 liters) of water per hour, a microspray (another application of drip irrigation) uses 10 to 15 gallons (38 to 57 liters) per hour, and an overhead sprinkler uses 2 to 5 gallons (7.6 to 19 liters) per minute. Drip emitters also put water right to the root zone, thereby reducing runoff and evaporation. Drip emitters work best with established trees and shrubs, while subsurface and microspray systems work well with grass, turf, or other ground cover.

Note to Reader: The following projects are included for informational purposes, and they would not have the potential to trigger any issues under NEPA.

11. Basewide Wetland Delineation

Management Action

- Delineation of the boundaries of all jurisdictional waters of the United States at the PHS using the USACE protocol is recommended to determine where legally protected wetlands occur on base.
- Bulrush-cattail habitat (Special Interest Natural Areas A and B) and other wetlands identified in the National Wetlands Inventory on base should be delineated using USACE protocols.
- Use of a global position system device to conduct wetlands delineation is recommended to accurately map jurisdictional wetlands boundaries at the PHS in geographic information system (GIS).

12. Sensitive Species Surveys and Floristic Inventory

Management Action

To identify the potential impacts of base activities on sensitive species at the PHS, basewide surveys for several sensitive species are recommended. Intensive species-specific surveys should be conducted in suitable habitat on base, using USFWS and/or CDFG protocols, to confirm whether or not these species occur at the PHS. Survey reports should expand upon information provided in the INRMP by discussing the habitat requirements of each species and providing recommendations for enhancement of these species.

The INRMP originally recommended surveys for red-legged frog, tidewater goby, light-footed clapper rail, and Belding’s savannah sparrow; however, based on further comments from USFWS and Navy biologists, surveys are unnecessary as these species would be unlikely to occur at PHS (Keeney 1999, 2000; USFWS 1999b). In addition, the tidewater goby was recently delisted by the USFWS.

Table A-3. Special-Status Species Surveys Recommended for the Naval Base Ventura County PHS

Silvery legless lizard (<i>Anniella pulchra</i>) (ISC)
Bats (several species) (ISC)

Notes: Species are listed in order of priority based upon their potential to exist at the Naval Base Ventura County PHS.
 ISC - Installation species of concern.

In addition, a complete floristic inventory of the PHS is recommended during the spring and summer to detect annual plants that may have been missed during past surveys (USFWS 1999b).

13. Revision of the Base Exterior Architecture Plan (BEAP)

Management Action

The following improvements to the landscape planting guidelines and landscape maintenance guidelines established in the existing BEAP for the PHS are recommended to ensure that future landscaping and grounds maintenance practices are conducted in a manner with maximum benefit to native plant and wildlife species:

- Enhance plant species richness in Area G (shelterbelts/windrows) to promote wildlife biodiversity by removing eucalyptus trees in these areas using a phased approach.
- Determine the proper landscape mosaic that promotes wildlife diversity at the Seabee Golf Course.
- Preserve and enhance the existing landscaping in the Bard Mansion grounds.
- Remove or replace landscaping on base only when the vegetation is dead, diseased, or dying and poses a risk to human safety, or when it is beneficial to native plant and wildlife species to do so (i.e., removal of exotics).
- Develop a native plant species list for the PHS to replace the existing plant list in BEAP, using a qualified biologist, that includes recommendations from the *NAS Point Mugu Landscape Plant List: California Native Plants* (Keeney and Kameon 1997) and other California botanical resources.
- Conduct all future landscaping using native plant species selected from the native plant species list developed specifically for the PHS. Use drought-tolerant species as much as possible.
- When replacing dead or dying vegetation, a native species of similar size and structure should be used for replacement.
- Develop procedures for protecting native bird species (including their nests, eggs, and young) according to the Migratory Bird Treaty Act, and potential monarch butterfly roost trees, from destruction during grounds maintenance activities. All potential roost trees for monarch butterflies at the PHS should be surveyed annually to determine if roosting sites have been established. Any existing roost trees for monarch butterflies at the PHS should not be disturbed. Removal of shrubs and trees should be avoided during the nesting period for native bird species to the extent practicable (e.g., spring and summer). All shrubs and trees should be checked for nests if scheduled for removal or replacement. If a nest for a native species is found, removal of the shrub or tree should be avoided or postponed until the nest is no longer being used.
- Conserve water as much as possible when irrigating landscaped areas by installing drip irrigation systems wherever possible.
- Apply fertilizers to landscaped areas in compliance with the Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan for the PHS.
- Control plant diseases and pests according to an Integrated Pest Management Plan.

14. Protection Measures for Potential Monarch Butterfly Roosting Sites at the PHS

Management Action

Implementation of the following protection measures for monarch butterflies and their roost sites is recommended at the PHS:

- Survey the base annually for monarch butterfly roost sites.
- Protect all potential roost sites for the monarch butterfly at the PHS including all eucalyptus, cypress, and pine trees to the extent practicable.
- Avoid clearing and thinning of vegetation in known roost sites and have clearance for removal of trees at the PHS reviewed by the Project Review Board.
- If butterflies are present from September through February, avoid construction activity in the vicinity of known roost sites. The appropriate setback distance should be determined on a case-by-case basis.
- Protect water and nectar sources for butterflies near known roosts.
- Avoid using insecticides, herbicides, or other toxic chemicals in the vicinity of known roost sites.
- Enhance landscaped areas to attract monarch butterflies through the planting of winter-blooming flowers, providing/conserving freshwater sources on base, and making additional tree plantings to provide shelter from cold and wind. Native plant species should be used for additional plantings (USFWS 1999b).
- Create a pamphlet on monarch butterflies and distribute to all base personnel. The pamphlet should describe the biology of monarch butterflies, and potential threats to this species on base, and provide rules for dealing with this species on base including methods for reporting important observations (e.g., roost site locations) to base natural resource managers.

15. Protection Measures for Kelp Beds at the PHS

Management Action

Implementation of the following protection measures for kelp beds at the PHS is recommended:

- Survey and map the extent of kelp beds within the base boundaries.
- Protect the kelp beds from destruction or damage during dredging operations or harbor construction through coordination with the USACE.
- Prevent destruction or damage of kelp beds by harbor traffic, to the extent practicable, especially by large vessels.
- Discourage further construction of rip-rap or disposal of any debris along the mouth of the harbor and along the existing sections of the west and east jetties.
- Create and distribute a pamphlet on kelp beds to all base personnel. The pamphlet should describe the ecology of kelp beds, potential threats to these areas on base, and provide rules for dealing with these areas on base including methods for reporting important observations (e.g., presence of new kelp beds) to base resource managers.

16. Protection Measures for the California Brown Pelican and California Least Tern at the PHS

Management Action

Implementation of the following protection measures for this species is recommended to prevent potential take of the species during routine operations at the PHS:

- Restrict access to the sandy beach at the PHS except for mission-critical activities.
- Install signs at the sandy beach at the PHS indicating the presence of a sensitive species. Signs should be constructed at a low height and should be fitted with materials to discourage perching, especially by predatory birds. Materials such as Nixalite™ and CatClaw™ are appropriate, non-lethal means of preventing potential predators from gaining additional advantage over other birds. Signs should also indicate seasonal prohibitions on access to the area where vulnerable species nest or roost (USFWS 1999b).
- Install and maintain a barbed wire fence along the west jetty of the harbor and install signs to prevent the public from fishing within the base boundaries.
- Avoid construction in the harbor to the extent practicable between the months of April through August to protect foraging least terns.
- Create a pamphlet on the California brown pelican and California least tern and distribute to all base personnel. The pamphlet should describe the requirements of the federal ESA, the biology of the California brown pelican, potential threats to this species on base, and provide rules for dealing with this species on base including methods for reporting important observations (e.g., presence of injured individuals) to base natural resource managers.

17. Protection Measures for Marine Mammals at the PHS

Management Action

Implementation of the following protection measures for marine mammals is recommended to prevent potential take of these species during routine operations at the PHS:

- Prohibit harbor traffic and base personnel from purposefully approaching any marine mammal within the PHS boundaries.
- Restrict access to the sandy beach at the PHS except for mission-critical activities.
- Install signs at the sandy beach at the PHS indicating the presence of a sensitive species. Signs should be constructed at a low height and should be fitted with materials to discourage perching, especially by predatory birds. Materials such as Nixalite™ and CatClaw™ are appropriate, non-lethal means of preventing potential predators from gaining additional advantage over other birds.
- Install and maintain a barbed wire fence along the west jetty of the harbor and install signs to prevent the public from fishing within the base boundaries.
- Create a pamphlet on marine mammals and distribute to all base personnel. The pamphlet should describe the requirements of the Marine Mammal Protection Act, the biology of the marine mammals that potentially occur at the PHS, potential threats to these species on base, and provide rules for dealing with these species on base including methods for reporting important observations (e.g., presence of injured individuals) to base natural resource managers.

18. Protection Measures for Native Bird Species at the PHS

Management Action

Implementation of the following protection measures for native bird species is recommended to prevent potential take of these species during routine operations at the PHS:

- Create a pamphlet on native birds and distribute to all base personnel. The pamphlet should describe the requirements of the Migratory Bird Treaty Act, the biology of the dominant native bird species that occur at the PHS, potential threats to these species on base, and provide rules for dealing with these species on base including methods for reporting important observations (e.g., nest locations) to base natural resource managers.

19. Development of a Natural Resources Monitoring Program and Database

Management Action

- Develop a template database with a comprehensive inventory of both plant and animal populations.
- Designate a point of contact on either the PHS or NBVC Point Mugu who will be responsible for receiving information and updating the database accordingly (at a minimum, on a quarterly basis).
- Create educational materials for all personnel at the PHS explaining how they can contribute to natural resources management by relaying their natural resource observations. These materials should provide procedures for dealing with stranded, injured, or dead wildlife found on base (e.g., marine mammals, sea turtles, or birds).
- Coordinate the database with NBVC Environmental Division natural resources staff.

20. Improvements to the Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan

Management Action

Implementation of the following measures to improve the SWPPP for the PHS is recommended:

- Expand the SWPPP and MRPP to cover all facilities at the PHS, including non-industrial facilities.
- Expand the use of oil/water and sediment separators throughout the facility. A variety of sediment catch basin, oil/water separator, and curbside filter designs are available. Since many metals and organic pollutants are adsorbed onto sediment particles or are found as light non-aqueous phase liquids, sediment, oil, and grease should be removed from storm water as thoroughly as practicable.
- Install structural BMPs. Structural BMPs can achieve multiple storm water management goals including: contaminant filtration, settling of sediments, storm water detention, and flood control. Appropriate measures may include, among others, vegetative swales, collection and reuse of storm water, constructed wetlands, infiltration devices, and wet detention/retention basins.

- Storm water sampling should be performed in accordance with the SWPPP, during operating and non-operating hours. The General Permit requires that storm water samples be collected during the first 30 minutes of storm water discharge to capture the “first flush” of pollutants.

21. Improvements to the Recycling Program

Management Action

Implementation of the following improvements to the Recycling Program at the PHS is recommended:

- Manage the Qualified Recycling Program under the Pollution Prevention Program rather than the MWR Department.
- Expand the reuse and recycling of construction materials and demolition debris and improve documentation of these recycling efforts (e.g., amount recycled per year).
- Establish a separate composting program at the PHS to expand recycling of green waste (e.g., yard waste and waste generated from grounds maintenance) and reduce the use of fertilizers on base.
- Enlarge the materials recovery facility at the PHS to accommodate composting and storage of reusable construction materials. Consider using an IRP Site that would be suitable for this land use after remediation (e.g., IRP Site 9 – Burn Pit).

22. Outdoor Recreation Assessment

Management Action

Completion of the Outdoor Recreation Assessment for the PHS would include:

- A survey of current recreation areas and uses on base.
- Assessment of recreational needs on base.
- Integration with the surrounding recreation areas (e.g., connecting base bicycle path with surrounding paths).
- Maintenance of fencing and signage to reduce or eliminate illegal public access for recreational purposes.
- Maintenance of the base picnic grounds, play fields, and associated recreation facilities.
- Maintenance of current and planned outdoor recreation opportunities.
- Promotion of passive recreational uses in natural habitat areas (e.g., Special Interest Natural Areas) except for seasonal prohibitions on access to areas where vulnerable species may nest or roost (e.g. the beach).
- Update the BEAP with recommendations from the Outdoor Recreation Assessment.

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APPENDIX B
USACE JURISDICTIONAL DETERMINATION FOR THE DRAINAGE CHANNELS
AT THE PHS

DEPARTMENT OF THE ARMYLOS ANGELES DISTRICT, CORPS OF ENGINEERS
P.O. BOX 8711
LOS ANGELES, CALIFORNIA 90087-8711

MAR 25 1994

REPLY TO
ATTENTION OF:Office of the Chief
Regulatory BranchLCDR R.P. Sauerwein
Environmental Officer
Department of the Navy
Naval Construction Battalion Center
Port Hueneme, California 93043-5000SUBJECT: Jurisdictional Determination for the NCBC Drainage
Canals (COE File No. 94-540-TW)

Dear LCDR Sauerwein:

Reference is made to your letters dated 3 February, 9 February and 8 March 1994 in which you provided the historical information requested by the Corps in a letter dated 24 August 1993 concerning your proposal to concrete line the NCBC drainage canals (COE file no. 93-902-TW). This information assisted the Corps in determining and delineating the extent of our jurisdiction.

We have determined that the Corps' geographic jurisdictional limit within the drainage canals extends as far as the canals are subject to inundation by mean high waters. The Corps' jurisdictional area has been delineated by the Navy in Attachment 1, and is hereby confirmed by the Corps. As such, work and/or structures that would occur below the plane of mean high water, requires a permit from the Corps, pursuant to Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act only.

This determination was based on the following factors:

1. According to 33 CFR 322.5(g), "a canal or similar artificial waterway is subject to the regulatory authority (of Section 10) if it constitutes a navigable water of the U.S." In this case, the NCBC drainage canals became a navigable water of the U.S. (33 CFR 329.4) once the connection to the Port of Hueneme, a recognized navigable water of the U.S., was made. The connection allowed the drainage canals to be subjected to tidal action in the absence of a tide gate. As such, the Corps' regulatory jurisdiction within navigable waters of the U.S. extends to the entire surface and bed of all waterbodies subject to inundation by the mean high waters. A waterbody which was navigable in its natural or improved state retains its character as "navigable in law" even though it is presently not influenced

by tidal action due to the presence of an obstruction, in this case the tide gate. Once having obtained the character of "navigable in law," the Federal authority remains in existence, and cannot be abandoned by administrative officers or court action (see 33 CFR 329.9).

2. The preamble of the Federal Register dated November 13, 1986, states that non-tidal drainages excavated on dry land are generally not considered a "waters of the U.S.", pursuant to Section 404 of the Clean Water Act. Based on the fact that the canals were excavated in the upland and tidal influence has not existed since enactment of the Clean Water Act, the Corps considers the drainage canals not to be a "waters of the U.S." However, if the tide gate were to be removed and tidal action were to return, the canals would be considered a "waters of the U.S." and the rules and regulations of Section 404 would be applicable.

The delineation of the Corps' regulatory jurisdiction should assist the Navy when planning future projects. If you have any questions concerning this determination, please contact Ms. Tiffany Welch of my staff at (805) 641-2935.

Sincerely,

David J. Castanon

David J. Castanon
Chief, North Coast Section

Post-It [®] brand fax transmittal memo 787		# of pages
To	Christina M	3
From	David P	
Co.		
Dept.		
Fax #	681-3108	

NCBC CANAL SYSTEM

 = Zone of Tidal Influence

ATTACHMENT I

APPENDIX C

ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIVITIES STATUS MAP, IR SITE LOCATIONS AT THE PHS

Environmental Activities Status Map IR Site Locations at CBC Port Hueneme

LEGEND

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1 | Sites Closed - All Actions Completed |
| 2 | Sites Proposed For No Further Action/Site Closure |
| 3 | Sites Requiring a Remedial Investigation or Feasibility Study |
| 4 | Sites Undergoing the Removal Action Process |
| 5 | Sites Requiring Long-term Monitoring |
| 6 | Sites Requiring Additional Data |
| 7 | Other Sites |

1	CBC 17	Fuel, paint, and solvent storage in soil - Contaminated soil removed
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6	CBC 15	Possible PCB transformer spill in soil
---	---------------	--

1	CBC 16	Paint and solvent disposal suspected in soil
---	---------------	--

1	CBC 18	Fuel oil spill in soil
---	---------------	------------------------

3	CBC 6	Solvents and herbicides in soil
---	--------------	---------------------------------

1	CBC 7	Crushed radioactive rock disposal in soil
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3	CBC 5	PCBs, battery acid, formaldehyde, and oil in soil
---	--------------	---

3	CBC 4	Sewage sludge in soil
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3	CBC 21	Construction debris in soil removed
---	---------------	-------------------------------------

6	CBC 20	Fuel leaking from underground tanks to groundwater
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6	CBC 19	Possible solvents, fuel, and metals in surface water
---	---------------	--

5	CBC 14	Historical landfill with solvents, fuel, and pesticides in soil
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4	CBC 12B	PCB spill in soil
---	----------------	-------------------

1	CBC 13	Suspected PCB spill in soil
---	---------------	-----------------------------

2	CBC 11	Solvent, paint, and fuel disposal in soil
---	---------------	---

6	CBC 12A	PCB spill in soil
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2	CBC 10	Solvent, paint, and fuel disposal in soil
---	---------------	---

4	CBC 9	Construction debris in soil
---	--------------	-----------------------------

3	CBC 8	Suspected solvents, acid, fuels, and paint in soil
---	--------------	--

1	CBC 22	Aboveground tank fuel spills in soil
---	---------------	--------------------------------------

4	CBC 23	Ordnance storage suspected - PCB spills in soil
---	---------------	---

6	CBC 19	Possible solvents, fuel, and metals in surface water
---	---------------	--

- IR Sites at CBC Port Hueneme**
- Site 4 - Sewage Sludge Pits
 - Site 5 - Old Laboratory Property (Disposal Office)
 - Site 6 - Truck Stop (3 Road) Parking
 - Site 7 - Ammunition Ponds
 - Site 8 - Dry-Liner
 - Site 9 - Burning Pit
 - Site 10 - Construction Equipment Department (CED) Wash Rack
 - Site 11 - CED Filter Shop
 - Site 12A - CED Spray Paint Shop Area
 - Site 12B - CED PCB Spill Area
 - Site 13 - Mobile Utilities Support Equipment (PCE) Spill
 - Site 14 - Former Earth Moving Area
 - Site 15 - Transformer Storage Yard
 - Site 16 - Fuel Storage Yard
 - Site 17 - Hazardous Waste Magazine
 - Site 18 - Tobacco Oil Cans
 - Site 19 - Surface Water, Ditches, Harbor, and Canals
 - Site 20 - Naval Operations Training Center Building
 - Site 21 - Old Waste Disposal Pit
 - Site 22 - Aboveground Fuel Tank
 - Site 23 - Stack Traps

APPENDIX D
INRMP COMMENTS AND RESPONSES

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE

Ventura Fish and Wildlife Office
2493 Portola Road, Suite B
Ventura, California 93003

November 2, 2001

Capt. J.W. Rainwater, Commanding Officer
Naval Base Ventura County
311 Main Road, Suite 1
Point Mugu, California 93042-5033

Subject: Final Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan for the Construction Battalion Center, Port Hueneme, California

Dear Captain Rainwater:

We have reviewed the final integrated natural resources management plan (INRMP) for the Construction Battalion Center, Port Hueneme (CBC), which is part of the Naval Base Ventura County. We received the final INRMP on June 4, 2001. This was followed by a letter from Ron Dow of your staff dated October 19, 2001, requesting our concurrence with the INRMP by October 26, 2001. Mr. Dow's letter notes that the Ventura Fish and Wildlife Office has provided input to the INRMP starting in November 1998, and again in September 1999, and that responses to our comments have been incorporated into the final INRMP.

Our concurrence would signal our recognition that the plan satisfies certain requirements pursuant to the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997. In general, we believe a satisfactory INRMP accomplishes three goals: 1) the INRMP is complete and provides a conservation benefit to listed species; 2) the plan provides assurances that the conservation management strategies will be implemented; and 3) the plan provides assurances that the conservation management strategies will be effective by providing for periodic monitoring and revisions as necessary. All three of these general goals are addressed to our satisfaction in the INRMP for the CBC.

Consequently, we concur that the INRMP for the CBC satisfies our objectives for such a plan pursuant to the Sikes Act. We look forward to receiving periodic updates from the monitoring described in the plan, and we anticipate that the sensitive plants and animals that are present will benefit from the protections and restoration efforts presented in the INRMP.

If you have any questions concerning this concurrence, please contact Rick Farris of my staff at (805) 644-1766.

Sincerely,

Diane K. Noda

**Response to Public Comment on the
Final Draft Integrated Natural and Cultural Resources Management Plan (IRMP)
CBC Port Hueneme, CA
November 5, 1999**

Comment Number	Page Number	Line No., Figure No., Table No.	Commentor	Comment	Response
1	1-8	Table 1-1	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS)	Table 1-1 (page 1-8) does not include the California Department of Fish and Game under the heading of State Agencies with oversight over natural resources.	The California Department of Fish and Game was purposefully left out of Table 1-1 because this agency does not have legal oversight over natural resources at CBC Port Hueneme. However, the California Department of Fish and Game's role as a cooperative partner in the preparation of the Plan is discussed in the first paragraph of Section 1.3.
2	3-33	Table 3-8	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	The only sensitive plant species listed in Table 3-8 is Coulter's goldfields (<i>Lasthenia glabrata</i> ssp. <i>coulteri</i>). The endangered salt marsh bird's beak (<i>Cordylanthus maritimus</i> ssp. <i>maritimus</i>) is found just to the east of Ormond Beach and at Mugu Lagoon. In areas at the CBC where habitat supports <i>Frankenia</i> spp., <i>Typha</i> spp., <i>Distichlis spicata</i> , or other brackishwater plant species, the possibility exists that salt marsh bird's-beak could be present. Also, the recently re-discovered Ventura marsh milk-vetch (<i>Astragalus pycnostachyus</i> var. <i>latosissimus</i>) may occur on the site. The only known population near McGrath State beach is in a degraded dune system area, and the habitat requirements are not well known.	The salt marsh bird's-beak and Ventura marsh milk-vetch have been added to Table 3-8 and to the corresponding text.

3	4-26 and 4-27	Lines 2-34 and Lines 1-2	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<p>The IRMP reports that because the CBC is near the coast and supports stands of trees such as eucalyptus, some areas may be suitable for winter roosting by monarch butterflies (<i>Danaus plexippus</i>). In addition to the management measures proposed under IRMP-NR-10 (page 4-26), the CBC could also enhance the landscaped areas to attract this species, through the planting of flowers, providing a freshwater source, and making additional tree plantings to provide shelter from cold and wind for monarchs. We recommend that any additional plantings in this regard use native plant species.</p>	<p>The additional recommended management measures for the monarch butterfly have been incorporated into IRMP-NR-10.</p>
4	3-45	Table 3-10	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<p>In Table 3-10, the tidewater goby (<i>Eucyclogobius newberryi</i>) is listed as federally endangered. This species was recently proposed to be delisted north of Orange County, California. It is still endangered until the final rule is established; however, we recommend that the proposed delisting be noted in the table.</p>	<p>The proposed delisting of the tidewater goby north of Orange County has been noted in Table 3-10.</p>
5	3-45	Table 3-10	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<p>Also in Table 3-10 (footnote 5), the decision to delist the peregrine falcon (<i>Falco peregrinus</i>) was recently finalized, and the species is no longer listed as endangered.</p>	<p>The American peregrine falcon has been removed from Table 3-10 as well as from the corresponding text under Section 3.7.2 Sensitive Species.</p>
6	3-49	Lines 32-40	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<p>On page 3-49, in the discussion of mosquito control, the IRMP lists malathion as the pesticide of choice for controlling flying adults. The Service strongly recommends that malathion not be used in areas or during conditions when the chemical may enter waterways or natural habitat areas. We further recommend that the integrated pest management plan be written to include designations of areas unsuitable for spraying and for weather conditions when the ULV spray is least likely to enter natural areas (e.g., onshore wind days).</p>	<p>Malathion (ULV) has been used at CBC Port Hueneme in the past but is not necessarily the pesticide of choice. Recommendations provided by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service regarding the appropriate use of malathion, however, have been included in the management recommendations for the Integrated Pest Management Plan.</p>

7	4-16	Table 4-6	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<p>The IRMP (Table 4-6) notes that several species warrant focused surveys to determine their status at the CBC. Surveys for the California red-legged frog (<i>Rana aurora draytoni</i>) and California tiger salamander (<i>Ambystoma tigrinum californense</i>) are unnecessary as these species are not likely to be present. The CBC does not support suitable habitat for either species. Instead, we would prefer to see surveys for the endangered light-footed clapper rail (<i>Rallus longirostris levipes</i>), state-listed Belding's savannah sparrow (<i>Passerculus sandwichensis beldingi</i>), and the uncommon silvery legless lizard (<i>Anniella p. pulchra</i>).</p>	<p>After discussions with Mr. Rick Farris of the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, a survey for the California red-legged frog is still recommended in bulrush-cattail habitat (Special Interest Natural Area A) located in the northwest corner of CBC Port Hueneme in the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area near 23rd Avenue. The recommendation to survey for the California tiger salamander has been removed from the document. After discussions with Mr. Rick Farris, surveys for the light-footed clapper rail and Belding's savannah sparrow will be recommended only if the presence of suitable nesting habitat for these species (e.g., <i>Salicornia</i> sp., <i>Juncus</i> sp., <i>Spartina</i> sp.) is found at CBC Port Hueneme. This determination will be made after a floristic inventory of the base has been completed (see Comment #11 below). A survey for the silvery legless lizard will be recommended at CBC Port Hueneme.</p>
8	4-28	Lines 18-19	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<p>Per management measure IRMP-NR-12, the CBC proposed to install signs at various locations to warn of natural resource protections. The service recommends that any such signs be installed at a low height and that they and any protective fencing be fitted with materials to discourage perching, especially by predatory birds. Materials such as Nixalite™ and CatClaw™ are appropriate, non-lethal means of preventing potential predators from gaining additional advantage over other birds.</p>	<p>These additional management measures have been added to IRMP-NR-12 and throughout the document where installation of signs are recommended.</p>

9	4-32	Lines 2-32	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<p>The protection of burrowing owls (<i>Athene cunicularia</i>) at the CBC is of great importance. Very few colonies of this species remain in Ventura County, or in the rest of the State outside of refuges. We recommend that the extent and location(s) of the burrowing owl population be mapped and that these areas be managed as preserves for the species. Also, new opportunities for burrowing owls to nest could be created in protected, unused portions of CBC through the construction of berms with burrows and nesting dens. Similarly, we recommend that California ground squirrel (<i>Spermophilus beecheyi</i>) controls be limited, both to protect the burrowing owl and other species from rodenticides, and because California ground squirrels create new habitat for the burrowing owl.</p>	<p>All of the recommendations and rationale for the protection of burrowing owls at CBC Port Hueneme have been included in management recommendation IRMP-NR-17.</p>
10			U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	<p>Passive outdoor recreation is not always compatible with the conservation of natural resources. This is particularly true for ground-nesting birds, such as the California least tern (<i>Sterna antillarum browni</i>) which relies solely upon the coloration to protect its nests, eggs, and young. The activities of humans, especially when accompanied by dogs, can cause adults to abandon nests and leaving eggs and young vulnerable to predation and environmental effects (e.g., overheating). We agree with some of the measures proposed under IRMP-NR-20 (page 4-36); however, we would prefer to see seasonal prohibitions on access to areas where vulnerable species nest or roost.</p>	<p>Believe that the comment is for IRMP-NR-22 on page 4-37 (Lines 30 and 31). The phrase "Promotion of passive recreational uses in natural habitat areas (e.g., Special Interest Natural Areas); and" has been changed to "Promotion of passive recreational uses in natural habitat areas (e.g., Special Interest Natural Areas) except for seasonal prohibitions on access to areas where vulnerable species may nest or roost (e.g., the beach) (USFWS 1999); and". It will be recommended that seasonal prohibitions on access to these areas will also be included on signs in these areas.</p>

11		U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service	Our last recommendation is that greater emphasis should be placed upon surveys and monitoring. Although the IRMP is accurate and fairly thorough, field surveys are vital in determining the presence and distributions of sensitive species on CBC. In that regard, we recommend that surveys be expanded to include a complete floristic inventory, performed in spring and summer to detect annual plants that may have been missed in December surveys.	Development of a natural resources monitoring program and database for CBC Port Huenehme has been recommended in management recommendation IRMP-NR-15. In addition, a complete floristic inventory at CBC Port Huenehme has been added to management recommendation IRMP-NR-3.
1		National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS)	With respect to marine mammals, I think your list (California sea lions and harbor seals) of protected species is complete, and unless the project area includes coastal waters (which could contain coastal bottlenose dolphins, and perhaps grey whales on their northward migration), you should not need to be concerned about any other marine mammal species.	The property boundary of CBC Port Huenehme does not extend into coastal waters therefore, we should not need to be concerned about any other marine mammal species.
2		National Marine Fisheries Service	Quite a few loggerhead turtles have stranded as far north as San Luis Obispo County this year. If you have any stranding records of sea turtles on the base, you should include them in the report along with management actions.	There have been no known strandings of sea turtles at CBC Port Huenehme. However, development of procedures for dealing with stranded or injured wildlife at CBC Port Huenehme (including sea turtles) will be included in management recommendation IRMP-NR-15 <i>Natural Resources Monitoring Program and Database.</i>
3	4-29	National Marine Fisheries Service	Do seals or sea lions haul out on the sandy beach that is referenced (i.e., it is not clear why access is restricted)? If they do, NMFS supports the placement of signs indicating the presence of seals, and our enforcement department has signs that are available to you, or can help you with the proper wording.	Neither seals nor sea lions have ever been observed to haul out at this location. However, this location is suitable habitat for seals and sea lions to haul out. Signs to protect this habitat for seals, sea lions, and the California brown pelican would be useful.
4		National Marine Fisheries Service	Seals/sea lions are a "protected" species, rather than a "sensitive" species (defined earlier on page 3-44).	"Sensitive" is used in the text to refer to any species protected under the Endangered Species Act, Migratory Bird Treaty Act, or the Marine Mammal Protection Act. The "protected" status of seals/sea lions will be clarified in the text.

5		National Marine Fisheries Service	<p>What is the purpose of the barbed wire fence along the west jetty? If any seals/sea lions haul out here, we need to be sure that they are not impacted by the barbed wire - i.e., may get tangled/cut by it.</p> <p>NMFS supports the distribution of a pamphlet, and again, we would be happy to help you with this or send you samples or pamphlets we have used in the past. We also have hotlines for Ventura County for dead and stranded marine mammals and sea turtles which should be printed in the pamphlet.</p>	<p>Neither seals nor sea lions have ever been observed to haul out at this location. In addition, this habitat is unsuitable for either seals or sea lions to haul out.</p> <p>Concur.</p>
6		National Marine Fisheries Service		

APPENDIX E

PEST MANAGEMENT PLAN IMPLEMENTATION RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are suggestions for additions to the Pest Management Plan for the PHS that would integrate it with recommendations contained in the INRMP.

1) Pesticide Application: A list of “least environmentally harmful” pesticides should be developed, and the use of Malathion (ULV) should be eliminated in areas where the chemical may enter waterways or natural habitat areas. The INRMP states that the PMP should include designations of areas unsuitable for spraying and for weather conditions when ULV should or should not be used. However, no mapping was completed for the PMP. Once the approved pesticide list is developed, “safe use” areas should be mapped taking into consideration the Special Interest Natural Areas that are designated in the INRMP. After mapping has occurred, natural resources staff should be contacted prior to the physical application of the pesticide to confirm it is safe for sensitive species in the area. In addition, a procedural guidance for all necessary coordination with natural resources staff should be distributed. If it is absolutely necessary to apply pesticides in a sensitive area, a biological monitor should be present. Alternative application methods should be investigated in sensitive areas.

2) Exotic Species Eradication: A focused removal plan for exotic species located near special interest natural areas on the PHS should be developed. The main species that should be removed include iceplant, pampas grass, giant reed, hottentot fig, tamarisk, and Tasmanian blue gum. In keeping with the Executive Order issued in 1994 on *Environmentally and Economically Beneficial Practices on Federal Landscaped Grounds* (April 26, 1994), native plants of similar size and structure (taken from the list that will be developed specifically for the PHS site) should be used to revegetate the area once the exotics are removed. A native plant list (originally developed for Point Mugu) is included as an appendix to the INRMP and should be used as a baseline for the PHS site.

3) Disease Vector Control: Disease vectors found on the PHS include two mosquito species and various rodents, such as the deer mouse. The PHS currently has no management program in place for these animals. These vectors can negatively impact native habitats and sometimes humans (hantavirus). Therefore, an active program that balances elimination techniques with the protection of wildlife and habitats should be developed.

4) Ballast Water Treatment: One method of preventing aquatic invasive species problems within the harbor is to exchange ballast water on the high seas. The introduction of peracetic acid into ballast water and treatment of ballast water in dockside facilities are treatment methods that are currently being explored. The Integrated Pest Management Plan should evaluate potential options for the treatment of ballast water in PHS ships, including the feasibility of treating the ballast water using the existing Bilge and Oily Wastewater Treatment System. The most feasible treatment option should be implemented as soon as possible.

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APPENDIX F
AIR QUALITY CALCULATIONS AND RONA

Air Quality Calculations

Proposed Action

Assumptions:

Vehicle data estimated by contractor.

Times for each mode of construction estimated by contractor.

Total time to complete demolition, construction, landscaping for the three PHS improvements is estimated to be 9 months.

Conversions

grams to tons = 1E-06

pounds to tons = 0.0005

Construction Equipment	days	# vehicles	hours/day	VOC			NO _x			CO			SO _x (g/hour)			PM ₁₀ (g/hour)		
				emission factor	amount	tons	emission factor	amount	tons	emission factor	amount	tons	emission factor	amount	tons	emission factor	amount	tons
wheeled loader ¹	270	1	3	110.4	89,424.0	0.10	858.1	695,061.0	0.77	259.5	210,195.0	0.23	82.5	66,825.0	0.07	77.9	63,099.0	0.07
planer/dozer ¹	270	1	3	84.7	68,639.4	0.08	1,889.2	1,530,219.6	1.70	816.8	661,616.1	0.73	158.0	127,980.0	0.14	75.0	60,750.0	0.07
motor grader ¹	270	1	3	17.6	14,280.3	0.02	324.4	262,788.3	0.29	68.5	55,485.0	0.06	39.0	31,590.0	0.04	27.7	22,437.0	0.02
excavator/crawler ¹	270	1	5	67.7	91,395.0	0.10	767.3	1,035,855.0	1.15	306.4	413,640.0	0.46	64.7	87,345.0	0.10	63.2	85,320.0	0.09
off-highway truck ¹	270	1	5	87.4	117,990.0	0.13	1,889.2	2,550,366.0	2.83	816.8	1,102,693.5	1.22	206.0	278,100.0	0.31	116.0	156,600.0	0.17
fork-lift ¹	270	1	2	67.7	36,558.0	0.04	767.3	414,342.0	0.46	306.4	165,456.0	0.18	64.7	34,938.0	0.04	63.2	34,128.0	0.04
off-highway truck (water truck) ¹	270	1	5	87.4	117,990.0	0.13	1,889.2	2,550,366.0	2.83	816.8	1,102,693.5	1.22	206.0	278,100.0	0.31	116.0	156,600.0	0.17

Fugitive Dust Emissions²

Project Total	tons	0.60	tons	10.03	tons	4.12	tons	1.00	tons	0.64
----------------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	--------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------

Notes:

¹ Emission factors in grams/hour; factors from USEPA 1985 (AP-42 Volume II, Section II-7) and USEPA 1995 (AP-42, Volume I, Section 13.2.3).

² PM₁₀ calculations have been determined assuming 1.2 tons per month of construction multiplied by the % estimated PM₁₀ (as determined by the soil type).

As the proposed project location has been described as being loamy sand/silty clay, (55% clay/silt). The conservative estimate for PM₁₀ is 30%.

PHS improvements Combined: 1.2 x 6 acres per project x 9 months total projects x 0.30 = 19.44 tons of PM₁₀ emitted + 0.64 tons = 20.10 tons

Source: USEPA 1999. AP 42. Section 13.2. <http://www.epa.gov/ttn/chief/ap42c13.html>

Fugitive Dust for the combined Enhancement Projects:

(6 acres for all three projects) x (1.2 tons/acre) x (9 months total) x (0.30 [PM₁₀ factor]) = 19.44 tons

(19.44 tons) + (0.64 tons [project total]) = 20.10 *tons per year*

APPENDIX G

NAVY CHAIN OF COMMAND AND RESPONSIBILITIES

A review of the chain of command and responsibilities of the newly regionalized Navy follows, based on <http://www.cpf.navy.mil>.

The Commander-in-Chief, Pacific Fleet reports administratively to the Chief of Naval Operations (CNO) and operationally to the Commander-in-Chief, U.S. Pacific Command (USCINCPAC). CINCPACFLT provides ships, sailors, and marines in support of several force users within the Department of Defense. In the Pacific Fleet Chain-of-Command, Type Commanders, Numbered Fleet Commanders (and Operations Commanders), and Regional Commanders within the area of responsibility of the Pacific Fleet report to CINCPACFLT.

In addition to its Operational and Type Commanders, the Pacific Fleet also coordinates Navy support activities ashore through Regional Coordinators. Overseas, these Regional Coordinators also serve as the Pacific Fleet's military liaison with host governments to facilitate combined exercises and enhance mutual force coordination. There are six Regional Coordinators:

- Commander, Navy Region Southwest (CNRSW);
- Commander, Navy Region Northwest;
- Commander, Navy Region Hawaii;
- Commander, Naval Forces, Japan;
- Commander, Naval Forces Korea; and
- Commander, Naval Forces, Marianas.

CNRSW is the naval shore installation management headquarters for the southwest region. Navy Region Southwest serves as regional coordinator for CINCPACFLT, which is headquartered in Hawaii, and coordinates support for installations in California, Arizona, and Nevada.

Naval Base San Diego is one of eight naval bases under the responsibility of CNRSW. The other installations under command of CNRSW include:

- Naval Base Coronado;
- Naval Base Point Loma;
- Naval Air Station Lemoore;
- Naval Air Station Fallon;
- Naval Air Facility El Centro;

- Naval Base Ventura County; and
- Naval Weapons Station Seal Beach.

Each of the eight installations in the southwest region is under the direction of a Commanding Officer. Most of the Commanding Officers also act as Assistant Chief of Staff to the various activities associated with the region; the Commanding Officer for Naval Base San Diego also acts as the Assistant Chief of Staff for Port Operations. The following organizational chart represents the chain of command for CNRSW. The chain of command for the CNRSW Environmental Department is also provided.

Business Process

Cross-Functional Leadership

BASE COs

- CO CORONADO
- CO SAN DIEGO
- CO POINT LOMA
- CO LEMOORE
- CO FALLON
- CO EL CENTRO
- CO SEAL BEACH
- CO VENTURA CO.

- INTERNAL SUPPORT FUNCTIONS**
- DIR CIV PERS
 - DIR COMMAND EVAL
 - DIR LEGAL SUPPORT
 - DIR PAO
 - DIR RELIGIOUS SVCS
 - DIR MIL PERS
 - DIR ADMIN

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002/007
CHRON(NR)✓

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY
COMMANDER IN CHIEF
UNITED STATES PACIFIC FLEET
280 MAKALAPA DRIVE
PEARL HARBOR, HAWAII 96860-3131

IN REPLY REFER TO
5090
Ser N46523/0481
22 Mar 02

From: Commander in Chief, U.S. Pacific Fleet
To: Commander, Navy Region Southwest (N45)

Subj: FINDING OF NO SIGNIFICANT IMPACT (FONSI) FOR PROPOSED
IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN (INRMP), NAVAL BASE VENTURA, PORT
HUENEME SITE, CALIFORNIA

Ref: (a) COMNAVREG SW ltr 5090 Ser N45/050 of 26 Feb 02
(b) OPNAVINST 5090.1B

Encl: (1) Finding of No Significant Impact (FONSI)
(2) Notice of Availability (NOA)

1. An Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP) and accompanying Environmental Assessment (EA) for Naval Base Ventura, Port Hueneme Site, California were forwarded by reference (a) for review in accordance with reference (b). It has been determined that preparation of an Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) is not required and that neither the proposed action nor management measures would generate significant impacts. Accordingly, it is considered that, with implementation of the following paragraph and any mitigation measures described in enclosure (1), compliance with the National Environmental Policy Act and the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997 has been effected, and the proposed management measures described in the above plan may be initiated.

2. The Council on Environmental Quality regulations require public notification of the availability of the EA and of the decision not to prepare an EIS. If appropriate, publication in a foreign-language newspaper should also occur.

03/22/2002 FRI 17:16 FAX

003/007

Subj: FINDING OF NO SIGNIFICANT IMPACT (FONSI) FOR PROPOSED
IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN (INRMP), NAVAL BASE VENTURA, PORT
HUENEME SITE, CALIFORNIA

Please provide verification of local publication to
CINCPACFLT (N465) upon implementation. The INRMP and
accompanying EA should be retained in project files for
possible future use.

3. Point of contact is Ms. Karen A. Verkennes, N46523, at
COMM/DSN (808) 474-0745 or E-mail VerkenKA@cpf.navy.mil.

Date 23 March 2002

D.L. CRISP
Deputy Chief of Staff, for
Shore Installation Management

Copy to:
NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY, PORT HUENEME SITE
SOUTHWESTNAVFACENCOM (Code 5GENP, 5GPN.TC)
CNO WASHINGTON DC (N456)
CHINFO WASHINGTON DC

DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE
DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

FINDING OF NO SIGNIFICANT IMPACT (FONSI) FOR ENVIRONMENTAL
ASSESSMENT (EA) FOR THE PROPOSED IMPLEMENTATION OF THE
INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN (INRMP) FOR NAVAL
BASE VENTURA COUNTY PLAN, PORT HUENEME, CALIFORNIA

Pursuant to Council on Environmental Quality regulations (40 CFR
Parts 1500-1508) implementing procedural provisions of the
National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA), the Department of the
Navy gives notice that an EA has been prepared and an
Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) is not required for the
implementation of an INRMP for the Port Hueneme Site (PHS).

In November 1997, the Sikes Act was amended via the Sikes Act
Improvement Act (SAIA) to require the Secretary of Defense to
carry out a program to provide for the conservation of natural
resources on military installations. To facilitate this
program, the SAIA states that all Navy facilities with natural
resources will prepare and implement an INRMP. The Navy
prepared the INRMP as part of a comprehensive resource
management document entitled "Integrated Natural Resources
Management Plan, Naval Base Ventura County Port Hueneme Site,
California". The INRMP was a cooperative effort among the U.S.
Navy, the United States Fish and Wildlife Service, the
California Department of Fish and Game, and the National Marine
Fisheries Service. Comments received on the INRMP from these
agencies were addressed in the final document.

Two alternatives are analyzed in this EA: the proposed action
(INRMP implementation) and the no-action alternative.
Implementation of the proposed action was reviewed for potential
conflicts with future planned projects at the PHS. No conflicts
were identified; therefore, a "modified" alternative was not
carried forward for analysis. No other alternatives were
identified that could fulfill the purpose and need for the
proposed action.

The proposed action is to fully implement the INRMP and its
recommendations, depending on the availability of appropriate
funding sources, consistent with the military uses of the
property and the goals and objectives established in the SAIA.
Components of the INRMP analyzed in the EA consist of:

- Pest Management Plan
- Habitat Protection and Restoration Plans for Special Interest Natural Areas including Bulrush-Cattail Habitats, Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage and Sandy Beach Habitats, and Coyote Brush Habitat
- Footpath/Greenbelt Loop
- Landscape and Recreation Improvements
- Adaptive Management Plan for Burrowing Owls
- Construction of Agricultural Out-lease Area at Installation Restoration Program (IRP) Site 14
- Drip Irrigation System Installation

The no-action alternative would entail continued implementation of existing natural and cultural resources management practices at the PHS. If the no-action alternative were implemented, ongoing, informal practices used for management of natural and cultural resources at the PHS would continue.

The EA addresses the effects of the proposed action on both the human and natural environment. Environmental issues addressed in this EA include biological resources, hydrology and surface water quality, land use and visual resources, transportation and circulation, air quality, noise, cultural resources, and safety. Specific concerns at the PHS include the protection of existing remaining habitat, conducting baseline surveys for plant and animal species, restoration of degraded habitat, recreational improvements, educational and monitoring programs, and plan programs and updates related to natural resources management, such as the Base Exterior Architecture Plan. Based on the analysis presented in this EA, the proposed action would not significantly impact the quality of the human environment and would have no significant effect on any federally listed species or critical habitat; therefore, an EIS is not required. The proposed action would be expected to have beneficial impacts on the environment at the PHS.

The EA also addresses cumulative impacts that could result from the incremental impact of the proposed action when added to other past, present, or reasonably foreseeable future actions. Review of the potential environmental impacts of this project, combined with those associated with implementation of the

proposed action, indicated that no significant cumulative impacts would occur.

Based on the information gathered during preparation of the EA, the Department of the Navy finds that implementation of the proposed action would not have a significant impact on the quality of the human or natural environment or generate significant controversy.

The EA prepared by the Navy addressing this action is on file, and interested parties may obtain a copy from: Teri Reid, Public Affairs Officer, Naval Base Ventura County, (805) 989-9234. A limited number of copies of the EA are available to fill single copy requests.

23 March 2002

Date

D.L. Crisp

D.L. CRISP
Rear Admiral (sel), U.S. Navy
Deputy Chief of Staff for
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03/22/2002 FRI 17:17 FAX

007/007

DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE
DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NOTICE OF AVAILABILITY (NOA) OF THE FINDING OF NO SIGNIFICANT
IMPACT (FONSI) AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESMENT (EA) FOR PROPOSED
IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT
PLAN (INRMP) NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY, PORT HUENEME, CALIFORNIA

Pursuant to Council on Environmental Quality regulations (40 CFR
Parts 1500-1508) implementing procedural provisions of the
National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA), the Department of the
Navy gives notice that an EA has been prepared and an
Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) is not required for the
implementation of an INRMP for the Port Hueneme Site (PHS).

The proposed action is to fully implement the INRMP and its
recommendations, depending on the availability of appropriate
funding sources, consistent with the military uses of the
property and the goals and objectives established in the SAIA.

Based on the analysis presented in the EA, the proposed action
would not significantly impact the quality of the human
environment and would have no significant effect on any
federally listed species or critical habitat. The proposed
action would be expected to have beneficial impacts on the
environment at the PHS.

Based on the information gathered during preparation of the EA,
the Department of the Navy finds that implementation of the
proposed action would not have a significant impact on the
quality of the human or natural environment or generate
significant controversy.

The EA prepared by the Navy addressing this action is on file,
and interested parties may obtain a copy from: Teri Reid, Public
Affairs Officer, Naval Base Ventura County, (805) 989-9234. A
limited number of copies of the EA are available to fill single
copy requests.

APPENDIX C
LIST OF NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT DRIVERS AND INTEGRATING
OTHER PLANS

TABLE OF CONTENTS

C.1 LAWS, REGULATIONS, DIRECTIVES, INSTRUCTIONS AND GUIDANCEC -1

TABLE C-1: APPLICABLE LAWS, REGULATIONS, AND EXECUTIVE ORDERSC-1

TABLE C-2: DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE POLICY, REGULATIONS AND GUIDANCEC -4

TABLE C-3: APPLICABLE STATE AND LOCAL REGULATIONSC -6

C.2 INTEGRATING OTHER PLANS.....C -7

APPENDIX C REFERENCES.....C -10

C.1 LAWS, REGULATIONS, DIRECTIVES, INSTRUCTIONS, AND GUIDANCE

The most relevant and influential federal, state, and local laws and regulations, Executive Orders (EOs), U.S. Department of Defense Instructions (DoDINST), U.S. Department of Navy (Navy) Instructions (Naval Operations Instruction [OPNAVINST]) and manuals that pertain to all types of projects occurring at Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC) Port Hueneme are listed in this Appendix.

Federal laws, regulations, and EOs are identified below in Table C-1. Department of Defense instructions, directives and guidance are in Table C-2. Applicable state laws and regulations are detailed in Table C-3.

TABLE C-1: APPLICABLE FEDERAL LAWS, REGULATIONS, AND EXECUTIVE ORDERS

Title	Citation
American Indian Religious Freedom Act of 1978, as amended	42 U.S.C. 1996
Anadromous Fish Conservation Act of 1965	16 U.S.C. 757a-757g
Animal Damage Control Act of 1931	7 U.S.C. 426 - 426c
Anti-Deficiency Act of 1982, as amended	31 U.S.C. 1341 et seq.
Antiquities Act of 1906, as amended	16 U.S.C. §§ 431-433
Archeological and Historical Preservation Act of 1960, as amended	16 U.S.C. 469-469c
Archaeological Resources Protection Act of 1979, as amended	16 U.S.C. §§ 470aa-mm and Public Law 96-95
Armed Forces - Real property; related personal property; and lease of non-excess property (1956, as amended)	10 U.S.C. 2661 - 2697
Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act of 1940, as amended	16 U.S.C. 668-668d
Clean Air Act (1994 and Amendments of 1990)	42 U.S.C. §§ 7401-7671q and Public Law No. 101-549, 104 Stat. 2399
Clean Water Act (1972, as amended)	33 U.S.C. §§ 1251-1387
Coastal Zone Management Act	16 U.S.C. §§ 1451-1466
Comprehensive Environmental Resources, Compensation, and Liability Act (1980)	42 U.S.C. §§ 9601-9675
Control of Noxious Plants on Government Lands	43 U.S.C. 1241 - 1243
Council on Environmental Quality Regulations	40 CFR Parts 1500-1508
Defense Environmental Restoration Program (1986)	10 U.S.C. 2700 - 2710
Emergency Wetland Resources Act of 1986	16 U.S.C. 3901 - 3932
Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended	16 U.S.C. §§ 1531-1544
Entering Military, Naval, or Coast Guard Property (1948, as amended)	18 U.S.C. 1382
EPA Guidelines for Resource Recovery Facilities	40 CFR 245
EPA National Drinking Water Regulations	40 CFR 141-143
EPA National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System Permit Regulations	40 CFR 122
EPA Regulations Designating Areas for Air Quality Planning	40 CFR 81
EPA Regulations for Ambient Air Monitoring Reference and Equivalent Methods	40 CFR 53
EPA Regulations for Pesticide Programs	40 CFR 150-186
EPA Regulations Implementing the Resource Conservation and Recovery Act	40 CFR 260-270
EPA Regulations on Criteria and Standards for the National Pollutant	40 CFR 125

Title	Citation
Discharge Elimination System	
EPA Regulations on Discharge of Oil	40 CFR 110
EPA Regulations on Disposal Site Determination under the CWA	40 CFR 231
EPA Regulations on Implementation of NEPA Procedures	40 CFR 6
EPA Regulations on Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Use	40 CFR 162
EPA Regulations on Land Disposal Restrictions	40 CFR 268
EPA Regulations on National Primary and Secondary Ambient Air Quality Standards	40 CFR 50
EPA Regulations on Regional Consistency under the Clean Air Act	40 CFR 56
EPA Requirements for Preparation, Adoption, Submittal, Approval, and Promulgation of Implementation Plans	40 CFR 51-52
EPA Requirements for Water Quality Planning and Management	40 CFR 130
EPA Special Exemptions from Requirements of the Clean Air Act	40 CFR 69
Executive Order (EO) 13211 Actions Concerning Regulations That Significantly Affect Energy Supply, Distribution, or Use (2001)	66 FR 28355
EO 13212 Actions To Expedite Energy-Related Projects (2001), as amended by EO 13286	66 FR 28357
EO 13286 Amendment of Executive Orders, and Other Actions, in Connection With the Transfer of Certain Functions to the Secretary of Homeland Security (2003)	68 FR 10619
EO 13175 Consultation and Coordination With Indian Tribal Governments (2000)	65 FR 67249
EO 12114 Environmental Effects Abroad of Major Department of Defense Actions (1979)	44 FR 1957
EO 13274 Environmental Stewardship and Transportation Infrastructure Project Reviews (2002)	67 FR 59449
EO 13352 Facilitation of Cooperative Conservation (2004)	69 FR 52989
EO 13514 Federal Leadership in Environmental, Energy, and Economic Performance (2009)	74 FR 52117
EO 13150 Federal Workforce Transportation (2000)	65 FR 24613
EO 11988 Floodplain Management (1977), as amended by EO 12148 and 13286	42 FR 26951
EO 12777 Implementation of Section 311 of the Federal Water Pollution Control Act of October 18, 1972, as amended, and the Oil Pollution Act of 1990 (as amended by EO 13286)	56 FR 54757
EO 13007 Indian Sacred Sites (1996)	61 FR 26071
EO 12372 Intergovernmental Review of Federal Programs (1977, 1983, and 1984)	47 FR 30959
EO 13112 Invasive Species (2009)	64 FR 2419
EO 13158 Marine Protected Areas (2000)	65 FR 34909
EO 11593 Protection and Enhancement of the Cultural Environment (1971)	36 FR 8921
EO 11514 Protection and Enhancement of Environmental Quality (1970), as amended by EO 11541 and 11991	35 FR 4247
EO 11990 Protection of Wetlands (1977)	42 FR 26961
EO 13186 Responsibilities of Federal Agencies to Protect Migratory Birds and Migratory Bird Treaty Act	66 FR 3853 and 16 U.S.C. §§ 703–712
EO 13423 Strengthening Federal Environmental, Energy, and Transportation Management (2007)	72 FR 3919
Estuary Protection Act of 1968	16 U.S.C. §§ 1221-1226
Federal Consistency with Approved Coastal Management Programs	15 CFR 930
Federal Facilities Compliance Act of 1992	42 U.S.C. 6961

Title	Citation
Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act of 1947, as amended	7 U.S.C. 136 et seq.
Federal Land Policy and Management Act	43 U.S.C. 1701
Federal Water Pollution Control Act of 1948, as amended	33 U.S.C. 1251 - 1376
Fish and Wildlife Conservation Act of 1980, as amended	16 U.S.C. §§ 2901-2912
Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act of 1934, as amended	16 U.S.C. 661 - 667e
Historic Sites, Buildings and Antiquities Act of 1935, as amended	16 U.S.C. 461-462, 464-467
Investigations Concerning Erosion of Shores of Coastal and Lake Waters (1930, as amended)	33 U.S.C. 426
Lacey Act of 1900, as amended	16 U.S.C. 3371 - 3378
Land and Water Conservation Fund Act of 1965	16 U.S.C. 460 <i>l</i> 4 - 460 <i>l</i> 11
Magnuson Stevens Fishery Conservation and Management Act, as amended (1996)	16 U.S.C. §§ 1801-1844
Marine Mammal Protection Act (1972)	16 U.S.C. §§ 1361
Marine Protection, Research, and Sanctuaries Act of 1972	33 U.S.C. 1401 - 1445
Migratory Bird Conservation Act of 1929, as amended	16 U.S.C. 715-715d, 715e, 715f-715r
Migratory Bird Rule	50 CFR Part 21, 28 FR 8931
Migratory Bird Treaty Act of 1918, as amended	16 U.S.C. § 703 et. seq.
Multiple-Use Sustained Yield Act of 1960, as amended	16 U.S.C. 528
National Defense Authorization Act of 2004	Public Law 108-136
National Environmental Policy Act, as amended	42 U.S.C. § 4321 et seq.
National Historic Preservation Act of 1966, as amended (2004)	16 U.S.C. §§ 470–470x-6
Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (1990)	25 U.S.C. §§ 3001 et. seq. and Public Law 101-601
Natural Resources Management Program (1989)	32 CFR 190
Neotropical Migratory Bird Conservation Act of 2000	16 U.S.C. 6101 - 6109
Nonindigenous Aquatic Nuisance Prevention and Control Act of 1990, as amended	16 U.S.C. 4701 et seq.
North American Wetlands Conservation Act of 1989, as amended	16 U.S.C. 4401 - 4412
Plant Protection Act of 2002, as amended	7 U.S.C. 7701 - 7786
Pollution Prevention Act of 1990	42 U.S.C. §§ 13101–13109
Promulgation Resource Recovery Facilities Guidelines	40 CFR 245
Protection of Archaeological Resources (1984)	43 CFR 7
Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (1976)	42 U.S.C. §§ 6901–6992k
Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899	33 U.S.C. 401, 403, 407
Safe Drinking Water Act of 1974, as amended	42 U.S.C. 300f - 300j.26
Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, as amended	16 U.S.C. § 670 et. seq.
USFWS Memorandum to Regional Directors, Regions 1-8, Delegation of INRMP Concurrence Authority. 12 June 2009	
Soil and Water Conservation Act of 1977	16 U.S.C. § 2001-2009
Wild and Scenic River Act of 1968, as amended	16 U.S.C. 1271 - 1287

Notes:
CFR Code of Federal Regulations
FR Federal Register
U.S.C. United States Code

TABLE C-2: DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE POLICY, REGULATIONS, AND GUIDANCE

Department of Defense Instructions, Directives and Memorandums
U.S. Department of Defense Instruction (DoDINST) 4001.01 (10 January 08) Installation Support
DoDINST 4150.07 (29 May 08) US Department of Defense (DoD) Pest Management Program
DoDINST 4165.57 (02 May 11) Air Installation Compatible Use Zones
DoDINST 4715.02 (28 August 09) Regional Environmental Coordination
DoDINST 4715.03 (18 March 11) Natural Resources Conservation Program
DoDINST 4715.4 (18 June 96) Pollution Prevention
DoDINST 4715.5 (22 April 96) Management of Environmental Compliance at Overseas Installations
DoDINST 4715.6 (24 April 96) Environmental Compliance
DoDINST 4715.7 (22 April 96) Environmental Restoration Program
DoDINST 4715.9 (03 May 96) Environmental Planning and Analysis
DoDINST 4715.10 (24 April 96) Environmental Education, Training and Career Development
DoDINST 4715.13 (15 November 05) DoD Noise Program
DoDINST 4715.14 (30 November 05) Operational Range Assessments
DoDINST 4715.15 (11 December 06) Environmental Quality Systems
DoDINST 4715.16 (18 September 08) Cultural Resources Management
DoDINST 4715.17 (15 April 09) Environmental Management Systems
DoDINST 5025.01 (28 October 07) DoD Directives Program
DoDINST 6050.05 (15 August 06) DoD Hazard Communication Program
DoDINST 6055.06 (21 December 06) DoD Fire and Emergency Services Program
DoDINST 7000.14 (03 March 03) DoD Financial Management Policy and Procedures
U.S. Department of Defense Directive (DoDDIR) 4705.1 (09 July 92) Management of Land-based Water Resources in Support of Joint Contingency Operations
DoDDIR 4715.1E (19 April 05) Environment, Safety, and Occupational Health
DoDDIR 4715.11 (10 May 04) Environmental and Explosive Safety Management on Operational Ranges within the United States
DoDDIR 4715.12 (12 July 04) Environmental and Explosive Safety Management on DoD Active and Inactive Ranges Outside the United States
DoDDIR 6050.7 (31 March 79) Environmental Effects Abroad of Major DoD Actions
Memorandum of Understanding Among The DoD and The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and The International Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies for a Cooperative Integrated Natural Resource Management Program on Military Installations. 31 January 2006
Memorandum of Understanding to Promote the Conservation of Migratory Birds between the USFWS and the DoD in Accordance with EO 13186. Prepared by the Under Secretary of Defense for Acquisition, Technology, and Logistics in April 2007.
Department of the Navy Manuals, Instructions, and Guidance
Secretary of the Navy Instruction (SECNAVINST) 4000.35. (17 August 92) (NOTAL) Department of the Navy Cultural Resources Program
SECNAVINST 5090.8 (18 December 00) (ASN[I&E]) Policy for Environmental Protection, Natural Resources, and Cultural Resources Program
SECNAVINST 6240.6E. (18 December 00) Implementation of DoD Directives under DoDINST 4700.4
Naval Operations Instruction (OPNAVINST) 4150.07 (29 May 2008) Pest Management Programs
OPNAVINST 5090.1C (18 July 2011) Environmental Readiness Program Manual
OPNAVINST 8000.16 Environmental Security Management
OPNAVINST 8026.2A (15 June 00) Navy Munitions Disposition Policy
OPNAVINST 11000.17 (17 September 99) National Preservation Act Consultations Related to Base Realignment and Closure Actions
OPNAVINST 11010.20F. (07 June 96) Facilities Projects Manual
Naval Facilities Engineering Command (NAVFAC) P-73. (May 87) Real Estate Procedural Manual, Volumes I and II; and Natural Resources Management Procedural Manual, Chapter 2 - Integrated Natural Resources Management Plans
Department of the Navy Manuals, Instructions, and Guidance (Continued)

Naval Facilities Engineering Command Instruction (NAVFACINST) 6250.3H. Applied Biology Program Services and Training
NAVFACINST 11010.45. (30 June 02) Comprehensive Regional Planning Instruction (Land Use Module/RSIP Links)
NAVFACINST 11012.111A Land Use Conservation Planning
NAVFACINST MO-100.4 Guidance on Special Interest Areas
Office of the Assistant Secretary (Installations and Environment) ((Memorandum for Commander Navy Installations Command (CNIC) (N45), Director Environmental Readiness Division (N45), Director Facilities and Services Division (CMC-LFL). Department of the Navy Natural Resources Program Metrics. 22 August 2006
Chief of Naval Operations (CNO) (N45) Integrated Natural Resources Management Program Guidance 10 April 2006 (5090 N456K/6U838101)
CNO (N45) Policy Letter Preventing Feral Cat and Dog Populations on Navy Property 10 January 2002 (5090 Ser N456M/1U595820)
CNO (N45) Navy Environmental Management System (EMS) Policy 06 December 2001 (5090 Ser N451G/1U595831)
Naval Base Ventura County Instructions
Naval Base Ventura County Instruction (NBVCINST)11010.1 Site Approval and Project Review Process (SA/PRB)

Notes:

CNO	Chief of Naval Operations
DoDDIR	US Department of Defense Directive
DoDINST	US Department of Defense Instruction
NAVFACINST	Code of Federal Regulations
NBVCINST	Naval Base Ventura County Instruction
OPNAVINST	Naval Operations Instruction
SECNAVINST	Secretary of the Navy Instruction
Source:	DoD 2011

TABLE C-3: APPLICABLE STATE AND LOCAL REGULATIONS

California State Laws and Regulations	
Water Resources	
California Harbors and Navigation Code (Division 1.5 sections 90-153, Division 2 Section 240-308, Division 3 Sections 650-685, and Division 6 Sections 1690-3980)	
California Water Code Section 1243	
Conservation, Development, and Utilization of State Water Resources (Water Code 10004-10013)	
Lempert-Keene-Seastrand Oil Spill Prevention and Response Act of 1990	
Ocean Use Planning (California Public Resource Code [PRC] 30960)	
Porter-Cologne Water Quality Control Act (California Water Code §§ 13000 <i>et seq.</i>)	
The Safe Drinking Water, Water Quality and Supply, Flood control, River and Coastal Protection Bond Act of 2006 (PRC 75001-75130)	
Watershed, Clean Beaches, and Water Quality Act (PRC 30901-30960)	
Wetlands Mitigation Banking (Fish and Game Code 1850-1852)	
Wetlands Preservation (PRC 5810-5818.2)	
Terrestrial and Aquatic Habitats	
Aquatic Invasive Species (Fish & Game Code 2300-2302)	
Ballast Management for Control of Nonindigenous Species Act of 1999 (PRC 71200-71271)	
California Coastal Act (CCA) of 1972, as amended, and the Federal Coastal Zone Management Program (CZMA) of 1972, (PRC 30000-30900 and 21000-21177)	
California Ocean Protection Act of 2004 (PRC 35500-35650)	
California Marine Life Protection Act (MLPA) (Fish and Game Code 2850-2863)	
California Waterfowl Habitat Program (Fish and Game Code 3460-3467)	
Channel Islands Marine Protected Areas	
Coastal Ecosystems Protection Act of 2006 (PRC 71205.3)	
Conservation and Management of Marine Living Resources (Fish and Game Code 7050-7090)	
Marine Invasive Species Act of 2003 (PRC 71200)	
Marine Managed Areas Improvement Act (PRC 36600-36900)	
Native Plant Protection (Fish and Game Code 1900-1913)	
Native Species Conservation and Enhancement (Fish and Game Code 1750-1772)	
Pesticides and Pest Control Operations (Food and Agriculture Code 6000 <i>et. seq.</i>)	
Wildlife Populations	
Birds (Fish and Game Code 3500-3864)	
California Wildlife Protection Act (Fish and Game Code 2780-2799.6)	
Conservation of Aquatic Resources (Fish and Game Code 1700)	
Conservation of Wildlife Resources (Fish and Game Code 1801-1802)	
Fish (Fish and Game Code 6400-6930)	
Fish and Wildlife Habitat Enhancement Act of 1984 (Fish and Game Code 2600-2651)	
Fish and Wildlife Protection and Conservation (Fish and Game Code 1600-1616)	
Mammals (Fish and Game Code 4150-4904)	
Management of Fish and Wildlife on Military Lands (Fish and Game Code 3450-3453)	
Marine Life Management Act (MLMA) (Fish and Game Code 7050)	
Reptiles and Amphibians (Fish and Game Code 5000-5050)	
Wildlife and Natural Areas Conservation Program (Fish and Game Code 2700-2729)	
Species of Concern	
California Endangered Species Act (CESA) (Fish and Game Code 2050 <i>et. seq.</i>)	

Notes:

PRC

California Public Resource Code

C.2 INTEGRATING OTHER PLANS

The following is a description of relevant plans referenced and considered during the development of this Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP).

Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division Point Mugu Sea Range Environmental Impact Statement/Overseas Environmental Impact Statement. The Point Mugu Sea Range (PMSR) is composed of ocean areas, including surface and subsurface area and military airspace covering 27,278 nm² (93,561 km²). The PMSR includes sophisticated range instrumentation centered on San Nicolas Island (SNI), a Channel Island owned by the Navy. The PMSR also includes extended, over-ocean range areas that are utilized for specialized RDT&E activities. These extended ocean areas cover approximately 221,000 nm² (758,000 km²). The primary mission of PMSR is supporting naval RDT&E activities, while the Southern California (SOCAL) Range Complex is primarily a training range. Notwithstanding, the SOCAL Range Complex supports limited numbers of RDT&E activities, and PMSR supports training events. This Environmental Impact Statement (EIS)/ Overseas Environmental Impact Statement (OEIS) covers all Navy activities on the SOCAL Range Complex (Navy 2002).

California Marine Life Protection Act (MLPA) Master Plan for Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), 2008. In 1999, the legislature approved and the governor signed the MLPA [Stats. 1999, Chapter 1015]. The MLPA required that CDFG develop a Master Plan to guide the adoption and implementation of a Marine Life Protection Program, which includes a statewide network of MPAs. The MLPA identifies a set of goals for the Marine Life Protection Program including: conservation of biological diversity and the health of marine ecosystems; recovery of wildlife populations; improvements to recreational and educational opportunities consistent with biodiversity conservation; protection of representative and unique habitats for their intrinsic value; ensuring that MPAs have defined objectives, effective management and enforcement, and are designed on sound science; and ensuring MPAs are managed, to the extent possible as a network (CDFG 2008).

Western Snowy Plover Recovery Plan, 2007. The Western Snowy Plover Recovery Plan was published in 2007 (USFWS 2007). Recovery objectives in the recovery plan include:

- Achieving well-distributed increases in numbers and productivity of breeding adult birds; and
- Providing for long-term protection of breeding and wintering plovers and their habitat.

Brown Pelican Draft Post-Delisting Monitoring Plan, 2009. The Draft Post-Delisting Monitoring Plan for the Brown Pelican was published in 2009. The purpose of the Draft Plan is to track the status of the brown pelican over time and to verify that the pelican remains secure from risk of extinction after it has been removed from the protections of the Act (USFWS 2009). Post-delisting monitoring as described in the Draft Plan will fulfill the final process in the recovery of the brown pelican (USFWS 2009).

USFWS Five-Year Reviews. Several Five-Year Reviews for federal listed species have been implemented and completed. A five-year review is intended to indicate whether a change in a species listing classification is warranted. Changes in classification recommended in a five-year review could include delisting, reclassification from threatened to endangered (i.e. uplisting), reclassification from endangered to threatened (i.e. downlisting), or no change is warranted at this time. Of the federally listed species that are known to occur on Port Hueneme, two species have recently gone under review. In 2006, the western snowy plover was reviewed with no recommendations made to change its threatened status. In 2009, as a result of five-year review findings, the USFWS published a final rule in the Federal Register (FR) to remove the brown pelican throughout its range from the list of endangered and threatened species.

California Marine Life Management Act Nearshore Fishery Management Plan, 2002.

Through its goals, objectives, policies, and mandates, the Marine Life Management Act (MLMA) provides a general framework for developing a management program for the nearshore finfish fishery. Management objectives and actions identified in the Nearshore Fishery Management Plan address the problems in the nearshore finfish fishery in a way that promotes achieving the goals of the MLMA (CDFG 2002).

California's Ocean Action Plan, 2004. Related to the California Ocean Protection Act, on 18 October 2004, Governor Arnold Schwarzenegger released an ocean action plan, Protecting Our Ocean: California's Action Strategy, with four primary goals:

1. Increase the abundance and diversity of species in California's oceans, bays, estuaries and coastal wetlands;
2. Make water in these bodies cleaner;
3. Provide a marine and estuarine environment that Californians can productively and safely enjoy;
4. Support ocean dependent economic activities.

Part of this ocean action plan is full implementation of the MLPA. Among other policies, the ocean action plan also addresses the relationship between California's management activities and DoD as follows: coordinate California ocean and coastal management activities that impact military facilities/operations with DoD, as well as requesting DoD to coordinate their activities and operational needs with the State of California to the extent possible without compromising national security objectives (CDFG 2008).

Regional Water Quality Control Board's (RWQCB) Los Angeles Basin Plan. The Los Angeles RWQCB Basin Plan is designed to preserve and enhance water quality and protect the beneficial uses of all regional waters. Specifically, the Basin Plan:

- Designates beneficial uses for surface and ground waters;

- Sets narrative and numerical objectives that must be attained or maintained to protect the designated beneficial uses and conform to the state’s anti-degradation policy; and
- Describes implementation programs to protect all waters in the Region.

In addition, the Basin Plan incorporates (by reference) all applicable State and Regional Board plans and policies and other pertinent water quality policies and regulations (Los Angeles RWQCB 1994).

California’s Wildlife Action Plan (WAP), 2007. In 2000, the U.S. Congress enacted the State Wildlife Grants Program to support state programs that broadly benefit wildlife and habitats but particularly “species of greatest conservation need” (Bunn *et al.* 2007). As a requirement for receiving funding under this program, state wildlife agencies were to have submitted a WAP (comprehensive wildlife conservation strategy) to the USFWS in 2005. The CDFG, working in partnership with the Wildlife Health Center at the University of California (UC), Davis, directed the development of the *California Wildlife: Conservation Challenges*, and concomitantly submitted the state’s WAP in 2007 (Bunn *et al.* 2007).

APPENDIX C REFERENCES

- Bunn, D., A. Mummert, M. Hoshovsky, K. Gilardi, and S. Shanks. 2007. California Wildlife: Conservation Challenges, California's Wildlife Action Plan. Prepared by the U.C. Davis Wildlife Health Center for the California Department of Fish and Game, Sacramento, CA.
- California Department of Fish and Game (CDFG). 2002. Nearshore Fishery Management Plan. California Department of Fish and Game, Marine Region. August.
- CDFG. 2008. California Marine Life Protection Act -Master Plan for Marine Protected Areas - Revised Draft January.
- DoD. 2011. Department of Defense Issuances Website.
<http://www.dtic.mil/whs/directives/corres/dir.html>. Accessed September 2011.
- Los Angeles Regional Water Quality Control Board. 1994. Basin Plan for the Coastal Watershed of Los Angeles and Ventura Counties. Los Angeles, CA.
- U.S. Department of the Navy (Navy). 2002. Final Environmental Impact Statement/Overseas Environmental Impact Statement, Point Mugu Sea Range. Prepared by Naval Air Warfare Center Weapons Division. March.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS). 2007. Recovery Plan for the Pacific Coast Population of the Western Snowy Plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*). In two volumes. Sacramento, California. xiv + 751 pages.
- USFWS. 2009. Draft Post-Delisting Monitoring Plan for the Brown Pelican (*Pelecanus occidentalis*). USFWS Ventura Fish and Wildlife Office, Ventura, California. 19 pp.

APPENDIX D
LAND USE AND COVER TYPES AND ACREAGES

TABLE D-1: LAND USE ACREAGES

LAND USE	ACRES
Administration	29.57
Community/Personnel Support	281.77
Natural Resource Management Areas	89.82
Housing	154.27
Logistics	424.32
Operations	276.80
Ordnance	2.40
Public Works	27.64
Training	227.22
TOTAL	1513.81

Note: Acreage noted in the table includes approximately 103 acres of leased lands. Acreage does not include surface water.
Source: NBVC GIS database.

TABLE D-2: LAND COVER AND WATER ACREAGES

Surface	Acres	Land Cover
Building	160.97	Buildings
Dirt	164.35	Exposed Soil
Grass	356.15	Lawn and Non-Native Grass
Paved	827.81	Paved
Water Canal	2.71	Water
Water Harbor	108.73	Water
Water Overflow Pond	2.07	Water
Water Pond	1.60	Water
Water Tidal Channel	2.51	Water
Water Drainage Ditch	5.13	Water
Surface Water Total	122.76	Water
OTHER		
Sand Dollar Beds	0.45	Underwater Beds
Kelp Beds May 2008	3.85	Water
TOTAL	1632.03	

Note: Total acreage does not include sand dollar and kelp beds due to their inclusion in the surface water total.
Source: Tetra Tech GIS databases.

APPENDIX E
NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP PROJECT LIST

Tables E-1, E-2, E-3, and E-4 summarize various aspects of the implementation of this INRMP.

The purpose of [Table E-4](#) is to summarize all the projects or activities that NBVC intends to implement over the duration of the INRMP time frame. Faunal surveys may occur concurrently with surveys at other NBVC installations, as a cost savings effort. [Table E-4](#) is organized according to INRMP management topic. Management strategies presented in Section 3.0 Current Condition and Management of Natural Resources, Section 4.0 Sustainability and Compatible Use, and Section 5.0 Implementation Strategy identify the means by which NBVC intends to achieve desired future conditions. Management actions, such as EPR projects, are specific projects or activities that provide NBVC a mechanism to strive towards achieving those desired future conditions. Individual EPR projects may address multiple management strategies encompassing various INRMP management topics. In order to reduce redundancy, management strategies are incorporated by reference in the "INRMP Management Strategy" column of the table. Management topics that do not appear as a heading in the table are identified in the "INRMP Management Strategy" column numerically and referenced to an EPR project that may encompass several topic areas. Also, management strategies that pertain to special status species have their own sections rather than including special status species management strategies in the broader sections that pertain to wildlife populations. This Implementation Table parallels the structure of the INRMP as presented in Sections 3 through 5, and all INRMP management strategies presented in these Sections are referenced in the "INRMP Management Strategy" column in this table.

Table E-1 identifies the various EPR project codes and descriptions that are referenced in the "EPR Project Code" column of [Table E-4](#); these include the EPR number or placeholder for future EPR projects if appropriate. [Table E-2](#) identifies the applicable funding sources for each project; for more information on funding sources refer to Section 5.5 INRMP Implementation Summary and Schedule. [Table E-3](#) identifies the applicable INRMP legal drivers, or compliance requirements, for all of the various INRMP management projects or activities. All projects listed in [Table E-4](#) support compliance with Naval Operations Instruction (OPNAVINST) 5090.1C and U.S. Department of Defense Instruction (DoDINST) 4715.03, which causes all INRMP management projects to be categorized at a minimum of Budget Priority/Class Level 2.

TABLE E-1: INRMP EPR PROJECT CODES AND DESCRIPTIONS

EPR PROJECT CODE	DESCRIPTION
69232x0102	Revision and Update of Hueneme INRMP and EA
69232x0155	Species Surveys of Hueneme
6923200050	Upland and Wetland Restoration for Hueneme
6923224086	Bio-Security Barge Monitoring
631226xxx37	Wetland Delineation 5-Year Update
0024298019	GIS and Data Management for INRMPS

TABLE E-2: INRMP PROJECT FUNDING SOURCES

FUNDING SOURCES	DESCRIPTION
NBVC ED In House	NBVC natural resource program funding
NBVC Other Navy In House	NBVC Public Works or other NBVC Department or Division funding
O&MN	Operations and Maintenance Navy funding
Navy Tenant	NBVC Naval tenant funding
Naval Air Operations	Naval Air Operations funding
Research Institutions	Research institution, non-governmental organization, or volunteer funding
Project Proponent	Project proponent funding

TABLE E-3: INRMP IMPLEMENTATION TABLE MANAGEMENT PROJECT OR ACTIVITY LEGAL DRIVERS

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
ASBS	Area of Special Biological Significance Requirement
BEPA	Bald Eagle Protection Act
BLM MOU No CA-939-08-02	BLM and U.S Navy Memorandum of Understanding for the California Coastal National Monument
BO 1-8-01-F-14	Biological Opinion for Activities on San Nicolas Island, California
CWA	Clean Water Act
CZMA	Coastal Zone Management Act
EFH	Essential Fish Habitat
EO 11988	Floodplain Management
EO 11514	Protection and Enhancement of Environmental Quality
EO 11990	Protection of Wetlands
EO 11991	Protection and Enhancement of Environmental Quality
EO 12342	Environmental Safeguard for Animal Damage Control on Federal Lands
EO 12962	Recreational Fisheries
EO 13101	Greening the Government Through Waste Prevention, Recycling, and Federal Acquisition
EO 13112	Invasive Species
EO 13123	Greening the Government Through Efficient Energy Management
EO 13148	Greening the Government Through Leadership in Environmental Management

TABLE E-3: INRMP IMPLEMENTATION TABLE MANAGEMENT PROJECT OR ACTIVITY LEGAL DRIVERS (CONTINUED)

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
EO 13158	Marine Protected Areas
EO 13423	Strengthening Federal Environmental, Energy, and Transportation Management
ERL	Environmental Readiness Level
ESA	Endangered Species Act
FNWA	Federal Noxious Weed Act
LRPPA	Legacy Resource Protection Program Act
MBTA	Migratory Bird Treaty Act
MMPA	Marine Mammal Protection Act
NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act
OPNAVINST 5090.1C	Environmental Readiness Program Manual
OPPA	Oil Pollution Prevention Act
RCRA-HSWA	Resource Conservation and Recovery Act - Hazardous and Solid Waste Amendments
SCA	Soil Conservation Act
SAIA	Sikes Act Improvement Act
DoDINST 4715.03	US DOD Natural Resources Conservation Program
DoDINST 6055.06	US DOD Fire and Emergency Services Program
WPFPA	Watershed Protection and Flood Prevention Act

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
<i>Natural Resource Management Objectives and Strategies</i>									
<i>Ecosystem Approach</i>									
Section 1.11	O&MN	69232x0102	INRMP update/revisions and associated EA to incorporate current resources and management knowledge.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	1. INRMP Project Implementation 2. Listed Species and Critical Habitat 3. Partnership Effectiveness 4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 5. Team Adequacy 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
<i>Managing the Physical and Chemical Environment</i>									
<i>Jurisdictional Waters- Wetlands Management</i>									
Section 3.2.3.3	O&MN	631226xxx37	Maintain a current inventory of wetlands by conducting surveys of jurisdictional boundaries, and making associated updates to GIS database, to support planning and management efforts to achieve no net loss of wetlands.	4	SAIA, CWA, CZMA, ASBS, EO 11990	Five Years	2011, 2016	6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 3.2.3.3	O&MN	6923200050	Enhance and increase native vegetative buffers around wetlands by conducting invasive plant control and native plant restoration.	4	SAIA, CWA, EO 11990	Annual	2011 - 2016	6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
<i>Management of Ecosystems</i>									
<i>Coastal and Marine Communities</i>									
<i>Marine Subtidal</i>									
Section 3.3.1.1	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Maintain current inventory and GIS shapefile of kelp bed distribution.	4	SAIA, CZMA, ESA, CWA, ASBS	Annual	2011 - 2016	6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Section 3.3.1.1	NBVC ED In-house Research Institutions	N/A	Support potential research of harbor waters to identify suitable locations for eelgrass or oyster bed restoration.	4	SAIA, CZMA, ESA, CWA, EFH, ASBS	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012) (CONTINUED)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
<i>Sandy Beach</i>									
Section 3.3.1.2	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Monitor beach for habitat loss; if being reduced, restore if feasible.	4	SAIA, CZMA, CWA, ASBS	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
<i>Terrestrial Communities</i>									
<i>Dune Mat</i>									
Section 3.3.2.1	O&MN	6923200050	Protect and enhance native dune species cover and diversity by conducting invasive plant removal and native revegetation.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
<i>Coyote Brush Scrub</i>									
Section 3.3.2.2	O&MN	6923200050	Conduct restoration and enhancement of this habitat type, as described in the Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat Restoration Plan (TEC 2003).	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
<i>Non-Native Annual Grassland</i>									
Section 3.3.2.3	O&MN	6923200050	Enhance native diversity of this habitat type by replacing non-natives with appropriate native plants.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
<i>Arroyo Willow Thickets and Drainage Channels</i>									
Section 3.3.2.4	O&MN	6923200050	Conduct restoration and enhancement of this habitat type, as described in the Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat Restoration Plan (TEC 2003).	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
<i>Fish and Wildlife Management</i>									
<i>Terrestrial Invertebrates</i>									
Section 3.4.1	O&MN	69232x0155	Conduct surveys of terrestrial invertebrates across all habitat types at Port Hueneme.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012) (CONTINUED)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
Pollinators									
Section 3.4.2	O&MN	69232x0155	Inventory insect and pollinator populations.	4	SAIA	Five Years		4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 3.4.2	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Develop BMPs specific to pollinators, to ensure pollinator species are not adversely affected by base activities.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 3.4.2	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Develop and distribute outreach and education materials on pollinators.	4	SAIA	Five Years		4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use	
Section 3.4.2	O&MN	6923200050	Control the spread of invasive species.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 3.4.2	O&MN	6923200050	Revegetate with native species contained on the NBVC Landscape Plant Selection Guide–Approved Plant List.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 3.4.2	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Develop and implement management program that supports bee relocation as opposed to bee eradication.	4	SAIA	Five Years		4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Reptiles and Amphibians									
Section 3.4.3	O&MN	69232x0155	Conduct surveys of reptiles and amphibians across all habitat types at Port Hueneme.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012) (CONTINUED)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
Birds									
Section 3.4.4	O&MN and NBVC ED in-house support	69232x0155	Conduct regular program of migratory and resident bird monitoring within all habitat types at Port Hueneme.	4	SAIA, MBTA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 3.4.4	O&MN	6923200050	Protect birds and their habitat throughout the base from human induced disturbance and invasive species.	4	SAIA, MBTA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Mammals									
Section 3.4.5	O&MN	69232x0155	Conduct surveys of mammals throughout the base.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Aquatic Invertebrates									
Section 3.4.6	O&MN	69232x0155	Conduct surveys of aquatic invertebrates across marine and wetland habitats on base.	4	SAIA, ASBS	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Fish									
Section 3.4.7	O&MN	69232x0155	Conduct fish surveys in shallow water and subtidal habitats across the base.	4	SAIA, ASBS, EFH	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Marine Mammals									
Section 3.4.8	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Conduct surveys to monitor marine mammal populations and evaluate interactions with base activities.	4	SAIA, MMPA, ESA, EFH, CZMA	Annual	2011 - 2016	2. Listed Species and Critical Habitat 4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Federally Listed and Special Status Species									
Section 3.5.1	O&MN and NBVC ED In-house	69232x0155	Conduct surveys to track occurrence, abundance and seasonal patterns of federally listed and special status species within the base and harbor.	4	SAIA, ESA, MMPA, CZMA, ASBS	Annual	2011 - 2016	2. Listed Species and Critical Habitat 4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012) (CONTINUED)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
<i>Invasive Species Management</i>									
<i>Terrestrial Invasives</i>									
Section 3.6.1	O&MN	6923224086	Implement prevention, detection and eradication practices outlined in the SNI BioSecurity Plan, as applies to activities at NBVC Port Hueneme.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 3.6.1	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Develop and implement an Invasive Species Management Plan that includes protocols and capabilities for prevention, early detection and rapid response of terrestrial plants and animals, including invertebrates.	4	SAIA, EO 13112, FNWA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 3.6.1	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Inventory, map and prioritize for removal, terrestrial invasive species. Promote cooperative interagency efforts to collect and analyze monitoring data.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 3.6.1	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Promote awareness of threats and pathways of terrestrial invasive spread to military and civilian personnel.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use	
<i>Aquatic Invasives</i>									
Section 3.6.2	O&MN	69232x0155 6923200050	Implement prevention, detection and eradication practices.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Section 3.6.2	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Develop and implement an Invasive Species Management Plan that includes protocols and capabilities for prevention, early detection and rapid response of aquatic plants and animals, including invertebrates.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Section 3.6.2	O&MN and NBVC ED In-house	69232x0155 6923200050	Inventory, map and prioritize for removal, aquatic invasive species. Promote cooperative interagency efforts to collect and analyze monitoring data within harbor waters.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012) (CONTINUED)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
Section 3.6.2	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Promote awareness of threats and pathways of aquatic invasive spread to military and civilian personnel.	4	SAIA, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Natural Resources Law Enforcement									
Section 3.7	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Provide information and education for the enforcement of natural resource laws, regulations, and special habitat closures, by professionally trained personnel.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use	
Data Integration, Access, and Reporting									
Section 3.8	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Set up a central clearinghouse for data, reports and publications pertaining to NBVC's EMS, that addresses natural resources and is accessible to staff.	4	SAIA, EO13101	Annual	2011 - 2016	1. INRMP Project Implementation 4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use	
Section 3.8	NBVC ED In-house and O&MN	0024298019	Develop and maintain NBVC Port Hueneme's data management capabilities, including GIS.	4	SAIA, EO13101	Annual	2011 - 2016	1. INRMP Project Implementation 4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use	
Sustainability of the Military Mission and Compatible Use									
Integrated Military Mission and Sustainable Land Use Decisions/Operations Planning and Review									
Section 4.1	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Maintain habitats using principles of ecosystem management and sustainability and continue to use NEPA documentation.	4	SAIA, NEPA, EO 13148, EO 11514, EO 11991, EO 11988, EO 13158, EO 11990	Annual	2011 - 2016	1. INRMP Project Implementation 2. Listed Species and Critical Habitat 3. Partnership Effectiveness 4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 5. Team Adequacy 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Sustainability in the Built Environment									
Section 4.2	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Participate in sustainable design criteria for Navy staff including engineers, water quality specialists, construction and design specialists to help design enhance existing or new natural resources.	4	SAIA	Five Years	2011-2016	6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012) (CONTINUED)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
Environmental Awareness									
Section 4.1	NBVC ED In-House	N/A	Develop and distribute educational materials (brochures) to new Navy and civilian staff, contractors, and lessees that cover the following topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MBTA and protocol for protection of nesting birds and removal of trapped birds and wildlife. • MMPA regulations and protections for marine mammals and their haulouts used at Port Hueneme. • Invasive aquatic and terrestrial species threats and pathways of spread. • ESA and legal protections afforded to any listed species that may occur at Port Hueneme. 	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	1. INRMP Project Implementation 2. Listed Species and Critical Habitat 3. Partnership Effectiveness	
Beneficial Partnerships and Collaborative Resources Planning									
Section 4.4	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Participate in regional conservation, ecosystem and invasive species planning in collaboration with other government agencies.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	1. INRMP Project Implementation 2. Listed Species and Critical Habitat 3. Partnership Effectiveness	
Section 4.4	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Coordinate with USFWS and CDFG at least annually to fulfill SAIA provisions and related inter-agency cooperative agreements.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	1. INRMP Project Implementation 2. Listed Species and Critical Habitat 3. Partnership Effectiveness 4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 5. Team Adequacy 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Section 4.4	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Foster relationships with university research programs to increase knowledge base of Port Hueneme natural resources.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	1. INRMP Project Implementation 3. Partnership Effectiveness	

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012) (CONTINUED)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
Regulatory Compliance									
Section 4.5	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Define and identify measures for "no net loss" of military value and seek agreement among resource and regulatory agencies on these measures during INRMP planning updates, NEPA review, and ESA consultations.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Section 4.5	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Continue to participate in the SA/PRB process and update the Site Approval Checklist to ensure consideration of all issues.	4	SAIA, NEPA, EO 11514	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Section 4.5	NBVC ED In-house Project Proponent	N/A	Monitor implementation of conservation measures proposed in NEPA, consultation and permit documents.	4	SAIA, NEPA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Section 4.5	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Develop and maintain a reference catalog of past avoidance, mitigation, and compensatory measures that have been used, and a system for ongoing evaluation of their effectiveness, to effectively track success of measures employed.	4	SAIA, NEPA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Section 4.5	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Catalog and track mitigation sites by maintaining records of all mitigation sites and the status and phases of each.	4	SAIA, NEPA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Consistency with Other Plans									
Section 4.7	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Collaborate on regional plans that may have an impact on natural resources of Port Hueneme.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	3. Partnership Effectiveness 6. Ecosystem Integrity	

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012) (CONTINUED)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
Consistency with Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan									
Section 4.7.1	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Continue to participate in the SA/PRB and coordinate with the Cultural Resources program when planning natural resources management activities.	4	SAIA, NEPA, EO 11514	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Remediation of Contaminated Media									
Section 4.8	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Coordinate with CERCLA program to ensure goals of CERCLA are aligned with the goals stated within this INRMP, and promote sharing of biological data between base biologists and CERCLA.	4	SAIA, RCRA-HSWA, EO13101, ASBS	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Oil Spill and Hazardous Substance Prevention and Cleanup									
Section 4.9	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Integrate the protection priorities of this INRMP into the Emergency Response Action Plan and the Integrated Contingency Plan for Oil and Hazardous Substance Spill Prevention and Response.	4	SAIA, OPPIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Section 4.9	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Maintain a current GIS database of natural resources, to support preparedness and response planning.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use	
Landscaping and Grounds Maintenance									
Section 4.12	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Continually update the NBVC Landscape Plant Selection Guide—Approved Plant List to reflect changes in regional invasive species lists.	4	SAIA, EO13148, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 4.12	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Coordinate with NBVC PW groundskeeping crew to communicate and ensure mowing, use of rodenticides and herbicides is in compliance with cultural and environmental laws, EOs and Navy policies.	4	SAIA, EO13148, EO 13112	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012) (CONTINUED)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
Leases and Real Estate Outgrants									
Section 4.13	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Coordinate with lessees to ensure that all activities of lessees are in accordance with federal environmental regulations, EOs and guidance outlined in this INRMP.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	
Recreation and Public Access									
Section 4.14	O&MN	6923200050	Coordinate with MWR to identify areas within golf course suitable for native plant installation. Implement native plant installation.	4	SAIA, EO 12962	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 6. Ecosystem Integrity	
Section 4.14	O&MN	6923200050	Install interpretive signage along natural areas and in created native vegetated islands that informs on native plants and pollinator species, and sustainable landscape design.	4	SAIA, EO 12962	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use	
Public Outreach									
Section 4.15	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Identify natural resource themes for public outreach. Participate in Earth Day and annual science festivals that occur in adjacent communities.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	3. Partnership Effectiveness 4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use	

TABLE E-4: NBVC PORT HUENEME INRMP IMPLEMENTATION SUMMARY, INCLUDING THE ASSIGNMENT OF PRIORITIES BASED ON LEGAL DRIVER BEHIND EACH PROJECT (MARCH 2012) (CONTINUED)

INRMP Management Strategy	Funding Source	EPR Project Code	Project Description	ERL	Legal Driver	Implementation		Natural Resources Metrics Focus Areas	Cost Estimate
						Frequency	Year		
<i>Implementation Strategy</i>									
<i>Staffing</i>									
Section 5.1.4	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Maintain staff knowledge of management strategies through training and participation in or hosting workshops, research presentations, and other activities of regional, interstate, and international professional natural resources research and conservation programs.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use	
<i>Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review and Metrics</i>									
Section 5.2	NBVC ED In-house	N/A	Monitor the progress of each of the strategies outlined in this INRMP, by maintaining an updated GIS and coordinating and conducting annual metrics reviews.	4	SAIA	Annual	2011 - 2016	1. INRMP Project Implementation 2. Listed Species and Critical Habitat 3. Partnership Effectiveness 4. Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use 5. Team Adequacy 6. Ecosystem Integrity 7. INRMP Impact on Installation Mission	

Notes: ED Environmental Department
 EPR Environmental Program Requirements
 ERL Environmental Readiness Level
 N/A Not Applicable
 O&MN Operations and Maintenance Navy funding
 SAIA Sikes Act Improvement Act

APPENDIX F
MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING

**MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
AMONG
THE U.S. DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE
AND
THE U.S. FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
AND
THE INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF FISH AND WILDLIFE AGENCIES
FOR A
COOPERATIVE INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PROGRAM
ON MILITARY INSTALLATIONS**

A. PURPOSE

The purpose of this Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) is to establish a cooperative relationship between the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD), the U.S. Department of the Interior, Fish and Wildlife Service (FWS), and the State fish and wildlife agencies as represented by the International Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies (IAFWA) in preparing, reviewing, and implementing integrated natural resource management plans (INRMPs) on military installations.

B. BACKGROUND

In recognition that military lands have significant natural resources, Congress enacted the Sikes Act in 1960 to address wildlife conservation and public access on military installations. The 1997 amendments to the Sikes Act require the DoD to develop and implement an INRMP for each military installation with significant natural resources. The INRMP must be prepared in cooperation with the FWS and the State fish and wildlife agency (States) and reflect the mutual agreement of the parties concerning conservation, protection, and management of fish and wildlife resources on military lands.

INRMPs provide for the management of natural resources, including fish, wildlife, and plants. They incorporate, to the maximum extent practicable, ecosystem management principles and provide the landscape necessary for the sustainment of military land uses. INRMPs allow for multipurpose uses of resources, including public access necessary and appropriate for those uses, provided such access does not conflict with military land use requirements. Effective partnering among the DoD, the FWS, and the States, initiated early in the planning process at national, regional, and the military installation levels, is essential to the development and implementation of comprehensive INRMPs. When such partnering involves the participation of all parties and synchronization of INRMPs with existing FWS and State natural resource management plans, the mutual agreement of all parties is achieved more easily. Consistent with the use of military installations to ensure the readiness of the Armed Forces, the purpose of INRMPs is to provide for the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military lands. Thus, a clear understanding of land use objectives for military lands should enable DoD, the FWS, and the States to share a common understanding of land management requirements while preparing and reviewing INRMPs.

This MOU addresses the responsibilities of the Parties to facilitate optimum management of natural resources on military installations. It replaces a DoD-FWS MOU on "Ecosystem-based Management of Fish, Wildlife and Plant Resources on Military Lands" which expired May 17, 2004.

C. AUTHORITIES

This MOU is established under the authority of the Sikes Act, as amended, 16 U.S.C. 670a-670f, which requires the Secretary of Defense to carry out a program to provide for the conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources on military installations in cooperation with the FWS and the State fish and wildlife agencies. The DoD's primary mission is national defense. DoD manages approximately 30 million acres of land and waters under the Sikes Act to conserve and protect biological resources while supporting sustained military land use.

The FWS manages approximately 96 million acres of the National Wildlife Refuge System, and administers numerous fish and wildlife conservation and management statutes and authorities, including: the Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act, the Migratory Bird Treaty Act of 1918, the Endangered Species Act, the Marine Mammal Protection Act, the Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act, the Anadromous Fish Conservation Act, the Nonindigenous Aquatic Nuisance Prevention and Control Act of 1990, the Federal Noxious Weed Act, the Alien Species Prevention Enforcement Act of 1992, the North American Wetland Conservation Act, and the Coastal Barrier Resources Act.

The States in general possess broad trustee and police powers over fish and wildlife within their borders, including – absent a clear expression of Congress' intent to the contrary – fish and wildlife on Federal lands within their borders. Where Congress has given Federal agencies certain conservation responsibilities, such as for migratory birds or species listed as threatened or endangered under the Endangered Species Act, the States, in most cases, have cooperative management jurisdiction.

The Sikes Act (16 U.S.C. 670c-1) allows the Secretary of a military department to enter into cooperative agreements with States, local governments, nongovernmental organizations, and individuals to provide for the maintenance and improvement of natural resources, or to benefit *natural and cultural resources research, on DoD installations.*

The Sikes Act (16 U.S.C. 670f(b)) also encourages the Secretary of Defense, to the greatest extent practicable, to enter into agreements to use the services, personnel, equipment, and facilities, with or without reimbursement, of the Secretary of the Interior in carrying out the provisions of this section.

The Economy Act (31 U.S.C. 1535 and 1536) allows a Federal agency to enter into an agreement with another Federal agency for services, when those services can be rendered in a more convenient and cost effective manner by another Federal agency.

The Intergovernmental Cooperation Act of 1968 (P.L. 90-577 (82 Stat. 1098)) allows the "improvement of the administration of grants-in-aid to the States, to permit provision of reimbursable technical services to State and local government.

D. RESPONSIBILITIES

The Parties to this agreement hereby enter into a cooperative program of INRMP development and implementation with mutually agreed-upon fish and wildlife conservation objectives to satisfy the goals of the Sikes Act.

1. **The DoD, the FWS and IAFWA (the Parties) mutually agree, in accordance with all applicable Federal, State and local laws and regulations:**
 - a. To meet at least annually to discuss implementation of this MOU. The DoD will coordinate the annual meeting and any other meetings related to this MOU. Proposed amendments to the MOU should be presented in writing to the parties at least 15 days prior to the annual meeting. The terms of this MOU and any proposed amendments may be reviewed at the annual meeting. The meeting may also review mutual Sikes Act accomplishments, research and technology needs, and other emerging issues.
 - b. To establish a Sikes Act Tripartite Working Group consisting of representatives from the Parties. This Working Group will meet at least quarterly to discuss and develop projects and documents to assist in the preparation and implementation of INRMPs and to discuss Sikes Act issues of national importance.
 - c. The Sikes Act Tripartite Working Group will encourage the establishment of INRMP Development and Implementation Teams to facilitate early communication during preparation, review, revision or implementation of an INRMP and to ensure that such INRMPs are comprehensive and implemented as mutually agreed.
 - d. Supplemental Sikes Act MOUs or other agreements may be developed at the regional and/or State level.
 - e. To recognize the current DoD and FWS Sikes Act Guidelines on <http://www.fws.gov> and <http://www.denix.osd.mil> as the guidance for communication and cooperation of the Parties represented by this MOU.
 - f. That none of the Parties to the MOU is relinquishing any authority, responsibility, or duty as required by law, regulation, policy, or directive.

- g. To engage in sound management practices for natural resource protection and management pursuant to this MOU with due regard for military readiness, the welfare of the public, native fish and wildlife, threatened and endangered species, and the environment.
- h. Consistent with DoD's primary military mission and to the extent reasonably practicable, to promote the sustainable multipurpose use of natural resources on military installations, to include hunting, fishing, trapping, and nonconsumptive uses such as wildlife viewing, boating, and camping.
- i. To designate the individuals listed below as the national representative from each signatory to participate in the activities pursuant to this MOU. Representatives may also be designated at the regional and local levels to participate in similar Sikes Act planning or coordination activities.
 - i. DoD: Conservation Team Leader, ODUSD (I&E) EM, 1225 Clark Street Suite 1500, Arlington, VA 22202-4336
 - ii. FWS: National Sikes Act Coordinator, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, 4401 North Fairfax Drive, Room 400, Arlington, VA 22203.
 - iii. IAFWA: Executive Vice-President, IAFWA, 444 North Capitol Street, NW, Suite 544, Washington, DC 20001.

2. DoD agrees to:

- a. Communicate the establishment of this MOU to all DoD Components.
- b. Take the lead in the development of policies related to INRMP development and implementation and seek the cooperation of the FWS and the State fish and wildlife agencies during development, review, and implementation.
- c. Ensure distribution of the DoD and revised FWS Sikes Act Guidelines to all appropriate DoD offices at every level of command.
- d. Encourage military installations to invite appropriate FWS and State fish and wildlife agency offices to participate in developing and updating the INRMPs. All such invitations should be extended well in advance of the needed date for the product or work in order to facilitate meaningful participation by all three Parties.
- e. Encourage military installations to take advantage of FWS and State fish and wildlife agency natural resources expertise through the use of Economy Act transfers and cooperative agreements. Priority should be given to projects that:

- i. Sustain the military mission;
 - ii. Consider the strategic planning priorities of the FWS and the State fish and wildlife agency; and
 - iii. Effectively apply the principles of ecosystem management.
- f. Encourage military installation to identify INRMP project requirements and give priority to those that:
 - i. Ensure conservation of natural resources while sustaining military mission activities;
 - ii. Achieve compliance with Federal, State, and local laws; and
 - iii. Provide adequate staffing for the development and implementation of the INRMP.
- g. Discuss with the FWS and the State fish and wildlife agencies all issues of mutual interest related to the protection, conservation, and management of fish and wildlife resources on DoD installations, and obtain the mutual agreement of the FWS and the States regarding all INRMP provisions related to activities within their legal jurisdiction.
- h. Subject to mission, safety and security requirements, provide public access to military installations to facilitate the sustainable multipurpose use of its natural resources.
- i. Identify DoD natural resource research needs, and develop research proposals with input from FWS and/or the IAFWA.
- j. Encourage the Military Services to establish natural resources management liaisons to facilitate:
 - i. Coordination and mutual agreement of INRMPs;
 - ii. Development and implementation of cooperative regional and local natural resource conservation partnerships and conservation initiatives with FWS and State fish and wildlife agency offices; and
 - iii. Natural resources conservation technology transfer and training initiatives between the Military Services, Federal land management agencies, and State fish and wildlife agencies.

3. FWS agrees to:

- a. Communicate the establishment of this MOU to each FWS Regional Office and appropriate field stations in close proximity to military installations.
- b. Distribute the DoD and revised FWS Sikes Act Guidelines to each FWS Regional Office and appropriate field station in close proximity to military installations.
- c. Designate regional and field station FWS liaisons to develop partnerships and assist the DoD in implementing joint management of ecosystem-based natural resource management programs.
- d. Identify FWS personnel needs for the development, review, updating, and implementation of INRMPs and expedite the fulfillment of those needs, as appropriate, based on funding and FWS priorities.
- e. Provide technical assistance to the DoD in managing Federal trust resources such as endangered species, migratory birds, interjurisdictional fisheries, invasive species, contaminants, wetlands, coastal resources, law enforcement, or other natural resource issues within the scope of FWS responsibilities, funding constraints and expertise.
- f. Work with the DoD to coordinate military natural resource research efforts and the creation of a consolidated source of information, with a particular emphasis on research on listed species and species at-risk.
- g. Disseminate upcoming proposed listing and critical habitat designations to DoD Headquarters offices and potentially affected installations as part of outreach efforts before the Federal Register publication of such proposed designations.
- h. Provide law enforcement support to protect fish, wildlife and plant resources on military installations within the jurisdiction of the FWS.

4. IAFWA agrees to:

- a. Communicate the establishment of this MOU to each State fish and wildlife agency director and appropriate field offices.
- b. Distribute the DoD and revised FWS Sikes Act Guidelines to each State fish and wildlife agency director and appropriate field offices.
- c. Facilitate and coordinate with the States to encourage them to:

- i. Participate in the development, review, updating and implementation of INRMPs upon request of military installations.
- ii. Designate State liaisons to assist in developing partnerships and to assist the DoD in implementing natural resource conservation and management programs.
- iii. Identify State wildlife management areas in close proximity to military installations and, where appropriate, participate in the joint management of ecosystem-based natural resource management projects.
- iv. Provide technical assistance to the DoD in managing natural resource issues such as endangered species, migratory birds, interjurisdictional fisheries, invasive species, contaminants, wetlands, coastal resources, law enforcement, outdoor recreation, or other natural resource issues within the scope of State responsibility and expertise.
- v. Identify State personnel needs for the development, review and implementation of INRMPs and expedite the fulfillment of these needs as appropriate based on available funding and State priorities.
- vi. Coordinate current and proposed State natural resource research efforts with those that may relate to DoD installations.
- vii. Coordinate with DoD installations in development of comprehensive state wildlife conservation plans.

E. STATEMENT OF NO FINANCIAL OBLIGATION

This MOU does not impose any financial obligation on the part of any signatory.

F. ESTABLISHMENT OF COOPERATIVE AGREEMENTS

The Parties are encouraged to enter into cooperative agreements to coordinate and implement natural resource management on military installations. If fiscal resources are to be transferred in support of this MOU, the Parties must develop a separately funded cooperative agreement. Such cooperative agreements may be entered into under the authorities of the Sikes Act (16 U.S.C. 670a-670f, as amended) and the Economy Act (31 U.S.C. 1535 and 1536). Each funded cooperative agreement shall include a work plan and a financial plan that identify goals, objectives, and a budget and payment schedule. A cooperative agreement to accomplish a study or research also will include a study design and methodology in the work plan. It is understood and agreed that any monies allocated via these cooperative agreements shall be expended in accordance with its terms and in the manner prescribed by the fiscal regulations and/or administrative policies of the party making the funds available.

APPENDIX G
BIOLOGICAL SURVEYS

TABLE OF CONTENTS

WILDLIFE SURVEY REPORT AND HABITAT AND RESTORATION PLAN

WILDLIFE SURVEYS AT CBC PORT HUENEME AND NAS POINT MUGU – FINAL REPORT

MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES ASSESSMENT FOR THE PORT HUENEME SEDIMENT DREDGING AND CONFINED AQUATIC DISPOSAL PROJECT

BIOLOGICAL PRE-CONSTRUCTION SURVEY AND ASSESSMENT – AOC 17 – SOIL REMOVAL

WILDLIFE SURVEY REPORT AND HABITAT AND RESTORATION PLAN

WILDLIFE SURVEY REPORT AND HABITAT AND RESTORATION PLAN

Naval Base Ventura County
Port Hueneme Site, California

October 2003

Acronyms and Abbreviations

CalEPPC	California Exotic Pest Plant Council
CDFG	California Department of Fish and Game
cm	centimeter(s)
ft	foot/feet
ha	hectare(s)
IRMP	Integrated Cultural and Natural Resource Management Plan
m	meter(s)
NBVC	Naval Base Ventura County
SINA	Special Interest Natural Area
TEC	The Environmental Company, Inc.
USFWS	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

**WILDLIFE SURVEY REPORT AND
HABITAT PROTECTION & RESTORATION PLAN
NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY, PORT HUENEME SITE**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Acronyms and Abbreviations	Inside Front Cover
1.0 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 WILDLIFE SURVEY REPORT.....	1
1.1.1 Goals and Objectives	1
1.2 HABITAT PROTECTION AND RESTORATION PLAN.....	4
1.2.1 Goals and Objectives	4
2.0 ECOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS	5
2.1 ECOLOGICAL SETTING.....	5
2.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE SINAS	5
2.2.1 SINA A: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat	5
2.2.2 SINA B: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat	6
2.2.3 SINA C: Coyote Brush Habitat.....	7
2.2.4 SINA D: Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage and Sandy Beach Habitat.....	8
3.0 IMPLEMENTATION OF HABITAT RESTORATION PLAN.....	11
3.1 GENERAL RESTORATION APPROACH AND GUIDELINES	11
3.1.1 Exotics Control.....	11
3.1.2 Revegetation	11
3.1.3 Habitat Protection.....	12
3.2 SINA A: BULRUSH-CATTAIL HABITAT	12
3.2.1 Exotics Control.....	12
3.2.2 Revegetation	13
3.2.3 Habitat Protection.....	13
3.3 SINA B: BULRUSH-CATTAIL HABITAT	14
3.3.1 Exotics Control.....	14
3.3.2 Revegetation	14
3.3.3 Habitat Protection.....	15
3.4 SINA C: COYOTE BRUSH HABITAT.....	15
3.4.1 Exotics Control.....	15
3.4.2 Revegetation	15
3.4.3 Habitat Protection.....	15
3.5 SINA D: SAND VERBENA-BEACH BURSAGE AND SANDY BEACH HABITAT.....	16
3.5.1 Exotics Control.....	16
3.5.2 Revegetation	16
3.5.3 Habitat Protection.....	16
4.0 MONITORING AND MAINTENANCE.....	17
4.1 WILDLIFE SURVEYS	17
4.2 HABITAT RESTORATION PLAN.....	17
4.2.1 Performance Criteria	17

4.2.2 Monitoring Activities 18

4.2.3 Maintenance and Remedial Measures 18

4.2.4 Restoration Program Schedule..... 19

5.0 REFERENCES.....21

6.0 PREPARERS.....23

**APPENDIX A: Photos of Seabee Earthmoving Training Area and Special Interest Natural Areas,
NBVC Port Hueneme**

APPENDIX B: Wildlife Species Observed at NBVC Port Hueneme

List of Figures

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1 Regional Location, NBVC Port Hueneme	2
2 SINAs and Historical Burrowing Owl Occurrence.....	3

List of Tables

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1 Occurrence of Non-Native Species and Suggested Native Species for Revegetation in SINAs, NBVC Port Hueneme.....	12
2 Suggested Seed Mix Prescription for SINA C	15
3 Preliminary Seed Mix Prescription for SINA D.....	16

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1 This Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan have been prepared for the
2 Environmental Division, Naval Base Ventura County, Port Hueneme Site (NBVC Port Hueneme).
3 NBVC Port Hueneme is located on the coast of Ventura County, California, adjacent to the cities of Port
4 Hueneme and Oxnard (Figure 1). Both the report and plan were developed to implement
5 recommendations provided in the Integrated Cultural and Natural Resource Management Plan (IRMP) for
6 the site (U.S. Navy 1999).

7 1.1 WILDLIFE SURVEY REPORT

8 1.1.1 Goals and Objectives

9 During biological surveys associated with the preparation of the IRMP for NBVC Port Hueneme,
10 biologists observed a burrowing owl (*Athene cunicularia*) and burrows within the Seabee Earthmoving
11 Training Area (Figure 2) (U.S. Navy 1999). Although not listed as threatened or endangered, the
12 burrowing owl has been declining across much of its range in western North America and is considered a
13 Species of Concern by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS), California Department of Fish and
14 Game (CDFG), and U.S. Navy (U.S. Navy 1999, CDFG 2003). Due to this decline and the potential for
15 NBVC to support burrowing owls, the IRMP recommended that an adaptive management plan for
16 burrowing owls be prepared for NBVC Port Hueneme. Originally the objectives of the plan included:

- 17 • develop land use practices that are conducive to protection of the species on base;
- 18 • limit control of ground squirrels on base because of the habitat this species creates for the owls;
- 19 • develop interim protection measures;
- 20 • develop educational materials for base personnel to recognize the owls and minimize disturbance
21 to them.

22 However, recent wildlife surveys at NBVC Port Hueneme specifically targeting the burrowing owl and
23 the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area failed to find any burrowing owls or associated sign (e.g.,
24 feathers, pellets) (TEC 2002, 2003). In addition, those areas of the base (e.g., the golf course) that
25 support California ground squirrels (*Spermophilus beecheyi*), which are the primary providers of burrows
26 for the owl, were also surveyed and neither burrowing owls nor sign were observed. Therefore, since the
27 preparation of a management plan for a species that did not occur on NBVC was impractical and would
28 not serve the environmental protection needs of NBVC Port Hueneme, Environmental Division, decided
29 that a general, wildlife survey of NBVC Port Hueneme would be appropriate and useful, especially when
30 combined with the Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan.

31 The goal of the Wildlife Survey Report is to provide a list and discussion of wildlife species (primarily
32 birds) that are present on NBVC Port Hueneme. For the purposes of this report, wildlife includes
33 amphibians, reptiles, birds, and mammals. Surveys will focus on the Special Interest Natural Areas
34 (SINAs) for which a Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan is currently being prepared (part of this
35 document). The objectives of the wildlife survey report are to:

- 36 • determine which species are present within NBVC Port Hueneme with an emphasis on the 4
37 SINAs;
- 38 • provide the seasonal occurrence of resident and migratory bird species within the SINAs and
39 NBVC Port Hueneme in general;
- 40 • provide management recommendations for the protection, management, and enhancement of
41 wildlife at the SINAs in coordination with the habitat restoration plan; and

Figure 1
Regional Location
NBVC Port Hueneme

Figure 2
SINAs an Historical Burrowing Owl Occurrence

- 1 • recommend when, where, and how often wildlife surveys should be conducted on NBVC Port
2 Hueneme to maintain the wildlife occurrence database.

3 **1.2 HABITAT PROTECTION AND RESTORATION PLAN**

4 **1.2.1 Goals and Objectives**

5 For the Habitat Protection and Restoration Plan, 4 SINAs have been identified for protection and
6 enhancement of natural resources. These areas include 2 freshwater marsh habitats with bulrushes and
7 cattails, a coyote brush habitat, and a foredune and coastal strand habitat with sand verbena (*Abronia*
8 *maritima*) and beach-bur (*Ambrosia chamissonis*).

9 The primary management goal for the 4 natural areas is to preserve, protect, and enhance the ecological
10 integrity of the habitats, including, but not limited to, the structure and function of these natural habitats.
11 The aim is to maintain and/or improve the physical and biological characteristics of the habitats, so that
12 the 4 natural areas have healthy and self-sustaining native plant communities and associated wildlife
13 populations.

14 Specific objectives related to the habitat protection and restoration goals include the following.

- 15 • Ensure that the 4 SINAs are relatively free of exotic species, and are not at risk from invasion by
16 such species from surrounding areas.
17 • Enhance native vegetation within the SINAs by seeding and planting native plant species, as
18 appropriate to these habitats.
19 • Ensure the continued stability of the soil in the SINAs and minimize erosion by wind or water.
20 • Protect the habitats from adverse impacts resulting from vehicle or foot traffic, while concurrently
21 providing opportunities for passive recreation in designated appropriate locations.

22 This document first defines the goals and objectives of habitat protection and restoration, and then
23 presents background information regarding the Port Hueneme site including its ecological setting, the
24 nature of threats and disturbances, and existing botanical resources. The plan then describes site-specific
25 restoration procedures for the 4 SINAs, including exotics control, revegetation, and habitat protection, as
26 appropriate. Monitoring and maintenance activities for the 4 areas include a discussion of performance
27 criteria, monitoring methods, and maintenance and remedial measures. Finally, timing and scheduling
28 issues are discussed for the protection and restoration program. Plant species nomenclature follows
29 Hickman (1993). Names and descriptions of vegetation communities follow Holland (1986) and Sawyer
30 and Keeler-Wolf (1995); some common names follow Smith (1998).

2.0 ECOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

2.1 ECOLOGICAL SETTING

The NBVC Port Hueneme site lies on the southern California coast, on a flat coastal plain south of the Santa Clara River in the Ventura Basin (Figure 1). Topography at the site slopes gently from the northeast, at 25 to 30 feet (ft) (9 meters [m]) above mean sea level, to the southwest, towards the Pacific Ocean. Soils at NBVC Port Hueneme consist of unconsolidated alluvial deposits, including clays, silts, sands, and gravel, and are relatively poorly drained. The climate in the region is Mediterranean, with warm dry summers moderated by coastal fog, and mild moist winters. No natural drainages occur on the base, and surface water flow is intercepted by a series of drainage ditches leading to the Port Hueneme harbor.

NBVC Port Hueneme lies in the South Coast subregion of the California floristic province. The majority of the base has been developed with parking lots, storage lots, buildings, and other facilities. Few natural biological resource areas remain at NBVC Port Hueneme. The 4 Special Interest Natural Areas (SINAs) addressed in this plan are therefore important, since they offer limited but valuable habitat for wildlife species.

2.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE SINAS

2.2.1 SINA A: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat

Vegetation

Special Interest Natural Area A is located in the northwestern part of NBVC Port Hueneme, north of 23rd Avenue (Figure 2 and refer to Appendix A, Figures A-8 and A-9). It encompasses approximately 1.4 acres (0.6 hectare [ha]) consisting of a relatively narrow band of freshwater marsh habitat approximately 1,200 ft (366 m) long and 50 ft (15 m) wide. Area A is divided into 2 unequal sections by a dirt road, fragmenting the habitat into 2 separate marshes.

SINA A is dominated by freshwater marsh vegetation including California bulrush (*Scirpus californicus*), common reed (*Phragmites australis*), and broad-leaved cattail (*Typha latifolia*). Arroyo willow (*Salix lasiolepis*) and narrowleaf willow (*S. exigua*) are present on the upland areas. Other native species include coyote brush (*Baccharis pilularis*) at the edges of the area, western ragweed (*Ambrosia psilostachya*), and horseweed (*Conyza canadensis*). Non-native species found in area A include sweetclovers (*Melilotus indicus*, *M. albus*), English plantain (*Plantago lanceolata*), tree tobacco (*Nicotiana glauca*), and annual bromegrasses (*Bromus* spp.). Although the IRMP (U.S. Navy 1999) states that there is a potential for invasion of area A by the exotic species pampas grass (*Cortaderia* spp.) and giant reed (*Arundo donax*) from a nearby wetland area, these species were not observed in or near Area A during recent site investigations. It appears that they were misidentified or confused with the native species common reed, which is relatively abundant in the area. However, the invasive exotic or non-native species fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*) does occur near a nearby wetland, and appears to have started to invade SINA A marsh edges. In addition, the exotic species myoporum (*Myoporum laetum*) occurs around the edges of the marsh.

SINA A is relatively undisturbed, with good habitat value, and has a high priority for protection and restoration. The land surrounding the marshes is currently used for a Seabee Earthmoving Training Area and for crane storage. Human activities in the area adjacent to SINA A present potential threats such as

1 physical damage, accumulation of trash and litter, sedimentation into the wetland, and potential
2 contamination from surface runoff. In addition, there is the potential for invasion by exotic plant species.

3 Wildlife

4 SINA A has probably the greatest potential for the highest diversity of wildlife on NBVC Port Hueneme,
5 particularly birds. Numerous migratory and resident birds are known to forage or nest within the marsh
6 and adjacent willow and coyote brush vegetation associated with SINA A. Bird species observed in the
7 area include black-crowned night heron (*Nycticorax nycticorax*), great blue heron (*Ardea herodias*), red-
8 winged blackbird (*Agelaius phoeniceus*), California towhee (*Pipilo crissalis*), hooded oriole (*Icterus*
9 *cucullatus*), yellow warbler (*Dendroica petechia*), yellow-rumped warbler (*Dendroica coronata*), barn
10 swallow (*Hirundo rustica*), violet green swallow (*Tachycineta thalassina*), northern mockingbird (*Mimus*
11 *polyglottus*), black-chinned hummingbird (*Archilochus alexandri*), western kingbird (*Tyrannus*
12 *verticalis*), black phoebe (*Sayornis nigricans*), mourning dove (*Zenaida macroura*), and house finch
13 (*Carpodacus mexicanus*). Black-crowned night herons are known to nest and roost in the thickest
14 portions of the northernmost marsh of SINA A. Audubon's cottontail (*Sylvilagus audubonii*) are
15 abundant in the area.

16 Immediately to the northwest of SINA A is the Seabee Earthmoving Training Area where a burrowing
17 owl and burrows were observed during biological surveys associated with the preparation of the IRMP
18 (Figure 2) (U.S. Navy 1999). The area is characterized by open grassland surrounded by earthen berms
19 along the western and eastern boundaries (Appendix A, Figures A-1 – A-6). Between the earthen berms
20 lies a large open space containing numerous piles of loose soil, low areas with built-up embankments on
21 either side, and numerous other areas where Seabees are instructed in earthmoving activities with
22 bulldozers, graders, backhoes, etc.

23 At one time the earthen berms contained numerous California ground squirrel colonies as evidenced by
24 the presence of numerous burrows (Appendix A, Figures A-6 and A-7). However, there has been no sign
25 of ground squirrel activity or burrow maintenance nor have any ground squirrels been seen within the area
26 during surveys in May and October of 2002, and February, April, and May of 2003 (TEC 2002, 2003;
27 surveys were conducted in accordance with the burrowing owl survey protocol recommended by the
28 California Burrowing Owl Consortium [1997]). Whether the ground squirrels abandoned the area due to
29 the earthmoving activities in the area or were eradicated as part of the base pest control program is
30 unknown. There is no indication that burrowing owls have used the area in the past year (i.e., lack of
31 feathers, pellets, etc.). Surveys in April and May found the burrow entrances choked with annual grasses
32 and forbs. The burrows are readily available during the fall and winter months after the summer's growth
33 has died off, and it is conceivable that a wintering, transient burrowing owl would occasionally use the
34 area; however, burrowing owls are not expected to be common nor would they remain to breed.
35 Burrowing owls are not expected to be common on other parts of NBVC Port Hueneme where ground
36 squirrels currently occur (e.g., golf course) due to the low numbers of ground squirrels. Feral cats (*Felis*
37 *catus*) are also very prevalent in the area and along the golf course.

38 **2.2.2 SINA B: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat**

39 Vegetation

40 Totalling approximately 8.0 acres (3.2 ha), SINA B comprises a system of relatively steep-walled
41 drainage channels in the western and southwestern part of NBVC Port Hueneme (Figure 2). The widest
42 of these channels lies northeast of Logistics Way and runs into Port Hueneme harbor (Appendix A,
43 Figures A-18a and b). It is approximately 800 ft (244 m) in length. Other narrower channels extend

1 about 4,400 ft (1,341 m) along Pennsylvania Avenue, about 2,000 ft (610 m) along Pleasant Valley Road
2 (Appendix A, Figures A-16 and A-17), about 1,050 ft (320 m) between Cargo Road and Pacific Avenue,
3 about 1,850 ft (564 m) north of Lehman Road (Appendix A, Figures A-14 and A-15), and about 2,200 ft
4 (670 m) along 23rd Avenue (Appendix A, Figures A-12 and A-13). The drainage ditches have some
5 marsh vegetation.

6 In general, Area B does not have dense vegetation, since the channels are cleared regularly. It has been
7 reported that under unmaintained conditions, the channels have freshwater marsh species such as
8 California bulrush, broad-leaved cattail, and common reed (U.S. Navy 1999). Native species observed in
9 SINA B under current maintained conditions include plant species found in salt marshes or saline soils,
10 such as saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*), pickleweed (*Salicornia virginica*), and heliotrope (*Heliotropium*
11 *curassavicum*). Non-native species observed in this area include golden crownbeard (*Verbesina*
12 *encelioides* ssp. *exauriculata*), sweetclovers, New Zealand spinach (*Tetragonia tetragonioides*), red-
13 stemmed filaree (*Erodium cicutarium*), and annual bromegrasses on higher terrain; brass buttons (*Cotula*
14 *coronopifolia*) occurs within the channels. Two of the channels are somewhat different from most of the
15 drainages that comprise SINA B: the 23rd Avenue Channel slopes have been stabilized with erosion
16 control blankets, and the Lehman Road Channel bottom has not been cleared recently and has the marsh
17 species California bulrush, chairmaker's bulrush (*Scirpus americanus*) and broad-leaved cattail. The
18 slopes of most of the drainages in SINA B have the exotic species iceplant (*Carpobrotus edulis*) and
19 crystalline iceplant (*Mesembryanthemum crystallinum*); a few isolated clumps of pampas grass and
20 myoporum also were observed.

21 Since the drainage channels have historically been maintained for flood control by regular clearing of
22 vegetation, the restoration potential of this area is limited. Furthermore, the drainage channels are
23 designated as part of an Installation Restoration Program (IRP) site due to contamination from spills and
24 leaks into storm sewers, and are degraded by the presence of exotic species as well as trash and litter.

25 Wildlife

26 Due to the open and cleared nature of the drainage channels, the number and diversity of wildlife species
27 found in SINA B is quite low. Although the drainage channels associated with SINA B currently have a
28 lower potential for high wildlife diversity when compared to SINA A, with revegetation and restoration
29 these areas could become quite suitable and diverse habitats without reducing or impeding channel flow.

30 **2.2.3 SINA C: Coyote Brush Habitat**

31 Vegetation

32 The 3.9-acre (1.6-ha) SINA C lies north of 23rd Avenue and along Track No. 14 Road in the northwestern
33 part of NBVC Port Hueneme (Figure 2). It is composed primarily of upland scrub habitat, and extends
34 approximately 1,350 ft (411 m) north to south, and is about 120 to 140 ft (37 to 43 m) wide (Appendix A,
35 Figures A-10 and A-11).

36 SINA C has upland scrub vegetation dominated by coyote brush. Small clumps of arroyo willow occur;
37 other native species include saw-toothed goldenbush (*Hazardia squarrosa*), isolated mule fat (*Baccharis*
38 *salicifolia*), and telegraph weed (*Heterotheca grandiflora*). Non-native species are red-stemmed filaree,
39 golden crownbeard, and Russian thistle (*Salsola tragus*). Many introduced annual grasses also were
40 observed in SINA C, including ripgut brome (*Bromus diandrus*) compact brome (*B. madritensis* ssp.
41 *rubens*), slender wild oat (*Avena barbata*), Bermuda grass (*Cynodon dactylon*), and smilo grass
42 (*Piptatherum miliaceum*). Exotic species included myoporum, occurring in relatively high numbers, and
43 small isolated patches of Australian saltbush (*Atriplex semibaccata*), pampas grass, and iceplant.

1 Although SINA C is relatively disturbed and fragmented by dirt tracks, it has good habitat value for
2 avifauna and has potential for protection and restoration. Vehicle and human traffic along these tracks
3 and in adjacent areas surrounding the natural habitat present potential threats from physical damage or
4 destruction, accumulation of trash and litter, and disturbance to wildlife species. Additionally, there is a
5 threat for invasion by exotic plant species.

6 Wildlife

7 Compared to SINA A, SINA C has the second highest diversity of wildlife on NBVC Port Hueneme and
8 would benefit greatly from the proposed habitat restoration. Coyote brush habitats have the potential to
9 support numerous migratory and resident birds. This area also has the advantage of being in proximity to
10 the golf course (to the west) and SINA A. Bird species observed in SINA C include warbling vireo
11 (*Vireo gilvus*), Hutton's vireo (*Vireo huttoni*), ruby-throated hummingbird (*Archilochus colubris*),
12 American goldfinch (*Carduelis tristis*), house finch, killdeer (*Charadrius vociferous*), mourning dove,
13 bushtit (*Psaltriparus minimus*), and yellow-rumped warbler.

14 **2.2.4 SINA D: Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage and Sandy Beach Habitat**

15 Vegetation

16 SINA D lies in the extreme southwestern corner of NBVC Port Hueneme (Figure 2). It is bounded by
17 Port Hueneme harbor to the south and the City of Port Hueneme to the west and north. It consists of 2
18 portions: a sandy beach in the south below mean sea level extending about 700 ft (213 m) west to east,
19 and a foredune area to the west and north extending about 1,050 ft (320 m) inland. In total, SINA D is
20 composed of approximately 4.4 acres (1.8 ha) of beach and foredune vegetation.

21 The sandy beach in the south is subject to wave action and scouring and is bare. The low bluff above the
22 beach has the native species beach-bur and beach evening primrose (*Camissonia cheiranthifolia* ssp.
23 *suffruticosa*); introduced plants include annual grasses, sourclover (*Melilotus indicus*), sea rocket (*Cakile*
24 *maritima*), and golden crownbeard. The exotic species iceplant densely covers the top of the bluff. The
25 foredune area and bluff to the southwest have the native species beach bur, dune saltbush (*Atriplex*
26 *leucophylla*), heliotrope, and saltgrass. Vegetation farther away from the beach on the slopes and tops of
27 the dunes to the west and southwest has the native species sand verbena, beach-bur, and beach morning-
28 glory (*Calystegia soldanella*); this area also has beach evening primrose and telegraph weed. Introduced
29 species seen in these foredunes include sourclover, white sweetclover (*Melilotus albus*), sea rocket, red-
30 stemmed filaree, scarlet pimpernel (*Anagallis arvensis*), isolated myoporum, and weedy cudweed
31 (*Gnaphalium luteo-album*). Non-native grasses found in this habitat were rigput brome, water bent grass
32 (*Agrostis viridis*), and annual beard grass (*Polypogon monspeliensis*). A small wetland is present in a low
33 area at the base of a dune slope in the northwestern part of SINA D; species found here include broad-
34 leaved cattail. In general, SINA D has a high cover of the exotic species iceplant; other exotics include
35 crystalline iceplant and Australian saltbush.

36 Area D is relatively disturbed, but has potential for protection and restoration, since it potentially provides
37 good habitat value for shorebirds and haulout areas for pinnipeds. Area D has been disturbed by vehicle
38 and human traffic, and by the disposal of dredge spoils and debris. It has an accumulation of trash and
39 litter, and also has been invaded by exotic species.

40 Wildlife

41 Although few species of birds were observed within SINA D and the adjacent marine waters during
42 recent surveys (e.g., brown pelican [*Pelecanus occidentalis*], California gull [*Larus californicus*],

1 Heermann's gull [*Larus heermanni*], double-crested cormorant [*Phalacrocorax auritus*], black scoter
2 (*Melanitta nigra*), eared grebe [*Podiceps nigricollis*], and Clark's grebe [*Aechmophorus clarkii*]), this
3 area does have the potential to support a number of migrating shorebirds, waterfowl, and other marine
4 birds. The small strand of beach is relatively isolated and protected compared to adjacent beaches which
5 are either developed or highly utilized by people. It is possible that the beach may provide habitat for
6 dispersing and transient California least terns and western snowy plovers, especially during the late
7 summer through winter, and possibly during spring when these birds are moving to their breeding sites
8 along the coast. In addition, due to its protection, the beach is a haulout area for pinniped including
9 harbor seal (*Phoca vitulina*) and California sea lion (*Zalophus californicus*).

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3.0 IMPLEMENTATION OF HABITAT RESTORATION PLAN

3.1 GENERAL RESTORATION APPROACH AND GUIDELINES

Since ecological restoration is a relatively new field and each restoration effort is unique in some ways, restoration planning must, by necessity, be flexible enough to adapt to changing circumstances. The procedures described in this plan are those that have been used in various projects in the region; however, few restoration projects have been monitored carefully over a long enough period of time to provide a complete understanding of the restoration process. All procedures, therefore, are still to some extent experimental. Adjustments to the procedures described in this plan may be necessary in the field during the time of implementation. All modifications will be made in consultation with, and with the concurrence of, the Environmental Division of the NBVC Public Works Department.

Due to the small areas that are proposed for revegetation and restoration and their location within heavily disturbed and developed areas, the SINAs are not expected to attract special-status wildlife species (e.g., federally listed threatened and endangered species). Although some special-status species may occur as transients within the natural areas on NBVC Port Hueneme, suitable habitat would not occur that would allow long-term nesting or residence of such species. However, with protection and management of the beach areas within SINA D, the federally listed endangered California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*) and federally listed threatened western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) could be expected to be transient visitors.

3.1.1 Exotics Control

As a general guideline, exotics control treatments should be carried out before revegetation. Mechanical removal of plants should not destabilize the soil and should be conducted with minimal damage to native plants. When herbicides are used, care should be taken to conduct spraying when wind velocities are low. The herbicide spraying crew should receive onsite training to identify target and non-target species and be supervised during their work; care should be taken to avoid non-target species during spraying. The commonly used herbicide glyphosate can be applied in either a 2% solution (Roundup Pro7) or a 1.5% solution (Rodeo7), accompanied by a surfactant and a dye to mark sprayed areas. Herbicide use should follow all label directions and should only be applied by someone certified to dispense herbicides in the State of California and on federal facilities.

3.1.2 Revegetation

Due to the limited area available at the Port Hueneme site for collection of seeds and plant material of native species to be used in revegetation, seed and container stock may be obtained from certified seed collectors and nurseries. However, all revegetation material for the 4 SINAs must be derived from local sources, to preserve the integrity of local gene pools and to ensure adaptability of the planted material to the local environment. To ensure genetic diversity, seeds, cuttings, or plugs should be collected from a number of different plants and a variety of locations within the collection area. Cuttings or plugs should be propagated promptly by a certified nursery and maintained properly in containers for future transplanting in the field. Collected seed should not be stored for longer than 1 year, due to loss of viability. Should the seed need to be stored for a longer period of time, viability tests for the component species would be advisable.

At all stages of revegetation, careful records should be maintained regarding the nature of revegetation carried out in each of the 4 areas. Specifically, for seeded areas, the amount of seed used, the mix of

1 species, and the seeded locations should be documented and mapped. The number, species, and general
2 locations of plantings should also be recorded to enable future tracking of survival of plantings.

3 3.1.3 Habitat Protection

4 The 4 SINAs currently have varying amounts of accumulated litter and trash, including but not limited to,
5 asphalt or concrete blocks, cables, debris, plastic, and rubber tires. Before commencing all restoration
6 activities, including exotics control, all trash and debris should be removed.

7 After revegetation is complete, erosion control can be carried out as necessary in each of the 4 areas. For
8 example, temporary stabilization of the soil on relatively flat areas can be accomplished through
9 hydromulching. Steeper slopes subject to wind or water erosion should be stabilized using longer-term
10 erosion control treatments such as jute netting or straw blankets, where appropriate. In addition,
11 following revegetation, foot and vehicular traffic through the 4 restoration areas should be restricted,
12 except for monitoring and maintenance activities. If necessary, signage could be installed in the areas
13 designating them as restoration sites that need to be protected from disturbance.

14 3.2 SINA A: BULRUSH-CATTAIL HABITAT

15 3.2.1 Exotics Control

16 Two non-native exotic plant species are found within SINA A: fennel and myoporum (Table 1). Fennel,
17 a tall anise-scented perennial plant that is becoming a serious invasive problem throughout California, is
18 on the California Exotic Pest Plant Council's (CalEPPC) list of Exotic Pest Plants of Greatest Ecological
19 Concern in California, and is designated as a List A-1 species). Myoporum, often used for landscaping
20 but now considered a pest plant, is designated as a List A-2 species) (CalEPPC 1999).

Table 1. Occurrence of Non-Native Species and Suggested Native Species for Revegetation in SINAs

<i>SINA</i>	<i>Non-Native Species Present (CalEPPC designation)</i>	<i>Suggested Native Species to be Used in Revegetation</i>
A: Bulrush-Cattail	Fennel (List A-1) Myoporum (List A-2)	Black cottonwood (<i>Populus balsamifera</i>) Western sycamore (<i>Platanus racemosa</i>) Coast live oak (<i>Quercus agrifolia</i> var. <i>agrifolia</i>) Arroyo willow (<i>Salix lasiolepis</i>)
B: Bulrush-Cattail	Iceplant (List A-1) Pampas grass (List A-1) Myoporum (List A-2) Crystalline ice plant (List B) New Zealand spinach	Saltgrass (<i>Distichlis spicata</i>) Pickleweed (<i>Salicornia virginica</i>) Frankenia (<i>Frankenia salina</i>) Heliotrope (<i>Heliotropium curassavicum</i>) Arroyo willow Black cottonwood Western sycamore Coast live oak
C: Coyote Brush	Pampas grass (List A-1) Iceplant (List A-1) Myoporum (List A-2) Australian saltbush (List A-2)	California sagebrush (<i>Artemisia californica</i>) Coyote brush (<i>Baccharis pilularis</i>) Coastal encelia (<i>Encelia californica</i>) Dune buckwheat (<i>Eriogonum parvifolium</i>)
D: Sand verbena – Beach bursage	Iceplant (List A-1) Australian saltbush (List A-2) Crystalline iceplant (List B)	Sand verbena (<i>Abronia maritima</i>) Beach-bur (<i>Ambrosia chamissonis</i>) Dune saltbush (<i>Atriplex leucophylla</i>) Beach morning glory (<i>Calystega soldanella</i>) Beach evening primrose (<i>Camissonia cheiranthifolia</i>)

Notes: List A-1 = most invasive wildland pest plants, widespread; List A-2 = most invasive wildland pest plants, regional;
List B = wildland pest plants of lesser invasiveness.

1 To prevent the potential for further invasion of fennel into the native marsh vegetation, it should be
2 eradicated within SINA A and from the nearby wetland to the west. In addition, the non-native species
3 myoporum found within the marshes of SINA A should be targeted for eradication. Eradication methods
4 initially should involve the mechanical removal of these species, followed by herbicide treatment of
5 remaining stumps or plant material.

6 **3.2.2 Revegetation**

7 Past restoration activities in SINA A included the installation of a gravel trail around the marsh areas,
8 with various plantings, mostly native trees and shrubs, placed around the edges. A drip irrigation system
9 has been installed to water these plantings. To date, many of the plantings have died, possibly due to the
10 lack of regular irrigation. Many of the plantings, such as dudleyas, pine trees, and chaparral shrubs, are
11 inappropriate for this marsh habitat. Should these plantings die in the near future, they should not be
12 replaced. In their place, native wetland or riparian species should be used as identified below.

13 No revegetation is necessary directly in the marsh areas of SINA A, due to the relatively high cover of
14 existing native vegetation. At the edges of the marshes, however, larger native woody species should be
15 planted to create a vegetative buffer and enhance the biodiversity of the habitat. The woody plants
16 include primarily arroyo willow, which can be planted by placing cuttings or wands directly into moist or
17 wet soil, about 10 to 20 ft (3 to 6 m) apart. This revegetation should also be conducted on the dirt road
18 crossing the wetland and dividing the marsh habitat into 2 parts. Compacted dirt in the road should first
19 be loosened mechanically to enable the establishment of the willows.

20 The willow wands can be supplemented by container plantings of black cottonwood (*Populus balsamifera*
21 ssp. *trichocarpa*), western sycamore (*Platanus racemosa*), and coast live oak (*Quercus agrifolia* var.
22 *agrifolia*). The container plantings of these 3 species should be interspersed, and spaced about 20 to 40 ft
23 (6 to 12 m) apart. Regular linear rows of plantings should be avoided, to give the restoration area a more
24 natural appearance. In general, willows should be planted in the lowest, wettest areas, progressing
25 upslope to cottonwoods, sycamores, and oaks. Each container planting should be placed in a planting
26 hole dug to twice the diameter of the root ball, and at least 6 inches (15 centimeters [cm]) deeper than the
27 container. Planting holes should be backfilled with a mixture of mulch and native soil, and watered
28 thoroughly. Since SINA A is utilized extensively by nesting and migrating birds, to minimize any
29 potential impacts to migratory birds, all revegetation activities should take place in the fall and winter.

30 The drip irrigation system that currently exists in SINA A should be repaired or replaced and directed
31 towards the new plantings placed in the restoration area. Irrigation should be maintained for 2 years. The
32 frequency and amount of irrigation should be adjusted based upon environmental conditions at the time of
33 planting and during the period of establishment of the plants.

34 **3.2.3 Habitat Protection**

35 After revegetation is complete, the existing dirt road crossing the wetland should be blocked by installing
36 a temporary fence or more permanent barrier system along the boundaries of the area. Signs on the fence
37 or barriers should indicate that the marshes need to be protected from disturbance. Foot traffic should be
38 restricted to the existing trail, which should be maintained regularly. The bridge should be repaired as
39 necessary and upgraded by installing new railings. With the addition of benches, it could be used as a
40 wildlife viewing area.

1 3.3 SINA B: BULRUSH-CATTAIL HABITAT

2 3.3.1 Exotics Control

3 The slopes of the drainage channels in SINA B have exotic species that should be eradicated (Table 1).
4 Iceplant is the most widespread and should have the highest priority for eradication. The exotic species
5 pampas grass, myoporum, and crystalline iceplant also are present and should be treated. In addition, the
6 non-native species New Zealand spinach should be targeted for eradication.

7 Iceplant is a spreading succulent shrub and forms mats. It is native to South Africa, and has been planted
8 widely in California as ground cover and for soil stabilization. It rapidly colonizes disturbed areas and
9 excludes native plants, thus posing a major threat to coastal habitats. Iceplant is on CalEPPC's List A-1.
10 Pampas grass is an erect perennial grass forming large tussocks with plume-like inflorescences. Most
11 species of pampas grass are native to South America. Two species were introduced as ornamentals to
12 California in the late 19th century, *Cortaderia jubata* and *C. selloana*. The first species is considered a
13 widespread invasive weed in California, spreading into native vegetation, occupying space, and
14 preventing natives from reestablishing. It is difficult to eradicate. The second species is not as invasive,
15 but both the species are on List A-1. Myoporum is on CalEPPC List A-2 and crystalline iceplant is on
16 List B (CalEPPC 1999). New Zealand spinach is not included on CalEPPC exotic plant lists, but should
17 be treated, since it now is considered locally a pest plant (Ferren et al. 1990).

18 With the exception of pampas grass and myoporum, these species should not be removed mechanically,
19 since such activity may destabilize the slopes of the channels. However, all the species should be treated
20 with herbicide.

21 3.3.2 Revegetation

22 No direct revegetation is necessary in the drainage channels of SINA B, since they have to be cleared of
23 vegetation regularly for flood control. However, the slopes of the drainage channels can be planted with
24 plugs of the saline soil species saltgrass, pickleweed, frankenia (*Frankenia salina*), and heliotrope. These
25 plantings should be interspersed, and spaced about 5 ft (1.5 m) apart. Most of these species exist
26 currently in SINA B, and if the revegetation is successful, they will help to stabilize the channel slopes
27 and would not impede or reduce channel flows.

28 Dirt areas along the tops of the banks of the channels can be planted with larger native woody species to
29 enhance the biodiversity of the habitat. In addition, flat, dirt areas above the largest channel at the
30 intersection of Logistics Way, Talos Road, and Pleasant Valley Road, can be revegetated. As in SINA A,
31 the woody plants can include cuttings or wands of arroyo willow, which can be placed directly into the
32 soil about 10 to 20 ft (3 to 6 m) apart. The willow wands can be supplemented by container plantings of
33 black cottonwood, coast live oak, and western sycamore. The container plantings of these 3 species
34 should be interspersed, and spaced about 20 to 40 ft (6 to 12 m) apart. Each container planting should be
35 placed in a planting hole dug to twice the diameter of the root ball, and at least 6 inches (15 cm) deeper
36 than the container. Planting holes should be backfilled with a mixture of mulch and native soil, and
37 watered thoroughly.

38 Tree species planted along the tops of the channel banks should be irrigated until they are well
39 established. A drip irrigation system can be installed in the restoration area. Alternatively, irrigation in
40 accessible areas may be carried out using water trucks and hoses. Irrigation should be maintained for 2
41 years. The frequency and amount of irrigation should be adjusted based upon environmental conditions at
42 the time of planting and during the period of establishment of the plants.

1 3.3.3 Habitat Protection

2 Implementation of the Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan for the Port Hueneme site will prevent the
3 contamination of the drainage channels of SINA B, thus protecting water quality and habitat for wildlife.
4 Other protective measures, such as fencing and signage, do not appear to be necessary.

5 3.4 SINA C: COYOTE BRUSH HABITAT

6 3.4.1 Exotics Control

7 Exotic species found in Area C include myoporum, occurring in relatively high numbers, and small
8 isolated patches of Australian saltbush, pampas grass, and iceplant (Table 1). As noted previously,
9 pampas grass and iceplant are on the CalEPPC List A-1. Australian saltbush is a spreading subshrub, and
10 colonizes dune habitats and disturbed areas. Both this species and myoporum are on List A-2 (CalEPPC
11 1999). All these species should be targeted for eradication. Eradication methods should initially involve
12 the mechanical removal of pampas grass and myoporum, followed by herbicide treatment of remaining
13 plant material. Iceplant and Australian saltbush should be treated with herbicide and left in place.

14 3.4.2 Revegetation

15 Revegetation should be conducted on the dirt roads and in bare areas of SINA C. Compacted dirt should
16 first be loosened mechanically to enable later seed germination. A native coastal sage scrub seed mix can
17 be hand-broadcast, and the seed raked or chained into the soil. Alternatively, the mix can be
18 hydroseeded. A suggested seed mix specification is provided in Table 2. Species and their application
19 rates may be adjusted as necessary depending on availability of seed during the collection season. A
20 relatively large number of species is included in the seed mix to increase the chance for successful
21 vegetation establishment in variable environmental conditions and to enhance biodiversity in SINA C. To
22 minimize any potential impacts to migratory birds utilizing SINA C, particularly those nesting, all
23 revegetation activities should take place in the fall and winter.

Table 2. Suggested Seed Mix Prescription for SINA C

<i>Species</i>	<i>Common Name</i>	<i>Growth Form</i>	<i>Application Rate (lbs/acre)</i>
<i>Artemisia californica</i>	California sagebrush	Shrub	4.0
<i>Baccharis pilularis</i>	Coyote brush	Shrub	6.0
<i>Encelia californica</i>	Coastal encelia	Shrub	3.0
<i>Eriogonum parvifolium</i>	Dune buckwheat	Shrub	2.0
<i>Leymus condensatus</i>	Giant ryegrass	Perennial grass	2.0
<i>Lotus scoparius</i> var. <i>scoparius</i>	Deerweed	Subshrub	2.0
<i>Mimulus aurantiacus</i>	Monkey-flower	Shrub	2.0
<i>Nassella pulchra</i>	Purple needlegrass	Perennial grass	2.0
<i>Salvia mellifera</i>	Black sage	Shrub	1.0
<i>Scrophularia californica</i>	California figwort	Perennial herb	1.0
Total lbs/acre			25.0

24 3.4.3 Habitat Protection

25 Large piles of crumbling asphalt present in SINA C should be cleaned up before restoration activities
26 begin. After restoration is complete, access along the newly revegetated dirt roads should be blocked off
27 by installing a temporary fence or a more permanent barrier system along the boundaries of the area. A
28 fence already exists along the boundary of the golf course, and this fence could be extended as necessary.

1 Signs should indicate that the restoration area needs to be protected. Foot traffic should be restricted until
 2 native vegetation is well-established, after which a new walking trail could be installed to allow passive
 3 recreational use of the habitat and wildlife viewing.

4 **3.5 SINA D: SAND VERBENA-BEACH BURSAGE AND SANDY BEACH HABITAT**

5 **3.5.1 Exotics Control**

6 In general, SINA D has a high cover of the exotic species iceplant; other exotics include crystalline
 7 iceplant and Australian saltbush (Table 1). As noted previously, iceplant is on the CalEPPC List A-1,
 8 Australian saltbush is on List A-2, and crystalline iceplant is on List B (CalEPPC 1999). All these
 9 species should be targeted for eradication but should not be removed mechanically, since this may
 10 destabilize the dune slopes; they can all be treated with herbicide.

11 **3.5.2 Revegetation**

12 Revegetation should be conducted in bare areas of SINA D. In addition, after iceplant has been treated
 13 with herbicide and has died, planting holes can be cleared in the dead mats, and revegetation can be
 14 carried out in these cleared locations. A native coastal strand and foredune seed mix can be hand-
 15 broadcast, and the seed raked or chained into the soil. Alternatively, the mix can be hydroseeded. A
 16 suggested seed mix specification is provided in Table 3. Species and their application rates may be
 17 adjusted as necessary depending on availability of seed during the collection season. If seed is not
 18 available readily for some of these species, particularly dune saltbush and sand verbena, container
 19 plantings propagated from cuttings can be used. Plantings of different species should be interspersed and
 20 spaced 3 to 5 ft (1 to 1.5 m) apart.

Table 3. Preliminary Seed Mix Prescription for SINA D

<i>Species</i>	<i>Common Name</i>	<i>Growth Form</i>	<i>Application Rate (lbs/acre)</i>
<i>Abronia maritima</i>	Sand verbena	Perennial herb	4.0
<i>Ambrosia chamissonis</i>	Beach-bur	Perennial herb	5.0
<i>Atriplex leucophylla</i>	Dune saltbush	Perennial herb	2.0
<i>Calystegia soldanella</i>	Beach morning-glory	Perennial herb	2.0
<i>Camissonia cheiranthifolia</i>	Beach evening primrose	Perennial herb	2.0
Total lbs/acre			15.0

21 **3.5.3 Habitat Protection**

22 Dune habitats are fragile ecosystems and are particularly susceptible to disturbance. Currently, there has
 23 been evidence of some damage to the habitat by vehicle tracks through the area, and foot and vehicular
 24 traffic should be restricted in this habitat after restoration is complete. An effective permanent barrier
 25 system could utilize heavy wooden posts around SINA D. Once native vegetation is well-established,
 26 access to the area could be made possible by the installation of a wooden boardwalk, with signage
 27 installed indicating that foot traffic must be restricted to the boardwalk.

4.0 MONITORING AND MAINTENANCE

4.1 WILDLIFE SURVEYS

To monitor the use of the SINAs by wildlife, particularly birds, and to maintain a wildlife occurrence database for NBVC Port Hueneme in general, regular wildlife surveys should be conducted before and after the habitat restoration plan and associated revegetation is implemented. Regular surveys before revegetation of the SINAs will add to the understanding of what species utilize the SINAs, how they utilize them (i.e., nesting, foraging, roosting), and which areas are more sensitive to disturbance at what time of year. Regular surveys after revegetation and habitat restoration have occurred will assist in assessing the effectiveness and success of the revegetation and habitat restoration and the habitat's ability to support wildlife on NBVC Port Hueneme. Suggested wildlife survey methods are described below.

- surveys should be conducted on foot a minimum of 4 times per year, once per season: spring = March-May, summer = June-August, fall = September-November, and winter = December-February; if funding allows, additional surveys should be conducted during the spring and summer;
- surveys in spring and summer should begin as close to sunrise as possible to allow for the detection of singing bird species and to observe those species that may be hidden during the heat of the day or during times of increased human activity;
- surveys should focus on the SINAs with particular attention to SINAs A (bulrush-cattail habitat) and C (coyote brush habitat) but other areas of NBVC should also be surveyed as time allows including the windrows along the golf course and the Bard Estate grounds;
- surveys should be conducted on weekends and weekdays to determine the potential effects of human activity on the SINAs, in particular, how the use of the crane storage field or Seabee Earthmoving Training Area affects SINA A;
- the beach area of SINA D should be monitored regularly for least terns and snowy plovers, particularly during late summer and winter when dispersing and wintering birds may be present;
- records should be kept of all wildlife species observed or heard including the species, time and location of observation, and any noteworthy activities (e.g., nesting, foraging, recently fledged birds being fed by parents).

4.2 HABITAT RESTORATION PLAN

4.2.1 Performance Criteria

Restoration programs generally define performance criteria to evaluate the progress and success of restoration activities, and to guide the implementation of remedial measures or contingency actions when the criteria are not being met. The goal of protection and restoration of the 4 SINA at NBVC Port Hueneme is to preserve, protect, and enhance the ecological integrity of the habitats. Specific criteria to be met in this restoration program over a monitoring period of 5 years are outlined below.

4.2.1.1 Exotics Control

By the end of the program, the cover of invasive exotic plants in and around the restoration areas should be reduced significantly to a minimal level. Weedy species should not threaten the establishment and growth of native species in the natural areas and should not invade adjacent areas.

4.2.1.2 Revegetation of the Natural Areas

Seeded areas should show successful germination of the seeded native species, with at least a majority of the number of seeded species being present. The seeded areas should attain at least 50% or more total

1 native vegetation cover in SINA C, and at least 25% or more total native vegetation cover in SINA D.
2 Plantings should survive at a rate of 80% or higher. Evidence of successful reproduction (flowering and
3 fruiting) of the established plants should be observed and recorded.

4 4.2.1.3 Erosion Control and Soil Stabilization

5 Erosion control or soil stabilization treatments, if used, should be maintained intact during the program
6 until revegetation results in adequate protective cover. No landslides, gullyng, or blowouts should occur,
7 and topsoil in the restoration areas should be stable and not subject to excessive wind and water erosion.

8 4.2.1.4 Fencing/Signage

9 All fences and barriers restricting access to the restoration areas, as well as installed signage, should
10 remain intact throughout the program. This may involve periodic inspection and maintenance.

11 **4.2.2 Monitoring Activities**

12 The objectives of monitoring are to document the establishment of native vegetation and identify areas
13 that may need maintenance or further revegetation. Monitoring will consist of regular evaluations of
14 vegetation development in the restoration areas over a period of 5 years.

15 Monitoring will take place quarterly and additionally after major storm events, and will include walking
16 the natural areas to observe and document the plant species present and general vegetation development,
17 evidence of plant reproduction, animal activity, invasion of weedy species into the restoration areas, and
18 potential erosion problems. Estimates of plant species cover will be derived from visual inspection of
19 each restored area taken as a whole. Plantings will be counted to assess their rate of survival. Permanent
20 photopoints may be established to document changes consistently over time, and to allow a direct
21 comparison between years.

22 Results of monitoring should be summarized in annual reports and submitted to the Environmental
23 Division. The reports should summarize restoration activities and monitoring data collected during the
24 previous year, and compare the results against the performance criteria to evaluate restoration success.
25 The annual reports will recommend continuing maintenance activities and remedial or corrective
26 measures, if needed, and will specify when such measures should be implemented. These reports also
27 will include the photo documentation results.

28 **4.2.3 Maintenance and Remedial Measures**

29 Maintenance of the 4 SINAs should be carried out periodically to ensure successful restoration. Remedial
30 measures should be applied as necessary during the course of the restoration program whenever
31 performance criteria are not being met, as identified during monitoring.

- 32 • Periodic weed control should be carried out regularly after initial restoration has been completed.
33 Weed control is an essential part of ensuring successful recruitment and growth of native species.
34 Other restoration programs in the region have demonstrated that invasive exotic species often
35 require repeated treatments to be eradicated successfully.
- 36 • Any installed irrigation system should be maintained in good working order, and irrigation
37 carried out as necessary.
- 38 • If there is no evidence of successful germination of seeded species, reseedng should be carried
39 out. Plantings that do not survive, particularly in the first year after planting, should be replaced.
- 40 • The restoration areas should be maintained free of litter and trash, with clean-up conducted on a
41 regular basis.
- 42 • The restoration area should be checked periodically for erosion, especially after major storm

- 1 events. If any erosion features such as gullies or ruts are observed, they should be repaired
2 immediately. This will ensure the protection of revegetated plant material, and also will prevent
3 sedimentation into the natural habitats.
- 4 • Damaged fences, barriers, or signage should be repaired or replaced as necessary.

5 **4.2.4 Restoration Program Schedule**

6 The optimum time to collect seed and planting material is in the summer and fall. Initial exotics control,
7 seeding plant species, planting, and soil stabilization should be completed no later than winter, preferably
8 before the rainy period begins. To minimize any potential impacts to migratory birds utilizing the SINAs,
9 particularly those nesting, all revegetation activities should take place in the fall and winter.

10 Restoration monitoring should be conducted quarterly. Erosion control monitoring and maintenance
11 should be carried out after major storm events in winter and spring, when erosion problems are most
12 likely to occur. Weed control monitoring and maintenance should also follow this schedule, because
13 winter and spring are the growing season for weeds, when they are most likely to be detected as well as
14 susceptible to herbicide treatment. Spraying is most effective at this time, before the weeds set seed. The
15 timing of all monitoring and maintenance activities may vary from year to year depending on seasonal
16 and environmental conditions.

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APPENDIX A
Photos of Seebee Earthmoving Training Area
and
Special Interest Natural Areas, NBVC Port Hueneme

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**Figure A-1. Seebee Earthmoving Training Area
(looking NW from eastern boundary)**

**Figure A-2. Seebee Earthmoving Training Area
(looking W from eastern boundary)**

**Figure A-3. Seebee Earthmoving Training Area
(looking SW from eastern boundary)**

**Figure A-4. Seebee Earthmoving Training Area
(looking S from eastern boundary)**

Figure A-5. Seebee Earthmoving Training Area

Figure A-6. Seebee Earthmoving Training Area

Figure A-7a

Figure A-7b

Figures A-7a and b. Old California ground squirrel burrows in the Seebee Earthmoving Training Area

Figure A-8. Special Interest Natural Area A: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat (looking N with the Seebee Earthmoving Training Area in the background to the NW)

Figure A-9. Special Interest Natural Area A: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat (looking NNW)

Figure A-10. Special Interest Natural Area C: Coyote Brush Habitat (looking S)

Figure A-11. Special Interest Natural Area C: Coyote Brush Habitat (looking NW from Track No. 14 Road)

**Figure A-12. Special Interest Natural Area B: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat
(N of 23rd Avenue, looking E)**

**Figure A-13. Special Interest Natural Area B: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat
(N of 23rd Avenue, looking W)**

**Figure A-14. Special Interest Natural Area B: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat
(N of Lehman Road, E of Pennsylvania Avenue)**

**Figure A-15. Special Interest Natural Area B: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat
(N of Lehman Road, W of Pennsylvania Avenue)**

**Figure A-16. Special Interest Natural Area B: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat
(S of Pleasant Valley Road, W of Track No. 13 Road)**

**Figure A-17. Special Interest Natural Area B: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat
(S of Pleasant Valley Road, E of Track No. 13 Road)**

Figure A-18a

Figure A-18b

**Figures A-18a and b. Special Interest Natural Area B: Bulrush-Cattail Habitat
(N of Logistics Way)**

APPENDIX B
Wildlife Species Observed at NBVC Port Hueneme

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Table B-1. Wildlife Species Observed at NBVC Port Hueneme

<i>Scientific Name</i>	<i>Common Name</i>	<i>SINA</i>			
AMPHIBIANS					
<i>Hyla regilla</i>	Pacific treefrog	A			
REPTILES					
<i>Pituophis melanoleucus</i>	Gopher snake				
MAMMALS					
<i>Sylvilagus audubonii</i>	Audubon's cottontail				
<i>Lepus californicus</i>	Black-tailed jackrabbit	A			
<i>Thomomys bottae</i>	Botta's pocket gopher				
<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	Bottlenose dolphin	adjacent to D			
<i>Spermophilus beecheyi</i>	California ground squirrel	A			
<i>Felis catus</i>	Feral cat	A			
<i>Phoca vitulina</i>	Harbor seal	adjacent to D			
		<i>Occurrence</i> ⁽¹⁾			
BIRDS		<i>Sp</i>	<i>Su</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>W</i>
Grebes					
<i>Aechmophorus clarkii</i>	Clark's grebe	D			
<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>	Eared grebe				D
<i>Podilymbus podiceps</i>	Pied-billed grebe				D
<i>Aechmophorus occidentalis</i>	Western grebe				D
Pelicans					
<i>Pelecanus occidentalis</i>	California brown pelican	D			D
Cormorants					
<i>Phalacrocorax penicillatus</i>	Brandt's cormorant				D
<i>Phalacrocorax auritus</i>	Double-crested cormorant	D			D
<i>Phalacrocorax pelagicus</i>	Pelagic cormorant				D
Hérons, Egrets, and Bitterns					
<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>	Black-crowned night heron	A		A	A
<i>Ardea herodias</i>	Great blue heron	A, B		A, B	A, B
<i>Casmerodius albus</i>	Great egret			A	A
<i>Butorides striatus</i>	Green-backed heron				A
<i>Egretta rufescens</i>	Reddish egret	A			
<i>Egretta thula</i>	Snowy egret				A, B
Ducks, Geese, and Swans					
<i>Melanitta nigra</i>	Black scoter	x			
<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Mallard	A, B		A, B	A, B
Hawks, Kites, and Eagles					
<i>Accipiter cooperii</i>	Cooper's hawk				A
<i>Falco columbarius</i>	Merlin	A			
<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>	Red-tailed hawk	x		x	x
<i>Accipiter striatus</i>	Sharp-shinned hawk				x
Falcons					
<i>Falco sparverius</i>	American kestrel	x			x
Rails, Coots, and Gallinules					
<i>Fulica americana</i>	American coot	A, D		A, D	A, D
Plovers and Relatives					
<i>Charadrius vociferus</i>	Killdeer	x			x

Table B-1 (cont.). Wildlife Species Observed at NBVC Port Hueneme

Scientific Name	Common name	Occurrence ⁽¹⁾			
		Sp	Su	F	W
BIRDS (cont.)					
Avocets and Stilts					
<i>Himantopus mexicanus</i>	Black-necked stilt				D
Sandpipers and Relatives					
<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Common snipe				x
<i>Tringa melanoleuca</i>	Greater yellowlegs				x
<i>Tringa flavipes</i>	Lesser yellowlegs	x			
<i>Actitis macularia</i>	Spotted sandpiper				D
<i>Aphriza virgata</i>	Surfbird				D
<i>Calidris mauri</i>	Western sandpiper				D
<i>Catoptrophorus semipalmatus</i>	Willet	D			D
Gulls and Terns					
<i>Larus californicus</i>	California gull	x			x
<i>Larus heermanni</i>	Heermann's gull	x			x
<i>Larus delawarensis</i>	Ring-billed gull				x
<i>Larus occidentalis</i>	Western gull	x			x
Doves and Pigeons					
<i>Zenaida macroura</i>	Mourning dove	x	x	x	x
<i>Columba livia</i>	Rock dove	x	x	x	x
Owls					
<i>Tyto alba</i>	Barn owl	A			
<i>Athene cunicularia</i>	Burrowing owl				adj. to A
<i>Bubo virginianus</i>	Great-horned owl	A			
Swifts					
<i>Chaetura pelagica</i>	Chimney swift				x
Hummingbirds					
<i>Selasphorus sasin</i>	Allen's hummingbird	A			
<i>Calypte anna</i>	Anna's hummingbird			A	A, C
<i>Archilochus alexandri</i>	Black-chinned hummingbird	C			
<i>Calypte costae</i>	Costa's hummingbird	A, C			A, C
<i>Archilochus colubris</i>	Ruby-throated hummingbird			A	
Kingfishers					
<i>Ceryle alcyon</i>	Belted kingfisher			A	A
Woodpeckers					
<i>Colaptes auratus</i>	Northern flicker	x			x
Tyrant Flycatchers					
<i>Sayornis nigricans</i>	Black phoebe	A, C			A, C
<i>Sayornis saya</i>	Say's phoebe				A, C
<i>Tyrannus verticalis</i>	Western kingbird	A, C			
Swallows					
<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Barn swallow	x			x
<i>Petrochelidon fulva</i>	Cliff swallow	x			
<i>Tachycineta thalassina</i>	Violet-green swallow	x			
Jays, Crows, and Magpies					
<i>Corvus brachyrhynchos</i>	American crow	x	x	x	x
Bushtits					
<i>Psaltriparus minimus</i>	Bushtit	C			
Wrens					
<i>Cistothorus palustris</i>	Marsh wren			A	A

Table B-1 (cont.). Wildlife Species Observed at NBVC Port Hueneme

Scientific Name	Common name	Occurrence ⁽¹⁾			
		Sp	Su	F	W
BIRDS (cont.)					
Old World Warblers, Thrushes, Gnatcatchers, and Kinglets					
<i>Poliophtila caerulea</i>	Blue-grey gnatcatcher				C
Mockingbirds and Thrashers					
<i>Mimus polyglottos</i>	Northern mockingbird	x			x
Shrikes					
<i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>	Loggerhead shrike				A
Vireos					
<i>Vireo huttoni</i>	Hutton's vireo	C			
<i>Vireo gilvus</i>	Warbling vireo	C			
Starlings					
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>	European starling	x	x	x	x
Blackbirds					
<i>Euphagus cyanocephalus</i>	Brewer's blackbird	x			x
<i>Quiscalus mexicanus</i>	Great-tailed grackle	x			x
<i>Icterus cucullatus</i>	Hooded oriole	A			
<i>Agelaius phoeniceus</i>	Red-winged blackbird	A		A	A
<i>Sturnella neglecta</i>	Western meadowlark	x			x
Wood Warblers					
<i>Geothlypis trichas</i>	Common yellowthroat	A, C		A	A
<i>Dendroica coronata</i>	Yellow-rumped warbler	A, C			A, C
<i>Dendroica petechia</i>	Yellow warbler	A, C			
Sparrows, Buntings, Towhees, and Relatives					
<i>Pipilo crissalis</i>	California towhee	A			
<i>Spizella passerina</i>	Chipping sparrow			A, C	A, C
<i>Melospiza melodia</i>	Song sparrow			A, C	A, C
<i>Zonotrichia leucophrys</i>	White-crowned sparrow	A, C		A, C	A, C
Finches and Relatives					
<i>Carduelis tristis</i>	American goldfinch	A			
<i>Carpodacus mexicanus</i>	House finch	x	x	x	x
<i>Carduelis psaltria</i>	Lesser goldfinch				A
Old World Sparrows					
<i>Passer domesticus</i>	House sparrow	x	x	x	x

Notes: ⁽¹⁾ Sp – spring = Mar-May; Su – summer = Jun-Aug; F – fall = Sep-Nov; W – winter = Dec-Feb.
 x = NBVC Port Hueneme in general or exact location unknown, A= observed in SINA A, B = SINA B, C = SINA C, D = SINA D.

Sources: Anteon 1999; U.S. Navy 1999; TEC 2002, 2003.

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WRF CVGF Table B-1. Wildlife Species Observed at NBVC Port Hueneme

<i>Scientific Name</i>	<i>Common Name</i>	<i>SINA</i>			
AMPHIBIANS					
<i>Hyla regilla</i>	Pacific treefrog	A			
REPTILES					
<i>Pituophis melanoleucus</i>	Gopher snake	x			
MAMMALS					
<i>Sylvilagus audubonii</i>	Audubon's cottontail	x			
<i>Lepus californicus</i>	Black-tailed jackrabbit	A			
<i>Thomomys bottae</i>	Botta's pocket gopher	x			
<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	Bottlenose dolphin	adjacent to D			
<i>Spermophilus beecheyi</i>	California ground squirrel	A, B, D			
<i>Felis catus</i>	Feral cat	A, B			
<i>Phoca vitulina</i>	Harbor seal	adjacent to D			
<i>Didelphis virginianus</i>	Virginia opossum	x			
		<i>Occurrence</i> ⁽¹⁾			
BIRDS		<i>Sp</i>	<i>Su</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>W</i>
Loons and Grebes					
<i>Aechmophorus clarkii</i>	Clark's grebe	D			
<i>Gavia immer</i>	Common loon				D
<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>	Eared grebe				D
<i>Podiceps auritus</i>	Horned grebe			B	
<i>Podilymbus podiceps</i>	Pied-billed grebe				D
<i>Aechmophorus occidentalis</i>	Western grebe				D
Pelicans					
<i>Pelecanus occidentalis</i>	California brown pelican	D			D
Cormorants					
<i>Phalacrocorax penicillatus</i>	Brandt's cormorant				D
<i>Phalacrocorax auritus</i>	Double-crested cormorant	D			D
<i>Phalacrocorax pelagicus</i>	Pelagic cormorant				D
Hérons, Egrets, and Bitterns					
<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>	Black-crowned night heron	A		A, B	A
<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Cattle egret	B		B	
<i>Ardea herodias</i>	Great blue heron	A, B		A, B	A, B
<i>Casmerodius albus</i>	Great egret			A, B	A
<i>Butorides striatus</i>	Green-backed heron				A
<i>Egretta rufescens</i>	Reddish egret	A			
<i>Egretta thula</i>	Snowy egret	B			A, B
Ducks, Geese, and Swans					
<i>Melanitta nigra</i>	Black scoter	D			
<i>Aythya affinis</i>	Lesser scaup				GC
<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Mallard	A, B		A, B	A, B
<i>Melanitta perspicillata</i>	Surf scoter				D
Hawks, Falcons, Kites, and Eagles					
<i>Falco sparverius</i>	American kestrel	x		A	x, B
<i>Accipiter cooperii</i>	Cooper's hawk				A
<i>Falco columbarius</i>	Merlin	A		A	
<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>	Red-tailed hawk	x, A		x, A, B	x
<i>Accipiter striatus</i>	Sharp-shinned hawk				x

Table B-1 (cont.). Wildlife Species Observed at NBVC Port Hueneme

Scientific Name	Common name	Occurrence ⁽¹⁾			
		Sp	Su	F	W
BIRDS (cont.)					
Rails, Coots, and Gallinules					
<i>Fulica americana</i>	American coot	A, D		A, D	A, D, GC
Plovers and Relatives					
<i>Charadrius vociferus</i>	Killdeer	x			x, B
Oystercatchers					
<i>Haematopus bachmani</i>	Black oystercatcher				D
Avocets and Stilts					
<i>Himantopus mexicanus</i>	Black-necked stilt				D
Sandpipers, Plovers, and Relatives					
<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Common snipe				x
<i>Tringa melanoleuca</i>	Greater yellowlegs			B	x, B
<i>Tringa flavipes</i>	Lesser yellowlegs	x			
<i>Limosa fedoa</i>	Marbled godwit	D		D	D
<i>Pluvialis fulva</i>	Pacific golden plover				D
<i>Calidris alba</i>	Sanderling	D		D	D
<i>Actitis macularia</i>	Spotted sandpiper				D
<i>Aphriza virgata</i>	Surfbird				D
<i>Calidris mauri</i>	Western sandpiper				D
<i>Catoptrophorus semipalmatus</i>	Willet	D			D
<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Wilson's snipe			B	
Gulls and Terns					
<i>Larus californicus</i>	California gull	x	x	x	x
<i>Larus heermanni</i>	Heermann's gull	x			x
<i>Larus delawarensis</i>	Ring-billed gull				x
<i>Larus occidentalis</i>	Western gull	x	x	x	x
Doves and Pigeons					
<i>Zenaida macroura</i>	Mourning dove	x	x	x	x
<i>Columba livia</i>	Rock dove	x	x	x	x
Owls					
<i>Tyto alba</i>	Barn owl	A ⁽²⁾			
<i>Athene cunicularia</i>	Burrowing owl				adj. to A (only observed in Dec. 1998)
<i>Bubo virginianus</i>	Great-horned owl	A ⁽²⁾			
Swifts					
<i>Chaetura pelagica</i>	Chimney swift				x
Hummingbirds					
<i>Selasphorus sasin</i>	Allen's hummingbird	A			
<i>Calypte anna</i>	Anna's hummingbird	A		A	A, C
<i>Archilochus alexandri</i>	Black-chinned hummingbird	C			
<i>Calypte costae</i>	Costa's hummingbird	A, C			A, C
<i>Archilochus colubris</i>	Ruby-throated hummingbird			A	
Kingfishers					
<i>Ceryle alcyon</i>	Belted kingfisher			A	A
Woodpeckers					
<i>Colaptes auratus</i>	Northern flicker	x		A	x, A
Tyrant Flycatchers					
<i>Sayornis nigricans</i>	Black phoebe	A, B, C		B	A, B, C
<i>Sayornis saya</i>	Say's phoebe				A, C, D, GC
<i>Tyrannus verticalis</i>	Western kingbird	A, C			

Table B-1 (cont.). Wildlife Species Observed at NBVC Port Hueneme

Scientific Name	Common name	Occurrence ⁽¹⁾			
		Sp	Su	F	W
BIRDS (cont.)					
Swallows					
<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Barn swallow	x			x
<i>Petrochelidon fulva</i>	Cliff swallow	x			
<i>Tachycineta thalassina</i>	Violet-green swallow	x			
Jays, Crows, and Magpies					
<i>Corvus brachyrhynchos</i>	American crow	x	x	x	x
<i>Corvus corax</i>	Common raven	x	x	x	x
Bushtits					
<i>Psaltriparus minimus</i>	Bushtit	C			
Wrens					
<i>Cistothorus palustris</i>	Marsh wren			A	A
Old World Warblers, Thrushes, Gnatcatchers, and Kinglets					
<i>Polioptila caerulea</i>	Blue-grey gnatcatcher	C		A	C
<i>Catharus guttatus</i>	Hermit thrush			C	
Mockingbirds and Thrashers					
<i>Toxostoma redivivum</i>	California thrasher			C	
<i>Mimus polyglottos</i>	Northern mockingbird	x, A		A	x, A
Shrikes					
<i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>	Loggerhead shrike				A, C
Vireos					
<i>Vireo huttoni</i>	Hutton's vireo	C			
<i>Vireo gilvus</i>	Warbling vireo	C			
Starlings					
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>	European starling	x	x	x	x
Blackbirds					
<i>Euphagus cyanocephalus</i>	Brewer's blackbird	x			x
<i>Quiscalus mexicanus</i>	Great-tailed grackle	x			x
<i>Icterus cucullatus</i>	Hooded oriole	A			
<i>Agelaius phoeniceus</i>	Red-winged blackbird	A		A	A
<i>Sturnella neglecta</i>	Western meadowlark	x		A	x, A, C
Wood Warblers					
<i>Geothlypis trichas</i>	Common yellowthroat	A, C		A	A
<i>Wilsonia pusilla</i>	Wilson's warbler				C
<i>Dendroica coronata</i>	Yellow-rumped warbler	A, C			A, C
<i>Dendroica petechia</i>	Yellow warbler	A, C			
Sparrows, Buntings, Towhees, and Relatives					
<i>Pipilo crissalis</i>	California towhee	A		C	
<i>Spizella passerina</i>	Chipping sparrow			A, C	A, C
<i>Melospiza melodia</i>	Song sparrow			A, C	A, C
<i>Zonotrichia leucophrys</i>	White-crowned sparrow	A, C		A, C	A, C
Finches and Relatives					
<i>Carduelis tristis</i>	American goldfinch	A		A	
<i>Carpodacus mexicanus</i>	House finch	x	x	x	x
<i>Carduelis psaltria</i>	Lesser goldfinch				A
Old World Sparrows					
<i>Passer domesticus</i>	House sparrow	x	x	x	x

Notes: ⁽¹⁾ Spring = Mar-May; Summer = Jun-Aug; Fall = Sep-Nov; Winter = Dec-Feb. x = NBVC Port Hueneme in general or exact location unknown, A= observed in SINA A, B = SINA B, C = SINA C, D = SINA D, GC = Golf Course.

⁽²⁾ only sign was observed (e.g., pellets and feathers).

Sources: Anteon 1999; U.S. Navy 1999; TEC 2002, 2003, 2004.

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SUMMARY OF FIELD NOTES FOR THE 3 ADDITIONAL SURVEYS

1-2 November 2003

SINA A: black phoebe, European starling, American crow, northern mockingbird, western meadowlark, loggerhead shrike, American goldfinch, yellow-rumped warbler, house finch, blue-gray gnatcatcher, mourning dove, American kestrel, red-tailed hawk, white-crowned sparrow, great blue heron, black-crowned night heron, common yellow throat, common raven, northern flicker, Anna's hummingbird, merlin.

SINA B: horned grebe, red-tailed hawk, California ground squirrel, greater yellowlegs, great egret, mallard, horned grebe, cattle egret, snowy egret, Wilson's snipe, black phoebe, black-crowned night heron, killdeer.

SINA C: hermit thrush, California towhee, California thrasher, white-crowned sparrow.

SINA D: willet, marbled godwit, western gull, California gull, Heermann's gull, pelagic cormorant, sanderling, mourning dove, brown pelican.

16 January 2004

SINA A: northern mockingbird, northern flicker, red-winged blackbird, black phoebe, great blue heron, black-crowned night heron, yellow-rumped warbler, California gull, western gull, European starling, American crow, western meadowlark.

SINA B: greater yellowlegs, mallard, mourning dove, snowy egret, black phoebe, great blue heron, American kestrel, feral cat.

SINA C: loggerhead shrike, blue-gray gnatcatcher, Anna's hummingbird, western meadowlark, white-crowned sparrow, yellow-rumped warbler, house finch, black phoebe, Wilson's warbler.

SINA D: harbor seal, black oystercatcher, Pacific golden plover, willet, sanderling, surf scoter, pelagic cormorant, western and California gull, Say's phoebe, common loon, marbled godwit; road-kill Virginia opossum on road.

Golf Course ponds: mallard, lesser scaup, American coot, Brewer's blackbird, European starling, American crow, western and California gull.

7 March 2004

SINA A: red-tailed hawk, red-winged blackbird, house finch, black phoebe, yellow-rumped warbler, black-crowned night heron, great blue heron, northern mockingbird, common raven, European starling, white-crowned sparrow, California and western gull, Anna's hummingbird.

SINA B: California ground squirrel, black phoebe, snowy egret, mallard, snowy egret, rock dove.

SINA C: blue-gray gnatcatcher, house finch, white-crowned sparrow.

SINA D: marbled godwit; sanderling; western, Heermann's, and California gull; willet, black scoter.

Golf Course ponds: mallard, greater yellowlegs, Say's phoebe, western gull.

**WILDLIFE SURVEYS AT CBC PORT HUENEME AND NAS POINT MUGU
FINAL REPORT**

October 15, 2005

Martin Ruane, Ecologist
NBVC Point Mugu
Environmental Division, N45V
B613, Laguna/12th St.
Point Mugu, CA 93042

Subject: Wildlife Surveys at CBC Port Hueneme and NAS Point Mugu – Final Report

1.0 INTRODUCTION

During 2005, wildlife surveys were conducted at CBC Port Hueneme and NAS Point Mugu as part of a continuing wildlife monitoring effort for 4 Special Interest Natural Areas (SINAs) at CBC Port Hueneme (Figure 1) and a new wildlife survey effort for 4 wetland-associated areas at NAS Point Mugu (Figure 2). The survey areas at NAS Point Mugu were prioritized by Martin Ruane, Environmental Division Ecologist. Survey area 1 had the highest survey priority followed by the 3 other sites.

Wildlife surveys within both CBC Port Hueneme and NAS Point Mugu focused primarily on birds but other wildlife were also noted (e.g., mammals). Bird species were identified by visual and/or auditory means. Bird identification by song or call was done primarily during the breeding season and in areas of thick vegetation where visual identification was not possible. However, formal point counts were not conducted. In addition, no effort was made to try and determine breeding status of any species. That is, nest searches or observations were not conducted to determine if a particular species was breeding in any of the survey areas on either installation. For surveys conducted at NAS Point Mugu, the total number of individuals of each bird species was estimated for each survey area for each survey date. These estimates are based on the observation of a species within a portion of a particular survey area and then extrapolating this estimate throughout the rest of the survey area given the amount of suitable habitat for the particular species.

Following is a brief description of the survey areas within CBC Port Hueneme and NAS Point Mugu. Further discussion and a summary of previous wildlife surveys at the SINAs, CBC Port Hueneme, can be found in the 2003 *Wildlife Survey Report and Habitat and Restoration Plan, Naval Base Ventura County, Port Hueneme Site*.

1.1 CBC Port Hueneme

SINA A – Bulrush-Cattail Habitat. Area A is located in the northwestern part of CBC Port Hueneme, north of 23rd Avenue (Figure 1). It encompasses approximately 1.4 acres consisting of a relatively narrow band of freshwater marsh habitat approximately 1,200 ft long and 50 ft wide. Area A is divided into 2 unequal sections by a dirt road, fragmenting the habitat into 2 separate marshes. SINA A is dominated by freshwater marsh vegetation including California bulrush (*Scirpus californicus*), common reed (*Phragmites australis*), and broad-leaved cattail (*Typha latifolia*). Arroyo willow (*Salix lasiolepis*) and narrowleaf willow (*S. exigua*) are present on the upland areas. Other native species include coyote brush (*Baccharis pilularis*) at the edges of the area, western ragweed (*Ambrosia psilostachya*), and horseweed (*Conyza canadensis*). Non-native species found in Area A include sweetclovers (*Melilotus indicus*, *M.*

albus), English plantain (*Plantago lanceolata*), tree tobacco (*Nicotiana glauca*), annual brome grasses (*Bromus* spp.), fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*), and ngaio tree (*Myoporum laetum*).

SINA B – Bulrush-Cattail Habitat. Totalling approximately 8.0 acres, SINA B comprises a system of relatively steep-walled drainage channels in the western and southwestern part of CBC Port Hueneme (Figure 1). The widest of these channels lies northeast of Logistics Way, runs into Port Hueneme harbor, and is approximately 800 ft in length. Other narrower channels extend about 4,400 ft along Pennsylvania Avenue, about 2,000 ft along Pleasant Valley Road, about 1,050 ft between Cargo Road and Pacific Avenue, about 1,850 ft north of Lehman Road, and about 2,200 ft along 23rd Avenue. The drainage ditches have some marsh vegetation. In general, Area B does not have dense vegetation, since the channels are cleared regularly. Under unmaintained conditions, the channels have freshwater marsh species such as California bulrush, broad-leaved cattail, and common reed. Native species within SINA B under current maintained conditions include plant species found in salt marshes or saline soils, such as saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*), pickleweed (*Salicornia virginica*), and heliotrope (*Heliotropium curassavicum*). Non-native species in this area include golden crownbeard (*Verbesina encelioides* ssp. *exauriculata*), sweetclovers, New Zealand spinach (*Tetragonia tetragonioides*), red-stemmed filaree (*Erodium cicutarium*), and annual brome grasses on higher terrain; brass buttons (*Cotula coronopifolia*) occurs within the channels. Two of the channels are somewhat different from most of the drainages that comprise SINA B: the 23rd Avenue Channel slopes have been stabilized with erosion control blankets, and the Lehman Road Channel bottom has not been cleared recently and has the marsh species California bulrush, chairmaker's bulrush (*Scirpus americanus*) and broad-leaved cattail. The slopes of most of the drainages in SINA B have the exotic species iceplant (*Carpobrotus edulis*) and crystalline iceplant (*Mesembryanthemum crystallinum*); a few isolated clumps of pampas grass (*Cortaderia* spp.) and myoporum are also present.

SINA C – Coyote Brush Habitat. The 3.9-acre SINA C lies north of 23rd Avenue and along Track No. 14 Road in the northwestern part of CBC Hueneme (Figure 1). It is composed primarily of upland scrub habitat, extends approximately 1,350 ft north to south, and is about 120 to 140 ft wide. SINA C has upland scrub vegetation dominated by coyote brush. Small clumps of arroyo willow occur; other native species include saw-toothed goldenbush (*Hazardia squarrosa*), isolated mule fat (*Baccharis salicifolia*), and telegraph weed (*Heterotheca grandiflora*). Non-native species include red-stemmed filaree, golden crownbeard, and Russian thistle (*Salsola tragus*). Many introduced annual grasses are also present in SINA C, including ripgut brome (*Bromus diandrus*) compact brome (*B. madritensis* ssp. *rubens*), slender wild oat (*Avena barbata*), Bermuda grass (*Cynodon dactylon*), and smilo grass (*Piptatherum miliaceum*). Exotic species included myoporum, occurring in relatively high numbers, and small isolated patches of Australian saltbush (*Atriplex semibaccata*), pampas grass, and iceplant.

SINA D – Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage and Sandy Beach Habitat. SINA D lies in the extreme southwestern corner of CBC Port Hueneme (Figure 1). It is bounded by Port Hueneme harbor to the south and the City of Port Hueneme to the west and north. It consists of 2 portions: a sandy beach in the south below mean sea level extending about 700 ft west to east, and a foredune area to the west and north extending about 1,050 ft inland. In total, SINA D is composed of approximately 4.4 acres of beach and foredune vegetation. The sandy beach in the south is subject to wave action and scouring and is bare. The low bluff above the beach includes the native species beach-bur and beach evening primrose (*Camissonia cheiranthifolia* ssp. *suffruticosa*); introduced plants include annual grasses, sourclover (*Melilotus indicus*), sea rocket (*Cakile maritima*), and golden crownbeard. The exotic species iceplant densely covers the top of the bluff. The foredune area and bluff to the southwest have the native species beach bur, dune saltbush (*Atriplex leucophylla*), heliotrope, and saltgrass. Vegetation farther away from the beach on the slopes and tops of the dunes to the west and southwest includes the native species sand verbena, beach-bur, and beach morning-glory (*Calystegia soldanella*); this area also has beach evening primrose and telegraph weed. Introduced species seen in these foredunes include sourclover, white

sweetclover (*Melilotus albus*), sea rocket, red-stemmed filaree, scarlet pimpernel (*Anagallis arvensis*), isolated myoporum, and weedy cudweed (*Gnaphalium luteo-album*). Non-native grasses include ripgut brome, water bent grass (*Agrostis viridis*), and annual beard grass (*Polypogon monspeliensis*). In general, SINA D has a high cover of the exotic species iceplant; other exotics include crystalline iceplant and Australian saltbush.

1.2 NAS Point Mugu

Survey Area 1. Site 1 is southwest of the Channel Islands Air National Guard taxiway and is bordered on its western edge by Perimeter Rd. and by transitional disturbed habitat to the east, north, and south (Figure 2). The habitat type of Area 1 is freshwater marsh dominated by southern cattail (*Typha domingensis*), California bulrush, and the submergent ditch grass widgeongrass (*Ruppia maritima*). The overstory is dominated by willows (*Salix* spp.).

Survey Areas 2 and 3. Areas 2 and 3 are bordered by Perimeter Rd. and the Point Mugu Duck Club to the west, and transitional disturbed habitat to the east, north, and south (Figure 2). Similar to Area 1, the habitat type of Area 2 is freshwater marsh dominated by southern cattail, California bulrush, and the submergent ditch grass with an overstory of willows and ngaio tree.

Survey Area 4. Site 4 is bordered by Perimeter Rd. to the north, Cotar Rd. to the west, and transitional disturbed habitat on the east and south. The habitat type of site 4 is freshwater marsh and is similar in structure and composition as Areas 2 and 3. However, the overstory vegetation of Area 4 is dominated by the invasive ngaio tree.

2.0 SURVEY RESULTS

Surveys were conducted on the mornings of February 19, April 23, May 27, July 23, August 20, September 10, and September 24 by Rick Spaulding, Senior Wildlife Biologist.

2.1 CBC Port Hueneme

A total of 44 bird species were observed during the 2005 surveys of the 4 SINAs at CBC Port Hueneme (Table 1). Most of the species were observed during all seasons of the year, but some migratory or seasonal species were also observed such as black turnstone, merlin, bushtit, white-crowned sparrow, common yellowthroat, Wilson's warbler, and yellow-rumped warbler. The greatest number of species was observed in SINA A (18) and the fewest in SINA C (11), with 15 and 14 species observed in SINA B and D, respectively.

Mammal species observed included feral cats on most survey dates and predominantly in SINAs A and B. Although no marine mammals were observed directly within SINA D (i.e., onshore), 3 species were observed in the adjacent waters: harbor seal (*Phoca vitulina*), California sea lion (*Zalophus californianus*), and bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*). Up to 3 California sea lions and 2 harbor seals were observed in May and September approximately 100 meters from shore. In addition, California sea lions were frequently observed on the channel buoy approximately ½ mile west of the harbor entrance. Although harbor seals have been observed on the beach at Port Hueneme in surveys conducted in prior years, no pinnipeds were observed hauled out during the 2005 surveys.

2.1 NAS Point Mugu

A total of 35 bird species were observed or detected during the 2005 surveys of the 4 survey areas at NAS Point Mugu. Area 1 (A1) had the greatest number of species and the greatest number of individuals. The most prevalent species observed in any area at any time of the year was the house finch.

Based upon the species observed, the number of individuals, and the proximity of the surveys areas to the active runways, none of the wetland-dominated survey areas are expected to be a concern with respect to Bird-Aircraft Strike Hazard (BASH) potential at NAS Point Mugu. None of the areas is a major attractant for waterfowl or other large birds that might pose a significant BASH risk, particularly since the areas that were surveyed are surrounded by much more extensive open, wetland areas and canals that are greater bird attractants. The only concern regarding these areas and their proximity to the runways is the potential for higher, woody vegetation to become established closer to the runways. Continued management of the perimeter of all of the wetland areas by mowing in proximity to the runways in accordance with the NAS Point Mugu BASH Plan will prevent the establishment of thick or high brush and provide a sufficient reduction in BASH potential.

If you have any questions or require further information regarding the surveys or observations, please don't hesitate to contact me at (206) 855-4997 or rlspaulding@tecinc.com. Thank you for the opportunity to support NBVC.

Sincerely,

Rick Spaulding
Senior Biologist

LEGEND

- CBC Port Hueneme Boundary
- Road
- Special Interest Natural Area A (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)
- Special Interest Natural Area B (Bulrush-Cattail Habitat)
- Special Interest Natural Area C (Coyote Brush Habitat)
- Special Interest Natural Area D (Sand Verbena-Beach Bursage and Sandy Beach Habitat)
- Seabee Earthmoving Training Area
- - - Golf Course
- Surface Water

Figure 1
Special Interest Natural Areas at CBC Port Hueneme

Figure 2
Wildlife Survey Areas at NAS Point Mugu

Table 1. Bird Species Observed within SINAs on CBC Port Hueneme (2005)

Species	Survey Date ⁽¹⁾						
	2/19	4/23	5/27	7/23	8/20	9/10	9/24
Pelicans							
California brown pelican (<i>Pelecanus occidentalis</i>)	D		D	D	D	D	D
Cormorants							
Double-crested cormorant (<i>Phalacrocorax auritus</i>)	D			D	C, D	D	D
Hérons, Egrets, and Bitterns							
Black-crowned night heron (<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>)		A	A	A	A		A
Great blue heron (<i>Ardea herodias</i>)		A	A	C	C		
Great egret (<i>Casmerodius albus</i>)						B	
Green heron (<i>Butorides striatus</i>)	A						
Snowy egret (<i>Egretta thula</i>)	B			C	C	B	B
Ducks, Geese, and Swans							
Mallard (<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>)	B	C				B	B
Hawks, Falcons, Kites, and Eagles							
Merlin (<i>Falco columbarius</i>)	A						
Red-tailed hawk (<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>)			A				
Rails, Coots, and Gallinules							
American coot (<i>Fulica americana</i>)	B						
Oystercatchers							
Black oystercatcher (<i>Haematopus bachmani</i>)		D					D
Sandpipers, Plovers, and Relatives							
Black turnstone (<i>Arenaria melanocephala</i>)		D					
Marbled godwit (<i>Limosa fedoa</i>)						D	
Long-billed curlew (<i>Numenius americanus</i>)				D			
Whimbrel (<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>)					D		
Sanderling (<i>Calidris alba</i>)	D	D					D
Willet (<i>Catoptrophorus semipalmatus</i>)	D	D		D	D	D	
Wandering tattler (<i>Heteroscelus incanus</i>)							D
Gulls and Terns							
California gull (<i>Larus californicus</i>)		D	D	D	D	D	D
Heermann's gull (<i>Larus heermanni</i>)	D	D	D	D	D	D	D
Ring-billed gull (<i>Larus delawarensis</i>)	D						
Western gull (<i>Larus occidentalis</i>)	D	D	D	D	D	D	D
Doves and Pigeons							
Mourning dove (<i>Zenaida macroura</i>)	A	A, B	A, B	A, B	B	A	
Rock dove (<i>Columba livia</i>)	B	B	B	B	B	B	B
Owls							
Barn owl (<i>Tyto alba</i>) ⁽²⁾	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Great-horned owl (<i>Bubo virginianus</i>) ⁽²⁾	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Hummingbirds							
Anna's hummingbird (<i>Calypte anna</i>)	A		A	A, B		A, C	A, C
Tyrant Flycatchers							
Black phoebe (<i>Sayornis nigricans</i>)	A	C				A, B	A
Western kingbird (<i>Tyrannus verticalis</i>)		A		B			A
Swallows							
Barn swallow (<i>Hirundo rustica</i>)			A				
Jays, Crows, and Magpies							
Common raven (<i>Corvus corax</i>)	B, C						
Bushtits							
Bushtit (<i>Psaltriparus minimus</i>)		B	B	B			
Wrens							
Marsh wren (<i>Cistothorus palustris</i>)	A						

Table 1. Bird Species Observed within SINAs on CBC Port Hueneme (2005)

Species	Survey Date ⁽¹⁾						
	2/19	4/23	5/27	7/23	8/20	9/10	9/24
Mockingbirds and Thrashers							
Northern mockingbird (<i>Mimus polyglottos</i>)		A, B	A, B	A, B	A, B	A, C	A, C
Starlings							
European starling (<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>)			B				
Blackbirds							
Red-winged blackbird (<i>Agelaius phoeniceus</i>)	A	A					
Wood Warblers							
Common yellowthroat (<i>Geothlypis trichas</i>)		A			A	C	
Wilson's warbler (<i>Wilsonia pusilla</i>)					A		
Yellow-rumped warbler (<i>Dendroica coronata</i>)	A, C						
Sparrows, Buntings, Towhees, and Relatives							
California towhee (<i>Pipilo crissalis</i>)	A		A, B	A, B			
Song sparrow (<i>Melospiza melodia</i>)		A					B
White-crowned sparrow (<i>Zonotrichia leucophrys</i>)	A						
Finches and Relatives							
House finch (<i>Carpodacus mexicanus</i>)		A, B	A, B	A, B	A, B	A, C	A, C

Notes: ⁽¹⁾Letters refer to the SINAs on CBC Port Hueneme. Refer to Figure 1.

⁽²⁾Only sign observed (e.g., feather(s) and pellets).

Table 2. Bird Species Observed within Survey Areas on NAS Point Mugu (2005)

Species	<u>Survey Date*</u>						
	2/19	4/23	5/28	7/23	8/20	9/10	9/24
Loons and Grebes							
Pied-billed grebe (<i>Podilymbus podiceps</i>)						A3 (1)	
Herons, Egrets, and Bitterns							
Black-crowned night heron (<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>)					A2 (1) A3 (1)		
Least bittern (<i>Ixobrychus exilis</i>)						A1 (1)	
Ducks, Geese, and Swans							
Mallard (<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>)		A1 (1) A2 (6)					
Hawks, Falcons, Kites, and Eagles							
American kestrel (<i>Falco sparverius</i>)					A3 (1)		
Plovers and Relatives							
Killdeer (<i>Charadrius vociferous</i>)	A2, A3						
Doves and Pigeons							
Mourning dove (<i>Zenaida macroura</i>)			A1 (4) A2 (4)	A1 (4)	A1 (6)		
Owls							
Barn owl (<i>Tyto alba</i>)				A1**	A2**		
Swifts							
Chimney swift (<i>Chaetura pelagica</i>)							
Hummingbirds							
Anna's hummingbird (<i>Calypte anna</i>)	A1, A2			A1 (2)	A1 (1) A2 (2)	A2 (3)	
Woodpeckers							
Downy woodpecker (<i>Picoides pubescens</i>)		A2 (1)					
Northern flicker (<i>Colaptes auratus</i>)	A1						
Tyrant Flycatchers							
Black phoebe (<i>Sayornis nigricans</i>)	A1, A2	A2 (4)		A2 (6) A3 (6)	A1, A2, A3, A4 (all areas 3 ea.)	A2 (1) A3 (2) A4 (3)	A2 (2) A3 (3) A4 (1)
Say's phoebe (<i>Sayornis saya</i>)	A1, A2						A1 (1)
Western kingbird (<i>Tyrannus verticalis</i>)	A3	A1 (2) A2 (2)		A2 (2) A3 (4)	A1 (2) A2 (3)		A2 (2)
Swifts and Swallows							
Vaux's swift (<i>Chaetura vauxi</i>)							A1 (5) A2 (4)
Barn swallow (<i>Hirundo rustica</i>)				A1 (8) A2 (8)	A1, A2, A3, A4 (all areas 5 ea.)	A1, A2, A3, A4 (all areas 5 ea.)	A1, A2, A3, A4 (all areas 3 ea.)
Tree swallow (<i>Tachycineta bicolor</i>)	A1		A1 (6)				
Bushtits							
Bushtit (<i>Psaltriparus minimus</i>)	A2	A1 (12) A2 (5)	A3 (4)		A2 (15)	A3 (25)	A2 (12)
Mockingbirds and Thrashers							
Northern mockingbird (<i>Mimus polyglottos</i>)	A3			A3 (8)	A4 (2)	A1 (4) A2 (2)	A1 (3) A2 (2)
Shrikes							
Loggerhead shrike (<i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>)					A2 (1)		
Vireos							
Warbling vireo (<i>Vireo gilvus</i>)		A1 (6) A2 (2)					

Table 2. Bird Species Observed within Survey Areas on NAS Point Mugu (2005)

Species	<u>Survey Date*</u>						
	2/19	4/23	5/28	7/23	8/20	9/10	9/24
Starlings							
European starling (<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>)	A2						A2 (2) A4 (2)
Blackbirds							
Great-tailed grackle (<i>Quiscalus mexicanus</i>)	A2	A1 (2)					
Red-winged blackbird (<i>Agelaius phoeniceus</i>)	A1, A2, A3	A1 (6)	A1 (6) A2 (6) A3 (6)	A3 (25)		A4 (2)	A3 (3) A4 (3)
Wood Warblers							
Common yellowthroat (<i>Geothlypis trichas</i>)	A2			A3 (1)	A1 (10) A2 (3) A3 (4)	A1 (6)	A2 (5)
Wilson's warbler (<i>Wilsonia pusilla</i>)			A1 (1)				
Yellow-rumped warbler (<i>Dendroica coronata</i>)	A1, A2						
Yellow warbler (<i>Dendroica petechia</i>)		A1 (14)			A2 (17) A3 (5) A4 (5)	A2 (8) A3 (8) A4 (2)	A2 (5) A4 (3)
Sparrows, Buntings, Towhees, and Relatives							
California towhee (<i>Pipilo crissalis</i>)	A1	A1 (4)	A1 (2)	A2 (4)		A1 (4)	A2 (3)
Song sparrow (<i>Melospiza melodia</i>)	A1	A1 (18)	A1 (8) A2 (6) A3 (6)		A1 (18) A4 (8)	A2 (6) A3 (6) A4 (5)	A1 (5) A2 (3) A4 (4)
White-crowned sparrow (<i>Zonotrichia leucophrys</i>)	A1, A2						
Lark sparrow (<i>Chondestes grammacus</i>)	A1					A1 (3)	
Finches and Relatives							
American goldfinch (<i>Carduelis tristis</i>)			A2 (14)	A1 (8)			
House finch (<i>Carpodacus mexicanus</i>)	A1, A2	A1 (30)	A1 (45) A2 (45)	A1 (20) A2 (18)	A1 (8) A2 (11) A3 (18) A4 (24)	A1 (12) A2 (10) A3 (12) A4 (15)	A1 (11) A2 (12) A3 (6) A4 (10)

Notes: * A1, A2, and A3 refer to the survey areas on NAS Point Mugu. Refer to Figure 2. Numbers in parentheses are estimated number of individuals within the survey area.

** Feather only.

**MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES ASSESSMENT FOR THE PORT
HUENEME SEDIMENT DREDGING AND
CONFINED AQUATIC DISPOSAL PROJECT**

**MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES ASSESSMENT FOR THE
PORT HUENEME SEDIMENT DREDGING AND CONFINED
AQUATIC DISPOSAL PROJECT**

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June 2008

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Introduction..... 2
Methods..... 2
Results..... 4
 Physical Site Conditions..... 4
 Marine Biological Resources Within the Survey Area..... 6
 Port Hueneme 6
 Flora..... 6
 Fish 6
 Invertebrates 6
 Beach Disposal Area..... 8
 Sensitive Species 8
Discussion 9
References..... 10
Appendix A..... 11

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Project area map - Port Hueneme, California..... 3
Figure 2. Marine biological survey and resource map..... 5

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Fish captured or observed within the survey area..... 6
Table 2. Invertebrates observed or captured within the survey area..... 7
Table 3. Protected species observed or expected to occur within the survey area..... 9

MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES ASSESSMENT FOR THE PORT HUENEME SEDIMENT DREDGING AND CONFINED AQUATIC DISPOSAL PROJECT

Merkel & Associates, Inc.
June 2008

INTRODUCTION

Bechtel Environmental, Incorporated has contracted Merkel & Associates, Inc. (M&A) to conduct an assessment of marine biological resources within Port Hueneme (Port) in support of the Port Hueneme Contaminated Sediment Dredging and Confined Aquatic Disposal Site Construction (Project). The project area includes all of Port Hueneme, including the Approach Channel, Entrance Channel, Turning Basin, and North Harbor Area, as well as a portion of Hueneme Beach that will receive some dredged material (Figure 1). Although outside of the direct project footprint, areas bounded by the jetties at the entrance to the Port, but outside of the Entrance Channel, were included in the survey results.

The survey goal was to document existing marine biological resources within both the Port and adjacent disposal site at Hueneme Beach. Emphasis was given to demersal and epi-benthic organisms in support of other efforts to assess and minimize the potential impacts of the dredging project.

METHODS

M&A biologists, Dr. Robert Mooney, Rachel Woodfield, and Seth Jones, conducted a marine biological survey of the project area on May 28 and 29, 2008. The survey area included the regions described above (Figure 1). The scope of the study, however, did not include the areas near the entrance jetties, so a comprehensive description of the kelp beds for this region was not provided. A SCUBA-based observation of the survey area was not possible; and as a result, a variety of other techniques (described below) were utilized.

An assessment of in-water habitats was conducted using side-scan sonar, which provided an image of seafloor backscatter within the entire project area. Interpretation of the backscatter data allowed for an assessment of the distribution of eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) and kelp. Side-scan backscatter data were acquired at a frequency of 600 kHz, with a scanning range of 50 m for both the starboard and port channels, resulting in a 100-m wide swath. All data were collected in latitude and longitude using the North American Datum of 1983 (NAD 83). The survey was conducted by running transects spaced to allow for overlap between adjoining side-scan swaths. Transect surveys were performed until the entirety of the survey area was captured in the survey record.

Following completion of the survey, the data were converted to the Universal Transverse Mercator system in meters (NAD 83), converted into a geographically registered photo-mosaic through digital post-processing, and plotted on a geo-rectified aerial image of the project site. Marine resources of interest were then digitized to show their distribution within the survey area.

Project Overview Map
Marine Biological Resources Assessment at Port Hueneme
and Adjacent Beach Disposal Site
Port Hueneme, CA
May 2008

Figure 1

An otter trawl was used to document the benthic fish and macroinvertebrate communities within the survey area. The trawl consisted of a 4.6-m trawl with 2-cm mesh in the body and 0.3-cm mesh in the cod end. The otter trawl was deployed from a survey vessel in seven locations within the Port and at two locations within the beach disposal site (Figure 2). All fish and invertebrates samples were identified and counted in order to generate a list of species that characterizes the various regions within the Port and disposal area.

A remotely operated vehicle (ROV) was utilized in an effort to further examine the bottom and to ground-truth the side-scan interpretation. The ROV was deployed and piloted from the survey vessel. The resulting imagery was displayed in real-time on the vessel where it was monitored by the biologists and also later reviewed in the laboratory. Using this technique, it was possible to document the benthic substrate, as well as to search for both floral resources such as eelgrass and surfgrass (*Phyllospadix* spp.) and any fauna that was present.

The beach disposal area was surveyed on foot during a tide of +0.2 m Mean Lower Low Water (MLLW) in order to search for evidence of marine life in the intertidal zone, including Pismo clams (*Tivela stultorum*).

RESULTS

PHYSICAL SITE CONDITIONS

In general, Port Hueneme is bounded by pile-supported shipping piers and sheet pile walls, with some areas of riprap shoreline that include jetties along the entrance to the Port. The depth throughout most of the Port is approximately -11 to -14 m (MLLW), with shallower areas present in the corners of the entrance jetties that range from approximately 0 to -5 m water depth (MLLW). The substrate is predominantly characterized by mud, with occasional rock debris at the base of the inlet jetties and sand along the beaches formed inside of the west and east jetties. The entrance channel shoreline slopes steeply from shore into the navigation channel. Two other small intertidal areas outside of the project area occur within the port: one at the far north end of North Harbor and one at the far east end of the area bounded by Berths 3 and 5.

The beach disposal area is located along the shoreline of Hueneme Beach. Much of the upper edge of the area is bounded by riprap revetment. At the eastern end of the placement area there is an intertidal sandy beach, with large riprap debris scattered throughout the sand. The subtidal portion of the site extends to a depth of approximately -3 m MLLW and is bare sand. No exposed rocky reef was detected from the sonar or ROV data.

Marine Biological Resources Map
Marine Biological Resources Assessment at Port Hueneme
and Adjacent Beach Disposal Site
Port Hueneme, CA
May 2008

Figure 2

MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES WITHIN THE SURVEY AREA

Port Hueneme

Flora

Kelp was documented along the riprap of the west and east jetties, as well as along much of the shoreline of the entrance channel and in the North Harbor. The kelp present was primarily giant kelp (*Macrocystis pyrifera*), with occasional patches of feather boa kelp (*Egregia menziesii*) on the shallower intertidal riprap. No kelp was found within the dredge footprint. Drift algae was observed in patches on the bottom and generally consisted of species of *Ulva*, *Gracilaria*, *Mastocarpus papillatus*, and *Macrocystis*, mixed with open coastal species that presumably drifted in from outside of the port, such as *Cystoseira*. The invasive non-native species of kelp *Undaria pinnatifida* was observed on the docks and hulls of docked vessels at the far eastern end of the port. It is not anticipated that dredging activities would facilitate the spread of this species out of the Port, provided that vessels associated with dredging did not transport sporophytes out of the harbor on their hulls. The invasive seaweed *Caulerpa* was not observed during the survey, and protocol surveys for its presence will be conducted between 45 and 90 days prior to the initiation of dredging (NMFS 2001).

Fish

A total of 13 fish species from 11 families were captured in the Port. They are summarized in Table 1. A list identifying count and otter trawl transect is included as Appendix A of this report.

Table 1. Fish captured or observed within the survey area.

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name
Agonidae	<i>Odontopyxis trispinosa</i>	Pygmy poacher
Atherinidae	<i>Atherinops affinis</i>	Topsmelt
Bothidae	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab
Clinidae	<i>Gibbonsia elegans</i>	Spotted kelpfish
Cottidae	<i>Artedius harringtoni</i>	Scalyhead sculpin
Cottidae	<i>Leptocottus armatus</i>	Pacific staghorn sculpin
Cottidae	<i>Scorpaenichthys marmoratus</i>	Cabazon
Pleuronectidae	<i>Pleuronichthys verticalis</i>	Hornyhead turbot
Scorpaenidae	<i>Sebastes dallii</i>	Calico rockfish
Sparidae	<i>Sepiphus politus</i>	Queenfish
Syngnathidae	<i>Syngnathus griseolineatus</i>	Bay pipefish
Embiotocidae	<i>Rhacochilus vacca</i>	Pile Perch
Synodontidae	<i>Synodus lucioceps</i>	California lizardfish

All fish captured or observed during the survey were found within the Port except for a single speckled sanddab that was captured offshore within the Hueneme Beach disposal area.

Invertebrates

Invertebrates representing 21 families were observed in the Port (Table 2). Two of these were only identified to order but were each included in the family count. A list broken out by count and otter trawl transect is included in Appendix A of this report. All of the organisms listed in Table 2 were captured or observed within the Port. The only invertebrates captured at the disposal site were Dungeness crab and mysid shrimp.

Table 2. Invertebrates observed or captured within the survey area.

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name
Aeolidiidae	<i>Hermisenda sp.</i>	Aeolid
Aglajidae	<i>Navanax inermis</i>	Navanax
Balanidae	<i>Balanus sp.</i>	Acorn barnacle
Cancridae	<i>Cancer magister</i>	Dungeness crab
Cancridae	<i>Cancer sp.</i>	Cancer crab
Caprellidae	*	Caprellid amphipod
Crangonidae	<i>Crangon alaskensis</i>	Northern crangon
Crangonidae	<i>Crangon nigromaculata</i>	Black spotted shrimp
Crangonidae	<i>Metacrangon munita</i>	Coastal spinyhead
Curculionoidea	<i>Asterina miniata</i>	Bat star
Curculionoidea	<i>Pisaster ochraceus</i>	Ochre sea star
Dendrasteridae	<i>Dendraster excentricus</i>	Sand Dollar
Dendronotidae	<i>Dendronotus iris</i>	Rainbow dendronotus
Gammaridae	*	Gammarid amphipod
Inachoididae	<i>Pyromaia tuberculata</i>	Tuberculate pear crab
Majidae	<i>Pugettia producta</i>	Northern kelp crab
Mysida (order)	**	Mysid shrimp
Octopodidae	<i>Enteroctopus dofleini</i>	Giant Pacific octopus
Ophiurida (order)	**	Brittle star
Pandalidae	<i>Pandalus sp.</i>	Pandalid shrimp
Phillinidae	<i>Philine sp.</i>	Philine
Strongylocentrotidae	<i>Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis</i>	Green sea urchin
Stylatulidae	<i>Stylatula elongata</i>	Soft sea pen
Tethyidae	<i>Melibe leonina</i>	Lion's melibe
Xanthidae	*	Xanthid crab

* Organism identified to family

**Organism identified to order

Most of the Project area within the Port consists of mud bottom and shows signs of burrowing invertebrate activity. Typical images from the ROV showed mud bottom with burrowing anemones, sea pens, and a variety of nudibranchs. The relatively diverse array of invertebrates listed in Table 2 was the result of captures made with the otter trawl. Many of these organisms were likely captured because the otter trawl intersected debris, drift algae, or algae attached to either debris or small rocks. These sources of more complex structure provide habitat for a diverse array of organisms.

A large sand dollar (*Dendraster excentricus*) bed occurs parallel to the beach inside the west jetty in a band extending from roughly -1.5 to -2.5 m MLLW (Figure 2). The sand dollars within the bed are densely situated, with up to several hundred per square meter in places. The sand dollar bed is outside of the proposed dredge footprint.

Beach Disposal Area

The intertidal sand beach occurring along a small portion of the disposal area supports abundant sand crabs (*Emerita analoga*) and small beanclams (*Donax gouldii*), which were observed along the length of the beach. No Pismo clams were detected, and only a few pieces of heavily worn and broken Pismo clam shells were found on the beach. The majority of the beach is bounded in the intertidal area by large riprap. The riprap within the intertidal and splash zone supports a very limited community dominated by the green alga *Ulva* and *Enteromorpha*, and acorn barnacles (*Balanus* spp.) and the snail *Tegula*. There were no surfgrass or kelp species observed growing on the rocks, nor was any debris of these species seen washed up on the beach, as would be expected if it occurred offshore.

The subtidal portions to the beach disposal area were characterized by sand devoid of any attached vegetation. Only one species of fish (speckled sanddab) was captured in this area. Invertebrates noted include dungeness crabs and mysid shrimp.

SENSITIVE SPECIES

Species identified as protected, rare, sensitive, threatened or endangered by the California Department of Fish and Game or the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service that were observed or may be expected in the area at various times include three bird species and two marine mammals (Table 3). Double-crested cormorants were observed nesting along a bulkhead wall of the entrance channel, and California sea lion pups

were seen loafing nearby on the riprap of the channel. California least terns were observed foraging within the North Harbor, though they are not known to nest on site. It is possible the terns were nesting at nearby Ormond Beach.

California brown pelicans were not observed and do not breed on the mainland California coast, but are likely to use the site occasionally throughout the year. Similarly, harbor seals do not breed at this site but are likely to forage in the Port occasionally throughout the year.

Table 3. Protected species observed or expected to occur within the survey area.

Common Name	Scientific Name	Status	Occurrence at Project Site
California Brown Pelican	<i>Pelicanus occidentalis californicus</i>	SE, FE	Regular
Double-crested Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax auritus</i>	CDFG SSC	Regular, Nesting
California Least Tern	<i>Sterna antillarum browni</i>	SE, FE	Regular *
Harbor Seal	<i>Phoca vitulina</i>	MMPA	Rare
California Sea Lion	<i>Zalophus californicus californianus</i>	MMPA	Regular

SE – State Endangered; **FE**- Federally Endangered; **CDFG SSC**- CDFG Species of Special Concern; **MMPA** – species protected by the Marine Mammal Protection Act

*Least terns are a migratory species found in the area from approximately April 1 through September 1 of each year.

DISCUSSION

The habitats and organisms encountered during the survey were similar to those observed along much of the southern California coastline. The exposed shoreline and shallow subtidal zone at Hueneme Beach receives significant wave action. Local current patterns have resulted in the accumulation of the sand beach. No subtidal reef was observed within the disposal area. The only rocky habitat available for colonization by marine invertebrates and algae is the shoreline armoring riprap at the northern end of the disposal area. The low diversity of habitats and high energy of the site has resulted in relatively low biological diversity. The few organisms encountered during the survey reflect the low diversity of this area. It should not be assumed, however, that the area lacks biological significance. Schooling fish such as various species of surfperch, smelt, anchovy, and mackerel would likely be encountered if different fish sampling techniques were employed or if sampling were expanded. Various bottom associated fish species such as stingrays, croaker, and flatfish would also be likely encountered if greater sampling were employed. Finally, it should be noted that the beach represents a potential grunion spawning habitat. It is recommended that surveys for grunion spawning activity be performed prior to disposal.

Inside Port Heuneme a variety of habitats were found. The shallow subtidal reefs inside the breakwater supported an abundance of kelp forest habitat. The variety of shoreline features further contributed to species diversity by providing attachment space for organisms and through provision of increased structure.

The soft-bottom habitats within the navigation channels and basins were generally observed to have low species diversity. The relatively diverse array of invertebrates listed in Table 2 was the result of captures made with the otter trawl. Many of these organisms were likely captured because the otter trawl intersected debris, drift algae, or algae attached to debris or small rocks. These sources of more complex structure provide habitat for a diverse array of organisms. Thus, most of the Port can be visualized as being relatively low-diversity mud-bottom areas with occasional small structures that create islands of habitat with high diversity of associated invertebrate organisms.

Notably absent from the fish data were some larger species typically found in bays and harbors. During previous survey work performed in the nearby Channel Islands Harbor, California halibut (*Paralichthys californicus*), spotted and barred sand bass (*Paralabrax* spp.), round stingray (*Urolophus halleri*), and bat ray (*Myliobatis californica*) were commonly observed. The absence of these species during this survey is surprising given the amount of sampling performed. It is safe to assume, however, that these fish species are present within the Port.

REFERENCES

National Marine Fisheries Service Southwest Region, 2001. *Caulerpa* Control Protocol (Version 4).

APPENDIX A
Detailed Species Capture Data

Transect		Species		Count	Fish Standard Length (mm)
1	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	55
1	Invert	<i>Cancer magister</i>	Dungeness crab	2	
1	Invert	Mysid shrimp	Mysid shrimp	present	
2	Invert	<i>Cancer magister</i>	Dungeness crab	5	
2	Alga	<i>Mastocarpus papillatus</i>	Turkish whitecloth	present	
3	Fish	<i>Syngnathus griseolineatus</i>	Bay pipefish	1	255
3	Fish	<i>Syngnathus griseolineatus</i>	Bay pipefish	1	240
3	Fish	<i>Syngnathus griseolineatus</i>	Bay pipefish	1	170
3	Fish	<i>Syngnathus griseolineatus</i>	Bay pipefish	1	150
3	Fish	<i>Pleuronichthys verticalis</i>	Hornyhead turbot	1	175
3	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	50
3	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	50
3	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	50
3	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	65
3	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	35
3	Fish	<i>Sepiophis politus</i>	Queenfish	1	23
3	Invert	<i>Cancer magister</i>	Dungeness crab	1	
3	Invert	<i>Pandalus sp.</i>	Pandalid shrimp	4	
3	Invert	Mysid shrimp	Mysid shrimp	present	
3	Invert	<i>Crangon sp.</i>	Crangon shrimp	1	
4	Fish	<i>Synodus lucioceps</i>	California lizardfish	1	91
4	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	162
4	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	32
4	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	80
4	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	40
4	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	48
4	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	50
4	Invert	<i>Cancer magister</i>	Dungeness crab	6	
4	Invert	<i>Dendronotus iris</i>	Rainbow dendronotus	1	
4	Invert	Mysid shrimp	Mysid shrimp	present	
4	Invert	<i>Pandalus sp.</i>	Pandalid shrimp	1	
5	Invert	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	38
5	Invert	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	33
5	Invert	Mysid shrimp	Mysid shrimp	present	
6	Fish	<i>Syngnathus griseolineatus</i>	Bay pipefish	1	
6	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	
6	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	
6	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	63
6	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	52

Transect		Species		Count	Fish Standard Length (mm)
6	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	57
6	Invert	<i>Melibe leonina</i>	Lion's melibe	1	
6	Invert	<i>Cancer productus</i>	Red rock crab	1	
6	Invert	<i>Navanax inermis</i>	Navanax	1	
6	Invert	Ophiurida (order)	Brittle star	3	
6	Invert	<i>Lytechinus sp.</i>	White sea urchin	1	
7	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	75
7	Invert	Mysid shrimp	Mysid shrimp	present	
7	Invert	<i>Dendronotus iris</i>	Rainbow dendronotus	2	
7	Invert	<i>Cancer productus</i>	Red rock crab	1	
7	Invert	Ophiurida (order)	Brittle star	7	
7	Invert	<i>Lytechinus sp.</i>	White sea urchin	1	
8	Fish	<i>Syngnathus griseolineatus</i>	Bay pipefish	1	225
8	Fish	<i>Synodus lucioceps</i>	California lizardfish	1	85
8	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	65
8	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	45
8	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	30
8	Fish	<i>Sebastes dallii</i>	Calico rockfish	1	38
8	Fish	<i>Gibbonsia elegans</i>	Spotted kelpfish	1	30
8	Invert	Ophiurida (order)	Brittle star	5	
8	Invert	<i>Philine sp.</i>	Philine	6	
8	Invert	<i>Pyromaia tuberculata</i>	Tuberculate pear crab	2	
8	Invert	<i>Crangon sp.</i>	Crangon shrimp	2	
8	Invert	Mysid shrimp	Mysid shrimp	present	
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	80
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	52
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	35
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	40
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	41
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	44
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	35
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	47
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	25
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	35
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	36
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	37
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	33
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	30
9	Fish	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	1	33

Transect		Species		Count	Fish Standard Length (mm)
9	Fish	<i>Syngnathus griseolineatus</i>	Bay pipefish	1	242
9	Fish	<i>Leptocottus armatus</i>	Pacific staghorn sculpin	1	77
9	Fish	<i>Odontopyxis trispinosa</i>	Pygmy poacher	1	78
9	Invert	<i>Enteroctopus dofleini</i>	Giant Octopus	1	
9	Invert	<i>Cancer magister</i>	Dungeness crab	12	
9	Invert	Mysid shrimp	Mysid shrimp	present	
9	Invert	<i>Crangon sp.</i>	Crangon shrimp	12	
*	Fish	<i>Atherinops affinis</i>	Topsmelt		
*	Invert	<i>Aurelia sp.</i>	Moon jellyfish		
*	Fish	<i>Rhacochilus vacca</i>	Pile perch		
**	Alga	<i>Undaria pinnatifida</i>	Wakame		
**	Invert	<i>Asterina miniata</i>	Bat star		
**	Invert	<i>Pisaster ochraceus</i>	Purple starfish		

*observed from the survey vessel / ROV

** observed at the docks at the west end of the port

**BIOLOGICAL PRE-CONSTRUCTION SURVEY AND ASSESSMENT
AOC 17 – SOIL REMOVAL**

Biological Pre-Construction Survey and Assessment

AOC 17 – Soil Removal

Naval Base Ventura County

Port Hueneme, Ventura County, California

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INTRODUCTION

This report documents the findings of a pre-construction survey and associated Biological Assessment conducted for proposed removal action of polychlorinated biphenyl (PCB)-contaminated soil at AOC 17 located at the Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC) - Port Hueneme, California. The assessment was completed to document existing site conditions prior to project implementation and determine potential impacts to sensitive biological resources based upon current project plans. This assessment was completed to meet the requirements of OPNAVINST 5090.1C Section 24-6.

Project activity is planned to occur within AOC 17, and in the Pleasant Valley Road Ditch (PVRD), a concrete trapezoidal channel located adjacent and to the north of AOC 17. The channel bottom contains sediment eroded from the upper site banks and other locations upstream of the site. The proposed activities require both a pre-construction and post-construction biological survey and assessment.

DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTION

Purpose and Need. A relatively small area of PCB-impacted soils is located next to two electrical substations. A non-time critical removal action is proposed to remove PCB contaminants and then stabilize the soil surface. The need for the project is to remove contaminated soils in compliance with Department of Navy policy and is being conducted under the Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation, and Liability Act (CERCLA).

Proposed Activities. The proposed activities at the site will include the removal of PCB-contaminated soil associated with two adjacent electrical substations. Soils planned for removal include the gravel-covered soil at the base of the transformers as well as materials within a concrete channel. The work is anticipated to involve the use of a backhoe or Gradall and heavy-duty trucks to removal the contaminated soil.

Action Location. The project site is located on NVBC Port Hueneme in Port Hueneme, Ventura County, California. The project location is at the junction of Stetham and Patterson Roads. The site occurs within an urban landscape. The site is depicted on the Oxnard, California, United States Geological Survey (USGS) topographic quadrangle (July 1978). Land uses surrounding the general project site include office buildings and parking to the south, railroad tracks and Shipside Road to the east, office buildings to the north, and a storage facility to the west. Beyond the immediate project site vicinity, land use is primarily industrial and residential.

METHODOLOGY

This biological assessment consisted of a review of relevant literature followed by a field reconnaissance survey. The literature review included information on sensitive resource occurrences from the California Department of Fish and Game (CDFG) California Natural Diversity Data Base (CNDDB), Biogeographic Information and Observation System (BIOS – www.bios.dfg.ca.gov), and U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) Critical Habitat Portal (<http://criticalhabitat.fws.gov>). Site plans provided by Oneida Total Integrated Enterprises (OTIE), aerial photographs, and topographic maps were also examined.

The field reconnaissance survey documented existing site conditions and the potential presence of sensitive biological resources, including sensitive plant and wildlife species, sensitive plant communities, jurisdictional waters and wetlands, and habitat for nesting birds. The field biologist surveyed the project site on foot and recorded the biological resources present onsite such as plant and wildlife species. The field survey was conducted on 11 October 2011, between the hours of 1345 and 1430. Weather conditions during the survey included an average temperature of 75 degrees Fahrenheit, with winds of 0-8 kilometers per hour (0-5 miles per hour) and no cloud cover.

The potential presence of sensitive species is based on a literature review and field survey designed to assess habitat suitability only. Definitive surveys to confirm the presence or absence of special-status species were not performed. Definitive surveys for sensitive plant and wildlife species generally require

specific survey protocols requiring extensive field survey time to be conducted only, at certain times of the year. The findings and opinions conveyed in this report are based on this methodology.

DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTION AREA

The site is located in an urban industrial setting, and as such contains little vegetation. The proposed removal activities would occur within a concrete channel and within gravel covered soil. The concrete channel contained both native and non-native vegetation associated with accumulated material, and the gravel covered soil contains a small amount of vegetation. The site topography includes flat areas above the channel slopes, an approximate two meter (six foot) high steep slope that forms the concrete bank of the channel (see Photograph 1), and the relatively flat area of the channel bottom. The site elevations are approximately from mean sea level to about 3 meters above.

The site provides minimal habitat for common wildlife species that occur in urban and suburban communities. No amphibian or reptile species were observed or sign detected. Species observed within or adjacent to the project site during the field survey include included domestic dog (*Canis familiaris*), ground squirrel (*Spermophilus beecheyi*), and common raven (*Corvus corax*). A comprehensive fisheries survey was not completed, but some of the fish observed within the canal were identified as fathead minnow (*Pimephales promelas*). The limited vegetation in the upland area includes jaumea (*Jaumea carnosa*), tocalote (*Centaurea melitensis*), and an unidentified horticultural aster. Vegetation in the canal includes rabbitsfoot grass (*Polypogon monspeliensis*), watercress (*Rorippa nasturtium-aquaticum*), and Mexican spangle-top (*Leptocloa uninervia*).

Sensitive Biological Resources. The CNDDDB has records for 4 sensitive plant species, 2 sensitive plant communities, and 15 sensitive wildlife species within the Oxnard USGS topographic quadrangle. Sensitive plant and wildlife species typically have very specific habitat requirements that do not occur within the activity area. Although tidally influenced brackish water is contained in the canal, the site also occurs adjacent to a developed substation and parking lot that lacks habitat constituents for sensitive species.

Sensitive Plant Species. Based on the existing development and disturbances, the project site does not contain suitable habitat for any sensitive plant species.

Sensitive Plant Communities. No sensitive upland or terrestrial plant communities as defined by CNDDDB are present on the project site. The status of the vegetation in the concrete channel is discussed under *Jurisdictional Drainages and Wetlands* below.

Sensitive Wildlife Species. Based on the plant communities present and the disturbances associated with the development and maintenance of the existing substation and parking lot, the upland portion of the project site does not contain suitable habitat for any sensitive wildlife species. The channel contains small fish, most of which appear to be fathead minnow, a non-native fish.

The federal listed endangered tidewater goby (*Eucyclogobius newberryi*) inhabits coastal lagoons, estuaries, and marshes in southern California. Its habitat is characterized by brackish (somewhat salty) water in shallow lagoons and in lower stream reaches where the water is fairly still but not stagnant. Vegetation within tidewater goby habitat generally is sparse, consisting of several species of submerged or emergent aquatic plants. Critical habitat occurs for this species at the J Street Canal approximately 2.75 kilometers (1.7 miles) to the southeast and at the mouth of the Santa Clara River approximately 14 kilometers (8.7 miles) to the northwest. This small fish (rarely longer than 5 cm [2 in]) has also been documented at the Hueneme Drain, Oxnard Industrial Drain, and East Hueneme Channel (all associated with the J Street Canal). The species is benthic in nature, living at the bottom of shallow bodies of water, and is not typically found in deep water. The channel at the site drains into the Port Hueneme harbor, a deep water (10.7 meters = 35 foot) harbor, and movement of individuals from the known populations to the PVRD would require crossing this deep harbor. It is not known to occur within the PVRD, nor is it considered likely to be present.

Nesting Birds. The federal Migratory Bird Treaty Act (MBTA) protects native birds and their nests. The project site contains minimal vegetation within the portion of soil to be removed, limiting the potential for nesting, though some native species may forage in the parking lot and adjacent vegetation within and along the canal. Several palm trees are adjacent to the north, east, and west of the substation and raptors such as barn owls may potentially nest in that location, but given the disturbance and the lack of vegetation with a radius of 400 meters (0.25 miles) from the project site, this habitat is not ideal for nesting and would not be selected as compared to better habitat outside the naval base. Small, common species such as house finches could nest within the equipment in the substation, but more suitable habitat for nesting is present outside the project site that is less subject to disturbance.

Jurisdictional Drainages and Wetlands. Pleasant Valley Canal Road Ditch is a man-made channel that empties into Port Hueneme, which eventually leads to the Pacific Ocean. Consequentially, it is not a traditional navigable water (TNW), but given its apparent tidal influence, it may be a Relatively Permanent Water (RPW) and it is within the jurisdiction of the Army Corps of Engineers under the federal Clean Water Act (USACE, 2007). However, because this action is being conducted under CERCLA, notification to and permits from the Corps are not required, but it is Port Hueneme Naval Base policy to provide a courtesy copy of the Work Plan at the time of regulatory review.

While suitable hydrologic conditions and wetland vegetation is present on the sediments within the channel, this deposited material and the concrete lining do not constitute a “hydric soil;” therefore, this area is not considered a wetland as defined by the Wetland Delineation Manual (USACE, 1987).

Protected Trees. Based on the site plans provided, no native or protected trees will be affected during the proposed activity.

Other Regulated Areas. The project site is not located within a Habitat Conservation Plan (HCP) area or other sensitive biological area as indicated by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service Critical Habitat portal (<http://criticalhabitat.fws.gov/>) or the California Department of Fish and Game Biogeographic Information and Observation System (<http://bios.dfg.ca.gov/>).

EFFECTS OF THE ACTION

Given the urban nature of the upland portion of the project site, small project footprint, and lack of habitat for sensitive species, this project is not expected to impact sensitive plants, sensitive plant communities, sensitive wildlife species, protected trees, or other regulated areas. No adverse effects on these resources are anticipated.

Removal of the sediment within the channel will result in the removal of several non-native and native facultative wetland plants that are present. This vegetation type is not rare, nor does this low quality habitat contribute significantly to the local ecosystem. The sediment removal activities may result in the death of any fish present locally within the channel because of the re-suspension of fine materials during excavation (resulting in fish suffocation) and direct injury. No sensitive fish species are known to be present in this portion of the channel, and as discussed above, the endangered tidewater goby is not expected to be present and so no adverse effects to that species are anticipated.

ESSENTIAL FISH HABITAT ASSESSMENT

Downstream and west of the project site, the PVRD and all portions of the Port Hueneme Harbor to the Pacific Ocean are designated as Essential Fish Habitat for groundfish by NOAA Fisheries (http://sharppfn.nmfs.noaa.gov/website/EFH_Mapper/map.aspx). The EFH for Pacific coast groundfish is defined as the aquatic habitat necessary to allow for groundfish production to support long-term sustainable fisheries for groundfish and for groundfish contributions to a healthy ecosystem. The combined groundfish EFH includes all waters from the mean higher high water line, and the upriver extent of saltwater intrusion in river mouths, along the coasts of Washington, Oregon and California seaward to the boundary of the U.S. Exclusive Economic Zone. The “estuarine” composite groundfish EFH is present within the harbor and associated tidal channels. Minimal estuarine habitat is present

within the downstream channel area designated as EFH, and the expected primary function for this area would be the production of food for foraging juveniles and adults. Given that the vast majority of this habitat in Ventura County is associated with offshore and nearshore environments, the Ventura River estuary, the Santa Clara River estuary, and the wetlands at Point Mugu, the project would be expected to have no adverse effect on EFH. Because the project would remove contaminated sediments from the channel prior to such sediments being washed into the EFH designated area, the project is considered to have a potentially beneficial effect.

CUMULATIVE EFFECTS

Cumulative effects include those of future state or private activities, not involving federal activities, that are reasonably certain to occur within the action area of the federal action, subject to consultation (50 CFR 402.02). Because the proposed action area is small, and contained within the Naval Base, no additional activities by non-federal agencies are known or likely to occur. Therefore, no cumulative effects are expected.

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed activities are anticipated to have no effects on upland terrestrial biological resources, and to have limited adverse effects to aquatic resources. Fish are present within the channel and may be subject to direct harm from the removal of the sediment and from suspension of silt that may cause suffocation as the silt clogs gills. It is anticipated that the fish will largely flee the area once sediment removal is initiated, consequentially, the number of fish directly harmed are expected to be minimal and would not substantially alter the local population as the fish present are naturally subject to very high mortality rates and so are also highly fecund. Any loss in numbers would be quickly replaced during the next breeding cycle. A post-construction survey is planned which will determine if fish are still present in the area following the sediment removal activity.

The Port Hueneme Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) is currently undergoing revision. Nonetheless, the proposed project is consistent with the INRMP because the purpose of the project is to remove PCB contaminated sediments that may be causing harm to the local ecosystem.

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Photograph 1. View of Pleasant Valley Canal looking east. The gravel-covered, loose soil in the right of the photo will be partially removed.

Photograph 2. View looking west of erosional areas in soil south side of Pleasant Valley Canal with substation in background.

Photograph 3. View of Pleasant Valley Canal looking west.

QUALIFICATIONS OF PREPARER(S)

Nancy Fox-Fernandez was the primary investigator for this project. Ms. Fox-Fernandez serves as a Biologist/Project Manager for biological, environmental, and land use planning studies specializing in ornithology. Ms. Fox-Fernandez has an M.S. in Natural Resources with a focus in Wildlife from Humboldt State University. She has over 10 years in the fields of endangered species management and behavior, wildlife and habitat ecology, resource management, regulatory compliance, and the preparation of biological reports and environmental documents for compliance with both NEPA and CEQA.

Dr. Duane Vander Pluym provided QA/QC and review for the project. He has more than 30 years of professional experience as an environmental consultant. He has a Masters in Biology from the University of California, Riverside and a doctorate from the University of California, Los Angeles, and also holds a credential as a California Community College Instructor in biological sciences and ecology. Over the course of his career, he has performed and reviewed more than 100 biologic investigations and is familiar with both CEQA and NEPA regulations, California Coastal Act regulations, state and federal Endangered Species Acts requirements, Army Corps of Engineers 404 jurisdictional wetlands analysis, California Fish and Game regulations, and the preparation and implementation of compliance documents under the Federal Endangered Species Act Sections 7 and 10, and the California Fish and Game Code Section 2080, et. seq. and programmatic permitting under Clean Water Act Sections 404 and 401, and Fish and Game Code Section 1600, et. seq. He has also served as an expert witness, providing court testimony with respect to biological issues.

APPENDIX H
SPECIES LISTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS

H.1 Plants

TABLE H-1: VEGETATION TYPE: AQUATIC.....	H-1
TABLE H-2: VEGETATION TYPE: DUNE MAT.....	H-1
TABLE H-3: VEGETATION TYPE: COYOTE BRUSH SCRUB.....	H-2
TABLE H-4: VEGETATION TYPE: NON-NATIVE ANNUAL GRASSLAND.....	H-3
TABLE H-5: VEGETATION TYPE: WILLOW-BULRUSH-CATTAIL.....	H-4

H.2 Invertebrates

TABLE H-6: INVERTEBRATES.....	H-6
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H.3 Vertebrates

TABLE H-7: FISH.....	H-10
TABLE H-8: AMPHIBIANS	H-10
TABLE H-9: REPTILES	H-10
TABLE H-10: MAMMALS	H-11
TABLE H-11: BIRDS.....	H-12
APPENDIX H REFERENCES.....	H-16

H.1 Plants

TABLE H-1: VEGETATION TYPE: AQUATIC

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Habit	N = Native I = Introduced	Occurrence
Alariaceae	<i>Egregia menziesii</i>	Feather boa kelp	Nonvascular	N	*
Alariaceae	<i>Undaria pinnatifida</i>	Wakame	Nonvascular	I	*
Brassicaceae	<i>Nasturtium officinale</i>	Watercress	Vascular	N	*
Gracilariaceae	<i>Gracilaria</i> sp.		Nonvascular	N	Drift
Laminariaceae	<i>Macrocystis pyrifera</i>	Giant kelp	Nonvascular	N	*
Phylloporaceae	<i>Mastocarpus papillatus</i>		Nonvascular	N	Drift
Sargassaceae	<i>Cystoseira</i> sp.		Nonvascular	N	Drift
Sargassaceae	<i>Sargassum muticum</i>		Nonvascular	I	*
Ulveaceae	<i>Ulva</i> sp.	Sea lettuce	Nonvascular	N	Drift

Notes: *Occurrence not reported in sources.

Sources: Merkel & Associates, Inc. 2008; California Department of Fish and Game (CDFG) 2008, Oneida Total Integrated Enterprises (OTIE) 2011.

TABLE H-2: VEGETATION TYPE: DUNE MAT

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Habit	N = Native I = Introduced	Occurrence
Aizoaceae	<i>Carpobrotus edulis</i> *	Iceplant	Perennial	I	Common
	<i>Mesembryanthemum crystallinum</i>	Crystalline iceplant	Annual, biennial	I	Scattered
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia chamissonis</i>	Silver beachbur	Perennial	N	Scattered
	<i>Gnaphalium luteo-album</i>	Everlasting cudweed	Annual	I	*
	<i>Heterotheca grandiflora</i>	Telegraph weed	Annual, biennial herb	N	Scattered
	<i>Verbesina encelioides</i>	Crownbeard	Annual	I	Common
Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium curassavicum</i>	Seaside heliotrope	Perennial	N	*
Brassicaceae	<i>Cakile maritima</i>	Sea rocket	Annual herb	I	Scattered
Chenopodiaceae	<i>Atriplex leucophylla</i>	Dune saltbush	Perennial	N	*
	<i>Atriplex semibaccata</i>	Australian saltbush	Perennial	I	Scattered
Convolvulaceae	<i>Calystegia soldanella</i>	Beach morning glory	Perennial	N	Rare
Fabaceae	<i>Melilotus albus</i>	White sweet clover	Annual/biennial	I	*
	<i>Melilotus indicus</i>	Yellow sweet clover	Annual	I	*
Frankeniaceae	<i>Frankenia salina</i>	Alkali heath	Subshrub	N	Scattered
Geraniaceae	<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	Red-stemmed filaree	Annual	I	*
Myoporaceae	<i>Myoporum laetum</i>	Myoporum	Shrub, small tree	I	*
Nyctaginaceae	<i>Abronia maritima</i>	Sand verbena	Perennial	N	Scattered
Onagraceae	<i>Camissonia cheiranthifolia</i> ssp. <i>suffruticosa</i>	Beach evening primrose	Perennial	N	*
Poaceae	<i>Agrostis viridis</i>	Water bent grass	Grass	I	*
	<i>Bromus</i> spp.		Grass	I	*
	<i>Distichlis spicata</i>	Saltgrass	Grass	N	*
	<i>Polypogon monspeliensis</i>	Annual beard grass	Grass	I	*
Primulaceae	<i>Anagallis arvensis</i>	Scarlet pimpernel	Annual	I	*

Notes: *Occurrence not reported in sources.

Sources: Hickman 1996, U.S. Department of the Navy (Navy) 1998, Woodward-Clyde 1998, TEC 2003.

TABLE H-3: VEGETATION TYPE: COYOTE BRUSH SCRUB

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Habit	N = Native I = Introduced	Occurrence
Aizoaceae	<i>Carpobrotus edulis</i>	Iceplant/Common hottentot fig	Shrub, subshrub	I	Scattered
Anacardiaceae	<i>Malosma laurina</i>	Laurel sumac	Shrub	N	Scattered
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisifolia</i>	Common ragweed	Annual	I	Scattered
	<i>Baccharis pilularis</i>	Coyote brush	Shrub	N	Common
	<i>Baccharis salicifolia</i>	Mule fat	Shrub	N	*
	<i>Hazardia squarrosa</i>	Sawtooth goldenbush	Shrub	N	*
	<i>Heterotheca grandiflora</i>	Telegraph weed	Annual or perennial	N	*
	<i>Verbesina enceliodes</i>	Crownbeard	Annual	I	Common
Chenopodiaceae	<i>Atriplex semibaccata</i>	Australian saltbush	Perennial	I	*
	<i>Salsola tragus</i>	Russian thistle	Annual	I	*
Fabaceae	<i>Melilotus alba</i>	White sweet clover	Annual/biennial	I	Scattered
	<i>Melilotus indica</i>	Sourclover	Annual herb	I	Common
	<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	Birdfoot trefoil	Perennial	I	Scattered
Geraniaceae	<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	Red-stemmed filaree	Annual	I	*
Malvaceae	<i>Malva parviflora</i>	Cheeseweed	Annual	I	Scattered
Myoporaceae	<i>Myoporum laetum</i>	Myoporum	Shrub, small tree	I	Scattered
Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	English plantain	Perennial	I	Scattered
Poaceae	<i>Distichlis spicata</i>	Saltgrass	Grass	N	Scattered
	<i>Avena barbata</i>	Slender wild oat	Grass	I	Scattered
	<i>Bromus diandrus</i>	Ripgut brome	Grass	I	Scattered
	<i>Bromus madritensis</i> ssp. <i>rubens</i>	Compact brome			Common
	<i>Cortaderia</i> spp.	Pampas grass	Grass	I	Scattered
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Bermuda grass	Grass	I	Common
	<i>Hordeum</i> spp.		Grass	I	Scattered
	<i>Piptatherum miliaceum</i>	Smilo grass	Grass	I	Common
Salicaceae	<i>Salix lasiolepis</i>	Arroyo willow	Shrub, tree	N	Scattered

Notes: *Occurrence not reported in sources.

Sources: Hickman 1996, Woodward-Clyde 1998, Navy 1998, TEC 2003, TEC 2005.

TABLE H-4: VEGETATION TYPE: NON-NATIVE ANNUAL GRASSLAND

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Habit	N = Native I = Introduced	Occurrence
Anacardiaceae	<i>Malosma laurina</i>	Laurel sumac	Shrub	N	Scattered
Asteraceae	<i>Baccharis pilularis</i>	Coyote brush	Shrub	N	Scattered
	<i>Ambrosia artemisifolia</i>	Common ragweed	Annual	I	Scattered
	<i>Heterotheca grandiflora</i>	Telegraph weed	Annual, biennial herb	N	Common
Brassicaceae	<i>Lepidium lasiocarpum</i> var. <i>lasiocarpum</i>	Peppergrass	Annual herb	N	Scattered
Fabaceae	<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	Birdfoot trefoil	Perennial	I	Scattered
	<i>Melilotus alba</i>	White sweet clover	Annual/Biennial	I	Scattered
	<i>Melilotus indica</i>	Sourclover	Annual herb	I	Common
Malvaceae	<i>Malva parviflora</i>	Cheeseweed	Annual	I	Common
Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	English plantain	Perennial	I	Scattered
Poaceae	<i>Avena</i> spp.		Grass	I	Common
	<i>Bromus</i> spp.		Grass	I	Common
	<i>Cortaderia</i> spp.	Pampas grass	Grass	I	Scattered
	<i>Hordeum</i>		Grass	I	Common
	<i>Pennisetum</i> sp.	Fountain grass	Grass	I	Scattered

Sources: Hickman 1996, Navy 1998, Woodward-Clyde 1998.

TABLE H-5: VEGETATION TYPE: WILLOW-BULRUSH-CATTAIL**

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Habit	N = Native I = Introduced	Occurrence
Aizoaceae	<i>Carpobrotus edulis</i>	Iceplant	Perennial	I	
	<i>Mesembryanthemum</i> spp.	Crystalline iceplant	Annual/biennial	I	Scattered
	<i>Tetragonia tetragonioides</i>	New Zealand spinach	Annual	I	*
Apiaceae	<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Fennel	Perennial	I	*
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	Common ragweed	Annual	I	Scattered
	<i>Ambrosia psilostachya</i>	Western ragweed	Perennial	N	*
	<i>Baccharis pilularis</i>	Coyote brush	Perennial	N	*
	<i>Conyza canadensis</i>	Horseweed	Annual	N	*
	<i>Cotula coronopifolia</i>	Brass buttons	Perennial	I	Rare
	<i>Jaumea carnosa</i>	Marsh jaumea	Perennial	N	*
	<i>Verbesina encelioides</i>	Crownbeard	Annual	I	Common
Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium curassavicum</i>	Seaside heliotrope	Perennial	N	*
Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica nigra</i>	Black mustard	Annual/ biennial	I	Scattered
	<i>Nasturtium officinale</i>	Watercress	Perennial	N	*
Chenopodiaceae	<i>Salicornia virginica</i>	Pickleweed	Perennial	N	*
Convolvulaceae	<i>Cressa truxillensis</i>	Alkali weed	Perennial, subshrub	N	Scattered
Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	Nutsedge	Perennial	I	Rare
	<i>Schoenoplectus americanus</i>	American bulrush	Perennial	N	Scattered
	<i>Schoenoplectus acutus</i>	Common tule	Perennial	N	Rare
	<i>Schoenoplectus californicus</i>	California bulrush	Perennial	N	Scattered
	<i>Scripus maritimus</i>	Alkali bulrush	Perennial	N	Scattered
Fabaceae	<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	Birdfoot trefoil	Perennial	I	Rare
	<i>Melilotus alba</i>	White sweet clover	Annual/biennial	I	Scattered
	<i>Melilotus indicus</i>	Yellow sweet clover	Annual	I	Common
Frankeniaceae	<i>Frankenia salina</i>	Alkali heath	Subshrub	N	Scattered
Geraniaceae	<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	Red-stemmed filaree	Annual	I	*
Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus</i> spp.	Hibiscus			Rare
	<i>Malva parviflora</i>	Cheeseweed	Annual	I	Rare
Myoporaceae	<i>Myoporum laetum</i>	Myoporum	Shrub, small tree	I	Scattered
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus</i> spp.	Eucalyptus	Tree	I	Scattered
Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	Narrowleaf plantain	Perennial	I	Scattered
	<i>Plantago subnuda</i>	Plantain	Perennial	N	Scattered
Poaceae	<i>Avena</i> spp.		Grass	I	Scattered
	<i>Bromus</i> spp.		Grass	I	Scattered
	<i>Cortaderia</i> sp.	Pampas grass	Grass	I	*
	<i>Distichlis spicata</i>	Saltgrass	Grass	N	Common
	<i>Hordeum</i> sp.		Grass	I	Scattered
	<i>Leptochloa fusca</i> ssp. <i>uninervia</i>	Mexican sprangletop	Grass	N	*
	<i>Phragmites australis</i>	Common reed	Grass	I	*
	<i>Polypogon monspeliensis</i>	Rabbitsfoot grass	Grass	I	*
	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Ruppia maritima</i>	Ditch grass	Perennial	N
Salicaceae	<i>Salix lasiolepis</i>	Arroyo willow	Shrub, small tree	N	Common
	<i>Salix exigua</i>	Narrowleaf willow	Perennial	N	*

TABLE H-5: VEGETATION TYPE: WILLOW-BULRUSH-CATTAIL (CONT.)**

Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Habit	N = Native I = Introduced	Occurrence
Solanaceae	<i>Nicotiana glauca</i>	Tree tobacco	Shrub/tree	I	*
Typhaceae	<i>Typha latifolia</i>	Broad-leaved cattail	Perennial	N	Scattered

Note: *Occurrence not reported in sources

** This vegetation type includes vegetation observed in drainage channels (TEC 2003, OTIE 2011).

Sources: Hickman 1996, Woodward-Clyde 1998, Tetra Tech 1998, Navy 1998, TEC 2003, TEC 2005, OTIE 2011.

H.2 Invertebrates

TABLE H-6: INVERTEBRATES

Phylum	Scientific Name	Common Name	N = Native I = Introduced C=Cryptogenic U= Unknown*	Source of Observation
Aquatic Invertebrates				
Annelida	<i>Amaeana occidentalis</i>		C	11
	<i>Amphicteis</i>		C	11
	<i>scaphobranchiata</i>			
	<i>Aphelochaeta monilaris</i>		C	11
	<i>Apoprionospio pygmaea</i>		C	11
	<i>Chone minuta</i>		C	11
	<i>Chone paramollis</i>		C	11
	<i>Chrysopetalum occidentale</i>		C	11
	<i>Cossura candida</i>		C	11
	<i>Cossura pygodactylata</i>		C	11
	<i>Ctenodrilus serratus</i>		C	11
	<i>Dipolydora giardi</i>		C	11
	<i>Dodecaceria concharum</i>		C	11
	<i>Dodecaceria fewkesi</i>		C	11
	<i>Dorvillea (Schistomeringos) annulata</i>		C	11
	<i>Euchone limnicola</i>		C	11
	<i>Exogone lourei</i>		C	11
	<i>Glycera americana</i>		C	11
	<i>Glycera convoluta</i>		C	11
	<i>Goniada littorea</i>		C	11
	<i>Harmothoe hirsuta</i>		C	11
	<i>Harmothoe imbricata</i>		C	11
	<i>Levinsenia gracilis</i>		C	11
	<i>Lumbrineris cruzensis</i>		C	11
	<i>Lumbrineris japonica</i>		C	11
	<i>Lumbrineris latreilli</i>		C	11
	<i>Lumbrineris limicola</i>		C	11
	<i>Mediomastus ambiseta</i>		C	11
	<i>Mediomastus californiensis</i>		C	11
	<i>Melinna oculata</i>		C	11
	<i>Monticellina sibilina</i>		C	11
	<i>Myxicola infundibulum</i>		C	11
	<i>Nereis pelagica</i>		C	11
	<i>Nereis zonata</i>		C	11
	<i>Notomastus tenuis</i>		C	11
	<i>Paraprionospio pinnata</i>		C	11
	<i>Pileolaria lateralis</i>		C	11
	<i>Pista brevibranchiata</i>		C	11
	<i>Platynereis bicanaliculata</i>		C	11
	<i>Poecilochaetus johnsoni</i>		C	11
	<i>Polydora cornuta</i>		C	11
	<i>Polydora limicola</i>		C	11
	<i>Polydora websteri</i>		C	11
	<i>Polyophthalmus pictus</i>		C	11
Annelida	<i>Prionospio heterobranchia</i>		C	11
	<i>Prionospio steenstrupi</i>		C	11

TABLE H-6: INVERTEBRATES (CONT.)

Phylum	Scientific Name	Common Name	N = Native I = Introduced C=Cryptogenic U= Unknown*	Source of Observation
	<i>Protolaeospira eximia</i>		C	11
	<i>Pseudopolydora paucibranchiata</i>		C	11
	<i>Sabaco elongatus</i>		I	11
	<i>Sigambra bassi</i>		C	11
	<i>Simplaria pseudomilitaris</i>		C	11
	<i>Sphaerosyllis californiensis</i>		C	11
	<i>Spiophanes duplex</i>		C	11
	<i>Syllis armillaris</i>		C	11
	<i>Syllis elongata</i>		C	11
	<i>Syllis nipponica</i>		I	11
	<i>Trochochaeta multisetosa</i>		C	11
Arthropoda	<i>Acanthomysis californica</i>		C	11
	<i>Achelia echinata</i>		C	11
	<i>Aeschna</i> sp.	Darner	N	1
	<i>Amathimysis trigibba</i>		C	11
	<i>Ammothea hilgendorfi</i>		C	11
	<i>Ampelisca abdita</i>		I	11
	<i>Ampithoe valida</i>		I	11
	<i>Aoroides secundus</i>		I	11
	<i>Argissa hamatipes</i>		C	11
	<i>Balanus</i> sp.	Acorn barnacle	I	2
	<i>Callibaetis</i> sp.	Mayfly	N	1
	<i>Cancer magister</i>	Dungeness crab	N	2
	<i>Cancer</i> sp.	Cancer crab	N	2
	<i>Caprella californica</i>		C	11
	<i>Caprella equilibra</i>		C	11
	<i>Caprella mutica</i>		I	11
	<i>Caprella penantis</i>		C	11
	Caprellidae (Family)	Caprellid amphipod	U	2
	<i>Cerapus tubularis complex</i>		C	11
	Chironomidae (Family)	Midges	U	1
	Cirolanidae (Family)	Isopods	U	1
	<i>Crangon alaskensis</i>	Northern crangon	N	2
	<i>Crangon nigromaculata</i>	Black spotted shrimp	N	2
	<i>Cumella vulgaris</i>		C	11
	<i>Emerita talpoida</i>	Mole crab	I	1
	<i>Enallagma</i> sp.	Bluet (damselfly)	N	1
	<i>Eochelidium</i>		I	11
	<i>Ericthonius brasiliensis</i>		C	11
	<i>Eusiroides</i> sp. A Cadien		C	11
	Gammaridae (Family)	Gammarid amphipod	U	2
	<i>Gammarus</i> sp.	Amphipod	N	1
	<i>Grandidierella japonica</i>		I	11
	<i>Hemicyclops japonicus</i>		C	11
	<i>Hemicyclops subadhearens</i>		C	11
	<i>Hemiproto</i> sp. A Scamit		C	11
	<i>Hyalolella Azteca</i>	Amphipod	N	1
	<i>Ianiropsis tridens</i>		C	11

TABLE H-6: INVERTEBRATES (CONT.)

Phylum	Scientific Name	Common Name	N = Native I = Introduced C=Cryptogenic U= Unknown*	Source of Observation	
Arthropoda	<i>Ischyrocerus anguipes</i>		C	11	
	<i>Ischyrocerus pelagops</i>		C	11	
	<i>Jassa marmorata</i>		I	11	
	<i>Jassa slatteryi</i>		C	11	
	<i>Laticorophium baconi</i>		C	11	
	<i>Leptocheilia dubia</i>		C	11	
	<i>Leucothoe alata</i>		C	11	
	<i>Libellula sp.</i>	Skimmer	N	1	
	<i>Limnoria tripunctata</i>		I	11	
	<i>Metacrangon munita</i>	Coastal spinyhead	N	2	
	<i>Metatiron tropakis</i>		C	11	
	<i>Microjassa litotes</i>		C	11	
	<i>Monocorophium acherusicum</i>		I	11	
	Mysida (Order)	Mysid shrimp	U	2	
	<i>Nebalia pugettensis complex</i>		C	11	
	<i>Nippoleucon hinumensis</i>		I	11	
	<i>Notonecta sp.</i>	Backswimmer	U	2	
	<i>Oithona davisae</i>		I	11	
	<i>Pacifastacus sp.</i>	Crayfish	N	2	
	<i>Pandalus sp.</i>	Pandalid shrimp	U	2	
	<i>Paranthura japonica</i>		I	11	
	<i>Phtisica marina</i>		I	11	
	<i>Podocerus brasiliensis</i>		C	11	
	<i>Podocerus cristatus</i>		C	11	
	<i>Pugettia producta</i>	Northern kelp crab	N	2	
	<i>Pygodelphys aquilonaris</i>		C	11	
	<i>Pyromaia tuberculata</i>	Tuberculate pear crab	N	2	
	Xanthidae (Family)	Xanthid crab	U	2	
	<i>Zeuxo normani</i>		C	11	
	Chordata	<i>Ascidia zara</i>		I	11
		<i>Botrylloides perspicuum</i>		I	11
		<i>Botrylloides violaceus</i>		I	11
<i>Botryllus schlosseri</i>			I	11	
<i>Botryllus sp. A Lambert</i>			I	11	
<i>Ciona intestinalis</i>			I	11	
<i>Ciona savignyi</i>			I	11	
<i>Didemnum vexillum</i>			I	11	
<i>Diplosoma listerianum</i>			C	11	
<i>Styela clava</i>			I	11	
<i>Styela plicata</i>			I	11	
Cnidaria		<i>Aurelia sp.</i>	Moon jellyfish	U	2
		<i>Stylatula elongata</i>	Soft sea pen	N	2
Echinodermata	<i>Amphipholis squamata</i>		C	11	
	<i>Asterina miniata</i>	Bat star	N	2	
	<i>Dendraster excentricus</i>	Sand Dollar	N	2	
	<i>Lytechinus sp.</i>	White sea urchin	U	2	
	<i>Ophiactis simplex</i>		C	11	
	Ophiurida (Order)	Brittle star	U	2	
	<i>Pisaster ochraceus</i>	Ochre sea star	N	2	
	<i>Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis</i>	Green sea urchin	N	2	

TABLE H-6: INVERTEBRATES (CONT.)

Phylum	Scientific Name	Common Name	N = Native I = Introduced C=Cryptogenic U= Unknown*	Source of Observation
Ectoprocta	<i>Amathia distans</i>		C	11
	<i>Membranipora membranacea</i>		C	11
Ectoprocta	<i>Schizoporella japonica</i>		I	11
	<i>Watersipora arcuata</i>		I	11
	<i>Watersipora subtorquata</i>		I	11
	<i>Watersipora subtorquata</i> sp. Mackie		I	11
Entoprocta	<i>Barentsia benedeni</i>		I	11
Mollusca		Rainbow dendronotus	N	2
Mollusca	<i>Dendronotus iris</i>			2
	<i>Enteroctopus dofleini</i>	Giant Pacific octopus	N	2
	<i>Hemissenda</i> sp.	Aeolid	N	2
	<i>Melibe leonina</i>	Lion's melibe	N	2
	<i>Mercenaria mercenaria</i>		I	11
	<i>Musculista senhousia</i>		I	11
	<i>Myosotella myosotis</i>		I	11
	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>		I	11
	<i>Mytilus</i> sp.	Mussel	N	2
	<i>Navanax inermis</i>	Navanax	N	2
	<i>Philine auriformis</i>		I	11
	<i>Philine</i> sp.	Philine	U	2
	<i>Tenellia adspersa</i>		I	11
	<i>Theora lubrica</i>		I	11
	<i>Venerupis philippinarum</i>		I	11
	Nemertea	<i>Amphiporus cruentatus</i>		C
<i>Amphiporus imparispinosus</i>			C	11
<i>Cerebratulus marginatus</i>			C	11
<i>Tetrastemma nigrifrons</i>			C	11
<i>Zygonemertes virescens</i>			C	11
Platyhelminthes	<i>Acerotisa californica</i>		C	11
	<i>Eurylepta aurantiaca</i>		C	11
Porifera	<i>Clathrina coriacea</i>		C	11
	<i>Halichondria bowerbanki</i>		I	11
Sipuncula	<i>Phascolosoma agassizii</i>		C	11
Terrestrial Invertebrates				
		Globose dune beetle	N	10
	<i>Coelus globosus</i>			
	<i>Danaus plexippus</i>	Monarch butterfly	N	3

Notes: * Identification was not to species level to determine native or introduced status.

Sources: 1 – Woodward-Clyde 1998.

2 – Merkel & Associates 2008.

3 – Tetra Tech 1998.

10–Navy 2011c

11– CDFG 2008.

H.3 Vertebrates

TABLE H-7: FISH

Scientific Name	Common Name	Source of Observation
<i>Artedius harringtoni</i>	Scalyhead sculpin	2
<i>Atherinops affinis</i>	Topsmelt	2
<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	Speckled sanddab	2
<i>Fundulus parvipinnis</i>	California killifish	1
<i>Gambusia affinis</i>	Mosquito fish	1
<i>Gibbonsia elegans</i>	Spotted kelpfish	2
<i>Leptocottus armatus</i>	Pacific staghorn sculpin	2
<i>Odontopyxis trispinosa</i>	Pygmy poacher	2
<i>Pimephales promelas</i>	Fathead minnow	12
<i>Pleuronichthys verticalis</i>	Hornyhead turbot	2
<i>Poecilia latipinna</i>	Sailfin molly	1
<i>Rhacochilus vacca</i>	Pile Perch	2
<i>Scorpaenichthys marmoratus</i>	Cabezon	2
<i>Sebastes dallii</i>	Calico rockfish	2
<i>Sepiphus politus</i>	Queenfish	2
<i>Synodus lucioceps</i>	California lizardfish	2
<i>Syngnathus griseolineatus</i>	Bay pipefish	2

Source: 1 – Woodward-Clyde 1998.
 2 – Merkel & Associates, Inc. 2008.
 12 – OTIE 2011.

TABLE H-8: AMPHIBIANS

Scientific Name	Common Name	Source of Observation
<i>Hyla regilla</i>	Pacific tree frog	1,4

Sources: 3 – Woodward-Clyde 1998.
 4 – TEC 2003.

TABLE H-9: REPTILES

Scientific Name	Common Name	Source of Observation
<i>Sceloporus occidentalis</i>	Western Fence Lizard	5
<i>Uta stansburiana</i>	Common Side-blotched Lizard	5
<i>Elgaria multicarinata</i>	Southern Alligator Lizard	5
<i>Pituophis melanoleucus</i>	Gopher snake	4,6

Sources: 4 – TEC 2003.
 5 – Navy 2011b.
 6 – PRC 1995.

TABLE H-10: MAMMALS

Scientific Name	Common Name	Source of Observation	Conservation Status
Lagomorpha			
<i>Sylvilagus audubonii</i>	Audubon's cottontail	4	
<i>Lepus californicus</i>	Black-tailed jackrabbit	3,4	
Rodentia			
<i>Thomomys bottae</i>	Botta's pocket gopher	4,6	
<i>Spermophilus beecheyi</i>	California ground squirrel	1,3,4,12	
<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>	Deer Mouse	7	
<i>Sciurus niger</i>	Eastern Fox Squirrel	7	
Carnivora			
<i>Enhydra lutris</i>	Southern sea otter	8	FT, MMPA protected
<i>Mirounga angustirostris</i>	Elephant seal	8	MMPA protected
<i>Zalophus californianus</i>	California sea lion	2,3,8	MMPA protected
<i>Phoca vitulina</i>	Pacific harbor seal	2,4,8	MMPA protected
<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	Bottlenose dolphin	4,8	MMPA protected
<i>Canis latrans</i>	Coyote	1,3,7	
<i>Felis catus</i>	Feral cat	3,4,7,8	
<i>Urocyon cinereoargenteus</i>	Gray fox	1,7	
<i>Procyon lotor</i>	Raccoon	1,7	
Marsupialia			
<i>Didelphis virginiana</i>	Opossum	1,7	

Sources: 1 – Woodward-Clyde 1998.
 2 – Merkel & Associates 2008.
 3 – Tetra Tech 1998.
 4 – TEC 2003.
 6 – PRC 1995.
 7 – Navy 2011a.
 8 – TEC 2005.
 12 – OTIE 2011.

TABLE H-11: BIRDS

Scientific Name	Common Name	Source of Observation	Frequency*	Conservation Status
Loons and Grebes (Podicipedidae)				
<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>	Eared grebe	1,4	Uncommon	
<i>Podilymbus podiceps</i>	Pied-billed grebe	1,4	Uncommon	
<i>Aechmophorus clarkii</i>	Clark's grebe	4	Uncommon	
<i>Aechmophorus occidentalis</i>	Western grebe	3,4	Common	
<i>Gavia immer</i>	Common loon	9	Common	CDFG-SSC, IUCN-LC
<i>Podiceps auritus</i>	Horned grebe	9	Uncommon	
Pelicans (Pelecanidae)				
<i>Pelecanus occidentalis californicus</i>	California brown pelican	2,3,8	Common	CDFG-FP, F and S Delisted
Cormorants (Phalacrocoracidae)				
<i>Phalacrocorax penicillatus</i>	Brandt's cormorant	1,4	Common	
<i>Phalacrocorax auritus</i>	Double-crested cormorant	2,3,4,8	Common	CDFG-WL, IUCN-LC
<i>Phalacrocorax pelagicus</i>	Pelagic cormorant	1,4	Uncommon	
Hérons, Egrets, and Bitterns (Ardeidae)				
<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>	Black-crowned night-heron	3,4,8	Common	IUCN-LC
<i>Ardea Herodias</i>	Great blue heron	1,3,4,8	Common	CDFG-s, IUCN-LC
<i>Casmerodius albus</i>	Great egret	3,4,8	Common	CDFG-s, IUCN-LC
<i>Butorides striatus</i>	Green-backed heron	1,4,8	Common	
<i>Egretta rufescens</i>	Reddish egret	4	Rare	
<i>Egretta thula</i>	Snowy egret	1,4,8	Common	IUCN-LC
<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Cattle egret	9	Uncommon	
Waterfowl (Anatidae)				
<i>Melanitta nigra</i>	Black scoter	4	Uncommon	
<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Mallard	1,3,4,8	Common	
<i>Aythya affinis</i>	Lesser scaup	9	Uncommon	
<i>Melanitta perspicillata</i>	Surf scoter	9	Uncommon	
<i>Aythya collaris</i>	Ring-necked duck	8	Common	
<i>Lophodytes cucullatus</i>	Hooded merganser	8	Common	
Hawks, Kites, Harriers, and Eagles (Accipitridae)				
<i>Accipiter cooperii</i>	Cooper's hawk	1,4	Common	CDFG-WL, IUCN-LC
<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>	Red-tailed hawk	1,3,4,8	Common	
<i>Accipiter striatus</i>	Sharp-shinned hawk	1,4	Uncommon	CDFG-WL
<i>Pandion haliaetus</i>	Osprey	8	Uncommon	CDFG-WL, IUCN-LC
Falcons (Falconidae)				
<i>Falco sparverius</i>	American kestrel	1,3,4	Common	PIF
<i>Falco columbarius</i>	Merlin	4,8	Uncommon	CDFG-WL, IUCN-LC

TABLE H-11: BIRDS

Scientific Name	Common Name	Source of Observation	Frequency*	Conservation Status
Rails, Coots, and Gallinules (Rallidae)				
<i>Fulica americana</i>	American coot	3,4,8	Common	
Plovers and Relatives (Charadriidae)				
<i>Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus</i>	Western snowy plover	4,8	Uncommon	F-T, CDFG-SSC, USFWS-BCC
<i>Charadrius vociferus</i>	Killdeer	3,4	Common	PIF
<i>Pluvialis fulva</i>	Pacific golden plover	9	Uncommon	
Oystercatchers (Haematopodidae)				
<i>Haematopus bachmani</i>	Black oystercatcher	8	Uncommon	IUCN-LC, USFWS-BCC, PIF
Avocets and Stilts (Recurvirostridae)				
<i>Himantopus mexicanus</i>	Black-necked stilt	3,4	Uncommon	
Sandpipers and Relatives (Scolopacidae)				
<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Common snipe	1,4	Uncommon	
<i>Tringa melanoleuca</i>	Greater yellowlegs	3,4	Uncommon	
<i>Tringa flavipes</i>	Lesser yellowlegs	4	Uncommon	
<i>Actitis macularia</i>	Spotted sandpiper	1,4	Uncommon	
<i>Aphriza virgata</i>	Surfbird	3,4	Uncommon	PIF
<i>Calidris mauri</i>	Western sandpiper	3,4	Common	
<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>	Whimbrel	8	Uncommon	
<i>Catoptrophorus semipalmatus</i>	Willet	3,4,8	Common	PIF
<i>Arenaria melanocephala</i>	Black turnstone	8	Rare	PIF
<i>Limosa fedoa</i>	Marbled godwit	9	Common	
<i>Calidris alba</i>	Sanderling	9	Common	
<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Wilson's snipe	9	Uncommon	
Gulls and Terns (Laridae)				
<i>Larus californicus</i>	California gull	1,4,8	Common	CDFG-WL, IUCN-LC
<i>Larus heermanni</i>	Heerman's gull	3,4,8	Common	PIF
<i>Larus delawarensis</i>	Ring-billed gull	1,4,8	Common	
<i>Larus occidentalis</i>	Western gull	3,4,8	Common	PIF
<i>Sterna forsteri</i>	Forster's tern	8	Rare	IUCN-LC
<i>Sterna anillarum browni</i>	California least tern	8, 2	Rare	F-E, S-E, CDFG-FP
Doves and Pigeons (Columbidae)				
<i>Zenaidura macroura</i>	Mourning dove	3,4,8	Common	
<i>Columba livia</i>	Rock dove	1, 3,4,8	Common	
Owls (Strigidae)				
<i>Athene cunicularia</i>	Burrowing owl	3,4	Rare	CDFG-SSC, IUCN-LC, USFWS-BCC, PIF
<i>Tyto alba</i>	Barn owl	4,8	Common	PIF

TABLE H-11: BIRDS

Scientific Name	Common Name	Source of Observation	Frequency*	Conservation Status
<i>Bubo virginianus</i>	Great-horned owl	4,8	Common	
Swifts (Apodidae)				
<i>Chaetura pelagica</i>	Chimney swift	1,4	Rare	
Hummingbirds (Trochilidae)				
<i>Calypte anna</i>	Anna's hummingbird	3,4,8	Common	PIF
<i>Selasphorus sasin</i>	Allen's hummingbird	4	Rare	IUCN-LC, USFWS-BCC, PIF
<i>Archilochus alexandri</i>	Black-chinned hummingbird	4	Rare	PIF
<i>Calypte costae</i>	Costa's hummingbird	3,4	Uncommon	IUCN-LC, PIF
Kingfishers (Alcedinidae)				
<i>Ceryle alcyon</i>	Belted kingfisher	3,4	Common	
Woodpeckers (Picidae)				
<i>Colaptes auratus</i>	Northern flicker	1,4	Uncommon	
Tyrant Flycatchers (Tyrannidae)				
<i>Sayornis nigricans</i>	Black phoebe	3,4,8	Common	PIF
<i>Sayornis saya</i>	Say's phoebe	3,4	Uncommon	
<i>Tyrannus verticalis</i>	Western kingbird	8,4	Common	
Swallows (Hirundinidae)				
<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Barn swallow	1,8,4	Common	
<i>Tachycineta thalassina</i>	Violet-green swallow	4	Uncommon	PIF
<i>Petrochelidon pyrrhonota</i>	Cliff swallow	4,8	Common	
Jays, Crows, and Magpies (Corvidae)				
<i>Corvus brachyrhynchos</i>	American crow	1,3,4	Common	
<i>Corvus corax</i>	Common raven	8, 12	Common	
Chicadees & Allies (Aegithalidae, Paridae, Remizidae)				
<i>Psaltriparus minimus</i>	Bushtit	4,8	Common	PIF
Wrens (Troglodytidae)				
<i>Cistothorus palustris</i>	Marsh wren	1,4,8	Common	PIF
Old World Warblers, Thrushes, Gnatcatchers, and Kinglets (Muscicapidae)				
<i>Poliophtila caerulea</i>	Blue-grey gnatcatcher	3,4	Uncommon	
<i>Catharus guttatus</i>	Hermit thrush	9	Uncommon	
Mockingbirds and Thrashers (Mimidae)				
<i>Mimus polyglottos</i>	Northern mockingbird	3,4,8	Common	
<i>Toxostoma redivivum</i>	California thrasher	9	Common	
Shrikes (Laniidae)				
<i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>	Loggerhead shrike	3,4	Uncommon	CDFG-SSC, IUCN-LC,

TABLE H-11: BIRDS

Scientific Name	Common Name	Source of Observation	Frequency*	Conservation Status
USFWS-BCC, PIF				
Vireos				
<i>Vireo huttoni</i>	Hutton's vireo	4	Rare	PIF
<i>Vireo gilvus</i>	Warbling vireo	4	Uncommon	PIF
Starlings (Sturnidae)				
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>	European starling	3,4,8	Common	
Sparrows, Buntings, Warblers, and Relatives (Emberizidae)				
<i>Euphagus cyanocephalus</i>	Brewer's blackbird	1,4	Common	PIF
<i>Spizella passerina</i>	Chipping sparrow	1,4	Uncommon	IUCN-LC
<i>Vermivora celata</i>	Orange-crowned warbler	8	Common	
<i>Dendroica petechia</i>	Yellow warbler	4,8	Common	CDFG-SSC, USFWS-BCC
<i>Dendroica coronata</i>	Yellow-rumped warbler	1,3,4,8	Common	
<i>Geothlypis trichas</i>	Common yellowthroat	1,3,4,8	Common	CDFG-SSC, USFWS-BCC
<i>Quiscalus mexicanus</i>	Great-tailed grackle	1,4	Uncommon	
<i>Icterus cucullatus</i>	Hooded oriole	4,8	Common	PIF
<i>Agelaius phoeniceus</i>	Red-winged blackbird	1,3,4,8	Common	
<i>Melospiza melodia</i>	Song sparrow	1,4,8	Common	CDFG-SSC
<i>Zonotrichia leucophrys</i>	White-crowned sparrow	1,3,4,8	Common	
<i>Sturnella neglecta</i>	Western meadowlark	3,4	Common	PIF
<i>Wilsonia pusilla</i>	Wilson's warbler	8	Uncommon	
<i>Pipilo crissalis</i>	California towhee	4,8	Common	PIF
Finches and Relatives (Fringillidae)				
<i>Carpodacus mexicanus</i>	House finch	3,4,8	Common	PIF
<i>Carduelis tristis</i>	American goldfinch	4	Common	
<i>Carduelis psaltria</i>	Lesser goldfinch	1,4	Common	PIF
Old World Sparrows				
<i>Passer domesticus</i>	House sparrow	4	Common	

Notes: * Frequency as cited by source, and based on regional patterns of occurrence.

PIF = DOD Partners in Flight species

S = State

F = Federal

CDFG = California Department of Fish and Game

IUCN = International Union for Conservation of Nature

USFWS = United States Fish and Wildlife Service

E = Endangered

s = Sensitive

T = Threatened

BCC = Bird of Conservation Concern

FP = Fully Protected

LC = Least Concern

SSC = Species of Special Concern

WL = Watch List

Sources: 1 – Woodward-Clyde 1998.

2 – Merkel & Associates, Inc. 2008.

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APPENDIX I
MIGRATORY BIRD MANAGEMENT

Each Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) must address the conservation of birds and their habitat to promote and support migratory birds in compliance with the Migratory Bird Treaty Act (MBTA), Executive Order (EO) 13186 and any subsequent rules, and agreements. Navy policy is that, during annual reviews of INRMPs, installations will discuss with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) conservation measures implemented and the effectiveness of these measures in avoiding, minimizing, or mitigating the take of migratory birds (U.S. Department of the Navy [Navy] 2006).

Migratory Bird Treaty Act

The MBTA of 1918 (16 USC 703-711) is legislation that covers species protected under four international treaties. These treaties are agreements between the U.S., Canada, Mexico, Japan, and Russia and protect most species of birds. The MBTA prohibits the taking or pursuing of migratory birds, their eggs, feathers, or nests. Game birds are listed and protected except where specific seasons, bag limits, and other factors govern their hunting. Exceptions are also made for some nuisance pests, which have standing federal depredation orders (e.g. yellow-headed, red-winged, tri-colored, Rusty and Brewer's blackbirds, cowbirds, all grackles, crows, magpies, rock doves, European starlings, and house sparrows). The MBTA provides the USFWS the opportunity to comment on projects potentially affecting bird species, and their habitats, that are not protected under the ESA. Violations of the MBTA can result in fines of up to \$2,000 or two years imprisonment. Therefore, if a project has the potential to affect nesting birds or nesting substrate (including the trimming of nest trees) a qualified biologist from Naval Facilities Engineering Command Southwest (NAVFAC SW) should be contacted to determine if there will be any violations of the MBTA. U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) policy states that migratory bird programs shall be established in support of and consistent with the military mission.

Executive Order 13186

The Migratory Birds EO 13186 (“Responsibilities of Federal Agencies to Protect Migratory Birds”, signed 10 January 2001) directs executive departments to take certain actions regarding the protection of migratory birds. Among these actions is the development and implementation of a MOU with the USFWS within two years of the EO on the protection and conservation of migratory birds. For DoD activities other than military readiness, migratory bird concerns are addressed through a MOU (July 2006) developed in accordance with EO 13186. The USFWS/DoD MOU (FR 30 August 2006) that evolved out of the requirements of the EO addresses the conservation of migratory birds on military lands in relation to all activities except readiness.

DoD Migratory Bird Rule and Guidance

The DoD has specific requirements under implementation of MBTA regulations. Following a U.S. District Court decision that granted an injunction on live fire military training on behalf of a private party, Congress enacted the 2003 National Defense Authorization Act (NDAA), which authorized an interim period during which the prohibitions on incidental take of migratory birds would not apply to military readiness activities. During this interim period, Congress also

directed the Secretary of Interior to, not later than one year after enactment of the NDAA, promulgate a regulation to deal with the incidental take of migratory birds in conjunction with military readiness activities from the take prohibition of the MBTA. Under the 2003 National Defense Authorization Bill, the House Armed Services Committee authorized a set of initiatives intended to “restore a balance between protecting the environment and military readiness.” One of these initiatives, regarding the MBTA, stated:

“The Migratory Bird Treaty Act allows federal agencies to obtain permits to remove migratory birds for economic or safety reasons, such as clearing geese from a golf course or runway. However, a federal court ruled in March 2002 that Navy activities at a training range near Guam violated the MBTA because the court felt that the law does not allow for permits for the accidental taking of birds during military readiness activities. As a result, the court temporarily shut down military training at the facility. In order to ensure that DoD can operate all of its facilities without further interruptions of this nature, the conferees provided the DoD with authority under which the MBTA would not apply to the incidental taking of a migratory bird by DoD during an authorized military readiness activity. In addition, the conferees directed the Secretary of the Interior, with the concurrence of DoD, to exercise its authority within one year to initiate regulations that would exempt DoD from the MBTA for incidental takings of migratory birds during authorized military readiness activities.”

In an effort to provide guidance for conflicts arising between military readiness activities and the MBTA, the USFWS issued the final rule on, "Migratory Bird Permits: Take of Migratory Birds by the Armed Forces" (50 CFR Part 21 in FR 28 February 2007, pages 8931-8950), hereinafter referred to as the Migratory Bird Rule. The Migratory Bird Rule authorizes the military to "take" migratory birds during military readiness activities under the MBTA without a permit. However, if the military determines that the activity will have a “significant adverse effect” on a population of migratory birds, they must work with the USFWS to develop and implement conservation measures to minimize and/or mitigate the effects. NBVC Port Hueneme does not anticipate any takes of migratory birds, and therefore, does not expect to use the exemption provided by the Migratory Bird Rule.

In addition to the requirements of the MBTA and its implementing regulations, the DoD and USFWS entered a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) (FR 30 August 2006), in accordance with EO 13186, which addresses the conservation of migratory birds on military lands in relation to activities other than military readiness activities. The MOU is an agreement between the DoD and the USFWS on how the two agencies will collaborate to promote the conservation of migratory bird populations. The MOU does not authorize any take.

Key to implementing the MBTA and the MOU between the USFWS and DoD are the wording of the authorization for take that requires an understanding of the definition of the following terms:

- *Population*, as used in Section 21.15, is a group of distinct, coexisting (conspecific) individuals of a single species, whose breeding site fidelity, migration routes, and wintering areas are temporally and spatially stable, sufficiently distinct geographically (at some time of the year), and adequately described so that the population can be effectively monitored to discern changes in its status.
- *Significant adverse effect on a population*, used in Section 21.15, means an effect that could, within a reasonable period of time, diminish the capacity of a population of migratory bird species to sustain itself at a biologically viable level. A population is “biologically viable” when its ability to maintain its genetic diversity, to reproduce, and to function effectively in its native ecosystem, are not significantly harmed. This effect may be characterized by increased risk to the population from actions that cause direct mortality or a reduction in fecundity. Assessment of impacts should take into account yearly variations, and migratory movements of the impacted species. Due to the significant variability in potential military readiness activities and the species that may be impacted, estimates of significant measurable decline will be determined on a case-by-case basis.

In April 2007, guidance was issued by the Under Secretary of Defense for Acquisition, Technology and Logistics on implementing the MOU to Promote the Conservation of Migratory Birds between the USFWS and DoD in accordance with EO 13186 (17 January 2001). This guidance covers all activities on DoD property including natural resources management, routine maintenance and construction, industrial activities, and hazardous waste cleanups.

The guidance emphasizes interdisciplinary collaboration in the framework of the U.S. North American Bird Conservation Initiative (NABCI) Bird Conservation Regions, collaborative inventory and long-term monitoring. Conservation measures under the Migratory Bird Rule require monitoring and record-keeping for five years from the date the Navy commence their conservation action. During INRMP reviews, the Navy must report to the USFWS migratory bird conservation measures implemented and the effectiveness of the conservation measures in avoiding, minimizing, or mitigating take of migratory birds.

However, many questions remain about how to implement the Migratory Bird Rule and the MOU. For example, how to evaluate significance and whether an effect is a “significant adverse effect” is still being determined. Since the impact assessment must be conducted on populations of migratory birds, there may be a need to collect better population baseline data.

A Council for the Conservation of Migratory Birds was established to help agencies implement EO 13186. The EO requires NEPA evaluations to include effects on migratory birds and that advance notice or annual reports must be made to the USFWS concerning actions that result in the taking of migratory birds. The EO also requires agencies to control the establishment of exotic species that may endanger migratory birds and their habitat. Pursuant to its MOU, each agency shall, to the extent permitted by law and subject to the availability of appropriations and within Administration budgetary limits, and in harmony with agency missions:

- Support the conservation intent of the migratory bird conventions by integrating bird conservation principles, measures, and practices into agency activities and by avoiding or minimizing, to the extent practicable, adverse impacts on migratory bird resources when conducting agency actions;
- Restore and enhance the habitat of migratory birds, as practicable;
- Prevent or abate the pollution or detrimental alteration of the environment, for the benefit of migratory birds, as practicable;
- Incorporate migratory bird habitat and population conservation principles, measures, and practices, into agency plans and planning processes (natural resource, land management, and environmental quality planning, including, but not limited to, forest and rangeland planning, coastal management planning, watershed planning, etc.) as practicable, and coordinate with other agencies and nonfederal partners in planning efforts;
- Within established authorities and in conjunction with the adoption, amendment, or revision of agency management plans and guidance, ensure that agency plans and actions promote programs and recommendations of comprehensive migratory bird planning efforts such as PIF, U.S. National Shorebird Plan, North American Waterfowl Management Plan, North American Colonial Waterbird Plan, and other planning efforts, as well as guidance from other sources, including the Food and Agricultural Organization's International Plan of Action for Reducing Incidental Catch of Seabirds in Longline Fisheries;
- Ensure that environmental analyses of federal actions required by the NEPA or other established environmental review processes evaluate the effects of actions and agency plans on migratory birds, with emphasis on species of concern;
- Provide notice to USFWS in advance of conducting an action that is intended to take migratory birds, or annually report to USFWS on the number of individuals of each species of migratory birds intentionally taken during the conduct of any agency action, including but not limited to banding or marking, scientific collecting, taxidermy, and depredation control;
- Minimize the intentional take of species of concern by: (i) delineating standards and procedures for such take; and (ii) developing procedures for the review and evaluation of take actions. With respect to intentional take, the MOU shall be consistent with the appropriate sections of 50 CFR parts 10, 21, and 22;

- Identify where unintentional take reasonably attributable to agency actions is having, or is likely to have, a measurable negative effect on migratory bird populations, focusing first on species of concern, priority habitats, and key risk factors. With respect to those actions so identified, the agency shall develop and use principles, standards, and practices that will lessen the amount of unintentional take, developing any such conservation efforts in cooperation with USFWS. These principles, standards, and practices shall be regularly evaluated and revised to ensure that they are effective in lessening the detrimental effect of agency actions on migratory bird populations. The agency also shall inventory and monitor bird habitat and populations within the agency's capabilities and authorities to the extent feasible to facilitate decisions about the need for, and effectiveness of, conservation efforts;
- Within the scope of its statutorily-designated authorities, control the import, export, and establishment in the wild of live exotic animals and plants that may be harmful to migratory bird resources;
- Promote research and information exchange related to the conservation of migratory bird resources, including coordinated inventorying and monitoring and the collection and assessment of information on environmental contaminants and other physical or biological stressors having potential relevance to migratory bird conservation. Where such information is collected in the course of agency actions or supported through federal financial assistance, reasonable efforts shall be made to share such information with USFWS, the USGS-Biological Resources Division, and other appropriate repositories of such data (e.g. the Cornell Laboratory of Ornithology);
- Provide training and information to appropriate employees on methods and means of avoiding or minimizing the take of migratory birds and conserving and restoring migratory bird habitat;
- Promote migratory bird conservation in international activities and with other countries and international partners, in consultation with the Department of State, as appropriate or relevant to the agency's authorities;
- Recognize and promote economic and recreational values of birds, as appropriate; and
- Develop partnerships with non-federal entities to further bird conservation.

Migratory Bird Management at NBVC Port Hueneme

Many natural resources management activities detailed in this INRMP benefit migratory birds including habitat management, erosion control, habitat restoration and invasive weed management. In addition, USFWS Birds of Conservation Concern and birds ranked in national and international plans that use NBVC Port Hueneme natural resources are identified.

Annual monitoring and regularly scheduled surveys including project or readiness surveys are performed on NBVC Port Hueneme in compliance with the Migratory Bird Rule for all avian groups and potentially affected bird species.

Of the almost 100 species recorded at NBVC Port Hueneme, 23 have some special status assigned by government or non-government agencies (ESA, CESA, MBTA, DoD Partners In Flight [PIF] species, and International Union for Conservation of Nature [IUCN]); see Appendix H Species Lists.

The following management measures are implemented by this INRMP and detailed in Section 3.4.4, Birds:

Objective: Ensure protection of bird species throughout the base and conserve, restore, and enhance migratory bird habitat, as practicable.

- I. Continue to use the NEPA Site Approval and Project Review Process (SA/PRB) (NBVCINST 11010.0) to avoid and minimize potential impacts and “takes” of migratory, resident, and special status bird species, and their habitats.
 - A. Implement bird conservation principles, measures, and practices through avoidance and minimization measures to protect migratory bird populations.
 1. Utilize species-level information gathered from surveys to guide development of project-specific BMPs for migratory birds.
 2. BMPs shall include protective measures such as siting projects to avoid important nesting areas or to avoid collisions of birds with structures, or timing projects to avoid peak breeding activity.
 3. There are no resident special status species, however, in the event that special status species are regularly recorded at NBVC Port Hueneme, identify areas of unintentional take of species of concern and minimize such take. EO 13186 states that agencies will identify where unintentional take reasonably attributable to agency actions is having, or is likely to have, a measurable negative effect on migratory bird populations, focusing first on species of concern, priority habitats, and key risk factors. With respect to those actions, the agency (NBVC) shall develop and use principles, standards, and practices that will lessen the amount of unintentional take, developing any such conservation efforts in cooperation with the USFWS. These principles, standards, and practices shall be regularly evaluated and revised to ensure that they are effective in lessening the detrimental effect of agency actions on migratory bird populations.

- a. Restrict access into and disturbance of nesting and breeding grounds during critical periods. Incorporate this restriction as mitigation for proposed projects.
 - b. Prevent or abate effects on migratory bird populations caused by pollution.
 - c. Reduce pesticide use (see also Section 2.3.1 Landscaping and Grounds Maintenance).
 - d. Limit the use of rodenticides. Remove any dead or dying rodents from a treated area to reduce the possibility of secondary poisoning through raptor predation of poisoned rodents.
4. Protect natural habitats, especially primary roosting, foraging, and nesting areas, from human induced disturbance and invasive species.
- a. Provide training and information to facility managers regarding protection of migratory birds in compliance with laws to avoid and minimize take, and conserve and restore habitat (EO 13186).
 - b. Limit disturbance during the breeding season. When such actions are absolutely necessary during the breeding season, ensure that NBVC ED has provided approval and disturbance is timed to minimize its impacts on nesting birds and avoid take.
 - c. Ensure tree trimming occurs outside the nesting season, except for instances where health and safety are a concern; in this instance, coordination with NBVC ED must occur prior to tree trimming activities.
 - d. Ensure surveys are conducted prior to building maintenance, restructuring, or demolition activities.
 - e. Ensure tenants are aware of protocols for responding to birds injured or trapped inside buildings and warehouses.
 - f. Protect wetland habitat as directed by EO 11990 and Navy policy (OPNAVINST 5090.1C).
 - g. Avoid detrimental habitat alteration caused by establishment of invasive plants. Eliminate and prevent the spread of invasive species that crowd out other species necessary to migratory bird survival (2003 Defense Reauthorization Act [DRA] Proposed Rule).
 - a. Conduct regular program of weed removal from areas identified as primary roosting, foraging, and nesting areas.

- h. Identify opportunities and funding for restoration or enhancement of degraded bird habitats.
- i. Support cleanup efforts to reduce contaminants and toxic buildup in the ecosystem, including monitoring and reducing nonpoint sources.
- j. Maintain closure signs and gates around Brandt's cormorants nesting colonies.
- k. Work with facilities to resolve conflicts associated with excessive cormorant bird feces by modifying the wall or potentially excluding nesting and roosting habitat and potentially providing cormorants with an alternative nesting site, if available.

Objective: Conduct a regular program of bird monitoring throughout the Base to improve the current inventory and inform on listed species' usage of the harbor, in order to facilitate and guide natural resource management decisions.

- II. Monitor populations and maintain, restore, and enhance habitats that provide for the health of migratory and resident populations of birds depending on habitats at NBVC Port Hueneme to complete their life cycles, emphasizing Birds of Conservation Concern and other special status species.
 - A. Inventory and monitor habitat and populations of migratory birds that use NBVC Port Hueneme to evaluate conservation effectiveness
 - B. Identify migratory bird species of concern that will be the focus of monitoring.
 - 1. To identify bird species of concern, use periodic reports of Birds of Conservation Concern published by the USFWS Division of Migratory Bird Management; priority migratory bird species documented in the comprehensive bird conservation plans (U.S. Shorebird Conservation Plan, Colonial Seabird Conservation Plan, North American Waterbird Conservation Plan); species or populations of waterfowl identified as high, or moderately high, continental priority in the North American Waterfowl Management Plan; focus species identified in the California Partners-In-Flight (PIF) plans; listed threatened and endangered bird species in 50 CFR 17.11; and MBTA-listed game birds below desired population size
 - 2.
 - C. Maximize the effectiveness of ongoing monitoring and management efforts by continuing to implement standardized, scientifically sound survey protocols to collect and analyze distribution of birds across habitat types and seasonally
 - 1. Consolidate existing migratory bird monitoring information.

2. Maximize cost effectiveness by collecting standardized data on multiple species in addition to any specialized protocols aimed at one species.
 3. Inventory birds using methods that can be integrated with the work of regional partners.
 - a. Investigate the compatibility of the USDA Forest Service (USFS) published guidelines for standardized monitoring techniques for monitoring birds (Ralph *et al.* 1993).
 - b. Determine how current established monitoring programs might contribute to regional databases and monitoring protocols.
- D. Collect and assess information on environmental contaminants and other physical or biological stressors having potential relevance to migratory bird conservation. Where such information is collected in the course of agency actions or supported through federal financial assistance, reasonable efforts shall be made to share such information with the USFWS, U.S. Geological Survey-Biological Resources Division, and other appropriate repositories of such data.
- E. To comply with the DRA, use the best scientific data available to assess through the NEPA process, or other environmental requirements, the expected impact of proposed or ongoing military readiness activities on migratory bird species likely to occur in action areas.
- F. Regularly monitor infrastructure that may pose a hazard to migratory birds in order to document any significant adverse impact to populations.
- G. NBVC Port Hueneme has no resident listed species, however, in the event that they are regularly recorded on base, the following applies: Through the SA/PRB process, address project impacts on species of concern thoroughly and specifically, focusing on the effects of the proposed action on the sustainability of these populations. Special consideration should be given to priority habitats, such as important nesting areas, migration stop-over areas, and wintering habitats.
- H. Include the results of monitoring in the annual review of this INRMP.
- I. Promote research and information exchange, including coordinated inventory and monitoring (EO 13186).
 1. Increase communication and coordination between land managers and specialists hired to implement specific projects or conduct monitoring.
 2. Use cooperative assistance from wildlife agencies, organizations, and volunteers to help collect needed data. Integrate with regional databases.

III. Monitor populations of resident land birds, shorebird, and seabirds to protect sustainability of populations, breeding colonies, and their habitat.

APPENDIX I REFERENCES

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APPENDIX J
BENEFITS FOR THREATENED AND ENDANGERED SPECIES

Under the National Defense Authorization Act (NDAA) of 2004 (PL 108-136), the Endangered Species Act (ESA) was revised to recognize Integrated Natural Resources. Management Plan (INRMP) conservation measures and species benefits, that could obviate the need for critical habitat on Navy lands. Section (a)(3)(b)(i) of the ESA reads: *“The Secretary of the Interior shall not designate as critical habitat any lands or other geographical areas owned or controlled by USDOD, or designated for its use, that are subject to an integrated natural resources management plan prepared under section 101 of the SAIA (16 USC 670a), if the Secretary determines in writing that such plan provides a benefit to the species for which critical habitat is proposed for designation.”*

All Navy installations with federally listed threatened or endangered species, proposed federally listed threatened or endangered species, candidate species, or unoccupied habitat for a listed species where critical habitat may be designated, must structure the INRMP to avoid the designation of critical habitat. If the INRMP specifically addresses the benefit provided to the listed species, and provisions are made for the long-term conservation of the species, the INRMP may preclude the need for critical habitat on the installation (Navy 2010). The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) determined that, where applicable, federal critical habitat designation is not warranted if the INRMP includes the following three criteria:

- 1. The plan provides a conservation benefit to the species.** The cumulative benefits of the management activities identified in a management plan, for the length of the plan, must maintain or provide for an increase in a species’ population, or the enhancement or restoration of its habitat in the area covered by the plan (i.e., those areas deemed essential to the conservation of the species). A conservation benefit may result from reducing fragmentation of habitat, maintaining or increasing populations, ensuring against catastrophic events, enhancing and restoring habitats, buffering protected areas, or testing and implementing new conservation strategies.
- 2. The plan provides certainty that the management plan will be implemented.** Persons charged with plan implementation are capable of accomplishing the objectives of the management plan and have adequate funding for the management plan. They have the authority to implement the plan and have obtained all the necessary authorizations or approvals. An implementation schedule (including completion dates) for the conservation effort is in the plan.
- 3. The plan provides certainty that the conservation effort will be effective.** The following criteria will be considered when determining the effectiveness of the conservation effort. The plan includes:
 - A. Biological goals (broad guiding principles for the program) and objectives (measurable targets for achieving the goals);
 - B. Quantifiable, scientifically valid parameters that will demonstrate achievement of objectives, and standards for these parameters by which progress will be measured, are identified;
 - C. Provisions for monitoring and, where appropriate, adaptive management;

- D. Provisions for reporting progress on implementation (based on compliance with the implementation schedule) and effectiveness (based on evaluation of quantifiable parameters) of the conservation effort are provided; and
- E. A duration sufficient to implement the plan and achieve the benefits of its goals and objectives.

Federally threatened and endangered species observed at NBVC Port Hueneme include the federally threatened western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*), federally endangered California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*), and federally threatened southern sea otter (*Enhydra lutris nereis*). The federally threatened least Bell's vireo (*Vireo bellii pusillus*) is addressed herein, due to its potential for occurrence on site, but to date, has not been found. These species and management strategies are addressed in Section 3.5 Special Status Species and Their Protection.

Western Snowy Plover and California Least Tern

1. The plan provides a conservation benefit to the species.

The plan will provide a cumulative benefit to western snowy plovers and California least terns that may occur at NBVC Port Hueneme, through management efforts focused on conservation and enhancement of foraging and roosting habitat, and protection of bird species and their nesting habitats. The implementation of management strategies detailed in the following sections will provide a cumulative benefit to western snowy plovers and California least terns:

Section 1.11, Ecosystem Approach

Section 3.2.2.1, Shoreline Sediment

Section 3.2.3, Water Resources and Water Management

Section 3.3.1, Coastal and Marine Communities

Section 3.4.4, Birds

Section 3.5, Special Status Species and Their Protection

Section 3.6, Invasive Species Management

Section 3.7, Natural Resources Law Enforcement

Section 3.8, Data Integration, Access, and Reporting

Section 4.1, Integrated Military Mission and Sustainable Land Use Decisions/Operations
Planning and Review

Section 4.3, Environmental Awareness

Section 4.4, Beneficial Partnerships and Collaborative Resources Planning

Section 4.5, Regulatory Compliance

Section 4.6, Natural Resources Consultation Requirements Project and Mitigation Planning

Section 4.8, Remediation of Contaminated Media

Section 4.9, Oil Spill Response and Hazardous Substance Prevention and Cleanup, and

Section 4.10, Harbor Operations

2. The plan provides certainty that the management plan will be implemented.

NBVC Port Hueneme intends to implement recommendations in this INRMP within the framework of regulatory compliance, national Navy mission obligations, anti-terrorism and force protection limitations, and funding constraints. All management actions prescribed in this INRMP are subject to the availability of funds properly authorized and appropriated under federal law. Section 5.0, Implementation Strategy, details how the plan will be funded and implemented.

Budget priorities for threatened and endangered species management, especially compliance with Biological Opinions, receive the *highest possible* budgeting priority (Environmental Readiness Level [ERL] 4), and support NBVC Port Hueneme's need to avoid critical habitat designations under Section 4(b)(2) of the ESA, or Section 4(a)3 of the ESA (exemption from critical habitat designations for national security reasons). ERL 4 is considered the absolute minimum level of environmental readiness capability required to maintain compliance with applicable legal requirements. (See Section 5.3.1, Natural Resources Management Priorities and Funding Classifications, for detail on funding classifications).

Persons charged with implementing the management strategies prescribed in this INRMP are NBVC Environmental Division (ED) staff and external support. ED staff that will ensure implementation include an ecologist, wildlife biologist, and environmental protection specialist (NEPA coordinator). Where specialized skill or certifications are required and not met with NBVC staff, external support from consultants, researchers, or other agency staff will be contracted. (See Section 5.3.2, External Assistance, for detail on opportunities for external assistance with INRMP implementation).

The management plan will be implemented through projects detailed in Appendix E, Table E-4, Implementation Table. Their funding and authorization is approved through designation of the following Environmental Program Requirements (EPR) project codes and descriptions:

- 69232x0102–Revision and Update of Hueneme INMRP and EA
- 69232x0155–Species Surveys of Hueneme
- 6923200050–Upland and Wetland Restoration for Hueneme
- 6923224086– Bio-Security Barge Monitoring
- 631226xxx37– Wetland Delineation 5-year Updates
- 0024298019–GIS and Data Management for INRMPs

The table details the schedule for specific management strategies, including proposed completion dates.

3. The plan provides certainty that the conservation effort will be effective.

The effectiveness of the management effort is ensured through defined goals and objectives for each issue area, and the assignment of specific strategies to meet these goals and objectives. The following sections detail objectives, parameters for measuring progress, monitoring and adaptive management, reporting progress on implementation, and duration, specific to the management of western snowy plovers and California least terns.

A. Biological Goals and Objectives

The following objective and management strategies are detailed in Section 3.4.4, Birds:

Objective: Ensure protection of bird species throughout the base and conserve, restore, and enhance migratory bird habitat, as practicable.

- I. Continue to use the Site Approval/Project Review Board process (SA/PRB) to avoid and minimize potential impacts and “takes” of migratory, resident, and special status bird species, and their habitats.
 - A. Implement bird conservation principles, measures, and practices through avoidance and minimization measures to protect migratory bird populations.
 - I. There are currently no nesting special status species. If special status species nest at NBVC Port Hueneme, identify areas of unintentional take of species of concern and minimize such take. These principles, standards, and practices shall be regularly evaluated and revised to ensure that they are effective in lessening the detrimental effect of actions on migratory bird populations.
 2. Protect natural habitats, especially primary roosting, foraging, and nesting areas, from human induced disturbance and invasive species.
 - a. Provide training and information to facility managers regarding protection of migratory birds in compliance with laws to avoid and minimize take, and conserve and restore habitat (EO 13186).
 - b. Limit disturbance during the breeding season. When disturbing actions are absolutely necessary during the breeding season, ensure that NBVC ED has provided approval, disturbance is timed to minimize its impacts on nesting birds, and avoid take.

- c. Avoid detrimental habitat alteration caused by establishment of invasive plants. Eliminate and prevent the spread of invasive species that crowd out other species necessary to migratory bird survival (2003 Defense Reauthorization Act [DRA] Proposed Rule).

3. Work with facilities to protect nesting habitat for cormorants and resolve conflicts associated with bird feces, by modifying the wall.

The following objective and management strategies that address protection of listed species are detailed in Section 3.5.3, Special Status Species Protection:

Objective: Protect and enhance federally endangered or threatened species, species proposed for listing as endangered or threatened, and federal candidate species for listing that occur at NBVC Port Hueneme in accordance with the federal ESA of 1973, as amended. Protect and enhance state-listed, state proposed listed, and state candidate species for listing.

- A. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to special status species and their habitats. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.
- II. Enhance and restore habitats used by special status species.
- A. Conduct habitat restoration as outlined in habitat-specific goals and strategies in this INMRP.
 - B. Limit human disturbance by protecting areas used by special status species.
 1. Restrict access to protected areas.
 2. Install signs to inform on sensitive species and habitats.
 3. Educate personnel on protected species regulations and responsibilities.

B. Parameters for Measuring Achievement of Objectives and Progress of INRMP Implementation

Progress of management plan implementation will be measured and tracked annually using natural resources metrics, as detailed in U.S. Department of Defense Instruction (DoDINST) 4715.03 *Natural Resources Conservation Program* and described in Section 5.2, Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review and Metrics. Annual reviews occur in coordination with USFWS and California Department of Fish and Game (CDFG), and results from the review are used to update and adapt management strategies.

The INRMP Implementation Guidance (10 October 2002 Memo) added tracking procedures, called metrics, to ensure proper coordination occurs and that projects are implemented. The Navy Conservation Website details a set of metrics, as defined by CNIC, for Navy natural

resources managers to measure conservation impacts on installation missions, and the success of partnerships with the USFWS and state fish and game agencies, as required by the Sikes Act Improvement Act (SAIA) of 1997 (as amended). The Navy Conservation Website describes seven natural resources metrics focus areas including: (1) INRMP Project Implementation, (2) Listed Species and Critical Habitat, (3) Partnership Effectiveness, (4) Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use, (5) Team Adequacy, (6) Ecosystem Integrity, and (7) INRMP Impact on the Installation Mission. Each focus area has three to seven criteria used to determine the status of a given functional area in natural resources.

The criteria used for tracking and measuring the effectiveness of implementation of the INRMP on managing western snowy plovers and California least terns include:

- The sandy beach habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme is free of human-induced disturbances and invasive species, and thereby provides habitat for western snowy plovers and California least terns. Management strategies that ensure this criterion will be met are detailed in Section 3.3.1.2, Sandy Beach.
- Results from regular monitoring of Surface Warfare Engineering Facility beach, for use by other shorebirds, will convey the suitability of the habitat for roosting and foraging western snowy plovers and California least terns.
- Results from regular monitoring of the Port Hueneme Harbor, for use by other foraging piscivorous birds, will convey the suitability of the marine subtidal habitat in providing foraging opportunities for California least terns.

C. Monitoring and Adaptive Management

Section 3.4.4, Birds, and Section 3.5.3, Special Status Species Protection, include provisions for monitoring western snowy plovers and California least terns, through regularly scheduled surveys. The objective and management strategies in Section 3.4.4, Birds that address monitoring are:

Objective: Conduct a regular program of bird monitoring throughout the base to improve the current inventory and document listed species' use of the harbor to facilitate and guide natural resource management decisions.

- I. Inventory and monitor habitat and populations of migratory and resident birds that use NBVC Port Hueneme, to evaluate conservation effectiveness.
 - A. Maximize the effectiveness of ongoing monitoring and management by continuing to implement standardized, scientifically sound survey protocols to collect and analyze distribution of birds across habitat types and seasonally.
 1. Consolidate existing migratory bird monitoring information.

2. Maximize cost effectiveness by collecting standardized data on multiple species in addition to any specialized protocols aimed at one species.
 3. Inventory birds using methods that can be integrated with the work of regional partners.
 - a. Investigate the compatibility of the U.S. Forest Service published guidelines for standardized monitoring techniques for monitoring birds (Ralph *et al.* 1993).
 - b. Determine how current established monitoring programs might contribute to regional databases and monitoring protocols.
- B. Collect and assess information on environmental contaminants and other physical or biological stressors having potential relevance to migratory bird conservation. Where such information is collected in the course of agency actions or supported through federal financial assistance, reasonable efforts shall be made to share such information with the USFWS, U.S. Geological Survey Biological Resources Division, and other appropriate repositories of such data.
- C. To comply with the DRA, use the best scientific data available to assess through the NEPA process, or other environmental requirements, the expected impact of proposed or ongoing military readiness activities on migratory bird species likely to occur in action areas.
- D. Regularly monitor infrastructure that may pose a hazard to migratory birds to document any significant adverse impact to populations.
- E. If special status species nest or occupy habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme, address impacts on species of concern more thoroughly and specifically, focusing on the effects of the proposed action on the sustainability of these populations. Special consideration should be given to priority habitats, such as important nesting areas, migration stop-over areas, and wintering habitats.
- F. Include the results of monitoring in the annual review of this INRMP.
- G. Promote research and information exchange, including coordinated inventory and monitoring (EO 13186).
 1. Increase communication and coordination between land managers and specialists hired to implement specific projects or conduct monitoring.
 2. Use cooperative assistance from wildlife agencies, organizations, and volunteers to help collect needed data. Integrate with regional databases.

The following objective details the objective and management strategies in Section 3.5.3, Special Status Species Protection, for monitoring special status species:

Objective: Continue to conduct surveys for presence of federally endangered or threatened species, species proposed for listing as endangered or threatened, and federal candidate species for listing. If listed species are found using habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme, then support surveys in accordance with the federal ESA of 1973, as amended. Support surveys for state-listed, proposed listed species, and state candidate species for listing.

- I. Conduct surveys (using established methodology) of listed species to determine presence of species during breeding and nonbreeding season.
 1. Develop a standard format and a database to collect and maintain records of observations.
 2. If new listed species are found, contact USFWS to discuss recommendations on how to modify the INRMP to manage this species.
- B. Promote research and information exchange, including coordinated inventory and monitoring (EO 13186).
 1. Increase communication and coordination between land managers and specialists hired to implement specific projects or conduct monitoring.
 2. Partner with, and use cooperative assistance from, wildlife agencies, organizations, and volunteers to help collect needed data. Integrate with regional databases.

D. Reporting Progress on Implementation

NBVC will annually update and report on progress of implementation for the INRMP and include management activities pertaining to western snowy plovers and California least terns that may occur at NBVC Port Hueneme. The measures that will be taken to ensure that the provisions for reporting progress are adhered to are detailed in Section 5.2, Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review and Metrics and provided below:

- I. Fulfill the reporting requirements of new measures to promote better understanding of the health of Navy conservation programs, using the Navy Conservation Website's natural resources metrics focus areas, as defined by CNIC.
- II. Track implementation to guide and learn from past experience.
 - A. Derive the most benefit possible from learning and experience by documenting it and disseminating the information.
 - B. To track the progress of each of the INRMP's strategies, a spreadsheet program (e.g., Paradox, Access) and GIS geodatabase should be constructed and maintained. Fields can be included to help (a) build queries; (b) track progress by location, type, sponsor, year, etc.; and (c) provide different types of reports.

E. Duration

The duration of the INRMP is indefinite and will be updated and revised as needed to adapt to changing conditions and management needs; this is sufficient to implement the plan and achieve the benefits of its goals and objectives.

Southern Sea Otter

1. The plan provides a conservation benefit to the species.

The plan will provide a cumulative benefit to southern sea otters that may occur at NBVC Port Hueneme, through management efforts focused on protection of kelp beds, marine subtidal habitat, sandy beach habitat, and other marine mammal haul out sites. The implementation of management strategies detailed in the following sections will provide a cumulative benefit to southern sea otters:

Section 1.11, Ecosystem Approach

Section 3.2.2.1, Shoreline Sediment

Section 3.2.3, Water Resources and Water Management

Section 3.3.1, Coastal and Marine Communities

Section 3.4.8, Marine Mammals

Section 3.5, Special Status Species and Their Protection

Section 3.6, Invasive Species Management

Section 3.7, Natural Resources Law Enforcement

Section 3.8, Data Integration, Access and Reporting

Section 4.1, Integrated Military Mission and Sustainable Land Use Decisions/Operations
Planning and Review

Section 4.3, Environmental Awareness

Section 4.4, Beneficial Partnerships and Collaborative Resources Planning

Section 4.5, Regulatory Compliance

Section 4.6, Natural Resources Consultation Requirements, Project and Mitigation
Planning

Section 4.8, Remediation of Contaminated Media

Section 4.9, Oil Spill Response and Hazardous Substance Prevention and Cleanup, and

Section 4.10, Harbor Operations.

2. The plan provides certainty that the management plan will be implemented.

NBVC Port Hueneme intends to implement recommendations in this INRMP within the framework of regulatory compliance, national Navy mission obligations, anti-terrorism and force protection limitations, and funding constraints. All management actions prescribed in this INRMP are subject to the availability of funds properly authorized and appropriated under federal law. Section 5.0 Implementation Strategy details how the plan will be funded and implemented.

Budget priorities for threatened and endangered species management, especially compliance with Biological Opinions, receive the *highest possible* budgeting priority (Environmental Readiness Level [ERL] 4), and support NBVC Port Hueneme's need to avoid critical habitat designations under Section 4(b)(2) of the ESA, or Section 4(a)3 of the ESA (exemption from critical habitat designations for national security reasons). ERL 4 is considered the absolute minimum level of environmental readiness capability required to maintain compliance with applicable legal requirements. (See Section 5.3.1 Natural Resources Management Priorities and Funding Classifications for detail on funding classifications).

Persons charged with implementing the management strategies prescribed in this INRMP are NBVC Environmental Division staff and external support. NBVC Environmental Division staff that will ensure implementation of this INRMP include an ecologist, wildlife biologist, and environmental protection specialist (NEPA coordinator). Where specialized skill or certifications are required and not met with NBVC staff, external support from consultants, researchers, or other agency staff will be contracted. (See Section 5.3.2 External Assistance for detail on opportunities for external assistance with INRMP implementation).

The management plan will be implemented through projects detailed in Appendix E, Table E-4 Implementation Table. Their funding and authorization is approved through designation of the following Environmental Program Requirements (EPR) project codes and descriptions:

- 69232x0102–Revision and Update of Hueneme INMRP and EA
- 69232x0155–Species Surveys of Hueneme
- 6923200050–Upland and Wetland Restoration for Hueneme
- 6923224086– Bio-security Barge Monitoring
- 631226xxx37– Wetland Delineation 5-year Updates
- 0024298019–GIS and Data Management for INRMPs

Appendix E, Table E-4 Implementation Table details the schedule for specific management strategies, including proposed completion dates.

3. The plan provides certainty that the conservation effort will be effective.

A. Biological Goals and Objectives

The following objective and management strategies are detailed in Section 3.4.8 Marine Mammals:

Objective: Protect marine mammals and their habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to marine mammals and their habitats.
 - A. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.
- II. Maintain compliance with MMPA mandates.
 - A. Continue to monitor marine mammal populations and evaluate interactions related to base activities.
 - I. Monitor and protect NBVC Port Hueneme haul out sites, where not in conflict with mission critical needs.
 - B. Implement educational instruction on marine mammal issues and individual responsibility for NBVC Port Hueneme personnel, for presentation during indoctrination.
 - C. Ensure facility tenants know who to call in the case of marine mammal strandings.

The following objective and management strategies address protection of southern sea otter habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme, and are detailed under Section 3.3.1.1 Marine Subtidal:

Objective: Manage for ecological integrity of marine subtidal habitat on base.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to avoid and minimize potential impacts to marine subtidal habitat.
- II. Implement protection measures for kelp beds at NBVC Port Hueneme.
- III. Maintain current GIS surveys of the spatial extent of kelp beds within base boundaries.

The following objective and management strategies that address protection of listed species are detailed under Section 3.5.3 Special Status Species Protection:

Objective: Protect and enhance federally endangered or threatened species, species proposed for listing as endangered or threatened, and federal candidate species for listing that occur at NBVC Port Hueneme in accordance with the federal ESA of 1973, as amended. Protect and enhance state-listed, proposed listed species, and state candidate species for listing.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to special status species and their habitats.
 - A. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.
- II. Enhance and restore habitats used by special status species.
 - A. Conduct habitat restoration as outlined in habitat-specific goals and strategies in this INMRP.
 - B. Limit human disturbance by protecting areas used by special status species.
 1. Restrict access to protected areas.
 2. Install signs to inform on sensitive species and habitats.
 3. Educate personnel on protected species regulations and responsibilities.

B. Parameters for Measuring Achievement of Objectives and Progress of INRMP Implementation

Progress of management plan implementation will be measured and tracked annually using natural resources metrics, as detailed in DoDINST 4715.03 *Natural Resources Conservation Program* and described in Section 5.2 Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review and Metrics. Annual reviews occur in coordination with USFWS and CDFG, and results from the review are used to update and adapt management strategies.

The INRMP Implementation Guidance (10 October 2002 Memo) added tracking procedures, called metrics, to ensure proper INRMP coordination occurs and that projects are implemented. The Navy Conservation Website describes a set of metrics, as defined by CNIC, for Navy Natural Resources managers to measure conservation impacts on installation missions, and the success of partnerships with the USFWS and state fish and game agencies, as required by the SAIA. The Navy Conservation Website details seven natural resources metrics focus areas which include: 1) INRMP Project Implementation, 2) Listed Species and Critical Habitat, 3) Partnership Effectiveness, 4) Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use, 5) Team Adequacy, 6) Ecosystem Integrity, and 7) INRMP Impact on the Installation Mission. Each focus area has three to seven criteria that are used to determine the status of a given functional area within Natural Resources.

The criteria used for tracking and measuring the effectiveness of implementation of the INRMP on managing southern sea otters include:

- The kelp beds in Port Hueneme Harbor do not decrease in size, and thereby continue to provide habitat for southern sea otters. Management strategies that ensure this criterion will be met are detailed in Section 3.3.1.1 Marine Subtidal.
- Results from regular monitoring of the Port Hueneme Harbor, for use by other marine mammals, will convey the suitability of the marine subtidal habitat for southern sea otters.

C. Monitoring and Adaptive Management

Section 3.4.8, Marine Mammals and Section 3.5.3, Special Status Species Protection include provisions for monitoring for presence of southern sea otters, through regularly scheduled surveys of harbor waters, Wharf D, and the sandy beach habitat. Following are the objective and management strategies under Section 3.4.8 Marine Mammals that address monitoring:

- I. Maintain compliance with MMPA mandates.
 - A. Continue to monitor marine mammal populations and evaluate interactions related to base activities.
 1. Monitor and protect NBVC Port Hueneme haul out sites, where not in conflict with mission critical needs.

The following details the objective and management strategies under Section 3.5.3, Special Status Species Protection, for monitoring special status species:

Objective: Continue to conduct surveys for presence of federally endangered or threatened species, species proposed for listing as endangered or threatened, and federal candidate species for listing. If listed species are found using habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme, then support surveys in accordance with the federal ESA of 1973, as amended. Support surveys for state-listed, state proposed listed, and state candidate species for listing.

- I. Conduct surveys (using established methodology) of listed species to determine presence of species during breeding and nonbreeding season.
 - i. Develop a standard format and a database to collect and maintain records of observations.
 - ii. If new listed species are found, contact USFWS to discuss recommendations on how to modify the INRMP to manage this species.

- B. Promote research and information exchange, including coordinated inventory and monitoring (EO 13186).
 - i. Increase communication and coordination between land managers and specialists hired to implement specific projects or conduct monitoring.
 - ii. Partner with, and use cooperative assistance from, wildlife agencies, organizations, and volunteers to help collect needed data. Integrate with regional databases.

C. Reporting Progress on Implementation

NBVC will annually update and report on progress of implementation for the INRMP and include management activities pertaining to southern sea otters that may occur at NBVC Port Hueneme. The measures that will be taken to ensure that the provisions for reporting progress are adhered to are detailed in Section 5.2 Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review and Metrics and provided below:

- I. Fulfill the reporting requirements of new measures to promote better understanding of the health of Navy conservation programs, using the Navy Conservation Website's natural resources metrics focus areas, as defined by CNIC.
- II. Track implementation to guide and learn from past experience.
 - A. Derive the most benefit possible from learning and experience by documenting it and disseminating the information to others.
 - B. To track the progress of each of the INRMP's strategies, a spreadsheet program (e.g. Paradox, Access) and GIS geodatabase should be constructed and maintained. Fields can be included to help (a) build queries; (b) track progress by location, type, sponsor, year, etc.; and (c) provide different types of reports.

E. Duration

The duration of the INRMP is indefinite and will be updated and revised as needed to adapt to changing conditions and management needs; this is sufficient to implement the plan and achieve the benefits of its goals and objectives.

Least Bell's Vireo

1. The plan provides a conservation benefit to the species.

The plan will provide a cumulative benefit to least Bell's vireos that may occur at NBVC Port Hueneme, through management efforts focused on conservation of riparian habitat and protection of bird species. The implementation of management strategies detailed in the following sections will provide a cumulative benefit to least Bell's vireos at NBVC Port Hueneme:

Section 1.11, Ecosystem Approach

Section 3.2.2.1, Shoreline Sediment

Section 3.2.3, Water Resources and Water Management

Section 3.3.2.4, Willow-Bulrush-Cattail

Section 3.4.4, Birds

Section 3.5, Special Status Species and Their Protection

Section 3.6, Invasive Species Management

Section 3.7, Natural Resources Law Enforcement

Section 3.8, Data Integration, Access and Reporting

Section 4.1, Integrated Military Mission and Sustainable Land Use Decisions/Operations
Planning and Review

Section 4.3, Environmental Awareness

Section 4.4, Beneficial Partnerships and Collaborative Resources Planning

Section 4.5, Regulatory Compliance

Section 4.6, Natural Resources Consultation Requirements, Project and Mitigation
Planning

Section 4.8, Remediation of Contaminated Media

Section 4.9, Oil Spill Response and Hazardous Substance Prevention and Cleanup, and

Section 4.10, Harbor Operations.

2. The plan provides certainty that the management plan will be implemented.

NBVC Port Hueneme intends to implement recommendations in this INRMP within the framework of regulatory compliance, national Navy mission obligations, anti-terrorism and force protection limitations, and funding constraints. All management actions prescribed in this

INRMP are subject to the availability of funds properly authorized and appropriated under federal law. Section 5.0 Implementation Strategy details how the plan will be funded and implemented.

Budget priorities for threatened and endangered species management, especially compliance with Biological Opinions, receive the *highest possible* budgeting priority (Environmental Readiness Level [ERL] 4), and support NBVC Port Hueneme's need to avoid critical habitat designations under Section 4(b)(2) of the ESA, or Section 4(a)3 of the ESA (exemption from critical habitat designations for national security reasons). ERL 4 is considered the absolute minimum level of environmental readiness capability required to maintain compliance with applicable legal requirements. (See Section 5.3.1 Natural Resources Management Priorities and Funding Classifications for detail on funding classifications).

Persons charged with implementing the management strategies prescribed in this INRMP are NBVC Environmental Division staff and external support. NBVC Environmental Division staff that will ensure implementation of this INRMP include an ecologist, wildlife biologist, and environmental protection specialist (NEPA coordinator). Where specialized skill or certifications are required and not met with NBVC staff, external support from consultants, researchers, or other agency staff will be contracted. (See Section 5.3.2 External Assistance for detail on opportunities for external assistance with INRMP implementation).

The management plan will be implemented through projects detailed in Appendix E, Table E-4 Implementation Table. Their funding and authorization is approved through designation of the following Environmental Program Requirements (EPR) project codes and descriptions:

- 69232x0102–Revision and Update of Hueneme INMRP and EA
- 69232x0155–Species Surveys of Hueneme
- 6923200050–Upland and Wetland Restoration for Hueneme
- 6923224086– Bio-security Barge Monitoring
- 631226xxx37– Wetland Delineation 5-year Updates
- 0024298019–GIS and Data Management for INRMPs

Appendix E, Table E-4 Implementation Table details the schedule for specific management strategies, including proposed completion dates.

3. The plan provides certainty that the conservation effort will be effective.

The effectiveness of the management effort is ensured through defined goals and objectives for each issue area, and the assignment of specific strategies to meet these goals and objectives. The following sections detail objectives, parameters for measuring progress, monitoring and adaptive management, reporting progress on implementation, and duration, specific to the management of least Bell's vireos at NBVC Port Hueneme.

C. Biological Goals and Objectives

The following objective and management strategies are detailed in Section 3.4.4 Birds:

Objective: Ensure protection of bird species throughout the base and conserve, restore, and enhance migratory bird habitat, as practicable.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to avoid and minimize potential impacts and “takes” of migratory, resident, and special status bird species, and their habitats.
 - A. Implement bird conservation principles, measures, and practices through avoidance and minimization measures to protect migratory bird populations.
 1. There are currently no nesting special status species, however, if special status species nest at NBVC Port Hueneme, identify areas of unintentional take of species of concern and minimize such take. These principles, standards, and practices shall be regularly evaluated and revised to ensure that they are effective in lessening the detrimental effect of actions on migratory bird populations.
 2. Protect natural habitats, especially primary roosting, foraging, and nesting areas, from human induced disturbance and invasive species.
 - a. Provide training and information to facility managers regarding protection of migratory birds in compliance with laws to avoid and minimize take, and conserve and restore habitat (EO 13186).
 - b. Limit disturbance during the breeding season. When disturbing actions are absolutely necessary during the breeding season, ensure that NBVC ED has provided approval and disturbance is timed to minimize its impacts on nesting birds and avoid take.
 - c. Avoid detrimental habitat alteration caused by establishment of invasive plants. Eliminate and prevent the spread of invasive species that crowd out other species necessary to migratory bird survival (2003 Defense Reauthorization Act [DRA] Proposed Rule).
 3. Work with facilities to protect nesting habitat for cormorants and resolve conflicts associated with bird feces, by modifying wall.

The following objective and management strategies that address protection of listed species are detailed under Section 3.5.3 Special Status Species Protection:

Objective: Protect and enhance federally endangered or threatened species, species proposed for listing as endangered or threatened, and federal candidate species for listing that occur at NBVC Port Hueneme in accordance with the federal ESA of 1973, as amended. Protect and enhance state-listed, proposed listed species, and state candidate species for listing.

- I. Continue to use the SA/PRB to minimize potential impacts to special status species and their habitats.
 - A. Use species information and their habitat requirements to guide the development of project-specific BMPs.
- II. Enhance and restore habitats used by special status species.
 - A. Conduct habitat restoration as outlined in habitat-specific goals and strategies in this INMRP.
 - B. Limit human disturbance by protecting areas used by special status species.
 1. Restrict access to protected areas.
 2. Install signs to inform on sensitive species and habitats.
 3. Educate personnel on protected species regulations and responsibilities.

D. Parameters for Measuring Achievement of Objectives and Progress of INRMP Implementation

Progress of management plan implementation will be measured and tracked annually using natural resources metrics, as detailed in DoDINST 4715.03 *Natural Resources Conservation Program* and described in Section 5.2 Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review and Metrics. Annual reviews occur in coordination with USFWS and CDFG, and results from the review are used to update and adapt management strategies.

The INRMP Implementation Guidance (10 October 2002 Memo) added tracking procedures, called metrics, to ensure proper INRMP coordination occurs and that projects are implemented. The Navy Conservation Website details a set of metrics, as defined by CNIC, for Navy Natural Resources managers to measure conservation impacts on installation missions, and the success of partnerships with the USFWS and state fish and game agencies, as required by the SAIA. The Navy Conservation Website contains seven natural resources metrics focus areas which include: 1) INRMP Project Implementation, 2) Listed Species and Critical Habitat, 3) Partnership Effectiveness, 4) Fish and Wildlife Management and Public Use, 5) Team Adequacy, 6) Ecosystem Integrity, and 7) INRMP Impact on the Installation Mission. Each focus area has three to seven criteria that are used to determine the status of a given functional area within Natural Resources.

The criteria used for tracking and measuring the effectiveness of implementation of the INRMP on managing least Bell's vireos include:

- The willow-bulrush-cattail habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme is free of human-induced disturbances and invasive species, and thereby provides habitat for least Bell's vireos. Management strategies that ensure this criterion will be met are detailed in Section 3.3.2.4 Willow-Bulrush-Cattail.
- Results from regular monitoring of willow-bulrush-cattail habitat, for use by other riparian-dependent passerines, will convey the suitability of the habitat for least Bell's vireos.

C. Monitoring and Adaptive Management

Section 3.4.4 Birds, and Section 3.5.3, Special Status Species Protection, include provisions for monitoring least Bell's vireos through regularly scheduled surveys. Following are the objective and management strategies under Section 3.4.4 Birds that address monitoring:

Objective: Conduct a regular program of bird monitoring throughout the base to improve the current inventory and document listed species' use of the harbor to facilitate and guide natural resource management decisions.

- I. Inventory and monitor habitat and populations of migratory and resident birds that use NBVC Port Hueneme, to evaluate conservation effectiveness.
 - A. Maximize the effectiveness of ongoing monitoring and management by continuing to implement standardized, scientifically sound survey protocols to collect and analyze distribution of birds across habitat types and seasonally.
 1. Consolidate existing migratory bird monitoring information.
 2. Maximize cost effectiveness by collecting standardized data on multiple species in addition to any specialized protocols aimed at one species.
 3. Inventory birds using methods that can be integrated with the work of regional partners.
 - a. Investigate the compatibility of the U.S. Forest Service published guidelines for standardized monitoring techniques for monitoring birds (Ralph *et al.* 1993).
 - b. Determine how current established monitoring programs might contribute to regional databases and monitoring protocols.

- B. Collect and assess information on environmental contaminants and other physical or biological stressors having potential relevance to migratory bird conservation. Where such information is collected in the course of agency actions or supported through federal financial assistance, reasonable efforts shall be made to share such information with the USFWS, U.S. Geological Survey Biological Resources Division, and other appropriate repositories of such data.
- C. To comply with the DRA, use the best scientific data available to assess through the NEPA process, or other environmental requirements, the expected impact of proposed or ongoing military readiness activities on migratory bird species likely to occur in action areas.
- D. Regularly monitor infrastructure that may pose a hazard to migratory birds to document any significant adverse impact to populations.
- E. If special status species nest or occupy habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme, address impacts on species of concern more thoroughly and specifically, focusing on the effects of the proposed action on the sustainability of these populations. Special consideration should be given to priority habitats, such as important nesting areas, migration stop-over areas, and wintering habitats.
- F. Include the results of monitoring in the annual review of this INRMP.
- G. Promote research and information exchange, including coordinated inventory and monitoring (EO 13186).
 - 1. Increase communication and coordination between land managers and specialists hired to implement specific projects or conduct monitoring.
 - 2. Use cooperative assistance from wildlife agencies, organizations, and volunteers to help collect needed data. Integrate with regional databases.

The following details the objective and management strategies under Section 3.5.3, Special Status Species Protection, for monitoring special status species:

Objective: Continue to conduct surveys for presence of federally endangered or threatened species, species proposed for listing as endangered or threatened, and federal candidate species for listing. If listed species are found using habitat at NBVC Port Hueneme, then support surveys in accordance with the federal ESA of 1973, as amended. Support surveys for state-listed, proposed listed species, and state candidate species for listing.

- I. Conduct surveys (using established methodology) of listed species to determine presence of species during breeding and nonbreeding season.
 - 1. Develop a standard format and a database to collect and maintain records of observations.

2. If new listed species are found, contact USFWS to discuss recommendations on how to modify the INRMP to manage this species.
- B.* Promote research and information exchange, including coordinated inventory and monitoring (EO 13186).
1. Increase communication and coordination between land managers and specialists hired to implement specific projects or conduct monitoring.
 2. Partner with, and use cooperative assistance from, wildlife agencies, organizations, and volunteers to help collect needed data. Integrate with regional databases.

D. Reporting Progress on Implementation

NBVC will annually update and report on progress of implementation for the INRMP and include management activities pertaining to least Bell's vireos that may occur at NBVC Port Hueneme. The measures that will be taken to ensure that the provisions for reporting progress are adhered to are detailed in Section 5.2 Adaptive Management: Annual Update, Review and Metrics and provided below:

- I.* Fulfill the reporting requirements of new measures to promote better understanding of the health of Navy conservation programs, using the Navy Conservation Website's natural resources metrics focus areas, as defined by CNIC.
- II.* Track implementation to guide and learn from past experience.
 - A.* Derive the most benefit possible from learning and experience by documenting it and disseminating the information to others.
 - B.* To track the progress of each of the INRMP's strategies, a spreadsheet program (e.g. Paradox, Access) and GIS geodatabase should be constructed and maintained. Fields can be included to help (a) build queries; (b) track progress by location, type, sponsor, year, etc.; and (c) provide different types of reports.

E. Duration

The duration of the INRMP is indefinite and will be updated and revised as needed to adapt to changing conditions and management needs; this is sufficient to implement the plan and achieve the benefits of its goals and objectives.

APPENDIX J REFERENCES

- Navy. 2011. Naval Operations Instruction Number 5090.1C (OPNAVINST 5090.1C) Environmental Readiness Program Manual, 18 July 2011.
- Ralph, C.J., G.R. Geupel, P. Pyle, T.E. Martin, and D.F. DeSante. 1993. Handbook of Field Methods for Monitoring Landbirds. U.S. Dept. of Agriculture, Forest Service, General Technical Report PSW-GTR-144.

APPENDIX K
NBVC APPROVED LANDSCAPING PLANT LIST

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE K-1: NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY APPROVED LANDSCAPING PLANT LIST K-2

TABLE K-2: PLANTS UNACCEPTABLE FOR LANDSCAPING UNDER ANY CIRCUMSTANCES K-6

[Table K-1](#) details species approved for use in landscaping at Naval Base Ventura County installations. [Table K-2](#) details plants prohibited from use at NBVC under any circumstances. Questions regarding species in [Table K-1](#) or species not listed on either table should be directed to NBVC Environmental Division Pest Coordinator. Coordination with NBVC ED should occur prior to planning any planting at NBVC.

TABLE K-1: NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY APPROVED LANDSCAPING PLANT LIST*

Botanical Name	Common Name	Native Status	Height	Spread	Irrigation Needs
Annuals/Bulbs/Perennials/ Succulents					
<i>Allium peninsulare</i> var. <i>peninsulare</i>	Mexicali Onion, Peninsula Onion	N			
<i>Armeria maritima</i>	Sea Pink Thrift	CA	1	1	L-M
<i>Astragalus didymocarpus</i>	Two-seeded Milk-vetch	N	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Astragalus</i> sp. (native to area)	Milk-vetch	N	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Clarkia unguiculata</i>	Elegant Clarkia	N			
<i>Calochortus catalinae</i>	Catalina Mariposa Lily	N			
<i>Delphinium cardinale</i>	Scarlet Larkspur	N	6'	2'	M
<i>Delphinium parryi</i>	San Bernadino Larkspur	N	6'	2'	M
<i>Dichelostemma capitatum</i>	Blue Dicks	N	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Dietes bicolor</i>	Fortnight Lily	E	2'	3'	L-M
<i>Dietes</i> 'Lemon Drops'	Yellow Fortnight Lily	E	2'	3'	L-M
<i>Dietes vegeta</i>	Fortnight Lily	E	4'	4'	L-M
<i>Dudleya caespitosa</i>	Coast Dudleya, Sand Lettuce	N			
<i>Dudleya cymosa</i> ssp. <i>Pumila</i>	Canyon Live-forever, Low canyon dudleya	N			
<i>Dudleya lanceolata</i>	Lanceleaf Liveforever	N	1'	1'	M
<i>Dudleya pulverulenta</i> ssp. <i>Pulverulenta</i>	Chalk Dudleya	N	2'	2'	M
<i>Echeveria</i> spp. & cultivars	Hens & Chicks	E	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Epilobium canum</i> ssp. <i>Canum</i>	California Fuchsia	N	2'	4'	L-M
<i>Erigeron glaucus</i>	Seaside Daisy	N	1'	2'	L-M
<i>Eriophyllum confertiflorum</i>	Golden Yarrow	N	2'	2'	L-M
<i>Eschscholzia californica</i>	California Poppy	N	1'	1'	L-M
<i>Eschscholzia caespitosa</i>	Foothill Poppy, Tufted Poppy	N			
<i>Heuchera cespitosa</i>	Tufted Alumroot	N			
<i>Heuchera maxima</i>	Island Alumroot	CA	1'	1'	L-M
<i>Iris douglasiana</i>	Douglas Iris	CA	2'	1'	L-M
<i>Iris missouriensis</i>	Western Blue Flag	N	2'	1'	L-M
<i>Lotus purshianus</i> var. <i>purshianus</i>	Spanish Lotus	N			
<i>Lotus strigosus</i>	Bishop's Lotus	N			
<i>Lupinus bicolor</i>	Miniature Lupine	N	1'	1'	L-M
<i>Lupinus chamissonis</i>	Dune Lupine	N	2'	2'	L-M
<i>Lupinus formosus</i> var. <i>formosus</i>	Summer Lupine	N			
<i>Lupinus latifolius</i> var. <i>latifolius</i>	Broad-leaf Lupine	N			
<i>Lupinus luteolus</i>	Butter Lupine	N			
<i>Lupinus nanus</i>	Valley Sky Lupine	N			
<i>Lupinus sparsiflorus</i>	Coulter's Lupine	N			
<i>Lupinus succulentus</i>	Arroyo Lupine	N			
<i>Lupinus truncatus</i>	Blunt-leaf Lupine	N	2'	2'	L-M
<i>Mimulus cardinalis</i>	Scarlet Monkeyflower	N	2'	2'	L-M
<i>Mimulus guttatus</i>	Golden Monkeyflower	N	2'	2'	L-M
<i>Mirabilis californica</i>	Wishbone Bush	N	1'	2'	L
<i>Opuntia oricola</i>	Round-pad Prickly Pear	N			
<i>Opuntia littoralis</i>	Prickly Pear	N	2'	3'	L
<i>Opuntia parryi</i>	Snake Cholla	N	2'	3'	L
<i>Opuntia prolifera</i>	Coast Cholla	N	2'	3'	L
<i>Pellaea andromedifolia</i>	Coffee Fern	N	1'	1'	
<i>Pellaea mucronata</i>	Bird's Foot Fern	N	1'	1'	
<i>Polystichum munitum</i>	Western Sword Fern	N	3'	3'	L-M
<i>Polypodium californicum</i>	California polypody	N			
<i>Salvia columbariae</i>	Chia	N			
<i>Salvia spathacea</i>	Pitcher Sage	N			
<i>Satureja douglasii</i>	Yerba Buena	CA	1'	3'	L-M

TABLE K-1: NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY APPROVED LANDSCAPING PLANT LIST*

Botanical Name	Common Name	Native Status	Height	Spread	Irrigation Needs
<i>Sedum</i> spp.	Stonecrop	E	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Silene californica</i>	Indian Pink, Cardinal Catchfly	N			
<i>Silene laciniata</i>	Indian Pink, Cardinal Catchfly	N			
<i>Sisyrinchium bellum</i>	Blue-eyed Grass	N	1'	1'	L
<i>Sphaeralcea ambigua</i>	Apricot Mallow	CA	4'	4'	L
<i>Thymus serpyllum</i>	Creeping Thyme	E	1'	3'	M
<i>Woodwardia fimbriata</i>	Giant Chain Fern	N	4'	3'	M
<i>Yucca whipplei</i>	Our Lord's Candle	N	3'	6'	L-M
Grasses/Rushes					
<i>Aristida purpurea</i> (var. <i>nealleyi</i> , var. <i>parishii</i> , var. <i>purpurea</i> only)					
	Purple Three-awn	N			
<i>Bothriochloa barbinodis</i>	Cane Blue-Stem	N			
<i>Bouteloua gracilis</i>	Blue Grama	N			
<i>Eleocharis montevidensis</i>	Spikerush	N	Varies	Varies	M
<i>Elymus glaucus</i>	Blue Wildrye	N	3'	-	L-M
<i>Juncus acutus</i> ssp. <i>leopoldii</i>	Spiny Rush	N	5'	-	M
<i>Juncus balticus</i>	Spiny Rush	N			
<i>Juncus macrophyllus</i>	Long Leaf Rush	N			
<i>Juncus mexicanus</i>	Mexican Rush	N	5'	-	L-M
<i>Juncus patens</i>	Common Rush	N			
<i>Juncus textilis</i>	Basket Rush	N			
<i>Juncus xiphiodes</i>	Iris-leaved Rush	N			
<i>Leymus condensatus</i> [= <i>Elymus condensatus</i>]					
	Giant Wild Rye	N	6'	-	M
<i>Leymus Triticooides</i> [= <i>Elymus triticooides</i>]					
	Giant Wild Rye	N			
<i>Melica imperfecta</i>	California Melic	N			
<i>Muhlenbergia species</i> (South Coast bioregion natives = <i>M. asperifolia</i> , <i>M. californica</i> , <i>M. microsperma</i> , <i>M. rigens</i> , <i>M. utilis</i> only)					
	Deer Grass	CA	Varies	Varies	L-M
<i>Nassella cernua</i>	Nodding Needlegrass	N	4'	4'	L
<i>Nassella lepida</i>	Foothill Needlegrass	N	3'	2'	L
<i>Nassella pulchra</i>	Purple Needlegrass	N	3'	2'	L
Ground Covers					
<i>Abronia maritima</i>	Red Sand Verbena	N	1'	3'	L
<i>Abronia umbellata</i>	Beach Sand Verbena	N	1'	3'	L
<i>Arctostaphylos glandulosa</i> ssp. <i>Crassifolia</i>					
	Manzanita	CA	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i> 'Green Carpet'					
	Prostrate Natal Plum	E	1'	4'	L-M
<i>Ceanothus verrucosus</i>	California Lilac	E	8"	12"	L
<i>Fragaria chiloensis</i>	Sand Strawberry	CA	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Fragaria vesca</i> (ssp. <i>bracteata</i> , ssp. <i>californica</i> only)					
	Wood Strawberry	CA	6"	3'	L
<i>Juniperus horizontalis</i> 'Wiltonii'					
	Blue Carpet Juniper	E	6"	8'	L-M
<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> species	Rosemary Selection	E	Varies	Varies	L-M
<i>Senecio mandraliscae</i>	Groundsel	E	1'	2'	L-M
Shrubs					
<i>Abutilon palmeri</i>	Indian Mallow	CA	5'	5'	L-M
<i>Adenostoma fasciculatum</i>	Chamise	N	8'	8'	L
<i>Adolphia californica</i>	Spineshrub	N	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Artemisia californica</i>	Coastal Sage	N	3'	3'	L-M
<i>Baccharis pilularis</i>	Coyote Brush	N	5'	5'	L-M
<i>Baccharis salicifolia</i>	Mulefat	N	3'	6'	L-M

TABLE K-1: NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY APPROVED LANDSCAPING PLANT LIST*

Botanical Name	Common Name	Native Status	Height	Spread	Irrigation Needs
<i>Bougainvillea species</i>	Bougainvillea	E	8'	8'	L-M
<i>Brickellia californica</i>	California Brickellbush	N	Varies	Varies	L-M
<i>Camissonia cheiranthifolia</i>					
var. <i>suffruticosa</i>	Beach Evening Primrose	N	4'	4'	L
<i>Ceanothus</i> cultivars	Wild Lilac	CA or E	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Ceanothus cuneatus</i> var. <i>cuneatus</i> , <i>C. tomentosus</i> , <i>C. verrucosus</i>	Wild Lilac	N	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Cercocarpus betuloides</i> var. <i>betuloides</i>	Western Mountain Mahogany	N	Varies	Varies	L
<i>Comarostaphylis diversifolia</i> ssp. <i>planifolia</i>	Summer Holly	N	10'	10'	M
<i>Coreopsis gigantea</i>	Giant Coreopsis	N			
<i>Croton californicus</i>	California Croton	N	6'	6'	M
<i>Dendromecon rigida</i>	Bush Poppy	N	8'	8'	L
<i>Encelia californica</i>	Bush Sunflower	N	5'	5'	L
<i>Ericameria ericoides</i>	Mock Heather	N			
<i>Eriodictyon californicum</i>	Yerba Santa	N			
<i>Eriodictyon crassifolium</i> var. <i>crassifolium</i>	Yerba Santa	N	5'	5'	L-M
<i>Eriodictyon traskiae</i>	Trask's Yerba Santa	N	5'		
<i>Eriogonum cinereum</i>	Wild Buckwheat	N			
<i>Eriogonum fasciculatum</i> var. <i>fasciculatum</i>	California Buckwheat	N	3'	4'	L-M
<i>Eriogonum parvifolium</i>	Seaside Buckwheat	N			
<i>Fremontodendron californicum</i>	California Flannelbush	N	15'	15'	L
<i>Fremontodendron mexicanum</i>	Mexican Flannelbush	CA	15'	15'	L
<i>Galvezia speciosa</i>	Island Bush Snapdragon	CA	6'	8'	L
<i>Garrya elliptica</i>	Coast Silk Tassel	N			
<i>Helianthemum scoparium</i>	Peak Rush Rose	N	1'	3'	M
<i>Heteromeles arbutifolia</i>	Toyon	N	8'	15'	L-M
<i>Isocoma menziesii</i>	Menzie's Goldenbush	N	4'	4'	L
<i>Isomeris arborea</i>	Bladderpod	N	5'	5'	L
<i>Iva hayesiana</i>	Poverty Weed	CA	3'	5'	L
<i>Juniperus</i> spp.	Juniper	E	Varies	Varies	L-M
<i>Juniperus californica</i>	California Juniper	N			
<i>Justicia californica</i>	Chuparosa	CA	5'	8'	L-M
<i>Keckiella antirrhinoides</i>	Yellow Bush Penstemon	CA	8'	10'	L-M
<i>Keckiella breviflora</i> var. <i>breviflora</i>	Yellow Bush Penstemon	N			
<i>Keckiella cordifolia</i>	Heart-leaf Penstemon	N	6'	8'	L-M
<i>Lavendula dentata</i>	Lavender	E	4'	5'	M
<i>Lonicera subspicata</i> var. <i>denudata</i>	Chaparral Honeysuckle	N	5'	5'	M
<i>Lotus argophyllus</i> var. <i>argophyllus</i>	Silver Bird's-foot Trefoil	N			
<i>Lotus scoparius</i>	Deerweed	N	3'	4'	M
<i>Lupinus arboreus</i>	Bush Lupine	N			
<i>Lupinus albifrons</i> var. <i>albifrons</i>	Silver Bush Lupine	N	5'	5'	L-M
<i>Lycium californicum</i>	Box Thorn	N	3'	6'	L-M
<i>Malosma laurina</i>	Laurel Sumac	N	15'	15'	L-M
<i>Mimulus aurantiacus</i>	Bush Monkeyflower	N	4'	4'	L-M
<i>Phormium tenax</i>	New Zealand Flax	E	Varies	Varies	L-M
<i>Prunus ilicifolia</i> ssp. <i>ilicifolia</i>	Hollyleaf Cherry	N	15'	15'	L-M
<i>Quercus dumosa</i>	Scrub Oak	N	10'	10'	L-M
<i>Quercus john-tuckeri</i>	Tucker's Oak	N			
<i>Rhamnus californica</i>	Coffeeberry	N	3'-6'	6'	L-M
<i>Rhamnus crocea</i>	Spiny Redberry	N	8'	8'	L
<i>Rhus integrifolia</i>	Lemonadeberry	N	15'	15'	L
<i>Rhus ovata</i>	Sugar Bush	N			

TABLE K-1: NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY APPROVED LANDSCAPING PLANT LIST*

Botanical Name	Common Name	Native Status	Height	Spread	Irrigation Needs
<i>Ribes aureum</i> var. <i>gracillimum</i>	Golden Currant	N			
<i>Ribes indecorum</i>	White Flowering Currant	N	6'	6'	L
<i>Ribes malvaceum</i>	Chaparral Currant	N			
<i>Ribes speciosum</i>	Fuchsia-Flowered Gooseberry	N	6'	8'	L
<i>Ribes viburnifolium</i>	Catalina Currant	N			
<i>Romneya coulteri</i>	Matilija Poppy	N	6'	6'	L
<i>Rosa californica</i>	California Wild Rose	N	Varies	Varies	M
<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Rosemary	E	Varies	Varies	L-M
<i>Salvia apiana</i>	White Sage	N	5'	5'	M
<i>Salvia clevelandii</i>	Cleveland Sage	CA	4'	5'	M
<i>Salvia leucophylla</i>	Purple Sage	N			
<i>Salvia mellifera</i>	Black Sage	N	5'	5'	M
<i>Santolina chamaecyparissus</i>	Lavender Cotton	E	2'	3'	L-M
<i>Solanum parishii</i>	Parish's Nightshade	N	Varies	Varies	L-M
<i>Solanum xanti</i>	Purple Nightshade	CA	3'	3'	L-M
<i>Trichostema lanatum</i>	Woolly Blue Curls	N	3'	4'	L
Trees					
<i>Agonis flexuosa</i>	Peppermint Tree	E	30'	30'	L-M
<i>Archontophoenix cunninghamiana</i>	King Palm	E	50'	15'	M
<i>Brahea armata</i>	Blue Hesper Palm	E	45'	10'	L-M
<i>Brahea edulis</i>	Rock Palm	E	30'	10'	L-M
<i>Butia capitata</i>	Pindo Palm	E	20'	15'	M
<i>Calocedrus decurrens</i>	Incense Cedar	N	80'	20'	L-M
<i>Cercis occidentalis</i>	Western Redbud	CA	20'	20'	L-M
<i>Chamaerops humilis</i>	Mediterranean Fan Palm	E	20'	8'	L-M
<i>Geijera parvifolia</i>	Australian Willow	E	30'	25'	L-M
<i>Jacaranda mimosifolia</i>	Jacaranda	E	30'	25'	L-M
<i>Lyonothamnus floribundus</i>	Catalina Ironwood	CA	50'	30'	M
<i>Metrosideros exelsa</i>	New Zealand Christmas Tree	E	30'	30'	M
<i>Pinus canariensis</i>	Canary Island Pine	E	60'	20'	L
<i>Pinus eldarica</i>	Afghan Pine	E	50'	30'	L
<i>Pinus torreyana</i>	Torrey Pine	CA	50'	30'	L
<i>Platanus racemosa</i>	Western Sycamore	N	80'	40'	L-M
<i>Podocarpus gracilior</i>	Fern Pine	E	60'	30'	M
<i>Populus fremontii</i>	Western Cottonwood	N	50'	30'	M
<i>Quercus agrifolia</i>	Coast Live Oak	N	50'	50'	L-M
<i>Quercus chrysolepis</i>	Canyon Live Oak	N			
<i>Quercus lobata</i>	Valley Oak	N			
<i>Salix exigua</i>	Narrow-leaved Willow	N			
<i>Salix laevigata</i>	Red Willow	N			
<i>Salix lasiolepis</i>	Arroyo Willow	N	15'	15'	M
<i>Salix lucida</i> ssp. <i>Lasiandra</i>	Shining Willow	N			
<i>Sambucus mexicana</i>	Blue Elderberry	N	20'	20'	L-M
<i>Syagrus romazoffianum</i>	Queen Palm	E	50'	15'	M
<i>Umbellularia californica</i>	California Bay	N			
<i>Washingtonia filifera</i>	California Fan Palm	CA	60'	15'	L-M
Vines					
<i>Bougainvillea</i> spp.	Bougainvillea	E	-	-	L-M
<i>Calystegia macrostegia</i>	Morning-Glory	N	-	-	M
<i>Clematis lasiantha</i>	Pipestem	N	-	-	M
<i>Clematis ligusticifolia</i>	Virgin's Bower	N	-	-	M
<i>Clematis pauciflora</i>	Ropevine	CA	-	-	M
<i>Clytostoma callistegioides</i>	Violet Trumpet Vine	E	-	-	L-M
<i>Phaedranthus bucinatorius</i>	Blood-Red Trumpet Vine	E	-	-	M
<i>Vitis californica</i>	California Wild Grape	N	-	-	
<i>Vitis girdiana</i>	Desert Wild Grape	N	-	-	L-M

TABLE K-2: PLANTS UNACCEPTABLE FOR LANDSCAPING UNDER ANY CIRCUMSTANCES*

Scientific name	Common Name
<i>Aptenia</i> spp.	Red Apple Ice Plant
<i>Asphodelus fistulosus</i>	Onion Weed
<i>Carpobrotus</i> spp.	Hottentot Fig Ice Plant
<i>Cephalophyllum</i> spp.	Red Spike Ice Plant
<i>Chrysanthemum</i> spp.	Chrysanthemum
<i>Cortaderia</i> spp.	Pampas Grass
<i>Delosperma</i> spp.	Disneyland Ice Plant
<i>Dorotheanthus</i> spp.	Livingstone Daisy Ice Plant
<i>Gazania</i> spp.	Gazania, Treasure Flower
<i>Hypericum canariense</i>	St. John's Wort
<i>Lampranthus (Oscularia)</i> spp.	Ice Plant
<i>Malephora</i> spp.	Ice Plant
<i>Mesembryanthemum</i> spp.	Ice Plant
<i>Myoporum laetum</i>	Ngaio tree
<i>Pennisetum</i> spp.	Fountain Grass
<i>Schinus terebinthifolius</i>	Brazilian pepper-tree
<i>Tragopogon</i> spp.	Goat's Beard

Notes: *Both plant lists are dynamic and will be updated as more is known about invasive and non-invasive species. Please coordinate with the NBVC Pest Management Coordinator before planning any planting.

APPENDIX L
NBVC BARD ESTATE PLANT LIST

INVENTORY OF TREES
BARD ESTATE, NAVAL CONSTRUCTION BATTALION CENTER
PORT HUENEME, CALIFORNIA

General Information

In response to an Engineering Service Request (ESR-NCBC-003) dated 11 October 1972, an inventory of existing trees on the Bard Estate was accomplished by the WESTNAVFACENGCOCM Staff Conservationist, assisted by the Gardener, Mr. Joe Largen, on 8 and 9 November 1972.

The objectives of this report are to present an identification list of the trees and to outline a general plan of management for the future maintenance of the trees.

Many exotic trees are located on the Bard Estate located in Pleasant Valley, about 60 miles north of Los Angeles. The plantings on the estate were made over a period of time from approximately 1940 to 1970. In 1942, the estate was acquired as a portion of the area included in what is at present the Naval Construction Battalion Center at Port Hueneme.

Preservation of existing exotic trees will require above normal maintenance to maintain the trees in a healthy physical condition. The immediate requirements appear to fall into two categories. All the existing exotic trees should be released from competition with other plants and proper maintenance such as pruning, feeding and watering should be provided.

Future plantings on the Bard Estate should be species and varieties of trees and shrubs resistant to Oak Root Fungus (*Armillaria Mellea*). Trees and shrubs resistant to Oak Root Fungus and adapted to the area are as follows:

<u>Botanical Name</u>	<u>Common Name</u>
<u>TREES</u>	
<i>Abies concolor</i>	White fir
<i>Acacia longifolia</i>	Sydney golden wattle
<i>Ailanthus altissima</i>	Tree of heaven
<i>Brachychiton populueum</i>	Bottle tree
<i>Broussonetia papyrifera</i>	Paper Mulberry
<i>Calocedrus decurrans</i>	Incense cedar
<i>Celtis occidentalis</i>	Hackberry
Fig - Kadota or Mission	
<i>Ilex aquifolium</i>	Holly
<i>Jacaranda acutifolia</i>	Jacaranda
<i>Liquidambar styraciflua</i>	Sweet gum
<i>Melaleuca stypelioides</i>	Melaleuca
<i>Persea indica</i>	Avocado
<i>Pinus canariensis</i>	Canary Island pine
<i>Pinus patula</i>	Jelescote pine
<i>Pinus Torreyana</i>	Torrey pine
<i>Quilaja sapanaria</i>	Soapbark tree

Botanical Name

Common Name

SHRUBS

Acacia verticillata
Cotinus coggygria
Lonicera nitida
Mahonia nevinii
Nandina domestica
Prunus caroliniana
Prunus ilicifolia
Prunus lyonii
Ditex agrus castus

Acacia
Smoke tree
Honeysuckle
Oregon grape
Heavenly Bamboo
Carolina laurel
Holly leaf cherry
Catalina cherry
Chaste tree

Tree and Shrub Selection, Establishment and Maintenance

Stock. Secure trees and shrubs of first grade quality stock, free from disease and insect pests, standard size for the container size specified, vigorous, healthy plants with a well-developed root system. Trees and shrubs showing indications of being root bound are not acceptable.

Site. Consider tree and shrub characteristics in selecting their locations and sites; i.e., do not plant walnut and oaks in lawn areas. The following are factors to consider in selecting trees and shrubs for landscape plantings:

- a. Size and shape at maturity
- b. Deciduous or evergreen (wind resistance)
- c. Growth rate (pruning requirements)
- c. Hardiness (cold tolerance)
- e. Adaptability to soil and climate conditions
- f. Habits (flowering, fruiting, type of root system, shedding)
- g. Density of shade cast (intensity of shade affects growth of grass)

Establishment

General. Preparation of the soil prior to planting is one of the essentials to success. Rich soil increases plant vigor. Moderately vigorous plants are more easily and economically maintained. Before planting trees and shrubs, investigate the possibility of past applications of herbicides or soil nutrients. Obtain a history of their use and determine if soil chemical condition is safe for plants.

Soil Preparation. Dig pits or holes 30 to 36 inches deep for trees and 18 to 24 inches deep for shrubs with a diameter of at least twice that of the plant container or root ball. For bare root stock, use a minimum diameter of 12 inches. Retain topsoil that is of good loam texture and reasonably free of salts for use as backfill material. Generally, excavated subsoil material is not used for backfill; instead, use the most suitable soil on the site for the backfill material. Normally, the addition of fertilizer and/or soil amendments to backfill material is not necessary and often is safe for best plant establishment. In special cases, a planting mixture may be made from topsoil available at the site and prepared (thoroughly mixed) in the following proportions:

1.0 cubic yard topsoil (sandy loam)
1.0 cubic yard soil conditioner (Turface or equivalent

add

12 to 15 pounds magnesium ammonium phosphate and magnesium potassium phosphate controlled release fertilizer with an N-P-K ratio of 7-40-6, plus 12 per cent magnesium (MagAmp or equivalent

or

use 12-gram Agriform or equivalent planting tablets around each tree and shrub, as follows:

4 or 5 tablets for 5-gallon containers
1 or 2 tablets for 1-gallon containers

with

1/4 pound Iron Chelate (Sequestrene 330 containing 10 per cent Iron as metallic).

Time of Planting. Balled or canned nursery stock may be planted at any time but it is not advisable to plant most kinds during hot weather occurring generally from June to September. Plant bare root stock only during the dormant season, December to March.

Planting. Plant trees and shrubs as soon as possible after they are received and do not expose roots to the air any longer than necessary. It takes only 15 to 20 seconds of root exposure to sun and wind to kill evergreens. Prior to placing the tree or shrub in the pit or hole, it shall be backfilled with sufficient soil or planting mixture so when thoroughly settled, and the plant is placed upon it, the plant will bear the same relationship to the ground surface as it did to the soil level in its container or original planting. Remove the container holding canned planting stock carefully. Score the ball 1/2 inch deep with a blunt instrument such as a 16-penny nail, from bottom to top in four or five places around the ball. After placing the plant in the pit at the proper height with the majority of main branches toward the prevailing wind, hold it in a plumb position until backfill has been placed and firmly tamped (compacted) around the ball or roots. Avoid straightening trees or shrubs after the backfill has been compacted. Damage to plants may result from air pockets formed under the roots when trees or shrubs are moved. In planting bare root stock, make the hole of sufficient diameter to accommodate the roots without bending them. Spread the roots out evenly. Place and firmly tamp the backfill material around and between the roots to fill all voids, with the plant held in the proper position and height until the pit is completely filled.

Staking. Stake all trees with two 2" x 2" stakes and a 1" x 1" leader stake. The stake length should vary in accordance with the height of the tree.

Place stakes and framework on the leeward side of the tree and in a manner to provide maximum protection to the tree.

Tying. Secure the tree to the leader stake located in the center of the staking framework with pieces of one inch wide plastic vinyl nurseryman's tape at not more than 18-inch intervals.

Watering. Immediately after planting, make a saucer-like basin by forming a circular ridge or mound of soil around the plant and filling the basin with water. Make the basin 4 to 6 feet in diameter with a ridge 5 to 6 inches high for trees and 2 to 4 feet in diameter, and 3 to 5 inches high for shrubs. Water frequently enough to prevent drying out of the root zone soil, yet at long enough intervals so as not to have continually wet (saturated) soil.

Mulching. Within two days after planting, spread a mulch such as peat moss, sawdust or wood chips over the entire basin to a depth of 2 inches.

Pruning. Prune only as necessary to remove injured twigs and branches and to compensate for the loss of any roots during transplanting, but never to exceed one-half the branching structure.

Tree and Shrub Maintenance

Irrigation. Irrigate trees and shrubs deeply and only frequently enough to insure adequate moisture for continuing plant growth. Overwatering will severely damage or kill plants by drowning or by rotting the roots and root crowns. Roots must have oxygen as well as water.

Pruning. Proper pruning begins during the planting operations. Function is the prime purpose of a good landscape, and proper and timely pruning can build the plant to do the job desired. First, remove all limbs and branches that obstruct walks and drives. Second, prune back to clear all doors, windows and visual obstructions. Then go back and prune the plants for form, shape, size, vigor and beauty. Prune landscape planting as soon as the need is seen; not by season, but by need. Encourage evergreens, especially shrubs, in some spots, to grow and branch to the ground. This not only produces a healthier but, in most cases, a much better looking plant. Prune to:

- a. Control habit of growth
- b. Remove all dead, broken or diseased parts
- c. Produce desired shape and form
- d. Improve flowering and fruiting
- e. Improve chances of survival

Seek professional assistance or instruction in proper pruning. Amateur or inexperienced pruners often do more harm than good. Common evidence of inexperienced pruners is the "coat hanger." Refer to Pruning Techniques.

Fertilizing. Fertilizer for trees and shrubs can be applied at any time from late October until midsummer. Do not make applications between 15 July

and 15 September as there is danger of stimulating a late, succulent growth which is subject to winter kill. Plants take in food nutrients (fertilizer) most readily during the period of early spring growth and they continue to absorb it in the autumn long after the leaves have been shed.

Method of Application. The feeding roots of most trees extend beyond the end of the overhead branches for a considerable distance (2 to 3 feet). Apply the fertilizer from the trunk outward beyond the branches but remaining two feet away from the tree trunk. Make holes with a soil auger or crowbar or similar tool approximately 1 inch in diameter, varying in depth from 12 to 15 inches from 15 to 18 inches apart over the entire area. Place the fertilizer in the holes, then fill the holes with water to dissolve the fertilizer.

Kind and Amount of Fertilizer. A complete fertilizer is one which contains nitrogen, phosphorus, and potash. A rule-of-thumb to follow in fertilizing trees is to apply a complete fertilizer at a rate of 2 pounds for each inch of trunk diameter. The proportions of nitrogen, phosphate and potash required in the complete fertilizer properly should be determined by soil tests. Until such time as determinations from soil tests are available, use a complete fertilizer of formula 24-24-8 (Blue Chip), 12-12-6 (Super Vegetable Cropper) or equivalent.

Note: Do not place commercial fertilizer in the hole in which a tree is to be planted except as specified in the planting mixture as the risk of burning the roots is too great.

Guying. Protect trees which might topple over by guying. This problem usually occurs during high winds and when soil moisture conditions are at or near saturation point. A simple method of guying is as follows: Drive three stakes equally spaced around the tree at the drip line so that the guy wires will not interfere with the lower branches. Lag screw hooks can be screwed into the trunk of the tree at about 6 to 7 feet above ground level. Space the lag screws evenly around the tree, leaving a space of 12 inches between the top and bottom lag screw. Stretch No. 12 gauge wire, with a turnbuckle inserted between tree and stake sufficiently taut to provide equal tension on all three guy wires. Place a warning sign such as a white painted board on the guy wires. After the trees have been firmly anchored, the guy wires and lag screws can be removed. Treat the holes left by the lag screws with a tree wound paint or fill them with wood putty. Technical assistance in making evaluations of such problem trees can be secured by contacting the Natural Resources Management Branch, Real Estate Division at this Command.

Chlorosis Control. Treat all plants showing a chlorosis condition with Iron Chelate containing 10 per cent iron as metallic (330 Sequestrene or equivalent). Apply at the rate of one-half pound per tree or shrub. Application of the Iron Chelate when needed can be made at the time of application of commercial fertilizer, as described herein. (See fertilizer method of application.)

The following chart can be used as a guide in determining possible nutrient deficiencies of trees and shrubs. It is not complete nor foolproof. For further information, diagnosis and recommendations, contact the Agricultural Extension Service, University of California.

Nutrient Deficiency Chart

<u>Symptoms</u>	<u>Causes</u>
Poor Leaf Growth	
Dwarf plants, yellow color	Lack of nitrogen
Dwarf plants, grayish color	Lack of phosphorus or potash
Tall spindly plants	Lack of sunlight
Chlorosis or Yellowing of Leaf	
Uniform all over leaf	Lack of iron, excess of lime, magnesium, sodium, potash, carbohydrates or manganese
Patchy, spreading from midrib outward	Lack of magnesium
Mottled	Lack of lime
Spotted	Lack of potash
Leaf yellowing, then dying at tip and from edges inward	Lack of potash
Leaf yellowing, then dying from midrib outward	Lack of nitrogen
Patches on Leaf	
Brown patches like scorching	Lack of potash
Brown patches chiefly in center	Lack of magnesium
Dark colored leaves, tendency to crinkle	Lack of potash in relation to nitrogen

IDENTIFICATION LIST

The approximate locations of the plants are shown on NAVFAC Drawing No. _____

Legend

<u>Maintenance</u>	<u>Pruning</u>	<u>Estimated Cost</u>
<u>Degree Symbol</u>	<u>Requirement</u>	
A	Heavy	\$75.00-100.00
B	Moderately heavy	\$60.00-75.00
C	Moderate	\$50.00-60.00
D	Light	\$25.00-50.00
E	Minimal	0-\$25.00
R	Remove	
Re	Relocate	
S	Surgery	

<u>Plant No.</u>	<u>Qty.</u>	<u>Botanical Name</u>	<u>Common Name</u>	<u>Origin</u>	<u>Degr of Main</u>
1	241	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> , Labill	Blue Gum	Australia	E
2	13	<i>Eucalyptus viminalis</i> , Labill	Manna Gum	Australia	E
3	6	<i>Eucalyptus ficifolia</i> , F.V.M.	Scarlet flowered Gum	Australia	C
4	2	<i>Ginkgo biloba</i> , L., Ginkgo	Maidenhair or Kow Tree	China	R, E
5	1	<i>Prunus lusitanica</i> , L.	Portugal Laurel (Cherry)	Portugal, Spain	C
6	11	<i>Pinus radiata</i> , Don.	Monterey Pine	U.S. (Calif.)	A
7	4	<i>Sequoia sempervirens</i> , Endl.	Coast Redwood, Sequoia	U.S. (Calif.)	B
8	12	<i>Cupressus macrocarpa</i>	Monterey Cypress	U.S. (Calif.)	S
9	1	<i>Phoenix canariensis</i>	Phoenix feather palm	Canary Is.	R
10	91	<i>Pittosporum</i> , Vent and related species	Victorian Box Mock Orange	Australia	C, E
11	1	<i>Uchellularia californica</i> , Nutt.	California Laurel	U.S. (Calif.)	D
12	1	<i>Liguetrum lucidum</i> <i>Liqustrum</i> Sp. (Tree)	Privet	Japan, China	D
	540	linear feet hedge (large leaf)			
13		<i>Erythea Eudulis</i>	Guadalupe fan palm	Guadalupe Is.	
14	2	<i>Magnolia</i> Sp. <i>grandiflora</i>	Bull Bay or Big leave <i>macrophylla</i>		C

Plant No.	Qty.	Botanical Name	Common Name	Origin	Degr of Main
15	4	<i>Fraxinus ormus</i> , L.	Dwarf Ash	S. Europe	D
16	3 trees 180 linear feet of hedge	<i>Eugenia myrtifolia</i> , Sims.	Australian Blush Cherry	Australia	E
17	2	<i>Acacia koa</i> , Gray	Koa	Hawaii	R,I
18	5	<i>Pinus torreyana</i> , Carr	Soledad Pine, Torrey Pine	U.S. (Calif.)	E
19		<i>Dracena</i>	Drago Palm		
20	3	<i>Persea americana</i>	Avocado	Mexico	1 D 2 E
21	3 trees 360 linear feet of hedge 180' hedge running east and west	<i>Leptospermum laevigatum</i> , F. Muell. <i>Atriplex breweri</i>	Tea Tree Quail brush	Australia U.S. (Calif.)	C E
22	2	<i>Ficus carica</i> , L.	Fig	Asia Minor	E
23		<i>Phoenix roebellini</i>	Dwarf feather palm	China	
24	8	<i>Quercus agrifolia</i> , Nee	Coast live oak	U.S. (Calif.)	D
25		<i>Washington robusta</i>	Mexican fan plam	Mexico	
26		<i>Livingston chinensis</i>	Chinese fountain palm	China	
27		<i>Arconthphoenix alexandrae</i>	Majestic feather palm	Australia	
28		<i>Chaemaerops humilis</i>	Mediterranean fan	Medit. area	
29		<i>Ficus rubiginosa</i> Desf.	Rubber tree	Australia	B
30		<i>Pinus pinea</i> , E.	Stone Pine	S. Europe	A
31	3	<i>Pinus canariensis</i> , C. Smith	Canary Island Pine	Canary Is.	2 E 1 B
32		<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	Senegal Palm		
33	8	<i>Ficus</i> sp.	<i>Ficus</i> Rubber tree 'decora'		E
34	17	<i>Eucalyptus</i> Sp.	Red box Australian Beech	Australia	E
35	8	<i>Pittosporum tobira</i> , Ait.	Tobira, Japanes Pitto- sporum	Japan	6 2 R

Plant No.	Qty.	Botanical Name	Common Name	Origin	Degree of Maint
36	1	Cactus sp.	Indian Fig Cactus		E
37	1	Fraxinus pennsylvanica, March.	Red Ash	Eastern U.S.	S
38	1	Laurus nobilis, L.	Laurel, Sweet Bay	Canary Is.	C
39	3	Umbellularia californica Nutt.	California Laurel	Western U.S.	C
40	3	Podocarpus sp.	(NCN)	S. Africa	2 C 1 E
41	1	Prunus Triloba	Almond	China	E
42	2	Ailanthus altissima, Swingle	Tree of Heaven	China	C
43	4	Tamarix articulata	Athel - Salt Cedar	W. Asia or N. Africa	E
44	2	Ulmus parvifolia	Elm sempervirens	China	D
45	12	Heteromeles arbutifolia	Toyon - California holly	Calif.	10 D 2 R
46	2	Fraxinus velutina, Torr.	Arizona Ash	Arizona	E
47	3	stump			
48	20	Cortadera selloana	Pampas grass	Argentina	E
49	1	Gleditsia sp.	Locust 'Moraine'	N. and Cen- tral America	E
50	1	Agave americana	Century plant	Mexico	E
51	1	Ficus altissima, Blume	(NCN)	India	C
52	1	Cordyline australis Dracena	Ti Tree Dracena	Africa New Zealand	Re
53		Wisteria sinensis	Chinese wisteria	China	D
54		Raphiolepis sp.	India Hawthorn 'Indica'	So. China	E
55	1	Lagunaria patersoni, Don	Primrose tree or orchid Sugar Plum Tree	Australia	B
56		Phyllostachys sp.	Bamboo clumps	China	E

Plant No.	Qty.	Botanical Name	Common Name	Origin	D. of Maint
57	1	<i>Araucaria heterophylla</i> , R.B.	Star Pine	Australia	B
58	2	<i>Araucaria bidwillii</i> , hook	Bunya-Bunya	Australia	1 R 1 D
59	2	<i>Magnolia grandiflora</i> , L.	Bull Bay Magnolia	SE US	A +
60	1 110	<i>Ligustrum lucidum</i> , Ait. linear feet of hedge	Privet Tree	Japan, China	C
61	1	<i>Crataegus phaenopyrum</i>	Washington Thorn	Eastern U.S.	C
62	1	Unknown - neither flowers nor fruits available.			D
63	2	<i>Myoporum</i> sp.	<i>M. laetum</i>	New Zealand	E
64	1	<i>Ulmus parvifolia</i>	Chinese Elm	China	D
65	3	<i>Yucca aloifolia</i>	Spanish Bayonet	U.S.	E
66		<i>Eucalyptus cornuta</i> , Labill	Yate tree	Australia	A
67	1	<i>Cotoneaster</i> Sp.	<i>C. parneyi</i>	China	E
68	2 1	<i>Podocarpus</i> Sp.	p. Fern Pine p. <i>Macrophyllus</i> Yew Pine	Africa Africa	E D
69		<i>Cypress Sempervirens</i>	Italian cypress 'glauca'	Asia	E
70	1	<i>Salix vitellina</i> L.	Yellow Willow	E. North Amer.	D
71	4	<i>Juniperus</i>	<i>J. Torulosa</i> 'Hollywood'	American hybrid	D
72	3	<i>Pyracantha coccinea</i>	Firethorn	Asia	E
73	37	<i>Acacia melanoxylon</i> , R.B. (A clump of many trees)	Blackwood Acacia	Australia	17 D 20 E
74	13	<i>Nerium Oleander</i>	Rose Ban Hedge planting	So. Europe No. Africa	E
75	20	<i>Morus</i>	Mulberry	U.S.	D
76	5	<i>Grevillea robusta</i> , Cunn.	Silk or Golden Oak	Australia	B
77	1	<i>Callistemon</i> Sp.	Bottlebrush		
78	6	<i>Hibiscus</i>	Hibiscus	China	E

Plant No.	Qty.	Botanical Name	Common Name	Origin	Degr of Main
79	2	<i>Ficus ratusa</i> , L.	Indian Laurel Fig	Malaya	C
80	3	<i>Juniperus</i>	J. Sabina <i>Tamariscifolia</i>	U.S.	E
81	5	Citrus	Orange	U.S.	E
82		Acacia	Blackwood Acacia		
83	1	<i>Ficus macrophylla</i> , Desf.	Moreton Bay Fig	Australia	A
84	1	Unknown (round top broad leaf, evergreen tree)			R
85	1	<i>Pittosporum crassifolium</i> Soland	Karo	New Zealand	D
86		<i>Populus italica</i> Du Roi	Lombardy poplar	Italy	R
87	2	<i>Melaleuca</i> Sp. <i>Melaleuca stypholiodos</i> Smith	(NCN) (NCN)	Australia Australia	E C
88		<i>Platanus racemosa</i>	Sycamore plane tree	California	B
89	2	<i>Persea gratissima</i>	Alligator pear	Mexico	E
90	1	<i>Ficus altissima</i>	(NCN)	India	C
91	2	<i>Pinus halapensis</i> , Mill	Aleppo Pine	Medit. Region	A
92	1	<i>Taxodium mucronatum</i>	Montezuma Cypress	Mexico	
93	3	<i>Sambucus</i>	Red berried elder	Asia	E
94	3	<i>Schinus Molle</i>	California Pepper Tree	Peru	E
95	1	<i>Quercus Suber</i>	Cork Oak	S. Europe or N. Africa	E
96	4	<i>Aesculus carnea</i>	Buckeye	garden hybrid	E
97	2	<i>Eucalyptus botryoides</i>	Banealay or Bastard Mahogany	Australia	B

Plant No.	Qty.	Botanical Name	Common Name	Origin	Leg o Mai
98		Rhopalystylis sapida	Shaving Brush	New Zealand	E
99		Trachycarpus	Windmill Palm	China	E
100		Agave Americana Variegated	Century Plant	U. S.	E
101		Phoenix (species)?	possibly Rupicola	Africa	E
102		Strelitzia Nicolai	Giant Bird of Paradise	unknown	E
103		Ceratonia Siliqua	Carob (Breadfruit Tree)	Mediterranean	E
104		Acacia baileyana	Bailey Acacia	Australia	C
105		Pandanus Utilis	Screw Pine	unknown	

APPENDIX M
ANNUAL METRICS REPORTS

The results of annual INRMP reviews and metrics reports will be added here on an annual basis. Annual reports briefly summarize projects and activities that have been implemented during the fiscal year, and how these fulfill specific objectives identified in the INRMP.

APPENDIX N
NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGER APPOINTMENT LETTER

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL BASE VENTURA COUNTY
311 MAIN ROAD, SUITE 1
POINT MUGU, CA 93042-5033

IN REPLY REFER TO:
5090
N45VCS
26 MAR 03

From: Commanding Officer, Naval Base Ventura County
To: Mr. Martin Ruane

Subj: DESIGNATION AS NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGER FOR NAVAL
BASE VENTURA COUNTY

Ref: (a) OPNAVINST 5090.1B

1. Per reference (a), you are designated as the Natural Resources Manager for Naval Base Ventura County (NBVC). Your responsibility is to coordinate management of the natural resources at NBVC, and ensure that we manage these programs in a way that supports the military missions performed at this base.
2. You will be responsible for coordinating the following: management of endangered species at NBVC; implementation of the objectives of the Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP); tracking and implementation of the requirements of the Biological Opinion (BO) with the U.S Fish and Wildlife Service; and day-to-day management of associated wetlands, sensitive habitat, and natural resource tasks. You will keep your chain-of-command informed of natural resource issues, conditions of the natural resources, status of implementation of the INRMP and BO, and any potential or actual conflicts between mission requirements and natural resource mandates.
3. Your designation as Natural Resources Manager will facilitate the development of specific and creative strategies for the protection and management of biological resources that support the military mission. This designation will remain in effect until you are either specifically relieved or transferred from NBVC.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "P. S. Grossgold".

P. S. GROSSGOLD